

Effects and effectiveness of maritime environmental legislation for commercial freight shipping on the North and Baltic Seas

An exploratory sequential mixed methods law and economics
study

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Commercial traffic on the Baltic Sea © Thea Freese

*Shipping markets function in a totally international arena
where national political boundaries pose only a minor irritation
to the smooth conduct of trade and commerce [...].
(Cullinane, 2005, p.2)*

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Abstract

Newspaper reports have claimed that cleaning up maritime shipping could lead to modal backshift to land-based transport and therefore to increased levels of environmental pollution. However, the mutual influence of different factors and effects is unclear today. Thus, this study explores effects and the effectiveness of maritime environmental legislation for commercial freight shipping in the North and Baltic Sea areas. The effectiveness of legislation was to be scrutinised by studying compliance with the laws, as well as comparing legal impacts on different types of shipping companies.

Employing sequential mixed methods research and triangulating empirical data with findings from prior studies and economic theory, this work studies how legislation affects company costs, freight rates and modal choice for the Northern European shipping industry. The study is situated in the research field of environmental law and economics and is based on legal and economic theoretical foundations. Empirical data stems from in-depth qualitative interviews with twelve experts in and around the shipping industry, as well as questionnaire data from 121 shipping companies active in the North and Baltic Sea areas. Qualitative content analysis was chosen to systematically extract knowledge from translated interview transcripts and build a theoretical framework to inform the subsequent quantitative data collection. Questionnaires were analysed statistically, for example with sum of squares analysis and structural equation modelling, specifically partial least squares analysis (PLS-SEM). Findings were triangulated with insights from prior studies and knowledge drawn from economic theories.

Key findings include significant effects of maritime environmental legislation on both investment and operational costs of shipping companies, while freight rates are only affected to a limited extent by laws. Consequently, the danger of immediate modal shift is found to be negligible, although changes both in freight rates and in modal choice may in future be witnessed with a time lag of several years. Noncompliance is found to be statistically significant in the range of 10-15% of shipping companies, influencing the economic effects of legal policies. An economic impact assessment differentiated by company characteristics showed that though companies are differently affected by legislation, no statistical correlation may be found between legislation and company type, size, or any other of the ten characteristics identified. Policy recommendations include a more economic approach to environmental laws, improved enforcement of legislation, and a longer-term perspective to account for time lags in economic effects.

List of abbreviations

AIS	Automatic Identification System
AFS Convention	International Convention on the Control of Harmful Anti-fouling Systems on Ships
BWM Convention	International Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast Water and Sediments
BWTS	Ballast water treatment system
CEO	Chief executive officer
CH ₄	Methane
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
DST	Demand for seaborne transport
dwt	Deadweight tonnage
EBP	Evidence-based practice
EC	European Commission
ECA	Emission Control Area
EEDI	Energy Efficiency Design Index
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EKC	Environmental Kuznets Curve
EMSA	European Maritime Safety Agency
EP	European Parliament
EU	European Union
FC	Full costs
FR	Freight rate
GEF	Global Environment Facility
GES	Good environmental status
GESAMP	Group of Experts on the Scientific Aspects of Marine Environmental Protection
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GT	Gross tonnage
HELCOM	Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission, also: Helsinki Commission
HFO	Heavy fuel oil
IAS	Invasive alien species
ICS	International Chamber of Shipping
ILA	International Law Association
IMO	International Maritime Organisation
ISM	International Safety Management Code
ISPS	International Ship and Port Facility Security Code
ITLOS	International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea
IUCN	International Union for the Conservation of Nature
Kt	Kiloton
LNG	Liquefied natural gas
LPG	Liquefied petroleum gas
MARPOL	International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships

MEC	Marginal external costs
MEL	Maritime environmental legislation
MEPC	Marine Environment Protection Committee
MGO	Marine gas oil
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MPB	Marginal private benefits
MPC	Marginal private costs
MS	Member state
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NECA	Nitrogen Emission Control Area
NIS	Non-indigenous species
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides (specifically NO and NO ₂)
O ₃	Ozone
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OSPAR Convention	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North- East Atlantic
PLS	Partial least squares
PM	Particulate matter
ppm	Parts per million
PSSAs	Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas
QUAL	Qualitative
QUAN	Quantitative
rpm	Revolutions per minute
RoPax vessels	Roll-on-roll-off-and-passenger vessels
RoRo vessels	Roll-on-roll-off vessels
S	Sulphur
SECA	Sulphur Emission Control Area
SEEMP	Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan
SEM	Structural equation modelling
SDB	Social-desirability bias
SOLAS	International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea
SO ₂	Sulphur dioxide
SST	Supply of seaborne transport
TBT	Tributyl tin
TEU	Twenty-foot equivalent unit
ULCC	Ultra Large Crude Carrier
UN	United Nations
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
U.S. EPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency
VLCC	Very Large Crude Carrier
WHO	World Health Organisation

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Thea

Declaration of originality

This is to certify that I am responsible for the work submitted in this thesis, that the original work is my own except as specified in acknowledgements or in footnotes, and that neither the thesis nor the original work contained therein has been submitted to this or any other institution for a degree.

Signed:

Date:

1 Introduction to the study

1.1 Introduction

Harmful vessel-source emissions have received increased attention in recent years, both in academic publications and public media. A study published by Corbett, Eyring and others in 2007 estimated that air pollution from the shipping industry was causing 60,000 deaths a year (Corbett et al., 2007), leading to a stream of articles in all major newspapers (in the German press Hans Schuh, 2006, Marlies Uken, 2008, Axel Bojanowski, 2010, Weiss, 2013) and a call for stricter environmental legislation for the shipping industry. Recent studies estimating deaths solely from sulphur emissions from ships to reach almost 600,000 a year and cases of childhood asthma in the range of 14 million have added further weight to the demands (Sofiev et al., 2018). Political pressure led to several legal initiatives to clean up the shipping industry, including the mandatory use of low-sulphur fuel, efficiency improvements in ship construction, the installation of ballast water treatment systems, and stricter rules on the release of sewage water. New environmental laws went hand in hand with articles and studies being published on likely impacts to the industry (Wang and Corbett, 2007, Bosch et al., 2009, Kalli, Karvonen and Makkonen, 2009, SMA, 2009, COMPASS, 2010, EMSA, 2010, Entec, 2010, ICS, 2010, Lemper et al., 2010, Notteboom, Delhay and Vanherle, 2010, Notteboom, 2011, SWECO, 2012, Jalkanen, Kalli and Stipa, 2013). The German weekly ‘Der Spiegel’ expressed fears that the clean up would lead not only to severe economic consequences for the shipping industry, but also to modal shift to the roads and a worse environmental situation (Christian Wüst, 2013). In a recent article the Economist talked of “crippling costs to the industry” (The Economist, 2018a) and argued that environmental laws would worsen global warming. Knowledge gaps exist on the true effects of environmental laws on the shipping industry. All the while, even more legislation will be phased in in the years to come, amounting to “a veritable hurricane of new environmental laws [...] about to hit” (The Economist, 2018b). Distinguishing between popular opinion, the industry’s anxiety, and real economic consequences is demanding. Exploring both the effects and the effectiveness of the current framework of environmental legislation on the shipping industry is the endeavour of this thesis.

1.2 Academic context and background of the study

Multinational and supranational legislators have taken on the task of implementing a system of efficient incentives to discourage the commercial freight shipping industry from harming the environment. In recent years, administrators have passed a comprehensive bundle of environmental legislation targeted at shipping in the European seas that is currently being implemented. New emission reduction requirements for marine fuels came into force on 1 January 2015 with international limits on SO₂ emissions applicable from 2020 onwards (European Parliament and European Council, 2012). The International Maritime Organisation [hereinafter IMO] has designated both the Baltic and the North Sea as NO_x emission control areas from 1 January 2021 forward (World Maritime News, 2016). New laws on sewage water emissions will come into force on 1 June 2019. Ballast water management became mandatory in September 2017 (IMO, 2016a) and an inclusion of shipping into the EU’s CO₂ emission trading system from 2023 onwards is currently under consideration (Peeters, 2016, World

Maritime News, 2017). As a first step, in April 2018 the IMO has proclaimed the aim of reducing CO₂ emissions from shipping by 50% by 2050 compared to 2008 levels (IMO, 2018a). Benefits for the health of humans and animals as well as positive effects on ecosystems are expected from each measure towards greener shipping operations. However, regulatory impact assessments studying the combined economic effect of maritime environmental measures are lacking. The present study seeks to address this shortcoming, providing an integrated analysis as a basis for comprehensive transport planning.

A lack of information is one of the greatest barriers to establishing the socially optimal price for a good such as maritime transportation. This thesis addresses several research gaps. It includes a comprehensive assessment of the costs of maritime environmental legislation measures, an analysis of noncompliance with legislation, an evaluation of impacts on distinct types of shipping companies, and an assessment of the likelihood of modal backshift toward road transport. Making use of original qualitative and quantitative data, these unsolved challenges are addressed, triangulated with data from previous studies and reviewed in the light of economic theory. This thesis follows a law and economics approach touching upon and combining the research fields of environmental law and environmental economics as well as maritime law and maritime economics. It is a work of applied science in the sense that it employs economic and legal theory to interpret and explain the practical economic phenomenon of trade effects from maritime environmental legislation.

1.3 Problem statement

Shipping is among the most environmentally friendly ways of transporting goods but also a significant polluter of our air and waters. Transporting goods has detrimental effects on the quality of life and the health of ecosystems, especially in coastal regions (Cullinane and Cullinane, 2013). Regulating the shipping industry touches upon essential questions of welfare. The prosperity of European citizens depends to a large extent on the possibility to trade and is threatened by increasing trading costs. 90% of world trade is forwarded on board of vessels, bringing positive welfare effects to consumers. At the same time, half of the European population lives within 50 kilometres of the sea and 16% of the 455 million citizens live in coastal cities directly (Eurosian, 2004, p.3, European Commission, 2011a, p.8). The well-being of these people depends on a healthy marine environment. Some scientists estimate that the benefits derived from coastal ecosystems exceed the GDP of some European regions (GSES, 2000, p.18). There is a conflict between preserving freedom of navigation and maintaining the current volume of trade and protecting the marine environment. Balancing costs and benefits from environmental legislation to increase overall welfare should be the ultimate political aim. This study contributes to a better understanding of effects of vessel-source emission legislation and can support legislators in making sounder choices for increasing overall welfare while protecting the environment.

1.4 Research aim, research objectives, and statement of purpose

The author aims to analyse how maritime environmental legislation is affecting shipping costs in the specially protected areas of the North and Baltic Seas. The research investigates how maritime environmental legislation affects business decisions of shipping companies, leading to increases in costs and freight rates. Having made sense of the mechanisms that influence behaviour, the author was determined to quantify the resulting effects. She was particularly interested in finding out whether distinct types of shipping companies are de facto affected differently by current legislation and which role noncompliance plays as an effect of stricter legislation.

Specific actions undertaken to achieve these aims include a critical review of pertinent legal and economic theories as well as prior studies in the field to lay the foundations for this study, followed by an impact assessment based on original interview and questionnaire data to provide new insights into the decision-making mechanisms of companies faced with environmental laws. Data from these three sources was compared to determine both effects of legislation on costs and freight rates and effectiveness of legislation in terms of compliance rates and equality of effects across the industry. The respective research design is presented in chapter 1.8.

The purpose of this research is multifaceted. Knowledge gained on the economic effects of environmental protection will help academics and politicians to better comprehend motivations and actions of the shipping industry specifically and the transport industry in general and may prove to be of great importance in discerning unintentional consequences of environmental transport legislation such as modal shift. Research results on noncompliance may further prove crucial in achieving effective legislation. The results of this research may be used to improve transport planning and legislation in the European Union and worldwide. Accomplishments stem particularly from an extensive study of the role of noncompliance, as well as the examination of differences among freight shipping companies with respect to environmental incentives. The relevance of this research lies in revealing imperfections in the legal framework by empirically studying shipping company behaviour in the face of environmental laws with the aim of fostering more effective policy making. Mirroring the results with economic theory on effective incentives provides new impulses to improve transport policy making for a cleaner environment.

1.5 Scope of previous research and research gaps

Maritime environmental economics is a developing area of research. In his essay on the evolution of maritime economics, Trevor D. Heaver finds that although the topic has been established, “surprisingly few papers” have been published in the field, with a mere 2% of all publications in relevant journals (Heaver, 2012, p.25). Despite increased media coverage and public interest, academic research has been limited on maritime environmental legislation in general as well as the issues discussed in this thesis. Although studies exist dealing with most subsegments of legislation on operational vessel-source pollution such as emission reductions of SO₂, NO_x, CO₂ and particulate matter, ballast water management requirements, limits on sewage and oily water discharges, laws on the dumping of waste, laws on anti-fouling systems, and the regulation of noise pollution, no multi-source economic impact assessment could be

identified by the researcher. The total costs of environmental measures to industry and the combined effect on transport on the North and Baltic Seas could not be determined from existing studies. A discussion of possible interactions among different laws has not been found in available publications and the likely effect on trade could not be identified. With this thesis the researcher will take a broader look at maritime environmental legislation, not just focusing on one specific legal measure, but studying the effects of a bundle of measures affecting the industry simultaneously. Also, unlike many prior studies, this work does not stop at estimating the cost effects of environmental legislation but explicitly discusses the threat of modal shift, thus making the link as to how legislation affects the market. This wider approach compared to previous studies can be seen in Figure 1-1.

Figure 1-1: Scope of research

Furthermore, not only final outcomes in terms of cost and freight rate increases, but also mechanisms leading to these effects will be studied. Compliance decision-making within companies is just as important for understanding trade effects of environmental legislation as the effects themselves. As a work of applied economics, this thesis stands out by establishing a deeper understanding of complex phenomena instead of aggregating information. This includes decisions for noncompliance influencing the economic effect of legislation negatively.

The majority of previous studies have employed quantitative methods exclusively, such as simulations or mathematically based theoretical considerations in order to quantify the cost effects of legislation. This study further analyses why and how these effects come about. Making the process transparent provides information on where political ideas and business realities might not work together and can provide support in improving legislation to achieve a cleaner environment. Mixed methods research has seldom been applied in the field. Qualitative research in the form of expert interviews can help generate process knowledge and bring forth new theories and approaches.

Different to most previous studies, not only vessel owners and operators, but a number of stakeholder groups are included in the study. This is done in order to control for bias of industry representatives and develop a more accurate picture of the problem at hand. Furthermore, instead of looking at the industry as a homogeneous group of companies, the differences among

various types of shipping companies are investigated. Questionnaire data collected from 121 shipping companies makes it the largest original data collection ever conducted in this field of research.

The present work is also the first to systematically study compliance with environmental legislation in the shipping industry. This might be due to the fact that research on compliance is particularly difficult to conduct, as prior researchers point out (Parker and Nielsen, 2011, p.6), but may also lie in the characteristics of the commercial shipping industry, which Tan describes to be particularly “secretive” (Tan, 2006, p.6). The exploratory qualitative study and subsequent statistical evaluation of quantitative data collected on the emerging concepts aims at closing existing gaps in industry-specific compliance research.

1.6 Research approach and ethical approval

With respect to philosophical assumptions, this work is not bound to one view of the world, but instead combines two ontologies. The first phase of research is led by the constructivist paradigm that the social world is “a subjective reality in a continuous state of flux” (Bryman and Bell, 2011, p.22). Environmental legislation is not seen as an objective reality leading to clearly defined behaviour by shipping companies. Instead, the perceptions of decision-makers are seen to have as much an influence on industry behaviour as the formal properties of the law. As reality is seen to be constructed by individuals, the qualitative study aimed at studying the perceptions of decision-makers forms an important contribution to knowledge. It generates theory from individual perspectives. The second quantitative phase of research follows a postpositivist worldview. The paradigm of a singular reality serves as an underlying necessity when attempting a verification of the theory developed in phase I. For the purpose of phase II, the thinking is employed that “there are laws or theories that govern the world, and that these can be tested and verified” (Bloomberg and Volpe, 2012, p.28). Reality is believed to consist of cause-and-effect relationships that can be reduced to important variables and whose interrelations can be numerically studied (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p.40). This study gives value to both subjective and objective forms of knowledge by drawing on different views of the world to enhance our understanding of the economic effects of maritime environmental legislation.

The nature of this research is objectivist theory-testing research. It is aimed at building and testing a theory with compliance-induced environmental costs as the dependent variable and various concepts such as company characteristics as explanatory factors. The research is of a kind to mix qualitative and quantitative data collection with the aim of both developing a deeper understanding of the research problem and, in a second step, of validating the emerging theory numerically. An exploratory sequential mixed methods design (compare Hesse-Biber, 2010, p.105, Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011, p.69, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015, p.170) is employed as depicted in Figure 1-2. Qualitative data collection and analysis serves to identify the social reality of shipping companies, their beliefs and motivations, their decision-making strategies and behaviour in relation to environmental legislation. Building on the variables identified in the exploratory study, the second quantitative phase tests and generalises the initial findings and assesses the prevalence of categories identified for a larger number of market

actors. An exploratory sequential design fits the purpose of this research well, as variables influencing compliance behaviour are widely unknown and need to be identified inductively from qualitative data in order to build a purposeful theory. Once the important constructs are identified, assessing the ability of the theory to be generalised to a larger part of the industry is of great interest.

Figure 1-2: Exploratory sequential mixed methods design

The multi-method mixed methods design serves to compare data from several sources. This strategy includes both the use of multiple sources of data and the use of multiple methods of data collection to increase the validity, credibility and authenticity of analysis and interpretation. Following a constructivist paradigm, the research design adds depth and richness to the research, while it helps to reveal the true nature of the effects of environmental legislation, when following a postpositivist worldview. A discussion on the benefits of mixed-methods research can be found in Saunders et al. and Denzin et al. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015, Denzin and Lincoln, 2017).

Ethical approval for the study at hand was granted on 12 October 2013 by the Ethics Committee and confirmed on 28 March 2018 by Thanos Kourouskis at the University of the West of Scotland. The University of Applied Sciences Hamburg has waived the need to submit the study for ethics approval given that approval has been granted by the UWS.

1.7 Research questions

Studying research gaps, it became apparent that the mechanisms leading from changes in maritime environmental legislation to changes in costs and trade flows were unclear. There was

barely any theoretical literature on the influence of legislation on the costs of shipping companies, and empirical studies conducted were usually limited in scale and methodology as explained in Chapter 1.5. Secondly, the mechanisms and likelihood of modal shift were insufficiently understood. As a third research angle, different shipping companies were likely to be differently influenced by environmental legislation. Identifying variables that would form the basis for varying changes in costs thus became a further focus of interest.

When developing research questions, the challenge arose that qualitative and quantitative research traditions tend to explore very dissimilar types of questions. While qualitative researchers mostly raise “how” or “what” questions and look for “the production of meaning” (Gubrium and Holstein, 1997, p. 14) in a certain social context, quantitative questions are rather verifiable hypotheses that study the relationship among certain variables (Hesse-Biber, 2010, p. 43). The author thus decided to work with two interrelated sets of questions to guide the two different phases of data collection.

The qualitative data collection, aimed at building theory, was guided by the following three question set:

QUAL1: How high are the costs of maritime environmental legislation for the shipping industry? Are they high enough to have a critical effect on the industry, i.e. lead to freight rate increases, modal shift, consolidation, or rerouting of vessels?

QUAL2: Are shipping companies reacting to increasing costs with increased levels of noncompliance? When, why, and to what extent?

QUAL3: Are distinct types of shipping companies differently affected by legislation? Can they provide environmental protection at different costs? Which company characteristics play a role?

Three linked null hypotheses guide the quantitative data collection and analysis, which serves to test theory:

H₀₁: Maritime environmental legislation (MEL) has no statistically significant effect on costs and freight rates of the shipping industry in the North and Baltic Sea areas.

H₀₂: Noncompliance with MEL is negligible.

H₀₃: No significant differences exist within the shipping industry regarding the costs of complying with MEL.

1.8 Conceptual research flow, research process and research design

The conceptual research flow is presented in Figure 1-3 and provides the conceptual framework for the literature review described in Chapters 2 and 3. The foundation of this thesis in the disciplines of environmental economics, environmental law, and environmental law and economics becomes apparent and it is shown how theoretical concepts from these fields are

merged to inform the research, particularly the effects of pollution, effects of incentives to discourage pollution, and the effects of the complexity of the system on economic indicators as well as the environment.

Figure 1-3: Conceptual research flow

The research design is shown in Figure 1-4. The research follows an **exploratory sequential mixed methods design** as described by Creswell (Creswell, 2014, p.214). An initial literature research serves as a knowledge base for a two-step original data collection. An exploration of the topic by way of qualitative data collection and analysis is followed by using the findings in the second quantitative stage. The theoretical model developed from expert interviews is tested by way of a quantitative study and again reviewed in the light of literature as a third source of data. This comparison of sources as a multi-perspective approach to validate data guided the choice of methodology as well as the choice of research participants at the qualitative and

quantitative stages. The critical analysis is built upon a comparison of qualitative and quantitative results with findings from prior studies and theoretical law and economics literature. Lastly, findings are interpreted, and policy recommendations developed.

Figure 1-4: Research approach

A step-by-step approach outlining the research process can be seen in Figure 1-5. Research gaps identified from the literature review formed the basis of an interview guide used for qualitative in-depth interviews with twelve experts from various stakeholder groups. The results were evaluated using MaxQDA. An initial theoretical framework developed from the literature was modified based on knowledge gained from qualitative data. Major drivers were identified and formed the basis for the quantitative study. A questionnaire was developed to collect empirical evidence on relevant variables from shipowners operating in the North and Baltic Seas. Applying Excel, SPSS, R, and Smart-PLS, main influencing factors could be weighed to increase the explanatory power of the qualitative model. Results were subsequently evaluated and discussed. The research methodology including sampling, data collection and analysis, as well as ethical considerations, issues of trustworthiness and method-specific limitations are discussed in Chapter 4.

Figure 1-5: Step-by-step research process

1.9 Assumptions

This work follows the Chicago school of thought in economic analysis, encompassing both the benefits and drawbacks of what has become a standard tool in economics. The law is explained, discussed and critiqued through economic logic, that is “as a series of incentives and disincentives to influence the behavioural choices of people who are viewed as rational and self-interested competitors for society’s scarce resources” (Hutchinson, 2015, p.90). This first assumption of how the law and its subjects are viewed is linked to a second crucial assumption, namely that an efficient allocation of resources can be established by establishing either Pareto or Kaldor-Hicks efficiency. Pareto efficiency means that a legal rule has to make someone better off without disadvantaging other parties. As this aim is largely unattainable when it comes to environmental legislation, Kaldor-Hicks efficiency is a more sensible choice. This principle dictates that with a legal rule, resources must be relocated so as to create a total benefit to society. The idea implies that certain market actors lose welfare due to legislative changes. The new situation is often not Pareto superior. Still, when controlling pollution, compensation paid by the actors gaining from health improvement to the actors being prohibited to pollute is well thinkable. Thus, the new situation is potentially Pareto superior. One problem with such compensation is that it is not voluntarily paid. It does not result from the market forces of supply and demand but must be prescribed by the government. As with any involuntary exchange, we cannot be sure that it actually increases welfare (see Posner, 2014, p.16). Kaldor-Hicks proposes a way around this, exploring what would happen in a world of zero transaction costs. Would shipping companies buy the right to pollute off the population, or would the population compensate the shipping companies for making an effort to keep air and water clean? It is highly

complex to simulate such a situation, but this thesis is based on the assumption that Kaldor-Hicks efficiency should eventually be aimed at.

This assumption is not universally accepted. An important criticism of basing legal rules on economic aims like Kaldor-Hicks efficiency stems from concepts on morality. Some researchers question whether efficiency and a normative approach to policy making are the correct aims of a successful society. This notion as shared by Polinsky, who demands less efficiency in return for a fairer division of welfare. (Polinsky, 2011, p. 8) In many cases, justice and efficiency are one and the same. Compensating the population for health effects caused by shipping may be both just and efficient. There are however cases that might be efficient, like sinking a small island to establish a faster water route, but are not in line with common perceptions on justice. This approach is mirrored in the Yale school, also termed “normative” school of law and economics. It differs from the Chicago school in its concern for distributional effects of the law, and questions of justice and fairness. A further criticism of the above-named assumptions can be found with the Virginia school, also called “functional” school of law and economics. It was developed in the 1990s and incorporates public choice theory. Along with criticising economic models for their simplified depiction of reality, it discusses failures in policy making and is concerned with the efficiency of legal systems. Scholars argue that legal systems need to work efficiently and in an unbiased way before a discussion of which laws lead to efficient outcomes even makes sense (Klick and Parisi, 2015, p.104). In this work, the legal system is taken as a given and unchangeable, and the efficient allocation of resources is taken to be the aim of legal systems, both assumptions in line with the Chicago school of thought.

1.10 Rationale and significance

The research has significance beyond the limited scope of the study itself. Though the setting is fairly local with a focus on the Northern European seas, the sample for the qualitative study consisting mostly of German organisations, and the sample for the quantitative study consisting of companies operating in the Baltic and North Seas, the results have a wider significance for the political debate. The social purpose is to ensure that the aim of environmental protection is correctly implemented and does not lead to a worse state of the environment, for example due to modal shift. Also, achieving a better understanding of how environmental legislation influences distinct types of companies may support policy makers in drafting legislation closer to business realities.

1.11 Definitions of key terminology used in the study

1.11.1 Research subject: Commercial freight shipping

The subject that is being researched in this study is the commercial freight shipping industry, as opposed to non-commercial shipping activities, such as the use of pleasure boats. Furthermore, this research is interested in vessels used for freight transport as opposed to vessels used for other commercial activities such as fishing or passenger transport. The OECD organises commercial shipping into five categories: Deep-sea international shipping (between continents), coastal or short sea shipping, inland shipping (on rivers, lakes, and canals), ferries, and cruise shipping (OECD, 2011, p.26). Of these categories, only deep-sea and short sea

vessels, as well as ferries used exclusively or partially for the shipping of goods are considered in this study.

In its ‘Review of Maritime Transport 2017’ the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development [hereinafter UNCTAD] describes the structure of the world fleet. They organise their statistics into five general vessel types: Oil tankers, dry bulk carriers, general cargo ships, container ships, and others (including gas carriers, chemical tankers, offshore, and ferries and passenger ships) (UNCTAD, 2017). As this thesis is focused on trade in the North and Baltic Sea areas, the category of ferries as a means of goods transport is of enhanced importance and will be treated as an individual category. This category includes Roll-on-roll-off-vessels [hereinafter RoRo vessels], which are ships carrying exclusively wheeled cargo, and Roll-on-roll-off-and-passenger-vessels [hereinafter RoPax vessels]. The structure of the world fleet respective to these categories can be seen in Table 1-1. Bulk carriers account for the largest part of the fleet with a share of 42.8%, followed by crude carriers (or oil tankers). RoRo and RoPax vessels account for a mere 0.3% of the world fleet but have a much more pronounced position in the refined areas of the North and Baltic Seas. According to European Transport Maps, 265 RoRo services operate in the North and Baltic Sea areas (European Transport Maps, 2018). Recent AIS¹ data analysed by HELCOM suggests that around 4% of the commercial fleet in the Baltic Sea consists of RoRo and RoPax vessels. Data for the North Sea could not be identified, but the structure is likely to be similar.

	World fleet (2017)	Share of the world fleet	Baltic Sea fleet (2015)	Share of the Baltic Sea fleet
Bulk carriers (Liquid/Dry)	796,581	42.8%	3,778**	62.0%
Crude carriers	534,855	28.7%	1,734	28.4%
Container vessels	245,609	13.2%	341	5.6%
Specialised cargo carriers	204,088	11.0%	n.a.	n.a.
General cargo carriers	74,823	4.0%	n.a.	n.a.
RoRo/RoPax vessels	5,896*	0.3%	242	4.0%

Table 1-1: Structure of the world fleet (adapted from UNCTAD, 2017, HELCOM, 2018)

**including passenger vessels, **including general and specialised cargo carriers*

Commercial freight shipping is conducted by shipping companies with diverse characteristics. These companies may be classified by the risks they carry and the interests they control. Stopford defines a shipping company as “a legal organisation which owns ships” (Stopford, 2013, p.282). Theotokas states that “the task of a shipping company is the management of ships

¹ Automatic identification system used on vessels to avoid collision, required to be used on board of all vessels above 300 gross tonnage (GT) and all passenger ships according to the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS)

for the supply of maritime transport services” (Theotokas, 2018, Chapter 1). This thesis combines the two concepts of ownership and the type of vessel employed to define shipping companies. A shipping company may either own vessels, operate vessels or act as an owner-operator. A shipowner has a controlling interest in one or more vessels. A management company usually handles the day-to-day operations of said vessels. An owner-operator manages his own vessels. In bulk shipping, shipowners charter their vessels to shippers for a single voyage (voyage charter on the spot market), a determined period of time (time charter) or an extended period of time (bareboat charter) (on specifics regarding risk, control and remuneration see Theotokas, 2018, Chapter 1). In container shipping, owner-operators are more predominant than in other sectors. Theotokas argues that the vessel types employed by a company determine the manner of operation of the company and Branch adds that the type of vessel employed depends on the type of traffic carried (Branch, 2007, p.50). Maritime carriers is thus generally categorised either by the type of vessel used or the type of cargo transported (Talley, 2012, p.89). It must be noted, however, that different industry sectors may compete for the same cargo if shortages in one segment arise. Furthermore, multi-purpose vessels are increasingly employed to make systems more flexible (Branch, 2007, p.50). The most important characteristics of the different shipping sectors by vessel type as used in this thesis are described in Table 1-2. Various other segmentations of the industry exist, and some vessels are difficult to categorise.

Industry sector	Core characteristics
Bulk carriers (Liquid/Dry)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Homogeneous cargoes loaded in copious quantities mainly in parcels over 10,000 dwt, often occupying the entire transporting capacity of the ship following the principle ‘one ship, one cargo’ • Split into four segments: Capesize, Panamax, Handymax, Handy • Main products carried: Building materials, agricultural products • Part of the fleet owned or operated in long-term charter by large commodity companies handling their own transport requirements; part of the fleet chartered for a single voyage, esp. in agricultural trades like grain and sugar, to transport the season’s harvest; companies often rather small, with an intimate knowledge of the market they serve • Carrying capacity measured in: Deadweight tonnage (dwt)
Crude carriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vessels specialised in the transport of crude oil from one bunkering port to another bunkering port in a worldwide network of tanker routes • Significant proportion of the fleet either owner-operated by oil-producing countries or operated under long-term charter by oil companies • Split into segments depending on vessel size: ULCC, VLCCs, Suezmax, Aframax, Panamax, Handy and small tankers (Different sizes usually operate on different trades) • Main product carried: Crude oil • Capacity measured in: Deadweight tonnage (dwt),

Container vessels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ships with box-shaped holds to allow speedy loading and unloading of containers. Provide and group transport services for cargoes that are too small to fill an entire vessel • Operation on regular schedules between ports at fixed prices, irrespective of utilised capacity; management-intensive business with large shore establishments; often sizeable fleet aimed at providing efficient services and multi-modal connections managed by large companies; vulnerable to marginal cost-pricing by competitors, thus characterised by cooperation among companies in liner conferences • Main product carried: Containerised cargo • Capacity measured in: Twenty-foot equivalent units (TEU) corresponding to a typical container length
Specialised cargo carriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialised carriers designed to optimise the transport of a certain good, e.g. forest products, where such an operation can reduce costs or improve quality • Operation often based on fixed timetables and optimised to carry high cargo volumes and offer fast loading and unloading of specialised cargoes; shipping company often services the whole trade rather than one customer, works in close cooperation with shippers. • Main products carried: Forest products, frozen cargo, chemicals, vehicles
General cargo carriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Often have open holds and cargo-handling gear to carry bulk and project cargoes and cargoes of all purposes, especially diverse forms of dry cargo, but also liquid or specialised cargoes, due to its multi-purpose design; cargo is generally lifted on and off the vessel • Main products carried: All categories of products
RoRo/RoPax vessels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide cargo hold access through ramps, operate in the short sea trade, generally on fixed schedules, often carry both passengers and wheeled cargo (RoPax vessels) or vehicles exclusively (RoRo vessels) • Main products carried: Wheeled cargo • Capacity measured in: Lane capacity (m) plus additional capacity for containers (TEU) and/or liquid cargoes in holds (m³)

Table 1-2: Core characteristics of sectors within the commercial shipping industry (own deliberations based on Branch, 2007, Stopford, 2013, Theotokas, 2018)

An important differentiation among different sectors of the shipping industry is between tramp and liner shipping. Liner shipping, meaning operation on fixed schedules, is often linked to container vessels, specialised cargo carriers and RoRo/RoPax vessels. General cargo, crude and bulk carriers will often trade without a schedule, but will operate worldwide wherever cargo is available (Branch, 2007, p.52). A last issue to clarify here is the use of the terms maritime and

marine. Although at times used as synonyms, for the purpose of this paper the suggested definition of Hilderbrand and Schröder-Hinrichs is applied, where the term marine refers to the ocean and is used when discussing its environmental status and level of pollution, whereas the term maritime refers to human activities on the ocean, in this context the activities of the shipping industry (Hildebrand and Schröder-Hinrichs, 2014).

1.11.2 Geographical area of research: Baltic and North Sea areas

The geographical area studied comprises the Baltic and the North Seas as delineated by the Helsinki and OSPAR Conventions (OSPAR, 1992, HELCOM, 2000) and shown in Figure 1-6. These areas are of particular interest as they are subject to stricter environmental legislation than other European seas, international waters and most other regional waters. Effects of legislation on costs are thus more likely to be measurable here. Furthermore, the vast majority of states bordering the Baltic and North Seas are member states of the European Union², making European laws widely applicable in these waters.³ Also, the researcher is based in Paisley, Great Britain as well as in Hamburg, Germany and thus in a good location to investigate changes in the seas surrounding her.

Figure 1-6: Boundaries of marine regions and subregions as laid down in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), North Sea in green, Baltic Sea in blue (ArcGIS, 2018)

² Great Britain, however, is bound to leave the European Union in 2019. It remains to be seen whether national legislation on vessel-source pollution will be drafted to replace European legislation currently applicable to British seas and harbours.

³ A conflict of laws does, however, seem apparent with Russia, who does not seem to accept the designation of the Baltic Sea as a SECA, as mentioned by some experts.

Geographical borders are often established arbitrarily in marine waters. They arise from occupational history and are based on current political interests. Often, delimitations are linked to onshore national borders. Rarely do they consider borders of marine ecosystems. The delimitation of the Baltic Sea is an exception in this regard, being more or less in line with the sphere of actual environmental effects, as there is little exchange with other waters. That is entirely different for the marine territory called the North Sea. Its delimitation makes little sense scientifically, based on the question of where the environmental effects of shipping pollution are measured. Structuring environmental legislation along the lines of politically defined delimitations of the sea which are not in line with ecosystem borders makes it hard to adequately address environmental challenges. Matters are even more complicated in the case of air pollution, where no real borders seem to exist among ecosystems. For this study, however, legislation as based on current limits of legal enforceability will be taken as a given.

1.12 Organisation of the dissertation

With a view to determining the economic effects of environmental legislation, a review of relevant economic theories is conducted in Chapter 2. Starting with an economic theory of pollution in 2.3, theoretical considerations on how to disincentivise pollution are reviewed in 2.4, considerations on modal shift and compliance with legislation in 2.5 and 2.6 respectively, and a discussion on the specific characteristics of the shipping industry can be found in 2.7. Having established the theoretical foundations, these chapters are supplemented by a review of prior studies on the aforementioned issues in Chapter 3. Chapter 3.2 reviews prior studies on how incentives to discourage pollution affect the costs to industry. Chapter 3.3 discusses empirical evidence on freight rate changes and modal shift. In Chapter 3.4 evidence from prior studies on deviant behaviour is reviewed, and empirical evidence on the characteristics of the shipping industry is discussed in Chapter 3.7.

The review of prior studies provides evidence on well-established and empirically proven theories, but also highlights research gaps and provides the fundament for this thesis. In Chapter 4, the methodology and research approach to this thesis are explained, including the methodological stance in 4.2, methods of data collection and analysis in 4.3, and ethical considerations and the role of the researcher in Chapters 4.4 and 4.5 respectively. Finally, a critique of methodology, a discussion on the trustworthiness of results, and limitations and delimitations are presented in Chapters 4.6 and 4.7. Findings can be found in Chapters 5 and 6, including the results of the qualitative study, as well as results from statistical evaluation of the quantitative study. A critical analysis of findings in the light of the research hypotheses, a nonresponses analysis and a synthesis of lessons learned are displayed in Chapter 7. Chapter 8 holds final conclusions, policy recommendations and suggestions for future research.

2 Theoretical foundations

2.1 Introduction

This thesis explores the effects of legal incentives to discourage vessel-source pollution on the shipping industry. A review of theoretical foundations of relevance for this exploration is conducted in this chapter. First, the term pollution is defined from a legal and economic point

of view and seven sources of vessel-source pollution are identified and described. In a second step, economic theory on incentives to discourage pollution is evaluated and discussed. Starting with general observations on incentive structures, theories on how to discourage pollution established by Pigou and Coase are reviewed. Legal incentives are subsequently classified and discussed in the light of economic considerations. In the following, Posner's and Polinsky's arguments on a full cost approach and the cheapest pollution provider are considered, with the aim of establishing how optimal environmental legislation should look like from an economic point of view. In Chapter 2.5.7 the current legal framework to disincentivise vessel-source pollution is reviewed and compared to recommendations from economic theory, discussing reasons for discrepancies between theory and practice.

Chapters 2.6 and 2.7 include theoretical foundations on unintended effects of legislation. Firstly, a certain increase in costs for the shipping industry may lead to a shift towards less environmentally friendly modes of transport, i.e. truck and rail, in the North and Baltic Sea areas. Also, transport cost elasticity may influence cost-benefit considerations. Furthermore, diminishing returns of additional environmental measures must be considered. These issues are reviewed in Chapter 2.6, laying out theories on modal shift. Secondly, noncompliance with legislation as a reaction to increasing costs has to be studied. The theoretical foundations for compliant and deviant behaviour are reviewed in Chapter 2.7. Chapter 2.8 incorporates a discussion on the specific characteristics of the shipping industry.

2.2 Scientific setting

“The only way in which a human being can make some approach to knowing the whole of a subject, is by hearing what can be said about it by persons of every variety of opinion, and studying all modes in which it can be looked at by every character of mind.”

John Stuart Mill (1895)

This thesis is a work of applied law and economics, indicating that economic theories are employed to solve real-world legal problems. Both the transport sector as well as the economic problem of environmental pollution lend themselves well to applied economics. Following suggestions by Peter Swann, a combination of different research methods is used to derive knowledge in ways that ensure the demand for rigour and accuracy, while deriving a wealth of knowledge in the sense of John Stuart Mill (Swann, 2006, p.3). Findings are based on empirical data collected from shipping companies and industry experts triangulated with lessons from economic theory and the critical analysis of prior studies.

2.3 Methodology employed in reviewing theoretical concepts

The review of relevant theoretical concepts to the current research was driven by a systematic approach to reviewing literature based on keyword matrixes and guidance questions. Legal, economic, and general knowledge databases were comprehensively searched to establish current strands of research, major textbooks were reviewed to identify established theories and

official publications by governmental and non-governmental institutions were examined to add the practitioner's perspective to academic research.

With the aim of demonstrating the systematic procedure of the literature review, the search for relevant legal literature is presented here as an example. The keyword matrix applied for the extraction of legal studies is depicted in Table 2-1. All possible combinations of first, second and third entry were entered into legal databases such as LexisLibrary, Juris, Westlaw UK, and ECOLEX. Whenever possible an "abstracts" search was conducted, as some themes would not necessarily appear in the title of papers.

First Entry	Second Entry	Third Entry
Marine*	Policy*	Pollution*
Maritime*	Legislation*	Environment*
Ship*	Law*	Emission*
Vessel*		

Table 2-1: Keyword matrix used for the legal database search

Search string: abstract(marine OR maritime* OR ship* OR vessel*) AND abstract(policy* OR legislation* OR law*) AND abstract(pollution* OR environment* OR emission*)*

Challenges related to the keyword search were linked to the substantial number of research disciplines producing knowledge on the subject of marine pollution. Academics from all disciplines of science as well as from schools of politics, sociology, medicine and others publish in the field. The task of reviewing the literature and identifying sources relevant for the research angle was thus quite time-consuming. This obstacle was aggravated by the fact that some databases, like ISI Web of Knowledge, only allowed for a full text search leading to a significant amount of inept results. An example of the number of total results found by applying the above-named search string is shown in Table 2-2. To better handle the considerable number of hits, all articles were classified by title and abstract into the three categories "valuable to research", "potentially valuable to research" and "not of interest" based on pre-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria. The keyword search in this one example yielded 182 articles that were either hands-on valuable or potentially valuable and were analysed more thoroughly.

Database	Type of search	Number of total results	Number of valuable and potentially valuable results
ISI Web of Knowledge	Full text search	11,427	151
Westlaw UK	Full text search	15	11
ECOLEX	Full text search	6	2
Wiley Online Library	Abstract search	245	13
Juris	Full text search	190	0
Cambridge Journals Online	Title search	7	1
LexisLibrary	Abstract search	55	4

Total		11,945	182
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Table 2-2: Number of total and valuable results from the database search

Further literature including handbooks, monographs, government reports, statistical data as well as a substantial quantity of supplementary journal articles was discovered and reviewed based on the bibliographies of the valuable results as well as “cited by” search tools in the named databases and Google Scholar.

A list of questions was established to guide the literature review:

1. *What is the current state of marine environmental legislation? What laws and regulations will come into force on the international and European level until 2030? Can the measures be ordered according to common themes? How does economic theory on environmental legislation link to actual legislation on vessel-source pollution?*
2. *What are the associated costs to industry of the environmental measures according to the literature? What influences on freight rates and trade flows are estimated?*
3. *What perspective do prior studies give on the issues of modal shift, compliance and differences among different shipping trades?*
4. *How do various studies relate to each other? What precise contribution do they make to the field? What are their limitations?*
5. *How can the present research fit into what has already been done?*

2.4 An economic theory of pollution

2.4.1 Definition of pollution

Before attempting a categorisation of vessel-source emissions, the scope of the term ‘pollution’ needs to be established. The concept has first and foremost a scientific dimension, but for the purpose of this research both the legal and the economic dimension are reviewed as well. From a scientific point of view, materials that are being discharged into the environment, but are not immediately useful there constitute ‘waste’ as depicted in Figure 2-1 (Hassan et al., 2005, p.419). These materials may, however, provide a service to mankind in another context, like oil that is lost in an oil spill can be used to power cars. Pollution in the natural sciences is commonly distinguished from waste in that a loss of ecosystem services has occurred. Ecosystem services describe the benefits the human population receives from an ecosystem. The definition from the UN Millenium Ecosystem Assessment is the most widely used (Millenium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005, p.40), with four categories of services proposed, namely provisioning services (e.g. providing food and water), regulating services (e.g. disease control), cultural services (e.g. recreation) and supporting services (e.g. water cycling). Other researchers propose other categories (compare Holmlund and Hammer, 1999, Daily and Dasgupta, 2001). Hassan and co-authors of the UN working group argue that the value of ecosystems like the North and Baltic Sea areas does not only stem from direct or indirect use, but also from preserving the option to use certain services in the future (option value) and from knowing that a resource

exists, without using it (non-use value). The value that society derives from the Baltic and North Seas stems from the direct uses of recreation, transportation, fish consumption, fresh water and others, the indirect uses of carbon sequestration, nutrient cycling and others, the option value of future generations benefitting from these seas as well as the non-use value or existence value of biodiversity (Hassan et al., 2005). A graphical depiction may be found in Annex A1. It is thus not only the direct consumption by our generation, but also the more abstract protection of biodiversity that has a value to mankind. A loss in any of the ecosystem services described would fit the scientific definition of pollution.

Figure 2-1: Scientific, legal and economic definitions of pollution (Author, adapted from Hassan et al., 2005, Copyright © 2005 Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. Reproduced by permission of Island Press, Washington, DC)

In the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment Report, the processing of waste and the detoxification of water is described as an important service of the marine ecosystem to mankind (Hassan et al., 2005: 417 et al.). It can thus be assumed that the environment can handle a certain amount of man-made pollution. The researchers argue that the capacity for assimilation of toxic substances is highly variable and depends on the specific ecosystem's ability to detoxify, process and isolate waste from the environment (Hassan et al., 2005: 419). Scientists are undecided whether the detoxification capabilities of the oceans increase or decrease when waste-loads are rising (Hassan et al., 2005: 419). The researchers around Hassan conclude that the ecosystems capabilities to assimilate waste have been reached in many areas (Hassan et al., 2005: 419). Coastal ecosystems provide significantly more services to the human race than most other systems, but are also among the most endangered (Hassan et al., 2005: 515).

The second dimension of the term pollution that is of relevance here is the legal definition. Differing from the scientific point of view pollution only becomes "legally significant" (Bowman and Boyle, 2002: 196) when a certain threshold of harm is reached. The legal concept of marine pollution has evolved over the years beginning with the Trail Smelter Arbitration in 1941. In the first ever dispute addressing trans-boundary pollution the tribunal ruled that environmental damage needed to have a "serious consequence" and the injury needed to be established by "clear and convincing evidence" in order for an act of pollution to become legally significant (For the influence of the Trail Smelter Arbitration on the Law of the Sea see Kaye,

2006). Regarding vessel-source pollution, the Trail Smelter Arbitration does not provide a workable definition, as it seriously limits the prima facie utility for preventive damage control. The aim of environmental legislation is usually to prevent deterioration of the marine ecosystem ex ante that is before “serious consequences” become evident. Laylin and Bianchi argue: “... [a] man dying of thirst cannot be revived with monetary compensation for his water,...” (Laylin and Bianchi, 1959). Furthermore, it is usually difficult to identify the polluter when the violation occurs in the vast spheres of the open oceans by moving contaminants. Also, the consequences of one single incident will be arduous to establish and even harder to prove; there might be no “clear and convincing evidence” at hand. The harm caused might not be measurable as the marine ecosystem is extremely complex. The 1941 definition which is often seen as laying the basis for all international environmental law is of little help when it comes to pollution of the marine environment.

The legal definition of environmental pollution that will be applied in this research is based on the one developed in 1966 by the International Law Association [hereinafter ILA] in the Helsinki Rules on “Uses of Waters in International Rivers”, indicating that “water pollution” refers to a detrimental change in the natural composition, content or quality of the water “resulting from human conduct” (International Law Association, 1966, Article IX). The idea of human involvement was incorporated into the currently most widely used definition of marine pollution as included into the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea [hereinafter UNCLOS], Article 1 (4):

“... ‘pollution of the marine environment’ means the introduction by man, directly or indirectly, of substances or energy into the marine environment, including estuaries, which results or is likely to result in such deleterious effects as harm to living resources and marine life, hazards to human health, hindrance to marine activities, including fishing and other legitimate uses of the sea, impairment of quality for use of sea water and reduction of amenities.”

This definition has been changed from an earlier United Nations terminology (UN 1971) replacing the formulation “...resulting in such deleterious effects...” by “... results or is likely to result in such deleterious effects...”. The formalisation has been significantly widened, including harmful effects that potentially occur in the future as well as changes on the body of water that are not of a serious nature. Furthermore, the definition is very open, as it includes all sources of pollution, current and new sources that may come up in the future. Also, with respect to the object of regulation, the definition is very wide. The “marine environment” includes marine living organisms which also fall under the protection of UNCLOS (Tanaka, 2012: 256). The notion of “deleterious effects” is, similar to above definitions, kept rather vague and leaves space for interpretation.

UNCLOS introduced the Precautionary Principle, which is Principle 15 of the Rio Declaration on the Environment and Development: “In order to protect the environment the precautionary approach shall be widely applied by states according to their capabilities. Where there are threats of serious or irreversible damage, lack of full scientific certainty shall not be used as a reason for postponing cost-effective measures to prevent environmental degradation.” (1992 Earth Summit in Brazil). The introduction of the Precautionary Principle in UNCLOS, meaning

that the release must be stopped if there is justifiable doubt related to the possible harm, has been transposed into European law with the coming into force of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive [hereinafter MSFD]. This evolution of the definition of marine pollution goes in line with the evolving environmental consciousness during the last decades.

When legal scholars talk about a certain threshold of harm that needs to be established, the area of reference for that harm-definition is important. Does a certain incident have to harm the entire ecosystem of the North or Baltic Sea for it to fall under the legal definition or will a smaller area satisfy? How small might that area be? These questions are of significance to establish a viable scientific definition of pollution, but when it comes to the research at hand, namely the economic outcome of legislation, the political area definition establishes the area where economic effects are measured. The area politically termed the North Sea might not be a closed ecosystem, but it is a political system. It is not the scientific definition of ecosystems, harm or pollution that play a role for legislation, but solely political definitions matter.

In this thesis economic effects of legislation are studied. Therefore, an economic definition of pollution needs to be considered. Pollution always has an economic dimension when costs to society occur. In a seminal publication on water pollution control the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency [hereinafter U.S. EPA] lists these societal costs as damages to tangible and intangible assets, reduced efficiency, additional production costs to on-going activities and reduced potential benefits emanating from foregone activities (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 1973, p.47).

Comparing the above definitions, it becomes apparent that pollution in the scientific sense and pollution in the economic sense are closely aligned. Where a measurable loss of ecosystem services occurs, costs to society are incurred. The legal definition of pollution differs in crucial aspects, as it covers not only actual, but also potential harm in line with the Precautionary Principle. In consequence, pollution in the legal sense may occur *before* a loss of ecosystem services or costs to society materialize. Legal incentives are thus developed to prevent pollution in the economic and scientific sense. Therefore, when pollution in the legal sense comes into play, costs to society may not occur from the pollution itself, but from societal effects of legal incentives. This relationship is further developed in Chapter 2.5 on incentives to discourage pollution.

If it is not prevented before occurring, pollution in the legal sense requires a certain threshold of harm to be reached as well as an established connection between the polluter and the pollution. It is thus not only possible that legal pollution eventuates where scientific and economic pollution are lacking, but also that scientifically and economically a loss of ecosystem services and societal welfare take place, while legally there is no case of pollution. Any conduct by shipowners and operators that does not qualify under the legal definition will not have any legal effect and thus not any cost effects related to legislation. As the focus of interest of this study lies on the cost effects of legislation, the legal definition of pollution according to UNCLOS, Art. 1(4) will be applied throughout the study. Where there is legally no pollution, no legislation to prevent pollution will bite and thus no cost effect due to pollution legislation will be noticeable.

2.4.2 Classification of vessel-source pollution

Pollution of the world's oceans is mainly associated with land-based discharges of harmful substances into the sea and atmospheric pollution from the shore (Sündermann, 2007, p.10). Vessel-source pollution contributes only to a small extent to the deterioration of the marine environment (Tan, 2006). A mere 3.1% of the world's CO₂ emissions stem from the shipping industry (IMO, 2014a, p.14). Still, significant savings are possible in a sector that is faced with environmental protection measures rather later than land-based emitters. In their seminal paper on mortality from ship emissions, Corbett et al. estimated that in 2007 around 60,000 deaths annually were related to emissions of particulate matter by vessels, with most death occurring near the coastlines of main shipping routes in Europe and Asia (Corbett et al., 2007). Eyring et al. support these findings, stating that nearly 70% of ship emissions arise within 400 km of coastlines (Eyring et al., 2010). In a recent study on the impact of cleaner marine fuels, a group of Finnish researchers working together with James J. Corbett give much higher estimates for ship-related deaths, stating that these amounted to roughly 400,000 deaths from lung cancer and cardiovascular disease and roughly 14 million cases of childhood asthma. The researchers strongly support legislative measures to control vessel-source pollution, stating that legislation on the use of low-sulphur fuels alone could reduce ship-related deaths by 34% and childhood asthma by 54% by 2020 (Sofiev et al., 2018). Delayed regulatory efforts may be explained by the international character of the industry and the necessity of an international approach to environmental legislation, which also means that there is still sphere of manoeuvre to improve negative impacts by the sector on the marine environment.

The most common type of ship release is operational vessel-source pollution, including both automatic emissions as well as intentional discharges pertinent to the normal operation of a ship. Incidents of accidental pollution may not be outlawed due to the very nature of their coming about. Legislators do, however, aim to limit accidents by imposing certain structural obligations, such as double hull requirements (see Regulation 19 in Annex I to MARPOL), on vessel operators. The focus of this thesis lies on normal vessel operations, however. Here, the effect of legal rules on strategic decisions is the focal point. Accidental incidents of pollution as shown in Figure 2-2 will thus not be studied.

Figure 2-2: Difference between operational and accidental incidents of pollution

Looking at the normal operation of a ship, seven distinct categories of pollution have been identified from the literature as shown in Figure 2-3. These are air pollution (emissions of SO₂, NO_x, CO₂ and particulate matter), ballast, sewage and oily water discharges, dumping of waste, harmful anti-fouling systems and noise pollution. Vessels pose a threat to animal and plant life in the oceans, and, by way of air pollution, also affect the environment in a larger sense.

Figure 2-3: Seven sources of pollution

These categories are by no means universally used in the law or the books. In a 1993 publication Brubaker distinguishes two types of vessel-source pollution: seawater pumped into ballast or fuel tanks and discharged into the sea and the dumping of waste including sewage (Brubaker, 1993, p.34). More than a decade later Tan organises his research according to the categories of oil pollution, air pollution, anti-fouling systems and discharges of ballast water (Tan, 2006). Few authors acknowledge emissions of noise as a form of vessel-borne environmental contamination (Firestone and Jarvis, 2007), but the issue has recently received increased attention both by researchers (McKenna et al., 2012, Tasker et al., 2012, Markus and Sánchez, 2018, Veirs et al., 2018) as well as officials at the IMO (Marine Environment Protection Committee, 2013). Air pollution and leakage of substances from anti-fouling systems are only mentioned in more recent publications. A source of vessel-borne emissions that has not entered the focus of attention and has only recently been noticed by the WMO in internal communications are microwaves from marine radars. Studies reviewed by the World Health Organisation [hereinafter WHO] do not offer convincing scientific evidence on whether exposure to radio frequencies induces cancer or shortens the life span of humans (WHO, 2018). As the effects and dangers of this type of emission are not sufficiently studied and as especially the impact of ship radars on the environment is not known, investigation of this type of pollution will be postponed to future studies.

The present research will focus on those seven sources of operational vessel-source pollution which are scientifically established to have an impact on the environment and which are currently, or may in the near future, be regulated and may thus be a cause of increased costs for the shipping industry. In international treaties marine pollution is usually regulated either by following a source-based approach or by regulating pollution for certain regions (Tanaka, 2012: 262). In this thesis the author focuses on two regions only, combining a regional approach with the study of different substances of marine pollution. A regional source-specific approach is thus applied. The seven sources of vessel-borne pollution will briefly be illustrated in the following.

2.4.2.1 Oily water

The control of oil pollution has been at the focus of attention when marine environmental policy making started in 1954. It is only a minor contributor to overall pollution today (Birnie, Boyle and Redgwell, 2009, p.380). Oil pollution can stem from shipping accidents but may also be associated with the normal operation of a vessel. Sündermann attributes only 13% of total oil pollution to accidents at sea, while he links some 32% to every-day shipping operations of oil tankers and other vessels (Sündermann, 2007, p.9). Oil may be discharged with the bilge water of diesel engine ships, as a residue in the ship's ballast water or directly as a product of illegal tank cleaning activities (OECD, 2003, p.20, Tanaka, 2012, p.357). Recent data on discharges of oily water is limited and is mostly achieved through aerial surveillance (OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.95). A recent study by Vollard et al. shows that, as surveillance methods improve, shipping companies displace their illegal discharges from daytime to night-time, where evidence collected by the authorities becomes contestable in court and chances of getting caught thus decrease (Vollaard, 2017). Overall pollution levels can be identified using the North Sea ECOQO, an indicator measuring the proportion of oily dead guillemots (deep-diving seabirds) that wash ashore each winter. While the number is higher close to busy shipping lanes,

overall rates have declined in the last decades (OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.95). In numbers, international releases by ships including accidental spills reach some 450,000 tons of oil yearly. This is less than the estimated 600,000 tons of oil flowing into the oceans from natural causes (Kvenvolden and Cooper, 2003, p.140). The problem of oil spills is thus no longer as pertinent as it was half a millennium ago.

2.4.2.2 *Sewage water*

Sewage water, also known as wastewater, is a solution of more than 99% water and less than 1% of polluting substances. Wastewater stemming from vessels is typically discerned into black and grey water, with black water (also known as brown water) referring to human waste from toilets, and grey water stemming from showers, baths, sinks and cleaning activities (Talley, 2009, p.162). Sewage water can contain a variety of harmful substances, like detergents and bacteria, leading to an excessive introduction of nutrients into the marine environment (Dowling, 2006, p.331). Grey water is the largest source of liquid waste generated by ocean cruises. Ordinary cruise ships produce between 30,000 and 80,000 l of black water/day and around 300 million litres of grey water a day (Herz, Davis and Conservancy, 2002, Dowling, 2006, p.331). Problematic discharges of wastewater are to a significant extent associated with passenger transportation and play only a minor role in goods transportation. A number of researchers warn of the dangers of black and grey water discharges, as they typically contain pollutants that negatively affect the water quality and have detrimental effects on marine life and health as well as posing risks to human health (Welles, 2003, p.100). Birnie et al. link the spread of diseases as well as eutrophication and oxygen depletion causing disruption in the marine ecosystem to sewage pollution (Birnie, Boyle and Redgwell, 2009, p.380). Sündermann argues that approximately half of the nutrients emitted into marine waters stems from sewage, while the other half can be linked to farming, forestry and other land uses. Nutrients promote the bloom of algae in coastal waters, leading to a depletion of oxygen in the water and thus killing marine animals. Furthermore, the bloom of certain toxic algae will lead to dying fish and cause harm to human health (Sündermann, 2007, p.8). Sündermann also holds sewage responsible for the contamination of coastal waters with pathogens, leading to diseases like typhoid and cholera (Sündermann, 2007, p.8). Welles qualifies the dangers somewhat. He argues that discharges on the high seas can usually be assimilated by natural bacterial action and dispersion (Welles, 2003, p.100). However, discharges of grey water near the coastline can lead to highly elevated levels of bacteria followed by the need to close beaches for swimming and shellfish beds for harvesting (Welles, 2003, p.100). According to the OSPAR 2010 Quality Status Report sewage discharges complying with the laws of MARPOL are usually linked to minimal effects as bacteria assimilate the material. Illegal discharges close to coastal areas, however, may become a local problem (OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.97). The 1990 GESAMP report identified sewage disposal as one of the most urgent problems responsible for the worsening of marine pollution since 1982 (GESAMP, 1990). Unfortunately, no similar study comprising recent data has been published since.

2.4.2.3 Dumping of waste

In a high-tech era of radiation, carcinogenic chemicals, and human-induced climate change, the problem of the trash produced by ocean-going vessels or litter swept out to sea must seem old-fashioned by comparison. [...] Regrettably, that perception is wrong.

US Senator Daniel Inouye⁴

For the purpose of this study waste can be defined as “manufactured or processed solid material disposed of, or abandoned, either directly or indirectly, in the marine and coastal environment.” (Hastings and Potts, 2013, p.49). While around 80% of waste is believed to stem from land-based sources some 20% is introduced into the oceans by trade and fishing vessels (Clean Water Action, 2016). No exact data exists on littering by vessels in the North and Baltic Seas. Monitoring both polluting incidents and environmental consequences are thus seen as the main priority by OSPAR (OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.94). Johnson could demonstrate that in some areas, the larger part of waste littering beaches is coming from passing vessels rather than land-based sources (Johnson, 2002). According to Hastings and Potts, detrimental effects on animal life include entanglement and ingestion, reduced reproduction, reduced quality of life and lastly death (Hastings and Potts, 2013, p.50). Plastics form a major problem of ocean dumping. They account for around 80% of all marine litter (Trouwborst, 2011, p.6) and make up 50-80% of waste washing ashore (Barnes et al., 2009). No data exists on the share of plastics products stemming from accidental or deliberate losses by ships (Jambeck et al., 2015, p.770).

2.4.2.4 Air pollution

Air pollution is defined here as all combustion products from engine fuel emitted during a vessel’s operation. The most relevant types are carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen oxide air pollutants NO and NO₂ (NO_x), sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and particulate matter (PM), as shown in Table 2-3. Compared to other industry sectors, the global emission share of shipping operations is negligible. Although atmospheric sources account for some 33% of overall marine pollution, most emissions originate on land. CO₂, the most relevant ship-source emission, was reaching not more than 3.3% of total global emanation in 2007. However, the shipping sector accounts for a fast growth in emissions with CO₂ emanation forecasted to rise by 50-250% in the period up to 2050 in the absence of policy (IMO, 2014b, p.34). These forecasts contradict plans by the IMO to decrease CO₂ emissions from shipping by 50% by 2050, making strict legislation on this pollutant likely. (IMO, 2018a) Emissions of sulphur dioxide were rising in two sectors only between 1970 and 2005: energy and international shipping. NO_x, SO₂ and PM emanation is expected to rise by 40-50% until 2020 (AirClim, 2011, p.1108, Smith et al., 2011) .

Exhaust gas	International shipping in European waters in	International shipping in international	Expected growth in the absence of policy
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⁴ 151 Congressional Record, S1261-02, S1295-S1296 (10 February 2005); cited in (Dautel, 2010, p.181)

	2000 (million t/year)	waters in 2007 (million t/year)	
CO ₂	/	870-1.000	50-250% by 2050
SO ₂	2.3	/	40% by 2020
NO _x	3.3	/	45% by 2020
PM	0,25	/	55% by 2020

Table 2-3: Exhaust gas pollution in European and international waters (OSPAR Commission, 2010, Wagner et al., 2010, AirClim, 2011, IMO, 2014b)

Scientists largely agree on the negative effects of air pollution on human, animal and plant life and health. SO₂ emissions have been shown to be the main contributor to acid rain (Tan, 2006, p.156). Furthermore, atmospheric emissions by shipping are suspected to lead to climate change, damage to the marine and other ecosystems and subsequently to social welfare loss and environmental costs (see Figure 2-4). Technical options to reduce vessel-source emissions are currently available and are constantly developed and improved. Control technologies for maritime shipping include scrubbing and efficiency improvements to control SO₂, filters and catalysts to decrease PM emissions, a large variety of pre-combustion, in-engine and post-engine control-technologies like fuel water emulsification and injection timing delay to decrease levels of NO_x and changes to the vessel design that will decrease CO₂ emissions (Winebrake et al., 2008, Endresen et al., 2010). Such technical possibilities are not available or financially feasible for all vessel types, but significant environmental improvements may be expected in the decades to come.

Figure 2-4: Vessel-source air pollution, adapted from the Second IMO GHG Study (IMO, 2009, p.113), © 2009 IMO. Reprinted with the permission of the IMO

Marginal air pollution costs of maritime transport are given in the European Commission's Handbook on the External Costs of Transport (Ricardo-AEA, 2014, p.48). Container ships and RoRo vessels were not included in the study. It becomes evident that damages for vessels travelling the North Sea are higher than for vessels travelling the Baltic Sea. Damage costs include health effects, corresponding to more than 90% of external effects, but also damages to buildings, biodiversity and crops. They are correlated with average population exposure to pollutants. Costs for certain ship types when active in the North and Baltic Sea areas are shown in Table 2-4.

Type of ship	Average load/tonnes	Marginal air pollution costs, € per 1,000 tkm	
		Baltic Sea	North Sea
Crude oil tanker 0-10 kt	1,761	8.70	11.81
Crude oil tanker 10-60 kt	18,413	26.78	36.55
Crude oil tanker 80-120 kt	49,633	46.93	63.98
General cargo 0-5 kt	1,527	3.92	5.33
General cargo 5-10 kt	4,274	12.09	16.46
Bulk carrier (feeder)	1,440	6.78	9.23
Bulk carrier (handysize)	14,300	19.86	27.06
Bulk carrier (handymax)	24,750	25.03	34.14

Table 2-4: Marginal air pollution costs for maritime transport on the North and Baltic Sea, average values, € per 1,000 tkm (adapted from Ricardo-AEA, 2014, p.48)

2.4.2.5 Ballast water

Ballast water is taken on to stabilize vessels especially when unladen. Discharges of ballast water have become the most critical means of introducing harmful biological material into marine ecosystems. However, non-native species may also be introduced clinging to the vessel's external or internal structures (Tanaka, 2012, p.258). In terms of definition, a difference must be made between non-indigenous species [hereinafter NIS], referring to organisms introduced into waters outside their historical population and invasive alien species [hereinafter IAS] which are known or believed to pose a threat to ecosystem services (European Commission, 2016a, 2016b). In a 2010 census on future challenges to the marine environment, NIS were named as one of the major threats to marine biodiversity (Costello et al., 2010). Similar to other types of pollution, available statistics vary significantly, and reliable data seems to be hard to come by. Recent studies suggest that daily, more than 10,000 non-native species are transported in the ballast water of trading vessels around the globe. Some 3,000 to 4,000 tons of untreated water are discharged in foreign ports and coastal regions every year (Sündermann, 2007, EMSA, 2008, Kettunen et al., 2008). Gollasch recorded more than 1,000 NIS in coastal European waters (Gollasch, 2006). 160 have been identified in the OSPAR region (OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.98). 118 NIS have been observed in the Baltic Sea with the highest numbers found alongside busy shipping lanes like the area around the Great Belt in Denmark (HELCOM, 2012). In comparison, 986 were totalled for the Mediterranean Sea (Zenetos, Ballesteros and Verlaque, 2012, p.328), a water much more frequented by vessels passing through from all over the globe. This data shows that shipping is the greatest contributor to NIS in European waters, introducing an estimated 49% of all foreign species into the seas

(HELCOM, 2012). Overall, numbers of NIS are steadily increasing which might be due to increased vessel speeds giving species better chances of survival, increased numbers and sizes of ships as well as separate ballast water tanks where species travel in a rather clean environment (HELCOM, 2012). Not all NIS pose a threat to their new habitats, but some 10-15% of introduced species experience exponential growth and pose a danger to regional biodiversity as well as human, animal and plant life and health (Sündermann, 2007, EMSA, 2008, Kettunen et al., 2008, European Commission, 2014). Possibilities to control bio-invasions include banning all ballast water imports by making ballast water exchange at sea mandatory or risk-assessed approaches as suggested by Hewitt et al. (Hewitt and Hayes, 2002, p.456).

2.4.2.6 Toxic anti-fouling systems

Anti-fouling systems are toxic protective underwater hull coatings. They have traditionally been applied to hinder the growth of marine organisms on the vessel's outer surface. Up until 2008 they were legally allowed to contain organotin compounds known as tributyl tin [hereinafter TBT] that have been described as "the most toxic compounds ever deliberately introduced by societies into natural waters." (Goldberg, 1986). TBT gradually leaches lethal substances into the seawater by a process called hydrolysis. Barnacles, shellfish and algae attempting to cling to the ship are thus killed and the ship's surface is kept clean and smooth. This prevents a process called 'biofouling', by which aquatic species may be transported on the ship's hull. While legislation prohibiting TBT has been passed, it still remains the most widely used substance until today. Also, it seems to be the most effective (Tanaka, 2012, p.258). While wiping out marine life, TBT also ensures continuous vessel speed and fuel efficiency (Tan, 2006, p.162, Tanaka, 2012, p.258). Currently, the toxicity of anti-fouling paint leads to environmental damages, while the abstention from usage would lead to environmental damages via increased fuel use and the introduction of NIS (See Figure 2-5). In light of the benefits of anti-fouling systems, there seem to be few alternatives but to protect the hull from marine organisms. Environmental potential must lie in the development of systems that pose less harm to the environment. An overview of possible systems and their linked environmental impact can be found with Dafforn et al. (Dafforn, Lewis and Johnston, 2011). According to research of Karlsson and Eklund, however, new hull coatings on the market do not prove to be much less toxic than TBT (Karlsson and Eklund, 2004). Abbott et al. similarly argue that the full prohibition of TBT does not necessarily lead to an improved environmental situation and that finding effective substitutes is a challenging process (Abbott et al., 2000).

Figure 2-5: Benefits and disadvantages of anti-fouling systems

2.4.2.7 Noise pollution

Noise can be defined as sound that produces undesirable effects (Cone and Hayes, 1980, p.89). The term itself anticipates negative consequences on the marine environment and goes in line with the legal definition of pollution employed here. Scientific discussions are in progress on the technical characteristics of what constitutes noise, i.e. frequency, amplitude, complexion and duration of sound. A number of scientists have shown that normal shipping operations lead to underwater radiated noise (Ross, 1976, McKenna et al., 2012). The shipping sector is characterised by both high-intensity short-duration noise as well as chronic low-frequency noise close to large shipping lanes. Noise pollution is specifically addressed in the EU's Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC (EP, 2008). According to Article 3 (8) pollution is "including human-induced marine underwater noise". Sounds that are carried above the ocean surface do thus not constitute noise pollution in the legal sense.

A number of scientific studies have aimed at measuring vessel-source noise (McCarthy, 2004). The first landmark-studies to examine natural sounds resulting from wind, rain, ice, seismic activities and marine mammals in the oceans were conducted by Knudsen in 1944 and Wenz in 1962 (Knudsen, 1944, Wenz, 1962). They were followed by studies focusing on anthropogenic sources (Richardson and Thomson, 1995). According to these studies, super-tankers and large container vessels produce low frequency noise between 2 and 500 Hz, which can be heard in up to 500 kilometres distance (Schachten, 2011, p.67). Depending on ship type a number of studies found vessel-induced noise levels between 140 and 200 dB (Hatch et al., 2008, Hildebrand, 2009, p.9, Schachten, 2011, p.67). Baleen whales use about the same frequencies to communicate. Recent research suggests that shipping is by far the main source of underwater noise from anthropogenic sources at low frequencies, especially in coastal zones (Dotinga and Elferink, 2000, p.153, Andrew et al., 2002, Hatch et al., 2008, p.746, Hildebrand, 2009, p.9, OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.98). The noise of a ship generally increases with loading capacity, speed, weight and age (Hildebrand, 2009, p.10, Schachten, 2011, p.67), but is also highly dependent on factors that are far more difficult to control, like water depth (McCarthy, 2004, p.37). Areas particularly prone to vessel-source undersea noise are the busy shipping lanes in the Northern Hemisphere, as well as regions where particularly noisy vessels like hovercraft and ice-breakers operate (Scott, 2004, p.2). According to the OSPAR Quality Status Report 2010, noise has doubled every ten years in some sea areas since the 1950s. Shipping is

named as the main contributor to this development (OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.98). Other researchers claim that the idea that noise by ships has increased seems to make sense given increased volumes of trade, but has not been proven scientifically (McCarthy, 2004, p.37). A recent study by Veirs et al. shows that half of the noise emissions stem from just 15% of the vessel fleet, meaning that improvements in certain types of vessels might lead to significant decreases of underwater noise (Veirs et al., 2018). The effects of noise from oceangoing vessels on the marine environment has not been sufficiently studied. Research by Rolland et al. shows that underwater noise from vessels leads to increased stress for baleen whales (Rolland et al., 2012). Research by Vazzana, Celi and others shows that even short-term exposure to noisy environments elicits stress responses in some aquatic species (Vazzana et al., 2017, similar studies for other marine species conducted by the same group of researchers). A Dutch group of researchers found, however, that offshore wind parks, also producing underwater noise, while being avoided by some species of marine mammals, fish and birds, were being sought and used for shelter by other types of marine animals, leading to an increase in biodiversity in the region (Lindeboom et al., 2011). The Handbook on External Costs of Transport used by the European Commission concludes that costs of noise pollution are “no major issue” (Ricardo-AEA, 2014, p.6). Research on underwater vessel-borne noise is so far inconclusive and the effects of underwater noise from vessels on the marine environment need to be studied further.

2.4.3 Why is there pollution? – The problem of market failure

*What is common to many is taken least care of,
For all men have greater regard for what is their own
Than for what they possess in common with others.
Aristotle*

Under optimal conditions markets should not need government intervention. The rules of supply and demand should induce prices to arrive at the optimum level maximising societal welfare. Adam Smith has termed this mechanism the “invisible hand” of the market (Adam Smith, *The wealth of nations*, 1776). Contradicting this theory, it has been seen in numerous settings that government inaction will lead to excessive pollution. When free market forces are unable to optimise societal welfare, we speak of market failure. Markets seem in many cases unable to respond appropriately to environmental overuse. Environmental damage can be explained by making use of the theory of common goods as well as the theory of externalities as explained below. Both approaches are related to each other. Inefficient resource allocation is usually aggravated by a third market failure, namely imperfect information (For a thorough discussion of the three see Callan and Thomas, 2012, p. 53 et sqq).

A clean environment is a scarce good. It is also a common resource, as it is non-excludable. It is difficult to inhibit society from breathing the air or swimming in the ocean. It is also rival in its use. Use by one person may reduce the value of the good to other people (Taylor and Mankiw, 2014, p.230). As for all common goods, market forces struggle to achieve an efficient equilibrium. Without intervention, the environment is used more than it should be. This is a classic economic problem first studied by William Forster Lloyd in 1933 and termed the Tragedy of the Commons (Lloyd, 1833). Said tragedy generally applies to transport services,

where prices normally fail to capture the full costs to society from environmental damage. If costs of an economic activity are incurred by society outside of the core business transaction this is called a negative externality (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p. 61). The spill over effect will not be covered by the commodity price and a misallocation of resources occurs. Transport services are offered in excess of what is best for all. Callan proposes that the environmental damage caused by shipping could in itself be called a public good (or public bad) as it is indivisible, and no one may exclude himself from lower air and water quality (For this challenging perspective on externalities see Callan and Thomas, 2012, p. 63). The welfare loss associated with excess levels of pollution by shipping can be seen in the model depicted in Figure 2-6.

Figure 2-6: Welfare effects of vessel-source pollution (model based on Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.66), Used with permission of Cengage. Permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc.

It is assumed that the shipping market is competitive and full information is available to all market actors. In the model, internal costs of production and internal benefits of consumption are compared with external costs of production or externalities. The supply and demand curves are thus termed marginal private costs (MPC) and marginal private benefits (MPB). In an undisturbed market, the price will arrive at the market equilibrium of P_{ME} with the quantity of Q_{ME} being produced where $MPB = MPC$ as shown in Figure 2-6. This market equilibrium does not constitute an efficient outcome, as externalities are not taken into account.

It is assumed that vessel-source pollution increases at a constant rate with the amount of goods being shipped. These costs are termed marginal external costs (MEC). Economies of scale are thus not considered in this model. To establish allocative efficiency the full costs of production

must be considered. The efficient equilibrium can be found at the intersection of MPB and (MPC+MEC), termed the full cost curve (FC). The costs of pollution may thus be defined as: $C_p = FC - MPC$. At the efficient equilibrium the price of shipping goods P_{EE} will be higher than before and the quantity Q_{EE} will be lower than in a free market situation. Society will gain more from protecting the scarce resources of clean air and water than it was gaining by additional goods being transported. Shipping companies will lose profit but will overall lose less than society is gaining.

The welfare loss in the absence of legislation and the costs of pollution to society can be seen in Figure 2-6. The red-coloured triangle between the straight lines shows the loss of welfare without political interference, the difference between the lines shows the costs of pollution to society for any given amount of goods transported. Putting a number on the size of externalities that equals the amount of damage caused is very difficult, however (compare Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.65). Shipping companies would tend to exaggerate the benefits from making free use of the environment for their transport activities, while victims of pollution might exaggerate the costs that said activities bring with them. Simple questionnaires will thus not lead to reliable results. Contingent Valuation Methods may be used (see the seminal work by Hanemann, 1994 for a description of this method, see Venkatachalam, 2004 for a discussion of its strength and shortcomings, compare Taylor and Mankiw, 2014, p.226 for a practical application) and a number of researchers have tried to put a value on a clean environment (on the value of clean water see Carson and Mitchell, 1993, on the value of nature see Daily et al., 2000, for a meta-analysis on the value of a statistical human life see Mrozek and Taylor, 2002, on the value of aquatic ecosystems Barbier, 2017), but no data exists on the value of cleaner water and air in the North and Baltic Sea areas and coastal regions. Only the mechanism is clear. A common resource, the waters of the North and Baltic Seas, is degraded by shipping companies to their own benefit and that of consumers (compare Tsimplis, 2011, p.422). The existence of externalities calls for political intervention. As the environment is not put to its most valuable use when transports are not being priced sufficiently, it is the role of politicians to influence market actors and change consumer behaviour (see Callan and Thomas, 2012, p. 69). Products may be consumed in excess where prices do not reflect the real costs to society. The model shown in Figure 2-6 supports one more important argument. An efficient equilibrium will often not be found at a point where pollution equals zero. More often, a reduction of pollution will be desirable, but only until a certain limit is reached. From there a further reduction would decrease overall welfare. For the purpose of this study it will be assumed that externalities exist without aiming to measure their exact value. In the Update of the Handbook of External Costs of Transport commissioned by the European Commission, it is recommended to base cost-benefit considerations on the central value of a statistical life for an adult in the EU, corresponding to €1,650,000 in 2010 prices (Ricardo-AEA, 2014, p.34). The same study finds, however, that effects of ship emissions, for example from vessel-source air pollution, are “difficult to allocate” (Ricardo-AEA, 2014, p.6), making a monetary evaluation of all external effects of maritime shipping extremely difficult. The question posed here is not whether environmental legislation is beneficial to society – it is assumed that it is – but how it affects market actors, whether some market actors are more affected than others and whether deviant behaviour may significantly influence economic models. Costs of political decision-making are not considered.

2.4.4 Bounded rationality and vessel-source emissions as a complex system

While the theory of common resources and externalities is straightforward, a practical application of the concepts is hard to achieve. This is not only due to the difficulties in measuring costs of pollution as stated above, but also due to the complex anthropogenic and ecological interactions underlying environmental pollution. Following a term coined by Rittel and Webber in 1973, Shortle and Horan call the pollution of global aquatic systems “a wicked problem.” (Rittel and Webber, 1973, Shortle and Horan, 2016). The researchers argue that all ten properties of a wicked problem are fulfilled when nutrients are introduced into rivers and seas and that designing and choosing appropriate economic instruments is thus extremely challenging. For example, a definite formulation of the problem of vessel-source emissions is lacking. Also, a solution to the problem may not be immediately or ultimately tested. Furthermore, there exists no exhaustively describable set of potential solutions and there is no opportunity to learn by trial and error. (for further properties see Rittel and Webber, 1973). What Rittel and Webber call a wicked problem, other researchers simply term a complex system (Simon, 1997). Simon states that particularly with public policy questions like air quality or environmental quality, “‘hard’ science and the behavioural sciences are inextricably intertwined, and the ‘softness’ of all the sciences, including the ‘hardest,’ becomes eminently clear” (Simon, 1997, p.6). For the study of complex systems, he calls for decomposing them into smaller models of causality. The characteristics of complex systems make it near impossible to analyse an issue in all its complexity but makes it necessary to focus on certain defined aspects of the problem. This approach is followed here, where only selected aspects of vessel-source emission abatement costs are discussed.

An important issue that is linked to complex problems is that the actors themselves, both within society and the shipping industry respectively, make decisions under constraints of knowledge, resources, and time, also defined as bounded rationality. A paper by Arthur on bounded rationality suggests that where decision-makers lack information, they will decide inductively, rather than deductively, relying on own past experiences. By this behaviour, the premises under which people make decisions will decide the outcome of said decision (Arthur, 1994, p.406). If for example a shipping company has not experienced any harbour state controls in recent years (and rarely heard about them from partner companies), they are likely to base their decisions of legal compliance on their perception of a low risk of controls.

2.4.5 Summary

This thesis deals with pollution. A challenge lies with fundamental differences in scientific and economic definitions of pollution on the one side and the legal definition of pollution on the other. Scientifically, all losses in ecosystem services, however negligible, are termed as pollution. As a loss in ecosystem services can be seen as equivalent to a loss in societal welfare, this conforms with the economic definition. In the legal sphere, a certain threshold of harm needs to be reached to satisfy the definition. Cost effects occur when shipping companies change their behaviour, which they are most likely to do if legislation mandates them to. It can be assumed that cost effects from environmental legislation occur where pollution happens in the legal sense and the threshold-of-harm-argument is satisfied. Pollution from commercial

freight shipping has been organised by source of pollution, with seven sources currently playing a role.

Looking at environmental effects, oily water pollution seems to be linked to the largest immediately measurable negative effects to the marine environment. Consequences of air pollution are severe, but difficult to attribute to the original source, making a comparison with other pollutants very difficult. Research on noise pollution is still in its infancy and current publications are largely contradicting each other. Sewage water can be assimilated by the marine environment to some extent, making the problem one of secondary priority and mostly of a regional scope. Waste pollution seems to be an ever-existing challenge for Baltic Sea and North Sea coastal states. Ballast water has long been neglected in policy making as a relevant source of marine pollution, but with increased monitoring of waters more and more invasive alien species are identified and the negative effects they pose on the marine environment become apparent. Anti-fouling systems are based less on TBT, but researchers argue that no other solution has proved equally effective as the now illegal substance. No comprehensive study on the overall environmental effect of commercial sea-borne trade could be identified, making this an important demand for future research. Excessive levels of pollution are an effect of market failure where the Tragedy of the Commons applies. Political intervention is called for to internalise external effects. Operational ship-source pollution is, however, a complex environmental problem not only due to the various sources of pollution and their diverse, interrelated, and poorly understood environmental effects, but also due the complexity of human conduct and environmental responses. Bounded rationality adds to the challenge of effectively regulating the industry.

2.5 A theory of incentives to discourage pollution

2.5.1 Introduction

*“Planning problems are inherently wicked. [...] ...the problems of governmental planning – and especially those of [...] policy planning – are ill-defined and they rely upon elusive political judgement for resolution (Not “solution”. Societal problems are never solved. At best they are only re-solved. Over and over again).
(Rittel and Webber, 1973, p.160)*

In the following chapter, incentives to discourage pollution will be discussed. Considerations from economic theory on how to assign environmental property rights are followed by a short excursion on how not only formal, but also informal institutions may serve to discourage pollution. A discussion of legal options of pollution abatement is conducted, comparing their economic effect as well as benefits and drawbacks of different methods. The theory of full costs and the cheapest polluter avoider are reviewed, followed by a discussion of the current legal framework to control vessel-source emissions in the North and Baltic Sea.

2.5.2 A theory of incentives

This work is developed upon the assumption that humans are rational maximisers of their utility⁵. Rational choice theory may be applied to all kinds of human behaviour, including choices made in face of the law. Applying rational choice theory implies that people respond to legal incentives (described by Taylor and Mankiw, 2014, p.187 as one of the Ten Principles of Economics). A change in the legal environment that increases an individual's utility or company's profit by changing their behaviour would incentivise them to do so. This assumption is of crucial importance for the research at hand, because assuming irrational behaviour would make it difficult to systematically study the effect of a legal rule on society⁶. Furthermore, it is assumed that an increase in the costs of shipping transport will lead to a lower demand for said transport. This is the so-called Law of Demand. Consumers might substitute goods shipped from afar by local produce or transport volumes might shift to other modes like truck or railway. A rational actor bases his decisions on expectations of the future (Posner, 2014, p. 8), thus the expectation that a law will change will already influence actors in their business decisions similar to an actual legal change. A discussion of how incentives should be structured to best control vessel-source pollution can be found below.

Designing incentives to influence economic agents has developed into a key area of interest for economists during the course of the last 30 years (Laffont and Martimort, 2009, p.1). There are several strands of incentive theory. A recent area of research stands in the tradition of rational choice theory, but is specifically interested in the actors within an organisation and how they may be influenced to exhibit a certain behaviour, rather than thinking of the organisation as a black box (Lohmann and Lohmann, 2001, p.78). Researchers linking incentives with organisational theory often employ principal-agent models (Laffont and Martimort, 2009). In the context of environmental legislation, the theory of incentives deals with influencing economic actors with the aim of overcoming externalities and increasing societal welfare. Mankiw argues that unintended consequences of legislation occur where policy makers fail to understand how their policies affect behaviour (Mankiw, 2017, p.7). Learning from organisational theory, principal-agent models may also prove helpful in the context of environmental laws, when the environmental authority is seen as the principal and the polluting industry as the agents (Conrad and Wang, 2012, p.69). Principal-agent models can serve to determine the cost-effectiveness of environmental policy instruments. One of the fundamental works in this field was published by Dasgupta, Hammond and Maskin in 1980 and bears the title 'On imperfect information and optimal pollution control'. The researchers base their argument on the fact that legislators have only limited information about the cost functions of polluters and have to establish legal rules under uncertainty (Dasgupta, Hammond and Maskin,

⁵ Rational choice theory is challenged by cognitive psychologists (Kahneman, 2011), who can present evidence for humans being systematically irrational in their behaviour. Especially when dealing with low-probability events, like the probability of measurable effects on health caused by ship traffic, people do not behave rationally. In the present case, however, the nation states have taken it upon themselves to protect the health of their population and are acting in their stead. It has to be noted though that political aims are not necessarily equal to maximising society's utility.

⁶ This position has been challenged by a new branch of economists employing learnings on human psychology and behaviour to build new, more sophisticated models on how humans react to incentives. This field of study called 'behavioural law and economics' is described by Marciago, 2010, part 2: 'Beyond economic analysis of law'.

1980). For a further discussion of information asymmetries between companies and legislators and the implications for policy-making see Weitzman (Weitzman, 1974). The theory of Dasgupta et al. applied to this research context in the following:

We have n shipping companies ($i = 1, \dots, n$) with a cost function of $C(e_i, \theta_i)$ where e_i are the emissions of an individual company and θ_i are the individual abatement costs, which are known to the company, but not the regulator. The social damage caused by all pollution $e = \sum_i e_i$ is denoted as $D(e)$. It is assumed that the legislator is able to monitor emission levels e and that it would thus be possible for him to minimise the sum of damages and total costs, if θ_i were known to him, following the function

$$\min_{e_i} D_{e_i} + \sum_{i=1}^n C(e_i, \theta_i) \quad (1)$$

In practice, however, legislators have limited information on emissions caused by shipping, let alone the associated damages, as well as abatement costs of shipping companies. Designing effective incentives is thus a great challenge even if companies are in fact behaving rationally in the face of the law.

2.5.3 Assignment of the right to pollute – The Coase Theorem

The Baltic and North Sea areas being a common resource and vessel-source pollution being an external effect of transport services, a market failure exists. Economists have argued since the publications of Nobel prize laureate Ronald Coase in 1960 that under optimal circumstances inefficiencies may be solved without government intervention, but by way of negotiating between the parties. This requires first of all allocating property rights to the common resources. If no one owns our air and water, there may consequently be no market for both these goods. Callan and Thomas claim that “property rights are critically important to the sound functioning of the market system” (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.69). The right to the marine environment may either be allocated to households or (shipping) companies. Developed by Pigou in 1920 (Pigou, 1932) and still the pillar of all environmental policy making is the polluter-pays-principle. This principle is strongly supported by OECD and European Union countries and has been incorporated into EU law by way of Directive 2004/35/CE, Article 8, stating that the “operator shall bear the costs for [...] preventive and remedial actions” of pollution he has caused or will cause in the future. In other words, households shall always be allocated the right to zero pollution and where companies wish to pollute the environment, they have to negotiate with households to accept a certain level of pollution in exchange for transfer payments (Phaneuf and Requate, 2017, p.39). The total costs of vessel-source pollution to the company $TC(VP)$ consists of abatement costs $AC(P)$, which are fully incurred by the firm as well as damages $D(VP)$ payed to the households and lastly transaction costs tr for negotiating with households. In this scenario, all actors have full information about technological developments and their own preferences.

$$TC(VP) = AC(VP) + D(VP) + tr \quad (2)$$

If the transfer payment ϕ is equal to or larger than the damages, that is if $\phi \geq D(VP)$, the household will accept the proposal and the company may pollute. Importantly, however,

Phaneuf and Requate point out that this outcome may only be achieved where transaction costs do not exceed the gains from negotiation (Phaneuf and Requate, 2017, p.40).

$$tr \leq AC(0) - [AC(VP^*) + D(VP^*)] \quad (3)$$

This relation must hold where the gains from negotiation are defined as the difference between costs to society if pollution from companies is zero, and costs to society if pollution is optimal at VP^* . The polluter-pays-principle may only be put into practice where two prerequisites are met: The identity of the polluter needs to be established without doubt and the costs of pollution need to be identified. Both will prove difficult in practice and a third problem may arise, where agreement has to be reached whether externalities shall be fully internalised (Morin and Orsini, 2014, p.156). In a situation where countries compete against each other for offering a competitive business environment to globally active companies, a full internalisation of externalities is often not politically feasible.

The Nobel prize laureate Ronald Coase stated that assigning property rights alone can solve the market failure of externalities. He also argued that the initial assignment of the right to pollute will not affect the ultimate use of the environment, given that transaction costs are zero (compare R.H. Coase, 1960). This claim is called the Coase Theorem. Coase proposes that no matter how property rights are assigned, they allow for bargaining between the parties and eventually lead to an efficient resource allocation. Property rights need not necessarily be allocated to the households but may just as well be allocated to the companies. In both cases the output level in Figure 2-6 will move from Q_{ME} to Q_{EE} and the price from P_{ME} to P_{EE} , when bargaining between the parties becomes possible. This way the environment will be put to its most productive use. If companies are endowed with pollution rights, households will have to offer compensation for reduced pollution and make transfer payments of amount ϕ . The utility of households will be maximised if

$$\max_{VP} \{y - (D(VP) + AC(VP) + tr)\}. \quad (4)$$

This outcome is again depending on the prerequisite that transaction costs are smaller than potential negotiation gains

$$tr \leq D(\widehat{VP}) - [D(VP^*) + AC(VP^*)] \quad (5)$$

with \widehat{VP} being the initial level of vessel-source emissions. As can be seen, the same social optimum will be reached in both cases, irrespective of the allocation of rights to households or shipping companies. That is at least the theoretical outcome of Coase's theory. His predictions are, however, based on two assumptions that make the model little applicable in reality. Coase's theory only works with limited transaction costs, a demand that presumes very few actors to be present in the market. In the case at hand, every person breathing air, using water and consuming traded goods, as well as operating vessels is a market actor. Unfortunately, the transaction costs of literally the entire population coming together to bargain are prohibitive. Mankiw and Taylor term this barrier "Coordinating Interested Parties" (Taylor and Mankiw, 2014, p.246). Secondly, Coase assumes that the value of damages is measurable. As the way in which vessels influence the environment is still a puzzle to scientists and attempts to measure the value of a

clean environment have proven futile, this assumption is far from the world as it is. A third problem occurs as private bargaining on the issue of environmental protection is prone to free riders (Compare Taylor and Mankiw, 2014, p. 246). When one group of citizens pays a shipowner to install a scrubber, not only that group is benefitting from cleaner air, but the wider population in the coastal regions of several countries. There is thus little incentive for a small group to enter into bargaining if many others benefit without contributing. The Coase Theorem is a very informative concept and should be kept in mind when further discussing incentives to discourage pollution, but may by and large not be applicable to environmental economics in shipping. When the entire population is concerned, private solutions may not be feasible. It is the role of the government to represent its people in such a case and take collective action.

Coase was concerned not only with reaching an efficient outcome, but also with a fair distribution of the benefits created. According to Coase, the distribution of wealth, not the allocation of resources, is a matter for public policy. If the economic activity of transporting goods has a higher value for society than mitigating the health risks caused by passing ships, than the goods will keep being transported and they should be. Public policy should concern itself, however, with a better distribution of wealth from the ones benefitting from transported goods to the one suffering from vessel emissions. It might well be, however, that the ones benefitting, and suffering are one and the same – any number of consumers living in proximity to the oceans and consuming imported products. This is a problem that Coase has not considered in his theoretical discussions.

2.5.4 Theory of formal and informal institutions to discourage pollution

Institutions have been defined by Douglass North, Nobel laureate in economics, as “the humanly devised constraints that structure human interaction” (North, 1994, p.360). Formal institutions that govern individual and company behaviour comprise laws, regulations and rules. The concept of informal institutions describes norms, cultures and ethics (Peng, 2017, p.37). This study is focused on formal institutions in the form of maritime environmental laws, but the researcher recognises that informal institutions may influence behaviour, especially compliance with the laws, as well. Peng argues that the coercive power of governments is influenced both by normative influences (behaviour of the group influencing the individual firm) and cognitive influences in the form of internal values and beliefs of decision-makers that guide company behaviour (Peng, 2017, p.37 et sqq).

In this work, perceptions of shipping experts as well as actual behaviour by shipping companies is measured. Influences by formal and informal institutions in relation to the behavioural effects that become noticeable are not distinguished. It is assumed, however, that informal institutions remain more stable over time and that sudden changes in behaviour are more likely to stem from changes in formal institutions. Also, policy makers will find it much harder to influence informal institutions. This research focuses on extracting sound policy advice from the observance of the effects of changes in formal institutions.

2.5.5 Economic discussion of legal options to discourage pollution

Discouraging pollution may be attempted in many ways. Public policies to internalise externalities are usually organised into the two categories of command-and-control and market-based policies (Mankiw, 2017, p.195). The most notable command-and-control mechanisms are introducing respective rules of liability or passing regulations mandating the polluter to change his conduct. These might be supplemented by measures of strategic information (For a discussion on the economic effects of information see Foulon et al., 1999). Traditional economists would argue that where the expected costs are the same, behaviour should be affected in the same way (Find a critique of this position by behavioural economists in Jolls, 2010). However, in the present case of environmental harm caused by operational shipping activities, regulations have several advantages over liability rules as shown in Table 2-5.

Rules of liability	Regulations
Enforced by individuals	Enforced by government agencies
<i>Ex post</i> approach	<i>Ex ante</i> approach
Advisable for rare occurrences of great harm	Advisable for common occurrences of little or moderate harm

Table 2-5: Rules of liability vs. regulations

Liability rules are aimed at deterring a polluter from harmful conduct and can be achieved either by implementing negligence or using strict rules of liability. Negligence describes an injury “caused by the failure to use reasonable care”. Under strict liability companies will be liable “even if they did not intend the harm and used reasonable care to try to prevent it” (Statsky, 2011, p.112). Theoretically, strict liability should achieve better results and empirical research has shown that in fact, pollution can be decreased by strict liability rules. Studies have shown, however, that in countries that apply strict liability rather than negligence, companies tend to organise into smaller production units in order to make strategic use of insolvency. Firms will rather invest in limiting the assets they expose to liability than invest in pollution control (Martin, Li and Qin, 2012). Liability rules are specifically unsuited for vessel-source emissions, as shown in empirical research by Hendrickx, who finds that when stricter rules of liability were applied in the case of oil spills, the polluters could not be identified for a higher proportion of spills. The research comes to the conclusion that under rules of liability, shipowners rather improve their skills in concealing their identity, than investing in environmental compliance (Hendrickx, 2007). Liability rules prove inadequate in the case of vessel-source emissions.

As regards the benefits of regulation over liability, firstly, laws are enforced by government agencies rather than individuals. This is important, as the individual harm will generally be lower than litigation costs when bringing a lawsuit. The majority of the population would thus decide against suing shipping companies, resulting in inadequate enforcement. For enforcing regulations, a government agency is set up with the aim of protecting the population from harm. The agency will generally be better informed about pollution by ships and thus in a better place to act. This argument might not hold true, however, if the respective agency is seriously underfunded or is not given enough legislative power to find and fine polluters. A second argument for regulation is that it follows an *ex ante*-approach. The shipowner is mandated to change his behaviour before harm has occurred. This approach is very much in line with shifting

policy concerns away from reactive methods towards the prevention of harm (Bell, McGillivray and Pedersen, 2013, p.31). The costs of regulating (time and money the legislature, judiciary and executive put into this effort) may be covered by the welfare gains from controlling pollution. Liability makes more sense for an activity that very rarely causes harm, but where the harm to an individual is great. Accidents, also shipping accidents, fall under this category (For a further discussion of the benefits and shortcomings of both methods see Polinsky, 2011, p. 149 et sqq.). Regulation is shown to be a more appropriate method of discouraging operational shipping pollution than litigation.

Regulations have several inherent shortcomings, however. They need to be aptly drafted to move company behaviour in the right direction. Also, they need to be fully enforced. A lack of enforcement will lead to an inadequate behavioural change. Polinsky is highly critical of regulations. He argues that as a rule they “lead to excessive participation in the harmful activity” (Polinsky, 2011, p.147), as the polluter will not be held liable for persisting harm once he has complied with the regulation. He maintains that under a regulation approach the full social costs of a good will not be reflected in its price. This position is not necessarily correct, as a regulation might well be drafted in a way as to reflect a full cost approach. One argument that is true, however, is that under a regulation approach companies are not made responsible for all the harm they cause, but solely for complying with the regulation. The risk thus lies entirely with society and with the potential victims of pollution (Polinsky, 2011, p.148).

There are basically four ways to go about regulating pollution. Firstly, there is **input control**, also called setting technology-based standards. Specific behaviour will be prescribed to legal subjects, like adopting certain technologies for pollution control. This type of regulation can for example be observed in demanding the installation of a ballast water filtering mechanism from a list of approved systems. Only the systems approved may be installed. The regulator specifies very clearly how the shipowners have to act. Politicians like these easy-to-sell, everyone-is-treated-the-same, easy-to-understand, laws. Shortcomings of setting abatement standards are discussed by Callan and Thomas. They argue that standard setting is often benefit-based, meaning that solely the increase in health and welfare is taken into account when choosing a standard, while the associated costs of the technology are not accounted for. This political mechanism may in itself lead to a wrong allocation of resources (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.87). Posner is very critical of input control as well. Even if costs and benefits are taken into account he argues that the definition of a standard is both costly and time-consuming, as it requires extensive analysis (Posner, 2014, p.505 et sqq.). Callan and Thomas maintain that imperfect information will most likely lead governments to set an inefficient abatement standard, as data necessary to conduct proper cost-benefit analysis may not be obtainable for environmental problems (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.88). Also, the industry is incentivised to propose only low-cost devices instead of costlier, but also more efficient systems. They will not attempt an improvement of current systems unless they are cheaper (compare Posner, 2014, p.505 et sqq.). Furthermore, setting an international standard might prove difficult, as regional differences in costs and benefits may not be taken into account (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.89). Lastly, “releases from polluting sources do not have a uniform impact on the environment” (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.90). As vessels are moving, their impact on ecosystems and populations varies significantly, even if emissions remain at constant levels.

Setting technology standards based on cost-benefit analysis become highly difficult, when benefits of a technology change constantly with every mile a vessel is moving away from a coast.

Output control, also called setting performance-based standards, is an alternative way to regulate industry emissions. The legislator might prescribe a maximum value of pollution allowed and might leave it to the industry to find the most efficient solution. Compared to an input control mechanism, the industry will search for and develop potent solutions at minimal costs. The benefits of output control over input control are reflected in the so-called “Porter Hypthesis”. Porter and van der Linde argue that performance-based environmental regulations can increase competitiveness as they can “trigger innovation that may partially or more than fully offset the costs of complying with them” (Porter and von der Linde, 1995, p.98). The practical applicability of this hypothesis has been questioned by other researchers, however. Jaffe and Palmer conducted a thorough panel data study and could not find any statistical evidence that would confirm the applicability of the Porter Hypothesis (Jaffe and Palmer, 1997). In any case, in order to set an ambitious pollution level that equals the actual costs to society, while not being so strict as to discourage a valuable economic activity, the legislator needs to know just as much about the industry as with input control (For problems related to output control compare Posner, 2014, p. 506). Again, imperfect information, regional differences and differing effects of the same amount of pollutants on the environment make it difficult to set the most effective standard.

A number of economists favour a third alternative which is, however, not applied in shipping law as of today: **Taxing pollution**. This approach follows the polluter-pays-principle (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.100). It proposes a Pigouvian tax following the idea that “the tax rate for each unit of pollution is set equal to the estimated social costs created by that pollution” (Posner, 2014, p. 506). The same method is explained in detail by Callan and Thomas (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.100 et sq.). One way to bring this into effect is to put a surcharge on each unit of production. The effect of such a tax is shown in Figure 2-7. The aim of the tax is to force companies to take the marginal external costs of production into account, thus the Pigouvian tax will be set at a rate to bring output from the Q_{ME} market equilibrium to the efficient equilibrium Q_{EE} .

Figure 2-7: Effect of a Pigouvian tax charged on unit of production (Author)

Pollution abatement as shown in Figure 2-7 can only be achieved by reductions in production quantity. Thus, a second alternative is proposed. Charges may also be put on quantity of emissions rather than quantity of products (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.101). The benefits are that externalities will be fully internalised, while companies will have a number of behavioural options, depending on their individual cost situation. They may continue polluting and pay the pollution tax but may also invest in abatement technologies. If the social costs of pollution are higher than the benefits of their activity, companies should be led to reduce their output or terminate their business activities altogether. Unfortunately, taxes might also induce shipowners to move their business to other countries where laws are not as strict or are not being strictly enforced. The Pigouvian tax approach seems quite attractive, as it is aimed at representing the actual costs of pollution. Also, as with output control, companies are induced to find the most efficient solutions for pollution abatement. Thirdly, taxation brings the advantage of limited administrative burdens and independence of enforcement, as direct controls of behaviour are not necessary (compare Baumol, 1972, p. 319). Still, the approach has some flaws. Firstly, the social costs of pollution are most of the time not a linear function of the amount of pollution (Posner, 2014, p. 507). In order to determine the actual function a prohibitive amount of information would be needed. Secondly, sufficient information will most likely not be available. Baumol makes a very strong case for the difficulties in applying Pigouvian taxes in his publication “On taxation and the control of externalities” stating: “We do not know how to calculate the required taxes and subsidies and we do not know how to approximate them by trial and error.” (Baumol, 1972, p.318). He proposes a way around this by choosing a level of pollution that is “considered satisfactory” (Baumol, 1972, p.318) and setting an according tax rate that will achieve that standard. His aim is not to achieve an optimum standard, but any solution satisfying an environmental minimum standard. Callan and

Thomas apply the same principle setting the abatement standard at an “acceptable level” (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.101). In view of a lack of information this seems the only workable alternative to a real Pigouvian tax. The approach is flawed, however, as a tax that differs from the Pigouvian level in being either too strict or too lax might lead to significant welfare losses.

A fourth way that liberal-minded economists are particularly fond of is creating a **market for pollution** in the form of tradable allowances. As with taxes, economic incentives are used to discourage companies from excess pollution. Externalities are thus internalised and influence company decision making. Callan and Thomas dedicate a whole chapter in their book to what they call the “market approach”, praising it above all other approaches (see Callan and Thomas, 2012, p. 98 et sqq.). Working similarly to the Pigouvian tax approach it would lead to the same outcome in a world of full information. Trade allowances start with a desired level of pollution as well, but instead of letting politicians determine the associated price – and likely deciding wrong – the market is left to establish the price level by trading allowances. Programs are often described as cap-and-trade systems, as the maximum number of allowances is fixed by the state and trading is allowed. One major benefit is that abatement is allocated to low-cost abaters (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.115). Creating a market for pollution will thus lead to particularly efficient pollution control. A thorough study on applying market-based measures for greenhouse gas mitigation on the shipping industry was conducted by Nikolakaki in 2013 (Nikolakaki, 2013). The researcher argues that a market-based approach has significant advantages over command-and-control mechanisms like input and output control. He says that a cap-and-trade system will encourage the use of the best available technology as well as compliance beyond regulatory requirements, as additional pollution abatement will benefit the shipping company (Nikolakaki, 2013, p.20). Another benefit is that the burden on legislators to be continually informed on latest technological developments, as is the case with input control, decreases (Austin, 1999). Callan and Thomas furthermore praise the flexibility of trading systems as the number of permits can easily be adjusted to meet stricter environmental goals (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.119). Not all scientists are entirely convinced of cap-and-trade systems for the shipping industry. Burtraw and Evans discuss the efficiency of an air pollution market, concluding that the specific design of the program and above all the initial allocation of rights to pollute will significantly influence the outcome (Burtraw and Evans, 2009). Another drawback are administrative costs, as both the trade of emission certificates as well as the emission of pollutants has to be registered. It might be much more practicable to prescribe the installation of a filtering mechanism for sewage water and let everyone emit as much as he likes once that system is installed, than to count every litre of water that every vessel is releasing and establish a market with permits for the release of sewage water. The same holds true for other areas of environmental policy making. Establishing a market for noise pollution seems curious at best. So far markets have mostly been created in the area of air pollution, while the author could find no examples of their existence regarding any of the other six sources of pollution shown in Figure 2-3. The danger of so-called “pollution hotspots” (Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.119) that are linked to the creation of an emissions trading system should not so much play a role in shipping, as vessels are ultimately made to move. Especially in light of the number of pollution permits to be initially offered it becomes clear that a great deal of knowledge about the industry is needed to provide for any sensible regulation of the industry.

Comparing the four approaches it becomes evident that the regulator needs to be particularly well informed in all four cases about the industry, the environment and mechanisms of human behaviour in order to develop a sound legislative framework that will increase social welfare. While clearly regulations are to be preferred over rules of liability when it comes to operational vessel-source pollution, choosing among the distinct types of regulation depends largely on the issue at hand. Cole and Grossman argue that the most efficient means of environmental protection depend on the marginal costs of pollution control, technological constraints, and existing institutions (Grossman and Cole, 1999). In their classical paper on regulating pollution under uncertainty, Roberts and Spence propose a combination of different incentives to efficiently reduce social costs (Roberts and Spence, 1976). Choosing the right method of discouraging pollution is significantly influenced by transaction costs (compare Srivastava and Batie, 2002, p.5). Transaction costs arise both on the side of legislators as well as ship operators. Governments need to gather information, legislate, monitor and enforce. With output control it might be particularly difficult to determine whether a company is complying or not, while input control is much easier to administer. Collecting information may become prohibitive in the case of pollution markets. For ship operators, information costs are significantly lower in the case of input control than output control, taxing systems or markets for pollution, as they are being precisely told how to act to be in compliance. All methods have further strengths and drawbacks, with input and output control quite easy to handle, but requiring extensive knowledge on costs and benefits by legislators. Taxing pollution can lead to optimal results if the Pigouvian tax approach is applied. As this is normally not possible due to lack of information, an inefficient result may be achieved. Pollution markets seem to guarantee the most efficient allocation of resources but are in many cases not applicable due to a prohibitive amount of administration. In any way, it will prove highly challenging to build an efficient set of laws on insufficient information about the complex and ever-changing reality of shipping.

2.5.6 Theory of full costs and the cheapest pollution avoider

“...An economic theory of law will not capture the full complexity, richness and confusion of the phenomena [...] that it seeks to illuminate.” (Posner, 2014, p. 17)

Achieving a cleaner maritime environment is high up on the political agenda. Awareness of the true environmental costs of shipping has increased, supported by environmental groups, green consumers and investors (Bell, McGillivray and Pedersen, 2013, p.39). A general problem of all four legal approaches is that the shipowner might not be the cheapest pollution avoider in all cases. A study by the Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency PBL shows that some land-based emission control measures for NO_x yield higher benefits at lower costs than measures targeted at ships (Hammingh et al., 2012, p.64). Studying all companies active in a market may show that some land-based emitters achieve a cleaner environment at lower societal costs than the shipping industry. This perspective needs to be mirrored with notions of fairness. If society perceives it as fair that all emitters should be equally targeted by legislation, irrespective of their marginal costs of pollution avoidance, it might be that the economic costs of social unrest due to perceived unfairness are higher than the potential societal benefits of targeting only those emitters that may avoid pollution at the lowest cost.

On another level, the legal options discussed may not yield optimal results if society may better mitigate the loss of ecosystem services than shipping companies. The population might in certain cases be able to protect its health at a lower cost than the shipping industry, for example by not living too close to the harbour, closing their windows at certain times, or by not swimming in certain areas. Phaneuf and Requate argue that this would change the consumer's utility maximisation function as discussed in Chapter 2.5.3. The damage function is now given by $D(VP, x)$, with x being a product or behaviour that might be purchased or employed by the population mitigating the impact of pollution and p being the price of said product or behaviour (Phaneuf and Requate, 2017, p.41). The new consumer utility maximisation function is given by:

$$\max_x \{y - (D(VP, x) + px)\} \quad (6)$$

The model shows a two-agent economy involving the choice variable x . The damage borne by the population is partially under its control. Societal costs will be minimised by the following function:

$$\min_{VP, x} \{D(VP, x) + px + AC(VP)\} \quad (7)$$

Phaneuf and Requate argue that in a setting where the polluter-pays-principle holds, there is no incentive for private households to undertake private mitigation, even if they are the lower cost pollution avoider. In an efficient situation, households should invest in mitigation so long as the incremental damage reduction does not exceed x . Full compensation by polluters will lead to inefficiently small levels of private engagement in pollution avoidance and a suboptimal solution (Phaneuf and Requate, 2017, p.42). Polinsky argues that the legislator needs to encourage a situation where both the polluter and the victim do their part in avoiding consequences of pollution. Polinsky proposes that one way to reach such an efficient outcome is by introducing a law of strict liability and adding a defence of contributory negligence (applicable when plaintiffs have contributed to the harm they suffered through their own negligence) (Polinsky, 2011, p. 111). However, as discussed above, laws of liability are of little help when the individual harm is smaller than litigation costs.

A third obstacle to optimal regulation comes into play when society both benefits and suffers from the provision of a certain product or service, like waterborne transport. Commercial shipping is responsible for a measurable amount of pollution to our air and water. One issue making legal rules for pollution control difficult is that the same people who are victims of pollution are also beneficiaries of goods transported to them. It is thus of scientific interest to weigh these costs and benefits against each other. An efficient solution can solely be reached if only people valuing the transport service more than its full costs will purchase it. Polinsky has discussed the issue of full costs and has come up with appropriate liability rules to make sure they influence human behaviour (Polinsky, 2011). The following example is meant to illustrate possible implications of the full cost effect. It is based on Polinsky's methodology:

Shipping company A has transport costs per unit of €1,000 without using low sulphur fuel and has transport costs per unit of €1,200 with using low sulphur fuel. The damage to society is €400 in the first case and €100 in the second case. However, the increase in transport costs will

lead to an increase in transport prices, a decrease in transport demand and less goods overall being transported. The damage to society of less trade is €200, as shown in Table 2-6.

Company behaviour	Production costs of company A	Damage to society by pollution	Damage to society by decrease in trade	Full costs per unit
Operate on high-sulphur fuel	€1,000	€400	€0	€1,400
Operate on low-sulphur fuel	€1,200	€100	€200	€1,500

Table 2-6: Full cost approach to environmental pollution (Author, methodology based on Polinsky, 2011)

This example serves to show how important it is to take benefits of the service provision into account, as they might entirely change the outcome of the calculation. Without looking at trade effects, the example would clearly suggest that ships operate on low-sulphur fuel. When adding trade effects, an operation on high-sulphur fuel yields more benefits for society as a whole, not just the owner/operator. The calculations by Polinsky support the argument that vessel-source emission abatement qualifies as a complex problem of policy making. Further discussions on a legislative framework based on a full costs approach can be found with Polinsky (Polinsky, 2011, p. 110 et sqq.).

Optimal regulation should take into account the most efficient pollution avoider, should encourage both polluter and victim to provide their efficient share in pollution-avoidance and should be based on a full cost approach with the aim of increasing total welfare to society. Difficulties lie in the prohibitive costs of obtaining all the information needed to model the complex interrelations between benefits from transport and costs from pollution as well as putting a prize tag on said benefits and costs. An issue not discussed by Polinsky are questions of social justice, namely how costs and benefits should be (re-)distributed among society and shipping companies once the optimal market outcome is reached. The paradigms and methods linked to the study of that field are discussed in the fundamental work on the full costs and benefits of transportation by Greene and Jones (Greene and Jones, 1997, p.3).

2.5.7 Current legal framework to discourage pollution

2.5.7.1 Three-tier system of environmental policy making

Several governmental actors are involved in environmental policy making for the Baltic and North Seas. The most influential ones are shown in Figure 2-8. A detailed map of the network of actors can be found in Annex A2. At the international level, the IMO has been established by the UN in 1959 with the aim of setting regulations for the shipping industry. In case of a dispute, countries may bring cases before the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea [hereinafter ITLOS] based in Hamburg. At the regional level, all internationally agreed laws on maritime environmental protection are transformed into binding and enforceable laws by the European Union [hereinafter EU]. This mechanism is quite intriguing in so far as the EU is not

and may not become a party to the IMO. (comp. Art. 5) Only the individual member states may become members to UN, IMO and ITLOS. UNCLOS requires states surrounding semi-enclosed seas to coordinate measures for the marine environment (Art. 122). This law is applicable to the Baltic Sea, where its demand is met by the HELCOM Commission. The North Sea as a semi-open sea (see Nihoul, 1982, p.1 for details on classification) does not have to have a coordinated approach. Still, the OSPAR Commission aims to coordinate the 15 countries bordering the North-East Atlantic (and the North Sea) towards bringing about a cleaner and healthier sea. Though the different actors endeavour to coordinate their approaches, supported by both HELCOM and OSPAR, this proves difficult at times. (on the challenges of implementing maritime environmental policy through multi-level governance see Roe, 2012, p.20 et sqq.) In certain cases, the international organisations struggle to reach a consensus on environmental questions. In these deadlock situations, regional bodies like the EU sometimes develop their own sets of laws. Regional legal endeavours will often be followed by complaints from the internationally operating shipping industry.

Figure 2-8: Network of actors in environmental policy making for the shipping industry [Detailed map in Annex A2]

UNCLOS (Pt XII) establishes a general duty on all states to protect the marine environment (on the role of UNCLOS and other framework conventions see Tsimplis, 2011, p.424). A vast amount of legislation has been passed on the international, supra-national, national and regional level to do justice to this duty. As international law usually represents the lowest common denominator, environmental shipping policy has shortcomings, is at times ill-drafted and inconsistent. Still, an international commitment to a cleaner marine environment is apparent. Regarding the laws that have been passed, the IMO has accomplished the ratification of both UNCLOS and the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships [hereinafter MARPOL] by most of its member states, as shown in Figure 2-9. UNCLOS includes a general obligation to protect the environment in Article 192, which is implemented in the annexes to MARPOL, setting out specific technical laws on environmental protection. MARPOL is supplemented by other international conventions dealing with specific issues like ballast water, anti-fouling or waste. All of these are implemented under the auspices of IMO. As mentioned before, international laws are being transformed into EU directives and regulations thus becoming binding on all EU member states. Also, regional organisations may support the implementation. At the national level, laws are being implemented by national and

local policy making and enforced by the local executive forces, specifically the harbour police. They can exercise their duty within 200 nautical miles of the shore, in the so-called Exclusive Economic Zone [hereinafter EEZ] as part of a strengthening of coastal state rights under UNCLOS Pt V.

Figure 2-9: Three-tier system of environmental policy making (Author)

At the European level, protection of marine waters is one of the aims of the EU Water Framework Directive as set down in Article 1 of the same (European Parliament and European Council, 2000a). The Directive prescribes that member states shall prevent deterioration as well as protect, enhance and restore all bodies of surface water as described in Article 4. All bodies of water, including the North and Baltic Seas, are supposed to have “good status” from 2015 onwards. As these bodies of water are shared among a number of EU member states (as well as non-members and one soon-to-be-non-member), the Directive strictly encourages cooperative approaches to protect waters from deterioration.

2.5.7.2 MARPOL as the main instrument to discourage vessel-source pollution

MARPOL is the main instrument regulating pollution from ships at an international level. It is organised according to six themes with one annex for each theme. As this work is organised by the seven sources of pollution identified above Table 2-7 shows where laws on these types of pollution can be found in the MARPOL annexes (an extensive analysis of all annexes can be found in the publication ‘MARPOL’ by Douvier, 2012). Only Annex I and II must be ratified by all IMO members. The other annexes are only binding upon ratification. Oily water, sewage, water, dumping of waste and air pollution all find their equivalent in an annex to MARPOL, while problems of ballast water, toxic hull coatings (anti-fouling) and noise pollution are not

discussed in this main legislative tool. The first two have their own legal instruments, namely the Anti-fouling Convention and the Ballast Water Management Convention. Noise pollution has not been regulated at the international level so far.

MARPOL Annexes	Seven sources of pollution
Annex I: Oil	Oily water
Annex II: Noxious Liquid Substances*	Sewage water
Annex III: Harmful substances in packaged form*	Dumping of waste
Annex IV: Sewage	Air pollution
Annex V: Garbage	Ballast water
Annex VI: Air pollution	Anti-fouling
	Noise pollution

Table 2-7: Seven sources of pollution as found in MARPOL annexes

* Regards the cargo of vessels, specifically chemical tankers (Annex II) and container carriers (Annex III), not their operation

2.5.7.3 Legislation on the seven types of pollution

At the international level, oil pollution from vessels is regulated in Annex I to MARPOL 73/78 (IMO, 1973). Said annex is binding upon all MARPOL signatories (see Annex A3 of this thesis for a list of signatories). As vessels are moving polluters, it is very difficult to inhibit illegal discharges of oily water. Legislation has thus focused on building and design criteria, which are easier to enforce. Oil pollution legislation follows an input control approach. Accidental spills are discouraged by so-called double-hull requirements, found in Regulations 19 and 20 to Annex I MARPOL and amended in 2005 and 2007 to speed up the phasing-in of double-hulls for tankers (MEPC, 2005a, 2007). Operational discharges are addressed following an output control approach set down in Regulation 9, which is prohibiting all discharges into the sea, except for minor amounts discharged far off the land and not within specially protected areas.⁷ These minor amounts shall be introduced into the sea via oil filtering equipment as set forth in Regulation 15 and 16 which makes sure the limit of 15 ppm is kept. Ideas to lower this limit to 5 ppm have so far not been implemented. Whenever oil discharges become visible on the water, the maximum standards have with certainty been breached. Oil residue (sludge) must be kept in specific tanks and brought to reception facilities in the harbour as stated in Regulation 17. Stefan Douvier discusses these laws in great detail in his book “MARPOL” (Douvier, 2012). For the Baltic and North Seas, special rules apply, as these are Special Areas as set forth in

⁷ Not exceeding 30 litres per nautical mile and 1/15,000 of total cargo for tankers and a content of oil in water of 15 parts per million for vessels above 400 tons (smaller vessels are supposed to store oily water) (see Regulation 9, Annex I MARPOL)

Regulation 10 to Annex I MARPOL and thus no discharges of oil into the sea are allowed whatsoever. Changes to MARPOL allowing the Baltic Sea to become a Special Area of oil pollution prevention were adopted as early as 1973, but only entered into force a decade later on 2 October 1983 (IMO, 2017a). Early regulation was due to the area being enclosed and thus particularly sensitive to pollution. The “North West European Waters” including the North Sea became a Special Area under Annex I in 1997 entering into force in 1999 (MEPC, 1999). In addition to this augmented level of protection, the Wadden Sea, Western European Waters, as well as the Baltic Sea Area came to be Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas [hereinafter PSSAs] under IMO auspices in 2002, 2004 and 2005 respectively – along with the Great Barrier Reef and the Galapagos Archipelago (MEPC, 2002, 2004, 2005b). Effects of this further heightened protection are a mandatory deep water route and traffic separation scheme in the Wadden Sea, a mandatory reporting systems for oil tankers of more than 600 tonnes⁸ dw carrying a cargo of heavy crude oils, heavy fuel oils or bitumen and tar in the Western European waters (including the North Sea) and traffic separation schemes as well as areas to be avoided in the Baltic Sea⁹ (IMO, 2017b). The designation of such a large PSSA was very controversial at the time and the intended purpose of this concept of increased protection is still critically discussed (Roberts et al., 2005). The underlying legal framework called “Guidelines for the Designation of PSSAs” leaves much room for political manoeuvre (IMO, 2002).

Despite a particularly strong legal framework and significant improvements in recent years, oil is still being routinely discharged into the Baltic and North Seas by vessels (Roberts, 2006, p.47, OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.95). However, positive effects are measurable. Operational oil discharges by tankers have been strictly regulated, thus only 4% of oil entering the oceans today stems from this type of vessel. Furthermore, methods of tank cleaning have developed significantly. Currently widely used, partly mandatory methods like “crude oil washing” or “load on top” have led to the virtual elimination of oil discharges during cleaning activities (Tanaka, 2012, p.257). Of those slacks detected, 80% cannot be linked to the polluter, thus the actual contribution by the shipping industry is difficult to quantify (OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.95). The challenging enforcement of oil pollution shows that while legislation is very strict, the nature of ships as a moving polluter makes the total elimination of oily water discharges even in PSSAs very difficult.

Annex IV to MARPOL regulates pollution by sewage from ships. The signature of Annex IV is optional to all contracting states. As of 10 June 2018, all 28 European member states as well as the non-EU states bordering the Baltic and North Seas, Norway and Russia, had signed the

⁸ A tonne equals 1,000 kilograms, also referred to as metric ton; a British ton equals 2,240 pounds, or 1,016.047 kilograms (not to be confused with the North American ton equaling 2,000 pounds). For the purpose of this thesis, tonnes and tons may be taken as roughly equivalent measures.

⁹ The original application by the concerned member states that a ban on the transit of all single-hull tankers could be instated in the area was withdrawn due to strong political opposition

Annex. Regulation 8 of the annex prohibits the discharge of sewage into the sea, except when a sewage treatment system is installed. Technical details of these systems are discussed by Douvier (Douvier, 2012, p.95 et sqq.) and can be found in the 2012 MEPC guidelines on sewage treatment plants (MEPC, 2012). Sewage treatment again follows an input control approach. A new regulation 13 was added in 2006 and entered into force in 2007 introducing port state control over operational requirements (MEPC, 2006). So far without any tangible effect, the Baltic Sea has been defined as a Special Area under MARPOL Annex IV, where distinct mandatory methods for the prevention of pollution by sewage may eventually apply. The respective changes to MARPOL Annex IV were adopted in 2011 and are supposed to apply from 1 June 2019 for new vessels and 2 June 2021 for existing vessels respectively. They will only come into effect once bordering states have established adequate port reception facilities (MEPC, 2011), which is not yet the case. Once this happens, much stricter laws on sewage water will come into effect in the Baltic Sea area.

Annex IV has been awaiting ratification (by 50% of the world tonnage) for 30 years, before it finally came into force in 2003 (Douvier, 2012, p.96). To fill the legislative gap both the Helsinki Convention and the OSPAR Convention bound their signatories to the MARPOL laws on sewage discharges as early as 1991. Though the laws are basically the same, the conventions differ from MARPOL Annex IV regarding the age and size of vessels they apply to (Douvier, 2012, p.97). Ship operators should thus carry all three treaties aboard.

Vessel-source waste disposal is regulated in Annex V to MARPOL, which all EU member states have signed. The annex entered into force in 1988 and has been amended regularly since. Garbage according to the regulation includes all kinds of victual, domestic and operational waste (see Regulation 1(1)). Extensive amendments to Annex V entered into force in January 2013, prohibiting discharges of all garbage into the sea except for certain cases described in Regulation 6 (MEPC, 2013a). The legislation on waste disposal follows an output control approach with the maximum pollution limit allowed being zero. Exceptions pertain mainly to cases where the safety and security of the ship or its crew is endangered as well as accidental loss of material despite all reasonable precautions being taken. The disposal of all plastics is prohibited according to Regulation 3, imposing a “zero-pollution” requirement (Pozdnakova, 2012, p.34). The annexes to Annex V, namely I and II, contain full prohibition on discharges in so-called “special areas”. The Baltic and North Seas have been IMO Special Areas for the Prevention of Garbage Pollution for many years. Changes to MARPOL Annex V were adopted in 1973 for the Baltic Sea entering into force in 1988 and coming into effect a decade later on 1 October 1989. The North Sea has been a Special Area for Garbage Pollution Control since 1989 with laws coming into force and immediately entering into effect on 18 February 1991 (MEPC, 1991). The disposal of garbage in both areas is limited by Regulation 5. There can be no stricter laws than the ones applicable for the North and Baltic Seas today with absolutely no

introduction of garbage into the seas allowed. The problem again is more the lack of compliance than the lack of strict laws.

In addition to the MARPOL laws, the London Convention adopted in 1972 (IMO, 1972) and the London Protocol adopted in 2006 (IMO, 2006) establish a longstanding legal framework prohibiting all vessel-source dumping of waste except for a permitted list, requiring an additional permit in the actual event of littering. The London Protocol entered into force in 2006 with the aim of eventually replacing the London Convention. It completely rewrites the Convention in order to introduce the polluter pays as well as the precautionary principle into the international legal framework. Neither the Convention nor the Protocol have been signed by all European member states, however. While the London Convention had 21 out of 28 EU signatories as of 24 October 2018, the Protocol had only been signed by 15 member states (see Annex A3: Signatories of IMO Conventions). Containing similar provisions, European waste legislation is based on the EU Waste Framework Directive, which entered into force in 2008 (European Parliament and European Council, 2000b). The framework directive is supported by Directive 2000/59/EC on port reception facilities for ship-generated waste, making appropriate reception facilities mandatory for ports and forcing ships to deliver their waste to these facilities before leaving a Community port (European Parliament and European Council, 2000b). Accompanying measures are a 25% minimum inspection requirement as well as the circumvention of financial benefits received from dumping waste in the open seas. This is done by reimbursing at least 30% of waste handling costs from all shipowners using a port, independent of them making use of the facilities. These laws are supplemented by the HELCOM Recommendation 28E/10 ‘Application of the no-special-fee system to ship-generated wastes and marine litter caught in fishing nets in the Baltic Sea area’. HELCOM recommends that vessels are not charged for using waste reception facilities in ports at all, but that costs are recovered from harbour fees (Helsinki Commission, 2010, p.34). Despite all these efforts, the main problem with offshore waste disposal remain burdensome enforcement mechanisms and actions. Attributing litter to a certain vessel is highly difficult. Hastings and Pott argue that although laws prohibiting waste dumping have been passed, still the “polluter does not pay.” (Hastings and Potts, 2013, p.50).

International policy making on vessel-source air pollution exists as much for environmental as for political reasons. The semi-enclosed Baltic Sea has traditionally been very sensitive to acid rain falls and bordering states have been advocating the desulphurisation of fuels for half a century. To avoid non-competitiveness on the bunkers market, Western European states pushed for international legislation. Even though political endeavours were long opposed by the shipping and oil industries as well as oil-producing states (Tan, 2006), a number of international and European laws are in place today and many more are envisioned for the upcoming decades.

The most effective solution to combat emissions was internationally agreed to be the use of low-sulphur fuels on board vessels by IMO member states (Tan, 2006, p.156).

The international community agreed upon Annex VI to MARPOL on air pollution from ships in 1997, leading to binding global limits on SO₂ and NO_x emissions entering into force in 2005 (IMO, 2005). The agreement was subsequently revised in 2008 (Resolution MEPC.176(58) adopted on 10 October 2008. Revised Annex VI entered into force on 1 July 2010., 2008, MEPC, 2010), including stricter emission caps for SO₂ for the years of 2010, 2012, 2015 and 2020 subject to review in 2018, which came to a positive result and confirmed implementation in 2020 (IMO, 2016b). This is shown in Figure 2-10. Legislation on sulphur emissions follows an output control approach. Current typical sulphur contents in residual oil reach 2.7%, which is a 45% surplus in sulphur content compared to future levels allowed (Matthias et al., 2010, p.2249). Both Baltic and North Seas are Special Areas for the protection of air pollution by ships (so-called Emission Control Areas or ECAs), where special limits for emissions of SO_x apply. The Baltic Sea Sulphur Emission Control Area [hereinafter SECA] was adopted in 1997, but only entered into force in 2005. Special area laws came into effect on 19 May 2006. The North Sea ECA was adopted in 2005, entered into force in 2006 and laws came into effect on 22 November 2007 (IMO, 2017a). A further move towards stricter emission limits will greatly affect both the shipping industry as well as the environment.

Figure 2-10: Global and SECA sulphur limits for marine fuels (Author, based on AirClim, 2011)

Shipping is believed to contribute to NO_x emissions in the North Sea coastal area with some 7-24% in 2030 (Hammingh et al., 2012, p.7). NO_x emission standards are set down in MARPOL Annex VI for diesel engines depending on the maximum operating speed with Tier I and Tier II representing global limits applicable from 2000 and 2011 respectively and Tier III only applicable in NO_x Emission Control Areas. An overview of these standards is provided in Figure 2-11. The only NO_x ECA designated so far is the North American Area with vessels build after 2016 having to comply with Tier III standards (IMO, 2018b). Designation of the

North and Baltic Seas as NO_x ECAs has been approved at MEPC 71 with both ECAs envisioned to come into effect on 1 January 2021 (IMO, 2016c). Legislation on nitrogen oxides follows an input control approach.

Figure 2-11: MARPOL Annex VI NO_x emission limits (Pedersen, 2018), reproduced with permission from dieselnets.com

With a view to CO₂ reductions, minimum energy efficiency requirements are mandatory for ships build after 01.01.2013, a requirement that is calculated as CO₂ emissions per capacity mile and that requires reductions every five years until efficiency is increased by 30% in 2025¹⁰ (MEPC, 2013b). Alongside this Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI), all ships above 400 tons are required to carry a Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP), a demand that may be waived in certain cases until 2019. This is the first step to include measures on CO₂ emissions into the MARPOL regime. Further steps will follow to achieve the new reduction aims of 50% less CO₂ from shipping by 2050. (IMO, 2018a)

With respect to emissions of particulate matter, no specific legislation has been passed so far, although it is argued that PM emissions automatically decrease alongside a decrease in sulphur emissions. An overview over legislation passed on all four types of atmospheric pollutants under IMO auspices can be found in Table 2-8.

¹⁰ EEDI reductions concern only newbuildings and will become gradually more stringent in three phases: Phase 1 (1/2015-12/2019): EEDI reduction 0-10%, Phase 2 (1/2020-12/2024): EEDI reduction 0-20%, Phase 3 (1/2025 onwards): EEDI reduction 0-30%

Type of pollutant	International legislation under IMO auspices
CO ₂	Annex VI MARPOL, Regulation 5 et al. MEPC 203 (62) of 2013 – Introduction EEDI MEPC 251 (66) of 2015 – Wider application of EEDI MEPC 72 of 2018 – Strategy to reduce GHG adopted
NO _x	Annex VI MARPOL, Regulation 13 MEPC 132 (53) of 2006 – Revised NO _x technical code MEPC 176 (58) of 2010 – Stricter limits, NO _x emission control area MEPC 271 (69) of 2017 – Requirements to make NO _x controls operational
SO ₂	Annex VI MARPOL, Regulation 14 MEPC 176 (58) of 2010 – Stricter limits MEPC 217 (63) of 2013 – Port reception facilities MEPC 70 of 2016 – Global sulphur cap for 2020 decided MEPC 72 of 2018 – Non-compliant fuel ban Special Area under MARPOL Annex VI (Baltic Sea and North Sea)
PM	/

Table 2-8: International legislation by type of pollutant - Air emissions

Adopting the 2008 MARPOL changes, the European Union has amended Directive 1999/32/EC on the sulphur content of marine fuels. It has introduced stricter IMO limits on bunker fuels as well as harsher rules on monitoring and enforcement. An additional 1.5% maximum sulphur content requirement was adopted by the EU for passenger ships. For an overview of sulphur content allowed see Table 2-9. According to Directive 2012/33/EU member states are required to ensure adequate port reception facilities for waste from exhaust gas cleaning systems. No special fee might be collected from port management for these services, meaning that costs will be allocated to all users of a port and will lead to an increase in port fees affecting the entire industry (European Commission, 2005, European Parliament and European Council, 2012). Instead of using low-sulphur fuel, scrubbers may be installed, although the European Commission found that these cause an increase in fuel consumption of around 1-3% and thus an increase in greenhouse gas emissions (European Commission, 2011b, p.29).

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in ECG, 2013.

Table 2-9: Sulphur Content Summary Table (ECG, 2013, p.14)

Lack of compliance is the most significant weakness of the current regulatory system on air pollution (Tan, 2006, p.4). The underlying problem, compared to other types of pollution like oil spills, is that often no direct effect of air pollution on the close environment can be measured. The emissions of a vessel rather contribute to the overall air quality leading to problems in

regions that might be located far away from the polluting incident. The cumulative effect typical for air emissions makes it difficult to link a certain outcome to the misbehaviour of one company. Enforcement must thus be based on the Precautionary Principle.

A comprehensive international legal framework on ballast water management came into force on 8 September 2017. The BWM Convention took a long time to be ratified, which is why regional solutions exist and laws on ballast water may be found in the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive and Regulation 1143/2014 on Invasive Alien Species. All three sources of law are briefly reviewed in Table 2-10.

Rule of law	Signatories	Content	Significance for trade on the Baltic and North Seas
IMO Ballast Water Management Convention (BWM Convention)	Entered into force on 8 September 2017, applicable to signatories	Requires all ships to carry a ballast water record book and to carry out ballast water management procedures to a certain standard	International binding instrument with significant power
EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (EU MSFD)	Applicable to all EU member states	Obligation to achieve good environmental status of the EU's marine waters by 2020, which is defined among others as "Non-indigenous species introduced by human activities are at levels that do not adversely alter the ecosystems" (Descriptor 2, Annex I)	Practical significance depends on the targets and measures set and implemented by the member states, but can be a powerful instrument
Regulation 1143/2014 on Invasive Alien Species of the European Parliament and the Council	In force since 1 January 2015, applicable to all EU member states	Requires early detection and prevention measures for all species of IAS in all biological environments (air, water, land)	Focused on early detection and prevention of IAS; no specific laws of conduct for the shipping industry

Table 2-10: Legislation on ballast water pollution – Content and Significance

First acknowledged by an IMO resolution in 1973 (IMCO, 1973), mandatory ballast water management has eventually become international law on 8 September 2017, triggered by the accession of Finland to the International Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast Water and Sediments [hereinafter BWM Convention] a year prior to that date. As of 10 January 2017, 52 states representing 35.14% of world merchant shipping tonnage have ratified the convention, thus satisfying the condition of 30 states representing 35% of world merchant tonnage set forth in it. Since autumn 2017 ballast water must be treated before it is released into foreign ecosystems to avoid the further spread of non-indigenous species. Ballast water legislation follows an input control approach. Shipping companies have to keep a ballast water record book, have to minimise the uptake of organisms and sediments during ballasting and have to chemically or mechanically treat the water before releasing it again (IMO, 2017a). 16 different sets of guidelines mostly of a technical nature have been published by the MEPC to facilitate the implementation of the BWM Convention and have been further amended at recent MEPC sessions (IMO, 2017b). MEPC 70 laid down in October 2016 that all ballast water treatment systems had to comply with guideline G8 by 20 October 2020 the latest.

Supranational involvement by the European Union on ballast water issues has long been reserved. Mainly, the Commission has proclaimed a "strong recommendation" that Member States should ratify the BWM convention (EMSA, 2008, Council, 2009). In its 2008 Marine Strategy Framework Directive, however, the European Union introduces non-indigenous species as one of 11 indicators for the evaluation of "good environmental status" [GES] of ecosystems (EP, 2008). Member states thus must come up with measures to achieve this goal. Regulation 1143/2014 on Invasive Alien Species entered into force on 1 January 2015 requiring early detection and prevention measures for IAS in air, water and on land. This regulation holds no specific rules of conduct for the shipping industry.

The legislative ban on the use of TBT-based anti-fouling paints came into force in 2008. The so-called AFS Convention (International Convention on the control of harmful anti-fouling systems on ships) adopted at an IMO conference in 2001 bans the application of harmful anti-fouling paints, specifically TBT coatings, on vessels as of 2003, followed by the elimination of active TBT coatings as of 2008. It follows an input control approach. It has been signed by 74 countries representing around 95% of the merchant fleet gross tonnage. The convention embraces the precautionary principle, leaving a way to prevent future harmful substances used in anti-fouling systems (IMO, 2008). It is supplemented by three sets of guidelines dealing with certification of systems (MEPC 102(48)), brief sampling (MEPC 104(49)) and inspection (MEPC 105(49)). At the European level, Regulation (EC) No 782/2003 of 14 April 2003 on the prohibition of organotin compounds on ships fulfils the same goal. The regulation makes the 2003 and 2008 deadlines from the AFS Convention mandatory for all ships flying the flag of a member state [hereinafter MS], operated under the authority of a MS without flying the flag

and vessels entering MS's ports. Small fishing boats and pleasure craft under 24 metres in length are not surveyed or certified.

While the international community has been worried about toxic hull coatings, they have also been worried about biofouling as a transfer mechanism of aquatic species. In 2011 the MEPC passed Resolution MEPC.207(62), setting guidelines on shipping companies keeping a biofouling management plan and record book and laying down that every vessel should have an anti-fouling system applied and regularly maintained. The AFS Convention is recognized in the Resolution, stating in 6.2 that "The anti-fouling system used should comply with the AFS Convention, where necessary." (MEPC, 2011). The wording of the resolution clearly shows the conflicting aims between biofouling and toxic anti-fouling. Compliance with the AFS Convention is not made mandatory and is not even demanded "where possible", but only "where necessary", gives it limited priority. While the biofouling resolution puts the transfer of aquatic species above all other aims and demands its inhibition even if toxic systems are used to fulfil the goal, the AFS Convention targets the use of all toxic paints, especially TBT. As discussed above, TBT is still widely used and seems to achieve the best results in limiting biofouling. Alternative hull coatings could also not be shown to be significantly less toxic, however. A viable solution to this dilemma still needs to be developed.

Noise pollution by vessels has received only limited attention by international regulators. Although it might fall under the general obligations of articles 194(1) and 211 UNCLOS, it is not specifically addressed in MARPOL or any other multilateral convention (Scott, 2004). The IMO MEPC has started working on minimising noise pollution by commercial vessels in 2008. Noise pollution has furthermore been discussed by the International Whaling Commission, the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals and the Agreement of the Conservation of Small Cetaceans of the Baltic and North Seas. The European Union has first acted in August 2004 with the European Parliament adopting a Resolution on the Environmental Effects of High-Intensity Active Naval Sonar, calling upon member states to adopt a moratorium banning the same. This has no impact on the operation of trading vessels, however. Noise pollution is specifically addressed in the EU's MSFD 2008/56/EC (EP, 2008). In Annex 1 to the MSFD, good environmental status is defined among others as the "introduction of energy, including underwater noise, is at levels that do not adversely affect the marine environment" (see para 11). A task group was employed by the European Union to recommend specific indicators to MS in order to achieve this aim. Indicators were chosen for low frequency impulsive and continuous sound, both typically produced by shipping activities. An indicator for high frequency impulsive sounds as produced by sonars on smaller vessels was not chosen (Tasker et al., 2012). The MSFD may provide an incentive to EU member states to take measures on underwater noise pollution by ships. Voluntary IMO guidelines were passed

in 2014, including measures such as choosing noise-reducing propellers or decreasing vessel speed.

2.5.7.4 Summary of current and upcoming legal measures

Vessel-source pollution has received great international attention in the last decades with an abundance of new laws coming into force. This development will still prevail over the course of the next decade at least. Most legislative endeavours are currently underway in the area of air pollution. With maximum sulphur standards for the North and Baltic Seas being implemented since 2015 and coming into force internationally in 2020 and the designation of North and Baltic Sea NO_x emission control areas under way, as well as CO₂ emission caps planned for 2025, the major air pollutants are being tackled. Particulate matter has not yet received any attention but is indirectly addressed via SO₂. Ballast water management is currently on the agenda with the BWM Convention coming into force on 8 September 2017. Disposals of oily water, sewage water and waste are strictly regulated, with new laws on sewage water being phased in in 2019. More effective enforcement is called for on these issues rather than more effective legislation. Toxic anti-fouling coatings like TBT have been banned since 2008 but are still employed, in part because they are effective in tackling biofouling. Also, alternatives to TBT are not significantly less toxic, leaving much room for improvement on hull coatings. No legislation exists so far on noise pollution at the international level. Also, officials at the IMO are currently looking into potential damages from radar devices.¹¹ Walker names mandatory measures as the number one priority in greening the shipping industry, followed by more sustainable transport specifically in Asia, incentives by ports to award green shipping, and raising awareness on environmental effects of shipping among the shipping industry to complement legislation (Walker, 2016). A full summary of legislation applicable to shipping on the North and Baltic Seas can be found in Table 2-11.

Type of pollution	Legislation applicable to the North and Baltic Seas
Basic laws on all types of pollution	UNCLOS, Article 145 MARPOL, Article 1 EU Water Framework Directive
Oily water	MARPOL, Annex I Special Areas under MARPOL Annex I (Baltic Sea, North Sea: Resolution MEPC 75/40) Designated PSSAs (Baltic Sea: Resolution MEPC 136/53; Western European Waters: Resolution MEPC 121/52; Wadden Sea: MEPC 101/48)
Sewage water	MARPOL, Annex IV Special Area under MARPOL Annex IV (Baltic Sea: MEPC 200/62 – not yet in force)
Dumping of waste	MARPOL, Annex V

¹¹ Personal communication with unnamed IMO official during the International Shipping Conference 2017 on 13 September 2017, London.

	<p>Special Area under MARPOL Annex V (Baltic Sea, North Sea: MEPC 36/28)</p> <p>London Convention and Protocol</p> <p>EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) supported by Directive 2000/59/EC on port reception facilities for ship-generated waste</p>
Air pollution	<p>MARPOL, Annex VI</p> <p>MEPC 203 (62) of 2013 – Introduction EEDI</p> <p>MEPC 251 (66) of 2015 – Wider application of EEDI</p> <p>MEPC 132 (53) of 2006 – Revised NO_x technical code</p> <p>MEPC 176 (58) of 2010 – Stricter limits on NO_x and SO₂, NO_x emission control area</p> <p>MEPC 271 (69) of 2017 – Requirements to make NO_x controls operational</p> <p>MEPC 217 (63) of 2013 – Port reception facilities</p> <p>Special Area under MARPOL Annex VI (Baltic Sea and North Sea)</p> <p>Directive 1999/32/EC amended by Directive 2012/33/EU</p>
Ballast water	<p>BWM Convention</p> <p>plus 16 sets of guidelines of a technical nature:</p> <p>MEPC 152 (55) – Sediment reception facilities</p> <p>MEPC 173 (58) – Ballast water sampling</p> <p>MEPC 123 (53) – Equivalent compliance</p> <p>MEPC 127 (53) – Ballast water management plans</p> <p>MEPC 153 (55) – Ballast water reception facilities</p> <p>MEPC 124 (53) – Ballast water exchange</p> <p>MEPC 162 (56) – Risk assessment</p> <p>MEPC 174 (58) – Approval of systems</p> <p>MEPC 169 (57) – Approval of systems using Active Substances</p> <p>MEPC 140 (54) – Approval of prototype systems</p> <p>MEPC 149 (55) – Sediment control</p> <p>MEPC 161 (56) – Emergency situations</p> <p>MEPC 151 (55) – Areas for ballast water exchange</p> <p>MEPC 163 (56) – Antarctic treaty area</p> <p>MEPC 252 (67) – Port state control</p> <p>EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC</p> <p>Regulation 1143/2014 on Invasive Alien Species</p>
Harmful anti-fouling systems	<p>AFS Convention</p> <p>MEPC 102 (48) – Certification of systems</p> <p>MEPC 104 (49) – Brief sampling</p> <p>MEPC 105 (49) – Inspection</p> <p>Regulation (EC) No 782/2003 – Prohibition of organotin compounds on ships</p>
Noise pollution	<p>EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC</p>

Table 2-11: Legislation applicable to the North and Baltic Seas

Most measures follow an input control approach, while waste disposal and emissions of sulphur dioxide are regulated via output control. The other two legal methods of controlling pollution, tax systems and establishing a market for pollution, are not applied for vessel-source emissions, although these instruments have several benefits over command-and-control mechanisms as explained above. A market for emissions will likely be introduced once mandatory CO₂ reductions become a part of the legislative framework in the form of a cap-and-trade system.

2.5.8 Discussion and outlook

Theories on incentives to discourage pollution were reviewed in this chapter and current legal rules on vessel-source emissions were examined in the light of theoretical foundations. Three sources of pollution underly zero emission rules, namely oily water, sewage water (not yet in force, but regulated with a zero emissions law), and waste pollution. Effective enforcement is another issue, though. Legislation on toxic anti-fouling systems needs to be improved to further decrease emissions of toxic substances, while controlling for the negative effects of biofouling, which makes this type of pollutant particularly tricky to regulate. Air pollution legislation is advancing, with strict laws on sulphur emissions in force and North and Baltic Sea NECAs coming into bearing in 2021. CO₂ and PM are not yet effectively included in the legal framework. Ballast water legislation has entered into force last year. More research is needed on noise pollution. So far, the mechanisms are too little understood to make a sound assessment of this source of ship pollution. Environmental law demands constant development in order to answer to environmental pressures that “increase with time and widen in scope” (Tsimplis, 2011, p.425). Further developments are expected on vessel-source pollution in the following years.

Comparing the legislative framework to legal and economic theory on avoidance of pollution, it becomes apparent that though laws on liability exist, for example in the case of oil spills, they have significant shortcomings in the case of vessel-source emissions, as identification of polluters is difficult and strategic insolvency can undermine liability laws. Instead, the legal system is built largely on regulation, which is well in line with theoretical recommendations. The right to a certain level of a clean environment has been assigned to society, following the theories of Pigou and the polluter-pays-principle. However, externalities of seaborne trade are not fully internalised, as the shipping industry has to limit pollution to some extent, but not necessarily to the optimal societal level. Nilsson et al. provide evidence that – at least in Sweden – shipping is paying less than its full marginal costs including externalities (Nilsson et al., 2018). This may be explained by the near-impossibility of determining the optimal societal level for such a complex problem as emissions from vessels, but may also be due to political reasons on two levels. Firstly, at the interplay of society, shipping companies and politicians, shipping companies are a small, well-organised group with a vested interest in influencing politics and the willingness and financial means of lobbying towards more lenient legislation, whereas society is a large, poorly-organised group whose individuals are often not aware of the harm they suffer from vessel-source emissions. Pollution from ships mostly takes place out of sight of individual members of society, who neither enter harbours, nor observe ships in the open seas (and if they do, it is rather a romantic picture, than one associated with harmful effects). Also, vessel-source emissions have diffused effects on the health of humans and

animals, where society is unlikely to be able to link the effect to the source. In such a situation, the lobby of the shipping industry will usually have a stronger influence on politics than the lobby of society, i.e. environmental organisations, meaning that politicians tend to reach solutions that are more favourable to the industry than to society and will not entirely internalise external costs. Marciano even goes as far as to argue that, especially in civil law systems, legislators are not only vulnerable to rent-seeking groups but have effectively no incentive to devise efficient laws (Marciago, 2010, part 4: ‘The economics of legal systems’). Secondly, political hesitation to impose legislation stems from the interplay among different national governments at the multilateral level of policy making. Where one government, or a small group of governments, push towards stronger environmental protection measures and thus higher costs for the industry in their sphere of influence, others might not follow. This creates a typical free rider problem, where the industry pertaining to the first group of countries is put at a competitive disadvantage, all the while creating environmental benefits which all countries are enjoying. The free rider phenomenon inhibits politicians to be overly ambitious when it comes to environmental protection.

Studying the legislative system, it becomes clear that it is largely based on input and output control with respective repercussions. On overview of legislative approaches applied can be found in Table 2-12. Legislators have opted to set technology-based standards for five out of seven types of vessel-source pollution, sometimes supported by measures of output control. Input control is politically easy to sell and thus widespread, but inferior in its economic effects to other legislative approaches. This is mostly because it does not incentivise the development of more efficient solutions or a further decrease of emissions. Performance-based standards, as used for oily water, sewage water, waste, sulphur, and nitrogen emissions, are superior in that they may trigger innovation, while again not incentivising further reductions in pollution. Both measures require an extensive amount of knowledge to achieve an optimal societal outcome. Legislative approaches favoured by economists, like Pigouvian taxes and market-based mechanisms, are not currently applied to disincentivise vessel-source pollution. The introduction of a cap-and-trade system for CO₂ emissions, like the one in place for the airline industry, is however under discussion.

Type of pollution	Legislative approach
Oily water	Input control: Building and design criteria, e.g. double hull requirements, oil filtering equipment; Traffic separation schemes; Mandatory reporting systems Output control: Limit of 15ppm discharged; zero discharges in specially protected areas
Sewage water	Input control: Building and design criteria, i.e. sewage treatment plants or holding systems; Laws on provision of port reception facilities Output control: Zero discharges of untreated sewage within 12 nautical miles from land
Waste	Output control: Zero discharges of waste
Air pollution	Input control: Building and design criteria, i.e. Minimum energy efficiency requirements and SEEMP to control for CO ₂ emissions

	Output control: Limited discharges of sulphur and nitrogen
Ballast water	Input control: Building and design criteria, i.e. Ballast water treatment systems
Anti-fouling	Input control: Prohibition of systems containing TBT
Noise pollution	No measures

Table 2-12: Legislative approaches by type of pollution for shipping in the North and Baltic Sea areas

As regards the theory of full costs and the identification of the cheapest pollution avoider, these considerations have until today not been considered in environmental legislation for the shipping industry. Complexity stems from the regulatory environment, where not one central agency, but actors at regional, national, supranational and multilateral level are acting simultaneously to achieve better environmental status, which makes endeavours that are more in line with economic theory, but more difficult to understand for politicians without any economic background, hard to sell and unlikely to be considered in the future.

2.6 Good ideas backfiring? - A theory of freight rate changes and modal shift

2.6.1 Freight rates in the short and long run

There is uncertainty among researchers whether environmental protection measures are coherently bringing about a cleaner environment. Some researchers argue that modal backshift to land-based transport would counterbalance positive environmental effects from legislating shipping. These effects may, however, only be witnessed where compliance cost increases are passed on to customers. Theoretical concepts on freight rates changes and modal shift are critically reviewed and discussed in this chapter.

Changes in the competitiveness of sea transport towards other modes will only be witnessed where increases in compliance costs will translate into increases in transport prices¹². The price of sea transport is the **freight rate**. Stopford proposes a basic formula of how demand and supply is formed and how freight rates are determined as a product of the two (Stopford, 2013, p.137; 160 et sqq.):

$$SST_{tm}(FR_{tm}) = DST_{tm}(FR_{tm}) \quad (8)$$

SST Supply of seaborne transport

DST Demand for seaborne transport

FR Freight rate

t Current year

m Ship type, e.g. container vessel, bulk carrier,...

Tamvakis argues that the **demand for shipping services** is a derived demand, depending on the complex demand for world merchandise trade (Tamvakis, 2012, p.52), often approximated by world economic growth. The growth of the world economy is generally a good indicator for the growth in demand for shipping services, although, as becomes apparent from the UNCTAD

¹² This thesis is focused on the transport of goods but price increases and modal shift may theoretically also be witnessed in passenger transport.

Review of Maritime Transport, world seaborne trade has been growing faster than world GDP since 1998. It also becomes apparent from Figure 2-12 that macroeconomic developments like the financial crisis have a more pronounced effect on the level of seaborne trade than on world GDP (UNCTAD, 2017, p.3), indicating that the demand for transport services is prone to fluctuate with macroeconomic developments and political occurrences. Stopford agrees that the world economy is “the most important single influence on ship demand”, but states that the relationship between sea trade and the world economy is neither simple nor direct (for deliberations on this point see Stopford, 2013, p.140). The cyclical development of the world industry may be the most important determinant of demand for seaborne trade, but random shocks and economic developments in individual countries or regions greatly influence overall demand, as do other factors like the seasonality of certain trades¹³, changes in supply sources and changes in average haul¹⁴ (Stopford, 2013, p.139 et sqq.). Stopford elaborates on the importance of random shocks for the system, including wars, new resources, commodity price changes and the weather. He also lists political events that have “turned the shipping market on its head” since 1990, emphasising the importance of politics on shipping demand (Stopford, 2013, p.148). A case in point are current trade restrictions imposed by the United States on several other countries, including China. Although the Economist Intelligence Unit expects only modest macroeconomic impacts of 0.1% on world economic growth¹⁵ (The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2018), a scenario analysis conducted by researchers from the German Bertelsmann Stiftung and ifo Institute suggests that trade restrictive measures by the United States might lead to a drop of more than 70 percent in U.S. exports in a worst case scenario (Petersen et al., 2017, p.16). As a general observation, Stopford suggests that demand for sea transport may change by as much as 10-20% in a single year (Stopford, 2013, p.139). The demand for maritime transport services is thus significantly more volatile than world economic growth.

Despite significant volatility, demand for seaborne transport is relatively inelastic. The actual responsiveness of demand to changes in freight rates depends on several factors, including the availability of alternative modes of transport and the substitutability of said modes in the eyes of the shipper as further addressed below in the discussion on modal shift. Another relevant factor influencing elasticity are transport costs as a share of total costs. Where the costs of transport only account for a minor share of the total product costs, demand will be rather inelastic. Also, elasticity of demand tends to be greater in the long term than in the short term. Considering that seaborne transport services may not be substituted by other transport modes on many routes, a certain inelasticity of demand is taken as given (Marinet, 2018).

¹³ Agricultural commodities depend on harvesting seasons, oil trades fluctuate with energy consumption, containerised cargo depends on major holidays, such as Christmas, Chinese New Year or Singles Day.

¹⁴ Transport demand is measured in ton-miles determined from the tonnage of cargo shipped multiplied by the average distance (or average haul) over which the cargo is being transported. Changes in average haul may occur for example when major transport channels like the Suez Canal will close for reconstructions. A consequential surge in transport demand will lead to a sudden increase in freight rates on the respective trades.

¹⁵ Decrease in world economic growth from 3% in 2018 to 2.9% in 2019.

Figure 2-12: Growth of world seaborne trade (Index with 1990 = 100) (UNCTAD, 2017, p.3), © 2017 United Nations. Reprinted with the permission of the United Nations.

The **supply of shipping services** is significantly less volatile than the demand. Larger-scale changes in supply require the building of new vessels and are linked to a time lag of several years. This makes the supply function an inelastic one. Stopford describes the supply of ships to be controlled by four groups of decision-makers: Shipowners building or scrapping vessels, shippers demanding transport capacity, banks exerting financial pressure and steering investment and disinvestment, and finally legislators who may induce scrappings or newbuildings with the introduction of new legal requirements. (Stopford, 2013, p.150). The complex relationship among these actors and the hard-to-predict behaviour of each of them will determine the long-term supply of tonnage.

Maritime economists argue shipping companies are able to influence supply in the short term. They may address demand peaks in one industry segment by employing vessels from other segments on this trade or by increasing or decreasing vessel speed (Stopford, 2013, p.162). In times of low demand, ship operators have their vessels running at slow speeds to save fuel and cut costs. This strategy may also be employed to address fuel cost increases from environmental legislation as modelled by Doudnikoff and Lacoste (Doudnikoff and Lacoste, 2013). As ship operators may adjust the speed of the vessel and thus the amount of supply offered in a certain year, the supply function for an individual ship is J-shaped. Stopford estimates that in times of high demand ships can increase productivity so as to offer an extra 36% of supply (Stopford, 2013, p.162). In a perfectly competitive market, the supply function thus depends on the optimum speed at which marginal costs equal the freight rate. Stopford proposes the following model:

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{R}{3p*k*d}} \quad (9)$$

where S is the optimum speed in miles per day, R the voyage freight rate, p the price of fuel, k the ship's fuel constant, and d the distance. He argues that the optimum speed further depends on vessel efficiency (Stopford, 2013, p.162). Also, rather than adjusting the speed, shipowners might decide to take their ships out of the market, accept part-cargoes, sign storage contracts or take longer routes with lower fees (Stopford, 2013, p.162). Figure 2-13 shows the short-run supply and demand functions with ship supply as a J-shaped curve and demand assumed to be inelastic. Four scenarios are marked in the graph to illustrate freight rate developments. In scenario X1, freight rates are low, the least-efficient ships are laid up and slow steaming is practiced widely by the remaining vessels. In scenario X2 all vessels are in service and running at normal speeds, achieving slightly increased rates. In scenario X3 all ships are in service and running at full speed for high prices. In scenario X4 freight rates increase further without any more transport quantity becoming available in the short-term. It becomes apparent that freight rates increase only slightly when demand increases from X1 to X2, while they increase more steeply between X2 and X3 and significantly between X3 and X4, where a 5% increase in quantity demanded may lead to a 50% increase in freight rates.

Figure 2-13: Short-run ship supply and demand functions (adopted from Stopford, 2013, p.165), Used with permission of Taylor & Francis; permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc.

In the long run, shipping companies may adjust the size of the fleet, thereby stabilising prices. As can be seen in

Figure 2-14, a shift in demand from D_{t1} to D_{t2} will lead to a decrease of supply by scrapping and thus permanently removing vessels from S_{t1} to S_{t3} . While freight rates will be at a low level

in t_2 , they will increase to their previous level in t_3 , after the market has had time to react to a lower demand for shipping services. Currently, the market finds itself in a situation similar to scenario X1 above. This scenario is not so much the result of decreased demand. As shown in Figure 2-12, the demand for seaborne transport has been steadily increasing in recent years. It is rather the result of extensive increases in supply with the ordering of more vessels than needed in the market. Instead of reducing transport capacity permanently to return to healthy rates, the industry keeps on ordering vessels, aggravating their own situation. This paradox is illustrated when comparing

Figure 2-14, showing the theoretical long-term demand and supply model and Figure 2-15, showing the development currently witnessed in the market.

Figure 2-14: Long-run supply and demand functions, theoretical model (adopted from Stopford, 2013, p.167), Used with permission of Taylor & Francis; permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc.

Figure 2-15: Long-run supply and demand functions, current development (Author)

The formulas and models discussed so far have their flaws, as they assume the shipping market to be in perfect **competition**. This is generally not the case, as entry barriers into the market are high due to very high initial investment costs in vessels. Depending on the route, an oligopolistic or even monopolistic situation might occur with only few active players (on competitive markets see Callan and Thomas, 2012, p.28 et sqq.). Therefore, increases in freight rates may be witnessed in the short term as well, mostly on routes with limited competition.

The **costs** of shipping companies such as compliance costs with environmental legislation appear hidden behind the supply function, as shipping companies might not be willing to offer any service below their operating costs in the long run and will be induced to take volume out of the market, thereby raising freight rates again. In the short term, however, before consolidation has had its effect, the costs of shipping companies play only a minor role. If demand decreases in the short run, shipping companies in a competitive market will increase their freight rates only slightly so as to keep their market share. If there is more capacity offered than capacity demanded, freight rates will remain at a low level, even if operating costs are increasing. In the longer term, market forces will clean the industry. Some companies will not be able to survive on rates below their costs for a longer term and will decide to leave the market. Typically, such a decision is taken when the freight rates that may be received lie below the individual total costs of providing the transport service in the long run and below the average variable costs in the short run. With the number of operating vessels declining, the price for transport services on the sea should increase and should be able to provide a sustainable financial position for the remaining competitors. As can be seen in Figure 2-17, the long-term equilibrium after compliance cost increases is much closer to the efficient equilibrium, while this effect may not be witnessed in the short term. The development of market consolidation is thus a necessary step on the way to an efficient market outcome (For a further discussion of

theoretical models see Taylor and Mankiw, 2014, p.41 et sqq., 157 et sqq.). It will thus take time before environmental legislation positively influences market forces, but in the long run the cost-increasing effect of environmental laws will become noticeable in freight rates and will thus influence the market actors' behaviour.

Figure 2-16: Short-term equilibrium after cost increases for the shipping industry (Author)

Figure 2-17: Long-term equilibrium after cost increases for the shipping industry (Author)

On a last note, Marshall's warning against believing in the achievement of a long-run equilibrium with a price that will cover the costs of production (the so-called natural price as defined by Adam Smith) has to be considered. Marshall argues that the natural price theory only works "if the general conditions of life were stationary for a run of time long enough to enable [economic forces] to work out to their full effect." (Marshall, 1994, p.28). In an industry

like the shipping industry, where constant changes in supply and demand occur and external shocks are frequent, the natural price is unlikely to prevail and market developments including the developments of freight rates are hard to predict. It must not be taken for granted that freight rates will move towards a level that will cover costs in the next years and thus a price-increasing effect of environmental legislation will not necessarily be noticed when the effect of other economic developments prevails.

2.6.2 A theory of modal choice

Researchers widely agree that there is currently no cleaner way than transporting goods on board a vessel (Institute for Transport Studies, 2010, p.9, Cullinane and Cullinane, 2013, p.396, Froholdt, 2018, p.220), apart from pipelines (Gordon, Leon and Scientists, 1991, p.143), a fact that can mainly be explained by economies of scale. Container vessels currently employed can carry up to 21.413 twenty-foot containers, whereas a truck would usually carry one or two containers. The European Union has actively encouraged a shift of cargo from road to rail and water (Brooks, 2012, p.307). It outspokenly aims to “shift at least the expected aggregate increase in international road freight traffic¹⁶, but preferably more, to short sea shipping, rail and inland waterway transport or to a combination of modes of transport in which road journeys are as short as possible” (European Parliament and European Council, 2006). Regulation 1692/2006 has laid the basis for infrastructural funding projects to improve environmental performance. Eight projects aimed at encouraging modal shift towards maritime transport have been conducted under the MARCO POLO II Program (Brooks, 2012, p.307). This “sustainable mobility” policy is also actively supported by big ports, which favour coastal shipping, inland waterways and railways over road transport due to road congestion around the ports (Notteboom, 2002, p.137). The European Parliament and the Council emphasise the importance of supporting water transport to deal with road overuse. In Regulation 1692/2006 they stress the “necessity of reducing congestion in the traffic bottlenecks in several regions, mentioning in particular the Alps, the Pyrenees and the Baltic Sea – an indication that the maritime lines of the Motorways of the Sea are an integral and important part of the Trans-European Transport Network” (European Parliament and European Council, 2006).

Following the official European perspective, any shift to other modes of transport is likely to lead to negative environmental effects. This view of clean shipping is not universally shared, however. Holmgren et al. argue that though shipping is linked to the lowest CO₂ emissions per ton transported, it is characterised by higher emissions of SO₂ and NO_x than land transport (Holmgren et al., 2014, p.62). An OECD report states that shipping is efficient and relatively clean “under ideal conditions” (OECD, 2011). Current research by the group around Inge Vierth at the Swedish National Road and Transport Research Institute shows that for transports on the Swedish mainland, trucks achieve a better economic performance than short sea shipping vessels, mainly due to the fact that very modern trucks complying with Euro 6 standards are competing with rather small, rather old vessels characterised by investment backlog. These findings are supported by case study research conducted by Santén et al., finding that for a specific route between Uddevalla and Gothenburg, short sea shipping is both costlier and more

¹⁶ They estimated an increase of 60% between 2007 and 2013, while actually the amount of goods transported by road fell by 20% in the same period. (compare Eurostat, Goods transported by Road)

damaging to the environment than truck and rail (Santén et al., 2017). In a personal conversation the researchers around Inge Vierth agreed that modern vessels would achieve a better environmental performance than modern trucks by way of higher load factors. This, however, does not represent the current situation of the short sea fleet in Sweden.¹⁷

The theoretical mechanism of adverse environmental effects of modal shift is shown in Figure 2-18. The theory goes thus: Environmental protection measures will increase costs and subsequently freight rates of the shipping industry, negatively influencing its competitive situation towards road and rail transport. Volumes will shift from ships mostly to road transport, as rail transport is defined by capacity constraints and limited flexibility. The same container transported on a truck rather than on a ship will cause more emissions and bring pollution closer to society. Efforts to clean the shipping industry may thus backfire. The risk of modal shift has been acknowledged by the European Commission in an impact assessment of stricter sulphur limits and a redirection of public funds to target undesirable modal shift has been proposed (European Commission, 2011b, p.28). The theory of modal shift finds supporters among the shipping industry and its interest groups, while it is outrightly dismissed by environmental organisations.

Figure 2-18: Theory of environmental damage due to modal shift (Author)

¹⁷ Personal conversation with the researchers Tobias Lindé and Inge Vierth at the SIGA2 Conference, 4 May 2018, University of Antwerp

An important aspect that needs to be considered here is that modal choice does not only depend on the price of a transport mode, although this is likely one decisive factor. Notteboom compares road, rail and water transport on several micro-economic criteria. His ideas are adopted in Table 2-13 (Notteboom, 2002, p.74). Ships can carry large volumes at low costs, are very reliable, associated with a low risk of damage and cause the least pollution per ton transported. Unfortunately, availability of this transport service is limited, as waterways do not exist on many routes. Accessibility and penetration are a problem; transport time may also become an issue. Road transport on the other hand is widely accessible, speedy and flexible, though it can only carry small volumes and is somewhat more expensive. Rail transport represents the middle-choice, being neither very cheap, nor very flexible or speedy, but may carry sufficiently large volumes at sufficiently low prices, where water transport services are not available. Brooks argues that as road transport usually has measurable advantages over water transport in terms of flexibility, departure frequency and transit times, ships have to offer significantly better rates in order to compete in the short sea sector (Brooks, 2012, p.321). The authors of the SKEMA study support this argument stating that short sea shipping needs to be 15% cheaper than land transport in order to attract half of the cargo (Kehoe et al., 2010, p.15).

Redactions due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Notteboom, 2002.

Table 2-13: Comparison of road, rail and water transport on microeconomic criteria (Notteboom, 2002, p.74)

A modal choice chart depicting the influence of cost differences between road and ship on market share can be seen in Figure 2-19. Fuel prices have not increased as much as anticipated by most economic studies on modal shift since the introduction of stricter sulphur limits in January 2015 (Zis and Psaraftis, 2017). However, it is not the price of fuel, but the price difference between transport modes that plays a role in modal choice. The competitive position of shipping compared to other modes of transport has certainly worsened since the introduction of stricter sulphur limits in the North and Baltic Seas.

Figure 2-19: Modal choice chart (Kehoe et al., 2010, p.16), reproduced with permission of Johan Woxenius.

The theory of modal choice invariably links compliance cost increases to increases in freight rates. This relation is an indirect one, however. Augmented costs will not necessarily lead a shipping company to increase its prices. This choice rather depends on the elasticity of demand. Where competition is fierce, be it with other sea-based operators or with land-based modes of transport, companies will rather opt for decreases in their margin. Thus, where the danger of modal shift is large, the increase in freight rates due to environmental cost increases will be relatively moderate. A different picture will emerge for long-distance services with a monopolistic or oligopolistic structure and for heavy-weight, low-value goods, which are fixed to sea-borne transport. There, demand is rather inelastic, leading to a substantial portion of compliance costs being passed on to customers. In a recent large-scale project contracted by the Conference of European Directors of Roads a group of researchers from four European countries made use of their respective national transport models to come up with a comprehensive handbook on modal choice. The researchers found that shipment attributes and trip distance will restrict options of modal choice to the effect that some shippers are captive to a single transport solution (Vierth et al., 2017). In those cases, legislation will likely lead to significant increases in freight rates, without giving rise to modal shift.

Also, the theory of modal choice invariably links increases in freight rates to decreases in vessel operations. This relation again must be examined carefully, as freight rates are not the only determinant of modal choice. Availability of infrastructure, the size of the consignment, the regularity of flows and the distance to be covered play a significant role as well (Institute for Transport Studies, 2010). Gibson et al. found that costs, effectiveness and trust are the most important criteria for shippers when finding a partner, while carriers will focus on trust, effectiveness and flexibility (Gibson, Rutner and Keller, 2002, p.676). The only comprehensive review on transport mode choice criteria that could be identified was conducted by Meixell and Norbis in 2008. The authors discuss 48 papers, presenting main outcomes and research gaps

(Meixell and Norbis, 2008). While different criteria are discussed in different papers, the issues of costs, speed, flexibility, reliability and equipment availability are often of the set. Despite the importance of other factors next to costs, increasing maritime freight rates has an influence on the decision-making of freight carriers. Vierth et al. show that transport costs are the most important choice criterion (Vierth et al., 2017). Short-term changes of suppliers are unattractive to many companies. Most wish to hold long-term contractual relationships for forwarding their goods (Brooks, 2012, p.322). Effects of cost increases are thus likely to appear with a time gap.

One problem with modal shift is that its existence is hard to prove. The choice of mode depends on many factors, including speed and reliability. Also, prices of all three competing modes are not transparent, constantly shifting and depending on a set of other factors apart from environmental compliance costs. The argument of modal shift is a very convenient one for the shipping industry to discourage further legislation and the most comprehensive study on the market was financed and contracted by that same industry. That might not necessarily make the content wrong, but a bias of the industry to exaggerate the danger of modal shift is pertinent. Further studies on the likelihood of modal shift need to be conducted as environmental effects of modal shift could counteract gains from environmental legislation.

2.7 A theory of compliant and deviant behaviour

2.7.1 Definition of regulatory compliance

The level of compliance with the laws is of crucial importance in a law-and-economics model, as shipping companies who do not comply with the laws will generally not observe an increase in legislation-induced operational costs. Despite the prevalence of legislative endeavours that should theoretically increase company expenditure no cost effect will be measurable in the case of general noncompliance.

The concept of regulatory compliance follows a letter of the law approach as dissociated from behavioural definitions used in the social sciences and is defined as the conformity of an organisation's behaviour with a prescribed legal rule (Mitchell, 1994, p.30). Noncompliance is thus a deviation from prescribed legal behaviour. Norrie argues that laws generally employ incentives to achieve "external behavioural conformity to the law", while legal concepts do not influence or aim to influence the internal moral duty of economic agents. He adds that "an immoral man may still act within the law" (Norrie, 2012, p.49). It might thus not be necessary to influence internal beliefs to achieve legal compliance, but it is likely that internal beliefs will have a bearing on behaviour. From an economic point of view, this definition is too narrow. To evaluate cost effects of legislation, changes of behaviour within the organisation leading to cost increases need to be considered, even if they do not lead to a fully compliant organisation. It is well possible that a shipping company switches to low sulphur fuel within emission control areas, but strategically switches only upon entry, instead of an hour before, making it noncompliant for a part of the journey within the ECA. Still, this company will incur higher costs from purchasing low sulphur fuel leading to a measurable economic effect despite legal noncompliance. Raustiala and Slaughter provide a helpful definition stating that compliance is a concept of causality looking at the behavioural influences of laws (Raustiala and Slaughter, 2002, p.539). Behaviour is relevant to the present research if it is directly or indirectly induced

by maritime environmental legislation and leads to costs in terms of money, time, or other resources. Where legislation has no effect on costs it can be assumed that incentives for noncompliance are nil.

Frequent compliance shortfalls in environmental law make Farber call environmental laws “merely targets rather than strict mandates” (Farber, 1999, p.299). In his article titled “Taking slippage seriously: noncompliance and creative compliance in environmental law” he claims that it would be “perilous” to assume that the law in the books and the law in action would correspond when it comes to environmental legislation (Farber, 1999, p.305). He argues that noncompliance is inevitable and natural in legislative processes and holds positive forces by leading to renegotiations of ill-drafted laws as well as the development of creative measures of problem-solving (Farber, 1999, p.307 et sqq.). Recent studies show that compliance levels may be increased if companies are effectively involved in designing legislation. (Malesky and Taussig, 2016)

2.7.2 Compliance and rational choice

As noncompliance with mandatory regulation is a criminal activity, economics of crime can be applied to analyse compliance behaviour. Following a law and economics approach, this work links regulatory compliance to rational choice theory. The principle of compliance as a cost-benefit calculation has been described in 1968 in a fundamental work on the economics of crime by Becker and defined further by his student Ehrlich (Becker 1968; Ehrlich 1996). Applying a related definition by Posner, shipping companies are likely to “economise by buying less of a good or commodity when its price rises” (Posner, 1974, p.763), specifically are likely to invest less in compliant behaviour if compliance becomes costlier, assuming that costs of noncompliance stay the same. Simpson and Rorie present compliance behaviour as a rational choice of companies among several alternatives. Noncompliance thus occurs where the benefits of unlawful behaviour outweigh the costs of compliance (Simpson and Rorie, 2011, p.60 et sqq.). In this context it needs to be noted that noncompliance may both be a product of action or inaction (Cohen and Simpson, 1997). When applying rational choice theory to compliance, limits to rationality need to be considered, like a lack of access to information, individual characteristics of companies, and circumstances. Simpson and Rorie thus propose an objective utility approach signifying that costs and benefits are “perceptual, rather than objective” (Simpson and Rorie, 2011, p.61). Perceived costs and benefits of a certain legislative endeavour may differ among companies and may lead to dissociated behavioural outcomes. Rational choice theory predicts that shipping companies’ incentives to violate the laws are likely to increase with augmented cost pressure. Environmental pollution being an externality, companies would generally only take their individual costs, not the costs to society, into consideration (Phaneuf and Requate, 2017, p.5).

2.7.3 Determinants of compliance behaviour

Publications from the legal, economic and social sciences were systematically reviewed to identify determinants of regulatory compliance. An important inclusion criterion was a focus on corporate instead of individual noncompliance. As few studies could be identified that were

specifically focused on the shipping industry, studies on other sectors as well as corporate compliance in general were included in the review. Studies on corporate social responsibility and self-regulation of industries, although often centred on compliance, were excluded, as this research is interested in behaviour in relation to governmental policy. An effort was made to consolidate factors identified and organise the resulting long-list of companies' compliance-determinants into categories.

As classical environmental economists, Phaneuf and Requate model compliance to depend on inspection probability and penalty level. They argue that both a higher inspection probability and a higher fee will increase the number of compliant firms, making the two variables substitutes (Phaneuf and Requate, 2017, p.199). Compliance levels may thus be influenced by either frequent harbour state controls, or high sanctions. According to classic economic theory, high fees should thus achieve high compliance levels in the shipping industry, where tight controls are costly and often not feasible. In a recent case study of a company “at the better end” of the industry Akamangwa finds that the prospect of criminal prosecution and fines was a strong motivation to comply with legislation (Akamangwa, 2017, p.3). This position is not uncontested, however. In their fundamental writings on environmental law, Bell et al. argue that enforcement has more levels than imposing fines. They propose an enforcement pyramid of measures, depicted here in Figure 2-20, starting with persuasion and education and ending with prohibition of operation (Bell, McGillivray and Pedersen, 2013). In an early empirical study on corporate compliance, Braithwaite and Makkai find that the certainty of detection may predict compliance, but neither the certainty nor the severity of sanctions will significantly influence compliance behaviour (Braithwaite and Makkai, 1991).

Figure 2-20: Enforcement pyramid (proposed by Bell, McGillivray and Pedersen, 2013), © 2013 Oxford University Press, Used with permission of Oxford University Press, permission granted via PLS Clear.

While the incentivising effect of inspections and penalties is put into question, other researchers argue that there is more to compliance than mere sanctions and controls. As an example of a

more intricate model, Parker and Nielsen propose what they call a “holistic and plural model of business compliance” in their book ‘Explaining compliance’ as pictured in Figure 2-21 below. They argue that compliance behaviour depends on the motives of the company, its organisational capacities and characteristics, and on formal and informal institutions, making enforcement just one of many determining factors. The researchers describe compliance choice as a complex decision-making procedure with various interdependent factors (Parker and Nielsen, 2011, p.5).

Figure 2-21: Model of compliance behaviour (Parker and Nielsen, 2011, p.5), © 2011 Edward Elgar Publishing, Used with permission of Edward Elgar Publishing, Permission granted via PLS Clear.

A similar stance is taken by Paternoster and Simpson in their classical ‘Theory of corporate crime’, where they propose nine explanatory factors of compliance, adding the perceived certainty and severity of informal sanctions, perceived certainty and severity of loss of self-respect, moral inhibitions, perceived sense of legitimacy or fairness of law, the situational context of the criminal event, and the prior offending record of the individual decision-maker’ to the list (Paternoster and Simpson, 1993, p.47). Arguably, these could be included into the above model as extended definitions of motives and informal institutions. Some researchers have found informal sanctions to have a stronger effect on behaviour than formal sanctions (Anderson, Chiricos and Waldo, 1977). Paternoster and Simpson and Parker and Nielsen show that compliance behaviour may be based on complex, interrelated sets of variables. Studying compliance is thus not only difficult because companies might be reluctant to share sensitive information on circumventing legal rules, but also because determinants of compliance are manifold.

Three main categories of determinants of compliance were identified by systematically grouping prior studies into recurring themes, namely (A) individual motivations, (B)

organisational capacities, and (C) exterior determinants of compliance. A clear distinction is at times difficult to achieve, as determinants may be interrelated. Incorporating the models by Paternoster and Simpson as well as Parker and Nielsen, these groups of determinants are discussed below:

A) Individual motivations

Corporate behaviour is characterised by accumulated individual decisions made by humans working for a company. Individual motivations, that is “forces within us that activate our behaviour and direct it towards one goal rather than another” (Shah and Gardner, 2008, p.235), are directly linked to perceived costs and benefits. Decisions on maritime environmental compliance are mostly taken by the management level (i.e. investing in a scrubber), or the captain aboard (i.e. switching to low-sulphur fuel in time). They may also be taken by standard seafarers (i.e. throwing garbage overboard), albeit with more limited environmental consequences. Compliance behaviour lies thus mostly in the hands of top management. Their individual motivations will drive corporate compliance. The subcategories morality and ethics, company culture, perceived benefits of compliance, and perceived costs of compliance have been identified from the literature as described below.

Paternoster and Simpson stress the importance of moral inhibitions and self-respect for compliance behaviour (Paternoster and Simpson, 1993). Simpson and Rorie support the view that personal motivations of key personnel may influence regulatory compliance of a company. They name morality and ethics of decision-makers, like the individual perception of crime seriousness, as a strong inhibitor of noncompliance. “Wrong is wrong regardless of the rewards of crime” is a perspective that not all managers share (Simpson and Rorie, 2011, p.64). The researchers argue that noncompliance levels will increase where an influential figure within the company orders it or a “criminogenic” culture exists within a company (Simpson and Rorie, 2011, p.63). The same researchers argue that the inhibitory effect of informal sanctions like discovery by family or business associates are usually much stronger than the effect of formal sanctions (Simpson and Rorie, 2011, p.69). Mankiw and Taylor agree, stating that externalities can be influenced by social norms (Taylor and Mankiw, 2014, p. 244). The management of shipping companies may be guided by certain values which will keep them from polluting extensively in the first place or will make them willing to comply with legal obligations. These theories make compliance decisions seem very dependant on key personnel.

Main motivators of decision-makers next to their ethical beliefs seem to be perceived costs of compliance and benefits of noncompliance (Paternoster and Simpson, 1993, p.47). Market actors will endeavour to minimise their individual environmental compliance costs (Shortle and Horan, 2016, p.6). Noncompliance may hold economic advantages for polluters and may thus be willingly done (Scorpecci, 2004). The principal administrator of the division of transport of the OECD claims that environmental regulations are more likely to be disregarded than safety standards or crew certifications, as negligence is not likely to pose a danger to shipping operations. Environmental laws tend to be less inspected and noncompliance more difficult to spot. Penalties are lower than for safety- and crew-related rule-breaking (compare OECD, 2003,

p.4, Scorpecci, 2004, p.3). The administrator furthermore claims that the amount of compliance costs might induce shipowners to circumvent compliance where margins are tight. Simpson and Rorie agree that financial rewards expected by individual decision-makers will influence noncompliance. The researchers found that levels of noncompliance were higher where companies believed they were losing competitive ground or where the costs of compliance were particularly high (Simpson and Rorie, 2011, p.62). On the other hand, in a case study conducted by Akawangma, competitive advantages were expected by “looking green” (Akamangwa, 2017, p.11).

B) Organisational capacities

Category (B) captures ‘hard’, measurable organisational characteristics. These include available resources and other characteristics such as size and area of operations. Dissimilar to category (A) these may be observed by a one-time visitor to the company. Organisational capacities modelled by Parker and Nielsen and characterised further by other researchers. Srivastava and Batié discuss capacities of legal knowledge. They term the difficulty to comprehend laws “compliance uncertainty” (Srivastava and Batié, 2002, p.5). The researchers argue that, especially where performance-based standards are applied, companies are sometimes unaware whether their current systems are working in accordance with the law or whether they are under- or over-complying. Technical capacities may be another factor. Sampson et al. argue that companies could fail to comply for “logistical reasons”, like struggling with the fuel changeover when entering an emission control area (Sampson et al., 2016, p.300). Behind the term “logistical reasons” stands a lack of knowledgeable human resources. Territorial outsiders are likely to be more affected by compliance uncertainty than insiders.

Looking at company characteristics, Simpson and Rorie review previous studies to find that certain company characteristics play a role in noncompliant behaviour, although their findings do not prove consistent across studies. Some of their work suggests that companies are more likely to offend if they have a history of noncompliance and where CEOs come from finance or administrative backgrounds, while they are less likely to offend if they are economically well off, are led by a CEO from a background like law or engineering, and are bigger in size (Simpson and Rorie, 2011, p.68 et sqq.). Other researchers find no relationship between compliance and company size (Clinard, Yeager and Clinard, 1980, p.130). An OECD report shows that circumventing legislation becomes economically more attractive with increased vessel age as well as with ships that have historically been badly maintained (OECD, 2003, p.5). Characteristics and capacities of a company may influence compliance behaviour.

C) Exterior determinants of compliance

The third category ‘exterior determinants of compliance’ summarises determinants imposed on the company by third parties, like governmental agencies, suppliers of technology and shipyards, other third parties and nature. The subcategories identified are termed ‘sanctions and enforcement’, ‘norms as effective deterrent’, ‘availability of feasible technical solutions’, ‘practical feasibility of noncompliance’, ‘human error’ and ‘higher forces’.

As discussed above, sanctions and enforcement are seen as crucial in determining compliance levels (Phaneuf and Requate, 2017). Enforcement of laws takes place both by the flag state, who is responsible for all vessels flying its flag, and by the coastal state, through which harbours and waters the vessel passes. In addition, classification societies play a significant role, making sure that technical standards are complied with. Akamangwa's case study revealed that regional differences in laws and enforcement mechanisms would discourage companies to comply, thus a complicated system of laws may lead to noncompliance (Akamangwa, 2017, p.13). The OECD argues that noncompliant ships, which are not sanctioned for their behaviour, will have significant competitive advantages on the market, thus putting pressure on other operators to break the laws as well (OECD, 2003, p.5). Taking into account economically induced willingness to breach the law, the OECD is requesting penalties to equal at least the cost savings from noncompliance (OECD, 2003, p.6). Next to inspection probability and the level of fines, the practical feasibility of noncompliance may prove important, related to general factors of vessel design, operation of control systems and so forth. Sampson argues that bunker delivery notes can easily be forged, leaving room for noncompliance (Sampson et al., 2016, p.301). Vollaard argues that the probability of detection of polluting incidents like oil spills is effectively inexistent during the night, where available monitoring devices do not produce evidence that is contestable in court (Vollaard, 2017, p.2).

It is not only enforcement which externally influences compliance behaviour, however. Akamangwa found that customer demands linked to certain certifications were deemed important by shipping companies (Akamangwa, 2017, p.13). Sampson et al. describe an incident in their paper where noncompliance happened by mistake, as the wrong fuel was supplied to the ship by a third party (Sampson et al., 2016, p.301). Inadvertent noncompliance may also be due to a problem called 'stratification' where blended low-sulphur fuel oil undergoes partial separation in the tank and the port-state control samples comes back positive. Instances of human error may occur more frequently where crews become increasingly multicultural and multilingual. (see Progoulaki and Roe, 2011 for a discussion of dealing with multicultural human resources on board ships) Lastly, uncertainty about compliance may also result from external factors. This dilemma becomes evident in a study by Carney et al. who describe difficulties in obtaining ballast water samples which are representative of all the ballast water on board a vessel (Carney et al., 2013).

Prior studies conducted on determinants of compliance show the complexity of interrelated factors influencing compliance behaviour. Although the outcome (the company acts or does not act in accordance with the law and does or does not bear the costs of compliance) may in most cases easily be established, the rational choice process leading up to this result depends on many variables. Influential factors were grouped into three categories, namely interior motivations, organisational capacities, and external factors. Adherence to the laws is likely when it yields economic benefits or as a result of effective deterrence from deviant behaviour. Research shows that noncompliance exists and that it might be due to compliance uncertainty, but may also be willingly done where economic benefits are expected. Lastly, an ineffective system of controls, including a low level of fines, could influence compliance levels. Previous studies provide helpful theoretical frameworks and evidence on determinants of compliance. Still, as only a handful of studies were conducted specifically on regulatory compliance within the shipping

industry, the researcher had a keen interest to collect primary data on maritime environmental compliance to strengthen the theoretical foundations and collect empirical evidence on noncompliance.

2.8 On the specific characteristics of the shipping industry

Jon Foreman proposes ‘sector-thinking’ and a sector-based approach to environmental policy-making, arguing that this improves regulatory outcomes (Foreman, 2018). The shipping industry differs in several ways from other sectors apt to influence the effectiveness of legal incentives. Shipping companies “do not face geographical limitations either in the acquisition of their resources or in making their services available” (Theotokas, 2018), writes Ioannis Theotokas, Greek professor for the management of shipping companies. Heidbrink attest that the industry is defined by a “low relevance of the nation state” (Heidbrink, 2012, p.48). The commercial shipping industry is characterised by compelling possibilities to avoid regulation via moving assets that may easily be relocated to other jurisdictions, varying levels of enforcement of international laws in port states, and global commons in the form of international waters, where enforcement is hardly possible. Also, interests collide at times between flag and port states as regards environmental protection and offering low-cost solutions to shippers. According to Tan, the industry is of “a generally secretive and fragmented nature” (consult Tan, 2006, p.6). Regulatory avoidance and free-riding are inherent to the sector, a recent OECD report argues (OECD, 2014, p.86). Roe explains this with the inherently mobile character of the industry and the difficulty to clearly associate a vessel to a certain sphere of law enforcement (Roe, 2006). Only some 45% of overall emissions in EU seas stem from EU-flagged vessels (OSPAR Commission, 2010, p.96), making the port-state, flag-state debate an important issue and the industry much harder to regulate than stationary sources of pollution.

Although ships may originally be defined as a point source of pollution, the travelling of pollutants through air and water for long distances and the subsequent impossibility to trace pollutants back to their source effectively makes them non-point sources of pollution. Thus, incentive mechanisms from non-point pollution literature may be translated into the shipping context. In their encyclopaedia on environmental and natural resource economics, Haab and Whitehead describe non-point sources of pollution as sources that are “prohibitively costly to monitor” (Haab and Whitehead, 2014, p.233). The researchers state that eventually, there is no such thing as a non-point source of pollution, but pollution sources can be ordered along a spectrum with easily classified sources on the one end and increasingly costly sources to classify on the other (Haab and Whitehead, 2014, p.233). On this spectrum, vessels are costly to monitor in that they are constantly moving, and often moving in international waters and traversing the territories of different nations, supporting the argument to call them non-point sources of pollution, as is often done with cars.

Legal compliance by these moving sources is primarily supposed to be enforced by their respective flag states (see Mansell, 2009 for a thorough discussion of flag state responsibility). After the second world war shipping companies started to separate the flag of their vessels from their state of ownership, moving towards flags that were particularly convenient to their business. Small states with insignificant own fleets, like Malta and Liberia, became important

flag states. UNCTAD data shows Panama, Liberia, and the Marshall Islands to be the leading flags of registration in 2017, holding a cumulated share of dead-weight tonnage of 41.86%. (UNCTAD, 2017, p.32) Fleets are owned, however, by companies from countries like Greece, Japan, and China, to name the top three. 79% of the ships owned by Greece as the largest ship-owning country fly a foreign flag. (UNCTAD, 2017, p.28) The symptom of “flagging out” has existed for centuries¹⁸, oftentimes undertaken for political reasons. Today, it is mostly driven by the wish to avoid “bureaucratic costs and costs of compliance” (Mansell, 2009, p.93) as well strict employment legislation for a high-wage unionised workforce (Knight, 2019). A specific problem are so-called flags of convenience (FOC), defined as registries from which ship owners can expect “limited or no sanctioning mechanisms if they are identified as operating in violation to international law” (Galaz et al., 2018). Galaz et al. find that detrimental environmental effects of limited enforcement by FOCs are further aggravated when these are at the same time tax havens (Galaz et al., 2018). An important mechanism to counteract flagging out particularly to registries with limited enforcement is the increased importance of port state control. In European harbours, controls are set out based on an agreed inspection mechanism under the Paris Memorandum of Understanding (Paris MoU) and results are shared via the THETIS database. The formation of an international agency working based on international inspection standards has so far not materialised due to regulatory and budgetary concerns (Knight, 2019). Heidbrink argues that a byproduct of flagging out is that certain governments are now often more influential in the development of international regulations than the traditional ship-owning nations of the world (Heidbrink, 2012, p.48). This proves difficult when different countries place a different priority on environmental protection, making international legislation of the shipping industry a challenging endeavour.

Vorbach argues that industry self-regulation is an important third enforcement mechanism next to flag state and port state control. (Vorbach, 2001) Efforts by industry leaders to provide safe and clean shipping are particularly noticeable in the tanker industry, where the so-called Oil Majors, major oil companies like Exxon, BP and Shell, are prominently involved in chartering operations. The oil companies conduct inspections of shipping companies as part of their supply chain management and provide thus a very effective means of enforcing international laws on safety and the environment (see ILO, 2000, p.25 on subsectoral agreements supporting the enforcement of international laws, see Bhattacharya, 2009, p.59 et sqq. on the specific role of oil majors). Similar mechanisms can be observed in the container shipping industry with major consumer goods companies exercising pressure on their supply chain as well as in more specialised segments of the shipping market, where wood or paper companies effectively influence the environmental compliance of shipping companies in their supply chain. King and Toffel note, however, that market pressure or new industry entrants may erode positive conditions of industry self-regulation (King and Toffel, 2009, p.108).

¹⁸ British vessels flew the Spanish flag when travelling to the West Indies in the 16th century to avoid trade restrictions (Mansell, 2009, p.91).

2.9 Chapter summary and theoretical framework

A discussion of legal and economic theories provides the foundation for empirical data collection. Seven sources of vessel-borne pollution of relevance to the current research were identified once the legal and economic definition of ‘pollution’ had been established. Economic theories provide insights on externalities and the Tragedy of the Commons, explaining why excessive pollution by the shipping industry may not be rectified by market forces. The need for government intervention is established and legal incentives to discourage pollution are discussed. The current legal framework is compared with recommendations on effective incentives from economic theory. It is shown that current laws are based on output and input control, while Pigouvian taxes and market-based measures are not applied despite their economic advantages. Posner’s and Polinsky’s theories on a full cost approach and the cheapest pollution avoider are presented. Despite convincing economic arguments, these theories are not considered in environmental policy-making. A discussion of theories regarding costs and freight rate effects of legislation shows freight rates to depend on the supply and demand for seaborne transport. Effects of environmental legislation will be visible through changes in the long-term supply function. Marshall’s warning needs to be considered, however. Various economic forces are at play over time and expected effects may eventually not be witnessed. The relationship between legislation, costs and freight rates is shown to be indirect. The theory of modal shift is discussed, and costs are shown to be an important factor in modal choice. However, a number of other variables influence the equation, like speed, flexibility, and trust. Freight rate changes are shown to depend on the elasticity of demand. Where competition by other modes of transport exists, freight rate increases due to legislation will be moderate. Where shippers are bound to vessel transport and encounter an oligopolistic or monopolistic market, however, freight rate increases may occur as a result of compliance cost increases. Long-term contractual relationships between shippers and shipping companies will delay potential shifting effects. Noncompliance is shown to be a potential unintended effect of stricter legislation, applying the theory of rational choice. Reviewing theories on compliance behaviour shows compliance to depend on various other factors apart from perceived costs, however. Lastly, the shipping industry is shown to be more difficult to regulate and control than land-based, point sources of pollution. Theoretical concepts discussed can be seen in the theoretical model in Figure 2-22.

Figure 2-22: Theoretical model developed from literature review

3 Exploration of data from prior studies

3.1 Introduction

Having explored and discussed the theoretical concepts guiding this research, this chapter will be dedicated to an exploration of findings from prior studies on effects of maritime environmental legislation. After a brief overview over the adopted methodology, prior studies on the costs of environmental laws for the shipping industry will be explored in Chapter 3.3. The review is organised by types of vessel-source emissions and concludes with findings on the total costs of compliance. Chapter 3.4 is dedicated to an analysis of prior findings on freight rate changes and modal shift. Studies conducted on the existence of noncompliance with legislation and the likely cost-savings from deviant behaviour are investigated in Chapter 3.5. Lastly, a study on prior findings on the characteristics of the shipping industry with respect to environmental legislation, specifically on the question whether distinct types of shipping companies are differently affected by legislation, may be found in Chapter 3.6.

3.2 Methodology adopted in exploration of data from prior studies

Prior studies were scrutinised following a process of systematic literature analysis. The analysis was driven by a theoretical approach based on keyword matrixes, inclusion and exclusion criteria and guidance questions. Comprehensive searches of legal, economic and general

knowledge databases were conducted using different sets of keywords according to the academic field of literature reviewed. In the first step a thorough study of the official publications by the European Union [hereinafter EU] and United Nations [hereinafter UN] institutions with special focus on the International Maritime Organisation [hereinafter IMO] was conducted, with a specific focus on regulatory impact assessments contracted by these organisations. This analysis was supported by a review of studies conducted by national governments, industry organisations, environmental organisations, and academic researchers. A special focus was placed on core variables identified from the review of theoretical concepts, namely compliance costs, freight rate effects, magnitude of modal shift, and magnitude of noncompliance. Databases used to identify relevant studies were LexisLibrary, Juris, Westlaw UK, ECOLEX, Wiley Online Library, Cambridge Journals Online, Science Direct, Springerlink, Web of Science, ISI Web of Knowledge, Emerald Inside, and Google Scholar. A particularly successful method used in establishing prior studies was a review of studies cited in papers identified, as well as the “cited by” tool in Google Scholar to identify recently published work. Also, experts taking part in qualitative interviews were encouraged to identify relevant studies to add to the body of literature.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to select relevant papers to be included in the review. These were an exclusion of all papers published prior to the coming into force of MARPOL in 1983, inclusion of papers with a legal or economic line of argument to the exclusion of scientific papers, inclusion of academic research focussing on commercial shipping for trading purposes, excluding a large number of articles on fisheries, the inclusion of working papers to reflect current strands of research and the prerequisite of an identified author, excluding dubious internet sources. All inclusion and exclusion criteria can be seen in Table 3-1.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Justification
Post-1982 publication	Pre-1983 publication	Major changes to the international legal framework (esp. MARPOL 73/78) came into force in 1983, outdating research conducted before that date
Working papers	Internet sources without reliable authorship	Working papers were included in order to reflect the most current strands of research
Focus on commercial shipping for trading purposes	Focus on other uses of the sea, e.g. fisheries, recreation, power production	The legal framework for other uses of the sea is fundamentally different making information unsuited for the research purpose
Legal or economic line of argumentation	Scientific or other unfamiliar schools of research	Although of significant interest for the subject, the researcher is adopting a law and economics approach touching at other disciplines only where necessary in order to develop the law and economics argument

Table 3-1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for sources of literature

3.3 Prior studies on costs of environmental legislation

3.3.1 Compliance cost estimates by type of pollution

The legal measures described in Chapter 2 lead to increases in compliance costs. The magnitude of cost increases due to environmental legislation has, however, not been comprehensively studied. Before a new measure comes into force, regulatory impact assessments are contracted by legislators to estimate the costs of that particular legal measure. Combined effects with other measures are usually not considered. Ex post studies on the actual impact witnessed are not conducted neither. In addition to the legislator, ex ante impact assessments are often carried out by lobby groups such as environmental organisations or industry associations, as well as national governments with a particular interest in the shipping industry, and academic researchers. Academia is generally the only group to consider legislative effects ex post. Lobby groups are generally concerned with supporting or preventing future legislation, adopting a “what’s-done-is-done” mentality towards legislation in force. Legislators similarly operate with a view to the future and, having in mind the time-consuming process of political decision-making, do not tend to regularly review measures already in force. Impact assessments exist primarily on measures deemed particularly costly to the industry. This review is organised by type of vessel-source pollution.

Compliance costs with legislation to discourage pollution through oily water mostly stems from the mandatory use of oil filtering equipment, fees for harbour state reception facilities for oil residue, and the construction of double-hull, instead of single-hull vessels. Double-hull requirements have been in force since 1990 and are thus not considered in the investigation of current cost increases. Still, estimations made at the time are given here to gain an idea of the magnitude of compliance costs. In 1998 the U.S. Marine Board estimated the price differential between double-hull and single-hull tankers between 9 and 17 percent in purchasing price, with an additional price differential between 11 and 37 percent for repairing and maintaining the protective coatings in the tanks of double-hull vessels. Also, insurance premiums were found to be around six percent higher for double-hull ships. As a share of total operating costs, double-hull vessels were found to be between five and 13 percent more expensive than single-hull vessels (Marine Board, 1998).

A review of charging systems for port reception facilities can be found with Carpenter and Macgill (Carpenter and Macgill, 2001). In line with recommendations by the European Parliament (European Parliament, 2000), several European ports decided to implement systems where no special fee applies to discharges. The aim is to discourage illegal dumping of oily water. No costs thus apply to the use of their harbour state reception facilities. In the respective European Directive 2000/59/EC it is laid down that “all ships calling at a port of a Member State shall contribute significantly to the costs [...], irrespective of actual use of the facilities”. Compliance costs thus become noticeable as a general increase of harbour fees but will be

linked only to a limited degree to actual discharges. No study could be identified estimating these cost increases in harbour fees.

Lastly, no academic studies or legal impact assessments could be identified estimating the costs of oily water separators. However, producers estimate costs of €2,200 to over €885,000, mainly depending on the flow rate and technology used (Cleanawater, 2018). Compliance costs linked to the limitations of oil spills into the environment thus amount to some 5-13% of operating costs for the construction, maintenance, repair, and insurance of a double-hull ship, plus an additional amount of a few thousand to more than a million Euros for the installation of an oily water separator and an increase in harbour fees largely irrespective of the use of reception facilities of an unknown amount.

With regard to compliance costs with sewage water legislation, cost increases may stem from the installation of sewage treatment systems and sewage holding tanks, as well as the discharge of sewage to port reception facilities. A mandatory discharge of untreated sewage to port reception facilities in the Baltic Sea area will come into force in 2019, after the missing notification of Russia on adequate port reception facilities was submitted to the IMO in 2016. On-board treatment plants have installation costs of €200,000 to €1.6 million, according to a study conducted by Bachér and Albrecht (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.29), but are unlikely to be installed on commercial trading vessels. They almost exclusively play a role for vessels carrying above 500 passengers, as the amount of sewage created depends on the use of showers and toilets by persons aboard. Compliance costs for vessels carrying goods will stem from storage and release of sewage in ports. A review of port reception facilities conducted by Swedish researchers shows that most ports have introduced a no-special-fee system with respect to sewage waste (Wilewska-Bien and Anderberg, 2018). In these ports, a general increase in harbour fees will likely be witnessed. Some 18% of ports do not act in line with HELCOM recommendations on the issue and adopt direct fees (Wilewska-Bien and Anderberg, 2018). Both the direct fees and the general increase in harbour fees are likely negligible, as commercial freight ships carry only small amounts of sewage water.

The prohibition of all dumping of waste into the specially protected areas of the North and Baltic Seas leads to compliance costs in the forms of holdings tanks and fees for port reception facilities. In the Baltic Sea area, a “no special fees” system is common in ports, leading to the replacement of specific compliance costs with higher fees for the harbour use in general. Only

one study could be identified on the magnitude of cost increase, focusing specifically on new laws of processing food waste. The study estimates investment costs of around €1.500 for the installation of a crushing device for food waste plus an additional €1.000 annually in operation costs (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.20). As a share of total vessel costs, laws on the dumping of waste are likely to have minimal effects. Bachér et al. argue that due to lack of data and significance of the costs, dumping of waste may be excluded from compliance cost calculations.

Air pollution control includes measures on limited sulphur, nitrogen oxide, and carbon dioxide emissions. With respect to sulphur legislation, the costs of compliance are represented by the price difference between distillate fuel and high sulphur fuel or the write-down for a scrubber investment (see Jiang, Kronbak and Christensen, 2014 on cost-benefit analysis for sulphur scrubber installation vs. use of marine gas oil) or investment in main engines powered by alternative fuel. With respect to nitrogen oxide legislation, engines must comply with Tier I, II, or III standards, depending on when they were first being installed. The Tier III standard will, however, first enter into force once North and Baltic Seas have been declared NO_x-ECAs starting from 1 January 2021. Once Tier III standards are mandatory, compliance costs will stem from either employing selective catalytic reduction (SCR), a urea-based system, or from switching to LNG-powered engines. Respective a reduction of CO₂ emissions, the EEDI requires increased efficiency of newbuildings, leading to increased investments in more efficient engines, while at the same time leading to reduced fuel consumption from increased efficiency. A reduction of air pollution is not only discussed for open-sea operations, but also for vessels in port. While the use of 0.1% low-sulphur fuel in port has been mandatory in EU waters since 2010, initiatives are pushing towards the use of shore-side electricity. This study focuses on operations at sea, and refers to Zis et al. for a discussion of costs and emission reductions of such measures (Zis, Mihalis and Psaraftis, 2017).

27 studies on air pollution legislation for shipping on the North and Baltic Seas conducted since the year 2000 were reviewed for this thesis. Eight were contracted by the European Commission (BMT, 2000, EC, 2002, Avis and Birch, 2009, Bosch et al., 2009, COMPASS, 2010, EMSA, 2010, Kehoe et al., 2010, European Commission, 2011b) and two further ones part-funded by the same (Jalkanen, Kalli and Stipa, 2012, 2013). Five were commissioned by national public authorities (Kalli, Karvonen and Makkonen, 2009, SMA, 2009, EPA, 2012, Hammingh et al., 2012, Vierth, Karlsson and Mellin, 2015), two by industry interest groups (Entec, 2010, Lemper et al., 2010) and one by an environmental organisation (CE Delft, 2016). Further studies appeared as research reports or in scientific journals (Kalli, Repka and Karvonen, 2010, Notteboom, Delhay and Vanherle, 2010, SWECO, 2012, Holmgren et al., 2014, Jiang, Kronbak and Christensen, 2014, Antturi et al., 2016, Kontovas et al., 2016, Nikopoulou, 2017, Åström et al., 2018). Figure 3-1 shows the scope of all 27 studies. It becomes evident that stricter sulphur limits both on the North and Baltic Seas have been the focus of attention of researchers and governmental bodies, while stricter nitrogen oxide limits seem to pose less of a threat

judging by the limited scientific interest. Most research treats the Baltic and North Seas as one logical unit of protected seas in Northern Europe as is done in this thesis.

Figure 3-1: Scope of economic studies on air pollution legislation

Prior economic studies were guided by different sets of research questions, focused on different geographical areas or different types of vessels, assumed different sulphur levels applicable in SECAs, different prices for heavy fuel oil [hereinafter HFO] and marine gas oil [hereinafter MGO] and different base years and lastly applied different research methods ranging from literature reviews over expert interviews to scenario analyses and mathematic models. Comparability of results is thus limited. Still, findings of these studies as presented in Figure 3-2 and Figure 3-3 serve as a rough indication of effects on shipping costs and freight rates.

Name of study	Estimated cost increases for shipping	Year, area, sulphur limit
Study on the economic, legal, environmental and practical implications of a European Union system to reduce ship emissions of SO ₂ and NO _x (BMT, 2000)	Total: €695 million Per ton of SO ₂ : €1,243	2015, all European seas, From 2.5% to 0.5%S
Advice on the Costs to Fuel Producers and Price Premia Likely to Result from Reduction in the Level of Sulphur in Marine Fuels Marketed in the EU (EC, 2002)	Per ton of fuel: around €75	2015, all European seas, From 3.5% to 1.0%S

Cost Benefit Analysis to Support the Impact Assessment accompanying the revision of Directive 1999/32/EC on the Sulphur Content of certain Liquid Fuels (Bosch et al., 2009)	Total: €0.6-2.7 billion in 2015; €0.9-4.6 billion in 2020	2015 and 2020, North and Baltic SECA, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Impacts on the EU refining industry & markets of IMO specification changes & other measures to reduce the sulphur content of certain fuels (Avis and Birch, 2009)	Per ton of fuel: €200-280 (Increase by 60-75%)	2015, North and Baltic Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Sulphur content in ships bunker fuel in 2015 - A study on the impacts of the new IMO regulations and transportation costs (Kalli, Karvonen and Makkonen, 2009)	Total: €341-564 million	2015, Finnish trade, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Consequences of the IMO's new marine fuel sulphur regulations (SMA, 2009)	Total: €29 billion Per ton of fuel: 50-55% For vessels operating only in SECAs: up to 70%	2015 compared to 2008, vessels calling at Swedish ports, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Assessment of the impact of the application of new sulphur limits to the Mediterranean and the Atlantic European Seas - Short Study (Kehoe et al., 2010)	Per ton of fuel: €253,57 in 2015 and €274,14 in 2020	2015 and 2020, North and Baltic Seas, From 2.5% to 0.1%S
The COMPetitiveness of EuropeAN Short sea freight Shipping compared with road and rail transport (COMPASS, 2010)	Total: 6-29% increase in total costs	2015, North and Baltic Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Study to review assessments undertaken of the revised MARPOL Annex VI regulations (Entec, 2010)	Per ton of fuel: €155-310; Average value €230 (Increase by 80%) Total: €3-3.6 billion increase in compliance costs	2015, North and Baltic Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Analysis of Consequences of Low Sulphur Fuel requirements (Notteboom, Delhay and Vanherle, 2010)	Total: 29-40% increase in shipping costs Per ton of fuel: +70-90%	2015, North and Baltic Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
The 0.1% sulphur in fuel requirement as from January 2015 in SECAs - An assessment of available impact studies and alternative means of compliance (EMSA, 2010)	Per ton of fuel: +67,4% in 2010, +59,37% in 2015, +62,5% in 2020 (Increase by 65-80%)	2010, 2015 and 2020, North and Baltic Seas, 1.5% to 0.1%S

Commission staff working paper: Impact Assessment accompanying the document Proposal for a Directive of the Euro pean Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 1999/32/EC as regards the sulphur content of marine fuels (European Commission, 2011b)	Total: €57-304 million	2020, North and Baltic Seas, 1.5% to 0.1%S
Confronting future reality. The price of sulphur reductions in Baltic Sea and North Sea Shipping (Jalkanen, Kalli and Stipa, 2012, 2013)	Per ton of fuel: €243-281 in 2015, €422 in 2020 Total: €3.1-4.3 billion in 2015	2015 and 2020, Baltic and North Seas, 1.5% to 0.1%S
Consequences of the sulphur directive (SWECO, 2012)	Per ton of fuel: €328 in 2015	2015, Sweden, 1.5% to 0.1%S
The evolution of shipping emissions and the costs of regulation changes in the northern EU area (Johansson et al., 2013)	Increase in fuel costs: +13-69%	2015, Baltic and North Seas, 1.5% to 0.1% S
Model calculations of the effects of present and future emissions of air pollutants from shipping in the Baltic Sea and the North Sea (Jonson et al., 2015)	Increase in fuel costs: 30-80%	2015, Baltic and North Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Effects of More Stringent Sulphur Requirements for Sea Transports (Vierth, Karlsson and Mellin, 2015)	Fuel cost increases: For ferries +12%, for RoRo vessels +72%, for container vessels +81%, for other vessels +36%	2015, North and Baltic Seas, From 1.5%S to 0.1%S
SECA Assessment: Impacts of 2015 SECA marine fuel sulphur limits - First drawings from European experiences (CE Delft, 2016)	Per ton of fuel: €192 Total: €2.2 billion	2015, North and Baltic Seas, From 1.0% to 0.1%S
Costs and benefits of low-sulphur fuel standard for Baltic Sea shipping (Antturi et al., 2016)	Total: €456 million/year	2016, Baltic Sea, From 1.0% to 0.1%S
Incremental costs for reduction of air pollution from ships: a case study on North European emission control area (Nikopoulou, 2017)	Scrubber: €595-3.884/ ton of SO ₂ reduced; €29-46 /ton of fuel oil consumed	2020, North and Baltic Seas, Global 0.5%S

Figure 3-2: Estimated costs for shipping due to stricter sulphur standards in Baltic and North Seas SECAs – Review of studies (all values in €, exchange rate: 1 USD = 0.9369 €)

Although the underlying assumptions of studies on stricter sulphur standards vary, they reach similar estimates on the impact 0.1% S might have on the industry. Increases in fuel prices when

moving from 1.5% to 0.1% S are estimated at around €155 to 328 per ton of fuel in 2015 with an average value of €262.71 across all studies. Additional costs for 0.1% sulphur fuel in 2020 are estimated to reach €274 to 422 with an average value of €348.07 across all studies. While the actual price development of fuel is hard to predict, the price differential between MGO and HFO develops more constantly (Kontovas et al., 2016, p.22). Total costs to the shipping industry of 0.1% S limits on the North and Baltic Seas are forecasted only by five studies. They envision total cost increases between €0.5 billion and €4.3 billion with an average value of €1.6 billion in 2015. Only two studies report values for 2020 with total cost increases between €57 million and €5.6 billion. These numbers seem to be hard to predict, given the vast differences in study outcomes. They should thus be treated with great caution. Some studies give estimates not in numbers but in percentage change. Fuel price is predicted to increase by 12-90% from 1.5% to 0.1% S, with more recent studies predicting a wider range of possible outcomes with lower boundaries. Studies conducted before 2013 would estimate fuel price increases to reach at least 50%, while researchers studying newer sets of data came up with scenarios as low as 12%, 13% or 30% fuel cost increase (Johansson et al., 2013, Jonson et al., 2015, Vierth, Karlsson and Mellin, 2015). In a recent study comparing the cost of different abatement methods, Nikopoulou finds that compliance costs differ depending on ship and engine type and size, abatement method, time spend in ECAs, and operational behaviour of the shipping company. The most cost-effective behaviour of shipping companies, be it operation on low-sulphur fuel, the installation of a scrubber or investment in LNG propulsion, needs thus to be decided on a case-by-case basis (Nikopoulou, 2017). Empirical work conducted by Psaraftis and Kontovas suggests that in 2015 “the negative implications of the [SECA] regulation were masked by the surprisingly low fuel prices that actually lowered the operating costs for the ship operators” (Zis and Psaraftis, 2017). Instead of empirically proving the increase in fuel costs suggested by all studies conducted before 2015 (and even still predicted by those published after 2015), the researchers thus find a decrease in fuel costs, leading to a linked decrease in total costs. Commodity price developments show, however, that after a further decrease in 2016 the price for crude oil has been steadily increasing since 2016 and has kept going upwards over the course of 2018 (on the strong correlation between crude oil and marine fuel oil prices see Kontovas et al., 2016, p.21, for current developments of crude oil prices see Tradingeconomics, 2018), likely rendering prior study results relevant again. Total costs are predicted to increase by 6-40% depending on study design and again depending largely on expected fuel price developments.

Most researchers agree that the benefits of sulphur legislation outweigh the costs or are at least roughly equal to them (Jonson et al., 2015). One of the more recent studies conducted by a team of Finnish researchers around Jim Antturi, however, find that the costs of a Baltic Sea SECA outweigh the costs by the factor four (yearly costs of €456 million, yearly benefits of €105 million), leading to a net welfare loss in the range of €360 million (Antturi et al., 2016, p.436). Further research is deemed relevant.

Name of study	Estimated cost increases for shipping	Year, area, nitrogen limit
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Study on the economic, legal, environmental and practical implications of a European Union system to reduce ship emissions of SO ₂ and NO _x (BMT, 2000)	Total: €2,678 million Per percentage point of reduction: €31 million	2015, all European seas, 2g/kWh NO _x
The COMPetitiveness of EuropeAN Short sea freight Shipping compared with road and rail transport (COMPASS, 2010)	Total: 0.6-2.5% for newly build ships	2015, all European seas
Baltic NECA - Economic Impacts (Kalli, Repka and Karvonen, 2010)	Total: €55.6-76.6 million in 2020, €206-289 million in 2030 Per ton of nitrogen: €3,000 to 4,000	2020 and 2030, Baltic Sea, Tier III
Economic impact assessment of a nitrogen emission control area at the North Sea (EPA, 2012)	Per ship: €6,500-400,000 (average of €52,000) Per ton of NO _x : €1,878 Total costs in 2030: €282 million (€127-389 million)	2030, North Sea, Tier III
Assessment of the environmental impacts and health benefits of a nitrogen emission control area in the North Sea (Hammingh et al., 2012)	Total costs in 2030: €243 million (€109-334 million) Per ton of NO _x : €1,900	2030, North Sea, Tier III
Specific evaluation of emissions from shipping including assessment for the establishment of possible new emission control areas in European Seas (Campling et al., 2013)	Total costs in 2020: €114 million/year; in 2030: €268 million/year Per ton of NO _x : €1,100 in 2020, €800 in 2030	2020 and 2030, Baltic Sea and North Sea, Tier III
Incremental costs for reduction of air pollution from ships: a case study on North European emission control area (Nikopoulou, 2017)	Per ton of NO _x : €491-700 in 2020 Per ton of fuel consumed: €17-30 in 2020	2020, North and Baltic Seas, Tier III
The costs and benefits of a nitrogen emission control area in the Baltic and North Seas (Åström et al., 2018)	Total costs in 2030: €111 (100-123) million/year for the Baltic Sea, €181 (157-209) million/year for the North Sea, €230 (195-273) million/year for both seas; Around 3% of total marine fuel costs	2030, Baltic Sea and North Sea, Tier III

Figure 3-3: Estimated costs for shipping due to stricter nitrogen standards in Baltic and North Seas NECA – Review of studies (all values in €, exchange rate: 1 USD = 0.9369 €)

Seven studies could be identified providing cost estimates for the introduction of a **Tier III standard** in ship construction as shown in Figure 3-3. Values are difficult to compare due to differences in methodology used and sea areas considered, but overall cost estimates stay significantly below cost estimates for stricter sulphur limits. In 2020 compliance costs are expected to reach €114 million annually for both North and Baltic Seas; for 2030 researchers expect total cost increases of around €195-273 million for both seas. Two studies provide percentage cost increases, expecting compliance costs for Tier III standards to reach between 0.6 and 3% of total costs. The limited expected cost effects may be due to the fact that nitrogen limits will only be applicable to newly-builds leading to 40-year-or-more introductory phase. Benefits of legislation are expected by researchers to outweigh costs. They are estimated by Hammingh et al. to amount to €380 to 954 million for the area of the North Sea, compared to costs of €243 million (Hammingh et al., 2012, p.61). Lastly, little studied but still likely of larger financial importance than NO_x measures, Bachér and Albrecht estimate that the **EEDI requirements** will lead to additional design and construction costs for vessels in the range of 5% (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.32).

Costs for complying with ballast water legislation stem both from investment as well as operating costs of systems. Two scientific studies could be identified giving estimates for compliance costs with the BWM Convention which came into force in 2017. The International Union for Conservation of Nature [hereinafter IUCN] together with the GEF and the IMO studied costs and benefits of enacting the convention in 2010. They noted that industry obligations included training of crew members and on-shore personnel, setting up and keeping BWM plans and record books and investments in either exchange of ballast water (D-1) or treatment of ballast water (D-2) (GEF-UNDP-IMO GloBallast Partnerships Programme and IUCN, 2010, p.40). Costs of installing a system are given at €88,000-880,000 (\$100,000 to 1 million), while treatment costs make for €0.01-0.2 per ton of ballast water treated (GEF-UNDP-IMO GloBallast Partnerships Programme and IUCN, 2010, p.17). Bachér and Albrecht argue that the system costs depend very much on the technology chosen and the treatment need, which may range from 250 m³/h to 3,000 m³/h (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.34). Depending on treatment capacity they estimate a cost range of €200,000 to €1.2 million as shown in Figure 3-4, which is very much in line with the estimates from the IUCN study.

Figure 3-4: Price of ballast water treatment systems in relation to capacity (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.33)

Further cost estimates can be found in industry publications. An article of World Maritime News reports on the four cost factors established by the IMO study. Based on information by UK P&I Club the article states: “The cost of compliance to shipowners will be very high. A ballast water treatment system can cost from half a million to four million dollars. There will be ancillary costs, including developing a ballast water management plan, dry docking and installation.” (World Maritime News, 2013). The industry magazine Ballast Water Treatment Technology states that installation costs could reach €4.4 million (\$5 million) per vessel. Further cost factors are consumables, spare parts and monitoring costs. Fuel costs to run the system are estimated at €22 to 175 a year. Chemicals that need to be supplied every 6 months will cost €0.07 per m³ of treated water. Maintenance costs are given with around €1,750 annually and the replacement of filters – necessary every 5-10 years, might cost €3,200 to 11,000 per screen (Ballast Water Treatment Technology, 2016). These studies need to be read with caution, as estimates are anecdotal in nature and represent industry interests. The results are not based on systematic empirical methods and the validity of the statements made can thus not be tested. Still, all four studies taken together can provide a rough cost estimate of compliance costs with ballast water legislation.

Recent cost estimates for anti-fouling coatings stem from a life cycle assessment conducted by Demirel et al. at the World Maritime University. They argue that costs for anti-fouling systems are linked to the initial and dry-dock paint application costs, which are counterbalanced by

potential savings in fuel costs as systems allow for less friction in the water (Demirel et al., 2018). The researchers conducted a case study comparing a tin-free, self-polishing paint with a fouling release coating and found that savings of roughly 3% in fuel consumption were possible at the expense of slightly higher initial investment costs, leading to total cost advantages of 2.5%. The researchers found the application costs to be roughly between €1.75 and 3.5 million (\$2 to 4 million) over the lifecycle of the vessel (Demirel et al., 2018, p.19). In addition to the application of coatings, the hull needs to be cleaned regularly while the vessel is in the water, leading to additional cost. A group of researchers around Pagoropoulos studied the economic and environmental impact of the frequency of hull cleanings in relation to fuel savings and found that, especially when fuel prices are low, savings may be offset by the costs for in-water cleaning of the hull, if this service is employed too frequently (Pagoropoulos et al., 2017). Economic impacts thus may be positive or negative, depending on the careful planning of the vessel owner.

As described above, no legislation has yet been passed on limited noise pollution from ocean-going vessels. In consequence, no costs of compliance exist. Furthermore, no study could be identified estimating a likely range of future costs of compliance, once measures are implemented.

3.3.2 Evidence on adaptive behaviour to influence compliance costs

Maritime economists theorise that certain adaptive behaviours might be employed by shipping companies to adjust to cost increases in the short term. Adaptive behaviours studied by researchers include modified vessel speeds, notably slow steaming, which finds early and prominent mention in the literature (On the introduction of speed reduction mandates and their positive environmental effects see Corbett, Wang and Winebrake, 2009, on companies adapting vessel speed to adjust to increased compliance costs see Doudnikoff and Lacoste, 2013, Stopford, 2013, Hämäläinen, 2014). While most researchers find speed reductions to be an effective way of decreasing vessel-source air pollution, Cariou et al. observe that CO₂ minimisation and cost-effective operation may only be reconciled in times of high bunker prices. When bunker prices decrease, shipping companies have little incentive for slow steaming (Cariou, Cheaitou and Larbi, 2017). Also, speed reductions are countered by cargo inventory costs. Lindstad et al. find that additional cargo inventory costs may be of the same magnitude as cost savings from slow steaming, making speed adjustments unlikely for higher-value cargo (Lindstad, Jia and Adland, 2017). Further obstacles to an optimisation of sailings speeds lie in charter clauses prescribing certain speeds or demurrage rates (i.e. penalties for late loading and unloading), as has been shown empirically by Jia et al. (Jia et al., 2017). While most researchers find speed reductions will both decrease the environmental impact of shipping and vessel operation costs, Woo and Moon argue that while a reduction in CO₂ emissions is

certain, slow steaming will not necessarily have positive cost effects for the shipping company (Woo and Moon, 2014). Another adaptive behaviour receiving increased attention recently is the rerouting of vessels to routes where less fuel needs to be used overall or where less time is spent in ECAs (on the time spent in ECAs influencing compliance costs see Nikopoulou, 2017, p.1073). A further possibility is the combination of route and speed improvements, increasing speed outside ECAs and slowing down inside ECAs to save on expensive low-sulphur fuel. Empirical evidence on these adaptive behaviours is thin. In a recent investigation, Adland et al. found no significant relationship between empirical vessel speeds and regional environmental legislation (Adland et al., 2017). Similarly, Mallidis et al. argued that sulphur legislation would not alter the routes used by shipping companies in the East Asia – EU trade, as shipping cost increases were offset by cost-efficient hinterland connections, making rerouting unprofitable (Mallidis et al., 2018). While theories on adaptive behaviour are convincing, their practical significance remains questionable.

3.3.3 Estimated total environmental compliance costs

As study designs differ, cost estimates provided may not be aggregated. Still, the approximate range of compliance costs becomes evident. A summary of costs associated with the seven environmental concerns discussed here can be found in Table 3-2. The aggregated study results provide a rough estimate of total compliance costs from environmental legislation. It is expected to lead to construction cost increases of vessels in the range of 14-23%, to costs for mandatory installations aboard vessels in the range of €300,000 to 7 million and to operational cost increases in the range of 11-56% of total vessel costs. These findings from prior studies will be empirically tested by way of questionnaires.

Environmental concern	Measures in place	Associated costs estimated by prior studies
Oily water pollution	Prohibition of single-hull tankers	9-17% increase in construction costs, 11-37% increase in repair and maintenance, 6% increase in insurance (5-13% increase overall)
	Port reception charges	Unknown, often no special fees
	Oily water separators	€2,000-1 million/vessel
Sewage water pollution	Sewage water treatment facilities	€200,000-1.6 million/vessel
	Holding facilities and port reception charges	Unknown, often no special fees
Dumping of waste	Holding tanks and port reception charges	Unknown, often no special fees
	Crushing devices for food waste	€12,500/vessel + €1,000 annual operation costs
Air pollution	Introduction of SECAs	6-40% increase in total costs, depending on fuel price
	Introduction of NECAs	0.6-3% increase in total costs

	EEDI requirements	5% increase in construction costs
Ballast water treatment	Mandatory ballast water treatment systems	€85,000-4.3 million installation costs + €0.01-0.2 per ton of ballast water treated (for fuel costs, chemicals, maintenance)
Non-toxic anti-fouling paints	Prohibition of paints containing TBT	Unknown, might be positive or negative
Noise pollution	No mandatory measures	None
Total	All measures	Construction cost increases in the range of 14-23% plus €300,000-7 million for installations Operational cost increases in the range of 11-56% of total vessel costs

Table 3-2: Aggregated costs associated with maritime environmental legislation as provided by prior studies, organised by environmental concern

In an industry characterised by overcapacities, the increase of compliance costs is likely to add additional pressure to strained businesses (Morley, 2016). Very few researchers have over the years endeavoured to estimate the combined cost effect of several environmental laws for the shipping industry. One such study was conducted by the OECD in 2003. Researchers estimated compliance costs at the time to reach around 3.5-6.5% of a ship's operating costs (OECD, 2003, p.5). Scorpecci estimated that compliance costs in 2004 reached up to 20% of the vessel's revenue. He argued that with additional legislative measures, compliance costs would likely increase by 1.5 up to 3 times the amount of 2004, thus increasing the incentive for noncompliance (Scorpecci, 2004, p.7). The 2003 OECD study calculated possible savings of up to €350,000 (\$400,000) a year for a noncompliant vessel compared to a fully compliant one (OECD, 2003, p.5). A further comprehensive study was commissioned by the Finnish Transport Safety Agency (Trafi) and conducted by the researchers Bachér and Albrecht in 2013. The researchers found that for mid-size bulk carriers, investment costs of €4.5 million and annual operating costs of €38,000 would accumulate to comply with maritime environmental legislation if a scrubber was installed. In case of the use of MGO as a fuel, investments of €1.5 million and additional annual operating costs of €1.3 million could be witnessed. The costs for newbuildings were found to be slightly lower (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013). With new maritime environmental laws becoming effective, behaviour formerly not unlawful is subjected to fines, increasing compliance costs.

The OECD study divides compliance costs into first and second order compliance costs as shown in Table 3-3. First order compliance costs consist of investment costs as well as variable costs for disposals and make up around 3.5-6.5% of the ship's operating costs (OECD, 2003, p.5). Second order compliance costs apply when no investments were made in equipment, leading generally to a higher number of costly disposals to port reception facilities. These numbers stem from calculations conducted in 2003, before laws on air pollution, ballast water

and anti-fouling came into force. Compliance costs should currently be significantly higher than those shown in Table 3-3.

First order compliance costs	
Capital, maintenance and repair costs for environmental equipment (Investments)	€26,000/year*
Costs for disposal of waste, sewage water, oily water	€48,000-131,000/year*
Second order compliance costs	
Disposals when no investments in environmental equipment were made	€44,000-350,000/year*

Table 3-3: Compliance cost estimates (all values in €, exchange rate: 1 USD = 0.9369 €) (OECD, 2003, p. 5)

** Depending on vessel type, size and trading routes*

Sampson et al. argue that the cost of compliance lies in the price differential between full compliance and noncompliance with legislation (Sampson et al., 2016, p.300). The price of noncompliance stems from the level of costs from deviant behaviour multiplied by the risk of detection. Bell et al. argue that the costs of noncompliance have been increasing in recent years. They discuss several categories of noncompliance costs, namely criminal liabilities (with rising fines and a rising willingness of regulatory agencies to prosecute), administrative sanctions (including suspension of licenses), clean-up costs (after pollution incidences; often exceeding the fines), civil liabilities (rather unlikely in the case of shipping), and adverse publicity (Bell, McGillivray and Pedersen, 2013, p.39 et sqq.). Following rational choice theory, a shipping company will weigh the costs of behaving in accordance with the law against the costs of deviant behaviour.

3.4 Prior studies on freight rate changes and modal shift

Empirical evidence on freight rate effects of maritime environmental legislation is scarce. Still, a small group of researchers has over the years devised theoretical models and simulated impacts of certain legislative measures on the costs of sea-based transportation. Notably, the influence of sulphur and nitrogen oxide legislation on freight rates has been studied. Researchers do not only disagree on expected outcomes of legislation, but also on the mechanisms of the market. Kalli et al. argue that increased costs will necessarily lead to higher shipping freight rates (Kalli, Karvonen and Makkonen, 2009), while the authors of the SMA study claim that the sector is far too competitive to pass on costs, as ship operators are competing for cargo with companies operating outside SECAs (SMA, 2009). This view is supported by the ECSA study, which emphasises that competition from road transport will prevent freight rate increases (Notteboom, Delhay and Vanherle, 2010). Only five studies among those reviewed for this thesis make an estimate of freight rate effects from environmental legislation. Kalli et al. estimate freight rate increases of 2-4.6% due to the introduction of Tier III standards for the Baltic Sea and the EPA study assumes 0.2-2% freight rate increases if the same laws would apply for the North Sea (Kalli, Repka and Karvonen, 2010, EPA, 2012). Estimates for freight rate increases due to low sulphur legislation on both

Baltic and North Seas are much higher reaching 8-51% of additional costs for shipping customers in 2015. The only empirical study among the set finds that freight rate increases due to stricter SECA requirements were implemented by 53.8% of respondents. Increases were found in the range of 1-10% (Yannoulis, 2015, p.805).

Name of study	Study design	Estimated freight rate increases for shipping	Year, area, policy
Sulphur content in ships bunker fuel in 2015 - A study on the impacts of the new IMO regulations and transportation costs (Kalli, Karvonen and Makkonen, 2009)	Scenario analysis	+28-51% depending on freight type	2015, Finnish trade, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Consequences of the IMO's new marine fuel sulphur regulations (SMA, 2009)	Scenario analysis based on freight model	+20-28% (with fuel costs making 40-50% of operating costs)	2015, Swedish shipping industry, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Baltic NECA - Economic Impacts (Kalli, Repka and Karvonen, 2010)	Qualitative interviews, scenario analysis	+2-4.6%	2020, Baltic Sea, NECA Tier III
Analysis of Consequences of Low Sulphur Fuel requirements (Notteboom, Delhay and Vanherle, 2010)	Simulations, scenario analysis	+8-40% (especially for long short sea routes)	2015, North and Baltic Seas, 1.5% to 0.1%S
Economic impact assessment of a nitrogen emission control area at the North Sea (EPA, 2012)	Scenario analysis	+0.2-0.6% for long distance shipping, 1-2% for short sea shipping	2015, North Sea, NECA Tier III
Monitoring Economic Impact of Low Sulphur Requirement ECSA-ESSF survey for ship operators (Yannoulis, 2015, Deligianni, 2016)	Empirical study, questionnaires (n=33)	+1-10% for 42.4% of survey participants	2014-2015, North Sea and Baltic Sea, 1.5% to 0.1%S

Figure 3-5: Estimated freight rate increases for shipping due to SECA and NECA laws in the Baltic and North Seas - Review of studies

Data is altogether missing on the effect of other types of legislation on freight rates in the North and Baltic Sea areas. One study could be identified simulating freight rate and modal shift effects for **ballast water legislation** in the US Great Lakes region. Here the researchers found the effect of mandatory treatment to increase freight rates by 0.008 US\$/ton to 0.14 US\$/ton of

cargo transported, a value not exceeding 0.3% of total freight costs. They predict a moderate shift of cargo in the area of 0.06-1.14%, a factor due as much to longer transit times from ballast water treatment, as well as slightly increased freight rates (Yang and Perakis, 2004, p.83).

Holmgren et al. argue that it is not the fuel price increases themselves that worry shipping companies. They have experienced a nearly eightfold increase in crude oil prices from 2001 to 2008 and have kept on operating profitably, the researchers argue (Holmgren et al., 2014, p.63). The difference to current developments is that cost increases are not driven by and do not coincide with increased transport demand, but come at a time where the financial situation of most shipping companies is already strained. With overcapacities in the market, raising freight rates will endanger the competitive situation of shipping companies and will likely occur mostly where demand is inelastic, and competition limited. Freight rates are first and foremost a product of a competitive market, mirroring supply and demand. Environmental friendliness does not seem to play a role in determining the price of a vessel. Very crucially, in an empirical study from 2000, Tamvakis and Thanopoulou find no statistically significant difference between freight rates paid to younger, safer (and usually more environmentally friendly) vessels compared to older vessels. In the few cases they find a statistically significant difference, the freight rate differential does not exceed 10% (Tamvakis and Thanopoulou, 2000). Having stated these macro-relations, it has to be noted that shipping freight rates are often freely negotiated leading to significant differentials in pricing for the same service (Joo, Min and Smith, 2017, p.2). Also, transport costs differ depending on whether a short-term or long-term contract is in operation or an own fleet is used (Joo, Min and Smith, 2017, p.3).

Empirical evidence on **modal shift** is almost as thin as evidence on freight rate changes. To support the underlying assumption that water-borne and land-based transports are interlinked, Vierth et al. show that with efficiency improvements for trucks, i.e. the allowance of higher dimensions, the share of water transport decreases (Vierth, Lindgren and Lindgren, 2018). Theoretical impacts of regulatory efforts on modal choice are shown by Blauwens et al. (Blauwens et al., 2006). Three studies have collected empirical data on a shift to land-based transport, while a further 13 base their findings on theoretical models and simulations. These studies generally take a single environmental measure into account, with 13 studies looking at sulphur emissions and three studies evaluating the introduction of a nitrogen ECA. The studies assess the likelihood of modal shift purely in terms of costs, not looking at other factors like speed and flexibility deemed to be important for shippers. Aggregated results can be found in Table 3-4.

Name of study	Study design	Findings on modal shift	Year, area, NO _x or SO ₂ limits
Consequences of the IMO's new marine fuel sulphur regulations (SMA, 2009)	Scenario analysis using freight model	Modal shift to road and rail depending on scenario: Shipping: -2 to -10% Road: +2 to +6% Rail: +0 to +5%	2015, Sweden, From 1.5% to 0.1%S

Assessment of the impact of the application of new sulphur limits to the Mediterranean and the Atlantic European Seas - Short Study (Kehoe et al., 2010)	Scenario analysis	Short sea shipping: -10% Road market share: +80%	2015, North Sea and Baltic Sea, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
The COMPetitiveness of EuropeAN Short sea freight Shipping compared with road and rail transport (COMPASS, 2010)	Scenario analysis based on secondary data and stakeholder consultation	Shipping: 1-9% changes in transport volumes Main good types affected: Others, metals, agricultural products Main ship type affected: Load-on, Load-off (LoLo ships): 7% modal shift	2015, all European seas, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Analysis of Consequences of Low Sulphur Fuel requirements (Notteboom, Delhay and Vanherle, 2010)	Scenario analysis	Modal shift: 3-50% of volume depending on route and fuel price	2015, North Sea and Baltic Sea, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Baltic NECA - Economic Impacts (Kalli, Repka and Karvonen, 2010)	Qualitative interviews and surveys, scenario analysis	Potential for modal shift from NECA introduction very small to non-existent	2020, Baltic Sea, NECA Tier III
Reducing the sulphur content of shipping fuels further to 0.1 % in the North Sea and Baltic Sea in 2015: Consequences for shipping in this shipping area - Final report (Lemper et al., 2010)	Simulation study with certain corridors, scenario analysis	Estimated amount of modal shift: 600,000 of 2.9 million trailers (22%) will shift directly to land routes or routes with shorter ferry options Main affected routes: To Russia and the Baltic	2015, Baltic and North Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
Study to review assessments undertaken of the revised MARPOL Annex VI regulations (Entec, 2010)	Review of prior studies	Modal shift likely to shorter short sea routes or truck only options	2015, Baltic and North Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1%S

Economic impact assessment of a nitrogen emission control area at the North Sea (EPA, 2012)	Scenario analysis	Modal shifts unlikely	2015, North Sea, NECA Tier III
Consequences of the sulphur directive (SWECO, 2012)	Scenario analysis	Temporary modal shift expected in 2015 (reversed by 2020) Shipping: -21% Heavy road: -8% Rail: +11% Increase of transports to ports outside SECA	2015, 2020, Sweden, From 1.5% to 0.1% S
Modelling modal choice effects of regulation on low-sulphur marine fuels in Northern Europe (Holmgren et al., 2014)	Agent-based simulation study	No modal shift expected to occur	2015, Baltic and North Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1% S
Effects of More Stringent Sulphur Requirements for Sea Transports (Vierth, Karlsson and Mellin, 2015)	Theoretical findings from transport model	Modest shifts expected, sensitive to cost increases for road and rail: Shipping: -0.88 to -2.5% Road: +0,5 to -0.5% Rail: +0.3 to +1.42%	2009 and 2013, Sweden, From 1.5% to 0.1% S
SECA Assessment: Impacts of 2015 SECA marine fuel sulphur limits - First drawings from European experiences (CE Delft, 2016)	Analysis of statistical data	No significant modal shift found	2015, North and Baltic Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1% S
Monitoring Economic Impact of Low Sulphur Requirement ECSA-ESSF survey for ship operators (Deligianni, 2016)	Empirical findings from questionnaires (n=33), interviews, and traffic volume monitoring	Few companies (14.5%) report minor volume losses (in the area of 5-10%), no volume losses according to traffic volume monitoring	2015-2016, North and Baltic Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1% S
Being green on sulphur: targets, measures and side-effects (Kontovas et al., 2016)	Simulation for one specific route	Changes in transport volume found of 5.2% of traffic	2016, specific route on the Mediterranean

			Sea, From 1.0% to 0.1%S
The implications of the new sulphur limits on the European Ro-Ro sector (Zis and Psaraftis, 2017)	Empirical findings from case study	Changes in transport volume found between 2014 and 2015: Between -18 and +20% depending on route	2014-2015, specific routes on North and Baltic Seas, From 1.5% to 0.1%S
The costs and benefits of a nitrogen emission control area in the Baltic and North Seas (Åström et al., 2018)	Theoretical findings from modelling	Changes in transport volumes unlikely	Projections for 2030, North and Baltic Seas, Tier III NECA

Table 3-4: Review of economic studies on modal shift in the North and Baltic Sea areas

Researchers argue that modal shift due to an introduction of Tier III standards for nitrogen oxide emissions is “unlikely” (EPA, 2012) for the North Sea and “very small to non-existent” (Kalli, Repka and Karvonen, 2010) for the Baltic Sea. These findings are supported by Åström et al. (Åström et al., 2018) The likelihood of modal shift due to stricter SO₂ standards is much more debated. While two studies, one of them contracted by an environmental organisation, expect no modal shift (Holmgren et al., 2014, CE Delft, 2016), six others give moderate estimates below 10% of total volume (SMA, 2009, COMPASS, 2010, Kehoe et al., 2010, Vierth, Karlsson and Mellin, 2015, Deligianni, 2016, Kontovas et al., 2016). A third group of studies, two of them contracted by industry interest groups, foresee modal shift in the area of 3-50%, 22% and 21% respectively (Entec, 2010, Lemper et al., 2010, SWECO, 2012). An empirical analysis by Zis and Psaraftis find both significant decreases as well as significant increases in transport volume for trade on the North and Baltic Seas, depending on route. (Zis and Psaraftis, 2017) Determining levels of modal shift is extremely challenging even ex post. Finding out which goods would have been loaded onto ships instead of truck or rail, all things but freight rate staying equal, is difficult, since the price of transport is not all that matters. Also, as shown by Zis and Psaraftis, modal choice seems to be influenced not only by legislative efforts but is influenced by larger economic developments like the fuel price (Zis and Psaraftis, 2017). The complexity of the problem makes estimations extremely challenging and will not allow for accurate observations of the impact of environmental legislation on modal choice. The Danish researchers Harilaos N. Psaraftis and Thalys Zis have extensively been investigating modal shift in short sea shipping. They argue that potential modal shift may be mitigated by shipping companies through various measures including improved fleet design, the use of alternative fuels like liquid natural gas [hereinafter LNG], investments in scrubber systems, and speed reductions. They maintain, however, that the danger of cargo shifting to land-based modes due to increased operational costs and loss of market subsists (Zis and Psaraftis, 2018).

3.5 Prior studies on noncompliance with maritime environmental legislation

Studies on environmental compliance exist for organisations in general (i.e. writings on corporate crime), but are very rare for the commercial shipping industry, with the exclusion of fisheries, where the study of overfishing has received widespread attention. This research gap

may be due to the international character of the industry. A rare exception is a 2003 OECD report, estimating that around 10-15% of the world fleet is operated “in full contravention to the IMO’s body of environmental regulations” (OECD, 2003, p.4). These numbers may in the meantime have become outdated and the report provides no distinction among different company sizes, flag states, areas of operation or other.

Evidence on the practical relevance of noncompliance stems from the annual reports of the Paris MoU on Port State Control. The 2016 report showed that pollution was the number three reason for detention of vessels in European harbours (Paris MoU, 2017). Noncompliance is regularly found with respect to laws on oily water (1.6% of deficiencies), sewage water (0.9%), garbage (1.2%) and air pollution (1.0%), while unlawful anti-fouling coatings are only detected in a negligible number of cases. Ballast water compliance figures in the 2017 report for the first time, amounting to 76 cases of noncompliance, or 0.2% of all deficiencies (Paris MoU, 2018, p.50). Freight ship types with the highest number of deficiencies were general cargo vessels (64.6% of inspections with deficiencies), refrigerated cargo vessels (60.7%) and bulk carriers (53.2%). They also had the highest share of detentions (Paris MoU, 2018, p.48). Certain shipping registers were found to be linked to particularly high numbers of noncompliance, particularly the Shipping Register of Ukraine and the Panama Shipping Registrar (Paris MoU, 2018, p.56). Similarly, certain flags were found to be linked to increased levels of detentions, particularly the flags of Ukraine, Comoros, and the Republic of Moldova. These will be subject to increased controls in the next years and are listed on the black list of flags currently headed by the Republic of Congo (Paris MoU, 2018, p.39). Still, even ships with white-listed flags had a detention rate of 2.5% last year (compared to 16.8% for black-listed flags) (Paris MoU, 2018, p.15). The report on port state controls provides a valuable source of information on noncompliance. Still, as vessels are on average controlled only once a year, inspections are not always focused on compliance with environmental rules and port state control officers mostly control vessels particularly suspicious of noncompliance, these numbers provide limited evidence on the overall level of compliance with environmental legislation within the shipping industry.

Differing from port state control statistics, empirical studies find oil pollution to still be a major area of deficiencies. Scorpecci argues that illegal discharges of heavy fuel oils make for the greatest source of discharges from ships (Scorpecci, 2004, p.7). The 2003 OECD report shows that annual illegal oil discharges amount to more than eight times the oil spilled during the Exxon Valdez disaster (OECD, 2003, p.4). The report also shows that a little less than half of all vessels controlled for the stowage and disposal of oil were in breach of at least one international law (OECD, 2003, p.4). A lack of current data makes it difficult to tell whether these issues persist. Empirical studies on sulphur emissions have increasingly been conducted in recent years. The 2003 OECD study on vessel-source pollution in general was followed up by the 2016 OECD study specifically on sulphur emissions (International Transport Forum and OECD, 2016), which found near-perfect compliance based on port state control inspection records. Noncompliance with SO_x was found to be between 1.5% and 3.5% based on THETIS data (fuel samples taken by port state control) with an average rate of MARPOL Annex VI deficiencies for 2.8% of vessels. Rather high rates of noncompliance were found in ECA countries known for thorough controls (Belgium: 12.5%, Poland: 9%, Germany: 5.5%). To

explain these numbers, the authors state: “However, one could wonder if there is a direct link between the non-compliance rate based on port inspections and the real level of non-compliance, considering the low odds to be caught in certain port states.” (International Transport Forum and OECD, 2016, p.20). Research by Mellqvist et al. via the CompMon project shows compliance levels to be rather lower were controls are expected by the industry. The researchers find SECA compliance to be above 90% in Denmark. Their data shows that territorial outsiders break rules more frequently and that compliance is higher at Great Belt Bridge than Baltic proper. They find that ships rather violate when leaving the SECA than on the way in as there is less risk of being controlled in port states. A point of special interest is that some ships that had installed scrubbers still had high emissions indicating that scrubbers have been switched off. (Mellqvist et al., 2017) This type of behaviour is particularly challenging to contain via port state controls. Data collected from port state controls thus must be treated with caution. A further study by Chalmers University of Technology finds that ships in the English Channel near the SECA border (13%) and the middle of the Baltic Sea (12%) have the highest rates of sulphur violations in Northern Europe. The study shows overall compliance levels to be between 87 and 98 percent from data acquired by remote monitoring. When passing the fixed measurement stations at the Oresund and Great Belt Bridge, a mere 2-5% of vessels are noncompliant with sulphur legislation (Chalmers University of Technology, 2018). A study conducted by Mestl et al. found that following the 2012 reduction in maximum sulphur content in marine fuels from 4.5% to 3.5%, noncompliance has increased greatly from 0.02% in 2011 to 2.3% in 2012 (Mestl et al., 2013, p.6099). Following their argumentation, another increase in noncompliance will likely follow the 2020 decrease in maximum sulphur content.

In an empirical study including a review of ship inspections as well as 50 expert interviews, Sampson et al. find that high levels of noncompliance may mostly be explained by a lack of effective enforcement of laws. They find that main obstacles lie in the difficult identification of fraudulent paperwork, strained budgets and technical problems limiting the use of enforcement mechanisms like sniffer planes, and testing times of laboratories for fuel samples that exceed the time vessels are spending in a certain port. They also find that fuel delivered by refineries does not always meet the specifications of the order, leading to unwitting noncompliance by some, and explicit fraudulent behaviour by others (Sampson et al., 2016). Differences in the effectiveness of port state control inspections were studied by Graziano et al. in 2018. They found that differences among member states of the Paris MoU are significant when it comes to detecting deficiencies and detaining vessels (Graziano et al., 2018). These differences are even more prominent at the international scale, as shown by Knapp and Franses. (Knapp and Franses, 2007) A study by Sampson and Bloor on international port state control inspections concludes that differences in resources and regulatory commitment are so vast between different nations that they judge the global governance of the shipping industry to be a “critical case” (Sampson and Bloor, 2007). Compliance levels published by port state control authorities are thus likely to reflect both the quality of controls as well as the share of environmental deficiencies.

Savings through noncompliant behaviour are challenging to estimate. Scorpecci calls noncompliance with environmental legislation “almost “risk-free” cost cutting” as “these cost

savings have no direct impact on the ship's safety nor its ability to navigate and earn income" (Scorpecci, 2004, p.6). Penalties

Savings are on average 100 000 € per ship per trip for sulphur alone, the OECD estimates, as sanctions are "very limited" and hardly ever surpass the cost savings from noncompliance (International Transport Forum and OECD, 2016, p.42). In extreme cases, savings of up to 400.000 € are possible for a noncompliant vessel compared to a fully compliant one (OECD, 2003, p.5). The OECD report shows that circumventing legislation becomes economically more attractive with increased vessel age as well as with ships that have historically been badly maintained. Scorpecci estimates that for these vessels compliance costs could reach up to 20% of the vessel's revenue (Scorpecci, 2004, p.7). Also, he argues that with new legislative measures coming up compliance costs are likely to increase further from 1.5 up to 3 times the amount of 2004 thus increasing the incentive for noncompliance (Scorpecci, 2004, p.7). The OECD argues that substandard ships that are not sanctioned for their behaviour will have significant competitive advantages on the market, thus putting pressure on other operators to break the laws as well (OECD, 2003, p.5). Sufficiently frequent and thorough controls are thus of importance to ensure compliance and thus a level playing field for the industry. Beyerlin remarks that adequate reporting requirements are needed in order to control for compliance (Beyerlin, Stoll and Wolfrum, 2006, p.283). The OECD demands for penalties to equal at least the costs savings from noncompliance (OECD, 2003, p.6). This seems sound advice but requires that legislators are knowledgeable about said cost savings.

3.6 Prior studies on specific characteristics of the shipping industry

A recent empirical study conducted by Tran and Haasis shows how a continuous enlargement of the world's shipping fleet has resulted in diminishing returns, with economies of scale being outweighed by under-utilisation of slots (an effect of over-capacities), as well as general increases in costs (Tran and Haasis, 2015). A group of German researchers at the Hamburg Institute of International Economics argue that the bubble that has been created will lead to further decreases in freight rates, further investments to be made in the coming years, and further increases in capacity. They explain this development with a prisoner's dilemma, in which individual actors rationally follow strategies to the disadvantage of all. As joint actions of companies are illegal, protected by competition laws, each shipping company will be led to invest in so-called "mega-carriers", ever larger ships providing economies of scale and a way to stay profitable with decreasing freight rates. However, as this is the rational strategy for all shipping companies, ever more inefficient overinvestments will take place (Quitau, et al., 2018, p.9). As shown by Tran and Haasis, these calculations do not lead to expected results, as economies of scale may only be realised under full utilisation.

Developments that are currently visible in the market are threefold. The first development is termed a "cascade effect" and consists of larger ships replacing smaller ships. The second development is one of consolidation, where smaller, less efficient companies are forced out of the market and taken over by larger companies. The third effect is one of strategic alliances forming to increase market power and decrease competition with the aim of increasing freight rates (compare Quitau, et al., 2018, p.10). Keeping these developments in mind it has to be noted that advances in maritime environmental legislation and increased compliance costs put

additional pressure on the industry at a point in time where low freight rates, low returns, fierce competition from overcapacities, and efforts of consolidation already have companies struggling. As can be seen in Figure 3-6, European shipping companies have only a minor share in the growth of the world merchant fleet.

Figure 3-6: World and European merchant fleets in tonnage, 1990-2018 (Author, raw data from UNCTADSTAT, 2018)

A seminal study looking at compliance costs with environmental legislation by type of ship was conducted by Finnish researchers Bachér and Albrecht in 2013. The researchers are the first to distinguish costs from environmental legislation by company type, and further surpass prior studies by taking costs of several environmental measures into account. They find significant differences among vessel types, both regarding overall compliance costs as well as the share of investment and operation costs. Their total compliance cost estimates can be seen in Figure 3-7. The researchers find that compared to other vessels, bulk and crude carriers will carry particularly high costs, with especially investment costs far surpassing compliance costs of container, general cargo, RoRo, and special purpose vessels. Investments to comply with environmental laws may surpass €2 million for a single bulk or crude carrier. The other four types of ships generally face rather limited investment costs to comply with legislation in the range of €200,000 to 700,000, but higher operating costs. Operating costs are much more dependent on vessel size than investments and can be as low as €200,000, but may surpass €2.5 million annually in the case of large Ro-Ro-carriers (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.44).

Figure 3-7: Investment and operating costs for different vessel types for complying with maritime environmental legislation (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.44)

The researchers also provide estimates for different types of legislation. As an example, the costs for distinct types of vessels for complying with sulphur legislation, under the assumption that the entire fleet is operated on MGO, are given in Figure 3-8. The data shows negligible investment costs for all vessel types and overall great similarities across the entire fleet as regards operating costs. Costs are shown to depend on vessel size and tend to be in the same range between €1 and 2 million annually for medium-sized to large bulk, oil, and car carriers, as well as container ships. General cargo ships face slightly lower operational cost increases; Ro-Ro ships have to deal with higher operational cost increases surpassing €2 million annually for large vessels of this type (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.45).

Figure 3-8: Investment and operating costs for different vessel types when operating on MGO to comply with low sulphur legislation (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.45)

Noticeable differences in compliance costs are found by the researchers when analysing ballast water legislation. Here, dissimilar to sulphur legislation, operation costs are negligible, whereas investment costs may range from €250,000 to more than €2 million per vessel. Bulk and crude carriers face by far the steepest cost increases, which may be explained by the fact that they tend to take large amounts of ballast water aboard on empty journeys. Other freight ships, with the exception of extra-large general cargo carriers, face investments volumes of less than €500,000 for ballast water treatment systems. As becomes apparent from Figure 3-9, investment costs are largely independent of vessel size (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.46). The researchers also investigate costs from new laws on discharges of garbage, but do not find any differences among vessel types (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.45).

Figure 3-9: Investment and operating costs for different vessel types when operating mandatory ballast water treatment systems (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013, p.46)

It becomes apparent that the shipping industry is currently, and likely to remain for years to come, in a particularly difficult competitive situation. It is thus likely to be struggling much more with increased compliance costs than at a time of surplus demand and higher freight rates. Environmental laws pose a non-negligible burden on shipping companies and, as becomes apparent from the research conducted by Bachér and Albrecht, pose a burden more on some types of shipping companies than on others. While bulk and crude carriers will face particularly high investment costs from ballast water legislation, Ro-Ro carriers will face comparatively high operating costs due to stricter sulphur emission laws. Looking at total costs, bulk and crude carriers are carrying the highest additional costs and general cargo vessels the lowest burden from maritime environmental legislation.

3.7 Summary and formation of key concepts for primary data collection

An analysis of prior studies reveals great differences with respect to the expected **effects of maritime environmental legislation on compliance costs**. Ballast water treatment, low sulphur operations and double-hull requirements are shown to be the most expensive measures. Sewage water treatment does not play a significant role in commercial freight shipping and the remaining measures have limited cost effects. Academic contributions reviewed found increases in shipping costs from MEL, notably in the range of 14-23% in general vessel construction costs, plus an additional €300,000 to 7 million for mandatory installations like ballast water treatment systems. Furthermore, operational costs were found to increase by some 11-56% of total vessel costs by aggregating results from prior studies. The evidence from prior studies is very strong that environmental legislation does lead to cost increases for the industry. Estimates on the effect size vary considerably and demand further investigation, however. While most studies find an increase in costs, three studies contradict the mainstream findings.

Firstly, two studies on the cost effects of hull coatings with reduced toxicity find that, depending on the specific paint used as well as the frequency of in-water cleaning of the hull, both an increase as well as a decrease in costs is possible (Pagoropoulos et al., 2017, Demirel et al., 2018). Considering the inherent ambivalent environmental effects of hull coatings, this specific issue may constitute a case where cost savings for the companies are linked to benefits for the environment. The third study finding a decrease in costs after new environmental laws for the shipping industry have been passed was published by Zis and Psaraftis in 2017. The researchers found that unexpected decreases in world fuel prices led to a decrease in vessel operation costs right after the introduction of stricter laws on sulphur emissions for the North and Baltic Sea areas in 2015 (Zis and Psaraftis, 2017). Still, researchers predicting cost increases from sulphur laws are likely to be proved correct, as fuel costs are currently increasing. The study of Zis and Psaraftis is of particular importance as the researchers show the great influence of international political and economic developments on the costs of the shipping industry. These may limit the influence of legislators over the socially optimum pricing of fuel.

Prior studies on the **effects of MEL on freight rates** are much scarcer than studies on cost effects but vary similarly in their findings. The only empirical study conducted finds increases in freight rates from stricter sulphur laws amounting to 1-10% for 42.4% of survey participants (with the remaining companies not having raised their freight rates during the period in question) (Deligianni, 2016). The remaining studies are based on theoretical findings from scenario analyses and investigate effects of either stricter SECA or NECA laws. They predict increases in freight rates between 8 and 51% due to low sulphur legislation and increases in the range of 0.2-4.6% due to nitrogen oxide emission limits. Predictions thus range from minor changes to shifts in freight rates of such magnitude as must seriously influence the competitive situation of the industry.

Apart from potential increases in costs and freight rates from maritime environmental legislation, a further economic effect is the possibility of **modal shift**. Despite recent studies suggesting that sea transport is not necessarily the most environmentally friendly transport alternative, there are vast economies of scale linked to vessel-based transport chains, leading to comparatively low pollution per ton of cargo transported. Prior studies suggest that a certain price differential between road and sea transport is necessary to make ships more attractive than trucks, despite their lower flexibility, speed and penetration. Freight rate effects of MEL might lead to a decrease in this price differential and a consequential modal shift. Economic theorists suggest that modal choice depends on the elasticity of demand, with heavy-weight, low-value goods transported on long-distance services often fixed to sea-borne transport. Given such inelasticity, shipping companies are likely to pass cost increases on to their customers without fearing a loss of cargo. Where trip distance and shipment attributes are such as to make other modes of transport feasible and demand is more elastic, economic theory suggests that shipping companies will refrain from passing on cost increases from MEL to customers and will thus actively limit the danger of modal shift where it exists. Also, prior studies suggest that the price of transport, though the most important determinant of modal choice, is not the only determinant and that a reluctance by many companies to change their suppliers might further limit or postpone instances of modal shift. Empirical evidence on modal shift is rather weak. Three prior studies could be identified that have collected empirical data, while another twelve are based

on theoretical models and simulations. The combined effect of several environmental protection measures was not considered, but all studies focus on a single legal measure, notably sulphur or nitrogen oxide emission caps. Theoretical studies suggest that modal shift from Tier III NO_x standards would be very small to non-existent, while estimates on modal shift from sulphur emission caps vary widely across studies. Two studies contracted by environmental organisations find no likelihood of modal shift, while two studies contracted by industry interest groups find likely modal shift of up to 50% of cargo volumes. Studies conducted by academic researchers provide estimates of moderate effects below 10% of cargo volumes. The empirical studies are more similar in their findings. The first study finds no significant modal shift, while the second finds minor losses of cargo in the area of 5-10% for a mere 14.5% of the companies in the sample. The third study finds changes in transport volume in both directions with increases of up to 20% on certain routes and decreases of up to 18% on others, suggesting no clear relationship between environmental laws and modal shift. Empirical studies generally find no effects of MEL on modal choice. The theoretical studies, with 9 out of 12, find modal shift mostly of moderate size. The divergence between empirical and theoretical studies may be explained by the time lag between the introduction of new laws and the effect on the market. Empirical studies aimed at controlling for the effects of sulphur legislation introduced on 1 January 2015 were conducted based on data from 2014 to 2016. Possibly, given overcapacities on the market, shipping companies had not adapted their pricing policies in this short term to account for cost increases. Modal shift in the range predicted by theoretical models may thus only become empirically measurable with a time lag.

Prior studies on **noncompliance** suggest this problem to be pertinent. The 2003 OECD report on noncompliance with maritime environmental legislation already estimated a rate of 10-15% of companies acting in contravention to international laws (OECD, 2003). Current reports by the Paris MoU on Port State Control suggest that most vessels are detained for defaulting on obligations pertaining to oily water. A study by Mestl et al. found that with more stringent legal demands, the rate of noncompliance on the specific measure would also increase (Mestl et al., 2013). This may be explained by the costs of noncompliance, i.e. the risk of detection staying the same. The frequency of controls does not change, while the benefits of noncompliance increase with stricter legislation. If controls stay at the same level, however, while the level of fines is increased, the decision-equation should stay the same. The OECD report suggest, however, that penalties do not equal savings from noncompliance, making the breaking of environmental laws an economically attractive option (OECD, 2003). The Paris MoU requires a vessel or company once found to be in noncompliance to be increasingly controlled thereafter, providing an effective mechanism for legal compliance. When considering noncompliance, it is important to adopt an objective utility approach as suggested by Simpson and Rorie. This approach follows the notion that noncompliance is an effect of rational cost-benefit considerations, but the costs and benefits considered are perceptual, rather than objective (Simpson and Rorie, 2011).

With respect to compliance cost differences for different types of shipping companies, theoretical literature emphasises the **flag state debate**, indicating that certain flag states put a higher emphasis on environmental laws than others. Port state control officers seem to think similarly on this specific feature of vessels, organising flags into white, grey, and black lists

and structuring the frequency of their controls accordingly. Empirical evidence on differences in compliance costs based on company characteristics is scanty. A study by Bachér and Albrecht finds that both overall compliance costs as well as the share of investment and operation costs in total compliance costs, differs with vessel type. The researchers find that bulk and crude carriers incur significantly higher environmental compliance costs than container, general cargo, RoRo, or special purpose vessels. Next to vessel type, compliance costs also depend on vessel size, they argue (Bachér and Albrecht, 2013). The researchers further highlight that cost differences for some types of legislation, specifically laws on ballast water and low sulphur operations, are significant for distinct vessel types, while for other types of legislation, they find no significant differences among vessel types.

A critical effect of MEL can be assumed where a credible danger of modal shift occurs (see Chapter 2.6.2 on modal choice). For the purpose of this study, three categories of effects are defined, namely negligible effects, moderate effects and critical effects. The thresholds for these effects are based on a study commissioned by the European Union to determine the likelihood of modal shift and may be seen in Table 3-5. The COMPASS study assumes that a fuel cost increase of 64% on the Baltic Sea would lead to an increase in total costs between 6% and 29%, depending on vessel type. Under these assumptions, a -5.45% decrease in shipping volumes is found, which amounts to a significant effect. A further modal shift is found when NECAs and measures on CO₂ emissions are introduced leading to an expected shift of 7.7%. Transport volumes will diminish as an effect by 2-12% depending on commodity type, the study claims (COMPASS, 2010, p.68). These figures are sensitive to cost developments in other modes of transport, like cost increases on road transport. Furthermore, shifting behaviour will influence load factors on vessels, making vessels even costlier (COMPASS, 2010, p.77). Relying roughly on the assumptions in the COMPASS study, it is assumed here that increases in voyage costs (consisting mostly of fuel costs) of more than 50% and/or increases in total costs of more than 15% would lead to significant modal shift and changes in trade volumes and would thus have a critical effect on shipping in the North and Baltic Seas. Moderate effects might already be measurable where voyage cost increases of more than 20% and/or total cost increases of more than 5% occur. Any cost increases below these thresholds are considered a negligible effect.

	Negligible effect	Moderate effect	Critical effect
Increase in fuel costs/voyage costs	≥0%	≥20%	≥50%
Increase in total costs	≥0%	≥5%	≥15%

Table 3-5: Definition of negligible, moderate and critical effects of MEL on the shipping industry

The increase in costs estimated in prior studies can be shown to have a moderate to critical effect on the industry. Empirical studies on noncompliance find an increase in deviant behaviour due to increased costs from environmental laws. Overall noncompliance levels are estimated to reach 10-15%. Detention statistics show the importance of illegal oily water discharges, followed by unlawful releases of garbage and air pollution. Studies comparing compliance costs for different types of shipping companies are rare but show that differences exist pertaining to vessel size and type. A further investigation seems necessary.

4 Methodology and research approach

4.1 Introduction and overview

This chapter introduces the exploratory sequential mixed methods approach applied in this thesis. Chapter 4.2 reviews the epistemological stance guiding primary data collection. Methods of data collection and evaluation are discussed in Chapter 4.3. Ethical considerations are explored in Chapter 4.4 and the role of the researcher is evaluated in Chapter 4.5. Chapter 4.6 holds a critique of the methodology applied, followed by an analysis of limitations pertaining to the methods used in Chapter 4.7.

4.2 Epistemological stance

This study is aimed at *comprehending* how environmental legislation affects the shipping industry and *quantifying* the effects on costs and freight rates. These aims relate both to understanding the creation of knowledge as a product of human interaction as well as measuring this knowledge and thereby treating it as something that is verifiable, objective and replicable. The two schools of qualitative and quantitative research both adopt very dissimilar ideas to the nature of knowledge. The researcher believes that both have their justification. There is hard data at the core of the research problem, like increases in costs or freight rates, which are measurable and may be treated as objective information following a positivist epistemology. How much shipping companies know and understand the laws or feel a need to comply with them is related to understanding the subjects involved in the process, however. Knowledge in this respect is negotiated and created among human beings following an interpretative epistemology. The researcher believes that both types of knowledge exist simultaneously, and both need to be explored in order to comprehensively understand the research problem. The research aim may only be reached by mixing qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection, thus applying a pragmatic approach to the nature of knowledge.

4.3 Methods of data collection and evaluation

4.3.1 Overview

To determine how maritime environmental legislation affects shipping companies, a multi-step research design was developed as presented in chapter 1.8 including elements of secondary research as well as qualitative and quantitative primary research. This research design was chosen for its ability to both create and test theory as well as its reliability and validity as discussed in chapter 4.6. A common alternative research design are simulations, with the drawback that results would be based on actual, not perceived cost-benefit considerations. To investigate compliance, Bryant proposes three study designs; either by studying sanction patterns, by observing occurrences of noncompliance or by interviewing concerned parties about correct and incorrect behaviour (Bryant, 1990, p.119). All three approaches are somewhat flawed, as especially with shipping not all deviant behaviour is sanctioned, and observation is little feasible on the open seas. Qualitative research might help in finding motives and in-depth information on compliance but will not produce measurable data. Mixed methods research was applied to overcome drawbacks of individual research methods. Figure 4-1 shows the sequence

of data collection. Data collected was evaluated and results of all three data sources compared to achieve a comprehensive picture and thorough understanding of the research problem.

Figure 4-1: Sequence of data collection

Firstly, a thorough **analysis of literature** was conducted to identify pertinent theoretical concepts and characterise relevant variables. This review led to the identification of seven fields of maritime environmental legislation which could influence the costs of shipping companies. A theoretical relationship among environmental compliance costs, freight rates, and modal choice was established and secondary data on these variables identified and discussed. Lastly, data on noncompliance with legislation as well as on the specific characteristics of, and differences within, the shipping industry with respect to MEL were critically reviewed.

In a second step of analysis, all information gathered by reviewing secondary sources was mirrored with **expert opinions**. A wide and diverse group of twelve experts representing all major groups of stakeholders was interviewed. Experts represented different types and sizes of shipowners and operators, European and national legislators, administrators, environmental, shipping and trade associations, maritime personnel, and classification societies. Qualitative content analysis using MaxQDA was conducted to advance the theoretical model from literature analysis. Several fields of maritime environmental legislation identified in step 1 were found to be of little or no practical significance. The relationship between costs and freight rates was challenged and remained unclear. The complex situation between shipowner and operator was reviewed and included in the model. Determinants of compliance and relevant characteristics of companies were elaborated on and included in the model.

In a third step of analysis a **questionnaire** was developed to acquire data from shipping companies to test and validate variables and causal relations among them as found in the theoretical framework. Shipping companies trading on the North and Baltic Seas of varied sizes and active in different fields of business were chosen as a sample and questionnaires were sent out based on a predefined process. Data acquired was fed into SPSS, R, and SmartPLS to calculate effect sizes of the variables identified and test the causal relations among the them. The influence of noncompliance was thoroughly investigated and quantified. Also, data was used to sketch out compliance costs of ten sample companies to provide a deeper understanding of differences among market actors. Mechanisms how maritime environmental legislation influences costs of shipowners and operators, freight rates and trade were identified with a specific focus on the different business models of shipping companies. Most affected and least affected groups were identified as a result, where possible.

4.3.2 The exploratory expert interviews

The aim of qualitative data collection was to verify the set of variables identified from the literature and the relations among them as well as to further develop and enhance the theoretical framework depicted in Figure 2-22. The qualitative study is necessary to determine mechanisms at play when new environmental laws are passed, how they impact the shipping industry, and how they influence freight rates. Qualitative analysis helps to achieve a deeper understanding of the variables and their relation from the specific point of view of a certain expert (see Kuckartz, 2010, Denzin and Lincoln, 2017 on the value of qualitative research).

Semi-structured expert interviews were chosen as an appropriate method for exploration. With the use of interview guides, it could be made sure that on the one hand all areas of interest would be dealt with during the interview and a number of pre-defined open ended questions would be discussed, while at the same time the researcher had the liberty to elaborate on a certain topic, probe the interviewee, follow up on what was being said, but also dismiss certain questions if the interviewee was not knowledgeable about a certain topic. This liberty was of utmost importance due to the large variety of experts that were chosen for the data collection. The respective interview guides used can be found in Annex B1 and B2.

Sampling was achieved by drawing up a map of all important stakeholder groups (see Figure 4-2) and choosing experts from different groups that would likely have different, if not opposing views on the research question. “Experts” were individuals knowledgeable about the research problem. Potential participants were identified as experts based on the role prescribed to them by society. They are not only “objectively” in possession of expert knowledge, but their knowledge is also socially relevant, meaning that they hold an official position with decision-making competences. This social-representative approach makes sure that the construction of experts is not only based on the author’s personal criteria but is objectively based on the construction of experts by society. Criteria for the selection of participants were as follows:

- At least 5 years working experience to ensure adequate experience and reliable knowledge on the research topic
- Representative function in the company/organisation to fulfil the social expert definition
- Based in the European Union to do justice to the research focus
- Working within the shipping industry, maritime politics or representing marine environmental interests

Figure 4-2: Main stakeholder groups and groups sampled for interview process (blue)

A purposeful sampling procedure was applied to the selection of experts. Sampling of contrasting cases was at the heart of the sampling procedure, meaning that experts came from diverse backgrounds representing a variety of stakeholder interests and being characterised by distinct characteristics. Most interviewees were selected based on pre-set requirements. However, interviewed experts had the opportunity to name other experts or relevant organisations in the field, leaving a small margin for snowball sampling (also referred to as network or chain sampling), while also verifying the main stakeholder groups identified and making sure to include particularly prominent and knowledgeable persons in the field into the sample. The sample thus developed from an original group of experts identified based on main stakeholder groups to the larger sample shown in Table 4-1. Experts within the groups were chosen for their superior knowledge in the field. Among the main stakeholder groups, banks, logistics companies, and the general public were not chosen as interview partners, because they were deemed to have comparatively little knowledge on the research questions QUA1 to QUA3. A specification of the knowledge claims of experts in the sample can be seen here:

No	Knowledge claim of experts
1	Environmental shipping law expert at trade association
2	Environmental law expert at vessel classification society
3	Shipping expert at environmental organisation
4	Environmental expert at small short sea shipping company
5	Environmental expert at large short sea shipping company

6	Environmental expert at shipping association
7	Environmental expert at large container carrier
8	Expert on shipping and the environment at national legislator
9	Captain for a large shipping company, responsible for environmental laws aboard
10	Environmental expert at large bulk carrier
11	Environmental expert at small container carrier
12	Expert on shipping and the environment at European legislator

Table 4-1: Knowledge claims of experts

Access to the field was gained in part by establishing a standing communication to the German Shipowners' Association. The association was particularly helpful in contacting four shipowners and operators according to the researcher's specifications of company size and business sector. In a few cases, personal contacts of the researcher or contacts established at business and research conferences were employed. Furthermore, all experts were encouraged at the end of the interview to provide names and details of further knowledgeable persons. These were contacted if they fit the research sample and were likely to provide advanced expert knowledge related to the research questions. Other experts were contacted via email and telephone by the researcher directly and encouraged to collaborate without any other parties being involved in the process. The leaflet used to explain the study can be found in Annex B3.

Interviews were conducted face to face whenever feasible. Interviewees located in other European countries were probed for their position via telephone. Three interviews were conducted at a distance. The exclusion of body language makes these different from personal interviews and answers are thus not fully compatible. Telephone interviews led to a wealth of information and were much more focused with more precise language being used. There was less straying from the topic and fewer interruptions, unrelated comments and talk on personal issues. However, information that was deemed to have a higher level of confidentiality was also more seldomly given than during personal interviews. Personal interviews took longer on average, in the range of 90 to 120 minutes compared to roughly 60 minutes for the telephone interviews. During personal interviews, interruptions occurred much more often, but the interviewees seemed more at ease. All interviews took place in the natural work surroundings of the experts in all but two cases. In one, the interviewee was called in a hotel room on a business trip; another interview took place in the office of the researcher. No significant differences could be noticed between these and other interviews apart from slightly more interruptions occurring when interviews took place at the destined worktable of an expert. Most experts chose a conference room at their office as the place for the interview which was experienced as a very beneficial setting by the researcher.

All interviews were **fully transcribed** following the conceptual notion of Kuckartz et al. to "smoothen" the language and to focus on the content of statements made (Kuckartz et al., 2007). Interviews were transcribed in the original language they were conducted in and then translated into English. Transcription observed a system of rules ensuring consistent results closely following the approach by Dresing and Pehl (Dresing and Pehl, 2013, p.21). Defining a system of transcription was of particular importance as the main researcher was supported in this work by student assistants. Assistants signed confidentiality notices and their work was thoroughly

rechecked by the researcher. The rules of transcription applied may be found in Annex B5. All but two interviews were conducted in German language, the remainder in English language. Thus, translations of 10 out of 12 interview transcripts were necessary. All interview transcripts in English language can be found in Annex B6. In the translations, the meaning of a sentence was translated instead of conducting a word by word translation. It must be emphasised, however, that these translations already contain an element of interpretation, as words chosen are reflecting the biased view of the main researcher. In order to ensure reliability of results, random parts of the translated documents and all quotations used in the evaluation chapter of this thesis were rechecked by another researcher. An elimination of biased translation was thus attempted. Software used for the analysis of qualitative data was F4 to support the transcription process, Microsoft Word for transcription and translation of interviews, and MaxQDA to support qualitative content analysis.

Qualitative content analysis was chosen as an evaluation method for the expert interviews as it is characterised by a systematic procedure. Material was analysed step-by-step based on a system of categories that is premised on a theoretical framework (Mayring, 2002, p.114). It is thus an approach that inhibits arbitrary and biased conclusions. The steps were as follows:

1. Developing a coding frame
2. Coding the material
3. Analysing the content

The definition of main and sub-categories was achieved based on the proposed system by Schreier (Schreier, 2012, p.94) with a number of modifications as described below. The main categories as well as some of the sub-categories were derived in a concept-driven way and thus follow a deductive approach to knowledge generation. They were based on the interview guide that was used for data collection and thus build on the theoretical concept developed from the literature. Variables identified from the literature as well as hypotheses on the causal mechanisms among them formed the basis for the coding frame. This approach is described by Gläser and Laudel (Gläser and Laudel, 2010, p.201). Main categories and main ideas behind are shown in Table 4-2:

Nr	Main category	Ideas behind	Colour code
1	Environmental legislation	Which legislative aims are mentioned by interviewees? Which environmental issues are important to them?	black
2	Legal framework	How significant is environmental legislation to the industry? In how far is the need for legislation accepted?	orange
3	Information	Is the industry aware of legislation? Do they understand what is expected of them?	light green
4	Effects	What are the effects of legislation on internal costs, freight rates and overall trade flows?	red
5	Compliance	How high is the level of compliance with the laws?	green

		Are actors willing to comply? Do they feel a need to comply? How effective are enforcement and controls? Are technological options available to make compliance possible?	
6	Differences	Are there differences among operators regarding effects of legislation?	blue
7	Modal shift	How likely is modal shift?	light blue
8	Market structure	Will there be changes in maritime transport demand? Will there be changes in maritime transport supply?	violet

Table 4-2: Main categories identified from theoretical model

Subcategories derived from theory are supplemented by categories developed from primary data, inductively creating knowledge. This approach closely follows the concept described by Schreier (Schreier, 2012, pp.41, 84, 87). The same course of action is furthermore recommended by Kuckartz specifically for structured guideline interviews (Kuckartz, 2010, p.204). A number of different forms of coding are discussed in the literature (for a comparison see Kuckartz, 2010, p.59). Thematic coding is used in order to inductively create subcategories from the data. Subcategories are first of all created each time a new aspect is mentioned within the trial coding interviews. The strategy of **subsumption** as described by Mayring (2010) is used at the end of the trial coding phase. Subcategories are summarised to common categories in order to better structure the material and condense content. New categories may, however, emerge during the main coding as well and will be included in the coding frame. The deductively and inductively developed coding frame with subcategories already condensed can be found in Annex B7. Definitions of categories can be found in Annex B8.

Units of coding are one piece of information. A thematic segmentation approach is thus used with each coding unit representing one piece of content. Context units are the preceding interview question and the full answer of the interviewee. These are not marked in the material but considered as context when analysing and interpreting findings. Findings are organised by research questions, whereas category 1 and 2 will mainly be employed to answer research question QUAL1. QUAL2 will mainly draw on categories 3 and 4 and QUAL3 will be answered based on information from category 5. Two categories emerged during the research process that could significantly influence the research model, namely modal shift (category 6) and differences among operators (category 7). Category 8 will serve to underline arguments made in other categories. The findings of this category are not in itself important to the research questions but serve as background information.

4.3.3 The self-completion questionnaire

The quantitative study aims at validating the model developed from literature and the qualitative study. **Standardised self-completion questionnaires** were chosen as a suitable data collection method, as they provided the possibility of online distribution and allowed for large, geographically dispersed, samples. The response rate for online surveys tends to be rather low,

estimated by Saunders et al. to reach 30-50% for web-based surveys within organisations, but may be lower than 10%, the researchers argue (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015, p.441). It is a rather cost-effective way of collecting data and the likelihood of distortion or contamination of answers is low, especially as no intervention by the researcher is possible. Also, if respondents are notified via email, the likelihood that the right person responds to the questionnaire is rather higher than with postal questionnaires (for further comparison of different questionnaire methods see Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015, p.441). Considerations on designing the questionnaire may be found in Annex C1 and the questionnaire itself in Annex C2. Both an English as well as a German-language version were provided to participants. A structured list of survey variables is presented in Annex C3.

Purposive sampling was employed when choosing participants from the accessible population. The accessible population consisted of all shipping companies that were either listed with one of the shipowner associations supporting the study, or whose contact information was available online through industry directories or on company websites. A full list of contact details can be found in Annex C4. Those companies who did not have their contact information listed were not part of the accessible population, according to the definition of Patten (Patten, 2014, Chapter 8), particularly noticeable in the case of Russian shipping companies. Among the accessible population, participants had to meet a number of eligibility criteria. They had to be

- Either owning or operating vessels
- Active in the commercial trading of goods (no passenger transport, fisheries or military vessels)
- Active in the specially protected North and Baltic Sea areas (this criterium was approximated by selecting companies that were listed in shipping registries of countries bordering the North or Baltic Sea)
- Willing to take part in the study

As the number of companies fitting these criteria was rather small, every company that fitted was included in the sample and hard work was put in by the main researcher and a student assistant to invite and encourage as many as possible among this sample to willingly volunteer for participation in the study. A tabular description of the efforts taken can be found in Annex C5.

Sampling bias exists. Due to the geographical location of the researcher in Hamburg, German shipping companies were much more exposed to the study and had a higher propensity to take part. Although all shipowner associations along the Northern European seas were contacted for support, the study was only advertised by three shipowner associations to their members, namely the German, Danish and Lithuanian shipowner associations. In conjunction with the total number of shipping companies located in these countries, their marketing efforts explain the high number of both German and Danish shipping companies in the sample. Also, personalised contact information was much easier to obtain for Scandinavian countries, whereas especially contact details for Russian and Baltic shipping companies were particularly difficult to come by, constituting a sampling bias. The survey was available both in an online as well as an offline version, not necessitating computer skills, but an email address had to be available for a

company to be included in the sample. An overview of survey participants is provided in Annex C6. Annex C7 includes a characterisation of participants.

It was crucial to the present research that participants would answer the questions truthfully, even if they dealt with criminal behaviour. Dillman et al. argue that with self-completion questionnaires, participants are less likely to give socially desirable answers, as they are not in direct contact with the researcher and their answers stay anonymous (Dillman, Smyth and Christian, 2014). Still, self-reported compliance attitudes and compliance behaviour are likely to be influenced by **social-desirability bias (SDB)** to some extent, leading to underreporting of noncompliance (Brace, 2013, p.210). Studying perceptions on compliance, 95.3% of participants reported that the phrase “My company would not do anything that is against the law” was “absolutely true”. Research on SDB shows that simply asking participants for honesty is to little avail to overcome the bias (Phillips and Clancy, 1972). Techniques used in this survey are the omission of a respondent identifier, assurances of confidentiality, anonymous data collection via an online survey tool or postal self-completion questionnaires, and indirect questioning. In a review of prior studies Fisher found that indirect questioning reduced SDB on variables subject to social influence and that subjects effectively projected their beliefs and evaluations to indirect response situations (Fisher, 1993). Brace presents indirect questioning as a viable method to overcome SDB, but highlights the danger that the researcher may not be sure about the percentage of participants who projected their own behaviour onto others and participants who honestly reported their judgement of others (Brace, 2013, p.217). Being aware of this danger, indirect questioning was used to determine levels of compliance with mandatory MEL and build a compliance index.

Saunders et al. argue that questionnaire design influences reliability and validity of data collected, but also the **response rate** (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015, p.439). This predicament was extensively considered by the researcher when making choices on the length of the questionnaire as well as the complexity of questions included. In designing a 12-page questionnaire including a rather elaborate collection of internal company data, such as data on costs and freight rates, the researcher aimed to collect data of particularly high value for answering the research questions at the expense of a higher non-participation and drop-out rate. To accommodate participants, the researcher developed questions that were highly informative to the research aim, while protecting privacy and sensitive data of companies. Instead of requesting full company data, most questions were aimed at one single vessel of the company. As participants did not have to provide any information apart from the vessel type, it was and will be impossible for the researcher or third parties to infer which company provided the data.

Questionnaire data was collected via an online survey tool called Questionpro. The questionnaire was available online both in German and English language and participants were told in the introductory email that they could request a paper copy from the researcher as well. However, no such request was made. The survey tool was online from September 2017 until the end of February 2018, allowing shipping companies to enter their data over a six-months-period during which various advertisement efforts were made. (see Annex C5) Evaluation was done by downloading raw data from Questionpro to Microsoft Excel, editing and cleaning the dataset and importing data to SPSS and R for statistical analysis. Furthermore, data on determinants of compliance was prepared for and imported into SmartPLS for partial least

squares analysis. Editing was done consistently following pre-determined rules to achieve integrity of data. Answers were checked for their completeness and consistency and obvious erroneous responses were eliminated in line with recommendations by Zikmund (Zikmund et al., 2012, p.460). Lastly, data was in parts recoded to facilitate the import into statistical programmes.

Data provided by shipping companies has been inspected for **inaccuracies** by the researcher before beginning with statistical analysis. According to the online survey tool Questionpro, the questionnaire has been opened 229 times between 1 September 2017 and 28 February 2018. Informed consent was given by 149 companies after reading through the introductory section, thus in a first step all participants that had not given their consent to participate in the study were eliminated from the sample. Despite giving their consent, a further 28 questionnaires were handed in without a single question answered. These were eliminated from the sample as well. The variable ECAOperations was used as a criterion to test data consistency. Two companies stated that their vessels spend 0% of their time within Emission Control Areas. As operations within North and Baltic sea areas was a sampling criterion, these were eliminated from the dataset. One other company stated that they owned 0 vessels and operated 0 vessels, not meeting the sampling criteria. This left 117 questionnaires with which to start statistical analysis.

Erroneous values are frequently observed in self-administered surveys. In the present study it was found that answers at times contained double entries where only a single entry made sense. For the question “How many vessels does your company own?” in questionnaire No 2, for example, both the answers “10-19” and “20-49” were chosen by the participant. Drawing on knowledge about the complex organisational structures in the shipping industry, it is assumed here that the participant has two organisational levels in mind, that is 10-19 ships are owned by the national subdivision, but the international company owns some 20-49 ships. As the researcher is interested in company size in terms of availability of knowledge and financial resources, it is assumed here that a larger structure in the background might provide such resources to the local organisational level. The larger number chosen is thus presumed to be correct for the purpose of this study. The same applies to the variable VesselsOperated. For VesseltypeChosen, when two types were chosen it was assumed that the values given were valid for both types. The first one was then selected by default. For other variables such as SurplusOperated and TotalCostDevelopment, where double entries occurred the data was omitted from the questionnaire, as no presumption could soundly be made as to which entry was closer to the truth. A percentage cost change was only taken into account when either ‘increase’ or ‘decrease’ was selected. Values of percentage change given in connection with ‘stay roughly the same’ were omitted, as they showed data inconsistencies. When two values for percentage cost changes were given, the more conservative estimate was chosen. The same was done for other variables, like AwarenessLegislation. For the variable FlagState, when two flag states were named, the first one named was entered. Twice the flag state given was “Madeira”. As Madeira is a part of Portugal, this entry was replaced for Portugal. The same applies to CentralManagement – where a town was named, the respective country was entered instead; where two countries were named, the first was chosen. Hongkong was replaced by China. With respect to total vessel costs, only the answers where 100 per cent of the costs were distributed were taken into account. On two occasions, participants had distributed less than

100 per cent, but had provided data for all 5 cost categories. In these cases, the values were proportionately increased to reach 100%. Where more or less than 100 per cent were distributed and less than 5 values were given, the data was eliminated from the sample as inconclusive.

Microsoft Excel was used to **recode variables**, making them comparable, bringing them in a workable order or condensing information. As an example, for question 1 “How many vessels does your company own?”, QuestionPro would automatically collect data on six different items, starting with the item “Zero” and recording a true-or-false value for the company. These six items were condensed to form a single variable with six possible answer categories. Furthermore, new variables were formed where appropriate. The variable OwnerType was calculated from the variables VesselsOwned and VesselsOperated to determine whether the company both owned and operated vessels are whether they were more active in the one field than the other. If data was inconclusive due to missing values, the variables CharterTypeVesselsOwned and CharterTypeVesselsOperated were taken into consideration. If these provided a clear picture as to owner type, data was added accordingly.

Missing values are frequent in the current study, which may be explained largely by the sensitivity of the information demanded. Participants were particularly wary of providing internal company data, like information on costs and freight rates. Similarly, questions on compliance behaviour led to a limited number of companies providing answers on all items, which may be explained with the delicacy of the issue. Furthermore, the length of the questionnaire as well as the method of data collection likely influenced the number of early drop-outs. Different from an interview situation, where personal interaction largely prevents incomplete answers, an anonymous online questionnaire may be exited at any time without repercussions. This anonymity was crucial in being able to collect sensitive and unbiased information at all, however. Missing data has been dealt with in two different ways. Mean value replacement was applied when less than 5% of values were missing for an indicator. Other missing data was dealt with by pairwise deletion. Although this might lead to biased results based on different sample sizes per indicator, it seems the best choice in light of the data’s many missing values. In these cases, mean value replacement would lead to a decrease in variability and thus explanatory power of the data and casewise deletion would further shrink the already small dataset.

With respect to data analysis, **statistical analysis** is used here with the purpose of implementing evidence-based practice (EBP), that is providing legislators with statistical results to help inform their future decisions. Collecting and analysing data on compliance costs with maritime environmental legislation served the purpose of providing policy recommendations, reducing guesswork on a hard-to-grasp industry and supporting plausible, evidence-based policy making in the future. By including both questions on the period from 1 January 2015 to 1 September 2017, as well as questions on expectations for the future, the effects of existing legislation could be evaluated and compared with what companies believed the future would bring. SPSS and R served as tools to support both descriptive, as well as multivariate data analysis. As the research at hand is characterised by multiple independent and dependent variables on metric scales, structural equation modelling is chosen as an appropriate method of data analysis (compare Zikmund et al., 2012, p.585).

Structural equation modelling [hereinafter: SEM] was used to test the validity of compliance models developed from qualitative content analysis. It may be applied to assess the unobservable latent constructs stemming from the qualitative model. Within SEM, partial least squares [hereinafter: PLS] was chosen as a modelling technique, as it proves apt to deal with specific challenges of the data at hand. PLS consists of a series of ordinary least squares (OLS) analyses and is a two-stage technique where first the outer model is evaluated in terms of reliability and validity and then the inner model is assessed. This structural equation modelling technique is able to handle small sample sizes, has minimal demand on measurement scales, can deal with violations of the normality distribution assumption and is robust with respect to multicollinearity (Wold et al. 1984). It also treats proxy variables as approximations of the constructs they replace, which is very fitting in this study, and makes it a superior method to CB-SEM for the study at hand (Hair, Jr. et al. 2018, 16). PLS may both be used to test theories and find relationships among variables. It may be distinguished from more traditional methods of data analysis such as multiple regression in being able to analyse both manifest and latent variables alike. Unobservable variables may thus be measured indirectly (Hair, Jr. et al. 2018, 3). Measurement errors in observed variables may also be accounted for (Chin 1998). The characteristics and benefits of PLS-SEM are well explained by Hair et al. (Hair, Jr. et al. 2018). One drawback is the lack of a global goodness-of-fit measure. Henseler and Sarstedt introduced the standardised root mean square residual, SRMR, which is used here to measure goodness of fit (Henseler and Sarstedt 2013). The consistency of parameter estimates is another issue that needs to be accounted for. Parameter accuracy is viable, however, when measurement models meet certain standards, i.e. having four or more indicators with indicator loadings of ≥ 0.7 (Astrachan, Patel, and Wanzenried 2014). These standards must be taken into account to ensure parameter accuracy.

With respect to **sample size**, constructs on compliance were based on a minimum of 36 companies providing data. Companies having provided information on less than 85% of indicators were deleted from the sample for the purpose of analysis, leaving 43 companies in the dataset. Following the 10-times rule by Barclay et al., sample size should equal at least 10 times the largest number of structural paths directed at a particular construct in the structural model (Barclay, Thompson, and Higgins 1995). As becomes apparent from the path model, latent variables are built upon five indicators at most, making $n=43$ a barely acceptable number. Results thus need to be treated with great care, as the rough guideline provided by Barclay et al. for minimum sample size is not met. Hair et al. suggest, however, to deviate from this rough guideline using means of power analysis on the part of the model with the largest number of predictors as an indicator for minimum sample size (Hair, Jr. et al. 2018, 24). Following calculations by Cohen, with the maximum number of independent variables being five, 37 observations would be needed to achieve a statistical power of 80% for detecting R^2 values of at least 0.25 (with a 10% probability of error) (J. Cohen 1992). The sample size is thus deemed acceptable in the light of this being an exploratory study on a sensitive topic in a seclusive industry.

Three steps were taken in order to derive knowledge on economic effects of environmental legislation on the shipping industry. First two-dimensional graphs were used to model simple relationships of a qualitative nature among variables identified. Subsequently, equations or

functions were identified to quantify the relationships shown in the models. In a last step, theoretical relationships were formally tested by way of empirical analysis using data collected from shipping companies via questionnaires. This work is based on two anticipated possible outcomes. The null hypotheses H_0 are tested against the alternative hypotheses H_A .

4.3.4 Obstacles to data collection

A significant obstacle to data collection lies in the nature of this research, especially in its focus on compliance with the laws. Parker and Nielsen argue that “it will often not be in the firms’ interest to open up their responses to regulation to external researchers” especially when they deviate from socially desirable conduct. Also, “the range of factors that are hypothesised to influence compliance are so complex and interrelated that it is very difficult to holistically test them all” (Parker and Nielsen, 2011, p.6). The researcher is very much aware of the challenges associated with studying compliance but feels that the issue is pertinent to studying economic effects of regulation and should not be disregarded. Concerned parties aware of incorrect behaviour may not wish to provide any information on their own conduct or the conduct of others known to them. Bryant explains that suspects not complying with the law are especially hard to study, as they are interested in privacy and secrecy, are fearful of being caught and often influenced by personal motivations in their choice to deviate. They are fearful of a public discussion of their behaviour. (Bryant, 1990, p. 120). Replication of results is often difficult. Kelly discusses specific problems regarding the person of the interviewer when studying deviant behaviour. Maintaining objectivity by keeping a certain distance to the subjects is crucially important while the interviewee should not feel pressured or threatened by the interviewer (Kelly, 1982). Studying noncompliance might also bring about ethical issues for the researcher, as he might get to know about criminal behaviour that has happened or will happen in the future. Usually, however, interviewees will make sure not to incriminate themselves while being recorded. Studying noncompliance is a choice among three inchoate alternatives. Still, as deviant behaviour may influence the economic equation behind legislation, tentative insights are better than no insights at all.

4.4 Ethical considerations

During qualitative data collection, experts were provided with a detailed consent form prior to the interview. It stated the purpose and associated risks of the research, and informed consent had to be given before the interview was conducted. The research consent form can be found in Annex B4. Every effort was made to ensure the confidentiality of personal data. Anonymisation in the form of encryption of names, positions and organisations was used at the data interpretation and publication stages and experts were referred to by number and knowledge claim only. Owing to their exposed positions, all experts in the study were used to interview situations similar to the one they were placed in for this research. As experts held leading political or organisational positions, they were trusted with understanding the nature of this research and potential consequences of participation.

With respect to the quantitative study, the research was based on informed consent by way of a detailed letter explaining the purpose and associated risks of the research. Explicit consent to participate in the study had to be given before the questionnaire could be accessed. Data was

gathered via an online tool and paper copies send to the researcher by post. Participants were entirely free in their choice to participate, answer a part of the questionnaire or quit the study whenever they liked. No personal contact between the researcher and the respective companies was established while answering the questions, thus no pressure could be exercised. No personal data was gathered during the study and due to the anonymous way of collecting data it was not possible to draw conclusions as to who participated in the study. Nonetheless, data collected has been safely stored on a password-protected computer and has only been published in an aggregated, completely anonymised manner.

4.5 Role of the researcher

The role of the researcher in the qualitative phase of the study is to investigate the multiple realities of study participants. Given that knowledge is viewed as context-specific and value-bound, the researcher influences the research outcome by becoming involved in the subjective reality of participants and interacting with them in expert interviews (compare Bloomberg and Volpe, 2012, p.28 et sqq). The date, time and place of the interview influence the outcome as much as the order of questions and the emphasis the researcher puts on certain issues. The cultural and social background of the researcher does not only influence the choice of research questions and the way research is conducted, but also the interpretation of results. As the researcher has grown up close to the sea, has long lived in the port city of Hamburg, holds a skipper's licence and has studied International Business and Foreign Trade, she is likely positively biased towards the shipping industry, globalisation and international trade. On the other hand, she grew up in a family of Green Party voters, has been a member of an environmental organisation and has small children of her own, biasing her towards stricter laws for environmental protection. Experts taking part in the study are also likely to be biased depending on their current organisational context and previous experiences. The information they choose to provide during interviews and the way they answer questions is also likely influenced by the researcher being rather young, female, previously not known to them, affiliated to a university and other factors related to the person of the researcher.

Furthermore, the researcher is already influencing the study participants by the area of research investigated and the research questions posed. A case in point can be seen when studying the following answer by an interviewed expert: "It is of relevance and something is obviously changing, otherwise you would not study whether there are any shifts in transport with your thesis." (T7, para 118), arguing that modal shift must be relevant supported by the evidence that the researcher is studying whether it is relevant. The interviewee presents himself to be positively biased towards modal shift by influence of the researcher. Data acquired through an interview process must thus be treated with great caution due to the highly relational way the data was collected.

In the second quantitative phase the results are much less dependent on the person of the researcher. The aim was to acquire objective information. Questionnaires were provided via post and an online survey tool, limiting the contact between researcher and study participant to a standardised email and in some cases telephonic reminders to take part in the study. Previous experiences of the researcher also played a much smaller role in interpreting the results of the

quantitative study. Empirical quantitative studies are significantly less prone to researcher bias than qualitative ones and statistical analysis of quantitative data serves as an important control to researcher bias likely prevalent during the qualitative part of the research process.

4.6 Critique of methodology

An important consideration in academic research is the validity and reliability of findings. Validity refers to the appropriateness of the measures used, generalisability of the findings and accuracy of the analysis, while reliability is concerned with replicability and consistency (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015, p.202). Validity in turn can be differentiated into measurement validity, internal and external validity, all of which will be discussed in this chapter. Reliability likewise refers to both internal and external reliability. With mixed methods research such as the present one, it needs to be considered in how far these concepts may be applied both to quantitative as well as to qualitative methods. This discussion links back to the differences in research paradigms highlighted in Chapter 4.2. While the quality indicator reliability applies equally to both qualitative and quantitative research, qualitative validity differs from quantitative validity (Creswell, 2014, p.201). Definitions of these indicators as applied here are presented in Table 4-3.

Quality indicator	Definition
Internal reliability	Consistency during the research project, achieved by making use of multiple researchers in data collection and analysis, with the aim of reducing researcher bias
External reliability	Consistency of findings, if data collection and analysis are repeated at another time or by another researcher
Qualitative validity	Accuracy of the findings, shown by trustworthiness, authenticity, and credibility
Measurement validity	Findings represent the reality of what is being measured, including face validity, construct validity, content validity and predictive validity
Internal validity	Research accurately demonstrates causal relationships
External validity	Research may be generalised to other relevant settings or groups

Table 4-3: Definition of indicators to ensure research quality (based on Creswell, 2014, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015)

Although the research was principally carried out by a single researcher, extensive steps were taken to ensure **internal reliability**. Three of the twelve interview transcripts used for qualitative content analysis were coded independently from the researcher by a student assistant and then compared to the codings of the principal researcher to ensure that the codings used were applied consistently, were clearly defined and left little room for interpretation. In addition, the researcher met twice-monthly in a coding group with two other researchers involved in qualitative research to discuss and strengthen the definition of codes. A respective agreement on the confidential treatment of data can be found in Annex B9. These meetings involved frequent blind-codings by the other two researchers of particularly difficult passages in the transcripts, thus reducing researcher bias. A third way to promote stability of the analysis

of qualitative data was the writing of memos to ensure that the researcher would apply the same standards for codings, analysing and interpreting the data over time. Questionnaire data was collected anonymously via an online survey tool, leaving little room for researcher bias.

External reliability was harder to achieve, as the researcher conducted the expert interviews in person, making an elimination of both participant and researcher bias impossible. As the interviews were only semi-structured, the researcher was bound to let her own experiences and prior knowledge on the subject influence the course of the interviews. Similarly, the interviewees were bound to be influenced by the person of the researcher, as well as their own recent experiences, the interview setting, and information experts might just have received from colleagues or other sources. It is thus likely that a different researcher would lead the discussion in a slightly different direction and might come up with different results. External reliability was supported by relying on the same guiding questions in each interview but may not have been fully achieved. Most crucially, the interviews took place in the six months before the introduction of stricter sulphur limits for the shipping industry. When conducting the study at a different point in time, it is very likely that participants would focus less on sulphur legislation and more on other legal issues dominating the news. Being aware of these threats, the researcher conducted a confirmatory quantitative analysis by way of questionnaire data. Excluding any contact between researcher and participants during data collection in this study and using statistical methods to evaluate data, external reliability of the quantitative study is high. Final results of the mixed methods study should thus lead to reliable findings.

The concept of validity is understood differently in qualitative and quantitative research. **Qualitative validity** is achieved where the findings are accurate from the standpoint of the researcher (Creswell, 2014, p.201). Creswell proposes to combine several strategies to achieve qualitative validity, starting with combining different sources of data. This strategy has been applied in the current research, increasing the validity of the study by converging findings from qualitative interviews with quantitative data and structured literature analysis. The next strategy employed here is the use of “rich, thick description” (Creswell, 2014, p.201) to convey findings, providing the reader with the possibility to closely follow the line of argument, again increasing validity. Thirdly, the role of the researcher and a potential bias is reflected on in Chapter 4.5. Creswell further proposes to present discrepant information running counter to the main theme, an advice that is closely followed in the qualitative analysis. Lastly, the researcher has applied the strategy to spend a prolonged time in the field, researching environmental legislation for the shipping industry for a total period of six years, getting into close contact with the research subjects, and visiting not only academic research conferences, but also industry conferences like the ICS International Shipping Conference and the SMM Global Maritime Environmental Congress to develop an in-depth understanding of the effects of legislation on the industry. Several intertwined strategies were thus applied to increase the validity of the qualitative study.

Quantitative validity is first defined by **measurement validity**, meaning that the findings represent the reality of what is being measured (compare Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015, p.450). Content validity is ensured by including only those issues in the questionnaire which were deemed to be important by the majority of experts during interviews, thus providing for adequate coverage of different facets of the research problem in the questionnaire, while also excluding non-essential issues. Predictive validity is concerned with the ability to make

accurate predictions. Milton Friedman suggests that in order to test a theory there is no need to test the underlying assumptions directly (Milton Friedman, 1966, p. 8 et sqq). More important is testing the predictive power of the theory. This notion is heavily contested by Ronald Coase, however, one of the most influential economists of the twentieth century. In the present study, both underlying assumptions and predictive power of the theory will be tested and reported on. Construct validity is checked for to make sure that questions actually measure the constructs they are supposed to. Also, the appropriateness and suitability of analytical techniques is considered.

Secondly, **internal validity** must be ensured. Relationships among variables which are reported must be accurate. A threat to internal validity may stem from informing participants about the research and thereby already influencing their answers. It is possible that participants overrate the importance of environmental laws for their company, knowing that the study focuses specifically on environmental legislation. To limit other threats to internal validity as described by Creswell, it was made sure that the research instrument was not changed during the research, so as to not affect comparability of results. Also, participants were surveyed only once to prevent a maturation of attitudes, and the availability of the study was limited to six months, so as to limit the effect of legal changes on participant's perceptions. In order to enhance validity of the findings, particular care was taken to exclude, as far as possible, participants from the quantitative study that were a part of the sample in the qualitative study. This was done to avoid undue confirmation of participants of their own systems of relevance in the second research stage. An exclusion was possible in most cases, as experts from the interview stage were either not shipping companies or could be excluded from receiving notifications on the questionnaire. However, as the questionnaire was also advertised by industry associations, the link could have been passed on to other companies. Complete anonymity of the responses allowed no deduction on which organisations completed the questionnaire, thus no guarantee can be provided on the success of the exclusion. To further ensure internal validity, it was made sure that no substantial new laws were announced during the period of data collection to make results comparable. A last threat to internal validity lies in ambiguities about the direction of causal relations. For example, where increases in compliance costs were deemed to influence compliance levels, at the same time, increases in compliance levels would influence compliance costs. Findings from expert interviews served to determine likely directions of causal relations, however.

Thirdly, **external validity** is concerned with the generalisability of findings. Qualitative findings may be generalised by way of theoretical sampling, where material is used for inductive theory development until saturation is reached (Mayring, 2007), which is applicable to this research. Furthermore, external validity of qualitative findings is achieved by applying a mixed methods design. Though the sample for the quantitative study was carefully selected and data analysis rigourously conducted, the results of this research are only externally valid to some extent. As companies in the sample were active in the North and Baltic Sea areas, findings might be generalised to this group, but may not be valid to shipping companies mostly active in other areas of the world. Also, due to constant developments in the legal environment, results of the study are time-bound and may not be generalised to past or future situations (for threats to external validity see Creswell, 2014, p.177). The theoretical concepts developed in the study

are, however, deemed to be valid for all types of commercial shipping companies over a period of time and might to some extent also be generalisable to other transport sectors.

Lastly, an academic concern is not only the validity of findings, but also their **usefulness**. Research is most useful, where it is of relevance to the problems faced by organisations. The results of this study are of great significance to a variety of actors. Policy makers, environmental organisations, enforcement agencies, and shipping companies themselves are very much concerned with the effects of environmental laws on the industry. While the one lobby group searches for support of the argument that the shipping industry is hit very strongly by environmental laws, demanding a postponement of future measures, the other group will try to show how little effect current measures have, demanding a fast advancement of further measures. A thorough unbiased academic study may serve both sides in grounding their arguments on reliable data, while especially serving legislators to base their decisions on credible findings, rather than lobby rhetorics.

4.7 Limitations of methodology

The results of this research must be seen in the light of several limitations, including a time limit of three years to conduct the research and a time gap between the collection of qualitative (2014/2015) and quantitative data (2017/2018). This gap may lead to discrepancies in results, as two important pieces of environmental legislation have come into force in-between. Exploratory interviews were conducted in the autumn of 2014, before the coming into force of the EU sulphur directive on 1 January 2015. Data from questionnaires was collected between September 2017 and February 2018. Ballast water treatment became mandatory at the end of September 2017. While the shipping industry was much concerned about the costs of sulphur legislation at the time of the interviews, they have had time to accustom themselves to these laws by the time of the questionnaires but were by then much concerned about the costs of ballast water treatment. The time gap between the collection periods may limit comparability of the data and needs to be considered when evaluating data. It is important to note in this respect, that data was specifically collected during a recession in the shipping industry. The study is likely to yield diametrically different results during a peak in the economic cycle (see limitations) but if this research is specifically interested in decisions as regards compliance. Noncompliant behaviour will be most likely to spot when money is tight, as explained above.

A further restriction applies to the geographical location of interview partners and questionnaire participants, who were all situated in countries bordering the Northern European seas. The researcher limited the geographical scope of research to the North and Baltic Sea areas. This limitation may be explained by limited resources and the presence of the researcher in the region but was also deliberately chosen. The region is globally among the most advanced, if not the most advanced, when it comes to environmental legislation. The particularly strict laws applying also make it a region with particularly prominent cost pressures for the shipping industry due to environmental legislation, with the strongest likelihood of observable effects. The North and Baltic Sea areas serve as a pioneer in cleaning up the shipping industry, with laws being adapted on the global scale with a time lapse. While it would have yielded greater

benefits to collect data from shipping companies worldwide, it seems a logical first step to start investigations in the North and Baltic Sea areas.

With the study receiving endorsement from both the German and the Danish shipowners' associations, a high propensity for companies from these countries to be in the sample is noticeable, leading to a biased database especially towards German shipping companies. The type of study may furthermore have discouraged shipping companies regularly not complying with environmental laws, not well informed about the same, or having limited personnel available, from taking part in the survey. This leads to a bias in favour of larger, better financed, and more law-abiding companies to reply to the questionnaire. A case in point is that not a single company taking part in the survey is flying a vessel under one of the 13 black-listed flags of the Paris MoU (Paris MoU, 2017).

A further limitation with respect to data collection lies in the methods applied to identify interview partners. Interview partners from stakeholders outside the shipping industry were identified based on their superior knowledge and position within their respective organisation, but interview partners within the shipping industry were partly identified with support from the German Shipowners' Association. Consequently, sampling was influenced by companies being listed with the organisation. Expert perceptions may differ for shipowners in other geographical areas, as cultural differences, different legal requirements and practical enforcement by the flag states and different financial possibilities may apply. With respect to quantitative data collection, industry directories were consulted to identify as many shipping companies as possible operating in the North and Baltic Sea areas. Still, the German and Danish shipowner's organisations served as partners in this exercise, contacting their members directly and advertising the questionnaire, thus the share of German and Danish shipping companies in the sample is somewhat larger than from other countries in the region. Also, directories for some countries were well administered, while it was particularly difficult to acquire contact lists for Russia and the Baltic states, explaining the rather low share of companies from these countries in the sample. A great effort was made by the researcher to make the sample as representative as possible, but the above-named limitations apply.

Limited resources in terms of the time allowed until completion of the thesis and a limit in financial resources led the researcher to limit the overall number of expert interviews conducted. Although further experts were suggested to the researcher that might have provided supplementary insights, the researcher curbed the qualitative research stage after the 12th interview. At that stage the emerging concepts were well established and further interviewees tended to confirm the emerging theoretical framework, adding evidence, but not adding new categories of meaning. Saturation was reached and further interviews did not seem effective keeping in mind that a full transcript of the interview, a subsequent translation into English language of the full transcript, and a systematic analysis of the transcript imposed a non-negligible time demand.

One limitation may be found at the stage of interpretation of data. Creswell argues that results of the qualitative and the quantitative study may not be compared, as they are based on different samples (Creswell, 2014, p.226). Instead, interpretation may only go so far as to describe the results of the qualitative study, how these informed the quantitative study and whether the

findings from the expert interviews may be generalised. A particular challenge lies in adequately combining results from the different types of data collection, which also underly different epistemological assumptions. The challenges start at the development of a theoretical framework that makes adequate use of the richness of the qualitative findings (Creswell, 2014, p.226), and lead towards the adequate analysis and interpretation of quantitative data including subsumption and aggregation of data, verifying the theory developed based on qualitative findings, while not losing the value of deep research.

Limitations also apply to the methods of data evaluation applied. Despite measures taken to ensure reliability of findings, a level of interpretation remains that is inherent to qualitative data analysis. With respect to the questionnaires, again despite careful drafting, reviewing by other researchers and pre-testing the questionnaire, the danger remains that participants did not properly read or understand the questions or instrumentalised the questionnaire, that questions did not sufficiently include all pertinent aspects of the problem or that statistical methods applied to analyse the data were insufficient. The researcher is aware of these limitations and discusses results with a view to these shortcomings.

4.8 Chapter summary

This research follows an exploratory sequential mixed methods design. Data from literature review, expert interviews and questionnaires is triangulated to inform the research problem following a pragmatic approach to knowledge generation. Informed consent at all stages of data collection provides the foundation for ethically sound research. The mixed methods design is apt to reduce influence of the researcher on results, which generally poses a threat in qualitative research. Reliability and validity of findings are critically reviewed. Several methods are applied to ensure both. Still, the methodology has inherent weaknesses as explained above.

5 Findings from qualitative data

5.1 Introduction

Expert perceptions on compliance costs and freight rate effects of MEL, as well as determinants of compliance, and the likelihood of modal shift were systematically gathered and analysed. The concepts presented here were chosen for their significance to experts, following an exploratory approach to knowledge creation. The presentation of findings is ordered by research question in line with the proposed research design. The research questions guiding the analysis of qualitative data are:

QUAL1: How high are the costs of maritime environmental legislation for the shipping industry? Are they high enough to have a critical effect on the industry, i.e. lead to freight rate increases, modal shift, rerouting of vessels, or consolidation?

QUAL2: Are shipping companies reacting to increasing costs with increased levels of noncompliance? When, why, to what extent?

QUAL3: Are distinct types of shipping companies differently affected by legislation? Can they provide environmental protection at different costs? Which company characteristics play a role?

In line with research question QUAL1, effects of environmental incentives on the shipping industry are discussed in Chapter 5.2. The effectiveness of legislation in the form of compliance with environmental laws is discussed in Chapter 5.3. Chapter 5.4 yields a discussion of the differences among shipping companies. The theoretical framework developed from qualitative data is presented in Chapter 5.5 and the conclusion summarising findings from qualitative data may be found in Chapter 5.6. Thick description, verbatim quotes and visual presentation of data is used to support arguments made and to show where data gathered proves to be inconsistent or unexpected. A theoretical framework is being developed based on qualitative findings, providing the basis for quantitative data collection. The findings from both qualitative and quantitative data are interpreted and triangulated in Chapter 7 “Critical analysis and synthesis”.

5.2 Effects of incentives

5.2.1 Expert perceptions on costs of maritime environmental legislation

A review of prior studies showed that air pollution and ballast water legislation were likely to lead to the most significant cost increases for the shipping industry, while other areas of pollution, like the dumping of waste and noise pollution, were unlikely to be associated with significant cost increases. It has to be noted, however, that studies were mostly based on theoretical considerations or provided circumstantial evidence on the issue, while sound empirical evidence proved to be rare. In the exploratory stage of this research, experts were questioned to provide deeper insights on the magnitude, structure, and effects of environmental compliance cost increases. In interviews, experts commented extensively on operational cost increases due to environmental legislation, discussed reconstruction cost increases, gave insights on the burden sharing between shipowner and operator and to a minor extent

commented on increased investment costs for newbuildings. An overview of codings ordered by total number is given in Figure 5-1, indicating the importance of issues in the perception of experts. It becomes apparent that operational cost increases have by far the most relevance for industry experts, while investment cost increases were of minor importance.

Figure 5-1: Total number of codings related to costs from environmental legislation

Operational cost increases were named by all twelve experts as an effect of environmental legislation. “That is a high rise in costs, no question.” an expert working for the European Commission claims. He adds: “...that is obviously influencing the competitiveness...” (T12, para 39; supporting this argument see also T1, para 117; T2, para 38; T8, para 289). Some experts provide estimates on the potential size of cost increases. These are summarised in Table 5-1. One says: “The additional cost to shipping in North Europe of the sulphur directive is around 3 billion Euros a year. That is a significant amount of money.” (T5, para 228; compare T6, para 196 estimating total additional costs of 70 billion dollars from 2020 onwards; T7, para 149; T9, para 73 stating that MGO is many times more expensive than HFO). On the side of individual companies, E5 estimates a significant cost increase for all operators (T5, para 186). “I think we are talking anything from - and that is an educated guess - from 5 to 40 per cent.” (T5, para 190) he says. A slightly clearer estimate is provided by another expert: “...the utilities costs increase somewhere between fifteen and twenty per cent...” (T8, para 271). At another point during the interview the same expert estimates the cost effect of stricter sulphur laws to amount to twenty to thirty percent additional fuel costs (T8, para 137). A third expert guesses the following cost increases due to sulphur legislation: “...let us say the fuel costs of a vessel for transport make for fifty per cent of the total price. And if these fifty per cent become fifty per cent more expensive then that has a tremendously high importance.” (T7, para 140). Elaborating on cost increases per vessel, an industry representative says: “...with a difference of 50 per cent and if you pay 600 dollar per ton or 900 and I would say a large container vessel consumes 100 tons a day, there you are easily at 30, 40, 50,000 dollars a day.” (T6, para 147). A RoRo-ferry operator calculates: “The price difference, as I said before, is at the moment at 250 Euros per ton. If I now simply take 250 times 10,000 then I have somehow two and a half million on my sheet – additional costs – for one vessel and we have six of them. Then I am already at 15 million for the whole fleet. You have to earn those first of all, those 15 million. Next year our accounts are stressed by that amount more compared to today, this year. If the difference between the two fuels increases, the costs will increase even further.” (T4, para 164). Experts are consistently arguing that operational cost increases stem mainly from sulphur

legislation. The magnitude of the cost increases they assume differs widely but is based in all cost calculations on the price differential between HFO and MGO. The different estimates may be explained by the significant volatility of fuel prices, making educated guesses difficult. This shows also in expert perceptions on fuel cost developments. **Fuel costs** might increase due to increased demand but might also decrease as increased demand brings increased deliveries from North America an expert argues (T4, para 85). Price developments depend to a greater extent on developments on the world markets than on maritime legislation. Prices have fallen after the introduction of the 0.1%S limit on North and Baltic Seas, leading to lower operational costs for shipping after the SECA introduction: “They really did not increase at all. In general, the raw oil prices, as you have surely been following in the press, have fallen by more than 50 per cent in the meantime. That means that we are today paying for the bunker we currently need still less than what we have paid half a year ago [for heavy fuel oil].”, argues E11 (T11, para 16-18). E9, however, expects future price increases (T9, para 177). One expert compares market fluctuation risks with risks from environmental legislation: “I guess environmental regulation is a bit of a constant. It is much more predictable; it is a much more predictable risk. It simply translates to a constant increase in operational costs.” (T2, para 124). Comparing the different statements made, agreement can be found among experts that the cost effect of MEL depends to some extent on the development of fuel costs, which are difficult to predict and develop independently from environmental legislation. While legislation itself is thus predictable, the effects of legislation may not be calculable and may prove as volatile as the price of fuel.

Expert	Cost estimate for sulphur legislation during interviews
T4	Price differential of €250/ton of fuel; vessel fuel cost increases of €2.5 million/year (with 10,000 tons fuel uptake); company fuel cost increase of €15 million/year (for six vessels)
T5	50% increase in fuel costs; 5-40% increase in overall costs for shipping companies, total costs of €3 billion/year to shipping in Northern Europe
T6	50% increase in fuel costs from €525 to 790/ton (USD600 to 900/ton), for a large container vessel consuming 100 tons/day this means an increase of €26,000-44,000/day (USD30,000-50,000/day); €61 billion (USD70 billion) additional costs to shipping from 2020 onwards
T7	45-55% increase in fuel cost due to switch to MGO from €525 to 790 (USD600 to 900), company fuel cost increase from €876 million to 1.3 billion (USD1 billion to 1.5 billion)
T8	20-30% increase in fuel costs, 15-20% increase in utilities costs
T11	Fuel price decrease by 50%

Table 5-1: Cost estimates for sulphur legislation by experts during interviews

Data suggests further that cost increases may not only be experienced from increased fuel costs, but also from increased **prices of related services**: “...the workshops are raising their prices very much, because all sorts of people now still need to clean one or two tanks.” (T10, para 83), an expert says. These added costs have not been mentioned or studied by academics before but may be significant. Environmental legislation is thus believed by all experts, including lobbyists on both sides, to pose significant cost increases to the industry. A concern that has been developed inductively from the data is the **time lag** between paying for fuel and receiving

income (compare T5, para 266), which may become seriously troublesome if credit is short and the time lag is long. Consequences of environmental laws on the cash flow have not yet been studied, despite likely posing a significant problem to companies: “If you are switching, which most people will, to the low sulphur fuel - their fuel bill at the end of January next year will have gone up by 50 per cent. Will they have the cash to do that? Do they have the credit line to do it? Will the fuel companies be allowed to extent 50 per cent more credit to their customers?”, an expert asks (T5, para 260). Shipping companies tend to comply with legislation as late as possible to account for shortages in cash. E10 states that purchases of low sulphur fuel will be made “...as close as possible to the limit of 2015, because no one on today’s market can afford to operate half a year on gas oil when he does not need to.” (T10, para 27).

As has become apparent from the literature and is confirmed by experts during interviews, certain **regulatory issues** will have larger effects on operational costs than others. Experts estimate that sulphur and ballast water legislation will be most expensive (T5, para 64-67; compare also T8, para 116, T11, para 151). E7 argues that between these two, sulphur legislation is even more expensive (T7, para 58, see also T4, para 82-85 stating that the expenses for low-sulphur fuel are threatening their existence as a ferry operator). Especially measures leading to a constant increase in fuel costs will influence the industry, an expert claims. “The clear difference with fuel compared to the other areas is that one has constant additional costs. Well, the one thing are the investment costs, that is what does it cost us to reorganise a specific area. The other thing is then what kind of subsequent costs do we have, for example fuel costs.” (T7, para 104). Another expert adds: “...the bunker consumption and the costs for the fuel. That is everything that has to do with the propulsion of the ship. That is expensive. The rest, I would argue, can all be managed.” (T11, para 340, see also T6, para 226 on fuel making the largest part of operational expenses). The significant scope of fuel cost increases due to SO₂ legislation is calculated by one ship operator: “Let us say we change to MGO [marine gas oil]. This MGO then costs an additional 50 per cent. It might be 45 at times or sometimes 55 but let us assume it is simply 50 per cent. Well, from 600 dollars to 900 dollars, even if prices are a little lower than that at the moment. Well, that means that my fuel costs are no longer a billion US dollars, but 1.5 billion US dollars. I believe I do not have to add anything to that. That is clearly apparent. And no other of these issues is only roughly coming into that range [of costs].” (T7, para 102). E7 argues: “There is likely no law in any area of transport, I’m very certain there is not, that has influenced transport so such an extent, to such an amount.” (T7, para 60). “...no other date than the 1 January 2015 is occupying the shipping industry here on the North East Atlantic and the Baltic Sea so much, compared to any other legislation for shipping in the last years.” (T3, para 61), an expert with an environmental organisation argues. The second legislative endeavour prominently discussed by experts is **ballast water management**. Industry insiders argue that next to installation costs, ballast water management systems also increase the costs of shipping operations: “Such a machine already has an electricity intake of 200 kilowatts alone. One machine when it is running plus the pumps. (...) That is not negligible when that thing is running for three hours.” (T9, para 51), an expert states. Another interviewee argues that a lack in reliability of available systems also leads to cost increases: “Well, everything that breaks down always immediately costs an incredible amount of money.” (T9, para 17). Experts argue that especially the laws on low-sulphur fuel and ballast water treatment bear only cost increases for the industry without any link to **efficiency gains**: “Sulphur

legislation and ballast water legislation - there is no immediate cost reduction at all combined with these regulations.”, an expert argues (T5, para 71; see also T12, para 39 on sulphur legislation being a pure cost factor for the industry). Another expert argues: “Ballast water stories are first of all expensive and that is a thing that, yes, that one does in order to comply, but that has no benefit for the company, in terms of costs not at all, I would say. Rather on the contrary. Well, I would not know of any benefits for us. For us that does not yield anything really.” (T9, para 173). This is different with **CO₂ legislation**, which entails potential cost savings for the industry. A ship operator says: “Unless we are thinking about CO₂. There one may again really make some cash.” (T7, para 102). The experts add that CO₂ legislation might become expensive for the shipping industry, depending on how the laws are set up: “...if a law on CO₂ is coming it will cost money. It is linked to investments or we plain and simply have to pay into a fund.” (T7, para 98). “With respect to CO₂ that is difficult to express in numbers, because first of all as of now we do not know that, because in that area everything is still... and because secondly you cannot say, well, this fuel here costs 300 and that one 600, but a CO₂ or energy efficiency regulation in some way always interferes with the business model.” (T6, para 107). With respect to carbon dioxide emissions, experts are divided as to what kind of cost effects to expect.

A further line of argument goes that also **less expensive measures will influence the industry**. An expert argues: “Well, I would think that the sum of many small contributions equals a sum in the end that you cannot balance with your earnings anymore.” (T11, para 344). An expert from a shipping association describes how operational costs of shipping companies are influenced by environmental measures: “...the shipping companies are in for a lot. They have to educate the people aboard, have to carry out the technical retrofitting of the vessels, have to deal with the economic implications – how do we manage with all the additional costs? At the end those are additional costs. That is something that influences the economic model. That is forming a kind of pedestal of things that just need to be paid, need to be met, due to laws and so forth, reporting obligations, and technical installations and so on. That will simple be there. There is no going back from that, it will increase constantly piece by piece and thus it is something that is predictable. It is nothing that comes and goes, but it is predictable – It is going to be expensive. We don’t know, how expensive, but it is something that... that we cannot run and hide from, so to speak.” (T6, para 236).

Increases in (re-)construction spending is a variable of importance to eleven out of twelve experts. The most expensive piece of legislation affecting vessel reconstruction mentioned was the BWM Convention. “That means a lot of work for us and a lot of technical effort, extremely expensive.” (T9, para 51; see also T6, para 83), a captain states. A container ship operator opinions: “Ballast water is not influencing us at all. We have to do it. We have to carry the costs. That is it. And no one is bearing the incurred costs.” (T7, para 106). Experts provide cost estimates for worldwide implementation of ballast water management systems, as summarised in Table 5-2: “For ballast water you can calculate per ship between 3 and 5 million, Panamax to Capesize...” (T10, para 169; compare T10, para 71 stating that expenses depend on ship size), an expert says. During the same interview E10 states: “We are talking about two to three million per vessel in newbuildings and in retrofits even more.” (T10, para 79; compare T9, para 171 on a facility costing several million Euros; T7, para 56 and 60 on each treatment system

costing a million dollars or more). Another expert adds: “That is going to be another major one for shipping. It’s going to cost shipping worldwide about 30 billion US dollars.” (T5, para 71). Cost estimates thus start at slightly less than €1 million per vessel, but vary considerably, depending on ship size and other factors.

Expert	Cost estimate for ballast water legislation
T5	Costs of €26 billion (USD30 billion) for shipping worldwide
T7	€876 million (USD1 million) or more/vessel
T9	Several million €/vessel
T10	€2-5 million/vessel (€2-3 million in newbuildings, more in retrofits)

Table 5-2: Cost estimates for ballast water legislation by experts during interviews

To a much smaller extent than ballast water treatment, reconstructions for switching to **low-sulphur fuel** also lead to costs: “...we evidently preferably want to do that with a pipe that does not come in touch with heavy fuel oil, because otherwise we will contaminate it for a long time to come... (...) That means we should preferably separate. Already while bunkering, that means tanks that have before been filled with heavy fuel oil, where the bunker connection is linked to the heavy fuel oil pipe, need to be rebuilt. I suddenly need to access this diesel oil pipe plus I need to connect all diesel oil tanks with this tank in order to be able to bunker. And all those are alterations in fuel-forwarding pipes, thus the fuel tanks need to be gas free, hot work. Those are extreme exertions that shipping has to undertake at the moment that are not making life easier.” (T10, para 31; see also T10, para 27 on the need for rebuilding the pipe system to reach justifiable switchover times when entering the SECA). Other types of legislation will also raise (re-)construction costs of vessels, such as designing the engines to produce little **nitrogen oxide** during the burning process once North and Baltic Seas are Nitrogen Emission Control Areas. An installation in newly-builds might not pose a problem, but reconstructing existing engines will become expensive, an expert argues: “These are obviously costs, no question. So whenever you want to change the way an industry is managing its activity, whenever you want to change this, you have to spend money, because this transition costs money. It is quite possible that it does not cost more money than before, but you have to reach that stage in the first place. That means you need to finance this transition...” (T12, para 77; see also T6, para 111). Another expert states that the installation of NO_x catalytic converters is not overly expensive and that the industry will “survive that” (T4, para 85). **Sewage water treatment systems** might become a cost factor: “For us that means that latest starting from 2017 or 2018, some time, we have to... running vessels thus need either a new sewage treatment system on board, that abides to even higher limits that today’s systems, or we have to dispose of the waste water on land.” (T4, para 70). Furthermore, **hull coatings** replacing the forbidden TBT-containing paints are more expensive than old toxic colours (T6, para 87). If legislation on **noise pollution** were one day to be passed that would also have a significant influence on vessel reconstruction costs, one expert claims: “...then it is also getting really expensive, because I would not know at all how one would do that. You then somehow need to absorb all vibrations of the main engine with silencers that they cannot get into the water via the hull. Which is not working at all, because on the other side you need to via the... you are in any way connected to the water again. I would not know how one wants to solve that really at the moment, but that would then become really expensive.” (T11, para 154; see also T8, para 73 and 119). On a last note, experts argue that

reconstruction spending is not necessarily a cost but can be used on **efficiency improvements** for ships: “I mean we have, on a number of our ships, we have changed the propeller, we have changed the motors and that is a significant cost. But there we can do a business case and see you know how much fuel we will be saving by doing it and as long as we are within the payback time it will be fine, acceptable. It is a thing we can do.” (T5, para 166). However, an expert states: “Normally environmental legislation does not lead to chances for the industry, normally it leads to bothersome investments for the industry.” (T3, para 126). Experts are in agreement with respect to both the importance of operational cost increases from sulphur legislation and reconstruction cost increases from ballast water legislation. With respect to other types of pollution, their evidence becomes more anecdotal, with fewer and less substantial remarks on the costs of legislative endeavours. In the perception of experts, these seem to play a lesser role for shipping companies.

One question experts raised, which has not been discussed by academics before is whether an installation of environmental equipment leads to an increase or a decrease in **ship value**. Installations take up space that is no longer available for loading cargo, might slow down a ship or increase fuel consumption and necessitate higher charter rates to refinance investments. When such a vessel is not operating in protected areas like the North and Baltic Seas it might have a competitive disadvantage in finding a charterparty. “Take for instance the retrofit of a scrubber. That is a cost of for us somewhere between 5 and 10 million Euros per ship. Is that an increase in the ship value or is it a decrease in the ship value?” (T5, para 260), an expert asks. A decision not to upgrade will limit the legal operating sphere to waters outside Northern Europe, however. “...those companies which operate on a tramp basis they will struggle the most. Their assets will either have to be geared up for worldwide compliance or become less flexible.” (T2, para 52). Shipowners have a difficult choice between lower costs and higher flexibility. Interestingly, one expert argues that cost increases for environmental protection only pose a problem due to currently difficult **supply-demand imbalances** on shipping markets. “I strongly think that if we had this discussion at a time where shipping was at a peak and the pre-financial-crisis-world, where we have had ships being built every day and this two-three million worth of equipment that we are talking about now would not be an issue” (T2, para 118).

A further concept not considered in compliance cost considerations before is the influence of **burden sharing** between shipowner and ship operator. This variable has been mentioned by seven out of twelve experts, proving to be of moderate relevance. When shipowners charter their vessels out, they have few incentives to invest in improvements. One way around this is sharing the burden of investment costs: “What happens increasingly is that some shipping companies want to install a scrubber in a vessel that they then want to charter out on the market or where they are already in negotiations with a charterer. They say: We have to invest as an owner in order to have that installed, but you have the profit, a split incentive, that means you would have to decide for a long-term charter and you would have to pay a share of the cost. Afterwards you may operate on heavy fuel oil and that will save you money every mile. That is somehow slowly starting a little bit in the direction: The one partakes in the costs of the other.” (T6, para 133), an expert explains. He adds: “Maersk for example has (...) done that for some vessels that they have said: We charter that ship for the next ten years. Well and then that is worthwhile, then you can say, charter company or owner, please install such a thing, we will

pay our share, because we will have the benefits afterwards. But in the normal market where you have charter periods of one month, three months, six months, that is a different issue. Something like that is not happening there.” (T6, para 135). When costs are not shared, investments in environmental ship performance become less likely. Technical compliance of the vessel with environmental laws might increase its competitiveness via charterers, however. “That is clearly again the question whether there is someone in the company thinking: Boah, if our charter shipping company is really up to speed in the area of environment, then we will be able to sell our vessels better to the liner shipping companies. Thus, we have to monitor closely what kind of laws there really are and see that our vessels comply with all requirements and that our vessel may be applied in all areas for example. If I realise as a charter shipping company I have a vessel coming on the market in two years, or in one or in a half year and I would like to get rid of that or charter it out and that will be given off somehow close to the North and Baltic Seas then it likely makes sense to make sure: Will it also be able to sail into the ECA? Can it handle the MGO, the marine gas oil or can it not?” (T7, para 77). “Whereby I would claim that that is something that every shipping company is focusing on for a new-building anyway, because the less a vessel consumes the higher the rate that you will receive from a potential charterer, because he is then saving a lot of money” (T11, para 128), another interviewee supports this argument. Asked whether the **charter market** is interested in environmentally friendly vessels, an expert answers: “I think at the moment that is not yet relevant. That will certainly come. Well, the development goes into that direction. Well, I believe that one day it will be.” (T9, para 103). Ship operators might not be interested in environmental legislation altogether: “I can take the standpoint that all of that is not my problem, shipowner you care about that.” (T11, para 168). The same expert states that there are, however, different types of operators: “...that always depends a bit on what kind of operators you are dealing with. As I said, there are two possibilities. Either they say: That is of no interest to me, shipowner that is your thing. Or I care about that myself and talk to the shipowner how that shall best be done. That depends a bit on how one wants to handle that in the company.” (T11, para 176). One expert clarifies the different perspectives towards environmental legislation between owner-operated vessels and the ones chartered out: “...we have sat together with the commercial people and have said: Okay, what are the requirements for us and in order to fulfil them it gets a bit more complicated, because they evidently take the own vessel for the more flexible service as well, when it gets difficult. And that is why the requirements remain higher than if I only had to charter out a vessel on the market and I just have this and that much and now it is your problem where you bunker. But also on the market... the market is making sure what the vessel is capable of and what I pay for that. Well, it also has a market value.” (T10, para 33). With respect to slow steaming, an expert argues that new vessels will likely not be built to more efficient, slower speeds “...because the charter party and the shipowners are still demanding that. They will likely still be able to well do 20, because the charter market is somehow also working with such parameters...” (T9, para 101). Even if shipowners pay for investments initially, they will need to get the money back via increased **charter rates**: “The shipowner is paying for that. But as we are chartering the ships and the shipowner evidently wants to retrieve the money for the investment, we are paying in the end of the day. That is the reason why we naturally need to grapple with these issues, because in the end of the day it costs our money.” (T11, para 38). It happens that the shipowner or ship owning fund cannot provide

funds to make necessary environmental investments: "...you have no real responsibility. The shipping company is doing the ship management that means it is operating the vessel and is collecting a fixed sum from the one-ship-partnership. And it is also getting that. Well and everything that is now... if the ship needs to go into classification, then it gets tough. Because then they need to find money somewhere. The shipping company itself is saying: I provide the crew and care about the operation of the ship and I simply state that I need to go into classification. Dear owner, please make sure that money is available. And if money is not available the vessel is so-to-speak put on the dump and when in doubt it is being sold or scrapped." (T8, para 38). Considerations on the complexities of burden sharing have not been investigated by academics and would merit the application of principal-agent-models from economic theory to shed light on the owner-operator relationship with respect to environmental investments.

An issue linked to burden sharing and just as little discussed in prior studies is the question of liability for noncompliant behaviour. **Liability** usually lies with the party having an influence on the respective law in question, one expert claims. "If the shipping company is chartering the ship out with crew members and operating the ship then it is certainly evidently also the shipping company that is held liable." (T9, para 159, see also T11, para 40 on liability according to spheres of influence). "...as a rule it is the case that for everything that is directly related to the ship the shipping company, thus the owner of the ship is liable and everything that is related to bunkering the charterer is [liable]." (T11, para 42). Another deems that the larger part of liability always lies with the vessel owner: "The owner is certainly the one. The owner is always responsible for the ship's availability, for the service of the ship. He chartered out a transport machine in accordance with the laws. That is written down in the charter party. That means the owner is the one who has to care for everything." (T10, para 145). Compliance with laws on fuel lies with the operator, however: "The disponent owner has to care for that [fuel compliance]. (...) That is the charterer. And then we get again to the vessel speeds. The owner hands a transport machine to the charterer and the disponent owner, the charterer is saying how fast he goes. That means as an owner I have no influence on air pollution, because I do not provide the fuel, do not prescribe the ship speed. (...)" (T10, para 145). E11 summarises: "As charterer we are in any case always addressed first by the authorities, but in the end of the day the liability still lies with the shipowner." (T11, para 44).

Increases in the costs of new-buildings are the third category of costs mentioned by experts during interviews, albeit a category of minor importance in terms of total codings and only of relevance to six out of twelve experts. Some environmental laws only have a cost effect on new-buildings: "The EEDI and the NO_x tier three are really applicable for new buildings - so until we decide on a new building it doesn't have an immediate cost effect.", an expert explains (T5, para 73). Another argues that inefficient vessels could be replaced by new ones to save on fuel costs in emission control areas: "At that point everything is going on the test bench again. The question is asked then, for example, do I throw away the ship and buy a new one that maybe saves 15 or 20 per cent fuel just by its ship design - is that cheaper for me, when I do the calculations, than to operate this vessel, that I am currently operating, that I maybe have been operating for seven years, for another seven years from now on." (T3, para 92). A rejuvenation of the fleet might be encouraged by environmental laws: "The trend goes to building larger

vessels, that have a new kind of design, need less fuel by themselves, may transport more, that is more at the same time, which evidently has a certain positive effect for example on the CO₂ emissions in the end and also on the setting of other emissions.” (T3, para 94; compare T2, para 50 on replacing older vessels by newer ones as a reaction to ballast water legislation). An expert explains how gaining funds to invest into a more efficient new-building might prove difficult: “...if we would order her [current ferry in use] anew today, than we would have to invest somewhere between 100 and 120 million Euros for such a ship. That is more or less double of what we have paid for that vessel at commissioning twenty years ago. Well, that is also a very long time, but the costs are extremely high and the money will have to be earned first of all and that is with the existing fleet. If the market is so much under pressure due to the fuel costs and all the uncertainty. How do you want to somehow recover this huge amount of money? You have to go to a bank and explain to them: Listen, I want to buy a vessel or want to have a vessel built, that costs such and such amount and I expect this and that profit a year from which I can repay my credit and that will then theoretically take 50 years for me to repay. The bank will then say: Here, you have bets in the belfry. You should better go home.” (T4, para 186). Future legislation expected by the industry already has effects on new-buildings today: “... we have a (...) game changer in the whole fuel history (...) That again has an impact on shipping investments. Shipowners are asking us now: Well, what about the fuel after 2020? We are planning a newbuilding, with which motors shall we furnish that, so that we may burn all fuels... and somehow keep all options open?” (T6, para 109). Acquiring funding especially for ships able to operate in the North and Baltic Sea protected areas might prove difficult: “...if you now want to have a ship that complies with all of these regulations – and you should not forget that they apply only to a very small area of the globe, Baltic Sea - you are thus building a vessel for a very special sea area. Shipping is international, however, and no bank will finance an extremely expensive ship that you can economically operate only there – unless the charter party guarantees that he will employ the ship for rate xy for the next ten years” (T11, para 334), an expert reports, adding that such guarantees will not be obtainable. He deliberates on a likely course of action that shipowners will take: “Normally the shipowner will try to build an alternative. That is a ship that he can use globally as well as in special areas, but that will also be expensive, but he will simply hope that when he is operating it in this special area where he actually also wants to go that he will receive higher rates for it accordingly. Thus, he employs so-called dual fuel engines where he can burn heavy fuel oil as well as gas.” (T11, para 338).

The variables influencing the relationship between environmental legislation and cost increases for the shipping industry can be seen in Figure 5-2. While experts agree that cost effects from ballast water and sulphur legislation are non-negligible, there is less agreement on cost effects of other types of pollution. The relational model shows that environmental legislation influences operational costs, retrofitting costs and costs of newbuildings, but may also lead to cost decreases via forced efficiency gains. The competitive situation of the shipping industry may thus be influenced in several ways. Operational costs may increase due to fuel price increases, but also due to price increases of related services based on increased demand for example for tank cleaning activities. Fuel price increases will only influence costs when certain shipping routes are used with special environmental protection in force and where shipping companies are complying with the laws. Installations in newbuildings or the existing fleet will increase construction costs and thereby change the competitive situation of a company. Original

variables that did not appear during literature review are cash flow problems as well as the question whether installing environmental systems will increase or decrease the value of the vessel on the world charter markets. Also, expert statements on the rate of legal compliance show how important further studies in this crucial field seem to be.

Figure 5-2: Variables influencing cost increases from environmental legislation as identified by QUAL data

5.2.2 Expert perceptions on freight rate effects of MEL

As becomes apparent in Figure 5-3, most statements on freight rates made by experts were towards freight rates increasing. Eleven out of twelve experts made observations to this purpose. Eight spoke about instances where they were unsure of the relationship between cost increases and freight rates, five talked about situations where they saw no direct link between costs and freight rates and finally four experts made statements towards the purpose that there was no influence of cost increases on freight rates. The reasoning for these considerations will become evident from the experiences illustrated below.

Figure 5-3: Total number of codings related to freight rate effects of MEL

Under the coding ‘**no change in freight rates**’ all information was collected where experts argued that they expected no decrease or increase in freight rates. An expert stated that he did not believe customers would accept any freight rate increases in view of the current competitive situation: “...no one is bearing the incurred costs. Well, so far I have in any way not heard from anyone anywhere - well, not only within [organisation 7], but in general – that a customer or anyone would say: Yes, well, now that you have installed a ballast water treatment system we would like to pay an additional 50 dollars per container. I do not know of such an incident. Nothing is happening there.” (T7, para 106). He adds: “We could not say, well, we are doing this or that environmental initiative, dear customer that will cost an additional 100 dollars per container. The market is far too competitive for that.” (T7, para 20; see also T8, para 139 on the impossibility of passing on additional costs especially the East Asia trade). Another expert supports this position stating: “...the freight rates are very, very low and normally the companies want, need really significantly more per transported unit in order to sail to some extent cost-effective. And the problem is that due to this competitive situation that currently exists it is just incredibly strong, the cost pressure is so strong that they cannot go higher with their rates.” (T9, para 179). A third says “...in the past it has been the way that the charter you would get for your ships increased in relation to the cost of living and that was an indication for what you later had to pay in addition for repair for example. That is not working any longer for a few years now. The rates that you get for your ship remain at an extremely low level. The costs, however, are still going further up.” (T11, para 344). The same expert claims that freight rates will not be increasing, as competition by road and rail does not allow for cost increases: “...due to the introduction of the SECA we have massively lost ground vis-à-vis the truck, also vis-à-vis the train, because our energy costs are, no matter where the current prices lie, around a third higher than before.” (T11, para 306). These experts argue in line with classical economic theory. They claim freight rates are unlikely to change, at least in the short term, if the same amount of shipping companies and customers are active on the market, despite increases in compliance costs.

Five experts argued that there was **no direct link** between environmental legislation and freight rates, meaning that they might expect freight rates to increase, but irrespective of the legal environment. Arguments supporting this statement were coded slightly more often than the aforementioned no-change-argument. “The freight rates are developed on the market by demand and supply – as simple as that.” an expert explains (T6, para 206; compare T10, para

175). Overcapacities of shipping volume are leading to low freight rates: “It is natural that the supply of vessel space on the world market is increasing accordingly, while the business demand, the transport demand stays the same. If you think about it, we naturally experience a decline in freight rates - Regardless of environmental legislation. That is developing unattached from that.” (T6, para 206). Another adds: “I do not think that we can find a direct link between increase in operational costs and increase in freight rates in the deep-sea, because simply if there are enough ships to carry the available cargo globally of all ship types, that is what will define the freight rate in many cases, with or without environmental legislation. The freight rate will simply reflect what additional ships and what cargo we have and therefore shipowners will be losing money. But that is what has been happening traditionally in shipping for hundred years, so it would not change now. What would change of course is the extra pressure on the shipowners on an already challenging market to basically survive.” (T2, para 108). Despite customers liking greener ships, they will not pay higher freight rates for environmental installations, experts argue: “Currently we have enough tonnage on the market that the customer can chose whom he takes. That then means that if I do green shipping it can make the difference that I do win the tender, but not necessary that I get a premium because of that. If the market is the other way round, that tonnage is short and cargo so much that every vessel is being taken, then it does not matter. Well, at the moment it is a little bit like the shipper can chose and he will certainly, if he has an ISO certificate, say: Okay, I take the one with a little higher standard as my partner. But that does not mean that we get a premium.” (T10, para 123). E10 argues that environmental legislation has no influence whatsoever on the freight rates. Also, he claims that consolidation is an effect of the market, not of environmental legislation: “If there is a surplus supply of tonnage the freight rates are down. If there is a surplus offer of cargo, the freight rates are up, independent of environmental frame conditions. The environmental frame conditions are valid the entire time. That means that if the market is so bad as at the moment – to maintain a vessel, to invest, to pay back debt services while complying with all obligations is expensive – then it can happen that many shipowners will go bankrupt. And that will also happen. But that has reasons based on the up and down tendencies of the market. Market! Well, the driving force for the survival of the shipowners is the market. If the market is bad very many shipowners are doing very badly.” (T10, para 177). Be it that freight rates are staying the same or changing, experts providing arguments in support of these first two categories strongly believe that environmental legislation and the price of transport are developing independently of each other, being a product of supply and demand for cargo transport on the market. The perceptions of these experts are in line with economic theory on supply and demand. Still, the minority of experts argue along these lines.

Evidence that they were **unsure** about the effect of environmental legislation on freight rates was given by eight experts. “I have no idea. No one knows that so far.” (T7, para 121; compare T2, para 74), an expert says on the possibility of passing on cost increases to customers. One reason of uncertainty might be that freight rates are a function of not only environmental costs, but terminal, charter and all sorts of other cost factors, that might see increases or decreases at the same time (see T7, para 138). A container carrier states they have little idea how freight rates will develop: “...such a fight for rates has occurred already three years ago, where the rates went way down, but eventually all of that remains to be seen. Well, I believe, we may not... we may not allow ourselves to comment on that...” (T7, para 124). An EU official states

that individual company behaviour is hard to predict and may depend on many factors: “You are de facto dealing with a competitive industry and it is an individual company decision whether they are passing on the marginal costs to the customer or whether they first absorb the costs to keep market shares. That also has to do with the positioning in the market. Therefore, I think it is more complicated than simply passing on the costs. In the end, you would expect and hope that in a well-functioning market the costs are ultimately passed on just like that as they also should be, because the final customer is after all the reason for why this activity is being done in the first place and should also pay the relevant costs.” (T12, para 126). That freight rate developments depend very much on individual company behaviour is supported by an employee of E7 present in the interview: “That is because ship operator 1 has a different margin or different pricing system than we have, for example and depending on each individual calculation a different leeway. And certainly, the one may give in more at times and the other one less. That is what I would say, economically speaking.” (T7, para 123). An expert with national legislation states that shipping companies might be unsure themselves whether they should increase or decrease rates: “That is certainly always the system supply and demand. That means I need to find a customer for the offered freight rate as well. If I do not find one I have to give some thought to the question if I want to operate on a smaller profit margin. And if I do not want to do that then my mill might stop grinding altogether and is contributing a profit margin of zero. There one needs to calculate thoroughly which way one wants to go.” (T8, para 280). E7 supports the notion that shipping companies must find their path between increasing freight rates to cover additional costs and avoiding bankruptcy when customers stop buying their service (compare T7, para 145, see also T4, para 170 on constant price wars among operators). The development of freight rates in this scenario is hard to predict. One expert argues that a difficult competitive situation might lead to freight rates decreasing further: “I mean, when you have this kind of change in the patterns and somebody is losing out you know people would take measures to try and regain a lost market share. It may happen.” (T5, para 237). Judging from experience in the automotive industry one expert believes that the shipping industry will find creative ways to cope with cost increases without increasing freight rates: “...with the introduction of a new emission legislation [for automotive] where the impact assessment would state 400 Euros per car, you never observed an average price jump of 400 Euros, but what happened instead was that the industry would introduce innovations as an option which they would have otherwise introduced for free or maybe a year later. So, inside that diverse operational framework the industry regrouped itself in order to somehow absorb the costs and you actually did not observe any effects on the purchase prices of the products. Apparently, that is how consumer markets work.” (T12, para 128).

A total of eleven out of twelve experts support the notion that environmental legislation will lead to **freight rates increasing**. This majority statement also received the largest number of codings on freight rates as shown in Figure 5-3. “...naturally if my utilities costs are higher than I also have to change something at the freight rates. Then I can think about what may be accepted. That’s it.” (T8, para 277; see also T11, para 282 on having increased freight rates and waiting to see how customers will react), an expert with national legislation explains. E9 agrees: “...the higher the operating costs the more we need to charge for the cargo” (T9, para 85; see also T10, para 163; T5, para 186). Immanent bankruptcy might encourage companies to try and charge higher prices: “...these increases in costs are so big that if you do not get additional

revenue you will go bust.” (T5, para 234). An expert working for an environmental organisation states: “Well, I think the shipping companies somehow have to pass on all of that [cost increase]. They could not pay that themselves, because the problem is, their own margins are currently already so small that if they are lucky or to a certain degree successful they will just break even...” (T3, para 96). An expert working for a container operator voices a similar idea: “One will come to according agreements with one’s partners, but everything will go on the way it is somehow and the customers will now hopefully come up with these additional costs.” (T7, para 108). He stresses: “...the customer has no, NO option in the end to bring his container from Hamburg to New York without the transporting shipping companies sailing through two ECAs. And if we now assume that the shipping company needs to comply with this legislation and if we now assume that MGO is the only real alternative at the moment then that will mean that the customer will not get the transport service at the old price, as every shipping company has to carry out investments for MGO.” (T7, para 112). Another expert argues that the same situation applies to the Northern European waters as well: “Where it becomes relevant is the ferry traffic, in the British Channel and in the Baltic Sea. There the costs may be passed on. They argue the contrary, but... (...) They will certainly ask for slightly higher freight rates for the passage of trucks or trailers and in my opinion, they will also receive them, because to drive the same distance with the truck is far too wasteful. That is even more expensive.” (T8, para 139).

A lack of viable alternatives seems thus a clear indicator of a likely increase in freight rates. E7 gives a rough estimate for freight rate increases: “Five to thirty per cent one can say. (...) ...depending on the journey, how often one passes through an ECA and how long one spends in said ECA – the longer one travels through that the more expensive it will get.” (T7, para 117). A short sea shipper estimates freight rate increases between 5 and 40 percent (T5, para 192). Being asked for differences among operators he adds: “I guess there is a difference in the way that the surcharges will be calculated and the price - but the principals will be the same.” (T5, para 196). The same opinion is given by a ferry operator who states: “...we have to pass these costs on to our customers. (...) We have absolutely no other choice. I cannot tell you by how much the freight rates will be increasing and the freight rates themselves are as well, let me say, confidential. They are bargained with each customer, thus with each big forwarding agency, individually, but there will be, in the form of a surcharge, there will be a cost burden passed on to the customers” (T4, para 166-168, see also T2, para 66 on Baltic Sea ferries increasing their fares to absorb extra compliance costs). He adds however: “To what extent the customer will accept that, we will have to see.” (T4, para 85). An expert working in national legislation states that cost increases can certainly be passed on “not everywhere, but in many places.” (T8, para 139). “The question is: Do the others do that as well? If I am the only one who is doing that, I am automatically losing cargo. If the add-on is too high and there are alternative routes like here in Northern Europe for example the rail or the street, then I am losing cargo to the competitors. That is the market.” (T11, para 280). One expert states that passing on cost increases will be **easier for shorter routes** than for longer routes: “...the share of fuel costs is higher with longer routes. We have competitors that sail from Travemünde all the way to Finland. These vessels need around 150, 160 tons of fuel per sail, times the higher costs. That is going to be more difficult to retrieve from the customers than if the route is shorter and the

share of fuel costs is not as high.” (T4, para 49). E5 collaborates on this stating: “...the longer the ocean route the bigger the increase will be.” (T5, para 198).

Experts do not seem to agree on the development of freight rates due to higher environmental compliance costs. Some argue not to know, while others believe there will be no increase of freight rates, despite a theoretical relation among variables. Other experts see no relation between the two concepts, while the forth (and most prominent) group expects an increase of freight rates once operational costs have increased. Variables mentioned by experts to influence freight rates are pictured in Figure 5-4. The likelihood that freight rates might be passed on to consumers seems to increase with fewer transport alternatives as well as with the length of the journey passed in the SECA. Ongoing consolidation might support companies in increasing freight rates, firstly by decreasing supply of shipping capacity and secondly by the facilitation of collusion where fewer actors are active on the market. Freight rates seem largely a product of supply and demand, although increases in environmental compliance costs might pressure the shipping company to increase their prices as a means of staying clear of bankruptcy. Freight rates are hard to study as they are agreed on individually between operator and freight forwarder and are oftentimes kept secret. The outcome of negotiations will certainly also depend on the bargaining power of each party. The costs that companies need to calculate with are not only a product of environmental legislation, but also incorporate harbour fees, expenses for staff and maintenance and importantly the individual operative efficiency of a shipping company. All these factors may be reflected in the freight rate. Other influencing factors mentioned by experts are the financial means a company has to support its strategy and the unpredictable behaviour of competitors.

Figure 5-4: Influence of environmental compliance costs on freight rates

5.2.3 Expert perceptions on modal shift

As discussed in the theoretical chapter, **available data on modal shift is insufficient** and current studies paint no clear picture on the prevalence and scope of shifts to other modes of transport. Estimates range from non-existent to 50% of overall volumes for modal shift due to environmental legislation in the North and Baltic Seas. The mechanisms of preferment of one mode of transport over another seem unclear and the freight rate seems not to be the only determinant of modal choice. The qualitative study aims to investigate what industry experts believe about modal shift and on which variables shipping companies base their decision-making for a certain mode.

Six sub-categories were developed from the data as shown in Figure 5-5. 53 statements were made on the possible existence of modal shift, compared to 23 statements on modal shift being impossible, with ten experts commenting on each subcategory. Considering the amount of text coded it can be subsumed that modal shift is a relevant issue for the industry. Modal shift to road transport was of higher importance to experts with 35 codings than shifts to other modes. Rail transport and shifts to other water routes followed with 17 and 14 codings respectively. Fives statements were made on changed sourcing, meaning that goods might be sourced locally or from other countries to avoid or shorten sea transport. As becomes apparent from Figure 5-5, the shift to road transport was also most prominently mentioned by experts in terms of the length of statements (see amount of text). The competitive position of other transport modes to the shipping industry becomes apparent from the number of codings, number of experts and amount of text coded simultaneously. Road transport is the main competitor followed by rail transport and other water routes. Changed sourcing was linked to few and short codings, likely making it the least influential variable discussed here.

Figure 5-5: Codings on modal shift by number of codings, number of experts and amount of text coded

Ten out of twelve experts argued that **modal shift can happen**: “If the add-on is too high and there are alternative routes like here in Northern Europe for example the rail or the street then

I am losing cargo to the competitors. That is the market.” (T11, para 280), one expert explains. Another adds: “...there will be a cost burden passed onto the customers and at that point the risk of modal shift is arising.” (T4, para 168). A third suggests: “...maritime traffic is becoming more expensive and by that other modes of transport are becoming interesting.” (T7, para 118). Despite these testimonies another expert stresses that the fear of modal shift is not based on hard data: “...people start talking about certain cargo being moved away from sea and moving to road or rail within Europe. And again, that is a bit of an unintended effect, because you know, ship transportation is the most efficient way of going about. But I have not seen any studies or any concrete data to show that this is happening, but it is a concern.” (T2, para 56). Another expert underlines that the scope of modal shift is hard to guess, but its existence is likely: “If shipping increases prices but the competing modes of transport do not, you must expect some kind of a modal shift. How much exactly where? I am not sure. But clearly, if you have to go out with a 15 per cent cost increase, your costumers will look out for alternatives. (...) I think everybody has got this idea of what may happen but there are so many factors in the equation here that you cannot really make a model.” (T5, para 186; see also T1, para 128 on the impossibility to come up with reliable numbers on modal shift).

Ten out of twelve experts name reasons why **modal shift is unlikely**. Shipping has several advantages over other modes, an expert explains: “There is no better alternative than shipping. One simply has to say that. It is super economical. It is just a very fine thing. You can transport everything. Secure.” (T9, para 181). He goes on: “...there exists no alternative compared to the vessel regarding such flexibility and such transport capacity. Well, a vessel can quickly enter different harbours and leave them again, can take all sorts of things aboard, also bulky goods, break bulk, heavy cargo. (...) Well, also in the Scandinavian area or in the Baltic area, whatever, there is absolutely no alternative to sea transport.” (T9, para 185). The cost advantages of shipping are stressed by another expert: “...ship transport is by far the most economical way of transport. Because few people are involved, because the route of transport does not cost any charges, because the maintenance of the route of transport does not cost any charges... (...) With a higher degree of efficiency than the train. Efficiency regarding the fuel efficiency. Well, a ship consumes much, much less than the train.” (T10, para 183). Other experts stress that it is the **political will** to favour shipping, an influence that might also make modal shift less likely. An expert working with EU institutions acknowledges the danger of modal shift: “It is certainly true that there is a risk related to having modal shift back on road not only in terms of emissions but also in terms of all those other effects related to road transport that ultimately come with it and that’s also one of the reasons why the European Commission is actively supporting modal shift to the sea as an example.” (T12, para 43). He goes on explaining: “Well, in the end you are dealing with a goods market and there are shippers and they will look for options and within a diverse decision-making environment. And the industry as well as politics try to influence this decision-making environment, so that someone who, I don’t know, has to transport one hundred tons of cement from A to B is induced to do that simply with a ship instead of doing it by road or rail.” (T12, para 45). The political intention is thus clearly to prevent a shift away from maritime transport. One expert claims, however, that political actions and intentions are not always coherent: “...if I take a look at what is currently financed especially by the EU in terms of traffic routes, be it railway, be it street... There they invest massively and extend [the routes] and the more they extend the more cargo they attract.” (T11, para 302).

One crucial variable that experts discuss is that modal shift may only occur where **competing modes of transport are available** (see T11, para 312). “Well I do not think it is the type of goods. It depends on the corridor that you are moving goods in. If there is an alternative that involves either road transport or rail transport or if there is an alternative that rather than a long ocean voyage you have a longer road voyage and a shorter ocean voyage. These are the kind of moves that you could see.” (T5, para 206), an expert explains. In the North and Baltic Sea areas, different to most other routes, alternative modes are oftentimes an option: “...there are parallel transport possibilities on land. Well, Germany-Finland, there I have the option to drive through Poland and the Baltic states and of course in the end to take a short sea route somewhere. I have the option as well to use the short sea routes here across Denmark and to use the bridge and I can drive through Sweden and take the little jump across from Sweden to Finland. There we see a danger of modal shift. And here with us, if I apply that to the Southern Baltic Sea, there is certainly the danger that cargo will be shifted to even shorter routes, as the crow flies and then take the way across Denmark.” (T4, para 51), an expert describes. Modal shift mostly seems to affect short sea shipping: “If there is modal shift, I only know it about the Baltic Sea...” (T7, para 174). There might, however, also be competing modes for longer routes: “The railway tries to run from Hamburg with the train to China.” (T10, para 183). An expert describes that longer sea routes might be replaced by shorter ones: “Our insights up ‘til now are that the longer the sea route is, the higher is the risk of modal shift.” (T4, para 47). He gives a rule for the route the cargo is usually using: “Wherever the shortest route is. The cargo is seeking the shortest path.” (T4, para 37). Sometimes goods are shifted back and forth: “But there are certainly goods that have been transported on planes until now that are again shipped in refrigerated containers. Such things are winning us cargo again.” (T6, para 212). One expert argues that statement on modal shift are difficult to make, as shipping makes only one part of the transport chain: “If I have customers sitting directly in Gdania, that is in the harbour where the container is being unloaded, it is evidently cheaper to do it with the ship. If I am, however, located in Warsaw or even further to the South of Poland it can easily be cheaper to do that by truck or by train. You have to take the whole transport chain into account. We are only a very small part of that.” (T11, para 294). E5 argues that depending on the route in question one mode of transport may be cheaper at one time and another mode at another. No clear indication on a difference in freight rate may be given, as it depends on many factors (T5, para 217-221). A **lack of road and rail infrastructure** will certainly inhibit modal shift. “For that you will also need the necessary infrastructure, that is the necessary road infrastructure at the same time. Well, to be honest, I don’t see – I don’t see that in the Baltic states – well, it is always argued that then everybody is driving through Poland to the Baltic states and back from the Baltic states – but I do not see the road infrastructure there.” (T3, para 112). The **price of alternative transport** will influence the modal choice decision. Fuel price decreases can lead to transport price decreases in all transport modes: “[Freight rates for street and rail] ...are currently getting less expensive, because the energy costs are sinking and that really was the biggest cost factor in the last years. For us as well by the way. (...) ... still due to the introduction of the SECA we have massively lost ground vis-à-vis the truck, also vis-à-vis the train, because our energy costs are, no matter where the current prices lie, around a third higher than before.” (T11, para 304), an expert argues.

A choice of mode depends not only on the route, but also the **product to be transported**: “For bitumen and such things, chemicals, it is more difficult. But in the short sea area: Container, ferries that have trailers aboard, trains and so on, those are all competing.” (T6, para 212) one expert says. Another explains which goods might experience modal shift: “...all goods that are rather lightweight but have some volume. That is electronics and stuff that is carted over from somewhere in Asia. These typical advertised-for-products that come from China.” (T8, para 153). Heavy goods will most likely not be moved to road and rail transport: “That is going to be difficult due to the weight of the good. The effort necessary to transport x tons of the good x is just too expensive. That will not be done. That does not pay off. For that case you have the small mini bulker that will distribute that. They run on small engines, they run slowly, they don’t consume as much fuel. That is another story. The earnings per ton are not so high that [road transport] would be an option.”, an expert states (T6, para 220). “...from Finland paper over here, paper reels I would deem rather impossible, because the weight plays a relative role there and then you can only load relatively few reels on such a truck.” (T8, para 153), E8 names as an example. “...when you are transporting bulk materials, iron ore, those things, that is currently done by ship for obvious reasons.” (T12, para 47), another expert collaborates restrictions in cargo weight and size.

Transport time might be a reason to switch mode: “Regarding the transport time, if you go from water to the street or to the rail you can even achieve an improvement. (...) Time can certainly also be a cost factor, if I only receive the money when the goods have reached the customer then a few days or weeks can certainly make a difference.” (T11, para 318-320). E5 argues that the relationship between transport time and transport mode is not set in stone: “In terms of time again it will very much depend on from where to where, you know. If you have to go a detour because you are staying on the road or are you basically driving along where the ship was sailing in the past. It is difficult to give one answer to that.” (T5, para 210). Rest times need to be taken into account as well: “The truck is loaded somewhere in the South West of Germany in the morning, or in the Netherlands and someplace. In the afternoon or in the evening it is here at the harbour. It is taken across at night. The driver can at the same time get his rest period, the legal rest period and is in Scandinavia the next morning and can drive on. That you cannot achieve with a general cargo carrier or with a RoRo-Carrier via Skagen using the long sea route, I think, within two to three days.” (T4, para 39), an expert explains. Certain goods have stricter requirements for transport time than others: “Some goods could go cheaper via ocean, but they are very time-sensitive, so they go by road all the way. That is a commodity thing.” (T5, para 216), an expert says. Another adds: “The more time-sensitive and the more valuable the goods are, the more often they are transported by truck.” (T1, para 131). “I believe that it is the value of the goods that determines that.” (T6, para 212), a third agrees.

Capacity restrictions form another variable influencing modal decisions: “They are claiming that cargo will then be moved to the streets but have not done any calculations what kind of costs that would imply there and whether there is enough truck capacity at all and enough drivers.” (T8, para 143), an expert argues. A shortage in truck drivers is a competitive argument for short sea shipping: “...if I take a look at the ferry connection to the Baltic states I do not drive on the ferry with my truck, but only leave the trailer there and let it be pulled onto the vessel and I take my tractor unit and drive on here. That means that it sails across with my trailer

alone and it is then taken over at the destination port by another tractor unit. (...) ...the bottleneck is meanwhile with the drivers of the trucks.” (T8, para 145). Also, roads may become congested: “In part we have overcapacities because we have many too many roads and too little traffic. And we have the complete opposite.” (T8, para 149), the same expert describes. Loading capacity is an important argument for shipping: “You can certainly load our iron ore onto a truck or also onto a train. Our barge makes 230,000 tons at once. The railway is at 1,000 tons I believe, the heaviest train, and the truck does not make 30 tons. How many trucks would we have to drive in order to transport 230,000 tons of iron ore? That will be the end of it.” (T10, para 179). Constraints apply to some extent to the shipping industry as well: “Even if the Baltic Sea is relatively small. A lot of ships fit on there. The problem is the waterways and the problem is the available berths. And: Yes, there are problems.” (T11, para 300), an expert describes.

Negative environmental effects might be linked to modal shift: “We have put the argument forward from the very beginning that (...) it may downright come to negative effects for the environment, as suddenly emissions that are today taking place at the sea and for that matter far away from society – (...) ...but the trucks, they are driving along right in front of us. The trucks themselves are, related to the sulphur emissions, indeed CONSIDERABLY better, as only almost sulphur free fuel is sold on the streets. That is correct. But they have other impacts. They have all these fine particulate emissions due to the diesel motors. They have NO_x emissions, even if there is a lot being done with the current Euro V or I don’t know what they have at the moment. But you evidently have the impacts of the traffic itself, of noise, of road congestion and so forth.” (T4, para 59). Another expert adds: “If you look at the emissions per unit of cargo transported, whichever way you define it, or whether it is CO₂ emission per unit or whether it is SO₂ and NO_x, I think these will go up, no doubt, because, you know, it does not have the economies of scale that you have with shipping.” (T2, para 64). The environmental effects of a shift to rail transport are not so clear: “...what is the environmental impact of rail? I do not know. I mean, is it a diesel engine? Is it powered by the grid? You know, and if you look at the grid, is the grid nuclear-powered? Is the grid coal-powered? Is the grid renewable? So, I think it is difficult to assess.” (T2, para 64). Questions of morality might play a role in modal choice: “...to shift something to the road I think no one today will somehow announce that with a clean conscience and say: Let us drive a few more trucks somehow to Scandinavia.” (T9, para 158). Environmental consideration, however, seem to play only a minor role in company modal decision-making.

Modal shift to road transport is discussed by ten out of twelve experts, far more than a shift to other modes of transport. “We think that freight will move mostly to the streets.” (T4, para 57) one expert argues. Another explains how shipping cost increases might encourage a shift to the road: “If you have a ferry from Rostock [harbour town in Germany] across to Sweden the trucks will drive up there and then cross with the ferry. The cargo is already on the truck. If the ferries now say, if Scandlines now says: We will increase the rates by 30 per cent, because we have to use more expensive fuel and a forwarder is not able to pay that he will say: Well, then the journey is not paying off like this. The truck will leave the ship and they will drive up the road until... as far as they can get, I don’t know, up until Latvia, Estonia, up there and they will say: If we want to go to Finland we will take the short sea connection with Tallink or something similar, because that is then becoming cheaper and we don’t have the longer sea connection

which is more expensive. Those are very simple planning models that the forwarders are using. And they make a lot of sense, these models.” (T6, para 222; see T6, para 214 for a similar example of a container that was previously transported from Rotterdam by feeder vessel through the Kiel Canal to Poland and is now being transported directly by truck). When discussing the competitive advantage of road transport one expert claims that for a route above 100 kilometres the ship will always be more competitive: “...well, everybody knows that up until a hundred kilometres that [modal shift] is not unlikely, but from a hundred kilometres upwards the factor, the increase so to speak relating to the rate for the train plus 100 or for the truck plus 300 is entirely unrealistic, entirely. (...) No ship is now going to Rotterdam and the goods are then coming from Rotterdam with the truck, that is truly total bullshit. (agitated)” (T3, para 106). The same position is taken by another expert: “Where it becomes relevant is the ferry traffic, in the British Channel and in the Baltic Sea. There the costs may be passed on. (...) They will certainly ask for a slightly higher freight rate for the passage of trucks or trailers and in my opinion they will also receive them, because to drive the same distance with the truck is far too wasteful. That is even more expensive.” (T8, para 139). From these statements it becomes evident that price is an important variable. One expert clearly states: “...we mainly move lorries or things that go on a lorry. So, whether it goes on a ship or they stay on a lorry - it is the same move. And therefore, which way it goes is very much a combination of price and time.” (T5, para 214).

While the costs of shipping are likely to increase, the **price of road transport** might also be subject to legal changes: “...look at the White Paper Traffic of the European Commission from the last election period. There it said very clearly that we need to get to the way of an internalisation of the external costs...” an expert argues, “...we now are the first ones who start to include air pollution control into the calculations. Other states are not yet doing that. It is permitted but is also being capped. Then one needs to have a concept for this noise story that also needs to be included in the calculations. Then the accident situations need to be included. Well, I am curious what will come out of that. (Laughing) The truck is not getting less expensive then, I do not need to worry.” (T8, para 177). Compared to other modes, the wide **availability** of roads might make shifts feasible: “...there will be a shift of transport capacity towards the road in the Baltic Sea. But there they have roads.” (T7, para 119) an expert argues the necessity of availability. “I mean, if you look at the congestion, everyone is saying that it is bad, but in general I believe that we have a very good infrastructure [on the roads]. Well, and the economic costs of traffic jams and such things are not yet really finding a way into the calculations.” (T6, para 218) another adds. An advantage of road transport is **flexibility**. “...[you] tell them: ‘Get the goods at 9pm and bring them over. That’s it.’” (T6, para 218), an expert describes this benefit. “The more it gets into the distribution, the distribution logistics, into very detailed consignments, the less easy it gets to do that by ship.” (T12, para 47), another expert adds.

Eight experts discuss **modal shifts to rail transport**. Many variables are mentioned by experts that would make a shift of cargo to rail unattractive: “...as the rail is not at all able, in our experience, to take on these quantities.” (T4, para 57). **Capacity constraints** are also mentioned by another interviewee: “The railway systems are already transporting everything that they are able to transport, and I believe by now everything that they might possibly transport. The rail infrastructure in Europe and in Germany is... in Germany it is rather poor for cargo transport,

but still relatively good compared to the rest of Europe. If you want to ship to Poland or to Latvia or somewhere up there it is really... it is almost impossible. (...) That is a superb option but limited by the infrastructure.” (T6, para 216). Capacity constraints play a role with the infrastructure as well as with the amount of cargo loadable on a train. “Well, there is this rail track to Shanghai, but evidently you cannot drag off as much by that as with the ship.” (T9, para 181), another expert adds. **Connectivity** might also pose a problem: “...it is simply not possible with the train, due to technical reasons due to connectivity.” (T1, para 122), one expert argues. Another explains: “...we also still have this lane system change in the area of the border between Poland and the Baltic states. They are still linked to the Russian network and it is thus very complex and it is no competition and for a foreseeable amount of time it will not be. Decades will still need to pass and furthermore the railroad systems there are rather ailing. In the direction of Sweden it is certainly worth a thought. (...) There are a lot of mass transports coming... also coming with the railway from Sweden.” (T8, para 159-161). Limited **flexibility** might prove a further hindrance to modal shift: “Oh, difficult, the train is coming at a certain point of time, will be provided at one point, they are coming punctually at 4pm to pick the goods up and that is all very difficult... until then... the container might not be quite ready or the shift has not ended or something like that.” (T6, para 218). **Dependability** is also an issue with rail transport, as the system is known for occasional strikes: “We have recently seen it with the railroad strike... in the instant where my medium of transport... where I need to rebuild my logistic chain as the one who is responsible for the supply of a certain factory because my present distributor is not able to deliver within the agreed time frame any more. (...) ...then I need to build my transport chain up anew, build my logistic chain up anew and when I do that I do that with the intention of letting it run like that a little time once more. When cargo is gone, it is gone.” (T8, para 155). In terms of **transport times** railways might have a competitive advantage: “There is already a hell of a lot transported via the railway. There is a great, great deal done via the railway. The vessel is, however, also not a serious competitor there because the transport times are simply too long.” (T8, para 163). **Price** is named as one of the more influential variables in support of shipping: “At the moment we are still cheaper [than the train]. That is why we get the cargo. That is very simple.” (T11, para 292, on a price advantage of vessels over railway compare also T10, para 179). Depending on the route this calculation might change, however: “...the customer figures out (...): What is cheaper for me? Is it cheaper to do that by train, then I am closer to my place where I want to have the container in the end or will I do that by ship and then I will still have to transport the container further forward again? That is a numerical example.” (T11, para 290). He adds: “Bulk materials, cheap, everything that is cheap. I mean for example if you have grit or something like that, building materials, if you have to take large amounts of that from A to B there is really only the alternative that you either take a ship or you try that by train. Whereas the ship is then still cheaper unless you need the building materials somewhere entirely different in the end. If your destination may not be reached by waterway in the end, if it is located in the middle of the inner land it can definitely make sense to rather do it by train, but trucks with those amounts that just does not pay off. You will do that with small charges, but not with big charges. Everything else depends on the price. That means: Where is the transport the cheapest?” (T11, para 316). **Further constraints** are voiced by another expert: “The railway is shooting itself in the foot, because it is not willing to accept that they need to be service provider for the forwarder, but they want to compete with

the forwarder. That cannot work in the long run. Well and apart from that the railway system would evidently be interesting, at least in certain areas on the main routes, if we were to truly develop that down there. Then one only disembarks one time in... in the Mediterranean one time and is distributing that in the whole of Europe, but there is also a lack of... there is also a lack of preparedness within the EU, Europe, to work on a coordinated approach.” (T8, para 171).

The feasibility of a **shift to other water routes** is discussed by six experts. Shorter sea routes may bring cost advantages (T5, para 250). Still, **bypassing SECAs or NECAs** is a main argument to do so: “Certain ports that are outside the emission control areas would certainly be gaining competitive advantage. If a slightly different route can mean you are out of an ECA then certain ports will certainly be happy to be in that position.” (T2, para 54, see T6, para 107 for a similar argument). The expert named ports on the British west coast as an option to circumvent the North Sea SECA (T2, para 56). Mediterranean ports might also be an option to save higher fuel costs: “And the question is, if there is a bureaucratic system Europe and all vessels that are currently going to Europe are subjecting themselves to that, okay. But will they do that? Well, the Chinese shipping companies, the COSCO and so forth, whether they will then say: No, we will then just sail until, I don’t know, Greece and throw everything off board, turn around and sail back and they then do not want to go to Rotterdam or Hamburg or to Poland in the Baltic Sea any more... such things.” (T6, para 107). This same argument is voiced by E1 as well: “If the EU now does something and defines SECAs and NECAs here for the North and Baltic Seas, that is evidently a competitive disadvantage for the harbours here in the North and also for [city A]. That is at least the fear of some shipowners, harbour companies, that the vessels do not unload their containers in the North range, in the North, for example, but rather go to the Mediterranean Sea - that the harbours there get more business, make more profits.” (T1, para 50). Regional laws that bring about bureaucratic demands might discourage ship operators from frequenting these seas, an expert argues: “One will see how that will influence shipping when national states or national areas are demanding such a thing and a vessel, a big shipowner that comes here one time and suddenly a thing is asked of him that he is not at all interested in, that brings a bulk of administration, if he is not saying: Okay, then I am just not going there, basta!” (T10, para 61). Another expert does not believe this option is viable: “How will you go around the SECAs? If I want to get to Gdansk or to St. Petersburg or even if I want to go to Rotterdam, how can I go around the SECA? Hence, we have all the big harbours within the SECA and I think that in the medium term another SECA will be established in the Mediterranean Sea.” (T3, para 108). Also, a **shift to other ship operators** on the same route could be a reaction to increased costs: “It could be moved to competitors, you know, it could increase the utilisation of other competitors within the same route. So, it is a bit of a last man standing wins.” (T2, para 62).

Only four experts have included **changed sourcing** into their arguments. Buying goods from companies outside emission control areas might save costs: “And in addition to that you will see some shift because of sourcing will completely change. So instead of buying your paper in Finland you may buy your paper in Canada.” (T5, para 206). “...it certainly would make sense, for many current transports, to think about whether they are very necessary, especially for global transports from the Far East or also from wherever within Europe.” (T1, para 125),

another expert adds. Changed sourcing can mean questioning the long-term viability of a globalised world: “I rather go by the idea that in the long term fewer goods need to be transported by way of shipping, simply because more and more is being transferred back to Europe and to America, simply because production costs in China are becoming too high. Ultimately it all got started, if you look back at it, with globalisation that is with the creation of... with the shift of basic production to China. That is how it mainly got started... that the services across the Pacific from America and Europe-Asia here got started. And there we again see certain tendencies, that one day this cost advantage is not there so much anymore. Then one can rather also handle that with countries closer to Europe. I am thinking towards the direction of Africa or also towards the East of Europe. And there we would not necessarily need these vessels anymore.” (T8, para 59).

One expert stresses that **predicting modal shift is highly complex**, especially in the light of price changes in other modes of transport: “Yesterday they said in the news that the railway is increasing its prices again in December. (...) How that is now shifting we cannot yet foresee. (...) Basically, we do not have these numbers either, because we do not know where the breakeven point is. We do not know. We have tried...” (T4, para 172, 212). The simple **model on modal shift** developed from the literature links increased costs of vessel operations directly with decreases in shipping operations. Evidence from the QUAL study shows that many other variables influence modal choice, including the availability of alternative goods, the characteristics of the goods, transport time and safety issues. Also, both the costs of vessel operations and the costs of road and rail transport are constantly changing due to economic and political influences. A model including the inductively developed variables on modal shift is presented in Figure 5-6.

Figure 5-6: Variables on modal shift developed from QUAL study

5.2.4 Expert perceptions on further economic effects of MEL

An increase in freight rates for shipping on North and Baltic Seas as a result of increased environmental compliance costs seems possible, but disagreement among experts regarding the relationship between the two variables remains strong. If increases in freight rates occur, this might affect trade flows. Experts discussed how MEL might lead to an increase or decrease in capacity supplied, as shown in Figure 5-7. 13% of statements coded were on increasing ship sizes and 4% on growing companies, both leading to an increase in shipping capacity. The large majority of statements was made on four variables that would lead to a decrease in shipping capacity, however. With 50% of all codings, consolidation of the industry was of great importance to the experts interviewed. 16% of statements coded were made on routes closing and a further 13% on vessel scrappings. Only very few statements were made on vessels being redeployed to other waters or routes, making redeployments variable number six to emerge from the data on trade flow effects.

Figure 5-7: Codings on effects of MEL on trade flows

Four experts argued that **shipping companies will be growing** and adding capacity. Added pressure due to environmental compliance costs also incentivises companies to work closer together. “Well, the shipping companies, the big liner shipping companies, are growing more and more together. They affiliate, they are growing bigger and bigger. Alliances are being built in order to operate profitably at all.” (T9, para 191; see also T3, para 88 on increased cooperation among competitors) an expert argues. Asked for what characterises these growing companies one expert explains: “It is the Greek owners, the Chinese, Japanese, German owners and some of the Nordic owners are those that traditionally and now still keep increasing their fleet capacity. In certain ship types, that they, you know, in their wisdom, perceive to be the ones that would need that capacity in the future.” (T2, para 122) .

Another development leading to increases in supply are **increasing ship sizes**. Five experts commented on this industry trend. “...it already now has trade effects that one also simply operates with bigger vessels and that one tries to operate more and more efficient due to the cost pressure.” (T9, para 207), an expert describes how companies try to make use of economies of scale. “What they are building now are the mega carriers, the huge cargo ships. Now they have the 20,000 TEU in the making...” (T8, para 237; see also T6, para 228) another expert adds. Saving on personnel is certainly one reason to operate with bigger units (compare T8, para 61). Lower investments costs per ton transported is another variable that might also be relevant with regards to ballast water treatment systems. “...the vessels become larger and larger out of pressure to become more efficient, to reach economies of scale. The bigger the vessel with the same engine, maybe even with a smaller engine, the lower the cost per container - that is why you need ever bigger vessels.” (T6, para 206), an expert stresses this argument. Increasing ship sizes may also have positive repercussions on the environment: “The trend goes to building larger vessels, that have a new kind of design, need less fuel by themselves, may transport more, that is more at the same time, which evidently has a certain positive effect for example on the CO₂ emissions in the end and also on the setting of other emissions. Well, that has certain advantages.” (T3, para 94). One expert describes what he terms the cascade effect, whereby larger vessels enter the market replacing smaller ones on certain routes. These smaller ones are in need of a new employment and are replacing the next smallest ship size leading to

increasing ship sizes on all services. "...the problem lies with these very big ones. There the summit is not yet reached. There is still a pile of them coming. That again has a cascade effect on the smaller ships. (...) ...due to this cascade effect, highly modern ships are being made redundant which then find a new employment. They are again replacing someone and so on and so forth.", an expert says (T11, para 368). The cascade effect is also mentioned by E6, but this expert argues that the effect has nothing to do with environmental cost pressures. "Maersk is now sailing into the Baltic Sea with 18,000 [TEU] vessels, that means that they are no longer sailing through the Kiel Canal, but are taking the North route to Gdansk and then you no longer need, I don't know, maybe five feeder vessels. They are no longer occupied, but still produce costs and so forth. What are you going to do with them?" (T6, para 202). E3 describes the cascade effect as follows: "The small ones, they are all sorted out and at the top so to speak new vessels are purchased in addition." (T3, para 94). Increasing vessel sizes and growing companies will lead to increases in capacity supplied and further downward pressure on freight rates.

Three experts argue that as an effect of environmental legislation, vessels might be **redeployed**. "So, certain vessels, older vessels, would be taken out of the routes where, you know, ballast water regulations for example are in place." (T2, para 50), an expert describes. Redeployments are a risky strategy: "It is a double-edged sword, because the shipping markets are so dynamic that you want to be able to quickly... especially for certain trades, you know for ships doing tramp trades you need that flexibility. And obviously, if you have ships that are not able to operate globally simply because of their equipment or their compliance flexibility this is not ideal. But the alternative, which is a fleet-wider renewal of technology implementation, it costs a lot of money. So, I think the laws are changing the dynamics of certain companies and I think, in a way, those companies which operate on a tramp basis they will struggle the most. Their assets will either have to be geared up for worldwide compliance or become less flexible." (T2, para 52). One expert argues that they would like to redeploy their vessels to get around environmental compliance but would not know where to go: "I can only move to where there are flows of cargo. Well and that depends again on... as I said, we are feeder, mainly a feeder carrier, that means we arrange the connecting transport for global shipping companies to Russia, Poland or wherever else. Where do you want to move to? There are no alternatives." (T11, para 330).

Increased **vessel scrappings** are a reaction to environmental protection laws mentioned by six experts. An expert explains how environmental legislation can lead to a significant rejuvenation of the fleet, as operating older assets may no longer commercially be sensible: "...a classic example of that would happen in the past, in the early 90s. It was the double hull tankers, as you may have heard, you know the law being passed at it. So this created a huge shift in the ownership and the age of certain fleets. In particular the Greek market was one of them. The average age of the Greek fleet now is less than 10 years. The tanker fleet. It was not the case before that." (T2, para 46). The expert argues that the ballast water regulation will be a strong driver for replacing older assets (T2, para 48; see also T9, para 97 on old vessels being broken up). Scrappings may thus represent a strategic decision to change to newer vessels, but it may also be necessary when financial means to implement upcoming legislation are not available. "...if money is not available the vessel is so-to-speak put on the dump and when in doubt it is

being sold or scrapped.” (T8, para 38), an expert describes the situation. He adds that often vessels are rather sold than scrapped and the tonnage will usually be kept in the market: “I would very much welcome a European initiative to severely take tonnage out of the market. What is happening at the moment is, if these vessels that are redundant... they are sold to somewhere if you are lucky. But they are not taken from the market.” (T8, para 235). Ship scrapping are, however, more often a reaction to overcapacities in the market than environmental laws. “...recently also due to this shipping crisis many, yes, a lot of tonnage was broken up... also partly ones that have not even reached twenty years. Simply to make space for new tonnage.” (T9, para 99; see also T3, para 65 and 94; T10, para 157; T11, para 368), an expert says. This development links to the cascade effect described above.

Shipping companies hope for **consolidation** of the market to be able to increase costs. As described above, economic theory relates a decrease in supply to price increases. “The number of suppliers is brought to its knees. That means that the number of vessels is decreasing and thus also higher freight rates can be achieved. I again get into a zone where we maybe get from a customer market to a supplier market or where we achieve that it is at least for once to some extent equal.” (T8, para 103), an expert hopes. Competitors wait for consolidation and subsequent increases in the prices they may charge: “If you control a fleet as big as possible then you can evidently one day also say: You will only get my ship if you pay the price of xy. That is what is behind it.” (T11, para 362). Only the most efficient companies will be able to cope with increased compliance costs, an expert argues: “One simply has to try to incorporate that in time and then one has to see whether one can live with that or whether one has to give up the business because it does not yield any profit anymore.” (T10, para 155). Fewer companies on the market might also make **collusion** easier, a captain suggests: “They would have to all agree and would have to say: Well, for example we want to operate more economically now and still, well, better, or whatever else. They would have to agree and say, well, we increase the rates together. Sea transport has become far too cheap. It does not cost anything anymore. A twenty-foot container from Hamburg to Asia, I don’t know, a few hundred Dollars or something, that is nothing anymore. And especially to make sure of sustainable operations one evidently needs to pay the price for that.” (T9, para 179). Although price agreements are illegal under competition law, further experts discuss this possibility. One expert hints that a consolidated market might leave more room for price increases: “I could now formulate a little bit cautiously: Evidently there is also a chance in such a market consolidation as will maybe take place – a chance for the survivors to find a better market environment.” (T4, para 190). The idea of possible collusion is supported by an expert working for the European institutions: “That is a really tricky topic. Someone in my position needs to be very careful with that too. There are legal requirements in terms of arrangements and each individual shipowner is in that situation where he needs to decide what he is doing, but you would hope that the individual market players are complying with the laws. Of course, I am also not naïve. Of course, there is this temptation to not be doing this but that is also associated with a legal risk.” (T12, para 130). The temptation might be higher than in other industries. One expert states: “Well, it is a small community, thus everyone knows the others a little.” (T10, para 221).

Seven experts argued that environmental legislation might lead to certain **routes closing** (See T2, para 44; T4, para 74; T6, para 107; T11, para 276). “Well, in the light of these enormous

cost increases that is naturally, I could imagine, that the one or other services is maybe for the time being discontinued.” (T4, para 87), an expert maintains. One short sea shipping expert reports: “We already see today, not with us, not with [organisation 4], but with some of our competitors, we see the first reactions. DFDS has closed the route Harwich-Esbjerg. Has pulled off the vessel. They say due to SECA. Stena has just proclaimed that they will thin out the Sassnitz route to one ship due to SECA. A number of shipping companies, our competitors, are partly speaking of laying off employees not to a negligible extent, as they expect the trade to decline.” (T4, para 55; see T2, para 58 and T7, para 108 on DFDS closing a route due to SECA laws; see T6, para 215 on TT-line changing their routes because of SECA laws). “We have publicly stated that a number of our routes could be at risk because of this. We have not named any. In spring we did close a route between [city A] in Lithuania and [city B] in Germany. Again, part of the reason here were the coming cost increases. And we could not see the route be sustainable going forward.” (T5, para 54), another short sea operator reports. Certain services are rather more prone to being closed than others. On North and Baltic Seas “the longer services are rather more endangered and then also the services that today can barely keep above the water economically. Thus, where the shipping companies are not taking out large profits, but where the services are also partly operated for strategic reasons. That you say: There will be a growing market in the future. Let me say the Baltic states maybe, Russia. Today I am not yet earning much money with that, but I already have my foot in the door. And if that really picks up I am the one that is already there. Well, in the light of these enormous cost increases that is naturally, I could imagine, that the one or other services is maybe for the time being discontinued.” (T4, para 87). Experts also suggest that shipping companies will try to avoid sailing in North and Baltic Seas. “...when the fuel is getting more expensive, will we still sail there or will we not sail there any longer? Do we want to keep these services running or do we alternatively sail to another harbour where they do not have these regulations...” (T6, para 107), an expert asks. “...local or regional legislation is eventually nonsense, because in the worst case it really only leads to displacement, that is some traffic is driven out...” (T4, para 110), another details the same fears. E10 argues that regional environmental legislation might lead to territorial outsiders either to stay away or to neglect the laws and take their chances with being caught for noncompliance. “And that would be competitive distortion.” he says (T10, para 61).

Effects on consumer prices have been coded only twelve times in total in the whole of qualitative data. This shows that experts were either not knowledgeable or not interested in the impact the industry’s decisions finally had on everyday people. Both explanations seem likely. Another sample would likely have made more sense to study consumer price effects including for example freight forwarders or large producers of consumer products. Variables mentioned by experts in this study will still be discussed here, however. Experts agree that “there are going to be economic consequences on the consumers as well.” (T2, para 66; compare also T3, para 12 and 54). The increase is expected to be moderate, as transport prices only account for a fraction of final product price: “...the customer just has to pay more for all the different items. That will be just some cents for small things and just some euros or, as far as I’m concerned, some 10 euros, for bigger things.” (T3, para 98). E8 calculates that a twenty per cent increase in transport costs will lead to twenty-four cents transport costs instead of twenty cents for a bottle of wine. “...they easily pass that on to the customer. That is not a problem at all.” (T8, para 169), he states. One expert argues that depending on shipping type the effects on consumer

prices might be smaller or larger: “I think we have to separate the commercial shipping, so the deep-sea shipping, we have to separate that from the short sea. (...) To put it that way: If – I’m just using an example – if Maersk or UASC or some other big container operator is in trouble or their operational costs is increased because of ECA this will not – I do not think that you and I as a consumer will see this in the price of the Ipad that we get from China. On the other hand, if let’s say PMO ferries or DFDS or... I’m just using some names for arguments sake – they decide that there is no way that they can absorb the extra costs of compliance other than increasing their fares. This will affect you and I and someone else as consumer. The consumers may or may not be affected depending on the type of shipping company.” (T2, para 66). The expert claims that all goods transported by freight, “ferries or bulk”, on the North and Baltic Seas, “you know, fruit, vegetables, agricultural products”, would be affected and would experience increases in final consumer price (T2, para 70). E12 argues that an increase in consumer prices is a prerequisite for environmental laws to develop their protective effect: “If you have a level playing field then the industry is forced in the end to pass those costs on to the end customers, how it is also supposed to be for good economic reasons. You need to see the costs in order to know which effects you are causing. And that’s only working if the industry is passing it on to the costumers and for that they need a level playing field.” (T12, para 39). E9 supports this argument stating: “The end consumer must be aware of the fact that that simply costs more money. That is the same like... here... fair trade coffee or something. That also costs more than normal coffee.” (T9, para 179). Environmental laws are also developed with the idea in mind that costs will be passed on along the supply chain: “The theory, well if you read a European impact assessment, you will generally find the assumption that marginal costs are passed on to the customer...” (T12, para 126), an expert explains. Expert perceptions that compliance costs might not be felt by the end consumer and might thus not serve to influence consumer choice should worry legislators, as this would mean that externalities might not be fully internalised, and legislation might not prove to be an effective incentive in nudging people towards economically efficient consumption behaviour.

5.3 Effectiveness of incentives

5.3.1 Introduction

Expert perceptions on the effect of environmental incentives have been discussed in length above. An important contribution of the present work is that it also studies the perceived effectiveness of incentives, often not considered in prior economic studies. An issue influencing the effectiveness of environmental incentives is the effect of **noncompliance** on costs. This issue has been raised and discussed by several experts at the interview stage. One expert states: “...the very concern that responsible ship operators have, because being compliant with the requirements means very high additional operating costs, costs of fuel, costs in equipment... ...so they are thinking that, okay, you know, if we do that, obviously, it puts a huge strain on our business and we have to do it, but isn’t it unfair that there will be some out there that will never get caught?” (T2, para 38). The expert hints that taking the risk of noncompliance might lead to significantly lower operational costs and a stronger competitive position. Another issue interviewees have raised has recently received academic attention, namely that operational cost increases depend on the **routes** the ships are taking: “Depending on how many ECAs and how long the journey is – it depends on that if we are talking about I’ll say 50 dollars or 200 dollars.”

(T7, para 114, see also T4, para 93 on the crucial influence of sailing routes for operational costs). The effectiveness of legislation may suffer where shipping companies are rerouting ships to circumvent areas with stricter regulations. For similar reasons than rerouting ships, companies will adapt **shipping speed** to influence fuel costs. “Evidently in the face of the crisis situation one sees how shipping companies have almost entirely I would say introduced slow steaming in order to save fuel, as that forms the biggest share of the costs and thus also the biggest share of opportunities to save money in any way during daily operations.” (T6, para 18). Although this is perhaps an effect not considered in regulatory impact assessments by the legislator, it does not limit the effectiveness of environmental legislation, but rather serves to limit emissions of CO₂ in addition to SO₂, increasing the positive environmental effects of SECAs.

5.3.2 Expert perceptions on compliance with MEL

5.3.2.1 *Estimated levels of compliance*

A substantial number of codes was recorded on compliance, meaning that experts were particularly interested in sharing their perceptions in this issue. They discussed the level of compliance, arguing that noncompliance did occur, and widely commented on determinants of compliance. The results are presented here, starting with estimated compliance levels. With respect to the **overall level of compliance** with environmental laws interviewees deem that it is “very high” (T11, para 242). Ten out of twelve experts make a statement to that purpose. One expert details that: “...environmental laws and regulations here in Germany [...] are complied with by 90-95%” (T1, para 98). Interviewees illustrate that compliance with the laws is imperative for shipping companies. It happens out of “pure self-interest” (T 11, 198), E11 illustrates. An expert with a classification society considers: “‘I will comply’ is not really a strategy, it is the licence to operate” (T2, para 31). Other interviewees narrate that one will jeopardise his credibility and risk losing cargo by losing the certification of big suppliers like car producers (T8, para 220). Furthermore, one might risk insurance cover by such behaviour (T6, para 167). Experts thus believe that the clear majority of market actors will be fully compliant with the laws.

However, regarding incidents of **lacking compliance** also ten out of twelve experts made explicit statements towards companies not following the laws. “...not everyone is complying” (T11, para 250), an expert says. “You never know what they do out at sea” (T9, para 35), another underlines. A third stresses: “I do not have a lot of faith in them, to be honest” (T3, para 74). There is thus certainly a number of companies in the market who decide against compliant behaviour. Be it for shortage of money, time, lack of commercial advantage or other reasons, there are shipping companies that will **willingly circumvent legislation**. “The thing is: The financial gains of not complying will be significant.” (T5, para 144), an interviewee reasons. “...the tendency to under-comply is immanent.” (T8, para 191), another expert adds. One expert describes noncompliant companies to operate under the logic: “...here I am, do try to stop me.” (T10, para 61). These “black sheep” (T4, para 125) that “operate on the cheap” (T10, para 97) will calculate with the unlikelihood of a detention of their vessels as described by a ship operator: “...I will assume that it will not be contained.” (T11, para 240). A hypothetical case is discussed by another operator: “I am so low that if they detain me it is their vessel. [...] What

will you do against that? Chain vessels up here, okay, and then you have the crap lying in front of your door.” (T10, para 97-99). Willing noncompliance occurs where financial gains are significant or where cheating is easy as fake documents may be acquired. Also, if port state control is unwilling to actually detain substandard vessels, the motivation for noncompliance increases. However, as one expert makes clear, though willing noncompliance does exist it has become the exception: “Well, things like cheating and doing things here and there does not exist, which certainly was the case with shipping in earlier times. That does almost not exist at all anymore.” (T9, para 53). Reasons for noncompliance will be discussed in Chapter 5.4.2.2 on determinants of compliance.

Behaviour might also go in the other direction, however. There are a number of market actors who **protect the environment more** than they are legally prescribed to. “There are companies who say: We want to stand out as a green sustainable company. That exists.” (T10, para 125), an expert describes. Another says: “A number of shipping companies try to establish a name with that.” (T1, para 100). With respect to the characteristics of over-compliant companies, interviewees stated that these are for example “cruise ship owners that are very much in the public eye” (T6, para 131), thus companies not involved in the trade of goods. There are also “big shipping companies [...] that are also the flag ships of the [...] industry” (T3, para 76) or that “want to be the industry leaders” (T2, para 29). One expert claims that over-compliance can only be found where a commercial benefit persists. He says over-compliant companies are at “the top-end of the market, they have a strategic plan and view and have found ways to gain commercial advantage if they are doing things beyond compliance.” (T2, para 31). From the expertise of industry insiders it seems like most shipowners and operators will simply do as the legislator says. They will comply with legislation fully to the best of their abilities. There are, however, a few substandard companies that will lack compliance for reasons discussed below. The existence of these has been confirmed by ten out of twelve experts. Furthermore, another small group will go beyond compliance. These will both have the financial means to do so and the hope to gain a commercial advantage from said behaviour.

5.3.2.2 *Determinants of compliance*

Building on the three categories influencing compliance developed from the literature, the theoretical framework presented below represents additional insights from industry experts. Determinants of compliance mentioned by experts were organised into the three main categories (1) individual motivations of key personnel involved in the operation of vessels, (2) organisational capacities, and (3) exterior determinants of (non)compliant ship operation. These categories and their underlying factors, as shown in Figure 5-8, will be defined and discussed in this section, supported by evidence from qualitative in-depth interviews.

Figure 5-8: Theoretical framework on determinants of compliance based on exploratory qualitative data

A motivator of compliant behaviour that became evident during expert interviews was that decision-makers **felt a need to contribute** to a cleaner environment. The acceptance of the necessity of environmental legislation is deemed the first step to compliant behaviour. During interviews, experts were questioned on whether they accepted the current legislative framework as representing a sensible set of laws or whether they deemed certain issues to be too much or too little regulated. As can be seen in Figure 5-9 only ten statements by five experts were coded indicating that environmental legislation for the shipping industry was set up in a sensible way. Some 14 codings support an over-regulation of the industry, while interviewees talked about certain issues being under-regulated on 33 occasions. These can be attributed to nine experts overall. By far the most codings went to the sub-category ‘adjustments necessary’ which meant that nine experts suggested improvements to the current laws in 51 overall codings. All codes were developed inductively from the data and represent expert sentiments.

Figure 5-9: Acceptance of environmental regulation by number of codings and number of experts

Five experts claimed that environmental issues were currently **well regulated**, indicating support for current laws. An interviewee stated: “The regulations that we have up here in the Northern European area they are already very good, and the controls are equivalent as well. Thus, I do not see much anymore that would have to be done in addition. [...] From the colouring of the hull over bunker up to waste disposal we have really covered pretty much everything in the meantime.” (T11, para 124-126). One refers to dumping of waste stating that “certainly the maximum is reached for the dumping of ship waste, because we have zero garbage over board. I am disposing of everything on land in a certified so-called reception facility. I mean, I would say, more than that is not possible.” (T9, para 51). E11 agrees on dumping of waste being well regulated and adds that oil-containing bilge water is no longer pumped out into the sea (T11, para 102), thus disposal of oily water is well regulated. Accepting environmental laws and believing that laws are well drafted might motivate decision-makers to act in accordance with them.

Companies might feel less induced to comply when their decision-makers feel **overburdened** by the current legal system, a perception voiced by five out of twelve experts. A short sea operator is among the ones feeling that certain environmental laws might reach too far. He specifically asks for exceptions on ballast water laws, because “it would be very much nonsensical to assume that after 50 years of ferry traffic between Germany and Sweden we had not long ago carried back and forth all little animals that maybe had not been living on the other side before” (T4, para 69; for a similar argument see T11, para 28). Another expert argues that ballast water treatment is in itself causing environmental pollution: “We have now had the first vessel delivered with a ballast water treatment facility that is now doing 5.500m³/h. For that you need 2.000 ampere continuous current. That has to come from somewhere. In addition to the by far larger ballast pumps of 375 kW. Those are powers – and that is environmental pollution.” (T10, para 73; for a similar argument see T9, para 51). One expert furthermore feels that stricter laws on sewage water treatment aboard are not in order, as “the sewage plants on land that now receive our waste water have [...] lower constraints than the new sewage water treatment systems that are supposed to be built on board ships. All in all a little absurd, but that is how the legislator wants it.” (T4, para 71). CO₂ regulation is another area where a shipowner feels there might be too many laws to suit the purpose: “...emission trading systems and other

mechanisms constituting huge administrative burdens to order to virtually achieve nothing at all. Or maybe only very little.” (T4, para 74). A feeling by decision-makers that current regulation exceeds a sensible level might induce conscious noncompliance.

The opposite might be the case where experts feel that the laws are still falling short of their aim. Nine out of twelve experts make statements towards the purpose that environmental issues are of yet **under-regulated**. Unsurprisingly, around 61% of these statements stem from the three experts working for national and European legislators as well as for a prominent environmental organisation. “I think that the state of the sea is regrettable, is not improving and we are facing a really big challenge.” (T12, para 67), one says. Another stresses: “...those are notorious polluters [“Dreckschleudern ohne Ende”] that are travelling the seas. We really are still 30 years behind with these things. [...] sulphur oxides, nitrogen oxides, particles, that is soot emissions, CO₂.” (T8, para 71). The expert adds: “We have not wasted any thoughts so far on the increases in noise level of these seas [“Verlärmung der Meere”].” (T8, para 73). Rather energetically the third expert claims: It “is also a task of politics certainly to make sure that jobs are maintained, that is very important, but I cannot only do that all the time by favouring allies and friends, that are verifiably becoming richer and richer, while other people may just suffer from the consequences of these politics.” (T3, para 142). Room for improvement is also seen by shipping companies themselves, however. One expert complains that the armed forces are not subject to environmental legislation: “The grey ones. The army. They are caring crap about all that. (Laughing)” (T10, para 121). Also, traffic on the open seas is not regulated and controlled enough in the view of one interviewee: “...if you look at it internationally I would claim that something needs to be done with all issues, because on the open seas you are still allowed to do all sorts of things. There you are allowed to wash your cargo holds, there you are allowed to throw waste overboard and EVERYTHING. Something would need to be done there urgently...” (T11, para 104). Another expert allows that the operations of the shipping industry have improved while the state of the oceans has not: “...you have to differentiate between the environmental goals related to the state of the environment and the environmental motivated goals related to the performance of a sector and of course there has also been progress in shipping in that sense. [...] So there are movements to improve shipping environmentally and that is why I believe that you are able to find positive examples if you are searching for them...” (T12, para 69).

The fourth and most prominent sub-category that emerged during interviews was that **adjustments to environmental legislation were necessary**, describing essential changes in legislation from the perspective of interviewees. Similar to feeling overburdened by the laws, feeling the laws to be poorly drafted might induce noncompliance. “Well, then you have got thousands of manuals on the ship’s bridge. That is a nightmare. That is why we are preferably looking towards an IMO regulation of any kind that will then be globally applicable to everyone.” (T6, para 20), one expert complains and demands fewer national and regional endeavours. This view is supported by another interviewee stating that: “...local or regional legislation is eventually nonsense, because in the worst case it really only leads to displacement, that is some traffic is driven out... gone... [...] We would like to see international legislation and ONLY international legislation.” (T4, para 110). A third adds: “The problem is: There is not really any international law. The IMO makes suggestions which, however, have to be

implemented in EU as well as national law afterwards. That means in the end of the day you have to see what comes out of it for each single harbour.” (T11, para 82). In addition, another argues that decision-making processes of legislators take far too long (T3, para 57). Another area of concern is legal uncertainty: “...certain areas or nations do not want the washing water that is now coming out at the end to be introduced into their waters. That means that there may possibly be a prohibition coming up. My open loop scrubber obviously is not of any help to me then.” (T7, para 147), one expert voices his concerns. “We have a new MARPOL V. It has not yet been implemented in the whole world, but is already totally enforced, that means a huge problem for bulk shipping. Washing water disposal through the hatches is partly not allowed any more. But there are also no exception rules, thus twilight zone. [...] We inform our flag state that we have a problem with the twilight zone and ask him to show us a solution and because he is also not able to do that he will at a certain point say: I will take note of that. And we will then pump it out someplace with the knowledge of the state, because he is also not able to do anything. IMO cannot do anything. No one can do anything, but the law exists.” (T10, para 61-63), another reports. Missing port reception facilities also seem to pose a problem in the area of waste: “We can than fill out such a paper that there are no facilities here or no uptake of garbage. But that is a toothless tiger. We have that paper aboard and what now?” (T10, para 217). A further issue of uncertainty is whether Russia treats the Baltic Sea as a SECA or not: “As far as I know they have never ratified these laws. That means that the EU has declared the Baltic Sea to be a SECA area, however, Russia has said: That is of no interest to me.” (T11, para 92). Uncertainty also existed at the time of the interviews with regard to the introduction of the global sulphur caps in 2020 or 2025: “And if you are a global operator today and you do not know whether there will be a global limit of 0.5 percent in 2020 or just a European limit – it is very difficult to take such a decision, such a significant financial decision, if you do not know in which environment you will be operating. And that is one of the reasons a lot of people are WAITING, in my mind.” (T5, para 180). Although this uncertainty has been resolved in the meantime, uncertainty about the coming-into-force of environmental legislation applies to other types of legislation as well. Some experts also voiced concerns about whether certain environmental laws actually serve the environment. One expert narrates: “...what some states ask is a disinfection of the [sewage] water before pumping it out. That, however, is equivalent to a total chlorination without control. That is questionable for the environment, because I am pouring chlorine into the environment. I do not know whether that is beneficial.” (T10, para 105). “As you know, the SECA area ends in Plymouth which means the English Channel is included. If you are now, however, on the other side of Great Britain, Irish Sea, there it does not apply. The wind comes from the West all the time. That means that stuff comes over here anyways. The Mediterranean is also not included. That does not really make total sense to me. If such regulations are coming they should apply worldwide and not only in some small areas.” (T11, para 102), another argues. One expert complains that environmental legislation for shipping does not follow a comprehensive plan: “...we are now talking about each vessel getting a treatment facility [for ballast water]. That is an absolutely immense waste of energy [“Energieverschwendung hoch drei”]. That means we will have a larger carbon footprint for the same amount of transport services performed. That means one is only looking at the one issue and is forgetting the adjacent issue. One is not doing a comprehensive survey of the system shipping. That does not exist.” (T10, para 71). Nine experts argue that environmental laws

should be improved. A lack of full acceptance of the current legal framework might bring about a more relaxed stance on full compliance with the laws.

Regarding the acceptance of regulation by the industry it can be said that only a small number of experts see environmental issues well regulated. While particularly legislators themselves and environmental organisations see much room for stricter regulation, especially regarding noise and air pollution, other experts question the poor state of environmental protection when it comes to international waters as well as vessels pertaining to national defence. Some experts mention dumping of waste, oily water and hull coatings as well-regulated areas. Ship operators in particular feel that certain areas of environmental legislation are over-regulated, however. They refer to ballast water treatment deeming it nonsensical and damaging for the environment due to energy uptake. Also, administrative burdens are questioned. A large number of experts see room for improvement with the current laws. A strongly voiced demand for international instead of national legislation as well as a call for long-term legal certainty occupies the industry. Also, the environmental impact of certain environmental laws is put into question.

When determining behaviour, the **motivations of subjects** are often of importance. Shipping companies are more likely to comply with legislation if they deeply feel that they need to contribute more to environmental protection than if they feel that they are already a very clean industry and are simply being harassed by further legislation. The most prominent statements of all interviewees towards the one or the other perspective were collected in Table 5-3. While one stakeholder had extreme views on the shipping industry calling it “the dirtiest method of transportation of all times” (T8, para 63), most other interviewees, both from within and from outside the industry hold more moderate views. They largely agree that shipping needs to contribute to environmental protection and the fight against climate change with eleven out of twelve experts supporting this position. Experts whose interests lie with the shipping industry (E1, E4, E6, E7, E9, E10 and E11), however, also stress that the industry is “already doing a lot” (T7, para 98) and that the “shipping industry is one of the most environmentally friendly methods of transport that exist” (T1, para 46). Statements like “There is no better alternative than shipping.” (T9, para 181) might suggest that some within the industry are proud of their achievements and have little intrinsic motivation to change their behaviour towards a more environmentally friendly conduct. While most shipowners and operators agree that the industry “needs to become cleaner” (T6, para 236) they emphasise that it is “the WAY to there” (T4, para 59) that concerns them. “One has to make sure first of all to keep the international trade running.” (T6, para 21), an expert from a shipping association argues.

Shipowners/operators			
		Have to contribute	Already clean industry
E 4	Small short sea operator	But needless to say we actually don't want any emission or rather as few emissions as possible, it is just the WAY to there that is questionable. (T4, para 59)	...the motor of the world economy that is not given any attention at all by the general public. [...] ...the vessels are simply transporting the goods very efficiently around the globe with comparatively small impacts on the environment and in general. (T4, para 179)

E 5	Large short sea operator	...personally I see PMs as a true area where you have to increase the efforts. PMs are really what is causing a lot of the bad air that we have around in Europe at the moment. And there is really nothing regulating that today. So I think that should come. (T5, para 107)	/
E 6	Shipping association	The shipping industry needs to become cleaner, new fuels and so forth and so on. (T6, para 236)	But I think that one has to make sure first of all to keep the international trade running. (T6, para 21)
E 7	Large container carrier	In principle it is a good thing to change to another fuel and to do environmental protection. We have in principle no problem, if these external costs are being internalised, as one likes to say. (T7, para 145)	We are already doing a lot. (T7, para 98)
E 10	Large bulk carrier	/	The legislator prescribes a minimum amount that needs to be fulfilled and shipping itself is in many areas much further... (T10, para 121)
E 11	Small container carrier	...in the past ships have dumped the waste that they had aboard over board. Today that does not happen anymore. Also, oil-containing bilge water was pumped out. Today that also does not happen anymore. A lot, a lot has happened and I am of the opinion that it was right that one has done that. (T11, para 102)	That 99.9% of sea traffic is conducted without a problem is not noticed by anyone. (T11, para 106)
Stakeholders			
E 1	Trade association	Nonetheless the shipping industry has to make its contribution to the global climate protection and environmental protection aims. (T1, para 46)	Roughly put, let's say in principle the shipping industry is one of the most environmentally friendly methods of transport that exist, compared to everything else. Therefore the shipping industry is first of all rather something "good" - in quotation marks. (T1, para 46)
E 2	Classification society	And if you look at what is happening in the world, there is a growing awareness of climate change outside shipping. Shipping is in a way under the radar in all that. (T2, para 126)	/
E 3	Environmental organisation	But if we take the IMO as a yardstick I would say that it is naturally not enough, what is happening at the IMO. Neither, so-to-speak, regarding the width of the decisions nor the speed of implementation, the time horizons. They are much too long considering the effects. (T3, para 42)	/
E 8	National legislation	...we finally put down our cards to see whether we want to go on with this most dirty method of transportation of all times or not. Well, that we then also bring the ecological standards to the level that we	Well, they complain a lot like any industry sector, but all in all we have... we need the shipping industry, we cannot do without them. (T8, para 327)

		have had for a long time on the land. (T8, para 63)	
E 9	Captain	...the airplane is more or less still powered by kerosene-eating turbines and that is the same as in shipping as well. Everything has become more efficient, but the underlying problem maybe,[...] that one has the old propulsion systems that burn dirty fuel. Resources are, I think, the main problem of the shipping industry and something has to change there. (T9, para 207)	A diesel motor with a vapour system with the whole shebang has an efficiency factor of fifty per cent. That is already incredible, if one compares that to a car or something, in which one guy is sitting. Well, basically sea transport is a fine thing. One hears that time and again. That is no environmental rascality in that sense. (T9, para 91) There is no better alternative than shipping. One simply has to say that. It is super economical. It is just a very fine thing. You can transport everything. Secure. (T9, para 181)
E 12	European legislation	In the end we will only be able to get a grip on climate change if all sectors are participating, of course that also includes the shipping industry. (T12, para 79)	/

Table 5-3: Felt need to comply with environmental legislation

To conclude, individual motivations of decision-makers may play a role in legal compliance, starting with individual morality and ethics. “I am actually INTERESTED that I do not pollute my oceans” (T9, para 87), an expert argues. “Nobody wants to be a bad person.” (T12, para 124), another narrates. A large share of the experts interviewed voiced a felt need to comply with environmental legislation, while some believed the shipping industry to be clean enough already. Acceptance of the current framework of laws was varied, with some experts feeling environmental laws to be well drafted, others feeling overburdened, and still others advocating stricter laws. The majority of experts in the sample argued that there was room for improvement of environmental laws, indicating that full acceptance is often lacking. The individual stance of decision-makers towards environmental laws may influence compliance.

The variable “criminogenic culture” discussed in the literature was reflected to some extent in expert statements in that ten out of twelve support the view that **company culture** influences compliance. According to an expert, company policy plays a significant role when abiding by the laws (T12, para 106; compare also T7, para 18). Companies “maybe have some moral grounds on which they base their actions” (T3, para 129), an expert argues. “I think due to a different mentality there are certainly also differences regarding environmental protection in

general I would say. And some shipping companies certainly have... take things a little easier and some don't." (T9, para 123), an expert describes differences in culture. "Yes, I think compliance is not only a question of whether you can do this, but also if you want to. There the group policy or company policy comes into play... [...] And as a consequence you will find a company policy that for example might also change with a change at the top." (T12, para 106, 124), another adds. It becomes apparent from this last statement that the moral stance of decision-makers and company culture are intertwined. Decision-makers will serve as a role model for their subordinates and will explicitly and implicitly influence both official company policy and effective actions by employees with respect to legal compliance.

Prior studies describe **perceived benefits** as a determinant of compliance. According to experts, these seem to be of foremost importance to the shipping industry. Ten out of twelve experts felt commercial gains from abiding by the laws to be an important decision parameter, arguing that environmental performance could be of interest to customers, investors and current and future employees. In addition, efficiency gains could decrease operational costs and make the vessel more attractive on the charter market. Experts agreed, however, that customers were unlikely to pay higher freight rates for more environmentally friendly vessels. A further commercial gain might be expected by the motivation to raise the company's reputation. Companies may be induced to comply with their public image in mind, as debated by eleven out of twelve experts.

A motivation that would positively influence compliance levels is thus an expected **commercial advantage** from compliance. "The business man finds it interesting if it yields something, for example he likes fuel consumption, and only with this argument something can be achieved in merchant shipping" (T9, para 139), one expert debates. One way is by efficiency increases: "CO₂ has an effect on your cost as well: If you reduce the fuel you reduce your costs." (T5, para 71). Slow steaming is another case in point: "...maybe efficiency and environmental protection are working hand in hand there, because one says: Well, a slower vessel is first of all also much less fuel and thus also more environmentally friendly." (T9, para 103). One shipowner argues that shipping companies have always made sure that no substances would get into the water, because it was in their own commercial interest: "...fuel is much too expensive to waste. [...] Green shipping or something is just creating paper in order to show what we have daily done before already." (T10, para 69).

A commercial advantage may also be gained if environmental performance is of interest to relevant stakeholders. One expert stresses that banks will be more likely to provide financing for environmentally friendly vessels: "I have been at various events where they said that the environmental, the environmental performance of a vessel is included in the investment appraisal, well the credit finance calculation." (T6, para 169). Also, environmental friendliness may be an argument of interest for current and future employees, "the one more, the one less" (T7, para 18), one expert reports. Customers are a third group that might be interested in

environmental performance: "...green shipping is a market segment, where everyone positions himself a little at the moment" (T10, para 171). Some customers will only allow environmentally friendly shipping companies to supply them, as one expert describes: "...many shipping companies need to be certified today, because these large companies like the car producers or the chemical industry have certification systems and the logistic chain is included in them as well..." (T8, para 220). Experts generally do not expect higher freight rates due to environmental performance, but simply hope that the vessel is more likely to attract cargo: "...if I do green shipping it can make the difference that I do win the tender, but not necessary that I get a premium because of that." (T10, para 123; see also T6, para 161; T7, para 79), one expert explains. Another narrates the case of Scandinavian paper producers: "Scandinavians are environmentally conscious. That means that the paper producer will tell the shipping company: Watch out! You have to fulfil these and those criteria in order to win my charge at all. And if the shipowner is able to say: Look here, I have an especially environmentally friendly ship, that consumes less, has a scrubber installed, I can offer you that. Then the chance is bigger that the paper producer says: Watch here, we will do that, because he can then say on his web page: See that is what I have all done." (T11, para 188, compare also T9, para 175 for similar arguments). Lastly, the general public is interested in environmental performance: "...that is also why the eye of politicians is VERY much focused on us - The social perception of the shipping industry in general has become greater, clearer and stricter and large loaders that are very much under pressure anyway, they now naturally take a look at how that influences their image if they transport their cargo from A to B." (T6, para 165). A shipowner claims that companies are unlikely to spend much money to impress their customers with environmental friendliness, however: "Yes, there has been a tendency in the last years to paint oneself greener. The problem is just that in the moment where that costs any money most are not willing anymore to go through with it full consequence. Well, many have written green on their flags, but it may not cost any money." (T11, para 186). Motivations to comply can be found in commercial advantages from compliance, an intrinsically developed want to comply or the feeling that there is no other option and one has to comply.

Just as significant as perceived benefits, **perceived costs** of compliance were discussed at length by experts. Ten out of twelve experts have made statements in this respect. A motivation for noncompliance may thus stem from seeing no commercial advantage in complying. Ten out of twelve experts mention this motivation. Just as some companies try to make a profit out of environmental performance, others will see no benefits for their company and will be induced not to comply. While efficiency increases may be worthwhile, especially ballast water and sulphur regulations are deemed to hold no economic benefit for ship operators (compare T5, para 71). Experts agree that generally customers will not pay higher fees if the transport service is conducted in a cleaner way: "We could not say, well, we are doing this or that environmental initiative, dear customer that will cost an additional 100 dollars per container. The market is far

too competitive for that.” (T7, para 20), a shipowner argues. “Maybe they are paying a bit more because a certain company works more reliable or has a better pre-carriage and post-carriage concept per container. But first of all for a final consumer it is interesting to bring his container from A to B as fast as possible and as cheap as possible.” (T9, para 141; see also T11, para 194), another expert adds. “We can do that, we can build an environmentally friendly vessel, but from the one that will charter the vessel we will only receive the standard market charter, not one cent more. Full stop. That is what we hear from everyone in unison. It is nice, but naturally they will not pay more. That’s it.” (T6, para 133), a third expert summarises how little the market appreciates cleaner vessels. That holds true for B2B as well as for final customers, as a short sea operator, who has been using superior fuels for some years, describes: “In all this time we have not been able to detect that we have had any economic advantage somehow from all that, apart from friendly pats on the back and friendly nods from politics and all sides. Well now, that the customer would have said maybe: No, I would rather like to go with [company 4], because they are so CLEAN. Nada.” (T4, para 133).

In container shipping this problem is further aggravated by another characteristic of the industry. With **container sharing agreements** the customer does often not know and has no way to choose which shipping company will eventually transport his containers. He thus would not have the option to choose the most environmentally friendly vessel, if he were to deem this issue important. “Theoretically you could certainly influence that if you knew that the vessels of [organisation 7] are positively better than those of the competitors and you knew that the vessels of [organisation 7] are leaving the harbour in certain weeks... Well, you would have to see, okay, I have to leave my container... but then... well and then... well, that is certainly an illusion. That is not possible.” (T7, para 24), a shipowner ponders the limited possibility of choosing an environmentally superior company. Shipping companies will not invest in environmental performance if that would put them at a competitive disadvantage: “...if you invested for any reason to make your ships cleaner, then you do not want your competition to have a cost advantage by still driving around dirty...” (T12, para 144; see also T3, para 76), an expert argues. Another one describes why shipping companies will generally not receive a commercial advantage from over-compliance: “...a large shipping company might now operate on gas oil even if heavy fuel oil is still allowed until the end of the year in order to achieve some kind of image benefit. If a shipping company decides to do that and they are able to finance that, they will do that. But currently the market conditions do not allow for that. That means they would just loose, they would just burn money and they would then be off the market and that really is not very sustainable.” (T6, para 131).

Individual decision-makers within shipping companies will influence compliance in various ways, depending on their ethical stance, the company culture they form, and how they perceive costs and benefits for the company to arise from legal compliance. It is important to note that the behaviour of a shipping company will not depend on the actual costs and benefits of compliance, but rather on perceived costs and benefits. Decision-makers will determine company behaviour based on the limited amounts of information they have available, their personal experiences, and their personal expectations for the future. These individual motivations will be balanced with organisational capacities and exterior determinants such as effective enforcement, as discussed below.

Compliance is not only a function of motivations, describing the wish to comply, but also organisational capacities influencing company-specific possibilities to comply. **Resource constraints** may significantly influence compliance options. This factor received only limited attention in previous studies. It is thoroughly discussed by all twelve experts in the present study, however. According to experts, constraints can stem from a lack of financial resources, personnel resources and, surprisingly, a lack of industry association membership.

A lack of financial resources as a determinant of legal compliance seems to be of particular importance to the shipping industry with cost pressure mentioned by all twelve experts. "...we are in the sixth year of the shipping crisis, meaning that bank financing is difficult..." (T6, para 226), E6 states. "...the financial resources are not necessarily there" (T1, para 50; also supported by T8, para 256), another expert adds. "Well, I think that for cost reasons each shipping company that is not one of the big shipping companies will try to circumvent that [environmental laws] wherever possible" (T3, para 74), an interviewee asserts. Shipping companies might not focus so much on compliance, but rather on survival as a key motivation: The "...extremely difficult income situation today you have to see as a shipping company, whether large or small – well, with the big ones it is always a little different – but with the small ones you have to see that you first of all survive." (T6, para 232), remarks an expert. He argues that shipping companies will operate under the motto: "Well, I will have to talk to my bank first to see if I may get a loan [to comply with sulphur legislation] and otherwise I cannot be bothered by anything like that." (T6, para 117). And, as another expert points out, they might as often as not find it difficult to receive more funds: "...smaller shipowners or rather shipowners that have their vessels financed close to a hundred per cent get into trouble, simply because they do not receive further credit lines for the additional costs." (T7, para 161). Even if shipowners can increase freight rates to cover their increased fuel costs, a cash flow problem might still pose a strong motivation not to comply: "...you will still have a cash flow issue that you will need to look at. How much credit are you getting with your fuel supplier? How much credit are you giving your customers? Normally there is a gap there." (T5, para 268). E5 argues that a danger of bankruptcy due to increased costs and few options of additional credit lines persist. There is "not a lot of money in the war chests." (T5, para 242), he says. T7 adds: "I mean, there are so many limited partnerships [German: Kommanditgesellschaft] that went bankrupt. There is no money [available]. Well, I believe it is very much a financial problem, especially for the smaller shipping companies." (T7, para 81). "That is a question of how long your bank has patience, because the financing of these ships is done by the bank and these banks have not received any money any more for roundabout seven years. Nothing. When is their patience ending?" (T11, para 352), an expert asks. He paints a picture of how money shortage will increase the

motivation for noncompliance: “And if you are short of money in the shipping company... Then one is saving – everywhere possible.” (T11, para 240).

Nearly 60% of all codings on motivations were coded on motivations for noncompliance (rather than reasons to follow the laws). Working under **time pressure** might be a reason for noncompliance as mentioned by five out of twelve experts. One expert describes: “It is easy when I have the TIME to deal with that. If I do not have the time, it is not easy...” (T7, para 71). Another states: “...the pressure and the resource constraint most organisations or shipping companies, ship operators are faced with. They just don’t have the time to assimilate this information. And let alone translate it into actions within their company.” (T2, para 42). One expert holds that time constraints are more an issue of smaller companies: “The time needed to analyse a law is a certain factor and the shipping company with more vessels may certainly break down the investment costs on more vessels.” (T7, para 142; for a similar argument see T6, para 48). A captain depicts how time pressure aboard might lead to noncompliance: “...we are already rather short of people aboard I would say. Well, we already really have a lot to do and a lot of... the area of responsibility is incredibly wide. [...] ...the more lying on your shoulders the more... the more prone you are to make mistakes. One should not forget that. [...] Well, due to fatigue or something. [...] ...I normally always work at least thirteen, fourteen hours a day.” (T9, para 131). A lack of time is linked to a lack of qualified personnel resources. This resource constraint is difficult to separate from a lack of financial resources, as ultimately more money might buy more personnel.

Both limited time and limited training might lead to a lack in **awareness and apprehension of legal information**. Theory tells us that subjects unaware of the laws they are supposed to follow will generally not follow said laws. The author thus wanted to control for behavioural effects due to unawareness. Interviewees were posed several questions related to the level of knowledge within the shipping industry, the sources of information, the amount of effort it took to receive sufficient information and the ability to translate the information received into action. The answers were grouped into four sub-categories, namely ‘high awareness’, ‘lacking awareness’, ‘easy apprehension’ and ‘difficult apprehension’. The value of making a difference between awareness and apprehension emerged during coding. ‘High awareness’ would mean that subjects would know very well about the existence of legal rules while they could have trouble understanding what was demanded of them specifically. A statement underlining such a case would fall into the category of ‘difficult apprehension’.

With respect to **awareness of environmental legislation**, in general interviewees agree that they are “well informed” (T7, para 67) and that it is “relatively easy to acquire information”

(T5, para 118). However, they also state that other market participants may be less well informed: "...I wouldn't be surprised that there wouldn't be shipowners, operators out there in the world that are less informed than we are." (T5, para 123). According to participants the high level of information is partly due to the fact that international political processes usually go on for a number of years before legislation is passed. One participant describes this as follows: "...the IMO is a huge organisation. Before one is really coming to terms there years go by. And thus, yes, we have very early information." (T11, para 113). What 'very early' may mean is explained by another expert: "They have been informed about the SECA regulation for seven, eight years, that it is about to come." (T12, para 96). A shipowner confirms this notion stating that they "have seen the problem coming and have been occupied with that for years." (T3, para 144). One issue that seems to be of great importance for the level of information is the **network** of decision-makers. "If you are on the inside for a bit longer you evidently have your portfolio of sources at a certain point and it is maybe easier for you" (T7, para 71), an interviewee describes. This position is also held by another expert stating that "one is really always talking to the same people and as soon as new things pop up one is talking about that" (T11, para 161). The network within the industry is mentioned by another interviewee, who summarises its importance as follows: "You hear about new things." (T5, para 172). Lastly, companies seem to be aware of legislation depending on how vital they deem the **interest to be informed**. An interviewee argues that they are well informed because they are "forced to deal with that" (T9, para 107) and otherwise "will someday get into trouble" (T9, para 109).

It is one thing to know about legislation. It is another to **understand legislation**. The sub-code 'apprehension of information' was created to capture this difference. Five out of twelve interviewees made statements suggesting that understanding shipping laws was not a difficult task. E2 suggested: "...I think the challenge [...] is not about the interpretation or understanding – this is a resource issue that can be solved" (T2, para 44). He adds: "...when it comes to air pollution and exhaust emission the text is pretty simple: What you need to do is just make sure that you use the correct type of fuel. So, the understanding of what one is to do is very simple [...] I'm a ship operator [...], I don't need you Mr Regulator to tell me what to do. I know what I need to do." (T2, pp. 44). E7 collaborates: "Maximum sulphur content 0.1 per cent, okay, I do get that. In this area the sulphur content of fuel may not be higher. I do get that." (T7, p. 71). Statements that the apprehension of information might pose problems at times were found in nine out of twelve interviews. One expert narrates that environmental legislation is "...highly complex and does not form part of the business of shipping companies. [...] ...when you send them the documents, they can hardly make any sense of them." (T6, para 55). "It is incredibly time-consuming, and it is incredibly hard to understand" (T10, para 43), another industry expert argues, "...if the legislator is not able to pass a clear law that very obviously keeps the shipowner from following it." (T10, para 127). An expert working for EU institutions explains: "You should make the legislation clearer and I am sure that we can reach improvements in many respects. And that is because all these laws have grown separately from each other. Each has a good reason for its existence and it is often crunching if they are being applied at the same time, no question." (T12, para 92). No clear picture emerges from expert statements regarding the apprehension of legal information, save that some companies feel they have adequate resources to understand what is expected of them, while others find it hard to deal with complex laws.

One problem mentioned by experts is the **implementation of international laws into national laws**. E11 deliberates: "...the local, the national implementation is always different." (T11, para 28). That even seems to hold true for EU legislation, as another expert explains: "So the sulphur directive for instance is 28 national legislations in the EU countries. They would all be slightly different" (T5, para 93). What will further complicate things is, as one expert describes, is that "...also each harbour authority has its own ideas what needs to be done." (T11, para 84). Problems arise when nation states bordering the same waters apply legal rules differently: "...our friends from Russia [...] have very different ideas on what should be done and what should not. That is difficult. [...] It starts with seeing reason whether they are accepting this as a SECA area or not" (T11, para 87-89). E6 reasons that regional differences in legislation put a significant strain on shipping companies: "...whenever you have something like that it is an extreme burden for the crew on board and also for the shipping company on land, because they have to check time and again: Where can we... where do we enter an area with different laws..." (T6, para 20).

A number of interviewees argued that it very much depended on the **specific law in question** whether it was easily comprehensible. "I think some of them are more difficult than others", one expert says, "[...] because the requirement may have a lot of different interpretations and a lot of different clauses, so one thing is about the text" (T2, para 44). While sulphur legislation seems to be quite straightforward experts complain about the "chaos" (T11, para 26) of ballast water legislation (Compare also T7, para 71; T10, para 127). One expert working for a classification society describes a recent case, where a customer wanted a short summary on ballast water requirements: "Can you just summarise everything that happens in one page? And I guess our answer was: Actually no, because it is so complex. That is the reason why we are having all these publications" (T2, para 42). Other complex legal issues mentioned by experts include the EEDI formula (T7, para 71), nitrogen oxide emission controls (T7, para 71), and particulate matter (T7, para 95). The demands of the industry towards legislation are put in clear words by an interviewee: "... it somehow has to be a system that is simple, that is comprehensible, that is targeted, but that is as simple and practical as possible, because that first of all increases the implementation frequency, or let me say the implementation willingness and secondly also the political acceptance." (T6, para 21). In sum it seems to depend largely on the specific issue at hand whether legal rules are being well understood by the shipping industry. While the laws on sulphur caps are apparently quite straightforward the laws on ballast water management leave much room for interpretation and apprehension by the industry is at a lower level. Information is in parts seen as complex and the process of apprehension time-consuming. In addition, differing national implementation and different laws in different ports can make apprehension a challenge. Strained resources may discourage hiring and keeping on sufficiently trained personnel. A lack of skilled staff increases compliance uncertainty. Experts hint that inadequate resources are a challenge quite new to an industry bountifully supplied with means before 2008. Resource constraints may thus be a strong determinant of compliance.

Information flows usually seem to be channelled through **associations** as one expert points out: “Every industry has its association on a European level and one of the tasks of these associations is to establish an overview of the laws that you are actually subject to.” (T12, para 92). Another expert confirms: “You can always address the German Shipowners’ Association. [...] ...they care about such concerns.” (T11, para 166). Shipping associations as relevant sources of information are mentioned by ten out of twelve interviewees. National associations work together with their regional and international counterparts and will usually already be involved at early consultation stages. “They are all sitting at the table at the IMO negotiations. They are all sitting at the table. They know about that.” (T8, para 128), argues a fierce expert from the legislative sphere. A few experts mention other institutions which are providing the shipowners and operators with information, like classification societies (compare T6, para 56; T10, para 41), the flag state (compare T6, para 56) and sector-specific organisations like InterCargo (compare T10, para 41) and InterFerry (compare T5, para 116). Two experts narrate making use of news feeds and internet searches in addition (comp. T5, para 116; T7, para 69). Another says “...in the end we are evidently also being told by the authorities.” (T4, para 147). However, one expert clarified that it is “mostly the shipper’s associations that inform us early on about new legislation and legislative developments and also integrate us into the discussion processes.” (T4, para 147). Insufficient information may thus occur where shipping companies have **decided to leave the association**. One expert narrates that there are “shipping companies that left in order to save costs under the pressure of the market.” (T6, para 42). He details further that they “are losing a lot of information, also cross information and fast tracks and so on. Just, I think that everybody knows that, but sometimes the economic pressure leaves no other option.” (T6, para 60). Another expert describes this behaviour as a simple cost-benefit consideration: “The membership in the association is obviously a cost factor, but the withdrawal from the association is a risk factor. For example you will have less knowledge about legislation on different levels than before [...] or you will risk falling in the legislative trap and then paying fines or otherwise.” (T12, para 102). Associations are found to be helpful in apprehending information as well: “They are translating that into Shipping English and they say this and that is of relevance and the rest is a covering law and not relevant for the law.” (T10, p. 45). Another expert claims that even if shipping companies are members to an association, they will receive insufficient information. She argues that “it is all getting there very late” (T8, para 373) and that the association is not fulfilling its task of informing small businesses properly, because “it only ever looks at the big ones” (T8, para 370). Association membership is by choice and costs a yearly membership fee. Industry associations play a vital role in being the main conveyors of legal information for shipping companies. Decreasing membership decreases legal awareness.

As shipping companies leave the association the overall level of information within the industry decreases. This trend might have an influence on overall legal compliance level.

Although awareness of legislation is generally high, especially smaller companies and territorial outsiders may struggle keeping up to date. This might be because the shipping associations seem to be crucial in providing information and the two mentioned groups are more likely not to be a member to an association than larger companies or companies active solely in the area in question. Companies make use of a number of sources to keep themselves informed, the associations and their own network of colleagues within the industry being the most important ones. Despite slow political processes, early warnings and supporting organisations, acquiring information can be time-consuming. Companies are thus more likely to keep themselves up to date if they feel it is a vital business interest to be well informed.

This chapter describes expert perceptions on how compliance may depend on operator characteristics, like company size or the area of operations. Differences among shipping companies as regards cost and freight rate effects of MEL are discussed further below in Chapter 5.3 ‘Differences among companies’. Prior studies mention operator characteristics like company size, vessel age, economic situation, and background of the CEO to have an influence on compliance. Shipping experts argue that the influence of company characteristics on compliance depends on the variable in question.

Company size is discussed by all twelve experts, with most experts agreeing that smaller shipping companies are more likely to circumvent legislation than big companies. “...they have a certain sense of responsibility as large shipping companies...” (T3, para 72), an expert argues, adding that “...with any small cheap-flag-state vessels [Billig-Staaten-Flaggen] I would always be rather sceptical and think that they will certainly try to circumvent the laws wherever possible.” (T3, para 76). This view is supported by another expert stating: “The small ones that are under a different cost pressure among other things... they will likely rather be tempted at times, that is quite possible.” (T6, para 157). The discrepancy seems to be linked to resource constraints: “And there exists a clear tendency for me that the big companies have an information advantage over the small companies due to the higher number of employees and actually also due to managers who have the time to go to such committees, that is what I think. Because it is very difficult to combine that, to stay up-to-date and to handle the daily work aboard, in part docking and repairs and at the same time to stay informed is very difficult, almost impossible.” (T10, para 59). From what experts are saying it seems that mostly smaller companies suffering from financial constraints will also take the step to leave shipping

associations (compare T8, para 306). This is likely influencing their awareness of legislation as “the added value of an association is naturally the bigger for the people the smaller their organisation is.” (T6, para 66). Experts claim that smaller companies “don’t have the personnel who could engage themselves with [environmental legislation]” (T1, para 108). They often do not have a legal department “like it is done in the huge groups” (T6, para 75). “He needs to do it himself, the owner” (T8, para 368), one expert describes. They “lack the expertise” (T8, para 306), but still “need to comply with [...] this whole stuff.”, E9 points out (T9, para 121). Interviewees widely agree that acquiring information can be time-consuming and that it is especially putting a strain on small businesses, also termed one-ship companies. Two interviewees explicitly state that for smaller companies to stay informed is “very difficult, almost impossible” (T10, para 59; T9, para 121). It can thus be assumed that smaller companies who have left the association may struggle to keep themselves informed about legislative developments. **Larger shipping companies** on the other hand seem to be “very well informed” (T3, para 76). One interviewee, a captain with a large shipping company describes: “...we evidently are also referred to the newest regulations by the company. [...] ...we are sometimes receiving new information daily. [...] ...we are really also through that always informed and are also dependent on that, because I do not have the time to deal with some new regulations all the time...” (T9, para 119).

Another distinct group that might struggle with compliance, according to experts, are **territorial outsiders**, vessels that visit the Baltic or North Sea area only on occasion. For them it seems somewhat more difficult to keep up with regulatory changes. “If you now have operators that operate their vessels worldwide it is a little bit more difficult to always keep a good overview. They are rather not so well informed.” claims an expert (T11, para 176; for the same argument see also T5, para 109). Territorial insiders on the other hand are much more likely to be well informed: “My experience is that operators that are only active within a small area are always well informed, solely based on self-interest.” (T11, para 176). Other characteristics mentioned by interviewees that could have a bearing on compliance are ownership structure, company culture, seat of operations, average age of vessels, type of customers, fleet composition, economic position or flag state. These factors to a large part find no mention in prior studies and should be studied in more detail. In summary, experts say that legal compliance may suffer where financial or personnel resources are strained, or where a company decided to leave the industry organisation. Certain groups like smaller companies or companies visiting the North and Baltic Seas irregularly might struggle more with legal compliance than others.

The third category of determinants of compliance are exterior factors. The first determinant ‘Sanctions and enforcement’ describes the existence of thorough and frequent controls effectively influencing behaviour. All twelve experts deliberate extensively on this factor

exhibiting varied opinions on the issue. They agree, however, that effective controls have a considerable influence on compliance. "...the economic influence of this [sulphur] law is so big that there is a certain incentive to circumvent that if it is not adequately controlled." (T7, para 188), one says. "And currently it is so that the fines [...] are so low that it pays rather to pay the fines instead of doing proper exhaust gas cleaning. That is going to be the problem, I fear." (T3, para 74), another adds. Perceptions were analysed on how effective experts felt enforcement currently was. Answers were inductively coded coming up with the three sub-codes "controls working", "controls lacking" and "unsure about effectiveness". Eleven out of twelve interviewees made statements towards a lack of enforcement. However, ten out of twelve experts very prominently argued cases where controls are working. Nine industry experts made statements to the purpose that they were unsure about the effectiveness of controls. In terms of the amount of text coded experts talked most extensively about controls working as can be seen in Figure 5-10.

Figure 5-10: Effectiveness of controls (in share of total interview text)

Some experts deem that **enforcement has significantly improved** in recent years. One expert narrates: "...due to the fact that they may always supervise, more and more people are becoming more careful and in earlier times, well, they deceived at each possibility. ["wurde an jeder Ecke beschissen"] Well, shipping has also been a little Mafia business in earlier times I would say, but meanwhile, no, I would not say that anymore..." (T9, para 83). "There are great efforts now, for example within the scope of the HELCOM Commission, to introduce an enforcement that is actually credible because the incentive to bypass it is of course big for individual operators. That's an exciting topic, now they are working with remote sensing there, with chemical sniffers, with planes..." (T12, para 39), E12 reviews the current state of enforcement. Three experts particularly emphasise that enforcement is working well in Germany or the Baltic Sea area. "It has improved, it has significantly improved, but basically it is only us there in the Federal Republic of Germany that do it relatively well." (T8, para 109), one remarks on the issue. "In the German area of responsibility, they are actually policing, there they also control by air... [...] ...it is being persecuted strictly..." (T8, para 107-109), an expert praises the effectiveness of controls in the area. "I have participated in such a harbour state control in the [city D] harbour once. That is quite a sincere business. ["Da geht es schon zur Sache"]" (T8, para 195), he adds. The third is of a similar opinion regarding the Baltic Sea area: "Up here you are reduced to complying, because here you will immediately be caught, at least for such big things like draining waste oil, cleaning tanks in the seas or something. You cannot do that on the Baltic Sea. That is simply too small here." (T11, para 252). However, E8 considers that

controls in other European waters may not be as effective: “No matter which direction you go to the West or the East it is getting worse.” (T8, para 109).

A few experts deem that there is a **lack of frequency** in controls: “...well, technically, the density of controls may likely not be very high, as there are also resources missing.” (T4, para 118; for a similar argument see T3, para 82), one says. Another one adds: “...there are practical difficulties in inspecting every single ship.” (T2, para 38). “If someone is standing behind me looking over my shoulder then I make sure that I comply with environmental legislation.” (T9, para 107), one expert explains. If, however, controls are not taking place frequently and thoroughly, market actors might start breaking the laws. “It is like a speed limit on a high way you know. If there is a speed limit and you advertise in the paper that there will not be any police then the chance that the speed limit will be ignored is bigger, right?” (T5, para 146), an expert says. One problem that experts see is that authorities are understaffed and underfinanced. “Ten per cent of the vessels are supposed to be controlled; that is what I recently read somewhere. Ten per cent. Thus 90 per cent are missing.” (T11, para 228). “They have also looked into that and then it was somehow only one in a thousand vessels that was controlled in any harbour. That is not very often.” (T7, para 184), an expert cites a study conducted by Maersk. “I would generally expect that controls are not sufficient, because public authorities are under cost pressure, especially at the moment in this current public atmosphere it is politically almost unenforceable to say, we will increase the staff in order to monitor the legislation.” (T12, para 114; see also T2, para 38). “Port state control is already in operation today and they check a lot of other things. They do not check a lot of fuel compliance. There is some worry within the industry that there won’t be a lot of policing going on from next year.” (T5, para 87), another expert voices his concerns. Where decision-makers doubt that controls will happen frequently, they might be induced to take their chances with legal compliance.

Other experts claim that **current enforcement largely proves effective**. A captain describes how thoroughly port state control is working: “Well, I would say things like the oil record book or something are actually being controlled often. Certificates are being controlled. Today one also has such emission certificates for example for the auxiliary engines and for the main engine and that is... they need to be up to date and that is being checked. That is often done. Well, I would say almost always. Certificates are the most important and all the logbooks, record books and so on. First of all, all this administration, this whole paper work, that is being inspected.” (T9, para 165). E11 argues that controls are effective not because of the level of fines, but because of the danger of future controls: “That is also not necessarily about the size of the punishment, but if you have attracted attention here somewhere then you will be endlessly controlled again and again and if an inspector WANTS to find something he will. For that a ship is simply too big.” (T11, para 196). The captain stresses that the system is also effective because the incentive for the personnel to comply is very high: “...so it is said in shipping as a general rule one is always sailing close to the wind [“mit einem Bein im Gefängnis stehen”], because one is jointly liable for everything. Everything that I write down somewhere with my signature – one has to sign everything with a signature – you have decided it that way, you have done it that way, you have documented it that way and you are liable. You are liable for everything.” (T9, para 151). From these statements it can be deduced that controls are increasingly working well to inhibit wrong-doing especially in the North and Baltic Sea areas.

This might not apply to other European waters. The majority of experts claim that controls in these areas are sufficiently frequent and thorough and that the danger of enhanced future controls or liability of the captain might be enough to keep the vessel from illegal pollution.

An inductively developed contribution to knowledge was developed by experts arguing that **authorities are deliberately steering clear of substandard vessels**: “One can also observe the port state [control]. They are going on the good vessels. On the ones where they know: I would have to chain them up here and that is a problem for the harbour there they are not seen.”, says E10 (T10, para 97). This argument is upheld by another expert: “...according to my experience the authorities responsible for controls rather inspect vessels that look good, where everything is in order, where they have nothing much to complain about, because then they don’t need to do much. If they are now entering an old Greek vessel that is 30 years old and where nothing is on the right, the correct place anymore and everything looks horribly, and everything is rusty and they are walking through the machinery and everything is oily and so on. What will they need to do then? Then they need to really become active. They really need to say: Here, take it you, you are first of all being chained up and you need to go into the shipyard and then a huge process needs to be set in motion [“...ein unheimliches Rad muss in Bewegung gesetzt werden.”]. [...] Well, they always rather like to enter the new vessels and also like to come to us, where they are saying: Here, come on, with you everything is in order anyway. Then we will have lunch and then they are happy.” (T9, para 133).

Experts express **uncertainty whether enforcement is always possible**. Some experts claim the system of pollution controls in ports rather than in the open seas leave many options for misconduct outside the harbour: “As soon as you are out of here you can theoretically do what you want.” (T11, para 252), one says. Others argue that port-based controls work absolutely fine. One interviewee explains how adherence to sulphur limits may be controlled: “...24 hours, you know the vessel size, motorization, that exhausts around 50 tons or 100 tons a day depending on the ship size and it should only have operated on low sulphur fuel. That means you can check, how was the tank... the bunker inventory in Rotterdam and how is it in Hamburg. There has to be a difference.” (T6, para 145). For sewage the system would be similar: “You would need to have so and so much sludge on board, show me the books, show me the stuff.” (T6, para 139). The same idea applies to discharges of waste, as described by E3: “Okay, they are 20 days at sea, 20 people on board and how much waste should be on board in principle so that I can say in the harbour afterwards, [...] 300 kilogram of waste accrued. That is fitting to what the crew consumes, that is so to speak considered realistic, we dispose of it here” (T3, para 59). By way of approximation and experience port state control is thus able to say if vessels have likely acted against environmental laws. The burden of proof lies with the shipping companies (compare T9, para 153). Uncertainty also related to the technical measures of enforcement: “I do not know, in how far one can measure somehow from an airplane, when flying over a vessel, if one can measure anything accurately enough so that you can also derive a watertight legal case [on sulphur levels] from that.” (T4, para 123), one interviewee considers. Another says: “Well, air pollution for example you cannot inspect in that sense. There exist no measuring modules for NO_x emissions or something like that.” (T9, para 167). A third expert recounts: “There is kind of two kinds of policing here. One is detecting if anybody is not compliant. The other thing is to have the details so you can prove it and issue a fine. These are

two different things. You can detect noncompliance for instance by having sniffers on the bridge or in a plane or drone or something like that. You can fly over the ship and say okay, this ship is not compliant. That is not valid evidence to issue a fine for.” (T5, para 88). According to the expert a fine may only be issued based on wrong entries in the oil record book or based on samples from relevant tanks. “How do you take a sample from a tank that was used two days ago?” (T5, para 91), he asks. Expert 11 maintains that in practice one would get through with willing noncompliance. (T11, para 246) If one has a number of bunker tanks in operation, an expert recounts, “one can certainly easily relocate [fuel from one to the other tank]” (T9, para 83) without port authorities being able to tell. Also, the mechanism to hold the captain liable for misconduct might not inhibit pollution under all circumstances: “If the vessel is caught with a forged oil record book then it is not the shipping company that is held liable, but the chief engineer. The fine for the chief engineer depends on his income. If he comes from the Philippines you can figure out yourself how high the penalty will be, because he has not been caught in the act, but rather it was proved afterwards that he has not done certain things like he should have done them. If the vessel is now caught on the spot as it is dragging along an oil trail that is again something different, but the real penalties, they are minimal.” (T11, para 248). The assumption that the level of penalties is not sufficient is also supported by another expert: “The fines are not yet very high.” (T8, para 217).

Frequent and thorough enforcement is important to inhibit misconduct, especially given the cost significance of certain types of legislation to the industry. Although controls seem to have improved in the course of the last decades, still their frequency leaves room for improvement. Limited budgets may be a reason for limited enforcement. Though enforcement proves largely effective, reasons for concern mentioned by experts are that proving misconduct by port state control might sometimes prove technically difficult, that fine levels may be too low to discourage noncompliance and that authorities might deliberately chose not to control substandard vessels. Again, as described above, noncompliance seems to be an option chosen by few shipping companies and linked to a lack of enforcement. However, experts claim that it is a minority who would do so: “...there is a certain fear that shipping companies are taking the risk saying: Yes, we are not being controlled that often and the cost savings are immense, we will try running on heavy fuel oil. But I can evidently say: Yes, those are the rotten apples.” (T7, para 176).

A second motivation can be found where decision-makers perceive a necessity to comply in order to operate. This same aspect has been studied by Akamangwa and has been termed here ‘Norms as an effective deterrent’. Eleven out of twelve experts have made statements to this purpose and have named the risk of losing certifications, insurance cover or bank financing as reasons for the absolute necessity of compliance. Demands from customers, banks, insurances

or other stakeholders will thus increase the likelihood of compliant behaviour. Eleven out of twelve experts made statements in support of shipping companies feeling they **had to comply** with the laws. An expert narrates: "...there were no alternatives to what we have done. That means the ships were simply switched fuel-wise from heavy fuel oil to gas oil and that was that." (T11, para 46). "If one wants to do business in Europe according to a certain standard as an economic firm [...] one needs to stick to the rules" (T10, para 97), E10 claims. Several interviewees relate that shipping companies would not act on their own but would solely change their behaviour if legislation told them to. One expert says: "That means as long as nothing is decided upon a shipping company will not move." (T9, para 143). He adds: "The regulations will be complied with that need to be complied with. Full stop. Nothing more will be done. No one will do excessively more than that." (T9, para 179). "They just wait it out until the last day when they have to implement changes." (T8, para 126), another narrates, while a third claims: "...they will not do anything voluntarily. I cannot imagine that." (T7, para 82). "Well, no company would by itself enforce any environmental protection measures or climate protection measures if it did not have to..." (T3, para 129), argues an employee of an environmental organisation. Still, experts widely agree that though companies are not motivated to do more than they have to they would still be motivated to do exactly what they should: "But, the majority of companies, I would say, in my experience, maybe 80-90% of companies that either own or operate ships, what they do is very much driven by what they have to do..." (T2, para 27), E2 describes. A typical stance of shipping companies is described by a shipowner: "It is in the DNA of most companies that we are doing business in an environment where there are certain laws and we might not like all the laws but you have to comply with the laws - that is what good companies do." (T5, para 150). Eleven out of twelve experts thus agree that shipping companies would in general feel effectively deterred from illegal pollution by environmental legislation. Especially the pressure from stakeholders supporting the effectiveness of legal incentives has not found mention in prior studies and is a knowledge gain inductively developed from qualitative data.

Thirdly, experts identified the **practical feasibility of noncompliance** as a determinant of compliance. The factor describes whether noncompliance may be achieved from a logistical point of view. Examples mentioned by experts are the ease of throwing waste over board, washing tanks at sea or switching to low-sulphur fuel later than legally demanded. There are a number of ways how legislation can be circumvented. The first one mentioned by interviewees being illegal waste disposal: "...some are maybe also not willing to simply spend money on some things. They say: Do I now need to order the ship disposal company if I can perfectly throw it over board here? [...] The ocean is big. A lot is fitting in there." (T9, para 129). Furthermore one can illegally discharge sewage water: "...let us say sewage water, grey water, black water, everything that comes from the shower more or less and excrement or something,

in the harbour they are running over the tank, well, they are not being disposed into the water here, but I think that that is not yet strict enough, well, it is nonetheless often done.” (T9, para 59). A third way mentioned by experts is switching fuel late or not at all: “And there certainly still exist shipping companies who do that or who say: No, we are not yet switching there or whatever.” (T9, para 83). Vessel tanks may furthermore be illegally cleaned at sea: “...they have washed the tankers, the tanks at sea in earlier times. That was completely normal and that is certainly still happening, [...] I have never worked on a tanker. I only know the stories how they clean their tanks before taking on new cargo.” (T9, para 87), an expert narrates. Another way to circumvent is cheating with the paperwork as one interviewee recounts: “Today it is not being in demand any more that a well-educated person is aboard, but it is only demanded that he has all papers aboard. On the Philippines, however, he gets them partly on every corner. That is where I see a problem.” (T10, para 193). This is, however, only possible to a certain extent. “Certainly [one can cheat]! Paper doesn’t blush, but my inspector also is not stupid.” (T11, para 236), another expert remarks.

Experts provide anecdotal evidence on several possibilities to circumvent legislation. To what extent companies make use of these possibilities or whether they do so at all remains questionable, but it plays a role for compliance levels that legal circumvention is technically possible at all.

The fourth exterior determinant of compliance identified is the **availability of feasible technical solutions**. After having studied the awareness of legislation as well as the willingness to comply, it will next be analysed whether shipping companies are generally able to comply with legislation. This determinant has received limited attention in previous studies but is mentioned by all experts in the present study. Subcategories for the code “Technical options” were inductively developed coming up with nine issues that were of importance to experts in this respect, as presented in Figure 5-11. Experts described cases where technical options were available, economically viable and their implementation and operation viable, but also instances where solutions were either not available, economically not viable or the implementation or operation difficult. As a last category, solutions that did not yet exist, but might prove helpful in the future, were coded under “developing”. Four of the categories, coloured light blue below, are likely to enhance compliance, while four other categories, coloured dark blue, are likely to decrease levels of compliance. Solutions available in the future have little influence on current compliance. They are discussed in Annex D1 to this thesis.

Figure 5-11: Subcategories for the code “technical options” with number of codings and number of experts per code

The availability of technical solutions will influence compliance. Whenever a law is implemented, technical solutions must be available to make compliance possible. Solutions seem to be available for most types of legislation under discussion here, although some issues with non-availability occur. The discussion is organised by the seven types of vessel-source pollution introduced above.

With respect to **oily water discharges** an expert describes that bilge water separators are available and able to comply with far stricter standards than the 15 ppm currently required: “...if one day it should come to 5ppm, that could be done as well with the technology” (T4, para 80), he says. No problems are mentioned by experts regarding non-availability of systems to prevent oily water discharges. With regards to **sewage water treatment**, which will become mandatory in the area as soon as sufficient port reception facilities are available, an expert illustrates that discharges on land are a viable option: “We have started since the summer to dispose of waste water on land in Sweden with one vessel in order to first gain some experience. So far that is running smoothly, that means until the appointed date [when stricter laws on sewage water treatment systems come into force on the Baltic Sea] at the latest we will have converted all vessels to disposal on land.” (T4, para 70). Another expert claims that land-side treatment is often not yet available in Baltic Sea harbours: “...it then also has to be viable with the sewage treatment plant that they have on land and not just qualitative, but also regarding the amounts and that today is still not the case.” (T6, para 91). He also argues that harbour states do not support the legal alternative of treatment of sewage water aboard: “Well, but there is always somehow a suspicious factor involved in that somehow. So that the member states are saying: No, you better dispose of that in the harbour.” (T6, para 91). With respect to sewage water from hatch cleaning activities an expert explains that port reception facilities are not available, thus discharges into the sea are further commonplace. “...we pump it out someplace with the knowledge of the state...” (T10, para 63), he argues. At times there seems to be a lack of systems for **waste disposal** in the harbours. (T10, para 217). No other expert mentions this issue.

With respect to **air pollution** experts, widely discuss the availability of compliant technologies for sulphur legislation. They do not mention other issues of air pollution. Experts agree that for SO₂ compliance technical solutions are easily available: "...they can simply operate on a better marine diesel, that will cost them more, but that is what they could always do if need be." (T3, para 61; see also T4, para 45, T5, para 131, T9, para 65, T10, para 35). E6 expects that the "predominant mass" of shipowners will choose this compliance option (T6, para 116, see also T5, para 132). As regards the alleged shortage of low-sulphur fuel an expert states: "Normally that is not a problem. Well, you normally get fuel everywhere." (T9, para 73, see also T5, para 136). Another expert claims that three ways of compliance are available for each vessel, speaking simply in technical terms: "Theoretically, if money does not play a role I could realise each of these three options, namely gasoil, scrubber, LNG, on each vessel." (T4, para 157; see also T6, para 16). This idea is supported by T10: "Technically virtually everything is possible given appropriate time, given appropriate planning, workshops or crew..." (T10, para 33). This view is contradicted by E2: "Scrubbers can NOT be used on all vessels. They can be used on the majority of vessels, from a vessel-type point of view. [...] ...it is not really vessel-specific as it is engine-specific and space-specific." (T2, para 98; on problems with retrofitting see also T8, para 269). The expert further explains that ferries and passenger ships will have most trouble fitting a scrubber due to limitations in space. Though all three technical solutions seem to be available for most vessels, E3 argues: "Still, I think everybody is waiting to see which solution is the best, because I think no one has so far seen which technical solution is proving to be the best. [...] I think everybody is waiting for the systems to improve, for the offers to so to speak multiply and naturally for the costs to decrease due to increased installation." (T3, para 61). The expert claims that there are options available, but there is not yet a low-cost, best practice solution on the market. Market actors might thus take recourse in waiting: "...the one or the other is waiting a little longer until there maybe comes a better offer to which they can say: Yes, that is maybe a technical solution that is more suitable to us..." (T3, para 61). T5 agrees with this perception, stating that "...the technology is ever evolving. If you decide on something today you have the risk it will be optimised tomorrow, that somebody invents something new and smarter and better." (T5, para 178). E11 doubts whether scrubbers are a reliable compliance option at all: "...the scrubber will have to be able to filter that [sulphur from 3.5%S fuel] out and that is under all operating conditions of the ship. [...] In the beginning it was said: No problem. And later everyone had to back-pedal and say: We cannot guarantee that." (T11, para 50). T6 argues that scrubbers are not yet available for larger vessels with higher machine performance: "Currently the technology works to some extent for the motors of small feeder and ferry shipping companies, even if it is very energy intensive, but not for the large container vessels. These systems are not yet designed for that, not yet developed." (T6, para 121). Speaking from an environmental point of view, one interviewee criticises scrubbers stating: "...scrubbers are no solution, because they are an end of pipe technology." (T7, para 151). An environmental issue arises from the wash water in the scrubbers that contains sulphates as an acidic residue. The wash water may first of all be released into the sea by way of an open loop scrubber: "I emit water over board that has a high level of sulphates, thus is practically acidic. That will be neutralised in the sea water, but what kind of effect that has on the marine environment will have to be further studied." (T4, para 197; see also T7, para 147 on a local acidification). E7 illustrates that some nations also discuss a prohibition of wash

water releases into their seas (T7, para 147). Secondly, the water may be released ashore by way of a closed loop scrubber, posing a different kind of problem: “Otherwise I have to somehow dispose of that on land, where we do not have real disposal systems for that yet. Not to talk of the costs.” (T4, para 197). E2 disagrees with these critics, stating that scrubbers, first developed for land-based power stations, have in the meantime developed to fit shipping needs and claiming that “...there are a lot of providers that offer solutions...” (T2, para 92). While experts agree that a technical option to comply with sulphur legislation is easily available, namely switching fuel, they are divided on the availability of adequate scrubber system to suit the needs of the entire industry.

Ballast water treatment systems are available and working, one expert explains: “And these new systems are now also able to devitalize these microbes and so forth if there are any in there and to filter the mud above all and so forth.” (T9, para 15). Another contradicts this view stating: “I would not know of a single producer who would be able to build enough systems to equip the world fleet.” (T10, para 79). A third argues: “There exist a large number of ballast water treatment systems. There are, however, huge problems with them... [...] it works according to the existing test criteria, if you simulate a certain water temperature and a certain salinity, but as soon as the vessel is sailing somewhere else – with hundreds of other temperatures and salinities in the water – the systems do not function properly any more, they are thus not reliable.” (T6, para 81). Also solutions for large-scale applications seem to pose a problem, if facilities are lacking treatment capacity: “With bulk vessels that is an entirely different question. If they transport ores to China and are empty they have to take in really very much ballast water. That means that those are large amounts and the treatment systems, as far as I know, [...] are not very reliably functioning for this application. Thus, it is a huge topic.” (T6, para 83), E6 reasons. Another expert adds: “We will be thrown off the pier if we do not take as much as this ship can take as cargo and that means we have to hold available very high ballasting capacities.” (T10, para 73). Next to a shortage of solutions for large amounts of ballast water, another problem arises from a shortage of *approved* technical solutions, as an expert claims: “There are in the meantime a few systems that are now approved, but the biggest problem has obviously been that they had only been approved by certain agencies and were not approved by others.” (T11, para 216, see also T10, para 79). Apart from systems approval, also compliance-checking still seems to leave room for discussion: “...the biologists want to do testing under all circumstances and cannot develop a sensible sampling procedure for the whole thing...” (T10, para 77), E10 illustrates. The availability of approved, functioning ballast water treatment systems, especially for large applications, is put in question by several experts.

Anti-fouling systems do not seem to pose an availability problem: “...the vessels are going into the dock and then it will be possible to paint that differently...”, an expert describes (T7, para 195). Paints to replace TBT are available on the market, but non-toxic coatings are still hard to come by: “...what has been successfully employed for many years now are basically paints where the tin, tributyltin, has been replaced by copper compounds. Thus, one moves away from this tin, but now one has copper in there as a toxin. The alternative would be silicon-based paints; they do not contain any toxin any more. There one tries to achieve that by the outer shell being very sleek to avoid that these creatures can cling to the vessel at all. That has advantages and disadvantages. Naturally very sleek outer shell coatings are always also good

for efficiency and for saving fuel. You have problems with the application, however, sometimes with the durability. We always only have very short time windows, sometimes only in the middle of the winter, to bring the vessels into the dockyard at all and then to apply a silicon-based paint that needs certain temperatures, curing times and so forth that is sometimes very, very difficult. That are the very practical problems.” (T4, para 80), an interviewee describes the current situation in detail. An additional problem arises when harbours discourage hull cleaning activities: “To clean a hull, at some time in-between, that is done, but the harbours do not like to see that neither, because if I am lying somewhere in Singapore and I say: I need to have some divers clean my hull and they do that in the harbour basin, then...” (T6, para 87), an interviewee hints at problems of in-harbour pollution arising from mechanical hull cleaning.

The availability of technical options to reduce **noise pollution** is only mentioned by one expert. He argues: “Well, that is going to be very interesting, because the ship hull is a resonator like no other.” (T8, para 123). The fact that other experts do not mention the issue seems logical, given that no legislation exists on said type of pollution and thus no technical solutions need yet be available to comply with legislation. With respect to increases in **operating efficiency** an expert states that especially on the Baltic Sea there are limits to an increase in ship sizes. Economies of scale may only be realised up to a certain point as “...first of all you have the Kiel Canal. There are sadly only certain ships fitting through that. When they are bigger they are only going in once and then the lock is shut forever indeed. The alternative is to sail around up North... is expensive, costs time and many harbours are not able to accommodate such large ships.” (T11, para 370). The same applies for the port of Hamburg: “...if the vessels are becoming even bigger, well, it is actually unlikely that there will be still another deepening of the river Elbe, and that then means at some point: end of the road.” (T3, para 120, see also T8, para 165). Limits to maximum ship sizes might limit further developments in operating efficiency.

The feasibility of operation and implementation of technical solutions is just as important as their availability to ensure legal compliance. Four codes are discussed here, namely ‘operation viable’, ‘operation difficult’, ‘implementation viable’, and ‘implementation difficult’. Table 5-4 on the number of codings and number of experts sharing these perceptions shows the great relevance of difficulties in implementation and operation to industry experts. A far lesser number of experts provide thoughts on the technical systems working well. One needs to be cautious with these numbers, however, as few people tend to elaborate on faultless solutions, while they generally spend a great length of time discussing things needing improvement.

	Implementation viable	Implementation difficult	Operation viable	Operation difficult
Number of codings	10	51	7	25
Number of experts	5	9	2	6

Table 5-4: Codes on operation and implementation of technical solutions by number of codings and number of experts

Most sources of pollution were not mentioned by interviewees with respect to the above codes, indicating that implementation and operation is an issue of relevance to very few anti-pollution measures. These are measures on air pollution, ballast water treatment and to a minor extent noise pollution. Others, like **waste disposal**, are in the most part easily implemented, as an expert illustrates “...no garbage overboard is not that difficult. You buy four dustbins, I think, for a coaster or a smaller vessel.” (T9, para 121). The implementation of a **switch to low-sulphur fuel** seems largely feasible: “For those companies that have chosen to comply by fuel switching as opposed to comply by technology it is very straightforward. There is a certain procedure that needs to be followed. For certain ships there could be some modifications that need to be done on the fuel tanks and on the fuel supply system. But they are not in an enormous scale. And most ship operators are quite familiar with what they need to do. So, the switching, technologically, it should not be a problem.” (T2, para 90), E2 describes. Another expert agrees that the implementation is simple: “...maybe they now need to put out the heating of an HFO tank and then they need to clean it once and then they put... or they don’t even need to clean it, they just need to pour MGO respectively on top of it and Bob’s your uncle [“Fertig ist die Laube”], because it is lighter anyway and will stay on top of it.” (T8, para 207). As regards the operation, E9 explains: “Well, gas oil really actually is what you are also canting in your car more or less. And the machines can handle that without problems...” (T9, para 67). He goes on: “...if you would operate a machine entirely with gas oil now from the beginning then... that would first of all naturally be incredibly good, because it burns very, very clean. It renders this whole heavy fuel oil preparation unnecessary. That means you no longer have this whole slush, this whole sludge, because you do not need separators anymore. Well, it has an incredible amount of advantages. You do not need that much steam anymore and steam also at the same time means more heavy crude oil consumption, because the steam also needs to be generated somehow.” (T9, para 71). Also, the operation seems feasible without overburdening the crew, as the same experts suggest: “...well, sometimes an engineer needs to get up at night time and needs to shift round a few outlets.” (T9, para 67). Other experts **disagree with the switch being easy** in terms of **implementation** asserting that changes to the tanks are rather complex: “Because not every tank is gas oil capable and the whole pipeline system in the engine room suddenly needs to be taken apart in order to realise economically justifiable switchover times. And all of that needs to, if we do it right, needs to be officially coordinated with the classification society, and needs to be rebuilt plan-approved.” (T10, para 27). E10 adds, however: “With a little bit of fantasy and a little bit of clever thinking that is manageable...” (T10, para 81). E6 explains why different properties of MGO and HFO may lead to problems: “...that is another grade that has a different viscosity, different physical properties and that you may not so easily, say, fill into the bunker tank and just keep on operating... [...] ...with regards to the viscosity you have a heavy fuel oil that is tough and light diesel oil. That goes through the fuel pumps and so on. A pump that is designed to push a tough substance through the pipes, if you then tuck in such a light liquid stuff the whole technical pumps will break into pieces. There are really some precautions that need to be taken on board.” (T6, para 16;119; see also T7, para 63). Another expert also reports uncertainty about “how we have to reconstruct our tank systems on board in order to comply with this 0.1 gasoil so that it will not mix with the heavy fuel oil that we are using as well, as we are operating worldwide. Currently that is an issue on board the vessels that that does not somehow intermix in the settling tank.” (T6, para

33). Another expert explains “we evidently preferably want to deal with a pipe that does not come in touch with heavy fuel oil, because otherwise we will contaminate it for a long time to come [...] I suddenly need to access this diesel oil pipe plus I need to connect all diesel oil tanks with this tank in order to be able to bunker. And all those are alterations in fuel-forwarding pipes, thus the fuel tanks need to be gas free, hot work. Those are extreme exertions that shipping has to undertake at the moment that are not making life easier.” (T10, para 31). “The most difficult in the ECA zone is the tank cleaning. That is the most displeasing and the most difficult.” (T10, para 81), the same expert adds. With regards to an alternating **operation** on HFO and MGO E2 reports: “...there is some data to suggest that there has been a noticeable increase in reported engine failures. Most of them are being rectified and they will carry on, but obviously an unrectified situation can resolve in a potential grounding, collision, with other consequences.” (T2, para 90, for the same argument see T11, para 68). Another expert adds: “...if you ask an engineer now he will not be happy that he needs to switch the stuff all the time. That is no pleasure for the machines neither evidently, let me say, to change the operating fluids all the time, well technically a challenge in any case. (...) First of all it is a risk to put a tank down and to put another one into operation. Well, something may not fit there, a valve may not operate properly and the fuel pressure might then fall and all of that has already happened to us... (...) Especially for old motors that are evidently due to the fact that gas oil is much lighter it leaks out of all corners, it really runs down at times.” (T9, para 67-69, on difficulties with continuous switching see also T10, para 25; T11, para 66). While some experts perceive the switch to low-sulphur fuel as trouble-free, others worry both about implementing changes to the infrastructure aboard, as well as the operation of a light fluid in a system constructed for a heavy fluid. Still, while experts might not be happy about the switch to low-sulphur fuel, they overall agree that the switch might lead to minor technical difficulties but is by and large feasible.

Installing a **scrubber** seems more difficult than switching from a technical point of view, according to expert perceptions: “To install and operate a complex exhaust gas emission cleaning system is rather more demanding. It costs money as well and so forth, but also takes space in the vessel, can lead to stability problems – that the vessels become top-heavy...”, E4 reports (T4, para 143). This position is supported by E11 stating: “you will be able to fit a scrubber, but you would have to place it at the forefront of the bridge, in front of the superstructures. Normally containers are placed there and you are massively changing the stability of the ship. You have problems with the feeder tanks for granulate and waste...” (T11, para 48). Another expert claims that technology implementation challenges are generally “quite ship specific – [depending on] the age of the ship, the space available on board, and all that.” (T2, para 92, see also T8, para 289, T11, para 214). Not only installing, but also operating a scrubber might pose problems: “...is not that easy in operations, because you now have much more systems that the crew now has to operate and has to operate correctly and so on.”, an expert narrates (T4, para 142). Another collaborates: “...that really is a rather big chemical laboratory that you have aboard. That means you also need to have people who understand something about that.” (T11, para 62). With regards to scrubber, several experts question the viability of installation and operation on all types of commercial vessels.

Nitrogen oxide prevention might also be difficult to implement, as discussed by one expert: “NO_x emission regulation is rather a technical problem. Difficult, by all means, especially when we are talking about retrofits. [...] New vessels have to comply with the stricter Tier III limits. That is again going about 75.8% further down in terms of NO_x reduction. That cannot be achieved so easily any more. That means you have to fit a catalyst. With the newbuilding that is not a problem as such as you may plan that in advance – then simply the motor and a cat behind. There you know what you may expect. But we fear a little bit, let me say... at the horizon we see a little bit the idea of politics to also reduce the NO_x emissions of the existing fleet. And that is touching upon the area of retrofits, well, upgrading. That is with everything that you have inside such a motor, with the turbochargers, with the whole supply system, with the exhaust gas currents, that is not that trivial to install. That is going to be complicated.” (T6, para 111). It has to be noted that no political endeavours exist so far to introduce nitrogen emission limits for the current fleet.

The installation of **ballast water management systems** seems technically feasible according to one expert: “It means plain and simply that we have to install according treatment systems into the different vessels by and by and eventually into all of them, depending on when the next dry docking is scheduled or how large the vessel is and so forth.” (T7, para 52.) Another expert mentions that technical implementation problems might arise where space is limited: “...we strictly speaking do not have space on such a vessel for any additional complex systems...” (T4, para 85). A third expert who is already operating ballast water treatment systems relates his experiences: “Those are incredibly complex systems that are still not working a hundred per cent fail-safe. Well, we have these things on the new vessels now and that still is such a trial-and-error story. Well, we have tremendous problems with them. Well, that they run fail-safe. It also has to fit... what I need to say... also somehow needs to fit into the work flow. Well, you do not want to busy yourself with correctly adjusting the system all the time. There are very, very many valves and pressures and so on, you need to make sure that all of it fits and the pumps also one day need to operate fail-safe. That means... yes, this system causes a lot of problems at the moment and is also extremely expensive. Well, everything that breaks down always immediately costs an incredible amount of money.” (T9, para 17). Another issue with ballast water laws might arise when the operation of the vessel makes ballasting or de-ballasting necessary despite the law: “...well, sometimes it is simply the case that we are forced to also take water in waters near the coast or to drain water because of different loading conditions, flotation depth restrictions, where you just need to take care that you do not have too much water aboard, because due to that you are diving in deeper logically and then you cannot enter the harbour any more at certain times.” (T9, para 15). Another issue that might make ballast water management operations difficult especially for services calling at many ports is the reporting of ballasting operations: “Yes, it is about the reporting. You have to report everything and if you imagine that: A feeder. Alone... it is about such trifles like the sailing list having to be changed at the last minute. That is really due to the short time between the harbours rather the rule than the exception. You can suddenly not do that anymore, because you have to comply with the reporting times or you cannot comply with certain criteria, because you now have loaded ballast water in a certain area that you are afterwards not allowed to release there anymore.” (T11, para 80). Practical problems are named by experts that might arise both when

installing and operating ballast water treatment systems. As the related technology is still in its infancy, it stands to reason that a number of these issues will be resolved over time.

All in all, experts see difficulties with the implementation and operation of technical solutions mainly in two fields. While most measures do not yield any problems, challenges of ballast water treatment and measures to prevent SO₂ and NO_x emissions are widely discussed by experts. Switching to low-sulphur fuel is seen by some experts as a straightforward process, while others mention rebuilding the systems aboard, different properties of the two fuels and likely engine failures as challenges. Scrubbers are discussed critically with experts mentioning problems with space, stability, operating knowledge and systems failures. NO_x emission legislation might pose a problem if requested for the existing fleet but seems feasible for new-buildings. Ballast water systems are criticised for a lack of reliability and for being at times incompatible with shipping realities, for example in the case of feeders calling at many ports or container vessels needing to release water in order to enter a certain harbour. Installation seems to be feasible. Regarding the amount of legislative changes taken together, however, an expert argues: “If one brings more and more technology aboard, more and more complex technology it will get more and more difficult to also concretely maintain that and to manage that and to supervise that.” (T10, para 205). Technical and operational interdependencies among new environmental technologies have not received academic attention so far.

Economic viability of technical solutions represents the last two subcategories of the code “Availability of feasible technical options”. Technical solutions need to be available, their implementation and operation needs to be feasible and lastly their adoption needs to be economically viable in order to give companies the true ability to comply with legislation. Expert opinions on economic viability are discussed in this sub-chapter. Seven experts commented in 13 codings on technical solutions that were economically viable, while nine of the twelve experts talked about instances where solutions were not economically viable in a total of 38 codings. Again, several environmental measures were not mentioned, specifically legislation on oily water, sewage water and noise pollution. One expert argued that laws on dumping of **waste** seemed to be economically feasible: “I think dumping of waste, or rather dumping... (...) Well, to dispose of that the right way is not a huge cost factor I think. That is not a big thing.” (T9, para 91).

With respect to **operating on low-sulphur fuel** one expert argues that legislation may lead to potential cost savings: “...we have evidently also had advantages due to these clean machine operations. Well: Significantly longer maintenance intervals, lower maintenance costs, spare part costs and such things...” (T4, para 133). Also, changing the pipes and tanks in order to make a ship SECA-ready can increase market value, E10 reports. A vessel lacking the flexibility to operate in SECAs will have trouble finding a charterer: “...the market is making sure what the vessel is capable of and what I pay for that. Well, it also has a market value.” (T10, para 33). One expert argues that economic viability of the fuel switch depends on many factors, making it feasible for some operators and not feasible for others: “A political decision is being taken – 0.1 in 2015 – and do all shipping companies and shipping operators, vessel types, vessels sizes, have the chance to really actually comply with regulations without taking the risk that they will not be able to keep their seat of operations or their economic profitability? And

in relation to the sulphur questions that was really a huge issue.” (T6, para 54). The installation of **scrubbers** to comply with SO₂ regulation becomes more interesting with an increasing difference in fuel price between high-sulphur and low-sulphur fuel. One expert argues: “...if the increase in demand of this fuel [MGO] within Europe and within ECA areas drives the increase in price, a certain increase in price then the incentive will be even greater [to install a scrubber]” (T2, para 96). Economic viability depends on the fuel price development. With increasing vessel age, economic viability decreases: “...if I have an old vessel then an expensive exhaust gas emission cleaning system (...) will likely not be worthwhile anymore.”, relates E3 (T3, para 65). Also, main operations outside SECAs decrease the economic viability of scrubber installation: “From a practical point of view, however, there are many vessels where economically that would not make any sense, because they are either too old or because they operate too little of their time in these SECAs.” (T4, para 157; see T5, para 134 on few companies meeting the criteria for a scrubber installation to make sense). Prohibitive costs may also be linked to space restrictions and issues of ship stability (see T11, para 48). E2 reasons that though scrubbers have proven to be economically feasible in individual cases there is still not enough operational experience to make a sound business case. “But with time it will become easier”, he adds (T2, para 96). One issue that is unclear is whether a scrubber installation increases or decreases ship values: “The other thing is that this new legislation what will that do to ship values? Take for instance retrofit of a scrubber. That is a cost of for us somewhere between 5 and 10 million Euros per ship. Is that an increase in the ship value or is it a decrease in the ship value?“, E5 asks (T5, para 260). Savings in CO₂ emissions by **slow steaming** are not politically prescribed but chosen by companies to achieve fuel savings in times of low demand. As a by-product it is an economically sound way of protecting the environment: “...most of what one may simply save in CO₂ emissions is simply by sailing more slowly as well. First of all it is more economical for the company and if I operate on half the amount it is also clear what is happening to the CO₂ emissions...” (T9, para 101), an expert explains.

While limiting air pollution from vessels may thus be economically feasible for shipping companies, experts agree that investments in ballast water treatment make for a less compelling business case. **Ballast water management systems** are “VERY expensive” (T6, para 81), an interviewee claims. Their economic feasibility in the eyes of the shipping company is quite low, as they do not yield any cost-saving options. (T9, para 173). Investments are particularly difficult for older vessels with a short life expectancy (T2, para 98). With respect to **hull coatings**, new paints are available on the market and technically feasible, but are significantly more expensive than TBT: “Yes, they are working, yes, clearly. Yes, they are naturally extremely expensive. That is why TBT still existed for so long. That was the only reason. There already exist much better systems, well somehow Teflon-containing or silicone-containing and that is also especially with the minimisation of friction today's regarding vessel efficiency an important issue.” (T9, para 43). Experts feel unanimously that ballast water and anti-fouling legislation is largely not economically viable. The case is very different with **increases in efficiency**, which will oftentimes be economically viable, as one expert envisions: “...one could maybe manage to lead the shipping company as a whole into the direction that they in any way build clean ships and operate these vessels very economically, which will evidently also benefit the shipowners...” (T9, para 195). Another expert states that “...that is something that every shipping company is focusing on for a new-building anyway, because the less a vessel

consumes the higher the rate that you will receive from a potential charterer, because he is then saving a lot of money and if you take a look at how the bunker consumption of ships has declined further and further in the course of the last ten years, fifteen years then one can see that there is already a lot happening.” (T11, para 128).

Some technical solutions to protect the environment, especially increases in vessel efficiency and slow steaming, hull coatings that minimise friction and low-sulphur fuels bringing about cleaner operations and lower maintenance costs are economically viable and can under certain circumstances bring cost savings to shipping companies. In other cases, especially with regards to ballast water management systems and scrubbers, companies have no economically viable solution available, but have to choose from a number of costly solutions for compliance. In certain cases, be it old vessels, ships with space restrictions or ships that seldomly enter SECA areas, the costs of available technical options are prohibitive and companies choose not to invest, but to take the respective vessel out of the protected area or out of service altogether. Another way when being faced with options that are economically not viable is a path of willing noncompliance.

	Availability	Implementation viable	Operation viable	Economically viable
Oily water	Bilge-water separators available			
Sewage water	Lack of port reception facilities			
Waste	Sometimes lack of waste disposal facilities in ports	Placing waste bins aboard easy	Training crew might prove difficult	Not expensive
Air pollution	Operation on low-sulphur fuel available	Minor modifications for low-sulphur operation	Cleaner operations, but maybe machine problems due to different viscosity	Economic viability in question, cost savings due to cleaner operations possible
Ballast water	Lack of large-scale, reliable, approved treatment systems	Installation difficult, where space is limited	Systems failing; ballast water handling difficult for normal operations	Expensive, no economic incentives for installation
Toxic anti-fouling	Toxic alternatives to TBT and some non-toxic	Application of non-toxic coatings difficult		Alternatives significantly more

	alternatives available			expensive than TBT
Noise pollution	No options available	Technically difficult to absorb vibrations of the main engine		
Operative efficiency	Limits to increasing ship sizes due to depth constraints			Efficiency increases economically viable

Table 5-5: Summary of the availability of feasible technical options (Colour code: green = available, orange = some issues with availability, red = major issues with availability)

Lastly, experts describe incidents where noncompliance happens unwillingly, due to **human error or higher forces**. This category has only been mentioned by half of the experts and seems to play a minor role in decision-making. Six experts discuss cases where employees made mistakes or technical failures occurred. Experts argue that employees might “put some wrong figure down” (T9, para 153). “...people make mistakes” (T11, para 189), E11 argues. “I don’t want to rule out people entering [the SECA] in the beginning of next year saying, oh no, somehow we were not consciously aware of that, no idea, forgot about it.” (T6, para 171), one interviewee deliberates. Also, laws may not be entirely clear, making it difficult to know when noncompliance begins: “...nobody is actively appearing as a criminal to actively avoid things and break laws. But many laws have many grey areas and I think that many grey areas are being used extensively.” (T12, para 104). Thirdly, the implementation of laws might prove difficult, as when port reception facilities for sewage waters are not available: “That means in the harbour states, or in the harbours the facilities are missing to implement these regulations.” (T10, para 63), an interviewee explains. “It is not possible to just prohibit something and to say: But we do not offer you an alternative” (T6, para 95), another expert argues. Technical failures are another issue that might lead to unwilling noncompliance: “When someone sails in the Baltic Sea next year, well, a scrubber might break down, I mean, that is a complex technical system, you never know. Somehow it is breaking down and you are still in an area with 0.1 per cent sulphur, but only have 3 per cent fuel aboard, what shall you do then?” (T6, para 171), an expert asks. Noncompliance can happen by oversight (compare T2, para 36) or by the influence of higher forces: “...if you would not comply occasionally it could be because of something which is beyond someone’s control...” (T2, para 33), an expert argues. The only thing that is hard to control for is human error and the weather: “If you are not training and instructing your crew correctly then you cannot implement that correctly. Above all things because if you take a look

at out of how many nationalities a crew is made meanwhile there exist great cultural differences there. As a Northern European it is clear that one does simply not throw waste into the environment. In other countries that is seen entirely differently. I even do not want to judge that. Thus, if you want to implement all of that then you also have to have someone who controls that. And you need to pay these people accordingly and instruct them accordingly and motivate them and control them and yes, that is a very cumbersome process, very tedious and in the end of the day it also costs money.” (T11, para 222). Unwilling noncompliance seems to be rather a rare case judging by the small number of codings in that category. However, human error, technical failures or higher forces may influence compliance levels without the shipping company planning to deviate from the laws.

5.4 Differences among companies

A core question that developed during this research is whether different companies experienced differences in compliance costs from maritime environmental legislation. The question whether company characteristics make a difference is strongly contested among experts. Some experts argue that there are relevant differences among shipping companies. E2 states: “...it is not easy to put the shipping industry in one big box and read everyone the same...” (T2, para 27; see also T10, para 12; T12, para 121). Other experts argue that the same laws apply to everyone: “..they are all bound by the question of emissions; that is independent of the type of vessel. [...] in my opinion it does not matter in the end whether it is a bulker or a container vessel, that is actually all the same.” (T3, para 80). E2 collaborates this statement, saying: “The requirement is the same for everyone.” (T2, para 40; for the same argument see T1, para 113; T8, para 273; T10, para 119; T11, para 206; see T6, para 161 on the argument that also non-European operators face the same legal environment.). E10 further support these statements: “All those things are different in nuances, but in the end it is all operating vessels that underlie the same legal acts. I do not see a big difference there.” (T10, para 120). E7 explains that operators of larger vessels and smaller vessels are equally affected by sulphur legislation, as price increases are born relative to vessel size (T7, para 145). With respect to ballast water systems, the same expert argues: “The more vessels I have the more ballast water treatment systems I need to install. And thus, speaking about the total sum it will be larger for shipping companies the more vessels they have.” (T7, para 160). With respect to knowledge within the shipping companies E6 argues: “Well, regarding the way in which they are informed, thus the quality or the quantity, they are not differently well informed.” (T6, para 68). A number of experts contest whether differences among companies are relevant for the compliance cost discussion at all. Still, twelve categories were developed from qualitative content analysis, mapping out how company characteristics could influence exposure to environmental laws. These categories are named in Table 5-6 and discussed below. Expert opinions regarding how company characteristics might influence compliance levels have been discussed in Chapter 5.3.2 on the determinants of compliance and will not find further mention here.

Company characteristics	Description	Number of codings
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Company size	Larger or smaller companies in terms of fleet size and number of employees	62
Fleet composition	Types of vessels employed, i.e. bulker, tanker, RoRo vessels	38
Company culture	Criminogenic or law-abiding culture	30
Age of vessels	Age of individual vessels and vessel fleet	30
Flag state	Jurisdiction under which the vessel is registered or licensed	28
Routes of operation	Short sea or deep-sea shipping, operations within or outside ECAs	27
Vessel building specifications	Buildup of specific company vessels	21
Seat of operations	Jurisdiction where the main seat of operations is located	18
Financial situation	Company assets, financing situation and opportunities, cash flow	9
Choice of classification society	Organisation certifying the company vessels	7
Portfolio of customers	Typical customer type, e.g. large cooperations, individuals	6
Ownership structure	Ownership of the company, e.g. state-owned, privately owned, limited partnership	6

Table 5-6: Categories of company characteristics influencing compliance costs with MEL

The largest number of codings can be found for the category ‘**Company size**’, indicating that experts believe size matters for compliance costs. They particularly mention the endowment with resources, economies of scale and a higher profitability as reasons why larger companies would experience lower compliance costs or would be affected less by environmental legislation. “The small ones [...] are under a different cost pressure...”, E6 states (T6, para 157). “...right, the smaller I am the less profitable my company is, logically.”, another expert argues (T3, para 120). He adds: “Clearly, in a big shipping company certain measures can be cross-financed and you can maybe afford somehow to make a little larger loss somewhere if you know that you make a little larger profit somewhere else and thus you at least stay at the same level, that you make ends meet to a certain degree. Smaller shipowners with fewer vessels and less opportunities do not have the chance to cross-finance and thus they certainly have, I could imagine, larger problems...” (T3, para 78; see also T7, para 160 on larger shipping companies being able to cover expenses better than a smaller one). Another expert collaborates this perspective, stating: “I would say it is the big shipping companies that first of all have the resources to implement various initiatives. It is about resources [...] Typically, it is not the company with one ship.” (T2, para 29). E4 does not fully agree with this statement, maintaining that eventually larger shipping companies have to remain profitable just the same: “...in a larger

company the services in deficit could be subsidised by other services or something like that. [...] That is certainly possible to a limited extent over a limited amount of time. [...] I think also larger shipping companies have to make sure, in the long run, that all their services run profitably.” (T4, para 89 et sqq.). Economies of scale may play a role in coping with environmental laws: “If one assumes that one shipping company has one vessel and another shipping company has fifty vessels. The time needed to analyse a law is a certain factor and the shipping company with more vessels may certainly break down the investment costs on more vessels. Thus, per vessel it is maybe cheaper, if you calculate it like that.” (T7, para 142). Also, E9, explains, larger companies will buy compliance equipment at cheaper rates: “...if a big liner shipping company buys this and that many facilities and they evidently already get different prices than if one person comes along...” (T9, para 175). Size, E2 reasons, will also determine the level of information on legal processes: “I think the larger companies they have the resources to interpret that information better and to develop their strategies and their procedures for implementation.” (T2, para 42). E6 supports this view saying: “Big ones, I would say, [...] they have departments that are dealing with political regulations. They have man power to do that. If you go to a small shipping company in the Altes Land [region near Hamburg], they have to see how to keep their vessels moving, to procure cargo. They do not have that.” (T6, para 55). Another expert explains that larger shipping companies might even be involved in political processes, stating that it “...is always easier in a big company to implement things and I also always have the feeling that they are a little closer to the whole events happening at the IMO and so on. One-ship companies, with certainty, they have it extremely difficult, because they have the same legislation. They need to comply with ISPS, ISM, this whole stuff, I’m just saying, comply like the big shipping companies and that is a crazy effort and to keep up to date with that is almost impossible.” (T9, para 121). E10 says: “...there exists a clear tendency for me that the big companies have an information advantage over the small companies due to the higher number of employees and actually also due to managers who have the time to go to such committees...” (T10, para 59).

Experts provide a wealth of reasons why larger shipping companies face lower compliance costs and have advantages when incorporating environmental laws into company processes. These perceptions are not universally shared, however. From own experience, E6 reports: “...we have a lot of small shipping companies that are absolutely exemplary with their two, three vessels and keep them in top conditions and that do not have any such black spots somehow in their history with regards to their image and the chartering out on the market.” (T6, para 159). The same expert adds that the differences between large and small companies regarding the effect of MEL are limited: “A small feeder operator has a cost concern just as much as a large company, because the relations are the same. You can earn little with such a small one. You have comparatively little fuel costs, but you also earn less than with a large Hamburg Express by Hapag Lloyd, well, because you can simply load less cargo. That means that the relations stay the same and that is why it is like it is.” (T6, para 202). E8 supports this view, stating: “Per vessel it has practically no influence, per vessel the costs are more or less always the same.” (T8, para 289). E5 further states that in his experience small companies may be just as well informed as large companies (T5, para 123 et sqq.). Still, a number of experts voiced that faced with increased costs from environmental legislation, it would be particularly smaller shipping companies leaving the market. E3 argues: “And I would say that there is likely a connection

between these types of fleets, that there are many small, old fleets or many small old shipping companies and the one or the other will certainly, will certainly still go down the drain, that is the way it is.” (T3, para 120). This view is collaborated by E9, stating: “Smaller shipping companies have no prospects on the market.” (T9, para 191). Regarding chances he sees for his company for the future, E10 says: “...what is a big chance? Spoken as a big one: That the small ones die. Than we have fewer competitors.” (T10, para 193).

The second-most-coded character of a shipping company that might influence the effect of MEL on the company is **fleet composition**. This code refers to the type of vessels employed by the company, specifically whether the fleet consists of container vessels, general cargo carriers, bulk carriers, RoRo vessels, crude carriers or specialised cargo carriers. E2 argues that different vessel types would be affected differently by sulphur legislation, depending on the share of fuel cost of operational costs, which could reach up to 85% for certain cargo vessels, but will be much lower for others (T2, para 84; compare T4, para 74 estimating that for short sea ferries the share of fuel costs in total costs is easily 50 per cent). E10 describes how his bulk carrier business is affected differently by MEL than a container shipping company. Firstly, ballast water legislation will affect bulk carriers and tankers more than container vessels: “Container vessels have been living for years [...] mainly from ballast water management, because through many small tanks respective to the cargo allocation the water is just being apportioned and only small amounts are collected or released, depending on the cargo situation. Never 100 per cent. Meanwhile a bulk vessel... we are loading a whole batch and have to release 100 per cent ballast water. Then we are sailing to the port of discharge, we empty out 100 per cent and take 100 per cent ballast water in again. Exactly the same applies to a tanker. For us that is an entirely different issue than for a container vessel.” (T10, para 73; see also T6, para 83 on bulk carriers being significantly more influenced by ballast water legislation than container carriers). He goes on: “The difference between them and us is that the container people hide their ballast trip in empty containers. We have to do the ballast trip. The container people on the other hand always operate half empty on average. While we, when we are loaded [...] not a single more gram will fit in there. We are operating at significantly lower speeds. That means if we look at the efficiency [...] There we are evidently far ahead of the containers, far, far, far. [...] Regarding cargo utilisation, what the vessel can carry and what it actually carries, we are certainly better. [...] If a container breaks and he needs to clean the cargo hold he has the same problems. He has much more to do with fuel and air pollution, however. Anti-fouling wear is much higher with him due to higher speeds...” (T10, para 117 et sqq.). With respect to crude carriers, the expert explains: “Tankers still have different concerns as well. [...] They have the same concerns in the ballast area, but apart from that they have different concern than we do. We have wash water in the hatches, they have tank cleaning by slot system, which is, however, based on older laws, because that has been much more important at the time, because the pollution was much bigger, based on older laws they already have shore facilities. They are releasing their slot ashore. A refinery HAS to take it and that is how it has been decided.” (T10, para 115). An operator of RoRo vessels claims that companies like his will be little affected by ballast water legislation, as they are likely to receive exceptions from the rule: “A nice example is that the ballast water issue for example is a huge issue for a bulk shipper, tanker I think is the same, as they have to deal with very much different amounts of ballast water than we do. And because they operate specifically this international trade. For us, [...] there is the prospect of a reasonable

solution at the end, where we do not have to solve that issue technically, but somehow formally by way of an exception will not have to do it.” (T4, para 93). Different vessel types might have different space restrictions, experts argue: “One really tries to completely fill each free metre with containers, thus where do you want to place a scrubber now? You can only put that somewhere... the main machine is back here, where do you place it? There is no space in the hulk, there are containers standing about everywhere, you can only put that up above. The chimney comes out here. That means with a new-building you would normally have to include it directly in the superstructures. You cannot do that retroactively anymore. The space is simply not available. That is simply too narrow.” (T11, para 214). Space seems to be equally limited on RoRo vessels, an expert claims: “...the technical challenges are mostly on the ferry and passenger ships, where the space limitations are simply prohibitive in many cases. Actually, those who need it the most are those who will struggle the most.” (T2, para 98). Some experts state that compliance costs will be particularly high for vessels travelling on many seas and thus having to comply with many different laws, especially tramp vessels: “It is a double-edged sword, because the shipping markets are so dynamic that you want to be able to quickly, especially for certain trades, you know for ships doing tramp trades you need that flexibility. And obviously, if you have ships that are not able to operate globally simply because of their equipment or their compliance flexibility this is not ideal. But the alternative, which is a fleet-wider renewal of technology implementation, it costs a lot of money. So, I think the laws are changing the dynamics of certain companies and I think, in a way, those companies which operate on a tramp basis they will struggle the most. Their assets will either have to be geared up for worldwide compliance or become less flexible.” (T2, para 52). The type of vessels employed by the shipping company will thus influence the exposure of the company to environmental laws.

Next, as supported by 30 expert statements, the **company culture** may play a role in influencing compliance costs. The company policy will have an influence on when and how investment decision in clean technology and operations are made. E12 holds: “...it also has to do with the company policy in the first place, with the attitude of the companies. There are for example company bosses who would like to be green if they could afford it. [...] Then there are... well there is political orientation from the management. [...] There is also a... how do you say, a spread, so a distribution of companies in every market. Some companies are technology leaders, some are followers...” (T12, para 124). E10 accentuates: “We are following different approaches. The one wants to be first class carrier and wants to advertise that and follow his business model and others say: Okay, I am in the low segment and I want to work very differently.” (T10, para 121). In some companies, environmental behaviour is laid down according to company goals, which might differ from prescribed legal rules. E9 describes: “...among other things I am naturally also the garbage manager. That means that I am the one who is trying to implement the company-own environmental policy aboard more or less to the best of my knowledge and belief.” (T9, para 13). He adds: “...we have a so-called clean ballast company policy. That means out at sea we take... we have about 200 miles distance from land and 2,000 metres water depth, that is this reference value where we take water.” (T9, para 15). E12 emphasises how the company culture may develop over time: “...you will find a company policy that for example might also change with a change at the top.” (T12, para 124, see also T11, para 176 on the importance of company policy). Company owners might have an influence

on company culture as described by E7: “Owners are also interested, well, we belong to the [a company holding] and this issue of sustainability, environment, social issues is definitely of relevance for the [owning family]. In that way they are naturally also a player.” (T7, para 18). The company culture may be linked to the cultural background of the management, experts suggest: “I think due to a different mentality there are certainly also differences regarding environmental protection in general I would say.”, one expert points out (T9, para 123). Another argues: “The Germans are always very... we are very, very aware of the whole issue of regulation. That is very present to everyone. That also means that we have a very sharp eye on what is being regulated, what has to be regulated, how rigorously, strictly that is being implemented, such things. The awareness here is bigger...” (T6, para 161). Based on these expert perceptions it can be said that companies have a choice in how important environmental protection is for their own company culture. Depending on this relevance ranking, costs associated with measures taken might be lower or higher.

Compliance costs may furthermore depend on the **age of vessels**. This code was supported by 30 expert statements during interviews. Older vessels might not merit environmental investments, as an expert explains: “...if I have an old vessel then an expensive exhaust gas emission cleaning system [...] will likely not be worthwhile any more. [...] And others will say: Man, I got an entirely new ship or a relatively young ship that will travel the oceans of the world for another twenty years - for that the investment is worth the while.” (T3, para 65). The expert emphasises that vessels having only a few more years of operating time left will not be retrofitted with scrubbers but run on MGO (T3, para 68). E2 describes the case of an old bulk carrier faced with environmental legislation: “...so if you have a, let us say, a bulk carrier which is 20-30 years old, 25, whatever, it passed a special survey and it is seaworthy and has approval and everything else, but is not worth, if you sell it on the second hand market it is worth maybe five million, three million, and if you have to spend on equipment which is almost the scrap value of the ship then this becomes a bit of a challenge.” (T2, para 44). E8 and E9 stress that older assets will not be retrofitted with LNG engines (T8, para 267; T9, para 95). Another expert argues that older assets may be kept updated with respect to environmental laws, but that the effort will be greater and options more limited: “...if a vessel is too old there are less options. Okay, I do not think we should necessarily discriminate against companies that operate older fleets, [...] you know, operating older assets has its advantages. And the advantage is, it is usually cheaper to drive second hand cars all your life and letting someone else pay for the depreciation. [...] Older vessels can comply. So, there are options there. [...] I have met a lot of clients who operate older assets, but they too comply [...] It is so, their options are much more limited.” (T2, para 46, for a similar perspective see T5, para 160). An expert argues that newer vessels are already build towards greater efficiency: “Clearly. The newer the vessel, the more environmentally friendly it is. Entirely clear. Especially in today’s time a lot of value is put on efficiency and also in that respect than on the fuel consumption...” (T9, para 161). “The more modern the ship the lower will the bunker uptake be, the better is the technical equipment.”, E11 agrees (T11, para 256). This perspective is challenged by another expert, who explains that the environmental performance of vessels depends rather on the year in which they were build: “What we have seen in the years 2004 to 2008 for example is that the shipyards have built a standard type. That type of vessel has been chosen based on the best production procedure and not on the best economy of the ship. And the shipyards were booked out. When a shipowner

wanted to build a ship, the shipyard has said: This is my vessel. Take it or leave it. Thus, the owner had no opportunity to build environmentally friendly or more economic ships, because they had no supplier. That has changed with the crash in 2008. [...] Then it was possible again to build environmentally friendly ships. That means that the supplying industry does not always offer environmentally friendly ships and the shipowner then has no possibility to get them. That is why the age of the fleet only is related to that if it fits into this time frame.” (T10, para 151). E11 also questions the notion that newer vessels are necessarily more environmentally friendly, arguing that the shipyard building the vessel might also play a role: “That depends a bit on what kind of vessels those are, where they have been build. There exist twenty-year-old ships that have been built for example here at Sieters; they are excellent, because one has simply built in modern technology from the start also with a view for certain things.” (T11, para 256). While most experts thus agree that a younger fleet will mean more efficient vessels and lower environmental compliance costs, two experts emphasise that both the year of built and the shipyard exercising the construction will influence the environmental performance of the vessel.

The **flag state** or flag states used might be another quality of a shipping company having a bearing on compliance costs. E2 argues that some flag states are more trustworthy than others when it comes to monitoring the environmental performance of their fleets (T2, para 35). It might thus be that companies registered with certain flags face lower compliance costs than other shipping companies. This notion is challenged by E1, stating: “The flag, that is first and foremost an issue of costs, but concerning labour costs, [...] not necessarily linked to environmental laws.” (T1, para 113). It is true that most environmental laws are decided at the international or supranational level and not made by flag states. However, shipping registers must make sure their members act in line with the laws. A number of experts emphasise, however, that many flags are better than their reputation: “If a vessel is flying the Liberian flag normally there is a German or Norwegian or British shipping company in the background or a Greek shipping company in the background. He is flying the flag, because that brings economic advantages to him. But the decisions are not taken in Liberia. Why should then... One has to be careful there. Why should the Liberians see that laxer than the Europeans? I cannot postulate that neither. And I will not.”, E4 claims (T4, para 141). E6 supports this perception, stating: “...the German shipping companies are mostly sailing the Liberian flag. A large share is Antigua and Barbuda flag, I believe. And then smaller ones. [...] Well I believe historically the Liberian flag is the dominating one, if I am correctly informed. Whereby I always need to say right away, not to give way to any misconceptions, the ship and flag register of Liberia has in fact nothing to do with the country. Rather, it belongs to the best and most efficient registers that exist worldwide, with regard to the environment and with regard to the treatment of the seamen as well...” (T6, para 52). Another expert explains that while some flag states might be lax in enforcing environmental laws, harbour state controls will be particularly keen to control ships flying these flags: “Everything that is regulated at the IMO, well if you get here with such a flag then you cannot escape from harbour state controls, if you really have such adventure-flags...” (T8, para 286; see also T11, para 200 on certain flags being controlled more often than others). However, shipping companies choosing low-quality flags may not be as well informed about legislation as others: “...the flag states implement, perceive that differently to inform their

let me say members...”, E10 argues (T10, para 47). Overall, the flag state chosen by a shipping company should have little influence on compliance costs, experts argue.

Shipping companies may also be affected differently by environmental legislation depending on their usual **routes of operation**. A distinction of particular importance is whether a company is operating almost exclusively within the North and Baltic ECAs as a short sea operator, or whether it is operating on deep-sea routes between the continents. With respect to the North and Baltic Sea SECAs, an expert argues: “The large container vessels will place their bets further on design optimisation and slow steaming and will then see what they have to do in the different zones – in the ECAs in the U.S. and in the SECAs in Europe they will under these circumstances then just switch to diesel.” (T3, para 66). E4 emphasises: “...the colleague that sails with his container vessels from Rotterdam or Hamburg to the Far East, the share of the total journey that he sails on diesel oil in the SECA is comparatively small. And thus, also the cost increase is significantly lower than with us.” (T4, para 93; see also T2, para 74). A container ship operator active on deep-sea routes states: “Sulphur will not really change our business model...” (T7, para 108). While these operators seem concerned with the SECAs only on the fringes of their operation, short sea operators face stark cost increases: “The small short sea people, the ferries, that operate 100 per cent on the Baltic Sea, SO_x-ECA, they are facing different problems than a huge container shipping company.”, an expert argues (T6, para 54). This statement is supported by E2: “...I think we have to separate the commercial shipping, so the deep-sea shipping, we have to separate that from the short sea. Because the deep-sea, that is a completely different business model.” (T2, para 66). The routes of operation are mentioned several times by experts as determining compliance costs. A particular focus is put on how much of their time shipping companies spend within the North and Baltic Sea ECAs.

Further categories of company characteristics influencing compliance costs will only be described in short, as they were of lesser importance to experts. 21 statements could be identified pertaining to **vessel building specifications**. Of specific importance to compliance costs with MEL are the available space and the specific layout of the company vessels. “That is certainly another question: Do I at all have the space on my vessels - and that would certainly depend on each type of ship...”, an expert comments (T3, para 68, see also T8, para 289). Another adds that technology implementation challenges are “quite ship specific – again, the age of the ship, the space available on board, and all that.” (T2, para 92, see also T6, para 159). “Thus we need to evaluate ship-specifically how big the tanks need to be, how the pipes need to be positioned and what we need to change.”, E7 explains (T7, para 63), “...with some vessels the effort may be higher and with others lower. [...] some ballast water tanks may be better accessible and then such a system may be simpler to install, with others it may be more difficult. With some vessels you need to do more maybe in order to get them sulphur-ready, well now with the other fuel, with others it is less.” (T7, para 195, see also T10, para 26). Building specifications influencing compliance costs are often related to vessel size: “An LNG tank would have to be much, much bigger than an oil tank that is clear, because the volume is very different. How one wants to put that into practice on small ships, without afterwards sailing about without cargo I do not know yet.”, an interviewee reasons (T11, para 268). For some vessels, especially vessels with notable space limitations, compliance with MEL may prove to be costlier than for others.

The **main seat of operations**, experts argue, may also influence company-specific costs of environmental legislation. E2 argues that for characterising a company, their jurisdiction of main operations is much more significant than the flag state: “...it is nationalities, not necessarily the flag, it is the domicile of the company. It is the Greek owners, the Chinese, Japanese, German owners...” (T2, para 122). The owner’s nationality may play a role for costs of MEL, as it may link back to compliance. E8 argues: “Russian oil tankers are evidently a problem. That is well known.” (T8, para 227). He goes on explaining: “If they fly a Russian flag or have the one of Liberia glued on is largely irrelevant, but the vessel is coming from Russia.” (T8, para 231). Scepticism about the environmental behaviour specifically of Russian shipowners is shared by E10: “Russian companies certainly have a different approach, partly. (Laughing) How shall I say that? I cannot say: Hey, corruption simply does play a role in Russia that is how it is.” (T10, para 139). Another expert voices similar scepticism with regards to Chinese shipping companies: “European shipping companies are very, very clearly focused on complying with that. That I do believe, yes. And how that is with the Chinese... I don’t know. They theoretically also need to comply with that and will also do that more or less...” (T9, para 123). E10 shares these doubts, stating: “Thus, we are fighting against the Chinese, who partly operate on the local market. We will never be able to reach them competitively, because they are simply operating without laws, because they never see another harbour than China. And China will not hurt China.” (T10, para 223). “...if you have the SECA area and clearly those of us who operate in the SECA area as well - if it is the European one or the U.S. one - will be aware of all the requirements. But whether your operators that are predominantly based outside of the SECA area - they may not be fully familiar with what the requirements are inside.”, another expert articulates doubts about the behaviour of shipping companies with their main seat of operations outside the EU or USA (T5, para 109). Differing approaches of shipping companies towards compliance will be rendered less relevant with effective port state control, however. E8 brings forward the argument that the main seat of operations would influence the possibilities of shipping companies to cope with MEL, stating: “...we now get into a situation in this year, next year at the latest, where the majority of the German fleet, that is the fleet operated by German shipping companies – they do not fly German flags anymore anyways –, are successively going bankrupt.” (T8, para 40).

Shipping companies may be differently affected by MEL depending on their current **financial situation**. Investing in environmental technology may be difficult, an expert explains: “...it is very difficult, if you do not have a lot of investors up your sleeve that say: We will do that, we are very patient. Then you are in a very lucky position. If you have a financing bank like the Commerzbank [German ship financing bank] they will say: Never again! Shipping! Help! Get out of here! In that case it is difficult.” (T6, para 234). This statement is supported by E7, stating: “Especially with the current banking crisis that one may observe. Thus, one could certainly say that if a vessel is financed to a hundred per cent and further follow-up financing is needed then the highly indebted shipowner may run into a bigger problem.” (T7, para 161). E8 argues that shipping companies who have not earned money in recent years and have not been able to build up reserves struggle the most to finance compliance with environmental laws (T8, para 305, see also T10, para 131; T6, para 232). Some experts hint that there might be interdependencies among company characteristics, as between company size and financial situation: “... smaller shipowners or rather shipowners that have their vessels financed close to a hundred per cent get

into trouble, simply because they do not receive further credit lines for the additional costs.”, E7 states (T7, para 161). E11 supports the link between size and financial means, stating: “Whereas it evidently is more difficult to make investments for a small shipping company with a thin capitalisation than for a company like Hapag Lloyd for example.” (T10, para 206). E8 agrees: “Those that are relatively well present in the committees still have it the easiest, because they know about developments early on. That means they COULD set aside reserves in time, could set up accruals, at least to absorb the risk, the financial risk with reserves in the accounts of the previous years, if the fiscal authorities play along.” (T8, para 307). Although based on a limited number of nine codings, experts unanimously declare that strained finances will lead to cash-strapped companies being more affected by environmental laws than companies with abundant resources.

The last three codes identified via qualitative content analysis relate to the **choice of classification society, portfolio of customers, and ownership structure**. “The classification society, as I said, the class is... does not play a role anymore.” (T10, para 47), an expert states. The classification society is involved in certifying the technical compliance of vessels and provides various services to shipping companies. The influence on compliance costs is seen as limited or non-existent by experts, however (see T2, para 35; T6, para 58; T6, para 163 et sqq.). Customers, on the other hand, are seen as a crucial influencing factor by the few experts who mention them. (T8, para 219; on the importance of customers see also T7, para 18). “...the chemical industry, the car industry is relatively strict. The chemical industry is very brutal on that issue [environmental legislation].” (T8, para 223), an expert argues. The expert describes customers as an effective measure of control: “...you can achieve a lot more that way than with governmental controls.” (T8, para 225). Lastly, the ownership structure of the company may influence the effect of MEL on shipping companies. State ownership may lead to increased investments in environmental technology, an expert argues: “...they are obviously partly state-owned enterprises, well in parts state-owned enterprises, and therefore alone they certainly also have a higher sense of responsibility for the compliance with environmental legislation.” (T3, para 72). E7 argues that it would also make a difference whether a vessel owner would operate their own vessels or whether they would be operated by a charterer (T7, para 77). E8 supports this view, stating: “...there is maybe the one or the other shipowner who acts within the system with more care on the whole, because the vessels also belong to him personally...” (T8, para 137). These last codes, however, were only mentioned by a limited number of experts and would have to be studied further to investigate their relevance for compliance costs.

5.5 Chapter summary and conceptual framework

Qualitative content analysis of expert interviews shows the concepts of most importance to industry experts and highlights their perceptions on compliance costs with MEL. Experts widely agree that operational and investment costs of shipping companies will increase due to environmental legislation, but that it will depend largely on the specific law in question. Regarding freight rates, opinions are divided on how strong economic effects are likely to be. Also, perceptions on modal shift are mixed. Expert interviews prove relevant in providing extensive information on determinants of compliance costs. One issue being widely discussed by experts during the interviews and almost entirely neglected by previous economic studies is

compliance with MEL. The researcher did originally not expect this issue to be of great importance, but the vast number of codings on issues of compliance prove the significance to industry experts. By the logic of inductive data collection, it is thus also becoming a concept to be included in quantitative data collection. Expert interviews further revealed a set of company characteristics that could influence compliance costs. A conceptual framework was developed from qualitative data, showing the main codes of relevance to industry specialists and the relations uncovered among them. This framework is shown in Figure 5-12 and includes the main concepts to be further investigated and quantified by way of quantitative data analysis.

Figure 5-12: Conceptual framework based on qualitative data analysis

6 Findings from quantitative data

6.1 Introduction

Quantitative data analysis serves to numerically test the conceptual framework developed from qualitative data in line with a sequential mixed methods design. The sample consisted of shipping companies with a seat of operation in countries adjoining the North and/or Baltic Sea. A total number of 896 contact persons from 829 companies could be identified fitting the sampling criteria. A full list of contact details can be found in Annex C4. With 121 self-completion questionnaires received, the **response rate was 14.6%**, however, not all companies provided data on all 129 items. Further statistics on participation can be found in Table 6-1. Data was collected using different scales of measurement depending on the type of information to be gathered but was mostly categorical. Formatting and data cleaning took place in Microsoft Excel to prepare for analysis in SPSS, R and SmartPLS. Data was in parts recoded to prepare for subsequent analyses.

Questionnaire opened	Consent to participate given	First block of questions answered	Full 12-page questionnaire answered
229 companies	149 companies	121 companies	38 companies

Table 6-1: Statistics on questionnaire participation

6.2 Effects of maritime environmental legislation

6.2.1 Effects on compliance costs

Data on the specific costs of each environmental protection measure was provided by a mere nineteen of the 121 companies in the sample. Statistical analysis proves insufficient for such a small dataset, as it yields no robust results. As six datasets showed further significant inconsistencies the remaining thirteen are presented here. The cases presented serve to widen the understanding of the complexity of compliance costs by describing the effect of maritime environmental legislation on two handfuls of specific, individual (but unnamed) shipping companies. Reading the cases alongside the results from quantitative analysis helps to balance statistical results with individual experiences to achieve a more comprehensive picture. Relevant data can be found in Annex C8 for reference. Analysis of the 13 sample companies shows that the share of compliance costs of total costs differs largely among companies, amounting to merely 2% in Case 2, but reaching 39% in Case 8, with an average of 11.6% and a mean of 9% across all cases. It becomes apparent from the data, that compliance costs tend to be significant in specific years where large investments are made. This can be observed in Case 1, where a scrubber for €800,000 is being installed in 2016, in case 4, where a new anti-fouling paint is acquired for the vessel amounting to €45,000 and 93% of expenses for compliance in that year, and in Case 10, where investments into a ballast water treatment system amount to €750,000 and 95% of overall compliance costs in 2016. Another observation can be made in that, depending on business model, some companies do not pay for fuel themselves and thus work with a very different cost structure (compare cases 4 and 5).

Companies were supposed to both to provide their actual costs in 2016 (the last full year before the study was conducted) of complying with each environmental measure, and to rank

environmental measures by their overall costs for the company in the past (2015-2017) and in the future (2018-2022). Interestingly, in several cases the data on costs provided does not match the ranking, indicating that actual costs paid and perceptions on which measures were the costliest, differed. Depending on the specific case at hand, four types of legislation accounted for the most expensive measure in 2016. While in one case anti-fouling and in another legislation on CO₂ emissions were the costliest, payments for compliance with sulphur and ballast water legislation were highest in six cases each. Six companies spend between 29% and 71% of overall environmental compliance costs on sulphur legislation, amounting to values between 1 and 25% of overall vessel costs. The six companies spending the largest amount on ballast water legislation paid between 27 and 96% of overall environmental compliance costs in 2016 towards the investment in and operation of ballast water management systems. Where full vessel costs were given in comparison, these payments amounted to 3-4% of all costs for the vessel in 2016.

Description of the cases

Case 1 is a Danish owner-operator of a small number of RoRo-/RoPax-vessels active exclusively in the North and Baltic Sea emission control areas. The vessels operate on fixed routes and have scrubbers installed to comply with sulphur legislation. In addition, they use batteries as a mode of power supply to increase engine efficiency and decrease power uptake during operations. Voyage costs, including fuel costs, account for 25% of overall expenses of the company. Complying with environmental legislation accounted for **six percent** of the overall annual vessel costs. The most expensive piece of legislation were laws on air pollution, where the investment in a scrubber cost €800,000 for one ship in 2016, plus an additional €60,000 in annual operation costs. Adhering to legislation on the release of oily water cost €455,000 for a single vessel in 2016 (or 26% of total compliance costs); the treatment of sewage water cost €365,000 (or 21% of total compliance costs) respectively. In terms of future expectations, the environmental manager of the company claims that upcoming laws on CO₂ emissions are going to prove the costliest of all measures for the company until 2022.

A Danish owner-operator of a larger number of specialised cargo carriers (between 20 and 49) is described in **Case 2**. The vessels spend a mere 20% of their time within emission control areas. They are entirely active in tramp operations. Expenses for the day-to-day running of the ships, i.e. crew, stores, and maintenance, account for the largest share of costs to the owner, amounting to 44% of total costs followed by 37% for voyage costs, including fuel. The environmental manager within the company names only two types of compliance costs that are of importance for the company, namely costs for the operation on low sulphur fuel and investment and operation costs for ballast water treatment. With €400,000 for a single vessel in 2016, low sulphur fuel accounts for 61% of total compliance costs; ballast water treatment account for the remaining 39%, made up of €250,000 investment costs and €10,000 operation costs for the vessel in question. Compared to the total expenses for said vessel in 2016, compliance with environmental legislation accounts for a mere **two percent** of overall costs.

Case 3 describes a German owner-operator of a medium-sized fleet of 10-19 bulk carriers. The vessels are comparably young with an average age of less than 10 years. They operate almost exclusively within the North and Baltic Sea ECAs (90% of the time) and are exclusively active in tramp operations. For an exemplary vessel, the company paid €45,000 in compliance costs in 2017, compared to €500,000 in total vessel costs. Compliance with MEL thus accounts for **nine percent** of total costs. The most expensive measure was ballast water treatment, accounting for 33% of total compliance costs and 3% of the overall vessel costs in 2016. This measure was followed by expenses for oily water treatment and anti-fouling paints. The environmental manager within the company is most concerned about ballast water legislation in the period up to 2022, naming both the significant investment costs and the high maintenance costs as reasons.

A small container vessel owner-operator with one or two vessels is described in **Case 4**. The German company operates its vessels almost exclusively on liner services outside of emission control areas (only 10% of time in spend in tramp operations; the same hold true for operations within ECAs). The environmental manager states that non-TBT-anti-fouling paints have accounted for the largest share of environmental compliance costs in the year 2016, amounting to €45,000 for the vessel in question, equalling 93% of total compliance costs for that year. It has to be noted that the company does not incur the voyage costs of the vessels and thus does not proclaim any expenses to comply with sulphur legislation. Minor sums were spent on waste disposal and sewage water treatment. Compared to the total vessel costs of €1.2 million in 2016, compliance costs amounted to roughly **four percent** of total costs. In response to questions on future expenses, the environmental manager stated that he expected the costs for ballast water treatment to outpace all other compliance costs for the period up to 2022.

Case 5 deals with a very large container operator, who has more than 50 vessels under operation in time charter. The German company is exclusively active in liner operations and the vessels spent a mere 20% of their time in emission control areas, which accounts for the use of low sulphur fuel by the entire fleet as a means to comply with sulphur legislation. With an average vessel age of less than 10 years, the fleet is rather young. The environmental manager states that the company does not pay the fuel bill, thus compliance costs for fuel are not considered in cost calculations. In terms of future expectations, the manager explains that ballast water will be the most expensive measure for the company for the period up to 2022. He argues that he is not necessarily worried about upcoming environmental laws, as technical solutions are available and may be implemented into the fleet, but that he is rather worried about an agreement of sustainable rates necessary to perform mandatory investments.

A large owner-operator of both bulk and specialised cargo carriers is described in **Case 6**. The company owns between 20 and 49 rather young vessels with an average age below 10 years, which they operate a mere 20% of the time inside emission control areas. The central management is located in Denmark and the vessels are employed in on-demand tramp operations 70% of the time. Compliance with sulphur legislation is both achieved with switching to low-sulphur fuel and with ethanol propulsion. Environmental officers within the company state that they are currently and will be in the future hardest hit by air pollution legislation. In 2016, the bulk carrier paid 29% of vessel compliance costs for low-sulphur operations. This amounted to 3% of total vessel costs. Overall, all environmental measures

combined have accumulated to **nine percent** of overall operational costs for a representative vessel in 2016, or €35,000 out of €400,000.

Case 7 deals with a small operator of bulk carriers without any own assets. The company operates 3-9 vessels, which are on average older than 10, but younger than 20 years. The central management is located in Finland and the company is active exclusively in liner operations inside ECAs. Sulphur compliance is achieved by purchasing MGO. Despite the organisation's claim that CO₂ is currently and will be in the future the costliest of all environmental measures, the environmental manager has not provided any data on costs they are currently incurring from CO₂ legislation. Instead, 71% of total compliance costs and 10% of total vessel costs have gone towards acquiring low sulphur fuel. Compliance costs have amounted to €140,000 for a single vessel. If total vessel costs are taken into account, compliance accounts for **14% of overall costs** in 2016, meaning that other environmental measures are of minor importance.

The company in **case 8** is a large owner-operator of more than 50 container vessels with an average age of less than 10 years. The company is located in Germany and active in non-ECA liner operations 90% of the time. They are a member of an industry association and comply by switching to low-sulphur fuel. The company estimates the total annual costs for a vessel at roughly €2.4 million, stating that of these costs of environmental compliance amounted to €969,000 in 2016, or **39% of total vessel costs**. By far the most expensive measure were low-sulphur operations, amounting to €600,000 annually, or 65% of total compliance costs, followed by costs of €300,000 for anti-fouling measures. The numbers provided by the company should be treated cautiously, as it seems unlikely that a company operating merely 10% of the time inside emission control areas would incur additional costs amounting to 25% of overall vessel costs for low sulphur operations. The numbers seem particularly high compared to other companies, like the operator in case 7, which are active exclusively within ECAs.

Case 9 describes an owner-operator of more than 50 bulk and crude carriers. These rather young vessels of less than 10 years spend 70% of their time on average within ECAs and 100% in tramp operations. The industry-association-member is located in Norway and has chosen low sulphur fuel as the preferred method of compliance. For this company, compliance with air pollution legislation is currently and will in the future be the most expensive measure, the environmental officer states. In 2016, the company spend €500,000 on low sulphur fuel for a single vessel, amounting to 50% of overall compliance costs. These costs were followed by €100,000 annual operation costs for ballast water, carbon dioxide, and oily water measures. Total compliance costs reached €1 million for a single vessel in a year.

Case 10 is a medium-sized owner-operator of specialised cargo vessels. The company owns between 10 and 19 vessels, while it operates others under time charter. The vessels are on average between 10 and 20 years of age and are active 80% of the time in tramp operations. The central management of the company, which operates 40% within ECAs, is located in the United Kingdom. In 2016, ballast water treatment was by far the costliest environmental measure, accounting for 95% of total compliance costs. This may be explained with a €750,000 investment in a ballast water treatment system for the vessel in question. The environmental

manager within the company expects ballast water treatment to remain the most expensive measure for the company up until 2022.

An owner-operator of 20-49 general cargo ships with its main seat of operations in Germany is described in **case 11**. The company operates its vessels aged 10-20 years on average exclusively within ECAs and 70% of the time in tramp operations. With 27% of total compliance costs, the operation and investment into ballast water treatment was the most expensive environmental measure in 2016, alongside carbon dioxide legislation, which accounted for another 27% of total compliance costs. No indication is given, what kind of measures were taken here. The environmental manager stated that the ships were running on low sulphur fuel but did not provide data on additional costs linked to this measure in 2016, meaning that data is either inconsistent or the company incurred no additional costs, which may well be the case due to a supportive development in fuel prices. The company expects ballast water treatment to remain the most expensive measure until 2022.

Case 12 describes a small bulk and specialised cargo carrier located in the Netherlands. The company is owner-operator of 5-9 vessels aged less than 10 years on average. The fleet, operated on low sulphur fuel, spends 90% of its time within emission control areas and 100% in tramp operations. Data provided by the environmental manager is inconsistent, as he or she states that sewage water treatment was the most expensive measure for the company between 2015 and 2017, while company data on environmental compliance costs shows investments in ballast water treatment in 2016 to have had the greatest effect on compliance costs. Compliance costs for all environmental measures account for **10% of overall vessel costs** with ballast water treatment as the most expensive measure, reaching 4% of total vessel costs. In terms of compliance costs, ballast water legislation makes for 44% of the total sum, followed by waste with 24% and sewage water with 16%. The manager expects ballast water legislation to remain the most expensive measure in the years to come.

Lastly, **case 13** deals with a Norwegian owner-operator of 3 to 9 bulk and general cargo ships aged less than 10 years on average. The owner-operator has his ships running 90% of the time in tramp operations and 80% within ECAs. In 2016, investments in ballast water treatment accounted for 96% of total compliance costs for a vessel, while the environmental manager states that between 2015 and 2017 air pollution was the costliest measure and will only be replaced by ballast water in the period 2018-2022. Despite operations on low sulphur fuel, the company states not to have incurred any additional costs from the measure in 2016.

It can be seen from the cases that compliance cost structures differ significantly among shipping companies. Compliance costs exceeding 15% of overall vessel costs could only be found for one single company (Case 8), where the share of 39% recorded can be considered a clear outlier compared to all other company cases. In five cases compliance costs between 5% and 15% of total vessel costs were recorded. For these companies, moderate effects of MEL could be noticed, but no significant danger of reduced competitiveness towards other transport modes became apparent. In two cases, compliance costs amounted to less than 5% of overall vessel costs, indicating that they might not have the magnitude to significantly influence profitability or business decisions of the company in question. A critical effect of MEL on the business of these companies is deemed unlikely.

6.2.2 Effects on costs of shipping companies

Data analysis is based on the definitions of effect sizes developed in Chapter 3.7 and presented in Table 3-5. Moderate effects of MEL on the industry are expected where increases in voyage costs surpass 20% and increases in total costs surpass 5%. Critical effects are likely where costs increase by 50% or 15% respectively. Quantitative data analysis shows that past increases in fuel costs were not critical to the industry, nor are future increases likely to be. Moderate effects on the industry can be expected from increases in total costs.

Company information on changes in total and voyage costs experienced since January 2015 until the date of data collection (which amounted to some time between October 2017 and February 2018) and expectations for future voyage cost developments for the period 2018-2022 were analysed. Voyage costs consist mostly of fuel costs, even though they also include canal dues and harbour fees. Histograms of cost developments may be found in Annex D2. It can be seen that all three distributions are negatively skewed with the distribution for expected voyage cost developments scattered to the right even more prominently than the other distributions. It becomes evident from the graphs, that shipping companies experienced and expect to experience rather an increase than a decrease in their overall and voyage costs. In Figure 6-1 cost data has been aggregated into a single diagram to allow for comparisons. As shown, decreases in total or voyage costs were experienced by only a small number of companies amounting to 7.2% and 8.7% of the sample respectively. One single respondent claimed that he had experienced an increase in voyage costs by more than 20% in the period 2015-2017, leaving 99% of the sample to experience lower increases or even decreases in voyage costs. Applying the definition of moderate and critical effects to voyage costs, it becomes apparent that the stricter sulphur limits of 2015 did not have a critical effect on the shipping industry. With regards to future expectations of fuel price developments, 8.7% of shipping companies expect increases of more than 20% over the coming four years; an increase of more than 50% was not explicitly studied. An at least moderate effect is thus only expected by a very small group of companies, while most shipping companies expect only negligible increases in voyage costs below 20%, which are unlikely to significantly affect competitiveness towards other transport modes to the effect that modal shift or reduced trade volumes become statistically significant.

Increases in total costs by more than 5% between 2015 and 2017 were witnessed by 56% of the sample, likely associated with moderate effects on trade, while less than 2% of companies experienced a critical increase of more than 20%. The increase in total costs may but does not have to be due to environmental legislation. Interestingly, increases in total costs experienced were quite similar to increases in voyage costs experienced, meaning that a large share of total cost increases could not be explained by increases in fuel costs, but had to have other causes. Linking to data discussed below, preparatory investments in ballast water legislation could be one source of cost increases.

Figure 6-1: Development of total and voyage costs, n=69 (2015-2022)

Spearman correlations were calculated to determine whether the developments in voyage costs or total company costs showed relationships with company characteristics determined from the questionnaires. Results of these calculations may be found in Annex D3. It becomes apparent that total costs are only correlated at a statistically significant level of $p=0.04$ with the average age of vessels employed, whereas the correlation is moderately positive with a value of 0.26. Companies employing older assets seem to experience slightly higher increases in total costs than companies employing younger vessels. All other company characteristics collected, namely company size, type of vessels employed, share of tramp operations, share of ECA operations, and industry association membership, are not correlated to cost developments at a statistically significant level. Whether decreases or increases in total and voyage costs were witnessed by the company seems to depend on the specific organisation in question and is not related to a particular group of companies.

An analysis of ranked data provided by shipping companies shows that ballast water legislation has potentially the most critical effect on the industry, followed by air pollution legislation on SO_2 and NO_x emissions and thirdly legislation on CO_2 emissions. Rankings provided by 51 shipping companies on the associated costs for the company of eight environmental protection aims for the years 2015-2017 are considered here, as well as expected associated costs for the period 2018-2022 (compare questions 13 and 14 of the questionnaire). Were only some items were ranked, the missing items were all classified with “8” (least expensive). The table below shows the cost effect of each measure calculated from the simple average of the reverse rank. It becomes apparent that mandatory ballast water treatment systems are currently deemed the most expensive measure, with their effect on costs expected to increase even further in the years 2018-2022. This measure is followed by planned air pollution reductions, specifically reductions in SO_2 and NO_x emissions, as well as emissions of CO_2 , with both political aims increasing in importance for cost calculations within the companies. Other measures such as environmental protection from leaks of oily water, non-toxic anti-fouling paints, and proper treatment of waste and sewage water, are losing in importance for the shipping companies and may not be regarded as having critical effects upon the industry. Currently the least costly

measure is noise pollution, with currently no legislation in place, but first tentative discussions at the IMO to include measures into the MARPOL framework. Accordingly, companies overall expect a slightly increased bearing of noise pollution measures on compliance costs, with it overall staying the least expensive measure, however.

	Cost effect (2015-2017)	Expected cost effect (2018-2022)	Trend
Ballast water	5.0	6.1	
Air pollution	4.7	5.4	
CO2	4.1	4.9	
Oily water	3.3	2.2	
Antifouling	2.9	2.2	
Waste	2.6	1.9	
Sewage water	2.4	1.9	
Noise pollution	0.5	0.7	

* Cost effect calculated from simple average of reverse rank

Table 6-2: Current and expected cost effects of MEL by legislative aim

6.2.3 Effects on freight rates of shipping companies

A section of the questionnaire was dedicated to current and future freight rate developments. The development of freight rates in the years 2015 to 2017 and information on which factors had the largest influence on freight rates were explored. Also, companies were surveyed for their future expectations. Questions were based on a freight rate model as developed from qualitative data, which may be found in Annex D4. Tabular data on freight rate developments including variances and standard deviations is shown in Annex D5.

Figure 6-2 shows the freight rate development of 19 shipping companies over the period of 18 months from April 2015 to October 2017. Most companies in the sample chose either not to submit data or submitted inconsistent data that had to be eliminated from the analysis. It becomes apparent from the figure that freight rate developments vary widely among companies, both in terms of variability over time as well as direction of change. While the standard deviation for company H lies at 0.0, indicating no change in freight rates over the entire period, company S exhibits a standard deviation of 42.8 with freight rates fluctuating between 23% of the January 2015 level in June of the same year and 144% of the January 2015 level in October 2017. Examining the vessel types employed by the companies in question does not lead to coherent results. Specialised cargo carriers seem somewhat less prone to fluctuations in freight rates, while fluctuations in the crude carrier business seemed particularly prominent, but due to limited sample size these findings might be circumstantial. Within the bulker and container business, some companies have experienced great fluctuations, others rather stable rates. It is notable from the graph that during the 18 months after the introduction of stricter sulphur regulations, all but five companies of the 19 in the sample have experienced decreases in freight rates, on average by 23.8%. A single company indicated entirely stable rates, while the four reporting increasing rates witnessed average increases over the period in question by 24.8%. Judging by these numbers it seems that increased costs from maritime environmental legislation have not led to cost-induced increases in freight rates.

Figure 6-2: Freight rate developments April 2015-October 2017, $n=19$

These findings are supported by data collected from 35 shipping companies ranking six different determinants by the influence they perceived them to have on freight rates. Environmental legislation was one category among five others, namely ‘changes in demand for transport capacity’, ‘changes in labour costs’, ‘changes in fuel costs (dependent on market developments)’, ‘changes in cargo-handling costs’, and the catch-all category ‘other costs’, with the option to specify further cost factors influencing freight rates. Figure 6-3 shows the aggregated results of the ranking organised by ranks 1-6. Nearly 80% of companies indicate that the demand for transport capacity is the single most influential factor on freight rates, followed by roughly 10% of companies believing environmental legislation to play the largest role. ‘Other costs’ was placed on rank 6 by almost half of the companies. A further helpful indicator is the average rank of determinants. With an average rank of 1.5 ‘changes in demand for transport capacity’ is again deemed to determine freight rates to the greatest extent, followed by market-induced changes in fuel costs with an average rank of 2.3. Environmental legislation obtains the third place with an average rank of 3.7. The remaining three determinants have very similar average rankings between 4.1 and 4.4 and are thus deemed equally irrelevant for freight rate developments.

Figure 6-3: Ranking of factors by their influence on freight rates 2015-2018, n=35

Keeping in mind that environmental laws are deemed to have only a minor influence on freight rates, expected freight rate changes for the years 2018-2022 will still be reported here. As can be seen in Figure 6-4, only one company of the 34 providing data on this question is expecting a moderate decrease in freight rates for the period in question. While 23.5% expect a no-change scenario, the remaining three-quarters of shipping organisations believe in freight rate increases, with a substantial share of 44% of companies expecting freight rates to increase by more than 10%. As these expectations might or might not be linked to more costly environmental laws, they are, however, of limited value to the current study.

Figure 6-4: Expected freight rate development 2018-2022, n=34

6.3 Effectiveness of incentives

6.3.1 Significance of environmental legislation

Data analysis shows that environmental legislation is significant for decision-making within companies, but a large spread exists across the industry. Based on findings from qualitative content analysis of expert interviews, individual motivations of decision-makers were deemed to play a role for compliance behaviour and thus for the effectiveness of environmental incentives. Companies rated the significance of environmental legislation for decision-making

within their company on a 10-point Likert scale from ‘not important at all’ to ‘very important’ (see Question 21 of questionnaire). Figure 6-5 shows that most companies rate the significance of environmental legislation for decision-making within their company high or very high, while a limited number of companies accounting for 21.3% of the sample would rank the significance of MEL for internal decision-making at 5 or lower on the 10-point scale.

Figure 6-5: Significance of maritime environmental legislation for decision-making within the shipping company on a 10-point Likert scale, n=47

Regression analysis was conducted to determine whether any of the company characteristics inquired for in the survey (company size, owner type, type of operations, area of operations, association membership, and average age of vessels) could explain how significant MEL was for decision-making within a company. As becomes apparent from Table 6-3, solely owner type could significantly explain rankings on the 10-point Likert scale with a p-value of 0.03. The negative correlation between ‘owner type’ and ‘significance of maritime environmental legislation’ was established further with a Spearman’s rho of -0.34 with p=0.02. Other company characteristics showed no significant linear relationship with the variable in question.

Simple linear regressions on significance of environmental legislation			Coefficients		Statistical significance x	
Regression	x	y	Intercept	β	t-value	p-value
lmsize	Company size	SignificanceLegislation	2.13625	-0.03484	-0.8	0.428
lowner	Owner type	SignificanceLegislation	2.16392	-0.09788	-2.327	0.0247 *
lmeca	Area of operations	SignificanceLegislation	0.665367	0.000078	0.004	0.9969
lmtramp	Type of operations	SignificanceLegislation	1.03248	-0.05373	-1.96	0.0562
lmassoc	Association membership	SignificanceLegislation	0.90917	0.02323	1.3	0.2
limage	Average vessel age	SignificanceLegislation	1.8367	-0.02939	-0.774	0.443
*Significant at the 0.05 level						

Table 6-3: Simple linear regressions on significance of environmental legislation

A scatterplot depicting the relationship between the significance of environmental laws and owner type can be seen in Figure 6-6. Owners with limited operations seem to feel that environmental laws are of reduced importance to them. This can be explained with the fact that a subset of legal rules, like sulphur legislation, is mainly concerned with the operation of vessels and is thus of moderate consequence to pure vessel owners. A similar argument may be made

6.3.2 Compliance rates for maritime environmental legislation

Figure 6-7 shows the compliance rate by type of pollution as developed from questionnaire data. Not all measures depicted in the graph were mandatory at the time the survey was conducted. Notably, the two measures exhibiting the lowest estimate of compliance rates – legislation on sewage and ballast water treatment – were not mandatory in the spring of 2017 and are depicted here chiefly to show the difference between estimates for mandatory and non-mandatory measures. The estimated compliance rates for the four legally prescribed measures show a somewhat similar distribution, with a large share of companies believing compliance within the industry to be above 95%.

Figure 6-7: Estimated legal compliance rates by type of pollution for the North and Baltic Sea areas, $n=37$

For some types of pollution, noncompliance levels are estimated to be higher on average than for other types of pollution. Table 6-4 shows the share of shipping companies who suggested that the compliance rate for a certain measure would lie below 95% (that is below full compliance) or even below 70%. In line with the theory of indirect questioning, these findings may give some indication of the company's own behaviour. Where a partaker in the survey rates industry-wide compliance to be very low, that company is likely to be noncompliant on occasion itself. A share of 35-43% of companies indicate that they trust in the existence of noncompliance when it comes to environmental measures, judging from their indications that compliance on mandatory measures may be below 95%. The remaining 57% to 65% indicate that they believe all shipping companies in the North and Baltic Sea areas always to act in line with environmental laws, however. These companies are unlikely to be noncompliant themselves. A small number of companies accounting for some 10-15% of the sample estimate compliance rates for all mandatory measures to be below 70%. These companies are likely to be noncompliant at least occasionally, following the theory of indirect questioning. This noncompliance rate seems to be in line with the 5-15% estimated by experts at the interview stage and by the OECD study (OECD, 2003). For a company judging compliance with a certain measure to be between 81 and 90%, for example, it is difficult to infer whether that company

tends to breach the law itself. Indirect questioning is no exact science but rather a tool to provide rough indications, where direct questions would not yield reliable answers.

	Compliance Sulphur	Compliance Oil	Compliance Waste	Compliance TBT
Less than 95%	43%	35%	43%	39%
Less than 70%	11%	14%	14%	17%

Table 6-4: Estimated compliance levels for mandatory legal measures for shipping on the North and Baltic Seas, n=37

6.3.3 Drivers of compliance with maritime environmental legislation

6.3.3.1 Path model with latent variables

Determinants of compliance identified from literature research and expert interviews constitute complex concepts that are defined here as latent or unobservable variables. These constructs may not be directly measured but must be studied indirectly by using indicators. Proxy variables were created and combined to form a single composite score. Measurement error from poorly worded questions or misunderstandings was aimed to be reduced by using several items to measure a concept. A compliance index was computed from 5-point Likert scales, while data on compliance attitudes was measured on 4-point Likert scales, not allowing for a “middle option”, but forcing a taking of sides. Likert items of all attitude scales were symmetric around a middle item and equidistant and could thus be used in SEM (Hair, Jr. et al. 2018, 9). Control variables included were company size, area of operations, average vessel age and type of operations.

The researcher computed a compliance index from questionnaire data as shown in Figure 6-8. Projecting data from indirect questioning onto the companies themselves (method applied to deal with social desirability bias), a compliance index was calculated for each company. It must be noted that the underlying Likert-scale is not equidistant. The histogram shows a distribution with n=36, a mean of 4.04, a standard deviation of 1.144, and a non-normal distribution with a negative skew. The mean signifies that overall compliance levels were estimated to be around 95%. This finding is well in line with findings from prior studies and expert interviews. It becomes apparent, that although the vast majority of companies in the sample exhibit very high levels of compliance, a small group of outliers can be found at the left-hand side of the graph indicating low levels of compliance. Cronbach’s alpha is 0.791, indicating internal consistency of the scale.

Figure 6-8: Calculation of compliance index

A path model developed based on the theoretical framework can be found in Figure 6-9. Path models are widely applied to visualize variable relationships and hypotheses in structural equation modelling (Hair, Ringle, and Sarstedt 2011). Both measurement theory and structural theory are shown in the graph. In this context, a formative measurement model is applied to identify drivers of compliance. Multi-item scales are used to increase predictive validity in line with recommendations by Diamantopoulos et al. (Diamantopoulos et al. 2012). Cronbach’s Alpha was employed to determine reliable proxy variables. Indicators were eliminated until Cronbach’s Alpha exceeded 0.6, leading to the exclusion of some measurements from the questionnaire. ‘Individual motivations’ eventually relied on five indicators with a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.733, ‘Organisational capacities’ relied on four indicators with a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.638, and ‘Exterior determinants’ relied on four indicators with a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.601. The author refrained from regression analysis based on sum scores (i.e. determining latent variable scores from average values of indicators) for the concepts, as it cannot be assumed that indicator weights are equal. Instead, PLS was employed as described above.

Figure 6-9: Path model including both structural and measurement models on determinants of compliance, indicators included marked green

6.3.3.2 Compliance drivers

PLS-SEM was conducted as described above with results shown in Figure 6-10. Histograms of constructs show approximately bell-shaped symmetric curves, as can be seen in Annex D6. While PLS-SEM does not assume a certain data distribution, it is important to assure that data distribution is not extremely non-normal, as this would lead to difficulties in assessment of parameter weights. Skewness and kurtosis were used here to assess how data deviates from normality with a value lower than -1 or higher than +1 for both considered non-normal. The construct ‘Motivations’ is not normally distributed. The nonnormality of the construct stems from extremely non-normal distributions for indicators Ind_Morals1 and Ind_Morals2 as can be seen by their skewness and kurtosis. These indicators were thus eliminated from the set, leaving three indicators to explain the construct ‘Motivations’ with a healthy Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.771. Other indicators were not deleted, even if their outer loadings were slightly below 0.7, so as not to decrease content validity (Hair, Jr. et al., 2018, p.113), but the construct ‘Exterior determinants’ was split into the two concepts ‘Sanctions and Enforcement’ and ‘Human error/Higher forces’ to increase content validity. No indicator showed outer loadings below 0.3, as these had already been removed when considering Cronbach’s Alpha in preparing the data for analysis with PLS.

The R²-value of 0.441 shows that around 44.1% of variance in compliance behaviour may be explained by the exogenous latent variables. According to Ringle et al., this can be described as a moderate effect (Ringle, Sinkovics and Henseler, 2009). Model fit is thus far from perfect

but the model has moderate explanatory value. Not all path estimates are statistically significant. Path coefficients have standardised values between -1 and +1. Any value close to 0 shows a weak relationship that is usually not statistically significant. As an indication it can be assumed that values above 0.2 are significant, which only is the case for the concepts 'Organisational Capacities' with a path value of 0.613 and 'Sanctions and Enforcement' with a path value of 0.209. T-values and p-values determined through bootstrapping are shown in Table 6-5. With a p-value below 0.01, organisational capacities were significant at the 1% level, while sanctions and enforcement could not be shown to be statistically significant. As can be seen from the outer loadings, particularly the indicators Ind_Time and Ind_Network have high loading factors on the concept 'Organisational Capacities', indicating that a lack of time and a lack of a network with other companies might be significantly related to a lower level of compliance with environmental legislation. The remaining two concepts determined from expert interviews and literature review could not be found to show a statistically significant relation with compliance rates. Instead, other drivers must explain deviations in compliance levels. Similar to other latent constructs, no significant relation could be found among control variables and compliance.

No universal measure for model fit is known for PLS. Root mean square residual covariance (SRMR) is used as one measure of model fit here. The model has an SRMR-value of 0.127. A value of 0 generally indicates perfect fit, while a value below 0.08 indicates good fit when applied to CB-SEM models. Hair et al. argue, however, that this threshold is too low for PLS-SEM and propose applying a higher (though unspecified) threshold (Hair, Jr. et al., 2018, p.193). SRMR does not indicate very good model fit. RMSttheta is considered as a second measure of model fit with a value above 0.12 indicating a lack of fit. The value calculated in Smart PLS for the model at hand is $RMSttheta=0.246$. This second measure indicates poor model fit. Further analysis and changes in model specification seem thus necessary.

Figure 6-10: Results of PLS analysis on determinants of legal compliance

	Original Sampl...	Sample Mean (...)	Standard Devia...	T Statistics (O...	P Values
Area of operations -> Compliance	-0.066	-0.065	0.145	0.454	0.650
Average vessel age -> Compliance	0.011	0.046	0.247	0.046	0.963
Company size -> Compliance	0.024	-0.014	0.218	0.112	0.911
Human error/Higher forces -> Compliance	0.110	0.110	0.224	0.492	0.623
Motivations -> Compliance	0.123	0.079	0.258	0.479	0.632
Organizational capacities -> Compliance	0.613	0.581	0.228	2.683	0.008
Sanctions and Enforcement -> Compliance	0.209	0.212	0.160	1.303	0.193
Type of operations -> Compliance	0.057	0.076	0.183	0.311	0.756

Table 6-5: Results from bootstrapping on PLS analysis on determinants of legal compliance

6.3.3.3 Reliability analysis

Measures of construct reliability are shown in Table 6-6. As in this study new measures for concepts are developed, a Cronbach’s Alpha of close to 0.6 is deemed acceptable, in accordance with assessments by Nunnally (Nunnally, 1978) and Hair (Hair, Jr. et al., 2018, p.24). With well-defined constructs, a minimum of 0.7 is demanded to describe reliability. Composite reliability tends to overestimate reliability slightly, while Cronbach’s Alpha might underestimate reliability for the type of study at hand, involving Likert scales with few points. Hair et al. estimate that true reliability estimates lie somewhere between these indicators (Hair,

Jr. et al., 2018). Following that argument, concepts are shown to be reliable with composite reliability above 0.7 for all concepts and Cronbach's Alpha above or close to 0.6 for all concepts. These measures are comparable to other exploratory studies.

	Cronbach's Alpha	Rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance
Area of operations	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Average vessel age	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Company size	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Compliance	0.795	0.803	0.865	0.617
Human error/Higher forces	0.639	2.865	0.781	0.657
Motivations	0.779	0.943	0.863	0.681
Organisational capacities	0.595	0.692	0.748	0.399
Sanctions and enforcement	0.589	0.596	0.829	0.708
Type of operations	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 6-6: Measures of construct reliability

6.3.3.4 Owner type and compliance

The significance of environmental legislation for decision-making differed depending on the type of responsibilities a shipping company would hold, as has been shown above. As different perceptions towards environmental laws might influence compliance, the compliance index was tested here against the variable 'owner type'. Results may be seen in the boxplots in Figure 6-11. It becomes apparent that compliance levels tend to differ depending on ownership type. Companies owning vessels and operating these assets themselves tend to show higher levels of compliance than companies operating vessels but owning limited or no own assets. The last category "owner with limited operations" is build on one single observation and thus not deemed representative. An ETA value of 0.428 shows a moderate relationship between the variables with ETA squared of 0.183 showing roughly 18% of variation in compliance behaviour explained by owner type. With a p-value of 0.095, these findings are significant at the 10%, but not the 5% level. This result fits well with observations made during expert interviews, where a large shipping company suggested that they would make larger investments and take better care of assets they operated themselves than assets they offered on the market, thus increasing compliance levels of owner-operated vessels.

Figure 6-11: Boxplots showing the relationship between owner type and legal compliance

Further tests conducted made to determine whether compliance levels coincided with other company characteristics, but no correlation could be found between compliance behaviour and central management location or flag state. Company characteristics included in PLS analysis were retested and the Eta-values determined, leading to the findings that with an Eta-squared of 0.279 and a p-value of 0.006, average vessel age may explain roughly 28% of variance in compliance levels. It can be observed that companies operating older assets show on average lower levels of compliance than companies with particularly young vessels. Company size tested against the compliance index showed no significant correlation. Experts suggested that smaller companies with older assets would be more likely to be noncompliant. Testing this relationship, here as an example for the treatment of oily water, it can be seen in Figure 6-12 that small companies with older assets are assumed to follow mandatory laws on oily water in less than 70% of cases, while large companies with young assets are assumed to treat their oily water properly in more than 95% of cases. Statistical evaluation shows, however, that these findings depend entirely on average age and not on company size as influencing factor, as Eta between compliance and company size is very low at 0.11 and Eta-squared shows no explanatory power with a value of 0.000. Similarly, the type of operation (liner or tramp) may not significantly explain differences in compliance levels.

Figure 6-12: Company size and average age of vessels against mandatory treatment of oily water

Eta squared η^2 is defined here as the sums of squares for the effect of interest divided by the total sums of squares, or the proportion of total variability in the dependent variable accounted for by variation in the independent variable. To compare the results, values of Omega squared and Cohen’s f are given in addition. The only indicators that could individually – not part of a construct as above – explain levels of compliance at a statistically significant level were the indicators time, legal personnel, network, association, and apprehension. These indicators belong universally to the construct of organisational capacities, confirming the findings from PLS analysis, that this set of determinants is the only one among the three sets identified from literature and expert interviews to hold under statistical scrutiny. Of the statistically significant indicators, time has the largest explanatory value with an Eta squared of 0.301. When company employees do not find time to deal with legislative changes, noncompliance may occur. It must be noted that though the indicator financial resources could not be shown to be statistically significant for compliance, employing a larger number of staff or more qualified personnel might solve the issue of time, but would have a bearing on company finances.

Dependent variable	Independent variable	Eta squared	Omega squared	Cohen's f	p-value
Compliance Index 2	Indicator morals 1	0.049	0.02	0.227	0.194
Compliance Index 2	Indicator morals 2	0.044	0.015	0.213	0.222

Compliance Index 2	Indicator Importance	Env.	0.021	-0.007	0.147	0.398
Compliance Index 2	Indicator Environmental rank		0.025	-0.004	0.16	0.364
Compliance Index 2	Indicator reputation		0.038	0.009	0.198	0.256
Compliance Index 2	Indicator sales		0.013	-0.015	0.116	0.504
Compliance Index 2	Indicator price		0.001	-0.028	0.035	0.843
Compliance Index 2	Indicator cash/ financial resources		0	-0.029	0.013	0.942
Compliance Index 2	Indicator time		0.301	0.274	0.656	0.001
Compliance Index 2	Indicator personnel		0.081	0.052	0.296	0.093
Compliance Index 2	Indicator Uncertainty		0.012	-0.016	0.111	0.521
Compliance Index 2	Indicator network		0.185	0.157	0.476	0.009
Compliance Index 2	Indicator awareness		0.033	0.004	0.184	0.29
Compliance Index 2	Indicator apprehension		0.111	0.082	0.353	0.047
Compliance Index 2	Indicator association		0.121	0.093	0.372	0.037
Compliance Index 2	Indicator controls 1		0.059	0.031	0.251	0.152
Compliance Index 2	Indicator controls 2		0.055	0.026	0.241	0.169
Compliance Index 2	Indicator circumvention		0.02	-0.009	0.141	0.415
Compliance Index 2	Indicator technical		0	-0.028	0.01	0.954
Compliance Index 2	Indicator Human error		0.051	0.023	0.233	0.184
Compliance Index 2	Indicator Higher forces		0.002	-0.028	0.039	0.825

Table 6-7: Analysis of variance tests on indicators explaining levels of legal compliance

6.4 Differences among shipping companies

Differences in compliance levels influenced by company characteristics have been discussed above. Here, findings on differences in compliance costs based on company size, company type, ownership structure, average vessel age, area of operations, type of operations (liner or tramp),

flag state, location of central management, and industry association membership are discussed. A description of these characteristics as found in the sample as well as evidence on how these variables were classified for the purpose of evaluation can be found in Annex D7.

PLS analysis was conducted to determine whether development in total or voyage costs may be linked to certain company characteristics. Results may be found in Figure 6-13. It can be seen that a negligible share of the development both in total costs and compliance costs may be explained by company characteristics, roughly 8% and 3% respectively. This already gives an indication that the type of shipping company in question has little to do with the development in compliance costs said company experiences. No path reaches a value above 0.2, necessary to indicate a moderate relationship, thus it may be found that a relationship between company characteristics and compliance cost developments may not statistically be proven. As all latent constructs rely on a single indicator in these calculations, internal reliability is perfect with a Cronbach's Alpha for all constructs of 1.0. As may be expected from the results below, model fit is poor.

Figure 6-13: Results of PLS analysis for company characteristics and cost developments

6.5 Chapter summary

Analysis of survey data revealed that shipping companies were affected very differently by environmental legislation. This finding proved valid in terms of the overall amount of compliance costs, their share of total vessel costs and the measures driving costs the most. In the cases examined, compliance costs would make between 2 and 39% of overall vessel costs, being notably higher in years when large investments were made in environmental equipment, such as a ballast water management system or a full cleaning and new coating of the hull. The measures found to be driving compliance costs were first and foremost the installation of ballast water treatment systems, followed by low-sulphur legislation and measures on CO₂ reductions. Further analysis shows that increases in voyage costs between 2015 and 2017, which were expected by shipping experts and academic researchers prior to the introduction of the 0.1% sulphur cap, amounted to less than 20% for 99% of the companies in the sample. Based on these findings it seems unlikely that environmental laws would lead to voyage cost increases likely

to disrupt the competitive situation of the shipping industry vis à vis other transport modes. 8.7% of companies expect increases in voyage costs of more than 20% in the years 2018-2022, thus future moderate effects on modal choice and trade flows are possible in individual cases. Moderate increases in total costs, which may stem from environmental legislation as well as a variety of other sources, were witnessed by 56% of companies between 2015 and 2017. Here, effects on the competitive situation of the industry are likely. These increases may not be linked to increases in environmental compliance costs but it seems likely that where the industry faces increases in total costs as shown in Figure 6-1 and decreases in freight rates as shown in Figure 6-2, an expansion of costly environmental measures is likely to aggravate the industry's competitive situation. A ranking on determinants of freight rates shows that developments in the demand for transport capacity will be most influential on industry decision-making, followed by developments on the crude oil market. Environmental legislation ranks third, very close to all other remaining determinants, and seems thus similarly irrelevant for freight rate developments. The effect of environmental laws on costs may be found to be small to moderate, the effect on freight rates negligible.

With respect to the effectiveness of environmental laws, quantitative data suggested that most companies in the sample would rank the significance of legislation to be important or very important for decision-making within their company. These findings were particularly valid for shipping companies both owning and operating vessels, indicating that companies who carried a higher responsibility felt the need to act more responsibly. A small number of 21.3% of companies deemed environmental laws to be moderately to not at all significant. Estimated compliance rates mirror these findings with most companies believing compliance to be above 95% for mandatory measures. A small group of 10-15% of companies in the sample estimate compliance on mandatory environmental laws to be below 70%. Following the theory of indirect questioning, these companies are likely to be noncompliant themselves. These conclusions need to be qualified first by acknowledging that indirect questioning is an inexact science, helpful in overcoming social-desirability bias, but yielding results difficult to interpret. Secondly, as can be seen in Annex C7, companies deemed by experts to be particularly prone to noncompliant behaviour, that is flying grey or blacklisted flags, did choose not to take part in the survey, thus a slight underestimation of noncompliance levels is likely.

Lastly, qualitative findings on drivers of compliance were statistically evaluated. Study results show that organisational capacities of a shipping company, particularly available time to collect and apprehend legal information, a strong network with other companies, and membership in an industry association, are statistically significant and positively correlated with increased levels of compliance with maritime environmental legislation. All other constructs that were developed from expert interviews and prior studies could not be found to have statistically significant effects. These results are particularly striking in the case of controls and enforcement, which is traditionally seen as the main driver of compliance in economic theory. This driver, despite a significant loading factor on compliance, did not withstand statistical scrutiny of empirical data. The main research outcome is that companies with more resources at hand fare better in complying with environmental laws than companies with less available resources. These findings are, however, not statistically linked to company size, signifying that both larger and smaller shipping enterprises may be endowed with the necessary resources to

make for a law-abiding market player. It seems that legal compliance is something that a company must be able to afford and that a player may consciously invest in by investing in personnel specifically tasked with following legal developments and building up relations with other companies to exchange information on new laws. Also, paying for industry association membership and making use of both information and relations will be strongly correlated with environmental compliance.

7 Critical analysis and synthesis

7.1 Introduction

A critical analysis and synthesis of findings from qualitative and quantitative data analysis is conducted here. Insights gained were analysed by way of an interpretation outline tool as developed by Bloomberg and Volpe (Bloomberg and Volpe, 2012, p.174). This involved a structured process starting with the seeking of significant patterns among the findings, followed by the interpretation of these patterns and lastly synthesis and integration. The chapter is structured both by the original research questions and linked hypotheses that the researcher set out with as laid down in Chapter 1.7 and by synthesis findings based on the theoretical framework presented in Chapter 2.9. Due to the multi-method nature of this research, “significant” patterns have a double meaning here. While significant findings from quantitative data analysis are based on levels of confidence, significant findings from qualitative data analysis must fulfil demands of “substantive significance” as developed by Patton (Patton, 2002). These require that findings be solid and consistent, increase the understanding of the phenomenon under study, and be useful in contributing to building theory and informing policy or practice. Findings may both confirm or refute the existing body of knowledge, without having a bearing on their substantive significance. Critical analysis stems from the identification and discussion of lessons learned by the researcher. It is based on a systematic study of all sources of data, driven by a search for meaning and supported by discussions and debates with critical colleagues and advisors to add a variety of angles to the research. Synthesis finally provides a holistic view on the data and aims to paint an integrated picture of the research.

7.2 Critical analysis of hypothesis H₀₁: MEL has no significant effect on costs and freight rates of the shipping industry in the North and Baltic Sea areas

7.2.1 Measurable effects on costs

In the first step, the following null and alternative hypotheses were tested and insights from prior studies, qualitative content analysis and statistical analysis of quantitative data were compared to develop a comprehensive understanding of the effects of MEL on costs, freight rates, and further economic indicators.

H₀₁: MEL has no significant effect on costs and freight rates of the shipping industry in the North and Baltic Sea areas

H_{A1}: MEL has a significant effect on costs and freight rates of the shipping industry in the North and Baltic Sea areas

Effects on costs are discussed first. **Qualitative content analysis** of expert interviews provides strong indications that both operational costs as well as vessel investment costs increase due to maritime environmental legislation. These findings are in line with results of prior studies. The perception is pertinent among experts that the repercussions to the industry in terms of forced consolidation and increased bankruptcies will be severe. Experts show nearly unanimous concern, particularly about the increase in fuel costs from sulphur legislation and reconstruction costs from ballast water legislation. While this concern is strongly supported by qualitative data and supports the findings from literature review, the findings from quantitative data analysis are less clear.

Empirical quantitative findings were discussed in the light of effect sizes. Compliance cost analysis demonstrates great differences among individual companies, with environmental compliance costs fluctuating between 2% and 39% of total vessel costs, averaging 11.6%. These findings pertain not to the development over time but measure the costs of environmental legislation to shipping companies in a specific year, here 2016. Some 25% of shipping companies experienced their compliance costs to amount to less than 5% of total costs. 62.5% provided financial data to the effect that compliance costs amounted to 5-20% of total costs. A single company provided evidence that compliance costs constituted over 20% of total vessel costs. Statistical analyses of questionnaire data on developments in voyage costs between 2015-2017 show moderate increases in voyage costs of more than 20% for a mere 8.7% of companies in the three years after the introduction of new sulphur laws. Increases in total costs of more than 20% were experienced by a mere 2% of the sample, while moderate increases between 5-20% were documented by 56% of companies. These increases may also stem from other sources apart from MEL, however. Empirical evidence shows that the increase in total costs in recent years is negligible to moderate for the clear majority of shipping companies, despite the introduction of new environmental measures. This indicates a disparity between expert perceptions and economic reality. While experts agree that the industry is significantly affected by increased compliance costs, their measurable effect on vessel costs is moderate with few exceptions. Perceptions and fears by experts do not seem to be in line with empirical cost data. Thus, while H_{A1} may be accepted in stating that MEL does have a statistically significant effect on costs, the average effect size is moderate.

Qualitative content analysis sheds new light on the **mechanisms** of how environmental laws affect the costs of shipping companies. Firstly, experts reveal that not only the prices of necessary installations drive compliance costs. Also, the prices of related services, like tank cleanings, are likely to increase with legally-induced demand. However, environmental legislation may also lead to cost decreases by way of efficiency gains. These positive cost effects must be taken into consideration when attempting a statement on the effect of MEL on the industry. An issue that have not been previously studied and merits further academic attention are the effects of MEL on the cash flow of companies. Evidence suggests that bankruptcies occur with the introduction of new measures not necessarily due to the impossibility of covering additional compliance costs, but from the unattainability of substantial financial means at a specific point in time to invest in environmental equipment or bridge the financial gap between increased operational costs and increased income from environmental surcharges. Cash flow shortages may lead to unnecessary consolidation within

the industry, an effect limiting competition and diminishing consumer and overall societal welfare. A second issue not studied previously is the effect of environmental reconstructions on vessel value. A decreased flexibility of assets likely to occur with regional legislative endeavours again limits competition and may decrease societal welfare. These findings should provide impulses for further investigations.

Findings from prior studies, qualitative content analysis, and questionnaires confirm the foremost importance of sulphur and ballast water laws for cost increases to the industry. This evidence needs to be examined in the light of political occurrences at the time, however. The interviews were conducted in the autumn and winter of 2014, right before new laws on low-sulphur fuel use came into force; questionnaire data was collected in the autumn and winter of 2017, right after the coming into force of the BWM Convention. Naturally, the industry was much concerned about these new developments at the time. At a conference on maritime economics the author attended in the spring of 2018¹⁹, the industry seemed much occupied with new laws on CO₂ and related costs. The IMO had proclaimed a 50% decrease of CO₂ emissions for the global shipping industry by 2050 a week before the conference. The frequent mention by experts of the costs of sulphur legislation and the high ranking of ballast water legislation among other measures in the questionnaires may thus be due to both the actual cost effects of the preventive actions as well as the timing of data collection.

Especially due to the step-by-step introduction of environmental measures, the effects are not felt in their entirety either by customers or by the industry. The prohibition of single-hull tankers in 1990 was an expensive legal measure for the industry. The additional costs, which are estimated to amount to some 5-13% of operating costs (Marine Board, 1998), are still occurring, but no longer perceived by shipping companies. They find no mention by experts in the current round of interviews or by environmental officers when providing data for the questionnaire. It seems that the industry has altogether forgotten the effect of these measures, despite the costs still being incurred. The combined economic effect of all environmental measures, even the ones that have been in place for decades, is important when governing the shipping industry. Knowing about legislative effects is crucial for bringing the price of shipping services to the social optimum. While current changes are of interest when predicting the behaviour of the industry and its customers, the aggregate amount of legal measures passed is of importance in determining the total costs and benefits of environmental legislation. An evaluation of the incentives in place and their effect on the behaviour of the industry may only be attempted when considering aggregate effects. Unfortunately, data to analyse the total effect of environmental measures is scarce. The current attempt to achieve a collection of such figures from shipping companies was met by two great obstacles. The first was a reluctance by companies to provide detailed information on what many felt to be confidential company data. The second is a tendency by experts to forget. Companies were found to leave out some of the cost factors discussed in the theoretical chapter, when legislation pertaining to these cost factors was passed more than a decade ago. Also, it seems that companies are often not aware of the cost differential between compliance and noncompliance, for example the cost difference between applying TBT-containing and TBT-free hull coatings. It is thus difficult for environmental

¹⁹ World Conference on Transport Research Society – Special Interest Group A2 – SIGA2 „Maritime and Ports“, 2-4 May 2018, University of Antwerp

managers to give an accurate statement of their companies' compliance costs. Comparing compliance with noncompliance costs becomes complicated where non-legal solutions are no longer available and thus do not have a price tag anymore, but also where additional costs are spread over time and hidden behind other costs. When having a new vessel constructed it is hard to tell which part of the vessel price increase is due to stricter environmental laws and which part is due to other factors, like developments of the price of steel or the cost of labour. In addition to focusing their attention on the most recent environmental measures, experts and environmental managers also focus their attention on the measures with the cost effect most easy to isolate. As the effect of anti-fouling measures on costs is particularly difficult to measure, related studies are exceptionally rare. A ballast water treatment system, on the other hand, is purchased for the sole purpose of compliance. Thus, the effect on compliance costs is easily measurable and widely discussed. This selective perception complicates the acquisition of accurate data and the calculation of true compliance costs.

7.2.2 Measurable effects on freight rates

In **expert interviews**, eleven out of twelve experts agreed that MEL would principally lead to an increase in freight rates, but frequent passages were coded where experts were unsure about the relationship between costs and freight rates or where they saw no link between the two. Several statements were coded where experts suggested that the competitive situation within the industry as well as the competition from road and rail would not allow for any increase in rates. Estimates by two experts as to the size of likely increases give values between 5 and 40 per cent, which would indicate a critical and non-negligible effect on the industry. Despite a strong indication that freight rates would increase, however, the findings from qualitative data analysis fail to provide a convincing narrative. They rather highlight the uncertainty of experts about the economic mechanisms at work, mirroring the disagreement prevalent in the academic community. Insights gained include the expert perceptions that freight rate developments depend on the length of the journey in ECAs, the availability of alternative modes of transport, the bargaining power of individual market actors, the behaviour of competitors, and lastly the financial means of the respective shipping company to support long-term losses, i.e. the ability to hold out longer than the competition. The likely effect of compliance cost increases for the price of shipping services remains unclear from qualitative data analysis.

This uncertainty mirrors findings from prior studies. Empirical studies suggest that freight rate increases from air pollution legislation do not occur for more than half of the industry and are negligible to moderate for the remainder of the companies. Freight rate effects of other environmental measures have not previously been investigated. Findings from prior research vary so significantly that no clear picture on freight rate effects of MEL emerges. A core challenge lies in the disagreement among researchers pertaining to the mechanism how and if environmental laws influence freight rates. This disagreement is also pertinent in expert interviews. While some trust in a direct passing on of cost increases to customers, others argue that the mechanisms of supply and demand will determine the freight rate, not allowing for increases in the price of the service in times of overcapacities and low demand.

Questionnaire data analysis on freight rate developments of companies between 2015 and 2017 shows great differences in the variability of rates over time as well as the direction of change. After the introduction of new laws on sulphur emissions, however, 14 out of 19 companies providing detailed data on freight rates decreased their rates, on average by as much as 23.8%, while just four increased rates in the same period. Cost-induced increases in freight rates after stricter SECA laws were thus not found in the data. These findings are supported by a ranking of factors influencing freight rates, which indicates that changes in demand for transport capacity and market-induced changes in fuel costs have a much greater bearing on rates than environmental laws. Quantitative data thus supports the notion that the effect of environmental legislation on freight rates is negligible to non-existent.

The theoretical considerations presented in Chapter 2.6.1 bring light into the dilemma of costs affecting freight rates. When discussing freight rate effects, a distinction must be made between short-term and long-term effects. This was not considered in prior studies. Also, experts show no appreciation for this economic phenomenon in interviews. While, given strong competition within the industry, companies are unlikely to raise their rates in the short term, an increase in costs leads to a decrease in supply in the longer term, leading to a new equilibrium price at a higher level and thus an effect of MEL on freight rates. As this development depends on vessel scrappings and consolidation within the industry, however, the process may take years. Identifying changes in freight rates thus becomes an almost impossible challenge, typical for complex problems such as the one at hand, as the time lag makes it difficult to connect cause and effect. Shifts in the price of maritime transport may stem from various sources, most notably from the ever-changing demand for goods from foreign countries. Isolating the effect of legislation that came into force years before its impact is visible seems unlikely to be possible with adequate accuracy. Findings from statistical analysis are supported by evidence from qualitative data analysis, as well as insights from economic theory to provide a convincing narrative of the economic mechanisms at work.

This delayed effect proves to be a great challenge to policy makers. Economic theory demands that politicians interfere to bring the market equilibrium to an efficient outcome, rectifying the Tragedy of the Commons. A clean marine environment is a scarce good. Maritime transport activities lead to negative externalities, not covered by their price, and excess levels of pollution from shipping lead to a social welfare loss. The mechanism that economists demand politicians to employ is to introduce laws that will change the price of maritime transport to reflect the real price to society, thus changing the behaviour of consumers and bringing consumption of the service to the social optimum. Economic theory on legal incentives provides for price increases of shipping services as a necessary consequence of stricter environmental laws. This is the core mechanism to discourage customers of shipping services to demand too much of the good, bringing the price as well as the quantity consumed closer to the social optimum. Freight rate increases are important to make the mechanism work. Where freight rates react with a time lag, legislation only becomes effective after the same time lag, and where freight rates do not react at all, the shift towards the social optimum does not occur. Still, by applying command-and-control types of laws instead of market-based measures, legislators may expect to achieve welfare gains from cleaner industry operations and may be satisfied with their achievements despite the market not reacting.

The greatest challenge to effective legislation stems from the fact that the pollution of global aquatic systems is a so-called wicked problem, meaning that the interactions between human behaviour and the environment are so complex, that optimal social costs are hard to define. A further challenge arises from bounded rationality, where decision-makers might not act in line with theoretical predictions based on rational choice theory. Vast research exists on designing effective incentives to influence economic agents, with economists clearly favouring pollution taxes and market-based mechanisms over command-and-control policies such as input and output control. Policy makers, however, have largely not acted in line with these recommendations, but have designed input and output control mechanisms almost exclusively to clean up the shipping industry. This may have several reasons. First, those measures that make the most sense economically often require some economic background knowledge to get a grasp of their mechanism. They are thus hard to sell not only to the wider public, but also to politicians themselves, who are seldom economists. Secondly, even if politicians are willing to act in line with economic recommendations, sound recommendations are hard to come by, due to a lack of information. Neither economists nor legislators have complete information on the amount of emissions caused by shipping, the associated environmental impact, or the linked abatement costs, making environmental policy making a guessing game.

Over the years, economists have come up with several solutions for creating effective incentives for environmental protection. However, these are largely not applicable to the protection of the marine environment from vessel-source pollution. Coase proposes the allocation of property rights, which might in general be a workable solution to solve the Tragedy of the Commons but does not seem feasible with respect to international waters, which by international law belong to all and may be used by all, so long as the laws of the International Law of the Sea are adhered to. As a basic principle of pollution control, Pigou established the polluter-pays-principle, which is today incorporated in both international and EU law. The practical implementation in the case of emissions from shipping is flawed, however, as the principle may only be applied where the polluter, the type and amount of pollution, and the associated costs of the pollution to the individual in question are known without a doubt. When an individual living in a coastal town develops lung cancer, the individual contribution of a single vessel having passed the coast at some point during the lifetime of said individual is prohibitively costly to establish. Also, an individual may not be expected to go up against big shipping companies and demand compensation in court, especially where the link between pollution and damage is so difficult to establish. Next to lacking practical feasibility to effectively incentivise cleaner vessel operations, more recent economic theory also challenges the polluter-pays-principle as not reaching the most effective economic outcome. Work by Posner, Phaneuf, Requate, and Polinsky on the cheapest pollution avoider reveals that other emitters, for example land-based companies, may achieve a cleaner environment at lower societal costs (Polinsky, 2011, Posner, 2014, Phaneuf and Requate, 2017). Consequently, it would be in the societal interest to target those companies instead of the shipping industry. These theories are supported by empirical findings from Hammingh et al. (Hammingh et al., 2012). Instead of having each polluter pay for the damage caused, those who may avoid pollution at the lowest cost should engage in the activity, the economists argue. This includes society. If people in harbour towns, for example, may protect their own health in a more cost-effective way by closing their windows at certain times, than the industry may protect it by filtering emissions, society may be the cheapest

pollution avoider. These considerations are currently not taken into account by policy makers when designing legal incentives. This might not only be explained by a lack of data to determine the cheapest pollution avoider, but also by a political ambition to design policies that are deemed fair instead of policies that increase societal welfare the most. Targeting everyone the same, that is demanding that all industrial sectors alike reduce emissions, is thought fair by the majority of people and is thus most likely to receive approbation and good election results. Similarly, demanding from the polluter, instead of society, to take remedial actions, is similarly thought fair and least likely to lead to social unrest. Societal discontent does also carry a substantial cost. A further challenge to designing optimal policy has been termed the theory of full costs by Polinsky (Polinsky, 2011). Optimal regulation becomes difficult to achieve where the operation of vessels brings both benefits as well as costs to society. Polinsky argues that only people who value the benefits of the maritime transport service more than the associated full costs, including the costs of pollution, should purchase said service. A full internalisation of externalities should thus lead to an optimal societal outcome. Still, the challenge of quantifying these externalities remains.

Linking freight rates to economic theory, it will only be possible to effectively influence market behaviour if compliance costs are passed on to consumers. Economists demand that incentives work effectively, that the wrong of externalities is put right and that the environmental costs are incorporated into the price of sea transport to encourage a healthy decrease in the provision of the services. To achieve that, it is necessary that the cost increases from legislation are translated into price increases for the transport of goods and subsequently to increases in the price of goods themselves, influencing customer choice. Where this mechanism does not work, or only works with great delays, environmental policy fails to have the expected effects.

7.2.3 Modal shift

Expert interviews reveal determinants of modal choice not addressed in previous studies, particularly developments not only in the availability, but also in the price of alternative transport. Environmental measures and increased compliance costs may not only be experienced by the shipping industry, but also specifically by road transport, currently facing a debate over emissions of particulate matter and linked cost increases. At the same time, large infrastructure projects and heavy investments in road transport throughout Europe bring down the price of this transport mode and make it more attractive compared to sea transport. Similarly, infrastructure projects may be conducted with respect to the shipping industry, like the deepening of the river Elbe in Hamburg, which will decrease costs for this transport mode. Another issue mentioned by experts are capacity restrictions for road transport not driven so much by infrastructure, as by the limited availability of truck drivers, again influencing prices and modal choice. Given the complexity of the modal choice problem and the expected time lag between cause and effect, the researcher refrained from collecting data on modal choice by way of the questionnaires, instead focusing on the effect of legislation on freight rates that would precede modal shift.

On a last note, it must be observed that a shift to other modes of transport is desirable when all external costs have been factored in with all transport modes. If prices of sea- and land-based

transport reflect the full costs of each alternative, then transport modes should be chosen by cargo owners reflecting the social optimum, however. This mechanism requires that pricing determines decision-making. As can be seen in the literature and expert discussion on modal choice, many other variables apart from price play a role in the choice of transport mode.

7.2.4 Further economic effects

Experts raised several issues during interviews which were not specifically mentioned in prior studies but prove essential in understanding the complexity of the effects of MEL on the shipping industry. It must be noted that the direction of effects is not always apparent. Two main categories may be distinguished, namely increases and decreases in capacity supplied, with most statements coded on decreases of shipping capacity. Experts were particularly concerned about consolidation of the industry as a result of environmental laws, while also expecting the closing of routes and vessel scrappings or redeployments outside of emission control areas. Comparing these predicted developments with economic theory on environmental incentives, a decrease in shipping capacity and an increase in prices of the service seems necessary to nudge the industry towards the social optimum. These developments necessarily come with less efficient companies leaving the market, less efficient ships being disposed of and less efficient routes being closed. If these developments occur, politicians may congratulate themselves on their policies achieving the intended effect. On the other hand, experts expect an increase in capacity particularly from growing ship sizes. Great concern exists within the industry over full order books especially for super-sized vessels at a time of overcapacities. The explanation lies in a harsh competitive situation – made harsher by environmental cost increases – in which only the fittest companies with the most efficient vessels survive. As the most efficient vessels are usually the largest ones with the greatest economies of scale, financially well-endowed companies invest in new assets particularly at a time when price competition is strong. They aim to win the race for the lowest rates and be counted among the survivors of necessary consolidation. In the long run, once the market has been consolidated and less efficient assets squeezed out, they hope to recover their current investments with increases in freight rates. However, their strategic behaviour is aggravating the current competitive situation in the industry, making compliance cost increases even harder felt. Consolidation is expected to follow a cascade effect, where the largest and newest vessels replace the middle-sized ones and the middle-sized vessels are employed on routes previously run by small vessels. Smaller, older, and less efficient vessels are often owned and operated by smaller shipping companies with limited financial resources. These will be forced to leave the market. If the consolidating effects are particularly strong, an oligopolistic situation may develop, where companies may start charging prices not reflecting the social optimum. It must be monitored closely that legislative endeavours to decrease externalities from environmental pollution, thereby increasing societal welfare, will not cost consumer rents due to oligopolistic pricing, leading to a decrease in societal welfare.

7.2.5 Summary

From the findings presented in Chapters 3 to 6 it becomes evident that alternative hypothesis H_{A1} may be cautiously accepted regarding cost effects but must be rejected with regard to

freight rate effects. The null hypothesis H_{01} may be rejected. A difference must be made between the statistical significance of effects and their effect size. The overall evidence strongly suggests that maritime environmental legislation has a measurable, statistically significant effect on the costs of shipping companies, while the effect on freight rates remains questionable. With respect to the effect size, findings suggest that the effect on costs is moderate, while the effect on freight rates is negligible at most. The current legal framework seems unlikely to significantly influence prices and related demand for shipping services.

7.3 Critical analysis of hypothesis H_{02} : Noncompliance with MEL is negligible

A comparison of findings from prior studies, expert interviews, and questionnaire data was conducted to investigate the following null and alternative hypotheses on compliance behaviour:

H_{02} : Noncompliance with MEL is negligible.

H_{A2} : Noncompliance with MEL is statistically significant.

Estimates of compliance rates stem from primary questionnaire data. Making use of a method called indirect questioning, analysis of quantitative data showed that some 35-43% of companies in the sample, depending on the law in question, witnessed instances of noncompliance. The rate is highest for legislation on sulphur emissions and waste and lowest for discharges of oily water. 10-15% of the sample estimate industry-wide compliance rates on mandatory measures to be below 70%. These are deemed very likely to be noncompliant at times themselves. Estimates are well in line with findings from expert interviews and prior studies. Noncompliance with MEL may thus be found to be statistically significant and H_{A2} may be accepted. Results suggest that no developments towards the improvement of compliance rates has taken place within the last 15 years.

Interestingly, current reports by the Paris MoU on Port State Control suggest that most vessels are detained for defaulting on obligations pertaining to oily water. These empirical results contradict the data provided by shipping companies. Findings from questionnaires indicate that noncompliance on matters of air pollution legislation, particularly on low sulphur laws, is higher than on matters of oily water pollution. Either the perception of environmental officers within shipping companies is flawed, or port state control officers are more successful at detecting noncompliance with one set of laws than with another.

Experts in interviews suggest that effective control may not only be exercised by authorities but by stakeholders as well. Interview statements suggest that noncompliance might induce big customers like car companies to revoke their certifications, might induce insurance companies to annul their coverage, or might induce banks to refrain from further credit contracts. All of these mechanisms may effectively prompt companies to act in compliance with the laws. Additional pressure by stakeholders may prove more efficient than legal fines but will again depend on the risk of being detected. These findings support conclusions of prior research for example on the role of oil majors to enforce legal compliance in the tanker market.

Contributions made by the mixed methods approach led to a more nuanced and complete understanding of the phenomenon of legal compliance, which will allow policy makers to

develop a refined cause of action. Literature analysis, expert interviews, and quantitative data analysis was applied to develop and test a model of determinants of legal compliance specifically applicable to the maritime shipping industry. The theoretical findings may serve to inform research on other transport sectors as well. A compliance model was developed from the literature and further refined and developed with expert statements, encompassing three categories of determinants. Findings with respect to these categories stemming from the different research methods applied may be found in Table 7-1.

	Literature analysis	Expert interviews	Questionnaires - Results from PLS analysis	Questionnaires - Results from ANOVA (Analysis of variance)
A: Individual motivations				
Morality and ethics	Moral inhibitions and self-respect of decision-makers, individual perceptions of seriousness of crime	Acceptance of environmental laws and administrative burdens; Felt need to contribute to a cleaner environment	Excluded due to extreme non-normal distributions of indicators	Not found to be statistically significant
Company culture	'Criminogetic culture' within the company	Company policy	Excluded to increase content validity	Not found to be statistically significant
Perceived benefits of compliance	Financial rewards to individuals and the company, perceived advantages of looking green	Commercial gains from environmental performance in relation to customers, investors, current and future employees; efficiency gains; higher attractiveness on the charter market; increases in freight rates; reputation and public image	Not found to be statistically significant	Not found to be statistically significant
Perceived costs of compliance	Informal sanctions, perceived danger to shipping operations, perceived danger of detection	Commercial disadvantages of compliance, no increase in freight rates, no possibility to distinguish environmentally friendly vessels due to container-sharing agreements		
B: Organisational capacities			Statistically significant with a loading factor of 0.613 and a p-value of 0.008	
Resource constraints - Financial resources	Current economic situation of the company	Shortages in financial resources due to shipping crisis (Limited income, limited possibilities to receive further credit lines), cash flow problems	Excluded to increase content validity	Not found to be statistically significant
Resource constraints - Personnel resources	Compliance uncertainty (legal personnel), logistical problems (technical personnel)	Time pressure, awareness and apprehension of legal information (Lack in number and qualification of personnel), network	Indicators time, uncertainty, network and personnel found to be statistically significant (Loading factors 0.812, 0.373, 0.841, 0.370 on organisational capacities)	Indicators time ($\eta^2=0.301$, $p=0.001$), personnel ($\eta^2=0.081$, $p=0.093$) and network ($\eta^2=0.185$, $p=0.009$) found to be statistically significant
Resource constraints - Industry association membership	n.a.	Membership in one or more associations as important sources of information	Statistically significant with a loading factor of 0.594 on organisational capacities	Found to be statistically significant ($\eta^2=0.121$, $p=0.037$), moderate effect on compliance

Operator characteristics	Company size, academic background of CEO, vessel age and state of maintenance	Company size, area of operations (territorial outsiders), ownership structure, company culture, seat of operations, average age of vessels, type of customers, fleet composition, economic position, flag state	Company size, average vessel age, area of operations and type of operations not found to be statistically significant	Significant correlation at the 10% level with moderate effect size between owner type and compliance ($\eta^2=0.183$, $p=0.095$) and significant correlation at the 5% level between vessel age and compliance ($\eta^2=0.279$, $p=0.006$)
C: Exterior determinants of compliance				
Sanctions and enforcement	Inspection probability, level of fines, regional differences in enforcement, feasibility of drawing representative ballast water samples	Frequency of inspections, inspection standards, level of fines, behaviour of control officers towards substandard vessels (staying clear vs. checking), possibility of retracing behaviour on the open seas during port state controls	Not found to be statistically significant with indicator loading of 0.209, but p-value of 0.193	Not found to be statistically significant
Norms as an effective deterrent	Probability of detection at night, certification by customers	Risk of losing customer certification, insurance coverage or bank financing	Excluded to increase content validity	Not found to be statistically significant
Practical feasibility of noncompliance	Forgeability of bunker delivery notes	Ease of circumventing legislation, e.g. throwing waste overboard, washing tanks at sea, switching late to low-sulphur fuel, forging paperwork	Excluded to increase content validity	Not found to be statistically significant
Availability of feasible technical options	Stratification of oil in the tank	Availability of approved technical compliance options and port reception facilities, feasibility of implementation aboard and operation of technical solutions, economic viability of technical solutions	Excluded to increase content validity	Not found to be statistically significant
Human error	Wrong fuel supplied	Mistakes by employees, oversight	Not found to be statistically significant	Not found to be statistically significant
Higher forces	/	Failure of technical systems, weather effects		Not found to be statistically significant

Table 7-1: Comparison of findings from various data sources on determinants of compliance

With respect to the first category – **individual motivations** – prior researchers have already discussed how moral inhibitions and the self-respect of decision-makers, as well as the costs and benefits of compliance they perceive, influence compliance behaviour. These include the existence of a so-called ‘criminogenic culture’ in the company, informal sanctions, as well as expected individual financial rewards. Findings from qualitative content analysis served to deepen and build upon these concepts, developing four distinct categories of individual motivations. The acceptance of environmental laws by decision-makers as well as their felt need to contribute to a cleaner environment were strongly evidenced to influence compliance by experts. The underlying concept of morality and ethics could not be found to have a statistically significant influence on compliance based on quantitative data from questionnaires, however. Similarly, company culture, substantiated by experts to be visible through company policy, could not be shown to have a statistically significant effect on compliance levels. Strong evidence was found in expert interviews and prior studies that perceived costs and benefits of legislation would influence compliance. Experts documented benefits to depend on commercial

gains from environmental performance in relation to customers, investors, current and future employees, as well as efficiency gains from legislation, a higher attractiveness on the charter market, possible increases in freight rates and gains in reputation and public image. They argued costs of compliance to stem from a lack of commercial advantages, for example where higher freight rates were not feasible, and customers would not choose more environmentally friendly vessels over conventional ones. While arguments from prior studies and expert statements were very convincing in supporting the role of individual motivations for compliance, none of the related determinants was found to be statistically significant.

The second category of determinants – **organisational capacities** – had also been mentioned in prior studies. Researchers had written about compliance uncertainty (Srivastava and Batie, 2002) and noncompliance for ‘logistical reasons’ (Sampson et al., 2016), both linked to the number and quality of staff employed with the company. Others had found vessel age (OECD, 2003), company size, and available financial means (Simpson and Rorie, 2011) to influence compliance. A link between company size and law abidance had been shown not to exist by another group of researchers, however (Clinard and Yeager, 1982). Simpson and Rorie had even found a correlation between the academic background of the CEO and compliance, with CEOs with financial or administrative backgrounds more likely to offend than CEOs with law or engineering backgrounds (Simpson and Rorie, 2011). Findings from qualitative content analysis have substantiated and deepened the understanding of organisational characteristics that might have a bearing on compliance. Four distinct categories were built, with the first three describing different facets of resource constraints and the last one describing operator characteristics. Financial resource constraints were briefly mentioned in prior studies, indicating that the current financial health of a company might be of importance. Experts affirmed this notion, adding statements on the relevance of the shipping crisis, constraining income and credit lines since 2009, as well as cash flow problems during the introduction of new environmental laws. Both PLS analysis and ANOVA on questionnaire data could not show a statistical significance of financial resource constraints for compliance. The second category of resource constraints identified were personnel resources, with experts strongly supporting the idea that time pressure, a lack of awareness and apprehension of legal information – which would stem from a lack in the number and qualifications of personnel – and the lack of a network with other companies to exchange knowledge, would influence compliance. The respective indicators time, personnel, network, and compliance uncertainty were found to be statistically significant. Constraints in time and an effective network were shown to have the most significant effect on compliance. Furthermore, the indicator ‘association membership’, which did not surface in literature analysis but was introduced during expert interviews, was found to be statistically significant with a moderate effect on compliance. Experts argued that industry association membership would influence the amount and quality of legal information a shipping company would receive. Lastly, experts built on findings from prior studies to come up with a long list of operator characteristics that could influence compliance, namely company size, area of operations (territorial insiders or outsiders), ownership structure, company culture, seat of operations, average age of vessels, type of customers, fleet composition, economic position and flag state. Those characteristics tested in PLS analysis could not be found to be statistically significant. Additional ANOVA showed a significant correlation between vessel age and compliance, with companies operating older assets slightly less likely to comply, and

a moderate correlation between owner type and compliance (only significant at the 10% level, however), indicating that companies carrying a higher share of responsibility for their vessels were more likely to comply. Overall, organisational capacities was the only group of determinants to be correlated with compliance at a statistically significant level, with a loading factor of 0.613 and a p-value of 0.008 in PLS analysis.

The third category – **exterior determinants of compliance** – includes compliance factors imposed on the company by third parties or linked to forces of nature. Five of the six factors identified by experts could also be found in prior studies, at least by way of anecdotal evidence, namely sanctions and enforcement (OECD, 2003, p.6), norms as an effective deterrent, practical feasibility of noncompliance, availability of feasible technical options, and human error. Higher forces have not been explicitly mentioned in the studies reviewed but could also not be shown to have a statistically significant effect on compliance levels. The same holds true for human error. The determinant ‘sanctions and enforcement’ finds the most prominent mention of all factors identified here in theoretical literature and prior studies. Inspection probability, the level of fines, regional differences in enforcement, and the feasibility of drawing samples have been extensively studied and their effect on compliance is taken for granted by many researchers. Support by experts as to the relevance of sanctions and enforcement for compliance is equally strong. In addition to confirming the factors mentioned in the literature, experts argue how inspection standards, the behaviour of control officers towards substandard vessels, and the possibility to retrace vessel behaviour during port state controls influences compliance. While evidence from literature and qualitative content analysis is strong, statistical data analysis of questionnaires did not show a significant correlation between compliance levels and sanctions and enforcement. While Eta-values are clearly not significant, PLS analysis comes up with a very moderate indicator loading of 0.209. The effect was associated with a p-value of 0.193, however, leading to a rejection of statistical significance. These findings do not mean that no significant effect exists. The effect can not be found in the data collected during this study, however. The same holds true for the determinants ‘norms as an effective deterrent’ and ‘practical feasibility of noncompliance’, both of which were not found to have statistically significant effects on compliance. These determinants were rather based on circumstantial evidence than robust study results in previous research, but had been supported by experts during interviews as playing a role for compliance. Lastly, the availability of feasible technical options was also not widely discussed in literature but proved to be of great importance in qualitative content analysis. Experts argued that the availability of approved technical compliance options and port reception facilities, the feasibility of implementation aboard and the operation of technical solutions, and the economic viability of technical solutions played an important role in the compliance behaviour of companies. Statistical analysis of quantitative questionnaire data did not confirm the statistical significance of this determinant, however.

Expert interview data suggests that determinants identified from the literature seem largely applicable to compliance behaviour of the shipping industry regarding environmental legislation. Factors mentioned in prior studies could be substantiated and findings could be supported with evidence from shipping experts, especially in cases where previous studies were based on circumstantial evidence. Also, additional determinants could be identified that might be especially important in explaining maritime environmental compliance. Resource

constraints found mention by all twelve experts interviewed and were thoroughly discussed as being of great importance to the industry at the current time. Also, the availability or lack of availability of feasible technical solutions features prominently among the arguments of all twelve experts to influence compliance. Statistical analysis of questionnaire data, however, showed that only one of three categories of determinants, namely organizational capacities, could be shown to withstand statistical scrutiny. Within this category, the determinants time, industry association membership, and network with other companies, were shown to have the largest effect on compliance behaviour. The overall model fit proved to be acceptable for an exploratory study such as this, leaving room for improvement. Weak model fit may be explained by a lack of correlation between compliance and compliance drivers identified, but may also be an effect of measurement errors, errors in translating the latent concepts into viable proxy variables or small sample size. Also, instrumentation of the questionnaire to receive a desired outcome is possible, where participants overestimate compliance costs and underestimate noncompliant behaviour to discourage further political involvement in the industry. The results are not atypical for exploratory studies, where tentative first steps are made to identify relationships among abstract concepts and much still needs to be learned in terms of describing and measuring the latent concepts. Also, the research shows the benefits of conducting mixed methods research. The theoretical concept presented above represents a convincing outcome of thorough qualitative research but does not withstand statistical scrutiny.

From a critical analysis of the three named data sources, it may be found that the null hypothesis H_{02} may be rejected and the alternative hypothesis H_{A2} may be accepted. The statistical significance of noncompliance with maritime environmental legislation is found to be strongly supported by data analysis. The effect size, however, is rather small. While noncompliance is found to exist, a moderate share of 10-15% of the industry is found to be noncompliant at times. The savings for these individual companies might be quite substantial, but the additional amount of environmental damage caused is likely small. Damages to societal welfare from a worsened environmental status due to noncompliant companies might be negligible, but societal damages stemming from a lack of trust in institutions to implement legislation may be more significant.

With respect to the level of compliance, control efforts must be balanced with the additional societal benefits of increased compliance levels. Port state control as a response to increased flagging out has been shown to provide fair results at a reasonable cost-performance ratio. Controlling ship behaviour outside of harbours, however, may become prohibitively expensive, with slight potential increases in compliance not warranting these efforts. Also, evidence from fly-over images taken at night and other evidence collected from remote sources on the open seas are not necessarily admissible in court, rendering the expense nonsensical. However, the benefits of these measures might be that companies feel monitored, despite not being effectively controlled. Compliant behaviour is a result of orders by decision-makers, who will act based on individual perceptions of the costs and benefits of compliance. Compliance may thus be seen as a rational choice outcome, weighing first and second order compliance costs against the costs of noncompliance. A perceived danger of detection thus influences compliance levels as much as a real danger of detection. While the benefits of remote sensing to increase compliance must be further investigated, an increase in port state controls or a further harmonisation of the

intensity of controls across Europe, is likely to bring positive effects. Effectively discouraging noncompliance also serves to increase the support for environmental laws within the industry. In interviews, experts claimed they would be less anxious about increased compliance costs if they could be sure that all companies would incur these costs and a level playing field would exist within the industry. Companies feel unfairly treated and protest against environmental laws when noncompliant companies are awarded a better competitive position without danger of criminal prosecution.

7.4 Critical analysis of hypothesis H₀₃: No significant differences exist within the shipping industry with respect to the costs of complying with MEL

The third pair of null and alternative hypotheses tested in this thesis are the following:

Hypothesis H₀₃: No significant differences exist within the shipping industry with respect to the costs of complying with MEL.

Hypothesis H_{A3}: Significant differences exist within the shipping industry with respect to the costs of complying with MEL.

The researcher aimed to test whether differences in company characteristics would significantly influence costs of complying with maritime environmental legislation. With respect to company characteristics that might be of interest, a thorough systematic literature review was conducted. Results from qualitative content analysis of interviews were used to inform and further develop the insights gained from prior studies to develop a matrix of potentially relevant characteristics. Experts in interviews contributed to a more nuanced and deeper understanding of cost-relevant company characteristics. In addition to the type of vessels employed by the company, and the flags frequently flown by the company, the following attributes were mentioned to potentially influence compliance costs: Company size, ownership structure, average vessel age, area of operations (specifically the share of ECA operations), type of operations (liner or tramp), location of central management, and industry association membership. The potential significance of these attributes may clearly be established from qualitative content analysis. Opinions of experts diverge, however, as to which types of shipping companies are less affected by environmental legislation than others or which companies might provide environmental protection at a better cost-benefit relationship than others. Evidence from qualitative data analysis suggests that the size of the company plays a role in reducing compliance costs per vessel for larger companies due to economies of scale. Furthermore, experts stated that compliance with ballast water legislation might be especially expensive for bulk and crude carriers and compliance with sulphur legislation especially expensive for RoRo/RoPax carriers mostly operating exclusively in emission control areas. These findings support the results of the Bachér/Albrecht study. Data collected through questionnaires was analysed to determine which company characteristics could be shown to influence compliance costs at a statistically significant level. Partial least squares analysis was conducted for this purpose. Results show that company characteristics can only explain a negligible share of cost developments in the range of 3-8%. Furthermore, no individual path value was above 0.2, indicating the lack of a statistically significant relationship among company attributes and cost developments.

Company characteristics were not only tested in relation to compliance costs, but also in relation to compliance levels. Again, partial least squares analysis could not find a statistically relevant relationship, indicating that company attributes had no bearing on legal compliance. Additional ANOVA analysis found a moderate relationship between owner type and compliance with $\eta^2=0.183$, indicating that owners who operate their own vessels are more likely to comply with environmental laws than both owners who charter out their vessels and operators chartering vessels that others own. Operating their own assets may induce companies to take better care, an observation that was also made during expert interviews. With a p-value of 0.095, this relationship is only significant at the 10%, not the 5% level, however. While all other company characteristics could not be shown to be statistically significant for compliance, one further attribute was found to have a significant relationship. With $\eta^2=0.279$ and $p=0.006$, the average age of vessels employed by the company could be shown to be related to levels of legal compliance. Companies operating older assets were less likely to comply with legal rules than companies operating newer assets. Roughly 28% of the variance in compliance may be explained by average vessel age. Statistical tests did not confirm expert perceptions that smaller companies, or companies operating mostly within ECAs, were more strongly affected by cost increases or showed lower levels of compliance. Comparison of sources led to the finding that alternative hypothesis H_{A3} could not be accepted and null hypothesis H_{03} could not be rejected.

When critically analysing these results, it must be noted that the regional focus of the study might have a bearing upon the findings. Differences between shipping companies might become apparent both with respect to compliance costs as well as levels of legal compliance when data is collected globally. The level of controls in the Northern European seas is quite high compared to other areas of seaborne trade, as has been noted by experts. It might thus be that differences become difficult to measure where the overall level of compliance is quite high. Industry-led compliance monitoring, as exercised by the oil majors for the tanker industry for example, can lead to great differences in compliance levels in parts of the world where harbour state controls are less sophisticated than in Northern Europe. In the North and Baltic Sea, however, no differences in compliance costs or compliance levels became apparent between tankers and other types of vessels.

7.5 Nonresponse analysis

Comparing characteristics of survey participants to statistical data on all shipping companies, it becomes apparent which types of companies took part in the study and which refrained from answering questions on compliance costs and compliance behaviour. A respective description of questionnaire participants may be found in Annexes C6 and C7. The distribution of responses by country may be seen on the map in Figure 7-1. The sample consisted of all shipowners and operators registered with any of the countries bordering the North and Baltic Seas. Responses coming from countries outside this sample, such as Canada, the U.S., Iceland and France, are due to emails being forwarded within companies, for example to specialised personnel situated in headquarters. Participating companies came from Germany in 56% of the cases, followed by Denmark (11%), Norway (8%), Sweden (7%), the UK (4%), the Netherlands (3%) and others (11%). The sample is heavily biased towards companies with their headquarters in Germany and Denmark. Other countries along the North and Baltic Sea coasts are significantly

underrepresented. Particularly Russian and Baltic shipping companies did not often choose to take part in the study. Similarly, companies from the UK are underrepresented, despite the study being linked to a UK university. This distribution may be explained to some extent by particularly strong marketing efforts in Germany, where the researcher was located, as well as endorsement of the study by the German and Danish shipowner's associations, while no such endorsement could be gained from other national associations. To some extent it also reflects the number of shipping companies active in the respective countries. Also, continental companies in Scandinavia and Western Europe seemed more willing both to provide personal contact information and data towards an academic study than companies across the Channel and along the Eastern coast of the Baltic Sea. This may be a matter of cultural differences but may also be explained by a higher level of English proficiency in these countries.

Figure 7-1: Response distribution for questionnaire, blue = respondent's locations (Extracted from QuestionPro)

More striking is the comparison of company sizes. Organising participants by the number of vessels owned, it becomes apparent that companies of all sizes are represented in the sample to a more or less equal extent. This does not reflect the actual composition of the shipping industry as described by Stopford, who finds that small shipping companies with less than 10 vessels make up 85% of the industry, while large companies account for a mere 2%. This indicates that small-sized companies are significantly underrepresented in the sample (Stopford, 2013). Considering average vessel age, it becomes apparent that companies with new or middle-aged vessels make up more than 90% of the sample, while in reality more than half of all vessels are older than 20 years (UNCTAD, 2017, p.27). An underrepresentation of companies with older assets is thus discernible. Thirdly, all sectors of the commercial shipping industry are represented in the sample, with bulk carriers being the largest group with 32.7%, as shown in Table 7-2. Comparing this with current UNCTAD data, this group is still underrepresented, normally constituting 42.8% of the world fleet. General and specialised cargo carriers are

slightly overrepresented, but differences of vessels in the sample compared to the world fleet might also stem from a different structure of vessels active in the North and Baltic Sea areas (UNCTAD, 2017, p.24).

		Frequency in sample	Percentage of sample (valid)	Percentage of world fleet (UNCTAD 2017)
Valid	Container vessels	26	23.6%	13.2%
	General cargo carriers	19	17.3%	4.0%
	Bulk carriers (Liquid/Dry)	36	32.7%	42.8%
	RoRo/ RoPax vessels	7	6.4%	0.3%
	Crude carriers	6	5.5%	28.7%
	Specialised cargo carriers	16	14.5%	11.0%
	Total	110	100%	100.0%
	Missing cases	7		
Total		117		

Table 7-2: Companies in the sample by main vessel type

The sample includes companies operating mostly or exclusively within emission control areas, as well as companies operating mostly or almost exclusively outside of emission control areas. Two company stating that they were operating exclusively outside of ECAs did not fit the sampling criteria and were excluded from the sample. Flag states of sampling companies were varied, with European flags being overrepresented compared to worldwide averages (see UNCTAD, 2017), which is well explainable by the regional focus of the investigation. Lastly, around 14% of shipping companies in the sample were not members of any industry organisation providing advice on legal developments. As this variable has not previously been studied, no data could be found to judge whether the sample is biased in this respect. Looking at the overall sample, it becomes apparent that the sample is biased towards larger shipping companies with more modern fleets flying European or other flags with an immaculate reputation. An explanation may be that larger companies have more personnel which they can employ towards scientific causes. Smaller companies, companies with older assets, and companies flying grey-listed or black-listed flags, showed disproportionately elevated levels of nonresponse to a questionnaire on environmental compliance. Especially the complete lack of grey- and black-listed flags in the sample is striking, as these vessels are marked by port state control officers as being the most likely to break legal rules. Nonresponse analysis suggests that especially those companies most likely to be noncompliant with environmental legislation chose not to take part in the study. The estimates provided on compliance levels may thus be taken as conservative. Also, the fact that no significant correlation could be found among flag state and compliance or other company characteristics like company size may also be explained by the likelihood that companies particularly prone to noncompliance did not take part in the study. Nonetheless, this group might be associated with specific characteristics, as suggested by experts during interviews, the relevance of which could not be evidenced during statistical analysis either because they were not relevant or else because specific responders are lacking from the sample.

7.6 Synthesis of lessons learned

Combining insights from theoretical literature, empirical studies, qualitative content analysis and statistical analysis of quantitative data enabled a partial validation of the theoretical model and has provided an advanced understanding of the complex dynamics of environmental laws in the context of the maritime shipping industry. The contribution of this research lies in demystifying the behaviour of the waterborne transport industry towards environmental legislation. Main findings are shown in Figure 7-2 and include a statistically significant effect of maritime environmental legislation on operational and investment costs of shipping companies, while no statistically significant effect on freight rates and, in extension, no statistically significant effect on modal shift could be found. However, these effects may be delayed and may be found with a time lag, as economic theory suggests. Noncompliance with maritime environmental legislation has been verified, with at least 10-15% of companies exhibiting deviant behaviour. A multitude of drivers of noncompliance could be identified from literature and expert interviews, but only resource constraints were correlated to compliance at a statistically significant level. No significant differences could be found among different types of shipping companies with respect to the effect of maritime environmental legislation.

Figure 7-2: Synthesis of lessons learned: Effects of maritime environmental legislation on the shipping industry

8 Conclusions and policy recommendations

8.1 Interpretation of results

This thesis embodies an exploratory mixed methods study on the effects and effectiveness of maritime environmental legislation for the commercial shipping industry. An analysis and discussion of economic theories and an exploration of current legal measures aimed at cleaning up the industry were conducted and mirrored with results from prior studies. Based on theoretical findings, research gaps were identified. The methodological approach, comprising in-depth expert interviews and a structured questionnaire, was described and critically reviewed. This was followed by a discussion of research results, stemming from the use of qualitative content analysis, statistical analysis of quantitative data and partial least squares analysis. The effects of maritime environmental legislation on costs, freight rates, and further economic indicators, as well as the effectiveness of legislation, measured by rate of legal compliance, were thoroughly evaluated. This was followed by an analysis of determinants of legal compliance and an analysis and discussion of differences among shipping companies. Eventually results of empirical analysis were triangulated and discussed in the light of theoretical concepts, highlighting disparities between the economic theory of law and empirical findings.

Main findings as presented in Chapter 7 show that both operational and investment costs of shipping companies increased significantly due to maritime environmental legislation and are bound to increase even more in the next years. However, freight rates did not adapt to cost changes to a measurable extent. Noncompliance with legislation has been shown to be a statistically significant challenge. Crucially, compliance is found to depend more on individual company resources than external possibilities to influence companies, like effective sanctions and enforcement. Differences exist among shipping companies both in relation to effects and effectiveness of environmental laws. However, these do not seem to be linked to specific company characteristics. Only two categories of company characteristics could be identified to have a minor statistically significant effect on compliance, namely the type of ownership and the average age of vessels employed. Other categories like company size, despite strong expert evidence to the contrary, proved not to be statistically significant. The mixed methods approach and analysis of data from different sources proved relevant in arriving at a more nuanced and complete understanding of effects of maritime environmental legislation. Confirmatory analysis served to distinguish individual perceptions from statistically relevant effects. In-depth qualitative analysis may support policy makers in arriving at a deep understanding of what drives compliance costs and compliance behaviour of the industry. The quantitative analysis identifies the most crucial factors policy makers wishing to influence compliance levels should focus on. Also, it discerns actual costs incurred and vague perceptions on the burden of environmental laws. Policy makers may learn from the results that environmental laws have significant effects on the costs of the industry, but cost increases are not effectively passed on to customers. The time dimension found in economic models on the internalisation of externalities is particularly important for this research. Politicians aiming to bring the price of commercial shipping to the social optimum will find that so far legal incentives have been insufficient. The empirical finding of decreasing, rather than increasing freight rates may be explained with the expected time lag between laws and witnessed effects but may also be due

to the specific characteristics and historical situation of the shipping industry. Overcapacities in the aftermath of the financial crisis linked with the further ordering of capacity and a cascading effect, as well as a bleak future²⁰ make freight rate increases an unlikely prospect. The broader implications of this research are, that historical economic instruments to bring supply and demand for a service to the social optimum, rectifying the Tragedy of the Commons and accounting for external effects, may clash with economic realities. Noncompliant companies may disturb the expected price effect of environmental policies. While the command-and-control approach might lead to 85-90% of companies operating more efficient assets with lower levels of pollution, the full environmental effect expected from economic models does not materialise. Empirical results show that competitive forces within the industry can have an even stronger influence, delaying or weakening the expected increase in freight rates. When service prices do not adapt to cost increases, purchasers of shipping services will not shift their demand to the socially optimal level.

Economic effects of maritime environmental legislation are found to be either less strong than initially expected or delayed to such an extent as to surpass the scope of this study. Still, it must not be forgotten that environmental legislation is an important driver of innovation. While market-based mechanisms are better apt to encourage companies to develop new, more efficient, and less polluting solutions, the introduction of command-and-control policies as has been done for the shipping industry also leads to desirable behaviour. Policies that drive up the fuel price, also drive innovative ideas. On 29 September 2018, the cargo vessel Maersk Pelican arrived in Saudi Arabia on its first voyage after having installed rotor sails on board, an effort to use wind power as an additional method of propulsion (The Economist, 2018c). Results of this research show that predicting the behavioural effects of environmental policies is challenging, and while the industry might not behave as expected, positive effects may still outweigh costs.

8.2 Contributions to knowledge

This study explores whether legal incentives to discourage maritime environmental pollution are influencing the industry's behaviour effectively. It analyses how maritime environmental legislation is affecting costs and freight rates in the commercial shipping industry. Contributions to knowledge are based on a comparison of original qualitative and quantitative data, as well as systematically reviewed secondary data, allowing for both the building and testing of new theoretical concepts. Originality of the study lies firstly in its incremental theoretical contribution, building on the theory of noncompliance, adding to it by way of an exploratory qualitative study and applying it in the specific context of the maritime shipping industry. It also stems from linking both legal and economic theory and building a common conceptual framework including concerns from the field of environmental law and environmental economics. This research fills knowledge gaps based on methodological rigour and provides a theoretical advancement useful to the academic research community. It also has a practical usefulness in informing legislators of the actual effectiveness of their endeavours

²⁰ The influential weekly magazine "The Economist" titled in October 2018: "The next recession – How bad will it be?"

and providing suggestions for improvement. A list of academic contributions based on this thesis can be found in Annex E1.

A first important contribution lies in reviewing and systematically organising the current legal framework to control vessel-source pollution in the Northern European seas and in examining this framework in the light of economic theory. Highlighting and discussing the divergence among theoretical concepts on how to best structure incentives and the legal reality of incentive structures to control pollution is an important input to the current academic debate. Findings may be applied to increase the efficiency of future legal measures.

A further contribution may be found in reviewing and building upon a theory of cost and freight rate effects of maritime environmental legislation, as well as the empirical testing of this theory. The most relevant knowledge gain lies in not finding a significant link between cost increases from pollution control and price increases for shipping services, suggesting that costs are not being passed on to consumers. In the short term, this is in line with economic theory, but price increases should be witnessed in the longer term to allow for the internalisation of externalities. A contribution thus lies in raising awareness among researchers and politicians for the time lag between legislation and its effects. It also aims at making researchers wary of further influential factors like the world demand for shipping services or fuel price developments, which might overlap and cancel out effects from maritime environmental legislation. This makes the impact of legal rules on freight rates challenging to measure.

Thirdly, the research contributes significantly to the study of deviant behaviour in the face of the law, particularly in the organisational context. The theory of noncompliance built, based on thorough literature review and extensive expert interviews, has great value not only for, but also beyond the shipping industry. The empirical testing of the theoretical compliance framework adds further relevance to the findings, suggesting that while many factors may influence legal compliance, only one group of determinants, namely resource constraints, has enough relevance to be statistically significant. A contribution lies furthermore in not finding a statistically significant correlation between compliance behaviour and sanctions and enforcement, contradicting a major foundation of economic theory on compliance.

A further contribution to knowledge lies in systematically analysing and empirically testing the likelihood of modal shift in the Northern European seas. Systematising economic theories on legislation-induced modal shift from sea to other modes of transport is in itself a contribution, strengthened further by a thorough review of prior studies on the subject. Failing to find statistically significant empirical evidence on a shift in transport modes due to environmental legislation contributes importantly to the academic discussion and contradicts some of the model-based studies previously conducted. A further examination and comparison to economic theory again shows the importance of time in witnessing economic effects, a finding that should increasingly be considered by researchers in economic impact studies.

Differentiating among distinct types of shipping companies and investigating the role of company characteristics for effects and effectiveness of legislation is a particular strength of this study. While theoretical writings on the shipping industry highlight the differences in the business models of shipping companies, empirical studies on the costs of legislation have

overwhelmingly treated the shipping industry as one homogeneous group. This work contributes to the academic discussion in providing a thorough analysis of company characteristics potentially important for research on the industry. These are accumulated and critically reviewed based on data from prior studies and expert interviews. Statistical analysis shows that the average age of vessels under operation, as well as the type of ownership a company has over its vessels may influence legal compliance. A link between company characteristics and costs of environmental legislation could not be empirically found, but the theoretical framework on relevant company characteristics may prove helpful in further academic studies.

In combining legal and economic thinking, this thesis shows weaknesses in creating effective economic incentives to overcome market failure based on applied legal principles like the precautionary principle and the threshold of harm rule. Highlighting and discussing these weaknesses is a contribution of this research both to the academic and political debate on how to discourage companies from polluting the environment. Findings from this thesis support a call for a more economic foundation of environmental policy making.

Lastly, as an example of exploratory sequential mixed methods research, the current study highlights both advantages and challenges of conducting mixed methods studies. It contributes positively to the debate by showing a way to handle epistemological differences, to build upon the strengths of both methods to improve the quality of research and to augment the knowledge gained from combining different sources of data. The study also highlights challenges in adequately comparing the relevance of results gained from qualitative and quantitative sources.

8.3 Limitations

The present research was carefully planned and conducted. Adding to the limitations inherent in the research methods and addressed in Chapter 4.7, the applicability of results is discussed here. With the sample showing a bias towards larger-sized German and Danish shipping companies and nonresponse analysis indicating that companies prone to noncompliance, for example flying black-listed flags, are lacking from the sample, results are likely not representative of the total industry. Rather, results likely represent a conservative estimate particularly on noncompliance levels. Theoretical findings may prove to be relevant beyond the shipping industry. The applicability to sectors of the transport industry other than commercial freight shipping may, however, be limited due to specific industry characteristics. Freight shipping is a unique industry being global in nature, operating to some extent outside the boundaries of effective state control, consisting of a number of smaller, but also some very large and powerful players, operating to a large extent off the radar of public debates and being an industry with frequent personal contacts among its members. The legal impact mechanisms presented may thus only be applicable to a limited extent to inland navigation and freight transport on road, rail and in the air. Applicability to shipping companies in Southern Europe and beyond may also be limited, as one must look out for cultural differences, questions of mentality related to the main seat of operations, different legal requirements and practical enforcement by the flag states and different financial possibilities that the behaviour of shipping companies may be influenced by.

Future research on vessel-source pollution may overcome the above-named limitations to some extent by employing a larger team of researchers over a greater length of time. This may serve to increase the geographical scope of the study to an international one, to conduct both qualitative and quantitative data collection simultaneously to reach maximum comparability, to systematically analyse data by several researchers independently to further objectivise results of qualitative data analysis and to conduct similar studies on competing modes of transport like road and rail transport to support the development of a comprehensive transport policy.

8.4 Policy recommendations

Key findings of this work lead to several recommendations on how to improve environmental policy making for the shipping industry to increase effects and effectiveness of environmental laws. Firstly, transport services offered by shipping companies should be priced so as to reflect the true social costs to society, keeping in mind that such a pricing is only effective where all other modes of transport equally reflect their true social costs. The current environmental measures, though seeming to affect the costs of vessel owners and operators, are deemed to have a limited or delayed influence on freight rates and are thus unlikely to influence the choice of transport mode or the amount to be transported by customers. If environmental legislation does not influence customer choice, but cost increases are almost entirely absorbed by service providers, the required effects of legislation to effectively influence behaviour are hindered. It must be noticed that the findings of this thesis apply largely in the short term. Long-term effects of MEL on freight rates may be more noticeable. As it is, effects seem negligible and unlikely to induce shippers or cargo owners to ship fewer goods overall. Politicians need to be aware of this gap between theory and practice and should not count on a legislation-induced shift in the demand-and-supply framework shortly after legislation is passed. As patience is required for legislation to develop its full effect, a recommendation to politicians would be to start legislative endeavours early. A further recommendation lies in applying a holistic approach to transport planning, inducing all modes of transport to charge their true social costs and thus providing the right incentives for environmental protection. Seaborne transportation of goods should be considered as part of a larger system, where humans derive benefits both from a clean environment by way of ecosystem services as well as from the consumption of goods based on international supply chains. Considering all parts of the system, including all available modes of transport, and weighing the costs and benefits of bringing goods to consumers, keeping in mind that the consumer himself might be the cheapest pollution avoider, is considered here as a holistic political approach. Incentive structures should aim at maximising societal welfare. This might include not only the cleaner operation of vessels, but also an encouragement that society consume more locally produced goods.

With respect to the effectiveness of legislation, compliance has been shown to depend largely on company resources. Creating easy-to-implement, easy-to-understand legal rules may decrease this dependency, allowing for companies not so well endowed to fully comply with the laws. While sanctions and enforcement could not empirically be shown to significantly influence compliance with environmental legislation, it is seen as an important determinant in economic theory. Currently, port state officers select vessels for inspection mostly on the basis of flag state. A more differentiated enforcement approach might increase compliance levels,

raising the perceived likelihood to be controlled for all shipping companies. Also, with experts stating that the thoroughness of harbour state controls differed substantially, and that paperwork could easily be forged, better systems to check documents for authenticity and a better training of control officers may serve to increase compliance.

Recommendations to policy-makers on maritime environmental legislation are thus:

1. When wishing to develop environmental incentives, act early and be patient. Effects might show with a time lag of several years.
2. Apply a holistic approach to transport planning. The prices of all modes of transport should reflect their true social costs to set effective incentives.
3. Base policies on cost-benefit-considerations adopting a full cost approach. Consider the societal benefits of transporting goods as well as the societal costs when planning legislation.
4. Be courageous in supporting policies that will lead to an increase in overall societal welfare but may not be considered fair by all market actors. Try to identify the cheapest pollution avoider, instead of religiously following the polluter-pays-doctrine.
5. Be aware that vessels as moving sources of pollution are difficult to control and that noncompliance with environmental laws may be a financially attractive option for shipping companies. Invest in effective enforcement of laws to develop trust and provide a level playing field to all companies. Also, a coordinated European approach towards harbour state controls including common training and central monitoring of activities can help to establish a common quality standard in controls, making a shopping for more lenient authorities by shipping companies less likely.
6. Be aware that compliance depends on a company's endowment with resources. Counteract this relationship by providing easy-to-implement information packages on new legal measures to all shipping companies. Also, keep things simple when passing environmental laws.

8.5 Further thoughts

Maritime environmental legislation is qualifying as a complex problem, which may be deemed impossible to be studied in all its complexity. The current study focuses on effects on the shipping industry. Building on these findings, further studies may compare the costs incurred with benefits derived from legislation. It must be noted that studies on societal benefits of environmental laws are often limited to emission reductions and positive impacts on health. A more holistic approach needs to be adopted, also considering the benefits derived from transporting goods. Failing to adopt a full-costs-full-benefits approach to political decision-making will lead to incentive structures not aimed at maximising societal welfare. An important problem in this respect is that politics seem often not based on maximising societal welfare but adopting legislative measures that society perceives as fair. While not reaching optimal economic solutions, the polluter-pays-doctrine or the principle that everyone should carry the same burden may easily be sold to politicians and society alike. Suggestions by economists to identify the cheapest pollution avoider or burden the one with the higher cost-benefit-ratio are hard to reconcile with public opinion, despite likely leading to better societal results. Further

factors which need to be considered in this respect are the costs of policy making and the costs of social unrest. A suboptimal solution on which consensus is easily reached, which is cheaply implemented and prevents social unrest may eventually lead to lower societal costs than a solution deemed economically optimal. This “better” solution may incur additional costs from convincing politicians of its superiority (costs stemming from vast academic studies on the subject, for example), from implementing a solution that requires extensive information on individual cost structures, production processes, and incidences of pollution from individual companies, and lastly from societal unrest, when complex incentives structures are poorly understood and people feel treated unfairly. Despite contradicting economic logic, current command-and-control measures for cleaner shipping might thus not be entirely unsound, all things considered.

In the light of current media coverage on air pollution, like excess levels of particulate matter in EU cities and related bans on driving, environmental issues and their impact on health have become more high profile in recent years. Societal attention especially on clean air has increased, green political parties have gained hugely in elections lately²¹ and local authorities have introduced ever stricter solutions on managing vehicle traffic in cities, the London Congestion Charge²² being only one of many ideas to be copied. Harbour cities will certainly increase their efforts to control emissions from ports and vessels entering the city next. Further environmental legislation will likely be introduced in the years to come, driven by a public call for cleaner air and a cleaner environment. An important consideration often forgotten is not to look at the individual modes of transport but to consider emissions and societal costs over the whole transport chain, including trucks, railways and ships. This includes looking at pollution and congestion at transport hubs like ports or hinterland logistics centers. The guiding concern should be how to get goods and people from one place to another with the lowest levels of pollution, at the lowest cost, while still accounting for necessary demands like speed, flexibility, and reliability of transport. Only a big-picture-approach to transport policy making may lead to viable solutions. This includes an open mind to consider innovative approaches. Maybe goods do not have to be transported at the same time or using the same routes as people. With pipelines being the most environmentally friendly mode of transport, related to even less emissions per ton transported than shipping, maybe goods can be brought from the harbour to inner-city hubs in tunnels under the earth, thus limiting emissions and congestion on the city’s streets. Developments in transport drones can open new ways to think about logistics as well. These or other scenarios might be developed and fostered. However, this requires that politicians have the entire network of goods transports in view, not only individual providers of transport.

A problem lies not only in political decision-making not adopting holistic approaches, but also in political decision-making being limited to political boundaries. Politicians make decisions at the local and national level, sometimes at the regional and very seldomly at the international level (but here again, decisions made at the IMO like the introduction of a Baltic Sea NECA or often only applicable at the regional level). While politicians may only make decisions for the

²¹ The Greens have become the second-biggest party in Bavaria with 18.5% of votes in the October 2018 elections in Germany.

²² Amounting to £ 10.50 per day and vehicle entering the City of London plus an additional £ 10 for older vehicles (Toxicity charge).

territory they control, environmental effects know no such boundaries. Also, the international shipping industry barely knows geographical borders. An optimal approach to environmental legislation would thus have to be both holistic and international. Given current political developments, the timing for international agreement is particularly unfortunate. Luring trade wars between the United States and several other countries, including China, as well as tendency of this influential country to either leave or downplay the importance of international organisations, proxy wars in the Middle East, a weak European Union split over finance and refugees and dealing with Brexit, upcoming nations like Brazil deeply engaged in home-made trouble, and Russia and Turkey more engaged in alienating than uniting with other nations, provide little hope for courageous international endeavours. The effect of these political developments on the global shipping industry should be closely monitored.

8.6 Suggestions for additional research

The present work could be developed further and strengthened by broadening the sample geographically to include not only companies with a seat of operations in the areas of the Northern European seas, but also from Southern European, American, African or Asian shipping companies. According to experts, some of these might be more prone to noncompliance with legislation. A broadening of the sample might thus lead to more significant results and might help to validate the findings of this study.

Furthermore, a longitudinal study monitoring cost structures and freight rates of shipping companies over the next decade could prove helpful in identifying short- and long-term economic effects of legislation. The respective theoretical developments were described in this thesis, but an empirical test has not yet been attempted by researchers and could benefit policy makers greatly in highlighting differences between legal theory and economic reality. In consequence, transport policy making could be strengthened.

Next steps in compliance research would be the further development of indicators to describe latent variables and a further search for explanatory factors of compliance which are not represented in the theoretical framework so far. Also, statistical analysis based on a larger sample size would be valuable to improve the analysis of compliance drivers and to further the understanding of regulatory compliance as a measure to improve environmental legislation

In the course of this thesis areas of research have been touched upon that are yet lacking a thorough academic approach and an established and tested theoretical framework. The researcher thus suggests these for additional research:

- a) The possible design of effective noise pollution legislation for ocean-going vessels to protect marine species from increased underwater noise, particularly close to heavily frequented shipping lanes, as well as the economic effects of such legislation.
- b) The possible design of effective legislation to control pollution from maritime radars, including a thorough impact study of the health effects of such radars for humans, animals, and plants, as well as an identification of possible technical solutions to limit emissions from maritime radars. Lastly, a respective economic impact study.

- c) A possible divergence between compliance behaviour of shipping companies and legal enforcement by port state control officers, including the effectiveness of controls in different harbours, and the fit between offences committed and offences controlled.
- d) The likelihood of modal shift studied from the perspective of logistics companies, exploring freight rate developments shippers experience from different modes of transport and their individual determinants of modal choice.
- e) Developments in technical compliance options, including possible synergies between technologies, to identify economical and ecological best-practice solutions.
- f) An exploration of market-based incentive mechanisms to control all seven sources of vessel-borne pollution in a way that would encourage innovative environmental solutions.

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Annex A1: Ecosystem services

Source: adapted from Hassan (2005)

Figure 10-1: Total economic value of the Baltic Sea ecosystem services, adapted from Hassan (2005)

Annex A2: Network of actors

Figure 10-2: Network of actors in maritime environmental policy-making

Annex A3: Signatories of IMO Conventions

EU Member states	MARPOL Annexes					London Convention and Protocol		Antifouling Convention	Ballast water Convention
	I/II	II I	IV	V	VI	Conv.	Protocol		
Austria	x	x	x	x					
Belgium	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Bulgaria	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Croatia	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Cyprus	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Czech Republic	x	x	x	x	x				
Denmark	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Estonia	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x
Finland	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
France	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Germany	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Greece	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Hungary	x	x	x	x		x		x	
Ireland	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Italy	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Latvia	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
Lithuania	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
Luxembourg	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Malta	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Netherlands	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Poland	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	
Portugal	x	x	x	x	x	x			x
Romania	x		x	x	x			x	
Slovakia	x	x	x	x	x				
Slovenia	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Spain	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Sweden	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
UK	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
European Union									
Total	28	27	28	28	26	21	15	24	17
Non-EU European states bordering the North and Baltic Sea									
Norway	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Russia	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Total	30	29	30	30	28	23	16	26	19

Table 10-1: Signatories of selected IMO conventions

Adapted from: IMO Status of conventions by country, 24 October 2018, @ 2018 IMO. Reprinted with permission of IMO.

(<http://www.imo.org/en/About/CONVENTIONS/STATUSOFCONVENTIONS/PAGES/DEFAULT.ASPX>)

Annex B1: Interview guide for shipping companies

a) Guide for interviews with shipping companies

Preliminary Remarks

Aim of the study: The aim of this study is to determine unintended trade effects of current changes in environmental legislation for the shipping industry. A thorough study of the literature is followed by expert interviews. The results of these interviews will be used to draft questionnaires for acquisition of data from concerned parties. Primary and secondary data will be fed into an econometric model and will provide an insight on the magnitude of effects on trade.

Aim of this interview:

- Acquire knowledge on the key issues the shipping industry is dealing with regarding current environmental legislation.
- Discuss the significance of current environmental legislation for the industry and the consequences on costs and freight rates.
- Discuss a number of variables like vessel age and size that might influence the magnitude of trade effects.

Results will be anonymized.

May the interview be audio-recorded?

[Signature of acceptance form.]

I Professional background of interview subject

What is your **position**?

Since when have you been working in that area?

What are the **topics** that you are currently working on?

How have you acquired specific **knowledge on environmental legislation**?

II Information on the company

How many **vessels** does your company own and operate?

What **business sector** do you operate in?

What **kinds of goods** do you transport?

What **volume** do you move on your vessels?

What **flag** do your vessels fly?

Does your fleet currently undergo **changes** due to environmental legislation?

III Awareness of environmental legislation

What is currently being done to protect the marine environment and by whom?

Who are the most **active actors** in the field?

Who is currently **passing** new legislation?

Who is **enforcing** that legislation?

Who is trying to **advance** stricter rules, who is **opposing** stricter rules?

Who has **more power** when it comes to legislation?

Have environmental efforts been **increasing** in recent years?

What do you see **next on the agenda**?

The most important sources of pollution from vessel operation are dumping of waste, ballast water discharges, air pollution, toxic anti-fouling systems, noise pollution, sewage water pollution and discharges of oily water. Would you agree with these **categories**?

Which sources of pollution are currently **regulated the most**?

Which sources are currently **regulated the least**?

Which rules **occupy** you the most?

Which have the **largest cost-effects**?

Which **matter little in terms of costs**?

For the Baltic and North Sea, would you say that it is rather national, regional, European or international policy-making that is defining the field?

IV Acquisition of information on environmental legislation.

How well are ship owners and operators **aware** of new legislation?

Where do they get information on new rules for shipping operations?

*Do you consider it rather **easy or difficult** to acquire information on maritime environmental legislation? Why?*

*Does everyone in the industry have the **same level of information**? Explain.*

*Does the level of information depend on **company size**, e.g. number of ships operated?*

*Does the level of information depend on **type of industry**, e.g. bulk or general cargo shipping companies?*

V Compliance and enforcement

***How** will short sea shipping operators comply with current environmental legislation?*

*Is that **different** to bulk carriers, tankers or container carriers?*

*What kind of companies do you expect to **over-comply**?*

*What kind of companies do you expect to **violate environmental protection** rules partly or entirely?*

*What difference does the **size** of the company make for compliance?*

*What difference does the **business sector**, e.g. bulk or container make to compliance?*

*What difference does the **source of pollution**, e.g. air pollution or ballast water, make to compliance?*

*What difference does the **flag** make that the vessel is flying?*

*What difference does the **main seat of operations** make?*

*Is the **average age of the fleet** a good indicator for the environmental friendliness of a company?*

VI Technological development

*What are the **major technological innovations** that help shipping companies comply with environmental legislation?*

*Can they use these innovations on **all vessels**?*

*Where do ship owners **acquire information** on technological innovations?*

*Which innovations are **economically paying off**?*

*Do you know of any technological innovations that are currently **too expensive** to be employed?*

VII Effects of environmental legislation

*In what way is the **business model** of shipping companies affected by current changes in environmental legislation?*

*To what extent will **costs** for shipping operators increase in the coming years?*

*To what extent will **freight rates** increase in the coming years?*

*Are the **differences** between short sea shipping and other trades?*

*To what extent do you expect **differences in freight rates** for the Baltic and North Sea and other European oceans?*

*Why might it be harder for **smaller or larger companies** to adapt to the changes?*

*Is it easier or more difficult for **ferry operators** to adapt to the changes than for other trades?*

*Which type of companies will have it **the easiest**, which will struggle **the hardest** with environmental legislation?*

*In which way will the **amount and share of goods** transported by way of the sea be influenced by current legislative changes?*

*In which way will trade on the **Baltic and North Sea** be affected? Within the **European Union**? On a **worldwide scale**?*

*Which **commodities or industry sectors** will be particularly influenced?*

VIII Modal shift

*Is it possible to **transport goods on rail or road** rather than on your ferries?*

*What **kinds of goods** would that be?*

*What does that mean in terms of **costs and time**?*

*How significant are the **differences in freight rates**?*

*Will goods move **rather to road or to rail** transport? Why?*

*What kind of **effects on the environment** do you expect due to modal shift?*

*What kind of **economic consequences** do you expect due to modal shift?*

IX General situation of the shipping industry

*How do you generally assess the current **competitive situation** of the shipping industry?*

What **developments** do you expect for the upcoming years?

What are the biggest **chances and risks** for the industry?

Does environmental legislation play a significant role **compared to other risks**?

What **other topics** are currently occupying the industry?

X Further research

Are there any **other topics** that I have not been addressing, that I should take into consideration when researching the effects of maritime environmental legislation on trade?

What **other experts** should I be talking to?

Is there anything else of importance that you would like to **tell me**?

Annex B2: Interview guide for other interested parties

b) Guide for interviews with other interested parties

Preliminary Remarks

Aim of the study: The aim of this study is to determine unintended trade effects of current changes in environmental legislation for the shipping industry. A thorough study of the literature is followed by expert interviews. The results of these interviews will be used to draft questionnaires for acquisition of data from concerned parties. Primary and secondary data will be fed into an econometric model and will provide an insight on the magnitude of effects on trade.

Aim of this interview: Acquisition of a broader picture of the structure of the shipping industry, the significance of and knowledge about current environmental legislation as well as discussion of a number of variables that might influence the magnitude of trade effects.

Results will be anonymized.

May the interview be audio-recorded?

[Signature of acceptance form.]

I Professional background of interview subject

What is your position in this company and since when have you been working in that area?

(What are the topics that you are currently working on?)

Have you been working for the shipping industry at any point in your career?

Have you acquired specific knowledge on this industry?

II Information on the company

Specific questions on the company's relation to the shipping industry and environmental legislation, here as an example for the Chamber of Commerce:

How many shipping companies are listed at the Hamburg Chamber of Commerce?

Are all of them having their main operations in Hamburg?

Would all of them be flying the German flag on their vessels?

Do you offer special advice aimed at the shipping sector?

Do you advice on legal developments, e.g. changes in environmental legislation?

How significant is the shipping sector for your company?

III Awareness of environmental legislation

Are you aware of current political efforts to protect the marine environment?

What is currently being done to protect the marine environment and by whom?

Have these efforts been increasing in recent years?

What do you see next on the agenda?

[Introduce the graph on the seven sources of pollution: During their operation, vessels pollute the environment in a number of ways. These have been organized to fit seven categories as you can see in this graph. (Read the seven sources aloud)]

Would you agree with this classification?

Which sources of pollution are currently regulated the most?

Are there any sources that are currently underregulated?

Who are the most active actors in the field?

- *Who is most active in passing new legislation?*
- *Who is the most active in implementing and enforcing legislation?*
- *Who is most active in advancing stricter rules?*
- *Who is most active in opposing stricter rules?*
- *Who has the most power when it comes to legislation?*

For the Baltic Sea, would you say that it is rather national, Baltic Sea regional, European or international policy-making that is defining the field?

IV Acquisition of information on environmental legislation.

Are ship owners and operators well aware of new legislation?

Where do they get information on new rules for shipping operations? Is your company involved in the information process?

Do you consider it rather easy or difficult to acquire information on maritime environmental legislation?

Does everyone in the industry have the same level of information?

Does the level of information depend on company size, e.g. number of ships operated?

Does the level of information depend on type of industry, e.g. bulk or general cargo shipping companies?

V Compliance and enforcement

What percentage of ship operators do you expect to comply with current environmental legislation?

Do you expect certain companies to over-comply? What kind of companies would do that?

Do you expect certain companies to violate environmental protection rules partly or entirely? What kind of companies would do that?

Does it depend on the type of company, e.g. will smaller or bigger companies comply more readily?

Does it depend on the business sector, e.g. are bulk or container carriers more prone to non-compliance?

Does it depend on the source of pollution, e.g. will compliance in the one area be higher than in the other?

Does it depend on the flag that the vessel is flying? Are vessels flying flags of convenience more likely to violate the rules than vessels flying national flags?

Is the average age of vessels a good indicator of the environmental friendliness of a company?

VI Technological development

What are the major technological innovations that help shipping companies comply with environmental legislation?

Can they use these innovations on all vessels?

Where do they acquire information on technological innovations?

Which innovations are economically paying off?

Do you know of any technological innovations that are currently too expensive to be employed?

VII Effects of environmental legislation

In what way is the business model of shipping companies affected by current changes in environmental legislation?

Do you expect a significant increase in costs for shipping operators in the coming years?

Do you expect a significant increase in freight rates based on potential increases of costs? Are there large differences in freight rates for the Baltic Sea and other European oceans?

Is it harder for smaller companies or larger companies to adapt to the changes? Why?

Is it harder for container or bulk carriers to adapt to the changes? Why?

Which type of companies will have it the easiest, which will struggle the hardest with environmental legislation?

Will the amount and share of goods transported by way of the sea be in any way influenced by current legislative changes?

Do you expect any effects on trade on the Baltic Sea? Within the European Union? On a worldwide scale?

Will certain commodities or industry sectors be particularly influenced?

VIII Modal shift

Do you expect modal shift due to current legislation?

Will goods move rather to road or to rail transport?

What kind of effects on the environment do you expect due to modal shift?

What kind of economic consequences do you expect due to modal shift?

IX General situation of the shipping industry

How do you generally assess the current competitive situation of the shipping industry?

What developments do you expect for the upcoming years?

What are the biggest chances and risks for the industry?

Does environmental legislation play a significant role compared to other risks?

What other topics are currently occupying the industry?

X Further research

Are there any other topics that I have not been addressing, that I should take into consideration when researching the effects of maritime environmental legislation on trade?

What other experts should I be talking to?

Is there anything else of importance that you would like to tell me?

Annex B3: Leaflet “Studying unintended effects of maritime environmental legislation”

Studying unintended effects of maritime environmental legislation on trade - Application on the Specially Protected Area of the Baltic Sea -

Research setting:

- The common resource of the oceans is degraded by shipping activities while the shipping sector enjoys all the benefits. (Tragedy of the Commons)
- Initiatives of states to protect the coastal marine environment are enhancing, likely increasing freight rates for commodity shipping.
- Environmental legislation could have detrimental effects on trade and increase emissions via changes in mode of transport.

Research hypotheses:

- European environmental legislation has an effect on costs of ship owners employing their vessels on the Baltic Sea.
- Cost increases lead to increases in transportation prices for merchant shipping on the Baltic Sea.
- Increases in transportation prices lead to effects in the amount of goods transported on the Baltic Sea via loss of competitiveness and transmodal shift.
- Different types of vessels are *de facto* affected in a different way by the new rules, even if the rules do not apply differently *de jure*.
- Cost increases are influenced by advances in technology.
- Cost increases are influenced by the rate of non-compliance.

Logical structure of my PhD thesis


```

graph TD
    subgraph Stage1 [1 Investigation of environmental legislation influencing freight shipping on the Baltic Sea]
        L1[Review of the literature] --> I1[Identification of open questions]
        I1 --> IG[Interview guide]
        IG --> C1[Conduction of expert interviews (Qualitative study) aimed at various stakeholders to explore the problem]
    end

    subgraph Stage2 [2 Investigation of major cost drivers for ship owners as well as differences between different business models/types of vessels]
        C1 --> E1[Evaluation of interviews with MaxQDA]
        E1 --> I2[Identification of open questions]
        I2 --> Q[Questionnaire]
        Q --> C2[Conduction of a quantitative study aimed at ship owners]
    end

    subgraph Stage3 [3 Evaluation and prediction of transport cost developments on the Baltic Sea]
        C2 --> E2[Evaluation of questionnaires]
        E2 --> I3[Identification of major drivers]
        I3 --> EM[Economic model]
        EM --> D[Development of a simple economic model using SPSS to weight main influencing factors]
    end

    L1 --> E1
    I1 --> I2
    C1 --> E2
    I2 --> I3
    C2 --> D
    D --> F[Final conclusions]
    F --> T[Thesis submission and publication of results]
    
```

Personal details withheld.

Annex B4: Research Consent Form

Research Consent Form

No. 001

Principal Researcher: Thea Freese
B.A. Foreign Trade and International Management
LL.M. European and European Legal Studies
PhD Student at the Business School of the UWS in cooperation with the HAW

Research Title: Legislation on vessel-source emissions affecting trade on the European seas

PART 1: RESEARCH DESCRIPTION

You are invited to participate in a research study that explores the effects on trade of environmental shipping legislation. Your participation in this study requires an interview during which you will be asked questions about your opinions and attitudes relative to your experiences with environmental legislation in the shipping sector. The duration of the interview will be approximately 60 minutes. Approximately ten other experts will be asked to take part in the same study. With your permission, the interview will be audiotaped and transcribed, the purpose thereof being to capture and maintain an accurate record of the discussion. With your permission, your name will be used during the research process. In the absence of your permission, on all transcripts and data collected you will be referred to only by way of a pseudonym.

This study will be conducted by the researcher Thea Freese, a doctoral candidate at the University of the West of Scotland in cooperation with the University of Applied Sciences Hamburg. The interview will be undertaken at a time and location that is mutually suitable.

Risks and Benefits

This research will hopefully contribute to understanding the trade effects of legislation on vessel-source marine pollution and so the potential benefit of this study is the improvement of policies related to shipping emissions. Participation in this study carries the same amount of risk that individuals will encounter during any scientific discussion. There is no financial remuneration for your participation in this study.

Data Storage to Protect Confidentiality

Given your consent, you will be identified by name in the course of this research study, or in publications thereof. In the absence of your consent, you will under no circumstances whatsoever be identified by name in the course of this research study, or in publications thereof. Every effort will be made that all information provided by you will be treated as strictly confidential. All data will be coded and securely stored, and will be used for professional purposes only.

How the Results will be Used

This research study is to be submitted in partial fulfillment of requirements for the degree of a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), University of the West of Scotland, Paisley. The results of this study will be published as a dissertation. In addition, information may be used for educational purposes in professional presentation(s) and/or educational publication(s).

PART 2: PARTICIPANT'S RIGHTS

- I have read and discussed the research description with the researcher. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the purposes and procedures regarding this study.
- My participation in this research is voluntary. I may refuse to participate or withdraw from participation at any time without jeopardy to future medical care, employment, or other entitlements.
- The researcher may withdraw me from the research at her professional discretion.
- If, during the course of the study, significant new information that has been developed becomes available that may relate to my willingness to continue to participate, the investigator will provide this information to me.
- Any information derived from the research that personally identifies me will not be voluntarily released or disclosed without my separate consent, except as specifically required by law.
- If at any time I have any questions regarding the research or my participation, I can contact the researcher, Thea Freese, who will answer my questions. The researcher's phone number is [REDACTED], the email address is [REDACTED]. I may also contact the researcher's facility advisor, Professor John Struthers, at [REDACTED].

Personal details withheld.
- If at any time I have comments or concerns regarding the conduct of the research, or questions about my rights as a research subject, I should contact the University Ethics Commission (UEC) of the University of the West of Scotland. The phone number is +44 (0)141 848 3771 3980, the email address is pgr@uws.ac.uk. Alternatively, I can write to the Chair of UEC Professor Avril Taylor, University of the West of Scotland, High Street, Paisley, Renfrewshire, Scotland, PA1 2BE.
- I will receive a signed copy of the Research Description and this Participant's Rights document. A second signed copy will remain with the Principal Researcher.
- Audiotaping is part of this research. Only the principal researcher and the members of the research team will have access to written and taped materials. Please check one:
 - I consent to being audiotaped.
 - I do NOT consent to being audiotaped.

My signature means that I agree to participate in this study.

Participant's signature: _____ Date: ____/____/____

Name: (Please print) _____

Investigator's Verification of Explanation

I, Thea Freese, certify that I have carefully explained the purpose and nature of this research to _____ (Participant's name). He/she has had the opportunity to discuss it with me in detail. I have answered all his/her questions and he/she provided the affirmative agreement (i.e., assent) to participate in this research.

Investigator's signature: _____ Date: ____/____/____

Annex B5: Rules of transcription

Rules of transcription

The method of transcription will follow the conceptual notion of Kuckartz et al. to “smoothen” the language significantly and to focus on the content of statements made. (Kuckartz et al., 2007) Interviews will be transcribed fully in the origin language they were conducted in and will then be translated into English. Transcription will observe a system of rules that ensures consistent results closely following the approach by Dresing and Pehl. (Dresing and Pehl, 2013, p.21) Defining a system of transcription is of particular importance as the main researcher is supported in this work by a student assistant.

A. Rules of transcription

1. Transcription is done literally, as opposed to vocalizing or summarizing methods. Dialects are translated as accurately as possible into standard language. If no direct translation is possible, the term is kept in dialect.
2. Word reductions will not be transcribed. Instead, they will be converged to accurate language. “He’s bought ‘nother book” will be transcribed as “He has bought another book”; “hamma” will be transcribed as “haben wir”. The form of a sentence will however not be changed, even if grammatical mistakes are made, e.g. “I to supermarket went”.
3. The breaking-off of sentences or words as well as stammering will be smoothed or left out entirely. Doubling of words will only be transcribed if they constitute a stylistic device to emphasize certain aspects, e.g. “that is very, very important to me”. Half sentences, that are missing their ending, will be transcribed. They will be marked with a termination symbol: /
4. Punctuation will be smoothed in order to increase legibility. When the voice goes down a little or in cases of unclear intonation a full stop rather than a comma is put. Logical units shall however not be separated.
5. Pauses will be marked as follows: (...)
6. Verbal signs of the respective listener, like “mmh, yes, right, ah,...” will not be transcribed. EXCEPTION: An answer consists solely of a verbal note as aforementioned without further explanation. This will then be transcribed as “mmh (negative connotation)” or “mmh (positive connotation)”.
7. Specifically emphasized words will be marked by CAPITALIZATION of letters.
8. Each contribution by each speaker will receive an own paragraph. There are blank lines inserted at each change in speaker.
9. Time codes will be inserted at the end of each contribution by a speaker. They will be in accordance with the following format: #00:11:12-31#; #00:11:31-12:51#

10. Emotional, non-verbal expressions will be transcribed if they are important in underlining the message of a statement, e.g. laughing, sighing. They are noted in brackets.

11. Incomprehensible words are marked by: (inc.). In the German original language transcripts that will be (unv.). Longer passages that remain incomprehensible should be marked with the time code and a description of the cause, e.g. (inc., noise of a helicopter) or (inc., microphone humming). If one suspects a certain wording, but may not be sure, the word is put in brackets with a question mark, e.g. (scrubbers?).

12. The interviewing person is identified by an I:, the interviewee is identified by an E followed by the number of the interview, e.g. "E4". Statements by the interviewer are printed in italics.

13. The transcript is saved under the date and the number of the interview, e.g. 2014-10-31 – Transcript Interview 3.

B: Example based on the rules above

I: *Thus, something could still be done there? #00:22:19-21#*

E1: (After some consideration) That is one way of seeing it. #00:22:27-30#

I: *In which areas is – or does the political interest increase the most at the moment? #00:22:32-39#*

E1: (Long pause) Increase the most? I don't know. It is the largest with air and noise. And dumping of waste as well is always... especially in the media and the cruising industry... a topic, also for politicians. (Hesitant, slowly, with many intermissions) #00:22:50-23:06#

Annex B6: Interview transcripts and translated transcripts for interviews 1-12

Interview No 1

Date: Wednesday, 11 July, 3 pm

Contact history: Random encounter and conversation with the superior of E1 at a night event. E1 establishes contact a day later signalling a readiness to talk via email. A telephone conversation to establish a date takes place three weeks prior to the interview. During this conversation E1 names a number of other experts that would be worth talking to (see Annex).

Interview situation: The interview takes place with a 20 minutes delay due to a prior meeting in the office of E1. The air is warm and humid and the windows to the noisy street are wide open. The dialogue is however only little influenced by the poor interview situation. At one point during the conversation the phone rings. E1 looks at the display to see who is calling, but does not pick up. E1 is available for one hour.

The interview runs calmly and smoothly. Few interposed questions are asked and questions are answered in detail. Overall E1 tends to present things in a very generic fashion and likes to give very diplomatic, political answers. A number of questions are not discussed due to insufficient knowledge of E1 regarding a number of details and previous questions on some subjects issuing to nothing.

All in all E1 is friendly and tries to be helpful. He freely gives contact information for further experts and offers to address him again in case of further questions.

[Reception, information on the aim of the study as well as the interview, questions of the interviewee in the person of the interviewer, the supervisory situation and the relation to the UAS Hamburg and the UWS Paisley, signature of the Research Consent Form, assent to being audio-taped.]

I: *My first questions regard your personal background, so that I can better assess the information you are giving me. What are you doing at [organization 1]? In what position are you working and which topics currently occupy you? #00:03:07-26#*

E1: Yes, well. I am head of the department for energy and environment and am occupied with all topics in the area of energy and environment that are relevant for companies [in city A]. On the one hand – there are two important areas – the one are consultancy services for our member companies – companies have to be members of our

organization by law – and we consult on all the topics that are linked to energy and the environment. Energy efficiency, environmental legislation,... #00:03:26-56#

I: *So that as well...* #00:03:56-58#

E1: That as well, that is the one major area. The other major area is advisory services, you could say, in the other direction. Advising politics or representation of interests or lobbying, you can name it however you want. We simply deliver the topics that are important to the companies towards politics and administration. #00:03:58-4:15#

I: *Thus there are lawyers and economists working here?* #00:04:15-21#

E1: Yes, in [organization 1] as a whole yes. *(Drawled out and hesitant)* #00:04:21-23#

I: *And in this department...* #00:04:23-24#

E1: Unfortunately that is not true for my department. This department comprises those four that have just been sitting in this office plus me plus a secretary a part-time position and another currently vacant part-time position. That is the order of magnitude. Those are three engineers, a social scientist, I'm rather a social scientist as well – there are unfortunately no lawyers in this department and no economists either. #00:04:24-50#

I: *How does consultancy in environmental law work then?* #00:04:50-54#

E1: Well. *(Hesitant)* Well, first of all you don't need to be a lawyer in order to understand technical environmental laws or directives. Furthermore we are integrated in a network. We are first of all closely linked to our legal department here internally. Whenever there are issues, we include our colleagues and they investigate that for us. We regularly have legal trainees [Referendare], who come to us, who then also compile little advisory opinions and then there is of course the [umbrella organization of organization 1] that is then responsible for all the overlying topics, that then processes information and there is also some support there. #00:04:54-40#

I: *Okay.* #00:05:40-41#

E1: Still, in order to explain to a company how packaging regulations work, for example, or REACH in the area of chemicals, you don't necessarily need to be a lawyer in order to explain the things to the company that are important for them. Mostly, those are not legal facts, but rather how does that look in practical application and what do I have to pay attention to. #00:05:41-6:06#

I: *Have you ever had direct contact to the shipping industry in this area? Thus that you specifically dealt with environmental legislation for the shipping industry?* #00:06:06-17#

E1: We have contacts to the shipping industry. There is in [organization 1] a committee on harbour and shipping and a department with the same name – Harbour and Shipping. They are in [division a] and we are, as you can see, in [division b] and regarding shipping topics, or climate protection and environmental protection in the shipping industry, that

is always a cross-sectoral topic, where the leadership, however, is always in the environmental area. Plus... we have companies from that field [in our committees]. In our committees - committee on the environment and committee on energy - those are two different committees - there are for example people like Mr Eckelmann with the LNG power barges, I don't know if that tells you anything - those projects to avoid emissions here in [city A] - such people, harbour service provider, are members in our committees.

All the ship owners are serviced by the committee on harbour and shipping. Still, we have contacts for example to the VDR [Association of German Ship Owners], [inc.] Herr Plötzke, for example, who deals with that [environmental issues]. Also, we have contacts to the [city A] administration, we have contacts to the environmental organizations here in [city A], especially to the NABU – we talked about that on the phone, about that topic. Thus the most important actors are acquainted with us. #00:06:17-8:10#

I: *Have you personally ever worked in the area of shipping?* #00:08:10-14#

E1: No. #00:08:15-16#

I: *Just so that I know.* #00:08:16-18#

I: *How many shipping companies does your [organization 1] attend to? Do you know that?* #00:08:18-27#

E1: No. That I cannot tell you. All companies that are registered at this location are definitely with us, but I cannot tell you how many those are. Still, one can found out. #00:08:27-43#

I: *How important is the shipping industry compared to everything, that [organization A] does here?* #00:08:43-50#

E1: It is somewhat important. In [city A] everything centres a little bit around the harbour, the shipping industry. The harbour is the heart of [city A], let's say it like that, important for the economy of [city A]. Everything that goes on in [city A] is somehow connected to the harbour and to international trade and logistics. #00:08:50-9:14#

In this company we have different fields of competence. Some of them are... Well, a significant task of [organization A] is to maintain the vocational training system. Here in [city A], whoever takes vocational training, or in the whole of [country A], in the end takes an examination by [umbrella organization of organization A]. That is maintained by us. Furthermore we have a significant general service area. However, in the area of political work the harbour has been and the shipping industry has been; they have always been the most important. That was always what played a role at all the high level meetings and events. In the last years that changed a little, in the way that the topics that I'm in charge of, the energy topics, gained enormous significance. There are a number of meetings of politicians regularly taking place. Previously the harbour and transport

- were always at the top of the agenda and now that turns a little and mostly energy is more important. #00:08:50-10:29#
- I: *Still, it keeps playing a role... #00:10:29-31#*
- E1: Shipping always plays a role, clearly. Evidently also under aspects of energy or here aspects of the environment... #00:10:31-37#
- I: *The companies that are represented here, are those then companies that have their main seat of operations in [city A] or could that also be companies, shipping companies that have their main seat of operations somewhere entirely different? #00:10:37-47#*
- E1: Obviously. You have to, if you are registered here in some way, with a subsidiary or branch, then you are by law a member of [organization 1]. When you reach a certain turnover you have to pay a contribution to [organization 1] and then you are entitled to be our services, just like any company that have their head office here. Everybody may then, well, we have a general assembly and a parliament and so on, and everybody then has his voice, no matter if he has his main seat of operations here or not. #00:10:47-11:12#
- I: *That means one can expect that vessels that carry a flag other than the [country A] flag would also find their interests represented here? #00:11:12-31#*
- E1: When the ship owner is located in [city A] or has a subsidiary here or something like that, yes. Although, I don't know if you know the discussion that has been going on for many years, about the tonnage tax and outflagging and re-flagging. There are somehow agreements and alliances, I think it is even called Maritime Alliance or something like that, between the ship owners and the federal government. There the federal government promises to afford the so-called tonnage tax, that somehow comes with tax benefits for the shipping industry or the ship owners that are registered here in [city A] – sorry, [country A] – and that are flying the flag [of country A]. In return, the ship owners stand up for that, so to speak, or re-flag that and that many ships in the course of the years. I can't conjure that up correctly at the moment, as it is not my area of expertise, but maybe, if it is important for your work, you would have to google that. #00:11:31-12:51#
- I: *I'll do that. That means that everything that [organization 1] does for the shipping industry regarding services is split in principle between this department, when it relates to energy and environmental themes and the other department especially for the shipping industry. And they do what then? #00:12:41-13:13#*
- E1: You can say that. They do industry sector support, thus all advisory services and the contacts to the sector are maintained there. However, overall our work for the harbour and the shipping industry is first and foremost lobbying. #00:13:12-34#
- I: *Then it would also be interesting to talk to them. #00:13:34-39#*
- E1: Possibly, yes. #00:13:39-42#

- I: *Wonderful. #00:13:42-44#*
- I: *Which current political advances are known to you when we are talking about maritime environmental legislation? That is, what is it that is currently hotly disputed? #00:13:42-14:05#*
- E1: Currently hotly disputed are the IMO resolutions, that have been existing for a longer time, this MARPOL Annex VI, with these mandatory time frames that are adopted there and the ECAs and the SECAs and the considerations by the EU to bring on its way further legislation for Europe, if I remember that correctly. #00:14:05-40#
- I: *What are the interests there? How is that represented here at [organization 1], that discussion? Well, that is likely represented in the area of lobbying as well, that one tries to establish a common path? #00:14:41-58#*
- E1: That would be in the area of representation of interests. Roughly put, let's say in principle the shipping industry is one of the most environmentally friendly methods of transport that exist, compared to everything else. Therefore the shipping industry is first of all rather something "good" - in quotation marks. Nonetheless the shipping industry has to make its contribution to the global climate protection and environmental protection aims. Climate protection does actually always refer only to CO2 emissions. In the shipping industry rather other issues, or other issues play a role as well – sulphur, nitrogen oxides. But for all that the shipping industry simply has to make its contribution. We have only just started. We obviously see that in harbour cities like [city A], that there are problems with emissions and that something has to be done. We then say that it is not enough to enact stricter laws, but rather it would make sense to provide incentives to the companies and to motivate them to do something. There are some pilot projects in the area of voluntary self-commitment, that... #00:14:58-16:20#
- I: *Does that work? #00:16:20-20#*
- E1: ...are under way in the harbour [of city A]. Only both measures together are working. You don't always need - well certainly in some way, regulatory law or a legal frame in order to initiate the whole process. Still, in other areas, you should want to see for yourself, you don't reach the aim with regulatory law only. By that you only stall the activities. When it comes down to it, that leads to a situation where companies, that is not as extreme for the shipping industry, move away and settle down somewhere else, where requirements are not as strict. Well, you always have to take those along with you, those with whom you want to achieve something, as a politician. You somehow have to motivate them to do something. #00:16:20-17:06#
- I: *Do you get the feeling that there is a motivation there? #00:17:07-10#*
- E1: There is a motivation, but the financial resources are not necessarily there. I just wanted to mention that in principle for us, and also for the harbour of [city A], it is always very important that there are as little as possible regionally confined solutions and requirements. If the IMO does something that is good as it is in principle valid around

the world. If the EU now does something and defines SECAs and ECAs here for the North and Baltic Sea, that is evidently a competitive disadvantage for the harbours here in the North and also for [city A]. That is at least the fear of some ship owners, harbour companies, that the vessels do not unload their containers in the north range, in the north, for example, but rather go to the Mediterranean Sea - that the harbours there get more business, make more profits. At the same time containers, when they have to get from there to Poland for example, or the Czech Republic, are much longer en route on the streets than from [city A] and therefore the whole thing does not really lead to a more environmentally friendly solution. #00:17:11-18:27#

I: *Are there already signs for such developments?* #00:18:27-30#

E1: (After some consideration) I cannot really make a valid assessment of that, but what you have - and that has been going on for a while in companies - in [city A] you have basically two large cargo handling companies. The one is the HHLA, the municipal cargo handling company, and the other one is EUROGATE, the large [inc.] and they for example are a private company. They have been active, for four years, not only in [city A], but also in other European harbours and they have settled down there and started business activities there. Whether there are actual relocation effects, I think, that is very difficult to verify. If at all, then the VDR [German Shippers Association] will be the one when it comes down to it. Well, you should talk to Mr. Plötzke - I don't know if he is still with the VDR - in any case. #00:18:27-19:35#

I: *I tried to summarize everything that could be regulated. [Diagram showing the seven sources of pollution identified from the literature is shown to E1] That are seven different ways of pollution and we basically have been talking about pollution just now. If you look at those: Which are the ones that are currently being regulated? Which are the one that are maybe rather well regulated? Where might something happen still? Which are maybe under- or overregulated?* #00:19:36- 20:14#

E1: Right, I like that slide- how did you come up with this topic, if I may ask? #00:20:17-22#

I: *I read the newspaper and found it fascinating.* #00:20:22-24#

E1 Well, we have first of all been talking about air [pollution], that is where currently most things are happening, I think. In the area of noise there are also considerable things happening. I think there is now the environmental framework directive of the European Commission that is related however first of all to road traffic, I gather, I think to know. Next to IMO requirements there is the air quality directive of the EU. Here in [city A] that is mostly relevant for road traffic, but also for the shipping industry. Toxic anti-fouling systems is the area, I would suspect, that is the least regulated at the moment... #00:20:25- 21:20#

I: *Is that so?* #00:21:20-21#

- E1: Intuitively I would say that. Sewage water and yes, ballast water, dumping of waste, I would see that regulated soon. I know however, that there are at many places, for example at the IMO, or here in [city A] an entrepreneur, who is active in the area of patents and norms, that at many places there are intense discussions going on, and he [the entrepreneur from city A] always brings up the issue of ballast water, for example. Well, I would see that area as the least regulated. Air and noise are likely the most [regulated] and the other four somewhere in the middle. #00:21:22-22:19#
- I: *Thus, something could still be done there?* #00:22:19-21#
- E1: (After some consideration) That is one way of seeing it. #00:22:27-30#
- I: *In which areas is – or does the political interest increase the most at the moment?* #00:22:32-39#
- E1: (Long pause) Increase the most? I don't know. It is the largest with air and noise. And dumping of waste as well is always... especially in the media and the cruising industry... a topic, also for politicians. (Hesitant, slowly, with many intermissions) #00:22:50-23:06#
- I: *Who are the most active actors? Well, when you look at current legislation, who is – is it actually the EU or maybe rather actors in the Baltic Sea area or are most things happening at the international level?* #00:23:09-25#
- E1: I would say that it is the EU and certainly also the IMO, even if the EU is currently more active, I think, as far as I can assess that. #00:23:29-48#
- I: *Regarding implementation and enforcement – who is active there? Who does that?* #00:23:49-57#
- E1: A lot of topics in the areas of traffic, mobility and shipping are maintained by the German federal states and then that is primarily done by the competent federal authorities. #00:23:57-24:14#
- I: *That means that it is then in principle the administration of [federal state A] that enforces legislation here?* #00:24:14-18#
- E1: Also implements it, exactly. Due to the fact that it is a multi-step process in which you have national laws and statutes, in Berlin or Bonn, and then the effectuation by the authorities here in [federal state A]. #00:24:18-38#
- I: *Does that work effectively? Do you know that? If you think of a tanker travelling on the Baltic or North Sea...* #00:24:39-50#
- E1: I think, I don't know. I cannot tell whether there is absolute efficiency. I assume, and I would say, that it works in any case more efficiently than in most other harbours of the world and also in the EU. #00:24:52-25:07#
- I: *Who tries most actively to push through stricter regulation?* #00:25:14-20#

- E1: That are certainly the environmental organizations. #00:25:23-24#
- I: *Do you know who... is it the NABU?* #00:25:25-27#
- E1: That is the NABU, right. Have you been in contact with them... #00:25:28-32#
- I: *I'm not yet supposed to start interviewing... (laughing)* #00:25:33-34#
- E1: Okay, well, but you should do that in any case... #25:35-37#
- I: *Yes, right, they are on my list.* #00:25:37-41#
- E1: Mr. Porschke is their chairman and you could talk to him in person, I would think. #00:25:41-47#
- I: *Are there others that are also active, apart from the NABU, or do you hear most about them?* #00:25:48-52#
- E1: I think the NABU is the most active. Apart from that the BUND traditionally plays a significant role in the city and also the WWF. #00:25:53-26:04#
- I: *Yes, wonderful. Who is the most active in trying to prevent regulation in this area?* #00:26:04-11#
- E1: (after a period of thought) Well, as industry representative I obviously don't think that the term "to prevent" is a very lucky phrase. I would rather say, in the sense of, enforced "reasonably and regarding global competitive relations". That would then probably be the associations on the other side, namely principally the VDR, who naturally becomes active for his members, the same as the NABU does it on the other side. #00:26:25-27:09#
- I: *Could one say who or what has more force in the legislative process?* #00:27:09-15#
- E1: There exist certainly very different positions on that. The environmental organization, they naturally always say that the industry organizations have more weight, as they have more possibilities, also financially. Whereby, I am certainly not referring to bribery or something like that when saying financial possibilities. These things that you know from television, maybe, do not exist, in my opinion. The industry organization that is operated by ship owners, can organize some larger events. They can do nicer parties. Still, I would say that especially in [city A] the role and influence of environmental organizations should not be underestimated. That is due to the fact that they have a very significant influence mainly on the public opinion and on the media and thus very intensively, positively reach the population. I'm just remembering – tomorrow, no, Friday there is an event organized by the NABU, I think, climate protection in the shipping industry or something like that. Do you know about that? #00:27:17-28:32#
- I: No... #00:28:32-33#
- [E1 catches an information sheet on the mentioned event from a neighbouring office]*
#00:28:33-29:19#

- E1: Well, Green Harbour Congress [Grüner Hafenkongress]. #00:29:20-22#
- I: *That sounds exciting.* #00:29:22-23#
- E1: That might be something for you - with Mr. Porschke, Mr. Bütikofer from the Green Party and further industry and all kinds of other representatives. #00:29:23-36#
- I: *May I have that?* #00:29:37-39#
- E1: No, as we just have the one, but if you want to write down the contact details, you could call and ask how to register directly. #00:29:40-50#
- I: *Yes, I'll write that down just now.* #00:29:50-52#
- E1: Anyway, if you say that you are writing a thesis on that and so on, nobody will say anything against that. #00:29:53- 58#
- I: *Yes, that is interesting. Wonderful. I would have some questions regarding how environmental legislation may actually be enforced and how many comply with it. Could you estimate the proportion of ship owners and operators that actually comply with all rules? Is that difficult?* #00:29:58-30:28#
- E1: That would be convenient! (laughing) #00:30:28-28#
- I: (Laughing) That would be convenient? #00:30:29-29#
- E1: No, I can't. I don't think that you can even determine that. How would you want to do that? Either you have to ask the monitoring agencies, but they naturally only have samples. And when you talk to the concerned parties, everyone will evidently say, sure, we comply with everything. That is evident. I would assume, that environmental laws and regulations here in Germany and by that also in [city A] are complied with to 90-95%, simply because the controls work correspondingly well. #00:30:30-31:11#
- I: *Are there companies that have a tendency to overcomply with environmental legislation?* #00:31:11-14#
- E1: They exist, obviously. A number of shipping companies try to establish a name with that. Well, the AIDA for example, they always advertise with and for the fact that they run particularly environmentally friendly. #00:31:18-34#
- I: *Well, that is in the area of cruise shipping. Does that exist in trade, in merchant shipping?* #00:31:34-38#
- E1: Not that I know of. #00:31:40-42#
- I: *Okay.* #00:31:42-43#
- E1: All of that is however... that is a subjective assessment. Hence you cannot take that as the absolute truth, you would have to ask other people and other companies. Evidently. #00:31:36-59#

- I: *These 5-10% of companies, that tend rather not to comply – who would that be? What characterizes those companies? #00:31:59- 32:08#*
- E1: I cannot really clearly say. As NEVER everyone follows the rules. #00:32:10-17#
- I: *Could you say that it somehow depends on the company size? Is it easier for bigger than for smaller companies to comply with the laws? #00:32:18- 27#*
- E1: Probably yes, surely. Certainly. I would say, although I only know that from other areas, that there is a large number of laws and regulation in the environmental field, especially in the environmental field. And as I mentioned the example with the packaging regulation, there are often small companies affected and medium-sized [companies], that don't even know about it, as they don't have personnel who could engage themselves with that. We are there for companies like that. The situation in the shipping industry – is probably a little different, as there are not really very many very small companies that then play a role for the industry. #00:32:28-33:11#
- I: *Are there differences according to type of ship, thus are there differences between someone operating a container vessel and someone operating a bulk carrier, that one can discover a tendency that they handle environmental protection differently? #00:33:15-31#*
- E1: I think so. I think that all vessels that first of all carry passengers and not containers or goods, that they handle the topic with more sensitivity. On the one hand precisely because they transport passengers, and when you talk a look at [city A], to the harbour of [city A], then you have the issue of different berths. Cruise ships are located very close to the harbour. The harbour is inside, with the residential buildings. Container vessels are not so much situated there, thus the cruise ships are more relevant and more sensitive. #00:33:32-34:12#
- I: *And regarding commercial vessels among another? Could you say that container vessels are usually newer and more environmentally friendly than bulk carriers or something like that? Or is there rather no tendency? #00:34:13-27#*
- E1: I would not say that. I think, however, well I assume that the colleague here with us could not really help you there either. There would then be the VDR [German Ship Owners Association]... #00:34:27-40#
- I: *Yes well. We have been touching on the topic of flags already – is there a tendency that you can say that those flying the Liberian flag pollute currently more than those, that fly the German flag? Or would that be, for example on the Baltic Sea, irrelevant at the end? #00:34:44-35:02#*
- E1: I would not say it like that. The flag, that is first and foremost an issue of costs, but concerning labour costs, as far as I understand it at least, but not necessarily linked to environmental laws. Plus, if we travel through European waters, I think, there are no big differences. You should also talk to the ministry of transport, as they are the shipping people in Bonn, thus it is imperative. #00:35:02- 30#

- I: *Yes, I will do that. One, certainly the most important issue for me in the end, are effects on trade. Are there or do you see impacts due to current environmental legislation, that influence the business model of the shipping companies? Is that somehow perceptible or measurable? Or is there basically hardly any influence? #00:35:30-36:01#*
- E1: I don't know if it is perceptible or measurable, but the legislation that is currently planned by the EU or is in force for European harbours certainly has effects on international trade and those who operate it. In such a way that for those, the bunker costs or whatever else are higher. #00:36:02-39#
- I: *Thus you can speak of an increase of costs in any case? #00:36:40-45#*
- E1: Evidently. #00:36:47-47#
- I: *Is that so? Can you say that that has an influence on freight rates or is the market so... is the market subject to such strong competition, that that actually only has an influence on the costs and not on the freight rates? #00:36:48-37:04#*
- E1: That certainly also affects the freight rates, as you have the shipping transport, no matter how environmentally friendly it is, that is understood to be without alternatives up until a certain point. If you now have all the [imports?] from the Far East and so forth, they cannot come by air plane and also not by train. But the question then is, where do they land here in Europe and how are they transported forward from there? And if they - there the issue of the increased depths of the Elbe [Elbvertiefung] also plays a role to some extent, I don't know, if that is relevant for your work, but if a container is then not unloaded in [city A], but in Rotterdam and has to go to the Czech Republic, it is simply so an so many kilometres more transported by truck and not on the ship – and thus that also has effects on the vessel freight rates. Certainly. #00:37:06-38:02#
- I: *Is that the obvious choice? Would one then shift volume to the street or rather to the rail or how is that... #00:38:02-11#*
- E1: There you also have to look the numbers up on the Internet, from the HPA, Hamburg Port Authority, and from the HHM, Hamburg Hafen und Marketing, how exactly the hinterland traffic is processed in [city A]. The majority is transported by truck, as it is simply not possible with the train, due to technical reasons due to connectivity. #00:38:12-39#
- I: *And my next question – if you look at the Baltic Sea, well, then you would for most routes actually have all three possibilities, you can always... #00:38:40-49#*
- E1: You can go through the Kiel Kanal with small feeder vessels, which is cheaper, but naturally takes a longer time, certainly, well, as a matter of fact you certainly have different alternatives. #00:38:49- 39:06#
- I: *We just said – that has effects on the international currents of trade, but also on trade flows within Europe. How significant is that really? Is that a huge problem that is coming on to us or is it actually only two containers? #00:39:12-42#*

- E1: That is certainly not a huge problem and it certainly would make sense, for many current transports, to think about whether they are very necessary, especially for global transports from the Far East or also from wherever within Europe. Well, meanwhile that depends to some extent on us, the consumers... The question is basically: What do we need? How much do we want to pay for that? Anyhow, with respect to these large relations, I think it is not really relevant. But then, I meant that first of all for transports within Europe, it would play a certain role, if there would be different requirements in... #00:39:45-40:35#
- I: *Well, they exist – especially for the North and Baltic Sea they are already there.* #00:40:35-38#
- E1: Yes, exactly. That is the fear there, or the assumption, that by that more traffic is going via [inc.]. Whereby you will likely have a lot of trouble coming up with reliable numbers. But, as I said, the VDR [German Ship Owners Association], they certainly have everything that is available at hand. #00:40:38-41:05#
- I: *What kind of consequences would that have on the environment, if everything would be processed via the Mediterranean or a significant amount more of goods traffic?* #00:41:06-17#
- E1: Well, when the people have different environmental rules, when it comes down to it, that would lead to the same environmental and climate pollution taking place, just somewhere else. Furthermore, in addition to what was said before, additional emissions will occur due to the hinterland traffic. That is due to the fact that a container cannot be transported such a long way into the country like before to [city A], but will rather [strand?] in some Mediterranean port and will then be transported forward by truck. Because the rail, I think, is withal most efficient here in Germany, but there, in the south of Europe, there is not an awful lot of goods transported by rail. #00:41:18-42:09#
- I: *Are there specific types of goods that are concerned by this more than others?* #00:42:09-13#
- E1: The more time-sensitive and the more valuable the goods are, the more often they are transported by truck. #00:42:17-27#
- I: *That means that it would be rather the goods that currently are transported long distances on board ships, the not-so-valuable, non-so-time-sensitive, that would then suddenly be transported on trucks? Or not?* #00:42:29- 48#
- E1: (after a period of thought) After all, that is likely, if they don't have a feasible alternative any more. #00:42:51-55#
- I: *To put that in perspective: We have now talked the whole time about environmental legislation. If you now compare this to other chances and risks that are relevant for the shipping industry at the moment. Is environmental legislation the topic number one or the the shipping industry occupied by... do they currently have different worries?* #00:43:06-30#

- E1: That is again rather a question for my colleagues from the harbour and shipping department. I think it is not the dominant theme. But it certainly plays a large role. #00:43:34-51#
- I: *Are there other topics that I have not considered, that I should take into account in the further continuation?* #00:43:57- 44:08#
- E1: Nothing comes to my mind straightaway. I think it is an exciting topic, but I'm not sure how far you will get with that. Still, otherwise it would be boring. I think it would be important if you talk to as many people as possible no in the beginning. Well, and then take out the most important points and then do your own research. #00:44:13- 44#
- I: *Exactly, and that is also my next question - the different people. We have talked about that a bit already: Who are the most important experts? Who can you recommend that I should talk to?* #00:44:46- 58#
- E1: Well, some I already mentioned. The VDR [German Ship Owners Association] in any case, the NABU in any case and the ministry of transport in Bonn – they are located in Bonn. And then, from [city A] well, the people that are responsible for the environment, in the council for the environment, I'm not entirely sure if they can actually contribute a lot. However, you can talk to the harbour administration, the HPA [Hamburg Port Authority], in any way. There you can get in contact with Mr. Dierke for example, he does company development, pass on kind regards from me - he can certainly tell you who would be the right person, if it is not him himself. You should talk to the two large cargo handling companies here in the harbour, the HHLA and EUROGATE. You should definitely talk to a few ship owners. You will find the most important ones in our member list for the committee on harbour and shipping, that is in the internet. I don't know if they all know me, but if you say, you have been at [organization 1], then talks should come about. #00:44:58- 46:33#
- I: *Is there – well, I have been thinking, I cannot talk to everyone – who is the most interesting? What kind of differences do I have to keep in mind? Is it important to talk to small and large ones, for example of with some, that do only bulk shipping? Where are the important differences?* #00:46:35-47:01#
- E1: I don't know. Maybe you talk to Mr. Plötzke first, for example, and he will give you further indications. I don't know if they exist, the significant differences, I could not tell you. #00:47:09- 26#
- I: *I will find out.* #00:47:26- 27#
- E1: Well, now someone else came to my mind, yes, I believe you should talk to the HWWI, the Hamburg World Economy Institute. They always have quite a good overview when it comes to trade but I don't know exactly, who is the right person now. Mr. Bräuninger, he is currently the director of research, is leaving the HWWI. Now there is a new head, the successor of Mr. Straubhaar – I don't know, if you knew him – [inc.] and his successor is an energy researcher. But you could address Mr. Bräuninger, for example

– [organization 1] is an associate also of the HWWI together with the University of Hamburg and there you could look in any way. And else... yes, well, what would also make sense – there is a confederation of enterprises of wholesale and export trade, short AGA. That is a nationwide association, but they are located here in [city A]. Mr. Kruse is the manager; he is sitting in our general assembly. You should contact him at one point, I think. Yes, well, that is all that I can think of. #00:47:27-49:03#

I: *My last question – Do you want to tell me anything else? Something, I have not been asking about? #00:49:04-11#*

E1: No, I don't think so. Well, as you have noticed, I'm not really familiar with some of the topics. That is in some part due to the internal processes here. I concentrate first of all on energy policy and shipping and environmental concerns are a crosscutting issue. But that is also a very complex issue - and that connection of the two topics, you talk about international trade and environmental protection – that can really be a market gap for you, as I don't know who has already dealt with that intensively at the moment. Well, in [city A] it plays a role first of all, at least to my knowledge, within my circles, if it relates to questions of regulatory power here in the harbour or innovative projects and models. There is currently a very intensive discussion about shore side electricity; that the vessels are plugged into the socket. Or are supplied by small barges and that these barges are then not fuelled with diesel, but with liquid natural gas, LNG. Such things are under discussion. But this connection, it is possible there is not a lot there so far. That would be good for you. #00:49:13- 50:39#

Annex: Experts named by E1 at a telephone conversation on 11.06.2014

- Shipping expert from the HSBA (Prof. Dr. Onestis Schinas)
- VDR – German Ship Owners Association (Mr. Plötzke)
- NABU – Environmental Protection Alliance (Mr. Siegert, Mr. Porschke)
- Ship owners
- Carriers/Forwarders/Shippers
- Trade association (AGA)
- BDI – Forum for industry transporting on the Seas

Interview No 2

Date: Wednesday, 24 September 2014, 11am German time

Duration: 77 minutes

Method of contact: Private contact existed to a German employee of C2 prior to the interview. Information on the interview process was provided via email to said employee on 29 August 2014 asking for support to establish contact to experts within the company. Contact details for three experts were provided on 1 September 2014. Contact via email to two of these experts that were recommended by the private contact in a personal

conversation on 2 September 2014 was established on 5 September 2014. An affirmative answer by E2 was received on 6 September 2014. The date for a telephone interview was set at 24 September, 10 am and was subsequently changed to an hour later.

Interview situation: The interview was conducted via telephone due to the expert being situated in the UK. The expert came directly out of another meeting and was running ten minutes late. Also, the interviewer could not directly establish an international connection and had to change office twice before said connection could be established. The interview thus took place in settings unfamiliar to the interviewer. Also, the office where the first half of the interview took place was needed by its owner. Thus the setting had to be changed after 40 minutes. Another 37 minutes of interview were conducted in other office. That led to disruptions in the interview flow, but a positive atmosphere could be established again after the break. In the second office street noise was a little distracting to the interviewer, before a window could be closed after about half of the time.

In general, the expert was very calm and supportive throughout the interview, providing information freely as well as he could and willing to discuss all topics that were addressed. The expert is knowledgeable on the majority of issues discussed and able to give illustrative examples from his daily work to support his point of view. E2 is very focused on providing the information requested and does not drift away from the topics discussed. He has no apparent political opinion towards the developments and discussed from a very technical, unemotional point of view.

E2 is not able to name further experts in the field, but he offers freely to be available if further information is needed.

[Interviewer introducing herself briefly and asking if there were any remaining questions before the start of the interview.]

E2: I've read your brief. It's all understood. So, nothing from my side I guess. #00:00:00-11#

I: *Okay. I received the research consent form. The only thing you didn't do is tick the box if you consent to being audio-taped.* #00:00:11-19#

E2: I do. Yes. #00:00:19-21#

I: *Okay. Perfect.* #00:00:21-22#

E2: Do you want me to do it again? #00:00:22-23#

I: *No, you don't have to. I can put that on tape and then that is fine.* #00:00:23-30#

Okay, perfect, than let us start. Well, the aim of this interview, as I already wrote to you, is to acquire a little knowledge on the key issues the shipping industry is dealing with at the moment regarding environmental legislation and then also to discuss the significance of that legislation for the industry regarding consequences on costs and freight rates. And then I have a number of variables like vessel age, size and others that I would like to talk to you about. The results of this interview will be anonymized completely, so nobody will know that it was you I was getting the information from. #00:00:30-01:19#

Just to get a little bit of background: What is your position within [organization 2] and since when have you been working in that area? #00:01:19-32#

E2: Okay. I'm a consultant in [organization 2], so I work for the marine business. And within marine we have an environment and sustainability group who looks after, I would say, both current and emerging environmental and sustainability requirements, either regulatory or non-regulatory, for shipping. #00:01:32-02:08#

I: *What happens with the results of your work?* #00:02:08-11#

E2: The results of our work are both internal-facing and external-facing. External results would be obviously, you know, consultancy-work, so projects done on behalf of plants, which could be most of the times quite bespoke. So we are taking an environmental issue or challenge which affects a certain plant in a certain way and we try to come up with a solution. This will be a report, an impact-assessment, a socio-economic assessment, anything that a client really wants to... #00:02:11-49#

I: *And a client would always be a shipping company?* #00:02:49-52#

E2: The business client would be from the shipping supply chain, I would say, so it could be a ship owner and also a ship owner-operator or monitor or it could be a technology provider as well. Or it could be a port authority. So we are not really limited to ship

companies. But because our main business are marine classifications, our main client base is ship owners/operators. #00:02:52-03:26#

- I: *Okay. What are the topics that you are currently working on?* #00:03:26-29#
- E2: Currently, because a lot of what we do is driven by regulation, a lot of our work is around ballast water management convention and the various implementation issues or challenges, technology selection, technology challenges around that. The other one is exhaust emissions, SO_x and NO_x requirements, again both regulatory implementation, but more importantly the technology challenges around that, the compliance challenges, ship recycling, this is another area we look into, waste management, different waste streams on-board ships, where there is a traditional household of waste and grey water and all that. And CO₂ related regulation requirements, so for example we get involved with [inc.] and monitoring and reporting and verification. Emerging [inc.] requirements within the EU. That is pretty much it in a nutshell. #00:03:29-05:01#
- I: *Okay, thank you. Just to make sure how your interests lie: Have you been working for the shipping industry at any point in your career?* #00:05:01-10#
- E2: I've been working - it depends how you define shipping industry – by background is naval technical marine engineering and I have been working in the marine industry for my entire career. I used to work for a marine consultancy in the past and I have been with [organization 2] for the past four years. #00:05:10-33#
- I: *Thank you. The first block of questions I have is regarding the awareness of companies on environmental legislation. So, it is basically what you said before: What is currently done to protect the marine environment and who are the main actors, who are currently doing something?* #00:05:33-59#
- E2: I guess, you know, it is not easy to put the shipping industry in one big box and read everyone the same. But, the majority of companies, I would say, in my experience, maybe 80%-90% of companies that either own or operate ships, what they do is very much driven by what they have to do, which is regulation. So that is the first part of the answer. The second part of the answer: Of course you have got some industry leaders or industry pioneers that will go beyond compliance in various different ways, but even those who do that, they do that because they recognize the commercial ... or they have found ways to gain commercial advantage from going beyond compliance. 00:05:59-07:16#
- I: *So how would you characterize those ship owners that go beyond? What kind of companies are those?* #00:07:16-25#
- E2: I think that, I would say it is the big shipping companies that first of all have the resources to implement various initiatives. It is about resources, it is always about being in a good financial position as well, but in the shipping industry that is very flexible and it can change overnight. So, in a way, it is those companies, strategically, they look

beyond compliance, they want to be the industry leaders, they have resources. Typically it is not the company with one ship. #00:07:25-08:11#

I: *You said that it could change overnight if you belong to the effluent ones. How is that?* #00:08:11-17#

E2: No, I don't... What I'm saying is: It is not necessarily the financial position of the company that would determine if it would go beyond compliance or not. Because this would be, you know, the shipping market is so dynamic that a company's balance book could change overnight almost. What I mean by that is that the companies look at that from a strategic point of view. So they have a long-term strategy and environmental sustainability is a big factor. And the strategy and is not limited to "I will comply", because "I will comply" is not really a strategy, it is the licence to operate. So what I am saying is, there is a vast majority that will comply with whatever is out there, because that is their licence to operate. And let's say the top-end of the market, they have a strategic plan and view and have found ways to gain commercial advantage if they are doing things beyond compliance. #00:08:17-09:30#

I: *What percentage of ship owners would you expect not to comply?* #00:09:30-35#

E2: (thinking) I don't have any answer to that. (laughing) I think, I would say zero. I mean, if you would not comply occasionally it could be because of something which is beyond someone's control, in some situation which has to be rectified. But with, I don't think, you know, in this day and age, there is a lot of ship owners out there who would choose willingly to cheat and not to comply, because they would be driven out of business. Again, we are trying now to put commercial shipping into a whole big basket and we treat everyone the same... #00:09:35-10:30#

I: *So if there are differences - what kind of companies are most likely to violate the rules?* #00:10:30-36#

E2: I think it is companies that you, I and no one else have ever heard about and never will. They are invisible shipping companies. They have one ship, one or two ships, which are either very old, maybe chosen willingly to operate not internationally, but maybe in a more restricted area of operation, they would probably choose a non-trustworthy or less trustworthy flag, they would probably choose a class society which is not a member of IACS [International Association of Classification Societies] and that you and I have never heard of. I don't think, you know, that companies who operate – certainly - within European waters, which I understand is your area of interest in your research, I don't think you find companies that would willingly try to escape compliance. #00:10:36-11:46#

That is not to say that, that there would not be non-compliance incidences, which will be discovered by port state control, but personally I do not believe that these happen willingly. They happen as a result of an accident, as a result of an oversight. But I don't think that strategically these guys have chosen not to comply. #00:11:46-12:14#

- I: *I just heard at a conference that ship owners expect very little controls, though, on SOx, for example. So when they would be travelling the Baltic Sea nobody is going to stop them in the middle and control them, right? #00:12:14-32#*
- E2: Yes. This is something that is being discussed a lot and I think it is the very concern that responsible ship operators have, because being compliant with the requirements means very high additional operating costs, costs of fuel, costs in equipment. So they are thinking that, okay, you know, if we do that, obviously, it puts a huge strain on our business and we have to do it, but isn't it unfair that there will be some out there that will never get caught? And I think this is the very alibi of associations, simply because how can you [release?] a ship with 60-70 miles off shore. I mean, port state control will enforce this to the extent that they can, but there are practical difficulties in inspecting every single ship. And how the industry is going to go around this – and we see that there are a lot of technical solutions being put on the table – but is really up to each country, each flag state to come up with strategies to enforce. And these strategies mean investment - in equipment, in resources. So, the law is there and the requirements are there to serve a purpose, which in the case of emissions is to protect the local population and mitigate [inc.?] effects. But enforcement is an entirely different matter. And with most European countries right now still under financial pressure and pressure to cut resources – most governments are in this kind of place – so it would be a challenge to enforce this very rigorously. And maybe that, and the knowledge of that fact, would motivate some companies, some of the companies which have been mentioned before, to say “oh, you know what, maybe we can [try that out here?]. But to me this is all speculation and right now I do not think that there is evidence that this will be happening. #00:12:32-15:10#
- I: *You said that the size of the company would also make a lot of difference so that larger companies would have it a lot easier to comply. Why is that? #00:15:10-25#*
- E2: The requirement is the same for everyone. I guess it is a case of resources. #00:15:25-36#
- I: *Is it also a case of information maybe? Do they have more information or better information on what can be done or what they are supposed to do? #00:15:36-47#*
- E2: I'm not sure about that. I think the information is out there. If anything, we suffer from an over realm of information. I think the larger companies they have the resources to interpret that information better and to develop their strategies and their procedures for implementation. And just to give you a very simple example: You know, we received this morning an enquiry from a client saying: I need your help with this whole ballast water implication. I have ordered all your guidance notes and overview material that was publicly available and a number of publications on how to comply – from an equipment point of view, from a convention point of view – what is the difference between U.S. and IMO regulations, all that. So he said, I've read all that - I have all that, but I just don't have the time to go through it. Can you just summarize everything that happens in one page? And I guess our answer was: Actually no, because it is so complex.

That is the reason why we are having all these publications. But it is quite indicative of the pressure and the resource constraint most organizations or shipping companies, ship operators are faced with. They just don't have the time to assimilate this information. And let alone translate it into actions within their company. #00:15:47-17:30#

I: *Does it make it a difference which source of pollution we are talking about? Is it easier to comply with ballast water rules than to air pollution rules or are all of them equally difficult to comply with? #00:17:30-47#*

E2: I think some of them are more difficult than others. A, because the requirement may have a lot of different interpretations and a lot of different clauses, so one thing is about the text. And when it comes to air pollution and exhaust emission the text is pretty simple: What you need to do is just make sure that you use the correct type of fuel. So the understanding of what one is to do is very simple. But the application is challenging from a cost point of view. So the difficulties will be simply, well: I'm a ship operator, I'm having a cross channel route, I don't need you Mr. [E2], I don't need you Mr. regulator to tell me what to do, I know what I need to do, but the fact of the matter is: In three months' time I am going to be spending 30 million USD a year more, I simply cannot challenge by books with that. So what is to be done? I will probably have to close the route. As an example. There are other requirements which are perhaps much more complex in terms of the text and in term of people understanding what they need to do by when. But even then, I do not think that this is a big issue. I mean, with a bit of guidance you come up with a flow chart of something. Again, how this translated in action, it could translate in installation of a very expensive equipment aboard, so if you have a, let us say, a bulk carrier which is 20-30 years old, 25, whatever, it passed a special survey and it is seaworthy and has approval and everything else, but is not worth, if you sell it on the second hand market it is worth maybe five million, three million, and if you have to spend on equipment which is almost the scrap value of the ship then this becomes a bit of a challenge. So I think the challenge, to summarize it, is not about the interpretation and the understanding - this is a resource issue that can be solved – the main challenge is the COST which is associated with compliance. #00:17:47-20:34#

I: *You talked about compliance being very expensive for older vessels, so probably for those, owners would not think of implementing... or doing a lot of technological innovations. So would you say that the average age of a vessel is a good indicator for the environmental friendliness of the company? #00:20:34-56#*

E2: (thinking) I would not say for the environmental friendliness, I would say for the flexibility that they have to comply. And as you pointed out – if a vessel is too old there are less options. Okay, I do not think we should necessarily discriminate companies that operate older fleets, because they could be operating older fleets, but it could be as simple as that. Basically, the decision – you know, operating older assets has its advantages. And the advantage is, it is usually cheaper to drive second hand cars all your life and letting someone else paying for the depreciation. (...) Older vessels can comply. So there are options there. I would not say that it is an indicator of the environmental friendliness. I have met a lot of clients who operate older assets, but they too comply

and they too (inc.). It is so, their options are much more limited. Sometimes, a certain moment of depreciation creates a shift in the industry and a shift in the stocks of many companies. If it no longer makes sense commercially to operate older vessels you [change?] your strategy altogether. And a classic example of that would happen in the past, in the early 90s. It was the double hull tankers, as you may have heard, you know the law being passed at it. So this created a huge shift in the ownership and the age of certain fleets. In particular the Greek market was one of them. The average age of the Greek fleet now is less than 10 years. The tanker fleet. It was not the case before that. It was not the case in the 90s. #00:20:56-23:09#

I: *Do you see a similar development with the legislation that now comes into force?* #00:23:09-13#

E2: I would see... I can see that happening, yes. Maybe not in such a drastic set, because it is not ship type specific. So yes, the tanker fleet certainly got renewed a lot after that, but here we are talking about requirements that affect the global fleet. It is very easy to scrap a tanker and replace it with a new one, but if you have a, I don't know, a 16 or 20 year old ferry, which is perfectly operational, it is not easy for a ship operator to find 2-3 hundred million Euros designated to replace that asset. But it will be a driver, for sure. For certain types of ships. And I think the ballast water regulation will be a strong driver, especially for ships trading in the U.S., because that is what we currently have and we know it is happening. #00:23:13-24:20#

I: *So, it would make more sense to buy a new vessel than to change to the new ballast water requirements?* #00:24:20-28#

E2: For some very old ships it becomes, yes, a possibility. For other ships it would just be a case of the company changing the strategy altogether and saying, okay, let us invest in a newer fleet, let us diversify a little bit to get some newer vessels. And what a lot of companies do actually, they redeploy vessels as well. So, certain vessels, older vessels, would be taken out of the routes where, you know, ballast water regulations for example are in place. So it is about shuffling the costs a little bit as well. #00:24:28-25:11#

I: *Is that happening more now, that I put specific ships only... that specific ships operate only in certain areas, so that I would for example take ships out of the Baltic and North Sea from next year on and only have them operate somewhere else?* #00:25:11-32#

E2: Well, certainly in the discussion that I have been involved it is in a lot of the ship operators and owners strategies – one of the strategies to cope and to comply is to simply redeploy. It is a double-edged sword, because the shipping markets are so dynamic that you want to be able to quickly, especially for certain trades, you know for ships doing tramp trades you need that flexibility. And obviously, if you have ships that are not able to operate globally simply because of their equipment or their compliance flexibility this is not ideal. But the alternative, which is a fleet-wider renewal of technology implementation, it costs a lot of money. So, I think the rules are changing the dynamics of certain companies and I think, in a way, those companies which operate on a tramp

- basis they will struggle the most. Their assets will either have to be geared up for worldwide compliance or become less flexible. #00:25:32-27:04#
- I: *Would that have an effect on competitiveness, because they would all have to change the vessels, right? #00:27:04-15#*
- E2: (thinking) Ideally all of these upcoming requirements should not have any effect on competitiveness, because they apply for everyone. So what are the golden rules of competitiveness? It is having a level playing field. Everything applies for everyone. So, actually, whoever is best able to adapt to the requirements, they will gain competitive advantage. So they are not intended to [inc.] competitiveness. On the other hand, I think, certainly with Emission Control Areas. Certain ports that are outside the emission control areas would certainly be gaining competitive advantage. If a slightly different route can mean you are out of an ECA then certain ports will certainly be happy to be in that position. #00:27:15-28:28#
- I: *So if we talk about Europe, which ports would that be? Or where would those be located? #00:28:28-33#*
- E2: Well, the English Channel, for example, between Europe and the UK, you know, on the channel side it is an emission control area, but Ireland is not. So, you almost, you know, within a small geographical distance you have an out-of-ECA port, which potentially could benefit. And then you could have, for example – people start talking about certain cargo being moved away from sea and moving to road or rail within Europe. And again, that is a bit of an unintended effect, because you know, ship transportation is the most efficient way of going about. But I have not seen any studies or any concrete data to show that this happening, but it is a concern. Whether this is going to happen, whether this is being used as a negotiating card from the shipping industry to say: Well, that is what you are actually causing, to the [European?] governments... #00:28:33-29:56#
- I: *So you have not actually experienced modal shift in the last whatever? There is nobody who is actually talking to you saying: We will have to move things to the road? #00:29:56-30:12#*
- E2: Well, there are people who are maybe talking that they will have to close certain routes. So that we have seen and the most recent example in the press was DFDS, who closed one of their routes. #00:30:12-26#
- I: *Is that due to environmental legislation? #00:30:26-28#*
- E2: Yes, 100%. It was due to the pending cost compliance with the ECA. And it is very clear that others are in a similar position. If companies are operating on a tight margin or break even, and I think certainly a lot of the short sea ferry operators in Europe, they are operating right now with very tight margins, you know, break-even or even in loss-making situations. If you are already there - in three months' time when your costs of compliance, when your operating... your fuel costs which constitute the main of your operating costs, when this increases by 30% it does not only eliminate any margin that

you had, it will push you very much in the red. Unless you have a very good strategy of how to cope with that, you know, there will be a board of directors going to decide that actually you will have to close the route. #00:30:28-31:43#

I: *The goods, will they be moved to road or to rail rather? Which is the... #00:31:43-31:50#*

E2: I do not have the answer to that. I simply do not know. I'm not involved too much in the intermodal type of things. It could be moved to competitors, you know, it could increase the utilization of other competitors within the same route. So it is a bit of a last man standing wins. Or if the route is exclusive by one operator, yes, then it will go to somewhere else. #00:31:50-32:27#

I: *What kind of effects on the environment do you expect if modal shift happens? #00:32:27-33#*

E2: I think it will be negative. You have increased traffic on the road, if that happens to be the road. If you look at the emissions per unit of cargo transported, whichever way you define it, or whether it is CO₂ emission per unit or whether it is SO_x and NO_x, I think these will go up, no doubt, because, you know, it does not have the economies of scale that you have with shipping. But then again it very much depends where it goes. If it goes to rail – what is the environmental impact of rail? I do not know. I mean, it is a diesel engine? Is it powered by the grid? You know, and if you look at the grid, is the grid nuclear powered? Is the grid coal powered? Is the grid renewable? So I think it is difficult to assess. #00:32:33-33:48#

I: *Thinking about economic consequences – what is the fear? How much are they going to be or what do you expect? #00:33:48-57#*

E2: (Thinking) Again, the concern from the industry is that ... will be lost and that there are going to be economic consequences on the consumers as well. And again, I think we have to separate the commercial shipping, so the deep sea shipping, we have to separate that from the short sea. Because the deep sea, that is a completely different business model. The consumer is not really affected. To put it that way: If – I'm just using an example – if Maersk or UASC or some other big container operator in troubles or their operational costs is increased because of ECA this will not – I do not think that you and I as a consumer will see this in the price of the Ipad that we get from China. On the other hand, if let's say PMO ferries or DFDS or... I'm just using some names for arguments sake – they decide that there is no way that they can absorb the extra costs of compliance other than increasing their fares. This will affect you and I and someone else as consumer. The consumers may or may not be affected depending on the type of shipping company. #00:33:57-35:43#

I: *What kind of products would that most effect then? #00:35:43-48#*

E2: What do you mean, in terms of what? #00:35:48-54#

- I: *If the deep sea market is not that affected but short sea is – what kind of products groups would see price increases and what kind of product groups would not?* #00:35:54-36:06#
- E2: Certainly, the freight, whatever is transported by freight, anything which I would say, ferries or bulk, you know, things that go from mainland Europe to the UK or non-mainland Europe, if you like, through North Sea, Baltic, anything that is being transported by ship would be affected in terms of, I would say, you know, fruit, vegetables, agricultural products, that are not transported in bulk, but they are transported in lorries or in containers, people, so, you know, passengers, this could be affected. #00:36:06-37:06#
- I: *What about bulk?* #00:37:06-06#
- E2: (thinking) Ähm... #00:37:06-13#
- I: Let us say bulk on the Baltic or bulk transported on the North Sea. #00:37:14-16#
- E2: I guess it depends on where it is coming from. If it is coming from outside, if it is not a regular route within that ECA, then the proportion of compliance cost increases is small. It is hard to say, it is just... My guess is that short sea, whatever is transported by short sea, a certain proportion of this cost will be passed on the supply chain and ultimately to the consumer. Now, it is how you define that, you have to look at what is being transported by sources. In my view it is probably mostly going to be passengers. And possibly certain, you know, food and this kind of products. But then again it is hard to say, if the freight is going to increase, to which extent this is going to be passed to the consumer or in which way it is going to be passed into reduced profit margins for the supplier, so for the sellers, it is hard to evaluate that. #00:37:16-38:42#
- I: *You talked about 30 per cent fuel cost increases. So, to what extent would the overall costs of ship operators increase?* #00:38:42-53#
- E2: The 30 per cent comes from a scenario where you operate a hundred per cent in an Emission Control Area. So, right now, you know, you are probably spending around 700 dollars a ton and it will be 1000 plus for the compliant fuel post-2015. #00:38:53-39:17#
- [Short intermittence of the interview due to a need of the interviewer to change to another office.]
- E2: Hello. #00:40:00-01#
- I: *Hi. It is not that easy.* #00:40:01-03#
- E2: Are you okay to talk now? #00:40:03-04#
- I: *Yes, yes. I can stay here until we are finished, so that is fine.* #00:40:04-10#
- E2: Okay, good. #00:40:10-11#

- I: *Okay, we were talking about the costs for shipping operators... #00:40:11-16#*
- E2: Yes, yes. So, I was trying to do a calculation in my head: Basically, you have got a 30 per cent increase in the fuel costs simply on the fact that if you are operating 100 per cent in an ECA and your fuel is going to be 30 per cent more expensive, that is your 30 per cent increase. Now, how much of that, how this is going to affect your operational costs depends on how much of your fuel costs is operational costs. In certain, certainly in cargo ship types it is the big majority. It is, I would say, 80-85 of the operational costs of the company, because have very small overheads, they do not have the big offices, so the majority of it is fuel costs. If you take for example a cruise ship with 3,000 people on board, maybe then the fuel cost is still important, maybe 50 per cent, but you have got other costs as well. So, all in all, it could be anything from, you know, I would say, 20, 15 to 20, 25 per cent of the overall operational costs of a company, could be affected by this, by ECA. #00:40:16-41:41#
- I: *Okay. And that is also the short sea shippers, that are mostly affected by that, right? #00:41:41-47#*
- E2: No, hmm... #00:41:47-49#
- I: *Or would it be bulk for example as well? #00:41:49-50#*
- E2: It is those who operate 100 per cent within the ECA, so it would be short sea, doing the journey within the same ECA, so I would define this as short sea. Now the deep sea shipping, the international shipping, they would spend a proportion of their time within the ECA. But it would not be that big. It would be 10 per cent? It depends where they are going and how long they are staying. The other thing of course is, if you start thinking about ships that are tramping, and they are going from one port and they do not know where they are going next and all that. It simply means that if they have to wait at an anchorage for the next cargo that cannot be, well, it can be within an ECA, but it means that you have to be burning expensive fuel whilst you wait there. Or you generate [inc.]. This is also a consequence which is just thought of now. #00:41:50-42:55#
- I: *Is it technologically easy to just switch from the one to the other fuel? #00:42:55-43:06#*
- E2: Yes. For those companies that have chosen to comply by fuel switching as opposed to comply by technology it is very straightforward. There is a certain procedure that needs to be followed. For certain ships there could be some modifications that need to be done on the fuel tanks and on the fuel supply system. But they are not in an enormous scale. And most ship operators are quite familiar with what they need to do. So the switching, technologically, it should not be a problem. Having said that, it was yesterday or the day before yesterday in the press; an article about the recent increase in the engine failures in American waters as a result of the U.S. ECA. And it has not been discussed a lot before. It is an engineering issue. Without going into the detail. Yes, it can happen. So that could be a new trend in unintended consequences if you are not doing it properly. And one of them, you simply loose power. Not a great place to be from a safety point of view. So there are some data to suggest that there has been a noticeable increase in

the reported engine failures. Most of them are being rectified and they will carry on, but obviously an unrectified situation can resolve in a potential grounding, collision, with other consequences. #00:43:06-44:50#

I: *So, when switching fuels is the one thing that one can do. Are there other major technological innovations that make it easier for shipping companies to comply with SECA requirements, for example?* #00:44:50-45:12#

E2: The other two major ones is either exhaust gas screening systems, which is I guess a technology transferred if you like from the land-based industry, from power stations with for over 60 years most qualified, certified power stations they are using exhaust gas screening, scrubbers as they call them, to clean the exhaust gas. This is transferred to ships and there are a lot of providers that offer solutions to this. And the basic principle is: You can still operate on dirty fuel, if you like, which would not be normally allowed to use, but this is being treated, so the resulting exhaust gas is at least as clean as it would have been if you were to burn the most expensive fuel. And although your operation cost remains very stable, to a certain extent, minus the operational costs of the system itself, you have got the capital costs as a ship owner which you have to consider. And also certain technology implementation challenges, which could be quite ship specific - again, the age of the ship, the space available on board, and all that. #00:45:12-46:45#

I: *Is there a learning curve? Are scrubbers getting less expensive by the time that they are on the market?* #00:46:45-52#

E2: (thinking, unsure) I am not... It is hard to predict if they are going to become less expensive. I do not think that they are expensive, because... I think... (thinking pause) It is hard to say whether they are expensive because they have to be expensive or whether they are expensive because they are necessary. So the companies, the equipment providers essentially serve a solution. So when you serve a solution to someone, whether that is a hardware product or whether that is... any kind of solution, in a free market the solution is priced according to the need of the buyer. Now, it is... Will they become cheaper? If the scrubbers become dominant, or a main-stream option for compliance, which at the moment they are not, they will not become cheaper, in the same way that we go out and buy something that we need, if it is necessary, it will not become cheap. If on the other hand they are not very much preferred, than pricing could be altered – so supply and demand. (thinking) Yes. #00:46:52-48:21#

I: *Do you expect them to become more popular than they currently are?* #00:48:21-26#

E2: (thinking) I think they will, yes, I think what is stopping their popularity at the moment is a) the cost and b) there is not enough operational experience still, so that for ship operators to say: Okay, I now have to spent a couple of million, but you know, within two or three years' time this cost will be recurred through reduced operating expensive, so it is very easy for me, as a technical person to go and make a case to my boss with the [sea?] financial officer and he will say: Okay, fair enough, it is good for our company, let us go for it. I do not think this evidence exists right now, although the

technology has been proven to work in individual cases, it makes the decision difficult. But with time it will become easier. The other thing that will make it easier is if the increase in demand of marine gas oil, which is the expensive fuel that you need to comply, if the increase in demand of this fuel within Europe and within ECA areas drives the increase in price, a certain increase in price then the incentive will be even greater. #00:48:26-50:00#

I: *Okay, yes. Can scrubbers, or if we talk about the third option, LNG, can those be used on all vessels? #00:50:00-10#*

E2: The scrubbers can NOT be used in all vessels, they can be used in the majority of vessels, from a vessel-type point of view. An engine - it is not really vessel-specific as it is engine-specific and space-specific. It is very similar to what I described about the ballast water, so are looking at a big investment, so if you have a ship with not a lot of life left to it, an older vessel, than those ship operators, they would decide either for technical reasons or for commercial reasons not to retrofit. I think it is more difficult - the technical challenges are mostly on the ferry and passenger ships, where the space limitations are simply prohibitive in many cases. Actually, those who need it the most are those who will struggle the most. When it comes to LNG now, on the other hand, I do not think from a retrofit point of view, although it is possible, the capital cost is simply too high to make it somehow considerate, so where we will see LNG coming in will be on the newbuilding market and in ships, I guess that operate within a fixed route where the supply of fuel is available. #00:50:10-51:49#

I: *Is the supply of fuel and actual problem? I thought it might be available everywhere basically in ports? #00:51:49-59#*

E2: The supply of LNG is not [available] at the moment. It is easier, I guess, in ports within Europe, so if you look at major ports it would be much more easy to take care of that. But again, if you look at deep sea, I think what is holding the industry down at the moment is making sure that there is going to be availability on certain ways where the ship is stopping. #00:51:59-52:33#

I: *I read something on methane as a forth possibility. Do you know anything about that? Is that a viable option? #00:52:33-47#*

E2: Well,... (thinking) LNG contains methane anyway. So, there is a lot of gas-based, fuels in the gas form which could emerge. I mean, did you mean methanol perhaps? #00:52:47-53:12#

I: *Yes, that is possible. #00:53:12-13#*

E2: It is methanol. , Yes, it is an option and I think certainly one big operator in Sweden, Stena Line, has announced strategically that they are rooting at this. It complies with the emissions requirements and it is clean and it is technically feasible, but I guess because it us not such a main stream fuel, the supply and availability would be the big issue. If a company has solved that part of the problem then it is possible. #00:53:13-55#

- I: *Do you know of any other technological innovations that are currently too expensive or not yet developed to be employed that might come in the future? #00:53:55-54:06#*
- E2: The other thing that is being, I guess, considered and we are considering ourselves in respect to certain clients is further down the line fuel cells and batteries and hydrogen fuel cells. This is a possibility, but I think we are probably at least five to ten years away from starting to see cases. Having said that we have, at least we have one ship that we have worked on, which contains batteries as one of the propulsion methods or fuel methods, if you like. So it is a bit like a hybrid car, so you have the conventional diesel engine and you have got the batteries and if all goes well and the batteries could take you a long way, but if it does not go well or if you need extra power the engine can kick in. I think the key there is really the fuel cell technology becoming less expensive per unit of power. So, in a way it is quite a similar issue with the smartphone. Everything has progressed enormously in terms of the technology that is out there and what you can do. But what seems to have stopped, or what seems to be the holding point is the battery power. #00:54:06-55:47#
- I: *We talked a little about costs and the next step would be freight rates. So if the costs increase to different extents depending on the shipping companies. Would you expect an increase in freight rates? #00:55:47-56:15#*
- E2: (thinking) I think if you look at again the ship owner/operator short sea market, if there is no other way to mitigate for that cost it will have to be passed to the customer. So, if the cargo owner is a customer, then the freight rate might increase. On the other hand, if you are in the deep sea, the freight rate is not so much affected by individual operational costs. It becomes a function of supply and demand of the [product?]. So I do not think that this, I mean, I do not think that we can find a direct link between increase in operational costs and increase in freight rates in the deep sea, because simply if there is enough ships to carry the available cargo globally of all ship types, that is what will define the freight rate in many cases, with or without environmental legislation. The freight rate will simply reflect what more ships and what cargo we have and therefore ship owners will be losing money. But that is what has been happening traditionally in shipping for hundred years, so it would not change now. What would change of course is the extra pressure on the ship owners on an already challenging market to basically survive. #00:56:15-58:10#
- I: *So do you expect companies closing down? #00:58:10-12#*
- E2: Consolidation, yes. It will happen, inevitably. It is... Yes, I think it will happen. Whether you can directly pinpoint it to environmental regulation or whether you can pinpoint it to a number of factors. #00:58:12-36#
- I: *What would the other factors be? #00:58:36-37#*
- E2: That is not necessarily a bad thing. We cannot simply blame society, progress and demand for greener air and a better environment, we cannot blame that. You know, certain companies will close down, it is going to be the evolutionary process and

whether it was possible, you know, 10-15-20 years ago to operate a ship, which was 30 years old and you did not have to comply with much, because much was not there, it probably will not be possible now and that is a fact. #00:58:37-59:22#

I: *You said that there could be other reasons, why consolidation would take place. What are those other reasons?* #00:59:22-27#

E2: Well, it is, I guess, it is efficiency stuff of having partner ships between different companies and reducing some of their operating costs, some of their overheads, being more competitive. You can see some of it happening in the container ship segment. So it could be all sorts of commercial reasons that force consolidation. It is better for everyone if you like, you know, bigger is better. You become more competitive, you have more control over things. But I think an element of that would be certainly environmental legislation and costs associated with it. #00:59:27-01:00:18#

I: *Do you expect consolidation in all the shipping sectors or is it linked to just the container market or just one of the markets?* #01:00:18-27#

E2: I'm really a market analyst to have this answer handy, but my guess is: It would be those who are affected more heavily by the environmental requirements, the cost will be considerable there. #01:00:27-49#

I: *How do you generally assess the current competitive situation of the shipping industry?* #01:00:49-54#

E2: Well, we have got an overcapacity in the major fleet and that is expected to continue over the next few years and we are on that part of the cycle right now where overcapacity means effectively very tight margins for companies, if any at all. Good time to be a charterer. But, you have always got regional variations. You have always got ship-specific variations. But if you think that a cycle normally, historically, lasts about seven years according to maritime economics and analysts it also happens that we are now... and how long this cycle will last, no one knows, but it also happens that we are in the negative part of the cycle for ship owners, if you like and this combined with the increased pressure in operational costs because of predominantly environmental regulations. And that is why the environmental regulations are being treated or [feared?] with possibility and concern. I strongly think that if we would have this discussion at a time where shipping was at a peak and the pre-financial crisis-world, where we have had ships being build every day. And this two-three million worth of equipment that we are talking about now would not be an issue. #01:00:54-03:00#

I: *So what developments do you expect next or what do you expect for the upcoming years for the industry?* #01:03:00-09#

E2: If I had this answer I would probably... (laughing) Well, you know, what the shipping industry does depends on what happens to the world. You know, all the economies they predict a global three per cent annual growth of the global GDP. You know, that is what you have to work with. The trouble right now is that the fleet is increasing a bit faster

than the GDP. So whether we are going to still have a prolonged overcapacity...
#01:03:09-55#

I: *Where is the fleet increasing? Which nationalities do those ship owners have that are currently buying, or increasing their capacity.* #01:03:55-04:05#

E2: I think the traditional four or five nationalities of traditional ownership. Because it is nationalities, not necessarily the flag, it is the domicile of the company. It is the Greek owners, the Chinese, Japanese, German owners and some of the Nordic owners are those that traditionally, and now still keep increasing their fleet capacity. In certain ship types, that they, you know, in their wisdom, perceive to be the ones that would need that capacity in the future. #01:04:05-57#

I: *If you compare environmental legislation to other risks that the industry is facing. What role does it play?* #01:04:57-05:04#

E2: I think environmental regulation, in this situation... (thinking) It is how you define that. The risk is... It is not the risk, it is the certainty in many ways. You know that you are going to receive certain requirements which mean costs, so I guess the risk is how to get there. I think it is a major one in terms of the operational cost, but then again, there are risks... in shipping there are risks every day. If you are a LNG gas tanker owner and you are spending all your hard earned [costs?] on building more ships, because you anticipate a massive boom in LNG trade around the world with the U.S. shale gas revolution and all that and then on top of that you have actually made a lot of money, you know, over the past four or five years because of the Fukushima accident in Japan, when Japan suddenly decided to close off all the nuclear power stations, to use gas to power the country. So you do all that and life is great and then all of a sudden, I think it was announced a couple of weeks ago that Japan started opening some of the Nuclear reactors again, made them operational. That is a massive risk and it means a massive reduction in cargo. So what does this do for your freight rates? What does that do for the ships that you have already been building? And all that. So this is an example of the kind of risk that ship owners live and die by every day. And actually, those who predict those better are those who make more money. I guess the environmental regulation is a bit of a constant. It is much more predictable; it is a much more predictable risk. It simply translated to a constant increase in operational costs. #01:05:04-07:29#

I: *Do you expect any further requirements on, say noise pollution or whatever other sources of pollution that you might have in the next years or in the future?* #01:07:29-43#

E2: I think the next big requirements which will come at some point will be something on CO₂, something further on greenhouse gases. Because what we have now are mostly design measures for new ships. In is sure that they could not adequately address a continuous increase in fleet and growth in shipping and associated greenhouse gas emissions. And if you look at what is happening in the world, there is a growing awareness of climate change outside shipping. Shipping is in a way under the radar in all that. But, I think, that the on-going global pressure on climate change and the lead

economies and countries start to do action on it; this will affect shipping in the coming years, too. #01:07:43-08:49#

I: *Apart from environmental legislation, what are other topics that are currently occupying the industry?* #01:08:49-58#

E2: (thinking) I am not very familiar in terms of what is happening in regulatory developments. There is always something on safety; there are always improvements in the requirements on safety. A lot has been happening, I guess, post-Costa Concordia incident that happened in ship safety. But I am not aware of something that is dramatically occupying the industry's time. Let me put it that way, the majority of enquiries, the majority of discussions that we have been having is around environmental legislation. #01:08:58-09:48#

I: *Three last questions. The first one: Are there any topics that I have not been addressing, that I should take into consideration when I research the effects of maritime environmental legislation on trade?* #01:09:48-10:04#

E2: (thinking) You know, I guess we spoke about the main things. We spoke about the technology, about enforcement, talked about trade and freight rates and we talked about the different requirements as well. (thinking, long pause) I guess... I do not think that there is anything. You know, it is... Are you planning to talk about the role of the EU or the European Commission as a driver in all this? #01:10:04-49#

I: *Yes, I will to take to experts of the EU as well to see what they say.* #01:10:49-56#

E2: Okay, I think that would be useful, because I guess the way shipping regulates itself in a way is with the different flag states and countries and registries. So I guess it would be interesting to see with the EU not being a flag state, but actually the EU member states having to align, it would be interesting to see what is the sentiment there and how this affects their environmental legislation and trade. And I do not have the answer to that. But I guess if you are speaking with some experts in there it would be quite... It is a good angle. #01:10:56-11:43#

I: *Are there any experts that you know of that I have to be talking to?* #01:11:43-45#

E2: (thinking) I cannot think someone in particular that I would say that you have to be talking to, because I guess the topic that you address is quite wide-spread. I guess what you need is different viewpoints rather than, you know, different technical specialities. You know, you can talk to the [organization 2] expert on marine gas oil, but I do not think it would add tremendous value in your research in the sense that, what you need is a perspective. I do not know, what data you are planning to use, but there is not an awful lot in the way of data. You can only use past experience and learnings to predict the future. So I do not think that there is anyone. I do not have anyone on the top of my hat, where I think that you have to speak to that person. #01:11:45-13:07#

I: *Last question: Is there anything else of importance that you would like to tell me?* #01:13:07-16#

- E2: I think... (thinking) Not really, no. I think you have answered a lot of questions that I would not have thought of, I guess, asking myself. And a lot of it was off the top of my head and opinions. It is not in the unintended effects and I think intended is... Whenever environmental legislation comes into force, or starts being discussed, before it comes into force, I guess a lot of assessment and a lot of consideration of the possible impacts, not only environmental, which is the intention, but also social and economical, all of these studies are being carried out, but I think what is now happening is an assessment before and assessment after. Perhaps it is not happening, because it is not really a popular thing to publish. So for example, when an ECA zone is being discussed or introduced, you would have a company undertaking on behalf of the proposal of the ECA, you would have someone undertaking this sort of assessment and say: Actually, we are going to save this many thousands of people every year, but in return we may lose a few jobs or we may have other unintended impacts, so on the balance I think we should do it. Or it justifies why we are decided to do it. So that works very well and that is happening, and actually a lot of industry is complaining: Oh, this is not happening. But it is actually happening. What is perhaps not happening is, you know, four, five, ten years down the line, to do an actual assessment of what has happened and compare it with that preliminary assessment. I do not know what would be the benefit of that, because I guess once the legislation is being accepted and approved there is no reason going back. But maybe the benefit would be to perhaps see if things need to be changed or improved. So that is what the idea was. I guess your study is good, because it covers not just one area, it covers a lot of different areas. So no, I do not think that there is anything else that I can think of right now. But, you know, if you come across either through the transcript of this or through your study, you come across something that you think you missed, let me know and I will be happy to help. #01:13:16-16:18#
- I: *Okay. Thank you so so much. I am through. If you have no questions to me, which you can take the liberty to ask, I will just wish you a good day. #01:16:18-33#*
- E2: Okay, thank you for considering me. I would be very interested to see the results of your research. #01:16:33-42#
- I: *Yes, I will keep you updated. #01:16:42-43#*
- E2: Okay. #01:16:43-44#
- I: *Thank you so so much. #01:16:44-46#*
- E2: Have a nice day. #01:16:46-47#
- I: *Bye. #01:16:47-47#*
- E2: Bye. #01:16:47-49#

Interview No 3

Date: Monday, 25 September 2014, 2pm

Duration: 71 minutes

Method of contact: E1 suggested E3 when being asked for further experts I should be talking to when studying the field of environmental legislation for the shipping industry. When contact via telephone could not be established an email was sent to E3 on 19 September 2014 which was replied to in the affirmative on 20 September 2014. The interview took place on 25 September 2014.

Interview situation: The interview was conducted in the office building of C3. When the interviewer reached the building, E3 already came down the stairs to greet her in the lobby. The establishment of contact was very open, friendly and gay. The Research Consent Form was signed in the office of E3 (small, crowded, but light space, open window, second employee on her desk nearby). E3 then suggested to move the interview outside to the sunny roof terrace as it was a very warm day for late September and the interview would be less disturbed. Still, a car cleaner next door operated quite noisily, a plane flew over at one point disturbing conversation, the supervisor of E3 entered the conversation in the very beginning asking unrelated questions to E3 and a few employees were passing through the interview space during conversation. Three chairs (one for the audio-recorder) were set directly on the path to the coffee kitchen and thus small disturbances occurred all the time throughout the interview.

In general, the expert was friendly and supportive, providing information as well as he could. Knowledge was lacking on all other legal initiatives but air pollution. Arguments were in parts very political and little substantiated. The expert has only been working in that position for two years with little prior experience linked to the shipping industry. The expert was calm throughout the interview, but became very agitated at the discussion of modal shift, repeating that modal shift would not exist without substantiating his argumentation very much.

E3 names one other expert and offers freely to be available if further information is needed.

[Introductions have been made, interviewer and E3 moved outside to make use of the good weather while conducting the interview.]

I: *So, again, as an introduction: I am currently writing my PhD thesis and I am researching effect of current legislation for the shipping industry on trade. I look at a number of different issues in that regard. I started with a literature review and am*

currently doing a number of expert interviews. I have been talking to some ship owners. I am talking to you today. Then I will be speaking to a captain to see how things look in practical application. I am going to speak with different legislators who are involved in this. I have talked to a classification society and I am trying to examine the field first of all from all the different angles. The expert interviews are aimed at clarifying the question. Then a broad investigation via questionnaires will gather a lot of data from ship owners and operators and will then try to get an idea of the scope of the problem linked to environmental association with the help of an economic model. The aim today is to hear your opinion, your expertise, regarding the effects on the environment, but also regarding effects, whatever you can tell me, on the cost structures of ship operators, trade, risks of modal shift and regarding the significance of environmental legislation for the industry. #00:00:00-0#

E1: [Introduction to the superior of E1, who is walking by; discussion between E1 and his superior on unrelated topics] #00:01:34-5#

I: *Okay, the first questions are quite simply, just to get an idea to who I am actually talking to. In which position are you currently working at [organization 3]? What are the topics that you are working on? #00:02:36-9#*

E1: Well, I am the head of the area of environmental policy. I am occupied with a variety of different questions, but eventually mostly with the issues maritime shipping, harbours, air pollution control, introduction SECA 2015, actually all the topics that interest you as well. Also naturally with the questions what that means for ship owners afterwards, what that means so-to-speak for the shipping investors, how that changes the market on all levels. That is not so very crucial for us, but we obviously have to see a bit, if people want to change something, that is perhaps better exhaust gas cleaning, then we either have to present a model on the other side, why we are of the opinion that that is either financially affordable or necessary from a legal point of view. And thus, we also speak to a lot of people, that is, two weeks ago we had a meeting with the head of environment of Maersk, we are speaking to HAPAG LLOYD, Hamburg Süd, also with producers, with VW, with Tchibo. We also try, just like you, to draw a picture of who has which needs, who suffers which hardships and how so-to-speak eventually, I mean, who pays for the more expensive transport eventually at the end of the way. At the end of the way that is strictly speaking the consumer. And how that would have to be passed on to the consumer. And how eventually, and that is then again our political perspective, how you have to sell that to the customer that he will then have to do it and pay for it. As a customer, you cannot expect that a t-shirt is brought around the corner for you for 0.2 Cent. One should spend more money on that. An I-Pad for ten cents and so forth. Well, that is anyways one of my main concerns. I am working in an EU life project with the name of Clean Air in Ports. We are caring for harbour and seabased emissions in harbours. And together with my colleague from Berlin we work on two campaigns. One is the cruise shipping campaign, where we have for once targeted the cruise shipping industry regarding their contribution to emissions. But then meanwhile also the container shipping project, where we expand on the whole issue of the container shipping industry and how that situation can be improved. It is entirely evident to us that

you cannot expect of the ship owners to, let us say, invest two, three, four, five million Euros right now in an exhaust gas emission cleaning system and then not to be able to refinance that through the freight rates. #00:02:49-5#

I: *Since when are you working in this area?* #00:05:17-3#

E1: Well, I am with [organization 3] for two years now, thus it is relatively limited. #00:05:24-9#

I: *Have you ever been in the shipping industry?* #00:05:29-1#

E1: No, I have not. #00:05:31-2#

I: *I have to know, where the interests lie. (laughs)* #00:05:33-5#

E1: That is entirely correct. Actually, with me that has been... Well, let me say it like that: [Organization 3] is anyways originally, well, [superior of E3] for example has been [political position related to environmental questions] for four years and before that also in the position of [political position related to environmental questions] has been dealing with the topic of harbours. Thus, since he is leading [organization 3] due to his knowledge and his engagement there has naturally always been a strong focus on the harbour topic for the last three years. Thus, there have been many things developing and he has been looking for someone to play that game with him at the full-time level and that is when I was elected. #00:05:35-0#

I: *Where did you get your knowledge on the shipping industry from?* #00:06:21-5#

E1: That is learning by doing. #00:06:25-7#

I: *From the last two years?* #00:06:27-9#

E1: From the last two years, yes. Well, I think... no... that is not entirely true. I have been working on Fehmarn for the last ten years and have been leading a large nature reserve. Well, you would naturally say, what does that have to do with that? But I have been working on the issue of the Fehmarnbeltquerung for the [umbrella organization of organization 3] and that naturally also plays... #00:06:29-0#

[Interruption by another employee calling through the open window to ask a question.] #00:06:51-2#

E1: ...yes, well, there I naturally had something to do with the issue of ocean-going shipping from other perspectives. Well, that rather had to do with the entry of waste and as I have done an issue together with the [umbrella organization of organization 3], that was called "oceans without plastic" and "fishing for litter", ocean-going shipping had and still has a large share in that. There we have however been dealing more with that issue and less with the question of emissions. Well, related to emissions I only do this really for two years. #00:06:52- 8#

- I: *Okay, great. How important is the topic of shipping related to other issues for [organization 3]? #00:07:28-4#*
- E1: There you have to differentiate. We have [details on business structure]. The topic is a very important topic for [organization 3] and it is also a very important topic for [umbrella organization of organization 3] in that it simply creates significant media attention. And via that media attention opportunities are created to acquire project funds to extent the whole thematic area of ocean shipping even further. Here in [city A] we have a delimitation to the [another environmental organization], where we have tried to divide up the topics a little bit. In consequence the [other environmental organization] deals with the topic of street emissions and we do the topic of harbour emissions. And that is evidently also linked to the expertise of [superior of E3], who once simply said at this place, let us just do it like that. Well, you can say for [organization 3] yes, a very important topic, very much in the front and also with the [umbrella organization of organization 3] – there the shipping topics also belong to those, that really receive a lot of attention. Also the questions related to the protection of the sea, that are so-to-speak indirectly attached to that, namely the ocean protection projects like “fishing for litter”, “oceans without plastic”... #00:07:35-9#
- I: *How important is this topic for the population? #00:08:51-4#*
- E1: Yes, that is an interesting... Do you mean ocean shipping in general or do you mean the emissions? #00:08:56-2#
- I: *I mean environmental legislation for the shipping industry. #00:09:02-4#*
- E1: Well, I think to be honest... that is, I think, not very present to the people. That is also our biggest problem. That is also very unsexy, to explain why that is necessary. Still, if you get the chance to explain the bigger relations or also at times in other settings... well, I sometimes do adult evening classes [Volkshochschule], I am invited there to lecture. And the the people are always very much surprised. But I also notice that the topic of CO₂ for example plays a huge role in the entire industry, but the topic of other emissions, that is black carbon and particulate matter and nitrogen oxides and sulphur dioxide, that is somehow not... well, somehow sulphur dioxide and nitrogen oxides still, but particulate matter and black carbon not at all. And that also has effects on the environment and the climate. I would thus always say, well, yes, that is fairly interesting. In the public, I would say the awareness is, moves towards zero, if we had not brought people to look close here in [city A] due to the cruise shipping champagne. As whatever the ship operators do that generally plays a limited role. That is just like that. In my perception. #00:09:04-4#
- I: *When you simply look at legislation – which endeavours are known to you that happen currently to better protect the maritime environment? #00:10:17-9#*
- E1: First of all the introduction of the SECAs now from 1 January 1015, well, that is the one that is now directly before us. And then evidently the question, how that goes on at the level of the IMO to put that in place until 2020, to bring that down to 0.5 and the question

then, so-to-speak, will that than work or will there by strong enough lobbying groups that are able to postpone the whole thing for another five years. That is what I would say. Well, if you are now about to ask me about all these MARPOL things that are currently being discussed I would have to pass. To be honest, with me everything is very strongly focused on the topic of clean air at the moment. #00:10:30-9#

I: Okay, yes. Who are the – when you just look at the topic of clean air – the most active actors in the area of legislation? #00:11:09-6#

E1: In the area of legislation the most active actors... well, that is always the question, if you... that are either lobbying groups, there you naturally logically have the ship owners, association of German ship owners that naturally voice the interests of the industry - that is the shipping industry - at this place. I would say [organization 3] as well as an environmental organization that is to say as THE environmental organization that deals strongly in the area of shipping. As I said, other organizations are doing different topics rather. Which actors... well, the legislators themselves naturally, the IMO... #00:11:18-5#

I: *Is more happening at an international or European level?* #00:11:57-1#

E1: No, if at all I think more things are happening at the international level. The problem is evidently that the Europeans, well, locally one is pointing to Europe and Europe is pointing to the IMO. In reality the music plays in London and everything is concocted [aushecken] there in the middle and long term. Whereby, naturally, I would say also at the national level. Well, if you see that now, we are working together with the federal states [Bundesländer], what is so-to-speak on the agenda there. There is a certain preparedness, but we also still have a thinking in terms of nation states between our federal states and thus I would always say everybody is referring to - also because we are in an international segment, that is organized globally – everybody is referring to the IMO and less to the question what is done nationally. Whereby, the introduction of the SECA is evidently a European story. #00:12:01-9#

I: *Who implements the legislation and who enforces it?* #00:12:51-4#

E1: Well, it is implemented in the end, passed, either on the European or at the IMO level. Who enforces it is still a very interesting question. That will remain to be seen who will take responsibility in the area of enforcement, also controls, from 1 January 2015 and who will say, we really take that so seriously and we have not just written that down, but we really want to do that as well. And we have learned from our talks with the ship owners that there are large shipping companies like Maerks who say, we would go forward, but not if the others are not being properly controlled. Because we cannot implement the things with us, when others are not doing it and then have a competitive advantage and we suffer from that. Thus in the end it is always the question of financing options and the question of the level playing fields. #00:12:57-7#

I: *Who is responsible for the control?* #00:13:47-1#

- E1: That is a good question. Well, in the national waters that is evidently each nation state for itself and in the exclusive economic zones, well, that is a good question who will then do that... That is unclear to me as well, to be honest, who is then responsible for the controls there. #00:13:54-4#
- I: *Who is most active at trying to impose stricter protection rules at the global level?* #00:14:15-2#
- E1: Well, globally, there is only the IMO, who else should do it? That is the only place that suggestions may be brought to, where a global chance may happen. But if we take the IMO as a yardstick I would say that it is naturally not enough, what is happening at the IMO. Neither, so-to-speak, regarding the width of the decisions nor the speed of implementation, the time horizons. They are much too long considering the effects. #00:14:25-0#
- I: *You said there are in principle two representations of interests, the Association of German Ship Owners and [organization 3] that form counterparts. Who has more weight?* #00:15:01-5#
- E1: Well, the Association of German Ship Owners! If I think about it for another moment there is likely the one or the other additional party involved. I would honestly say the environmental organizations have had a great influence on the question which voluntary, which VOLUNTARY measures the shipping industry or the ship owners will undertake. That has been working very well with AIDA, as AIDA has said we will refurnish our fleet, we invest 100 million Euros in exhaust gas treatment systems. There you could see that the pressure that we have aroused has led to voluntary measures being taken that went far beyond the level that was required by law. But most companies do what is required by law at a maximum. That is, now starting on the 1 January, whereby some of them have no idea what they are even supposed to do three months before that. That is somehow, that leads one to conclude how little the industry is generally prepared for these changes. Well, at least here in the North East Atlantic and in the Baltic Sea. Well, I mean, not to know now with which design to start off at the 1 January, that is with a scrubber or with changing completely to the other shipping fuel, I feel that that is honestly speaking very short-sighted. #00:15:16-4#
- I: *Yes. I have said before that I have been reading a bit and I have tried to depict the different ways in which shipping operations influence the environment. Those are seven ways. If you look at those, would you say that this comprises all ways in which shipping pollutes the environment, just looking at operations?* #00:16:35-8#
- E1: Well, I would say that these are the ones. I would say that, yes. #00:17:10-4#
- I: *Which of these seven areas are currently most regulated?* #00:17:14-9#
- E1: I would say air pollution, dumping of waste, noise, ballast water has just been done... #00:17:19-0#
- I: *Noise as well?* #00:17:34-5#

E1: Noise, no, noise has not been done. That is not true, no noise has not been done. Well, in any case at least air pollution, at least until – also if that is not enough – but it is at least half regulated. Ballast water is regulated, no, that is so far unregulated. Waste they want to do, that is not done so far, if I am not wrong. (thinking) I could not say that. Anti-fouling systems, has something been done there? You see, my focus is rather on the topic of air pollution. #00:17:36-7#

I: *Yes, let us talk about air pollution then. Air pollution – Over- or underregulated?* #00:18:07-4#

E1: No, underregulated. Quite clearly. Well, that what is currently done, relating to, even to the SECA from 1 January 2015, is not enough. #00:18:15-7#

I: *What would have to be done?* #00:18:27-8#

E1: Well, first of all one would have to say in general, globally operating only on MGO, that is marine gas oil, as that is simply - relating to the emissions - significantly better. Still we have the problem that PM for example - that is particulate matter - is virtually not at all, thus too little regulated and soot is not regulated at all. Thus we have no limiting values for soot at all. And we naturally need limiting values at all for some emitters and for other emitters we need stricter limiting values. Thus insofar we do not have any regulation in some parts and we need regulation there and for other things, where something is happening we need somehow a stricter kind of regulation. Hence that could be done in the SECAs. Theoretically the European Union could do that. Why they are not doing that is honestly speaking a mystery to me. But for all that it is naturally always the fear that the shipping industry is too heavily burdened (with scarcely concealed derision) whereby I always think that at the end of the day the consumer has to pay that. Insofar the industry has to ponder, also in principle the ones that are commissioning, the companies, have to ponder how to pass that on within their chain in the end. So to speak how shall that in the end reach the customer. And if an Ipad costs 10 euros more or 15 or 20 for all I care, even if you take into consideration other areas where the costs are increasing... (break due to loud background noises)

... then the customer has to pay that at the end of the day. That is for politicians to organize that in the end that it all works properly. In principle that has to be decided in Brussels. Well, first of all in Brussels for Europe, for the SECAs and evidently than somehow also for all the other areas. #00:18:29-4#

I: *How has the political interest been developing in recent years if we talk about maritime environmental protection?* #00:20:25-3#

E1: Well, I think that a certain consciousness has developed for that issue in the political sphere, why there are certain influencing factors that lead to lasting damage also for our industry. Thus if we now look at ballast water, all the organisms that are so to speak shipped around the world and then get somewhere, where they cause a certain damage - the Chinese mitten crab seems to be the best known example – then it has a reason, naturally, why the legislator is then reacting, as the damage is so to say visible. And

when different interest groups appear and say “Yes, we need to do something there”. Then it is not only the environmental organizations, but at some point also some areas of industry that say a certain disadvantage or a damage or a handicap is developing here, you have to solve that. And then something is getting started. Well, I do think that the awareness is relatively high, but that anyways, as I said before, the processes according to which decisions are taken are still much too long. #00:20:34-9#

I: *Which topic or which topics do you see next on the agenda? #00:21:30-4#*

E1: Well, I do think that noise is a big issue, at least in harbours. Noise is surely no issue on the open seas - that needs to be said very clearly. I now also have to say to that, in all honesty, that in the project that we do, another project that we do starting in 2015, a UBA project to that topic, that is dealing rather with, well, the focus is on harbours. That is related to environmental protection in harbours and we will then look at all these areas, ballast water, noise, light, areas, that is so to speak everything that is related to the harbour. But on the high seas... (thinking) I could imagine that waste is a big topic, as you read about that more often in the current general discussions, also related to the question of plastics in the ocean. That has reached, I find, thinking in terms of awareness, in what you see about that, it has in the meantime reached a relatively high threshold at which I think that politics cannot circumvent that in the long run to look closer at that and to regulate that somewhat more. That is also related to questions like how do you do that on shipboard, how do you look – “Okay, they are 20 days at sea, 20 people on board and how much waste should be on board in principle so that I can say in the harbour afterwards, when they get to the harbour, well, there are now, I don’t know, 300 kilogramm of waste accrued. That is fitting to what the crew consumes, that is so to speak considered realistic, we dispose of it here”. Thus in principle control systems that care about the fact that the waste that is on board is not somehow for practical purposes disposed of in passing in the high seas. Well, I think that is going to be one of the topics, as one has seen which influence waste has, naturally also in part on the fishing industry. That is the whole question of nets breaking and and and and and. And then evidently also all the ecological aspects that are linked to that. Well, I think that is going to be one of the next large issues. #00:21:36-7#

I: *Okay. You said before that there would be three months to go and that most ship owners would not be sufficiently prepared. Are ship owners and operators well informed about environmental legislation? #00:23:39-5#*

E1: Well, I think yes. I think that the association, that is the Association of German Ship Owners, it is in principle the task of lobbies - there exist a few others too - they will necessarily provide their members with reasonable information. But I think that no other date than the 1 January 2015 is occupying the shipping industry here on the North East Atlantic and the Baltic Sea so much, compared to any other legislation for shipping in the last years. The costs related to that are so significant – that is either the question: do I retrofit - exhaust gas emission cleaning – or do I change to other fuel – they are to quite some extent significant. Insofar it certainly constitutes a burden on the whole industry at the end of the day and insofar I can hardly believe that the industry is not yet

intensively occupied with that. Still, I think everybody is waiting to see which solution is the best, because I think no one has so far seen, which technical solution is proving to be the best. That is, does one employ scrubbers or as I said, does one change just like that. Does one install soot particle filters, does one use nitric-oxide catalysts, whatever... I think everybody is waiting for the systems to improve, for the offers to so to speak multiply and naturally for the costs to decrease due to increased installation. And because everybody is waiting for that, there is much too little that one can look at that is put in practice. There are such few ships sailing around with scrubbers that one has to wonder: When will they all start to do exhaust gas emission cleaning? I think that all naturally have the security as a last resort that they can simply operate on a better marine diesel, that will cost them more, but that is what they could always do if need be. Thus in this respect the one or the other is waiting a little longer until there maybe comes a better offer to which they can say: Yes, that is maybe a technical solution that is more suitable to us or for the field that we want to plough is somehow more fitting. #00:23:55-1#

I: *Are there then any major technical innovations that are coming onto the market?* #00:25:51-5#

E1: No. Not that I would know of. Well, there are only, well, you have scrubber, you have soot particle filters, you have nitrogen oxide catalytic converters and there is clean fuel. That is it. #00:25:56-9#

I: *If we now have these four solutions – are they equally eligible for all vessels?* #00:26:10-5#

E1: Well, let me say it like this – It is most likely in the end a question of estimated costs for the ship owner. Certainly, if I have an old vessel than an expensive exhaust gas emission cleaning system - whatever you do with it, I mean whatever is done today, a scrubber or catalysators or filters - may under certain circumstances, will likely not be worthwhile any more. Insofar one will likely just do the things that are most cost-effective at the end of the day. And for someone it could be that he does not want to retrofit any more or maybe is planning to operate his ship for only another two years and for those reasons he will do it them with MGO. And others will say: Man, I got an entirely new ship or a relatively young ship that will travel the oceans of the world for another twenty years - for that the investment is worth the while. And I think that is how the ship owners will decide. Or they will under certain circumstances decide to get rid of a certain ships entirely or to scrap them and order new vessels, but there is a certain vacuum there, because the others...

Oh, and we forgot about another fuel, that is LNG. That is the other debate that is currently there, that is to say the switch to liquid gas. There also the engines and the offers are still limited and there is also relatively little experience there. And I think that there also may ship owners are still waiting to see how the market for LNG is developing as well as the infrastructure in the harbours. One needs to be reasonably able to refuel the tanks. And I could imagine that in the next two years there is going to be come kind

of corridor where on the one hand it is being observed that likely at least here in [city A] an infrastructure for LNG is put in place – Bomin-Linde are currently undertaking developments there. Antwerp is involved in developing something. Rotterdam is involved in developing something on the Maasvlakte 2. Thus insofar there will soon be the opportunity in the big harbours. That will be interesting to the feeder traffic, thus everything we have in the area of short sea shipping; for them it will be interesting; certainly not for the container shipping industry between China and Europe. For that the space on board to take up LNG is not sufficient, as LNG has significantly more volume and the tanks would need to be bigger and that would nibble off loading volume and that is certainly not to the mind of the ship owners. The large container vessels will place their bets further on design optimisation and slow steaming and will then see what they have to do in the different zones – in the ECAs in the U.S. and in the SECAs in Europe they will under these circumstances then just switch to diesel. #00:26:17-5#

I: *That means which vessel types will not invest but rather operate on low-sulphur fuel?* #00:28:46-3#

E1: Well, as I said: The older vessels, that will only operate for another one, two years, they will not retrofit any more, they will just operate on MGO. That is certainly another question: Do I at all have the space in my vessels - and that would certainly depend on each type of ship – to retrofit something. And that is so to speak a factor: Can I retrofit? Can I already scrap my vessel? That will present many ship owners, well is presenting many ship owners with problems and thus is might make sense up to a certain degree that they are waiting so long. But still, yes, it is puzzling to me. #00:28:53 –1#

I: *Very well. The next block of questions that I have is linked to the observance of environmental legislation. How large would you estimate the share of ship owners that will comply with for example the new rules regarding air pollution?* #00:29:41-0#

E1: Do you mean around the world? Or within Europe? #00:30:00-2#

I: *Around the world and also for example for the North and Baltic Sea.* #00:30:03-5#

E1: I think, I would say that depends a little bit on the shipping companies. Well, I think that the large shipping companies - CMA CGM or Hapag Lloyd, Hamburg Süd, Maersk - that they will all largely comply with the rules. I think that they have a certain sense of responsibility as large shipping companies, and also because they are obviously partly state-owned enterprises, well in parts state-owned enterprises, and therefore alone they certainly also have a higher sense of responsibility for the compliance with environmental legislation. But I fear that there are many smaller shipping companies that will try under certain circumstances to lever out the rules.

As we... well, as I said before, the level of controls is relatively low and the possibilities to control the whole area extensively are not yet fully developed, even if a few systems, well, even if some systems are currently under development... difficult. Well, the Danish could quite well do that- they could employ sniffers at the Storebelt bridge, thus when the ships are sailing through under the bridge they could measure for that part, but

you would not know for certain: They could put it off and then just put it on shortly and then five kilometres further, at the Fehmarn Belt, everything is different again. Nobody can control them there. The question is: What are the Russians doing? That is always a black box.

Well, I think that for cost reasons each shipping company that is not one of the big shipping companies will try to circumvent that wherever possible. I do not have a lot of faith in them, to be honest, and if that is not very strictly controlled and if the fines are not very very severe than no one is going to do it. And currently it is so that the fines are likely lower... well, that the fines are so low that it pays rather to pay the fines instead of doing proper exhaust gas cleaning. That is going to be the problem, I fear.
#00:30:07-2#

I: *Which companies are likely to overcomply with the rules?* #00:32:03-7#

E1: Well, I think those that are at the forefront of public attention. Well, nationally I would say certainly the big shipping companies like Hapag Lloyd or Hamburg Süd that are simply, that are also the flag ships of the German industry, I would say. And thus they can afford the very least, with respect to the German public opinion, to do that. And they certainly also have, like Hapag Lloyd as being partly state-owned, very different obligations. Similar things apply to Maersk, by the way, who have made it very plain to us as well at this point that they see this responsibility. That is not like 30 years ago that they say: What? There is a problem? No, we have nothing to do with that. – Not at all. They have said from the very beginning: We belong to the largest group of emitters; we know that we have to take a very large share in that and we want to take a very large share in order for everything to get better. But then always with this limitation: We do it together with everyone else. If we are all alone, we cannot do it. But I do see that the big ones are willing to do something themselves. I mean, they have their own sustainability people that are dealing with this topic. They are very well informed. There are different circles, the Clean Cargo Working Group or other groups, there is a new initiative here, what is the name... I just forgot. There is a new action group by some large shipping companies related especially to the topic of air pollution control – thus, they all want to. But, as I said, with any small cheap-flag-state vessels [Billig-Staaten-Flaggen] I would always be rather sceptical and think that they will certainly try to circumvent the rules wherever possible. #00:32:08-1#

I: *Thus, could you say that that depends on the size of the company?* #00:33:41-5#

E1: I would say that depends very much on the size of the company. Clearly, in a big shipping company certain measures can be cross-financed and you can maybe afford somehow to make a little larger loss somewhere if you know that you make a little larger profit somewhere else and thus you at least stay at the same level, that you make ends meet to a certain degree. Smaller ship owners with fewer vessels and less opportunities do not have the chance to cross-finance and thus they certainly have, I could imagine, larger problems are more likely, wherever possible, to circumvent legislation or not to comply with the rules. #00:33:46-8#

- I: *Does it depend on the type of vessel? Could you say that container vessel operators rather comply with the rules than tanker operators or bulk operators and is that... ? #00:34:18-2#*
- E1: No, I do not think so. I mean, they are all bound by the question of emissions; that is independent of the type of vessel. I think we always have... when we talk about the international transport of goods we always more or less think of containers first of all, of a large container ship, but in my opinion it does not matter in the end whether it is a bulker or a container vessel, that is actually all the same. #00:34:32-5#
- I: *Okay. Does it have to do with the type of pollution? If we look at these seven again – do I rather comply with rules on air pollution instead of waste disposal over board or it that also all the same in the end? #00:34:55-5#*
- E1: I would think it always depends on how severely that is controlled. It depends exclusively on the level of controls. I am of the opinion that if there are or would be a lot of controls then there would be more compliance. We know that all. I mean if we drive a car it is just the same. If we drive the same route time and again and we know that there is a speed camera then there we drive slowly. Even if we maybe tend to drive faster that we would normally be allowed to before and after that. That is the way it is. Thus it depends strongly on the level of controls and the question is: How strongly is that controlled and how expensive is it if I get caught? I think if it becomes very expensive then we do it once or twice and at the third time, if we know, oh, they will come again for a fourth or fifth time, we will now rather cease doing that – that could help. But for that you naturally need human resources that those that are available in the harbour of [city A] or in Bremerhaven or in other harbours to control that. You can control that in the harbours or also on the sea – you can do that with scan flights and then measure the sulphur emission. There are technical solutions available, but you need people as well that will do that then. #00:35:15-6#
- I: *You said before: They will comply as they are German exemplary models or German flag ships. Does it depend on the flag as well? #00:36:29-7#*
- E1: Well, in Germany we have a very wayward system that we have a second, a second solution that you can do something with a cheap nation [Billigstaat] and still your vessels will be officially listed under Hapag Lloyd and will also be perceived as such. I am just not sure to what that leads within the shipping companies, that they... if they will then exactly on this question employ a different kind of management to the vessels within the same shipping company. But I think that that depends very much on the question of which flag the vessel is flying. If it is anyways the German flag that it of importance. But I think even stronger than that, if I think about it, is the question who the shipping company is, as most people are not looking at the flag, they look at the question: Where does the ship come from? Which shipping company stands behind that? And I think rather that the shipping company is at the focus there, independent of which flag – which flag the ship is flying. That is what I would say, it is most likely like that. #00:36:42-7#

- I: *Can I say that the average age of the fleet of a shipping company is a good indicator of the environmental friendliness of that shipping company? #00:37:48-5#*
- E1: The average age of the fleet, yes, I would say so. In any case, well, if I have outdated vessels and thus have to invest insane amounts and also have to ponder where in god's name to get the money from than I would likely have a problem. And certainly if I would have a relatively young fleet and one that is constantly renewing and one of which I know that there are two, three, four, fifteen ships in the pipeline, that will now come, then one can also very well guess the credit standing of the company from that, I would say, yes. #00:37:55-5#
- I: *How is the business model of the shipping companies influenced by current environmental legislation? #00:38:27-2#*
- E1: The business model, well, you can see very strongly that the shipping companies are now cooperating much more extensively. Well, I think that that is an opportunity for them to optimize their route networks and also if they are all in all rivals they determine with which competitors they could maybe achieve their aims the best and create the best synergies. That is the one opportunity, the measures that are in the area of cooperation and the other one is simply mergers. Well, there have been many in the last time as well, smaller and bigger ones, that have clearly led to the overall market power increasing and have led to new synergies, with these new constellations, relating to job reductions, route optimization, larger coverage, something that might be interesting for customers as well, as they can offer everything globally, east, west, north, south. Well I think that those are the two ways that shipping companies may follow. #00:38:35-6#
- I: *If you assume a consolidation of the shipping market – can you rate that positively for the customer or the consumer? #00:39:37-4#*
- E1: Well, let me say it like that. In the end that is probably not that easy to determine. There are very different components to that, but if you for example look at the pillars of sustainability that is evidently socially difficult. Ecologically it may be better, as then evidently, logically larger shipping companies with a stronger economic standing are naturally rather more prepared or in a position in the first place to work on their fleets regarding all environmental impacts. Thus insofar it is probably not altogether wrong. And naturally, large mergers are economically seen always increasing efficiency, also related to the question of payroll costs. Or also related to other questions. Thus insofar, economically seen it is evidently an advantage, but you can still ask yourself if it is what we want in the long run, seen from a social point of view. Just to have giant players any more that can certainly also as large conglomerates certainly also monopolize the market in the end more effectively. If we only have four to five in the whole world that make the action, that is what we de facto... where we are at by now... but if we in the end only have one or two then there is basically no market any more and that is then naturally a problem, logically. #00:39:56-9#
- I: *In how far does the current environmental legislation have an influence on the costs of ship owners? #00:41:21-6#*

E1: Well, the legislation has an influence as the ship owners need to do something. They have to, well, they are forced to think about what they will do, how they will invest, how they will retrofit. That costs money. Or they just simply have to use another fuel. That means they now have to think about what that means for the budgets, what that also means for the freight rates, what that means for the costs, what that means for everything. At that point everything is going on the test bench again. The question is asked then, for example, do I throw away the ship and buy a new one that maybe saves 15 or 20 per cent fuel just by its ship design - is that cheaper for me, when I do the calculations, than to operate this vessel, that I am currently operating, that I maybe have been operating for seven years, for another seven years from now on. I think there are many different calculations that need to be made now and that that is certainly challenging the industry financially, I think that goes to say without a doubt. #00:41:30-0#

I: *Can one expect a rejuvenation of the fleets?* #00:42:20-4#

E1: Yes, and you can already see that. That is already the trend that... well, that is also a topic that is occupying us here, the deepening of the river Elbe and the fairway adjustment is another involved actor in this game. The trend goes to building larger vessels, that have a new kind of design, need less fuel by themselves, may transport more, that is more at the same time, which evidently has a certain positive effect for example on the CO₂ emissions in the end and also on the setting of other emissions. Well, that has certain advantages. And that is exactly the industry: The small ones, they are all sorted out and at the top so to speak new vessels are purchased in addition. But looking at these... there is always this seaport traffic forecast study by the federal government that estimates a doubling of international maritime traffic until 2030. That means, well, you will always have to have so many vessels available that they can handle at least these expected capacities. And thus we definitely have the problem at the moment that in the aftermath of the 2008 crisis we still have overcapacities and the industry is trying one the one hand for economic reasons to remove these overcapacities by vessel immobilizations. At the same time however EVEN BIGGER ships are added to the fleets and one will see when the business will be growing again, so that in the end there is enough [demand] there at all. Since one should not under any circumstances come into a situation in the end, where too many vessels have been scrapped, where the market has been too strongly consolidated and there is not enough capacity available in the end to ship the things that are suddenly standing somewhere on the quaysides of this world. #00:42:24-1#

I: *You said that that has an influence on the freight rates – how big is that influence? How much of the price increases will be passed on?* #00:44:13-0#

E1: Well, I think the shipping companies somehow have to pass on all of that. They could not pay that themselves, because the problem is, their own margins are currently already so small that if they are lucky or to a certain degree successful they will just break even, that is the case with Maersk or they only make a small loss like Hapag Lloyd or... that is a comparatively small loss like Hapag Lloyd or Hamburg Süd, who can do that for

some time, as they have maybe simply been very successful and have accordingly economized very well and can finance that from capital reserves for two, three years... what was the question? #00:44:22-0#

I: *(laughing) It was related to the question how much of the freight rate increases are passed on. #00:45:02-6#*

E1: Yes, right. I think, as I said, as there is currently no shipping company that could afford that and that maybe does not even have enough capital reserves to pay for the losses they accumulate at the moment, they simply have to pass that on. That also makes a lot of sense. I really cannot see why we should get all our goods so very cheaply if the customer may be charged significantly more also at that point. Well, I really cannot understand at all that that is not a totally natural discussion to say, yes, why, the customer just has to pay more for all the different items. That will be just some cents for small things and just some euros or as far as I'm concerned some 10 euros for bigger things. (Carelessly talking) And when I say bigger things that can also be a TV or an Ipad. An Ipad is also quite small, but if I now pay 830 or 850 euros for an Ipad that is at the end of the day, in the eyes of the customer, I think he will not even notice that. And therefore it is also reasonable. And therefore it is not at all comprehensible why the industry is not just doing that... but because they are all just waiting. They are looking at their competitors and what they are not allowed to do, they are not allowed to coordinate their actions and thus, as they are not allowed to coordinate their actions, also for reasons of competition, no one is doing anything. #00:45:06-5#

I: *If we now assume that there are freight rate increases, is there a danger of modal shift to the street or the railway? #00:46:16-4#*

E1: That is, that is funny. Then you have likely been reading that article as well, right? That has been in Die Zeit the day before yesterday? #00:46:25-0#

I: *I have not read that. #00:46:31-2#*

E1: "Loaded with arrogance" ("Beladen mit Ignoranz"), well that was... #00:46:32-5#

I: *I would have to look at that. #00:46:35-6#*

E1: You should read that one. #00:46:36-7#

I: *I have read a lot of things, but that one... #00:46:37-8#*

E1: Yes, it has only in the newspaper (Die Zeit) on Thursday and I have now been really intensely arguing with the editor who has written that for the last three days. That is, written something back and forth, as he is setting up a very cool calculation (ironic language): You are all total ignorants, you have not been taking into account that when the deepening of the river Elbe is not taking place all the traffic is going to be moved to the street and then we will have an increase in CO₂ till we drop. And, well, everybody knows that up until a hundred kilometres that is not unlikely, but from a hundred kilometres upwards the factor, the increase so to speak relating to the rate for the train

plus 100 or for the truck plus 300 is entirely unrealistic, entirely. Thus seen like that... but as we do not have a harbour in the range of 100 kilometres that could be relevant – the next harbour is Bremerhaven – we are not even speaking of the JadeWeserPort, the next is Bremerhaven or even Rotterdam or Antwerp, the bigger ones. No ship is now going to Rotterdam and the goods are then coming from Rotterdam with the truck, that is truly total bullshit. (agitated) And that is also a discussion that really truly provokes me, as it is obvious to everybody that that would be so expensive that it would be unprofitable, so that every ship owner and every logistics company – it is not only every ship owner, you have to see who is responsible – that each logistics company will think of other solutions. And furthermore it will be a question for the ship owners: Do I sail with half the cargo with the restrictions to [city A]? Do I for example leave one part of the cargo at the quayside of the JadeWeserPort and do that with feeder traffic or unload more in Rotterdam and sail with only part of the cargo to [city A]? Well, I think that the shipping companies will adapt to that, that is what they are de facto already doing today - all big container vessels apart from the (inc.) have already been to [city A], that is, evidently not fully loaded and evidently with the restrictions that they can sail in and out of [city A] only at specific tides, but they accept that and when I look at it, only Rotterdam and the JadeWeserPort in Europe may handle vessels independent of the tides, thus these restrictions are also applicable to Antwerp. Antwerp is the third biggest harbour. And there are many harbours worldwide that are not able to deal with these vessel sizes at all. Thus relating to Europe and also relating to the Northrange I feel that this discussion is evidently entirely over the top, yes, when the deepening of the river Elbe were not to take place the goods would be transported per truck... I think that that is an entirely absurd scenario, as I said. There are rather others that so to say pick that up. But at the end of the day that is a question of the costs and a question of the handling. And I think that shipping is still the best for [city A], also because of its hinterland connection, if you see how far a vessel can come into [city A]. Those 120 kilometres that you can do here on the sea route and on the water route would have to be done on the road for the x-times amount. No logistics company would do that. In my opinion that is a horror scenario. #00:46:38-1#

- I: *We have been speaking about air pollution – is that also a horror scenario if we think about getting around the SECAs or may such a thing be though of?* #00:49:42-6#
- E1: How will you go around the SECAs? If I want to get to Gdansk or to St. Petersburg or even if I want to go to Rotterdam, how can I go around the SECA? Hence, we have all the big harbours within the SECA and I think that in the medium term another SECA will be established in the Mediterranean Sea. That is also, I think, the next step. There is rather going to be more regulation on that level and the goods DO want to go somewhere. And I mean, I have not heard that anyone has been complaining a lot on the North or East coast of the United States so far. Everybody is saying, we do not like that very much, but we have to deal with it. I mean, the harbour of Los Angeles is saying: Chop, chop, 50 per cent of all vessels that call here have to have shoreside power supply. They want that as a guideline and that means they force all shipping companies currently to retrofit a part of their liner ships with shoreside electricity options so that they may

even call at these ports. Where is the problem? Everybody is doing it. Thus I do not see... I find that there is too great a hue and cry sometimes and the question is more or less clear: The goods want to go there, they want to be sold, they want to go to the United States and thus the harbours can just do that and here in Europe it is the same. We are a rich continent, the goods want to go here, thus we can basically force those who come here to provide for that (comply with air pollution) and I really do not see a problem with that. #00:49:56-2#

I: *The discussion is often present especially relating to short sea shipping on the Baltic Sea.* #00:51:22-7#

E1: To circumvent that? #00:51:28-9#

I: *Right. That you say, for the first 100 kilometres that I ship on the Baltic Sea, from harbour to harbour, I have an actual alternative to load the goods onto a truck.* #00:51:30-0#

E1: For that you will also need the necessary infrastructure, that is the necessary road infrastructure at the same time. Well, to be honest, I don't see – I don't see that in the Baltic states – well, it is always argued that then everybody is driving through Poland to the Baltic states and back from the Baltic states – but I do not see the road infrastructure there. And to be perfectly honest, if as a legislator I want to prevent that, I will just pass according restrictions for the roads. That is surely very simple. That is a question of ruling power how I react to that, how I manage the traffic flows and how I establish incentives for the one and how I penalize the other for doing something that I do not want to be done as a legislator. And if I want to prevent more traffic on the streets I will just have to increase the toll for lorries even more. Ready. Well, that is one option how I... because the question always clearly leads to a calculation model in the end and I have to monitor all the time as a legislator, have to adjust, have to monitor, does my calculation model fit? Or does my calculation model still fit for the major intersection of players? And if that is not the case any more, if I suddenly come to realize then that there has been some shift in the modal split, then I have to react to that. That is that. And not only in five years, but immediately. #00:51:41-1#

I: *That means: Do you expect any kind of changes of the amount or the share of goods that is transported on the sea?* #00:52:54-3#

E1: Due to the SECA or in general? #00:53:07-9#

I: *Due to environmental legislation in general.* #00:53:09-1#

E1: No, I do not think so, because I think that we, as I said... If I now say: Sea harbours traffic forecast study 50 per cent increase in the international shipping traffic – there are by the way also other institutes that say that – I would say: No, we will always have more goods and more goods will want to go someplace, thus there will not be less, but more traffic. And there will thus be correspondingly more pressure on the harbours and correspondingly more goods will be transported by ship. That means I do not see a

problem either economically or related to employment and I also think that, if there is sufficient control and enforcement, the shipping companies will also accomplish a sufficient level of compliance, I do not doubt that at all. Hence, that will not happen immediately, it naturally depends also on how that is enforced in the end. #00:53:11-5#

I: *I have once been jumping a bit in the text. I have a few further questions on the effect on the shipping companies and if there are any differences. We have been saying that the size of the company has a very significant influence on how difficult it is for the shipper to adapt to environmental legislation. We said, the type of vessel that is employed, that is a container vessel or a bulker, basically does not play a role. That means which shipping companies would, if you had to characterize them, have it the hardest in the end to comply with environmental legislation? #00:53:56-3#*

E1: Those with the oldest fleet. #00:54:35-6#

I: *Also the smallest? #00:54:38-8#*

E1: Well, the small ones, yes, well, yes, that is true. If you say it like that, a little bit suggestive, then I would like to agree with that, because yes, right, the smaller I am the less profitable my company is, logically. Well, obviously. So the smallest and the oldest. And I would say that there is likely a connection between these types of fleets, that there are many small, old fleets or many small old shipping companies and the one or the other will certainly, will certainly still go down the drain, that is the way it is. You can then say, well, that is horrible, but if I may say so, that is... in the economy there are processes of consolidation and change anywhere at any time. I would say so. Nobody maybe wished in the black coal industry that that would one day come to an end and the whole federal state of North Rhine-Westfalia had to come up with an idea of how to manage the structural change. When I now look at it, [city A] still had 20,000 people employed at the HHLA at the beginning of the 80s, as an extremely high amount was still unloaded by hand and so forth. Today those are only 5,000, but nobody is talking about the fact that 15,000 jobs have been lost at one terminal alone. There are also the other terminals and with them it is exactly the same in the end. Thus I must also say that societies and also economic societies have to prepare for processes of change. It is only important that here at the Council for the economy, transport and innovation (BWVI) and at the senate everybody understands and realizes in time that you have to anticipate everything that may now come to happen. And I am sometimes not sure if politicians are thinking far enough ahead. Maybe they do think far enough ahead, but tell the public something else, but I do expect from politicians in the end that they think twenty years ahead and play through different scenarios and that they simply know, how they have to react to certain changes or how they may react, when these changes occur. And let me say, relating to the question of the deepening of the river Elbe, the question, how the large vessels will get here, if the vessels are becoming even bigger, well, it is actually unlikely that there will be still another deepening of the river Elbe, and that then means at some point: end of the road. In Antwerp an agreement has been reached and they have said: No, 13.5 meters and than let's really call it a day. And they than accept that and say, okay, maybe the very big vessels will not call at our port any more, but the port just

has to deal with that and has to think about how else it will distinguish itself. And I think that that is what marks a developed economy, to be able to deal with structural changes. I am originally from Braunschweig. In the past there was a large can industry and my father has been leading a can factory in Braunschweig in the 70s. And then at one point all the fresh goods started arriving, at one point everything was delivered fresh. Then you did not need to can anything any more as that was not necessary any more. And ten can factories went bankrupt in Braunschweig, small ones and big ones. Well, that is just how it is. That is structural change. You don't need that any more and something new is happening. And I think, and that is then the real question, how do we deal with that? That applies to politics, to the economy, to all actors, like that. And we do not need to cry because of that, but we have to understand that as a chance as well, as we are always finding ourselves in a latent process of change. That is probably only indirectly linked to this, but I just had to... #00:54:40-6#

I: *And in how far are the politicians, in how far are the ship owners currently prepared for this change process? #00:57:47-4#*

E1: Honesty, I'm sometimes even not so sure. Well, I do believe that they... they obviously also make business games and they will think about how to react to that, but I think that everybody is waiting – they are waiting to see what is happening with respect to the deepening of the Elbe or they are waiting to see what is happening with respect to other legislation. Currently they are also monitoring what is happening for example with the Mediterranean, because there are in the meantime some shipping companies that sail only to the Mediterranean, which means so far they do not have any limitations. The question is for example: What changes for them if we get another SECA in the Mediterranean. Or a NECA. I think the ship owners, the industry reacts always to the things directly in front of them. And they try up until the last moment, if possible, to lobby that away. That is probably going to be the same with the introduction of the 0.5 per cent sulphur cap at the global level and they will likely also all start relatively late again to react to that. And as long as they have another alternative that they can apply, although it is maybe economically painful, but at least workable, namely to adapt the fuel, then they could always do that, they could always wait as long, as long as they have still time. #00:57:55-9#

I: *In order to get the whole problem of environmental legislation a little in line, how do you see the overall economic situation of the shipping industry at the moment? #00:59:02-0#*

E1: Well, I think that many shipping companies have not yet recovered from 2008, that we overall have too large capacities for too little tonnage or for too little container traffic, that that is only slowly increasing and that there just needs to be consolidation on the market. Thus I think that most shipping companies are not doing well. I think there has just been one shipping company in the world that has been breaking even this year and that was Maersk, and has been breaking even last year. Thus in this respect most companies are either so-so or simply not good and the question is: How will two things change. First of all, how will the supply be decreasing so that prices may go up again

and will the ones, on the other hand, that are already not doing well today, will they be able to hang on until then. That is the question. And what kind of consolidations will there still be within the market, which of the small ones will have to give up and... yes.
#00:59:12-1#

I: *How do you see the development in the following years – what are the biggest chances and what are the biggest risks for the industry?* #01:00:12-8#

E1: Well, let me say it like that. Normally environmental legislation does to lead to chances for the industry, normally it leads to bothersome investments for the industry. Thus, insofar you can probably hardly see that as a chance. Thus a chance for them would be, if they did not have to do anything. That would be the best chance for them, if they could sail with heavy fuel oil right into the harbour at best, that would be a chance for them, I would heretically say. Hence, they have to deal with the claims that are raised towards them and that is, as I said, financially difficult for most of them as they are forced to retrofit or to operate on different fuel and to adapt themselves and to see how they will somehow deal with the legislation and I think that is very difficult for many. #01:00:23-3#

I: *Compared to other risks that the industry is facing, is environmental legislation playing a superior or an inferior role?* #01:01:15-3#

E1: Well, the question is how do you define superior? Well, if you say economically superior, as that has an influence, namely as I have to pay a fine, as that costs money... I think, to be honest, environmental legislation plays an inferior role for most companies. That is, would play an inferior role, if it would not exert financial pressure to such an extent. Well, no company would by itself enforce any environmental protection measures or climate protection measures if it did not have to, I argue. There are many some that are a little better, that maybe have some moral grounds on which they base their actions and that have somehow understood that, that they maybe have to do that. But if you look at it purely from an economical point of view and the industry consists as a rule of big companies that are committed towards their share holders; that have to and want to show certain earnings per share at the end of the year; and the share holder will ask for that, because otherwise he will not have to buy any shares. And this pressure is forcing companies to refrain from doing what they maybe partly wanted to do themselves, at least some of the involved parties in the companies, that is to say: Yes, that is our responsibility. Instead it is being said: No, we do not at all have money for that, that is to do something on top of the legislation, for that we do not have money, thus we rather leave it be. #01:01:23-9#

I: *Which other topics apart from environmental legislation are occupying the industry?* #01:02:42-7#

E1: Which other topics apart from environmental legislation... that is really a good question. (thinking) I would say the whole issue of competition, that is all the rules related to competition, I think that is for most of the companies the main game. Well, P3 or something like that,... well, where do you have... as it is a global market moreover,

where do you maybe have obstacles related to the question of how can we as a company optimally position ourselves on the market so that we have a chance at all and then – is that working by building large conglomerates or is that not working, as you then always need... from the big ones... well, as you need worldwide approval. And then it is of no use if at the end of the day China is saying: No, we will not play that game. Thus, I would say, all the questions and all the rules related to competition, for the companies, I think, next to issues of the environment, interfere with them the most or challenge them the most with regards to how they have to act on the market. #01:02:52-1#

I: *I have three last questions: Are there any other topics that we have not been talking about that would be important for my understanding of the situation?* #01:03:55-4#

E1: Well, there is something, that a short while ago I... we have shortly been discussing something, that is very important to me: That one says, well, obviously, we are basically only looking at the amount of sulphur and I think that one has to link the whole topic of air pollution control much more strongly with an awareness of the costs that occur where people are living, for example. See, the European Union is spending here in Europe for air pollution control, just for air pollution control in cities that is with regards to all sources of emission over 700 billion Euros. More than 50,000 people are verifiably dying every year...

(Break due to background noises) #01:04:45-4#

...are verifiably dying early in the European Union due to poor air quality and they have been, well, they are not immediately dead, but they have been ill before, thus the question is, where are the profits accumulated and at the expense of whom. I think that is an important connection that needs to be made in order to understand this whole system, because I do just not see that on the one hand certain lines of industry are stuffing their pockets at the expense of society in the end - that is just not working. I believe that one is simply obliged to do something. I think, it is with no other industry so very obvious as now with the cruise industry, as that in not a must have, as one says, as we do not need these goods for our lives on earth to function, but rather the cruise industry is a pure pleasure industry, you may have it, but you do not need to have it. And thus you can use that industry very well to show why it is such a problem, if vessels without exhaust gas emission cleaning systems are sailing right into the Harbour City (Hafencity) – and the Harbour City is just at one and a half kilometres from the city centre and the Harbour City is located there directly – where there is also another 20,000 people living. Thus, that is not possible. And to make that connection I feel that that is quite important. Well, that you also have to think about what is happening at the sea if you look at the consequences of that on the landside. Particles are dislocated up to 400 kilometres and one knows, well, that most of the emissions impacting in coastal zones and in harbour cities clearly do have an influence on the people that live there. That is, most people are living at the coast and in the harbour cities, at least most people live there, where shipping is largely taking place. And I think this connection is really very important, that you somehow make that again even more evident. Well, it certainly is an issue of health, an issue of climate, but it is also an issue of society, that is linked to

significant costs and I feel that you just cannot say: Yes, we take the economy out of this calculation, no, no, bloody hell, the economy does not only have a certain responsibility, it also has to partake in the costs and it may then in the next step think to itself how it passes on these costs. Because for them, they always have the opportunity that the one, precisely the one that is healthwise protected, that one can then go shopping for another three years, as he is only dying three years later. That is actually a very clever way of thinking, if you look at it like that. And I feel that this connection really really needs to be very vividly emphasized on as well. That is maybe not... that is rather relating to the harbour, but I would say that always has to do with the other, at least in the coastal areas. And by the way – the influence of nitrogen oxides on the whole agricultural sector in coastal areas and then again the related eutrophication when flowing back into the oceans... well, thus, these are also all systems, that is so to speak mutually dependant. And at the end of the day there are damages as well, on the one hand, as I say, for the environment, and on the other hand logically also for the people, as we all have to eat the whole rotten stuff. #01:04:09-4#

I: *Are there other experts with whom I should definitely speak about this topic?* #01:08:06-1#

E1: Well, I can very much recommend a very good expert that I know... he is tiresome, incredibly tiresome, you will not have a lot of fun with him, but... (laughing) but he is just... in former times he was... well, he is mainly concerned with air, but if you ask him, he can tell you something about everything. He is so to speak an expert for everything, that is Dr. Axel Friedrich. Have you heard of him? #01:08:13-7#

I: *No, I have not heard of him.* #01:08:38-8#

E1: Well, fine. Dr. Axel Friedrich has been among other things head of the department on air at the Federal Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt) up until three years ago. He now is external advisor for a number of environmental organizations. At times he works for the Deutsche Umwelthilfe, sometimes for us, also for the BUND, thus for different organizations. He is not only working for environmental organizations, but also for the economy. He really is a man of conviction, but he is incredibly tiresome. He knows a lot and I feel that you can also interview him, as he can obviously very well give you the agency perspective. Thus, how does the agency work, what kind of decision processes are going on and based on what are decisions taken and on what not. And what is done and what is not done and why, on which factors does that depend? Well, I think he is simply a very interesting conversation partner, I can only recommend him. I can give you the email address... he lives in Berlin, but he is often a time in [city A], thus, I do not know how fast you... #01:08:38-6#

I: *I will have to see.* #01:09:49-0#

E1: Well, he is from time to time in [city A], there will anyway be a chance. Otherwise, I do not know, one would have to go to Berlin or something like that, whereby he is always on the road. I can give you the email address in a minute. #01:09:51-2#

- I: *Yes, wonderful. Last question: Do you still want to tell me anything? #01:10:02-7#*
- E1: Do I still want to tell you anything... well, we have actually been talking about everything. The most important thing, well, what I personally find outrageous, is that the actors that are responsible for the largest share of emissions - and those are the ship operators, the ship owners, depending, or both of them, that is always different – would have a true responsibility and for many of them that plays a totally inferior role, because obviously in such a global system one always says: Yes, well, we cannot do it here if not everybody is doing it... But it does not matter to them, who is doing that in the end, even if they all know, what disastrous consequences that has in the end. I think that that is, to be honest... well, I have to wonder about that. Whereby, that is probably not just a characteristic of the shipping industry, but that is a symptom of how our society thinking. But when we now break that down for this sector, I would say I find that outrageous, to be honest. Also that politics are in the end subservient lapdogs for those- let me say it like that – dealings - a little disrespectful. But thinking about the work practices of these companies – because really, I think, it is also a task of politics certainly to make sure that jobs are maintained, that is very important, but I cannot only do that all the time by favouring allies and friends, that are verifiably becoming richer and richer, while other people may just suffer from the consequences of these politics. But apart from this very general sentence as a conclusion, I cannot think of anything else, really. #01:10:08-4#
- I: *Okay. Thank you very much. #001:11:54-7#*

Interview No 4

- Date: Tuesday, 30 September 2014, 10am
- Duration: 93 minutes
- Method of contact: The contact to E4 was established via an association of shippers. The contact details were provided by the association on 4 September 2014 and the study purpose and design had been explained to E4 by the association. An email with information on the interview process was sent by the researcher to E4 on 5 September 2014 and was replied to in the affirmative on the same day. An interview date was set subsequently to the 30 September.
- Interview situation: The interview took place in an empty office of a co-worker of E4 in the office building of C4. The interview started on time and took a few minutes longer than the expected 90 minutes. The window to the office was open, but little noise disturbance occurred. After about 40 minutes E4 stopped the interview to fetch some water, but came back a minute

later and the interview went on for another hour in full concentration. No further interruptions occurred during the interview process.

E4 was friendly, but cautious not to provide sensitive data. He repeated several times that certain numbers or information were not supposed to leave the building and could thus not be provided. As an engineer E4 could provide an abundance of technical details and technical knowledge, but had little knowledge or interest in issues of costs and economic consequences. In these areas, the willingness to provide information was limited. The expert had a lifetime experience in the technical issues discussed and hinted at a number of interesting technical problems.

E4 named classification societies (Germanischer Lloyd, DNV), policy makers and experts within shipping associations as important persons to talk to. Although friendly throughout, further support was not offered at the end of the interview.

I: *By way of a short introduction: I am currently writing my PhD thesis and I am investigating effects of environmental legislation that relates to the shipping industry on trade. I have a rather long review of literature behind me. Data shall be acquired via questionnaires and in order to limit the field a little and in order to see where the real problems are I am currently doing a round of expert interviews. There are a few ship owners among them, I have been talking to an environmental organization yesterday. There is also the other side, that is also logistics companies in the sample, the legislator, a boat captain... in order to make sense of the field. Today that will be on out of four interviews – or maybe it will be five – with ship owners of different sizes and different backgrounds. That means, it is my aim to record your expert opinion. I am not so much interested in [organization 4] in particular, but in the industry itself and the effects themselves. I am interested in the cost structures, trade effects and risks of modal shift. #00:01:21-8#*

E4: I will answer that as well as I can. I am not an economist. I am a technician. #00:01:21-7#

I: *That is very interesting to me, yes. #00:01:26-2#*

E4: I am more involved in the whole environmental problem, in the rules and the developments, but also in the whole implementation things, that we have to do or are doing. #00:01:43-1#

I: *That is also my first question: What are you doing? What is your position within [organization 4]? #00:01:50-1#*

E4: In relation to MARPOL VI, or what? #00:01:53-8#

I: *Well, all in all, so that I know what kind of information I can ask of you. Thus, what is your function? What kind of topics are you occupied with? #00:02:02-9#*

E4: I am entrusted with a number of tasks. I am THE environmental expert with

[organization 4]. I am also strongly engaged in the area of safety, namely ISM code - I am the Designated Person – and also ISPS, that is Security. I am the Company Security Officer. And I am also, owing to my background as a technician, as an engineer, I am thus also occupied with technical questions rather of a general nature. Well, my colleagues are dealing with the daily operation of the vessels, the dear inspectors. And I am rather more occupied with the general questions, but also with questions relating to the port facilities, that is with the interface ship-harbour, this whole variety of tasks, I would say. #00:03:05-2#

I: *For how long have you been doing that?* #00:03:07-7#

E4: I am now almost 21 years here with [organization 4]. #00:03:14-3#

I: *That is quite some experience. What are currently the most important topics in your area?* #00:03:26-5#

E4: (Laughing) Yes, well, for once this environmental issue, naturally. The 1 January 2015 is just around the corner. Still, also every day these safety issues, that occupy us on and on. That is more linked to the daily operations, that it where there are some smaller challenges here and there. #00:03:49-0#

I: *If you say environmental issues, what do you mean?* #00:03:53-4#

E4: Implementation of MARPOL VI, very specifically. And latterly increasingly also all these discussions around CO₂ emissions, climate protection, very specifically a little bit this monitoring that is just being invented at the moment. And where we are also often asked for our opinion via the association, where we contribute data in order to substantiate something or other, as it may be. #00:04:23-3#

I: *[Organization 4] itself own how many vessels?* #00:04:29-1#

E4: We are operating six vessels. Of those four are our own. One is in bare boat charter, one is in time charter. We operate six vessels on three routes. #00:04:51-4#

I: *Do they all transport freight and passengers?* #00:04:58-4#

E4: All six are so-called RoPax/RoRo ferries, that is combined freight and passenger ferries. #00:05:06-6#

I: *How is that more or less divided up? Freight to passengers?* #00:05:12-1#

E4: Well, freight has the lion's share. I would say about three thirds is freight. #00:05:18-7#

I: *Well, I am only looking at merchant shipping.* #00:05:25-0#

E4: Whereby, that fluctuates over the year. It is more in the summer, in the off season it is considerably less. But roundabout three thirds to one third is the average over the whole year. #00:05:37-7#

I: *The seasons are related to the passengers or do they also apply to freight?* #00:05:41-3#

- E4: Both. Well, in the high season, we are speaking about roughly mid-June to mid- to end-August - that depends a little on the weather conditions and on the travel behaviour - passenger numbers are jumping up significantly. There we transport... that is then the whole summer travel season. And at the same time, freight decreases. Not during the whole time, that is rather a shorter time from maybe mid-July, mid- to end-July until mid-August, where due to the closings of all the factories in Europe and so forth the freight traffic is decreasing a bit. #00:06:29-6#
- I: *What kinds of freight volumes do you move, roundabout?* #00:06:34-8#
- E4: I could not tell you now. I would have to provide the numbers later. #00:06:39-3#
- I: *Do you know what kinds of goods those are mainly?* #00:06:45-9#
- E4: That is EVERYTHING possible. Mostly everything that is transported by truck. Well, that is no or very little bulk cargo. Thus you can say it is first of all the final products, thus relatively high value goods. And also partly the source materials, that move into the other direction. #00:07:11-5#
- I: *Where do the goods come from? That is how far... where do the trucks come from?* #00:07:19-9#
- E4: As far as I know they come from the whole of Europe. On the one hand. Thus, the catchment area is going from... We also have trains, cargo is arriving here from the south of Europe by train, they are loaded onto chassis, are brought on board and are put back on trains in the other harbour. I know that. There is a train coming from Italy. Well, for the harbours of Rostock and also recently for Swinoujscie in Poland, we have the catchment area is strong in the East to South-East of Europe. Here in Travemünde it is traditionally the Benelux countries. Everything that is here in the Western part of Europe and evidently Germany, the Ruhr area. Wherever the shortest route is. The cargo is seeking for the shortest path. #00:08:09-8#
- I: *Thus it does not make sense to go the long way round on the ship, especially from the South of Europe?* #00:08:15-9#
- E4: I think for these higher value goods that takes too long. It just goes faster. The truck is loaded somewhere in the South West of Germany in the morning, or in the Netherlands and someplace. In the afternoon or in the evening it is here at the harbour. It is taken across at night. The driver can at the same time get his rest period, the legal rest period and is in Scandinavia the next morning and can drive on. That you cannot achieve with a general cargo carrier or with a RoRo-Carrier via Skagen using the long sea route, I think, within two to three days. #00:08:59-5#
- I: *Which flag are they flying?* #00:09:02-1#
- E4: We have three vessels flying the German flag, two vessels flying the Swedish flag and one vessel flying the Polish flag. #00:09:10-9#
- I: *Is the fleet currently experiencing any changes due to environmental legislation?* #00:09:16-2#

- E4: We have been retrofitting one vessel this summer, but that is first of all the only change that we will now take in hand. We have built in a new scrubber, hence, a scrubber installation, an exhaust gas cleaning system. Actually, strictly speaking there are four in the ship that make sure that the sulphur oxides are separated from the exhaust gas, but also particles in order to reach the MARPOL limits. #00:09:47-4#
- I: *What happens to the other vessels?* #00:09:52-1#
- E4: They will switch to a low-sulphur fuel with the turn of the year. #00:09:56-8#
- I: *Are there any changes to the routes? That more or less freight is transported?* #00:10:04-5#
- E4: No, so far not. Well, not beforehand. Obviously we will have to monitor that very closely, as we fear already since the environmental rules have been passed that that will lead to modal shifts. We have also participated and supported in the background in at least two studies that were prepared on this, for example one of the ISL in Bremen, in order to find out how significant the danger of the shift of traffic from the ship to the road may be. Our insights up til now are that the longer the sea route is, the higher is the risk of modal shift. #00:10:59-0#
- I: *One would think that that is exactly the other way around - that especially shorter distances may be easier to replace.* #00:11:04-2#
- E4: No, as the share of fuel costs is higher with longer routes. We have competitors here that sail from Travemünde all the way to Finland. These vessels need around 150, 160 tons of fuel per sail, times the higher costs. That is going to be more difficult to retrieve from the customers than if the route is shorter and the share of fuel costs is not as high. #00:11:42-4#
- I: *For which routes and which goods is such a modal shift thinkable?* #00:11:48-5#
- E4: I would say for all kinds of goods... well, first of all for all routes, where there are parallel transport possibilities on land. Well, Germany-Finland, there I have the option to drive through Poland and the Baltic states and of course in the end to take a short sea route somewhere. I have the option as well to use the short sea routes here across Denmark and to use the bridge and I can drive through Sweden and take the little jump across from Sweden to Finland. There we see a danger of modal shift. And here with us, if I apply that to the Southern Baltic Sea, there is certainly the danger that cargo will be shifter to even shorter routes, as the crow flies and then take the way across Denmark. How that will come into being in the end, we will have to see. That is all a very uncertain issue. #00:12:54-2#
- I: *Are there concrete sign, that certain customers will now transport their cargos by other means?* #00:13:01-6#
- E4: Not that I know of. I am not close to the customers. #00:13:08-5#
- I: *That is going to be interesting.* #00:13:11-3#

- E4: That is certainly going to be interesting. We already see today, not with us, not with [organization 4], but with some of our competitors, we see the first reactions. DFDS has closed the route Harwich-Esbjerg. Has pulled off the vessel. They say due to SECA. Stena has just proclaimed that they will thin out the Sassnitz route to one ship due to SECA. A number of shipping companies, our competitors, are partly speaking of laying off employees not to a negligible extent, as they expect the trade to decline. Such effects are already visible today. We have to see next year where all that is going. #00:14:03-6#
- I: *If there are effects of modal shift, do they apply to a shift to the street or to the rail?* #00:14:10-2#
- E4: We think that freight will move mostly to the streets, as the rail is not at all able, in our experience, to take on these quantities. #00:14:22-0#
- I: *Is the road infrastructure sufficient? Is the road able to take on these loads?* #00:14:31-2#
- E4: That is a good question. That is a very good question. We have put the argument forward from the very beginning that due to such effects it may downright come to negative effects for the environment, as suddenly emissions that are today taking place at the sea and for that matter far away from society – evidently there are, and the environmental experts will tell you a long rigmarole on that, naturally there are influences from these emissions, that are taking place out on the open sea on the people living on land, clearly – but the trucks, they are driving along right in front of us. The trucks themselves are, related to the sulphur emissions, indeed CONSIDERABLY better, as only almost sulphur free fuel is sold on the streets. That is correct. But they have other impacts. They have all these fine particulate emissions due to the diesel motors. They have NO_x emissions, even if there is a lot being done with the current Euro V or I don't know what they have at the moment. But you evidently have the impacts of the traffic itself, of noise, of road congestion and so forth. I think one has to look at that from a more general point of view, then to always look only on the sulphur issue, that to our knowledge is actually not existing to that extent any more. Since when you look at measuring stations here at the Baltic Sea coast, the effective value measured for SO₂ in the air is far below the limits, even if there are vessels coming in and out of the harbour every day. There are measuring stations in Warnemünde and that is proven without a doubt. That is not just a little bit below the limit, but the value measured is here and the limit is up there. All of that is from our point of view a little ill-founded. Well, we know, on the other hand, that the whole discussion on sulphur is actually a discussion on particulate matter in disguise. What we do not understand then is why the legislator is demanding the use of diesel oil – just through the sulphur limit – and with diesel oil operation you get far more of the small particles, I think PM 2.5 or however these things are called, that are considerably more dangerous to human health than the larger particles that we have with the heavy fuel oil. But needless to say we actually don't want any emission or rather as few emissions as possible, it is just the WAY to there that is questionable. We as the shipping industry see the whole now as a helter-skelter measure that might have negative effects. #00:17:26-5#
- I: *If we think about modal shifts once more. How significant are the differences in freight rates? At a rough estimate. Is there even a difference if I put my freight on a truck or on the ship? And how much more expensive is the one or the other?* #00:17:46-6#

- E4: I can unfortunately not tell you the numbers. Still, these numbers I am willing to supply later. You are asking for the difference in costs between the sea transport... #00:17:57-9#
- I: *You said that trucks are the alternative. Thus, if we may not see the railway as a real alternative then we would have to compare the differences in freight costs between vessel and truck. #00:18:13-8#*
- E4: I think there is something on that in the ISL study. #00:18:19-4#
- I: *I know the study. #00:18:22-4#*
- E4: I am, as I said... I am not that familiar with this issue of freight, with this issue of logistics. I can supply little numbers there. #00:18:39-9#
- I: *Well, then let us talk a little bit about the rules now. Which current political endeavours are known to you in order to protect the marine environment better? What are the different new rules that exist? What is coming next? What is maybe coming in the next few years? #00:19:02-9#*
- E4: One thing in the pipeline is the ballast water management convention. That is however also a global approach from our point of view. Well, it is mainly linked to the idea that one does not bring species that are originally native in Asia to Europe and the other way around. #00:19:23-4#
- I: *Is that a topic that your company is affected by at all? #00:19:27-5#*
- E4: First and foremost: Formally, yes, as the ballast water management convention applies to everyone. It has not yet been enforced. Still not enforced. Once thing that we are intensively working on is that we receive exceptions for these ferries, as we are of the opinion that it would be very much nonsensical to assume that after 50 years of ferry traffic between Germany and Sweden we had not long ago carried back and forth all little animals that maybe had not been living on the other side before. Well now, that the marine fauna and flora is not anyways the same. Well, except that that is an assumption that we likely still have to prove somewhere. And the main discussion at the moment is actually this one: Who is responsible for these analyses? Who is paying for that? For how long is that valid? At the moment the ballast water convention to my knowledge offers an exception that says, well, the ship owner has to... well, if I want to go someplace and I do not want to drive a treatment system and all these things, then I have to prove that I do not introduce anything into that harbour. That means the ship owner has the obligation to provide prove [Nachweispflicht]. We are saying, however, come on people, we are happy to participate in the costs, but from [city 4] [organization 4] goes to Sweden, [a competitor] goes to Sweden, [another competitor] goes to the Baltic States and [another competitor] goes to Finland. Let the harbour or the competent authority here take the sample, then it is anyways already in the right hands. And naturally there will then be a distribution model for the costs, but everybody can rely on the results. And the same should happen in Sweden. Then we would have a much more practical approach for the short sea traffic that we operate here. That is the one thing. The other thing that is in the pipeline was the issue of sewage water. That is however already decided. There are now only certain transposition times.

For us that means that latest starting from 2017 or 2018, some time, we have to... running vessels thus need either a new sewage treatment system on board, that abides to even higher limits than today's systems, or we have to dispose of the waste water on land. We have started since the summer to dispose of waste water on land in Sweden with one vessel in order to first gain some experience. So far that is running smoothly, that means until the appointed date at the latest we will have converted all vessels to disposal on land.

On the side: From the perspective of the ship owners that is again rather idiotic, because the sewage plants on land that now receive our waste water have significantly lower or lower constraints, not significantly, but lower constraints than the new sewage water treatment systems that are supposed to be built on board ships. All in all a little absurd, but that is how the legislator wants it.

And then there is also the discussion, that would be the third aspect that spontaneously comes to my mind, there is this whole issue of climate protection, CO₂. That does not directly include this local aspect of environmental protection, but rather a global one. Thus we are occupied a lot [schlagen uns viel herum] with efficiency and all these things. In light of the shipping industry being... (thinking) well, before... That was quite interesting: There has just been one... the ICS has just, well, the International Chamber of Shipping, has published data according to which the global CO₂ emissions of the shipping industry have declined by 20%. You always have to be careful with percentage calculations. You always have to ask yourself: What is the initial value? What is that in general? Well, it is a fact that before the share of shipping of the global CO₂ emissions was 2.8% and now it is rather 2.2%. #00:23:57-1#

I: *Yes, that is the new IMO study.* #00:24:00-4#

E4: I have read that in this context in the THW, the ICS had somehow published something there. Well, we have saved 20 per cent, but in total numbers that represents 0.6% of the total emission and finally if I would maybe save another 2 per cent that would do away with the shipping industry. And there you start to kill yourself laughing. If you get more and more new requirements placed on you on the other hand that are very difficult to adhere to. Today we have the highest fuel costs in history - that have ever existed. The share of fuel costs of total operating costs of the vessel are sky high. Depending on the ship type and route and so forth easily half of the total costs, if not more. What is the motivation of the ship operator that is thereby emerging? Certainly to save fuel. Saving fuel means saving CO₂. That is a very simple correlation. Actually we do not see any necessity at all to implement any further efficiency models and monitoring and then also, I don't know, create some... emission trading systems and other mechanisms constituting huge administrative burdens to order to virtually achieve nothing at all. Or maybe only very little. In the worst case however to achieve that vessels cannot operate at all any more or whole services have to be given up. We naturally are very worried about that. #00:25:35-6#

I: *I have tried... we have spoken about different areas that are currently being regulated... to picture the seven areas in which a vessel pollutes the environment. Would you say that is correct? Or is there something missing?* #00:25:56-9#

E4: (Thinking). On the first glance you have everything on there. #00:26:06-3#

I: *If we... we have spoken about legislation in the different areas. If you look at these now: Which areas are currently not at all or under-regulated and which are currently maybe*

strongly or over-regulated? Where is a lot happening? #00:26:24-2#

E4: Yes, certainly. We have already spoken about that. Air pollution is a huge issue. Sewage water is an issue, but currently already regulated. Related to the IMO, the implementation is still coming, but that is in fact the issue. Ballast water, clearly. We have spoken about that. Relating to the anti-fouling systems, thus our anti-fouling requirements, there we have done the big step a few years ago, away from the TBT-containing paints... (thinking) To my knowledge that is currently not a problem. Even if in the long run it is to be expected, in my opinion, that someday there will be a new approach to move away from toxic anti-fouling systems altogether. #00:27:22-4#

I: *Are there in the meanwhile good alternatives to TBT? #00:27:26-1#*

E4: Well, what has been successfully employed for many years now are basically paints where the tin, tributyltin, has been replaced by copper compounds. Thus one moves away from this tin, but now one has copper in there as a toxin. The alternative would be silicon based paintings; they do not contain any toxin any more. There one tries to achieve that by the outer shell being very sleek to avoid that these creatures can cling to the vessel at all. That has advantages and disadvantages. Naturally very sleek outer shell coatings are always also good for efficiency and for saving fuel. You have problems with the application however, sometimes with the durability. We always only have very short time windows, sometimes only in the middle of the winter, to bring the vessels into the dockyard at all and then to apply a silicon based paint that needs certain temperatures, curing times and so forth that is sometimes very very difficult. That are the very practical problems. But at the moment that is not an issue. Oily water we are not allowed to spill over board anyways. We have our bilge water separators on the vessel, 15ppm. That is being controlled at every control on board. We partly already have newer systems that are even better than the old 15ppm system. Thus if one day - I am not informed how the current status of discussion is at the IMO – but if one day it should come to 5ppm, that could be done as well with the technology. That is also not such a problem for me. Waste water we have spoken about: We will dispose on land and that makes more sense for the ferries. We are in the harbour every day. We collect maybe 20, 30 tonnes of waste water per round trip. That you can dispose of within two hours on land. That is something else with the large cruise ships. They have totally different problems. Noise is so far not a topic with us at all. Unless we are talking about harbours, where there might be noise emissions produced when the cargo is going across the ramps. That gives a bang at times. If there are people living in the proximity that is occasionally a topic. But in general, also at the IMO level, that is unknown to me... that we also additionally have to do something against noise pollution. And waste we are not throwing over board for full 30 years now. We are also not burning it. It is being collected on board for a long time and also separated, as we know it on land and then dispensed of in different fractions again, because partly we even receive a little money for that, if we separate it. Hazardous waste is collected in special containers on board and handed over to a specialized company. All these things we have been doing for 20, 30 years. #00:30:46-0#

I: *Which of these issues, also the ones where something is happening at the moment, which are really expensive for shipping companies and which may be safely ignored? #00:30:55-8#*

E4: Well, very expensive is the sulphur issue. Simply because the fuel is so expensive. That

is the issue that for us the ferry shipping industry may lead to threatening our existence.
#00:31:12-3#

- I: *And afterwards, ballast water or something like that, that is not so ...* #00:31:17-5#
- E4: We just expect, because we are time and again... naïve I would not say, but optimists and we say there has to be an allowance for, let me say, a pragmatic approach. We expect that we do not have to build any complex sewage water treatment... not sewage water, but ballast water treatment systems onto these ships. Even if one has to do that, it will not kill us. Although it will pose problems. Not only because it costs money, but also because we strictly speaking do not have space on such a vessel for any additional complex systems, but I think that one will always find a solution. Thus the only thing that lies really heavy on our stomach it this specific sulphur issue. Also with NO_x. We have done trials with NO_x katalytic converters. Already in the 90s there was a research project. We know what that means. We know that it works. We know what it costs as well. The industry will also – quotation marks – survive that. The obligation to use gasoil, that can cost the existence of some services. Simply due to the higher costs. Today we have some... the problem is that we do not know where the prices will go to. We know the current price structure and I think, the difference today between heavy fuel oil and gasoil is somewhere at 250 Euros per ton. You can calculate that. You will have to ask more money of the customers for the journey. To what extent the customer will accept that, we will have to see. But what we do not know is if it stays at 250 Euros per ton or if the price difference will not significantly increase in Europe or in the SECA areas due to the increased demand from 1 January. Some say it will also get smaller, because suddenly there is higher demand, there will be more delivered. There will be coming more from North America and I don't know where, there will be more distillate fuels brought here to Europe and that will put downward pressure on the prices. But we do not know. #00:34:00-6#
- I: *You said for some services that might be a question of existence. What kind of services are that? How are they characterized? Which shipping companies will make it?* #00:34:12-8#
- E4: That are those... a), as I said, the longer services are rather more endangered and then also the services that today can barely keep above the water economically. Thus, where the shipping companies are not taking out large profits, but where the services are also partly operated for strategic reasons. That you say: There will be a growing market in the future. Let me say the Baltic states maybe, Russia. Today I am not yet earning much money with that, but I already have my foot in the door. And if that really picks up I am the one that is already there. Well, in the light of these enormous cost increases that is naturally, I could imagine, that the one or other services is maybe for the time being discontinued. #00:35:05-4#
- I: *In how far is that related to the size of the shipping company?* #00:35:13-1#
- E4: I do not think that there is a direct relationship to the size of the shipping company. You mean... I understand a little bit that you want to ask if in a larger company the services in deficit could be subsidized by other services or something like that. #00:35:31-4#
- I: *For example, yes.* #00:35:33-6#

- E4: That is certainly possible to a limited extend over a limited amount of time. I think that also large shipping companies – we are really rather a small player here – I think also larger shipping companies have to make sure, in the long run, that all their services run profitably. And only where one says, for example due to strategic thoughts: Maybe I am not making that much profit in the beginning, but I'm already there, I can do that for a certain amount of time. But in the long run I do not think that that plays such a role. I might be wrong about that. I am also not really an expert on that. #00:36:27-7#
- I: *If we look at the shipping industry as a whole, is it rather easier or more difficult for certain types of business models – thus, if I do containers or bulk or tanker – do they have different problems to deal with the legislation or is that essentially the same, as the rules are the same?* #00:36:52-7#
- E4: One has to differentiate depending on the legislation in question. Well, you have just had this nice picture with the different environmental themes that we have in the shipping industry. A nice example is that the ballast water issue for example is a huge issue for a bulk shipper, tanker I think is the same, as they have to deal with very much different amounts of ballast water than we do. And because they operate specifically this international trade. For us, in spite of the fact that it is at first formally an issue, but as I said, there is the prospect of a reasonable solution at the end, where we do not have to solve that issue technically, but somehow formally by way of an exception will not have to do it. And such a vessel at times takes up maybe 100 tons of ballast water per trip or 200 tons, in order to have a better trim or something like that. I mean, with a bulk carrier you are talking about many thousands of tons if that goes into ballast voyage. Thus, there the colleague from the bulk trade has a problem and we not so much. While we have this huge problem with the SECAs, as we do 100 per cent of our business in the SECA. We are only here. While the colleague that sails with his container vessels from Rotterdam or Hamburg to the Far East, the share of the total journey that he sails on diesel oil in the SECA is comparatively small. And thus also the cost increase is significantly lower than with us. Thus in this respect: It is very different, from topic to topic I would say. #00:38:44-4#
- I: *That means if we say: Sulphur is THE big issue...* #00:38:50-5#
- E4: (interposes) For US as a ferry shipping company in the SECA, yes. #00:38:55-1#
- I: *Well, then I have to ask differently. If we say for the ship owners that sail on the North and Baltic Sea it is a huge issue. Now I forgot what I wanted to ask. Well, than let us go to the next topic. I will come back to that.* #00:39:15-0#
- E4: May I propose that I first of all offer you something to drink? In the meantime? #00:39:20-7#
- I: *Yes, that is also an option.* #00:39:22-1#
- E4: Because we are talking the whole time. Would you like a coffee or rather some water? #00:39:27-2#
- I: *I would gladly take some water.* #00:39:27-4#
- E4: Yes, then I will quickly get some water for us both. #00:39:30-4#

I: *Yes, perfect. Thank you very very much. #00:39:31-3#*

E4: And put your machine on hold for once and then we will continue in a minute.
#00:39:34-9#

(Short break, expert catching some water.)

I: *We are jumping back and forth all the time. That is great. We will go on from here. We still have a few questions left from the beginning that I still have to process. If we look at the legislation in its entirety, how has the political interest changed in the last years in the shipping industry itself? #00:40:08-9#*

E4: I would say that the shipping industry has much more come to the focus of attention. I have been doing this business already since the 90s. Since the beginning of the 90s. In those times... evidently, we already had these issues in our mind. We as a ferry operator, we are very much at the focus of attention here. The guests in summer here in [holiday village close to city 4] marvel at the big beautiful white ships and if there is black smoke coming out of the chimney... that has been already been an issue in the local press twenty years ago. Thus we have been occupied with these questions in those days already and have partly found quite interesting solutions already. But looking at the global or at the big picture is has only received more attention in the last years. I think also because then, in the 70s and 80s there were first of all other problems to deal with. They then first of all dealt with the car traffic, with the large power plants, all these things and did a lot of legislation and brought than on the way and shipping was always a side issue. A vessel is at times in the harbour and then it is gone again and then you do not see it any more, like that. #00:41:29-3#

I: *Out of sight, out of mind. #00:41:30-7#*

E4: Exactly. And that has quite SIGNIFICANTLY changed in these 20, 25 years. The vessels are much more at the focus of attention. One speaks much more in the harbours, more about for example shore side power supply or pollution in general. Quite evidently. #00:41:52-0#

I: *On which political level are most of the things happening at the moment? Does one look at the international level or is European legislation playing an important role for shipping companies? Or is it also the national level? #00:42:07-1#*

E4: We ship owners... the ship owners would like to see it, if it WOULD take place more on the international stage, as shipping is an international business. From our point of view it does not make any sense at all to invent regional or local rules in order to tackle any problem, if that could not be at least as reasonably be embedded in the international context. I mean, well, we here can NOT run away from the whole thing, as a ferry operator, that is really also rooted in the South-Sweden traffic and really has never done anything else. But that is a special story. If you look at our competitor Finnlines, behind that is the Italian major shipping company Grimaldi, ancient family business. Meanwhile they are also operating internationally. They are strongly involved in the ferry operations in the Mediterranean Sea as well. Whatever is not working up here anymore will be pulled off and will be moved to the Mediterranean and then the money is earned there. That is how simple the world is for THEM. A little bit strongly

simplified, but I am saying, local or regional legislation is eventually nonsense, because in the worst case it really only leads to displacement, that is some traffic is driven out... gone... yes, well, driven out one could say. Insofar, yes, it is... We would like to see international legislation and ONLY international legislation. We also know however, or experience shows that especially in the EU it is strongly tried to go a very own... let's say... to invent everything anew again. The IMO passes MARPOL VI and three years later the EU is talking about an EU sulphur directive. That is almost the same. #00:44:16-5#

I: *Is it then difficult to adjust to that? Or does it not matter as it is the same content anyways?* #00:44:26-5#

E4: No, it is not always... there is no guarantee for that. And it is also not always the same, because the EU has years ago said, on top of what was internationally agreed, yes, but when you are in a EU harbour and longer than two hours you have to operate on gasoil in the harbour. That we already do since 2010 due to the EU legislation. And if you look at the new sulphur directive, that is not one to one copied from MARPOL, instead the EU always tries time and again to put a little bit on top, whereby she can only do that evidently in her sphere of influence, thus only in the national waters. But the tendency in Europe is quite clear to always again and again also have an own approach and if possible to do a little on top. #00:45:24-4#

I: *You said before: Each time somebody comes to control that. How often do these controls occur and who is doing them?* #00:45:36-3#

E4: That is very different, but these that I spoke of before, with the bilge water separators, that is here in Germany the harbour police that acts as an organ for the BSH (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie), thus for the controlling authority in the end. Well, the security approvals are done by the ship security department of the BG Verkehr (Berufsgesellschaft für Transport und Verkehrswesen). The tasks are distributed. #00:46:02-6#

I: *Who is controlling the sulphur regulations in the end?* #00:46:06-0#

E4: Yes, we would like to know that as well. (Laughing, ironic undertone) That I do not know yet. I cannot at all tell you. #00:46:14-3#

I: *Okay, well, that is still three months away. (Ironic undertone)* #00:46:15-9#

E4: We will see then. At the moment there is an upcoming discussion... well, technically, the density of controls may likely not be very high, as there are also resources missing. #00:46:31-8#

I: *Can you control that in the harbours? Or would you normally have to control that on the open sea?* #00:46:38-1#

E4: Well, theoretically you could control the emissions with appropriate measuring tools always when the diesel is running and the vessel is producing emission. But de facto it is being controlled via a bunker sample. That means, when you are somewhere in the harbour, somebody in coming on board and is taking a sample of your fuel, sends it to the laboratory and two weeks later or one week later he receives the results, where he

can see... It already works like that today. Today we already have limits for the sulphur content. At the moment we may not have more than 1% sulphur in the fuel and that is also every now and again verified through the analysis of a bunker sample by the harbour state. #00:47:30-5#

- I: *What happens if I have a vessel that also leaved the Baltic Sea at times and then I have several tanks with different fuels on board?* #00:47:38-6#
- E4: Well... (laughing) That is where the practical problems begin, I think. That is again not applying to us. Well, we do have two fuels on board today. In the future it will then only be one. But with a vessel that has two or three different types of fuel on board. Yes... (thinking) There is the oil record book, there everything is meticulously recorded and you will probably first of all take that. And then, okay, this and that fuel is in this tank and we will first of all take a sample. If I have actually used that tank I naturally have to note down in the oil record book. Full stop. (laughing) The rest I leave to your imagination... (meaningful voice) Well, it is certainly not easy to control that. I am also stumped for an answer... I do not know, in how fare one can measure somehow from an airplane, when flying over a vessel, if one can measure anything accurately enough so that you can also derive a watertight legal case from that. Well, that is still a very exciting question, the implementation of the rule. #00:49:03-6#
- I: *How significant will the share of ship operators eventually be that are adhering to sulphur regulations?* #00:49:13-0#
- E4: That question I cannot answer. (Laughing) How shall I know, how many black sheep there are? #00:49:21-1#
- I: *That should be interesting to know, as they will have completely different cost structures as well.* #00:49:28-4#
- E4: There is a ship coming from somewhere, from Africa or wherever and sailing into the Baltic Sea or already when they are coming into the North Sea they have to switch. But how may I really control that? #00:49:43-5#
- I: *Are there companies that over-comply with the rules?* #00:49:48-5#
- E4: In general or rather specifically to the individual... #00:49:53-1#
- I: *If we for the moment just talk about sulphur. If that is going to be the main issue.* #00:49:59-0#
- E4: Over-comply... Well, I have a number of options to comply with this law. I have first of all the option to burn low-sulphur fuel. If that is a liquid fuel today that is normally gasoil, which is then allowed to have a maximum sulphur content of 0.1%. In practice it lies likely somewhere slightly below that, but let us say that with that I do not yet over-comply. There are occasionally also among the ferries already vessels that use liquefied natural gas. There is virtually no sulphur at all contained in liquefied natural gas. They are de facto over-complying. And we are just now learning about our scrubber, that is now peu à peu entering into operations, we see that the emissions translated into the sulphur... if I translate that to sulphur in the fuel... the emissions obviously are better compared to if I burn the 0.1 fuel, as the scrubber has a better

separation efficiency, cleaning performance. Insofar I am then over-complying. Actually I just wanted to reach 0.1, but now my system is better, if you meant that. #00:51:22-1#

- I: *Can I use something like that for my marketing? Do I get a benefit from that?* #00:51:29-6#
- E4: From past experience: No. No. Well, we started here already in 1995 with a new generation of ships at the time to burn not yet gasoil, but marine diesel oil. That is quasi gasoil. It has small differences in the specification. The sulphur content was slightly higher. That was somewhere between 0.2 and 0.3%. That was however, for the 90s, when we normally had like two and a half to three per cent sulphur fuel on the Baltic Sea, that was a CLEAR over-compliance. We have done that, because first of all the fuel costs were lower at the time, also the difference was correspondingly lower and we have evidently also had advantages due to these clean machine operations. Well: Significantly longer maintenance intervals, lower maintenance costs, spare part costs and such things. That was a very clear concept that we had that we at the time also, let us say, we shouted from the rooftops a little bit for advertisement, with our green ships it was called then and so on. Just, according to my knowledge, we have done that for ten years with this shipping generation and have then reconstructed to heavy fuel oil, because the costs had increased so much. That was economically simply no longer sustainable, these distillate operations. In all this time we have not been able to detect that we have had any economic advantage somehow from all that, apart from friendly pats on the back and friendly nods from politics and all sides. Well now, that the customer would have said maybe: No, I would rather like to go with [company 4], because they are so CLEAN. Nada. #00:53:24-2#
- I: *What a shame.* #00:53:24-8#
- E4: But such is the world. As soon as the own funds are in question, environmental issues become a bit second-ranked. Unless I have so much dough that I can afford that. The maybe I prefer to travel with a green cruise ship than with another. But I think that these things do not play a big role in customer behaviour. #00:53:46-1#
- I: *You said: Then an African ship is coming. Does that then depend on...* #00:53:53-0#
- E4: Well, just as an example. #00:53:53-6#
- I: *Can you say that...* #00:53:55-9#
- E4: I do not want to discriminate anyone here. Well, the vessel is coming from anywhere, where these rules do not apply. Let us say it like that. #00:54:00-1#
- I: Well then, can you... does it depend on the country of origin or flag, if one rather adheres to such rules? Well, you could say: Vessels flying the German flag tend to comply more than vessels that fly the Liberian flag? No? #00:54:22-0#
- E4: No, no. If a vessel is flying the Liberian flag normally there is a German or Norwegian or British shipping company in the background or a Greek shipping company in the background. He is flying the flag, because that brings economic advantages to him. But the decisions are not taken in Liberia. Why should then... One has to be careful there.

Why should the Liberians see that laxer than the Europeans? I cannot postulate that neither. And I will not. No, that is not related to the flag. That is really related only to money. (laughing) #00:55:00-6#

I: *Is it difficult, simply technically difficult for certain vessels to comply with environmental legislation?* #00:55:13-8#

E4: There you have to differentiate again. Well, to bunker a clean fuel is easy. It just costs money. To install and operate a complex exhaust gas emission cleaning system is rather more demanding. It costs money as well and so forth, but also takes space in the vessel, can lead to stability problems – that the vessels become top-heavy – is not that easy in operations, because you now have much more systems that the crew now has to operate and has to operate correctly and so on. LNG, that is liquefied natural gas, is an interesting story, but technically very demanding and will certainly only be practicable and operational with specially trained staff, who know how to deal with this technology. That is a substance that is -163°C cold. You cannot touch that any more. It also cannot touch on any unprotected structures anywhere, as they will thereby be destroyed. There is also a certain problem with explosions risks and such things with gas. Thus thereby the shipping operations get more complicated. In that respect the gasoil operations are really easier. #00:56:54-2#

I: *Are all ship operators equally well informed about the legislation and also the technical possibilities?* #00:57:02-7#

E4: I suppose so. Well, in this trade, in the ferry business, I would spontaneously answer that with a yes. (Confident voice) Because as a ferry operator who is moving within the SECA we have been affected very early by that and have seen the problem coming and have been occupied with that for years and that applies to my colleagues in the other shipping companies just the same. #00:57:31-8#

I: *Where do you get information on new legislation?* #00:57:36-1#

E4: First of all from the German Ship Owners Association, also from international associations. We are a member of Interferry, of EXA and of those again, of the ICS. But it is mostly the shippers associations that inform us very early on about new legislation and legislative developments and also integrate us into the discussion processes. And in the end we are evidently also being told by the authorities. #00:58:08-3#

I: *But one cannot complain that he has not known about it, so to speak?* #00:58:13-1#

E4: No, no, definitely not. #00:58:15-5#

I: *Are there currently major technological developments in the pipeline that maybe make it easier for ship operators in the future to comply with sulphur regulation?* #00:58:44-5#

E4: Well, relating to sulphur I would say: Yes, in any case, because all these... first of all these scrubbers are in development. I am convinced that the technology that we built in today will already significantly differ from the scrubbers that you will get on the market in five years' time. They are then more mature. One knows the processes better. One was maybe able to make the equipment smaller and more efficient. Definitely: yes. LNG

is also... is really a very old technology, as liquefied natural gas has been driven around the world on tankers for many, many years. To use it as a fuel on such vessels like ferries is however new. The Norwegians have been doing that already a little longer, but the development naturally lies more in the details. A new, interesting development is currently coming from the oil companies, who now also have to struggle with this issue and who are now increasingly coming into the market with heavy fuel oil that contains not more than 0.1 per cent sulphur, what we have always said in the earlier times that that would not exist. When I started I knew that occasionally there is heavy fuel oil with 0.5% sulphur, but only in small amount, in limited amounts. And now suddenly the colleagues from the oil industry are coming onto the market saying: Dear shipper, I offer you heavy fuel oil with 0.1, with which you can... #01:00:36-5#

I: *Is that then significantly more expensive than...* #01:00:38-9#

E4: It is certainly more expensive than the heavy fuel oil that we bunker today, but at the moment not as expensive as gasoil. #01:00:49-5#

I: *Are there any experiences with that yet?* #01:00:51-8#

E4: We have none so far. But we will also occupy ourselves with that. Naturally. Evidently. Because the battle is fought over the price in the end and over the costs and that is clearly interesting for us. Also if that was not the original idea of the legislator, who wanted to get away from the heavy fuel oil. He has just not written that into the law like that. He did not say: From 1 January heavy fuel oil is prohibited, but he did that via the sulphur content, ASSUMING that there is no heavy fuel oil with 0.1 per cent. What will now happen from my point of view? I am now speculating as well. The oil industry suddenly has a problem with getting rid of the residual oils from the oil refineries. Before it has worked wonderfully as a fuel for the shipping industry and how that option is taken away or partly taken away. And naturally they are thinking about what they can do in order to get rid of the residual material like before. Otherwise that would be hazardous waste that would be expensive to dispose of. Well, I could image that from that corner there was a drive in the question: How do I get my heavy fuel oil to 0.1? Than likely in the next step the legislator will think of something else, but for now the situation is like that first of all. #01:02:20-0#

I: *In how far do... we have talked about different options to deal with that. In how far are these options applicable to all vessel types and in how far do technical restrictions exist?* #01:02:38-5#

E4: Well, there are... theoretically... as a technician I would say: Theoretically, if money does not play a role I could realize each of these three options, namely gasoil, scrubber, LNG on each vessel. From a practical point of view however there are many vessels on which economically that would not make any sense, because they are either too old or because they operate for too little of their time in these SECAs. There I would not do a scrubber. There I would not do LNG. There I would just simply switch the fuel. What we also realized is that the retrofit of existing vessels to LNG, at least for our fleet, would be extremely expensive so that it would not pay back. Also not pay back any more with younger ships. That simply has to do with the fact that you have to recuperate the costs within some reasonable amount of time. In this business it is not possible any more to do that within a reasonable amount of time. Thus one will see that rather little. At the moment, in relation to the ferry shipping industry, I would say that scrubber are

rather an interim solution, are a technology that I built on existing ships that still have a reasonable life expectancy. I will also not do that on old vessels, there I will have the higher fuel costs as a millstone around my neck and see how I can still economically make ends meet with that steamer. LNG is something for new vessels. That is something for new buildings. #01:04:31-4#

I: *Thus if now a new... I mean, if you were to order a new ferry LNG would be an interesting option.* #01:04:39-2#

E4: ... LNG would be an interesting option, one that we would sincerely study. Although it has to be seen in the light that at the moment there is no infrastructure available for LNG in the harbours, but one would still sincerely study this option and would also come together with the harbours and see how to get this fixed. #01:05:01-6#

I: *Are there innovations that currently are much too expensive to amortize, but that are somehow dreams of the future, if they become more... I have heard somewhere... is that called methanol or something?* #01:05:19-3#

E4: Yes, Stena is trying methanol as a fuel. That is not really very much science fiction, I would say. But it is still something that one has to observe first of all. Well, methanol is a substance that is not so very easy to handle. In addition one has to see as well, where the methanol is coming from. Methanol is an alcohol. There you have to very closely scrutinize the sources, so that you do not somehow enter into a food-for-fuel or the other way round fuel-for-food discussion, not that somewhere arable land is used in order to produce fuel. The next question, well, I am not really familiar with the details, but it is a question that comes to me spontaneously, is the question of water consumption in the production process of such substances. Water is also a limited resource on this planet. Thus – does it make much sense? You also have to look at that. What also could one day become interesting, in the future, so to say, would be hydrogen as an energy source. There we already said 10 years ago: Gosh, that is maybe already coming in 10 to 20 years and hydrogen is interesting – no emissions at all apart from water vapour. In rare cases that already exists in the automobile sector, but already for a long time in test applications, via a combustion engine as well as via a fuel cell. The German navy has submarines that are powered by fuel cell propulsion with hydrogen. Also on the Alster [lake in Hamburg] a pleasure boat is swimming around with a fuel cell motor. That can also become interesting. By way of the LNG we get towards, I would say, the technology how to deal with very cold materials. Once that is established in the shipping industry one could imagine to also do the next step towards hydrogen that also needs to be cooled down very much in order to store it somehow reasonably. And with these explosions... let me say... with all these security issues one would also already have approaches from the use of LNG. The question that I need to ask in relation to hydrogen is: Where is the matter then produced, so that I do not free much more CO₂ during the production process than I am saving in the end? Still, that might also one day be possible. I am also not familiar with the details there. But those are maybe some options for the future one day. #01:08:22-2#

I: *If we look at the SECA directive, but also at everything that is happening at the moment, in how far does that have an influence on the costs of vessel operators?* #01:08:44-5#

E4: A cost increasing influence. #01:08:48-2#

- I: *How significant is that?* #01:08:51-4#
- E4: Well, I could not give you any numbers. If you take one of our vessels then that vessel needs about 10,000 to 11,000 tons of fuel a year. Then you can sail back and forth for a year. The price difference, as I said before, it at the moment at 250 Euros per ton. If I now simply take 250 times 10,000 then I have somehow two and a half million on my sheet – additional costs – for one vessel and we have six of them. Then I am already at 15 million for the whole fleet. You have to earn those first of all, those 15 million. Next year our accounts are stressed by that amount more compared to today, this year. If the difference between the two fuels increases, the costs will increase even further. Thus at this point alone I already have, I cannot calculate that now, but a significant increase in costs. #01:10:08-3#
- I: *In how far does that have an influence on your freight rates?* #01:10:14-3#
- E4: Yes, we have to pass these costs on to our customers. #01:10:18-3#
- I: *Can you pass them on to the full extent?* #01:10:22-4#
- E4: We have to. We have absolutely no other choice. I cannot tell you by how much the freight rates will be increasing and the freight rates themselves are as well, let me say, confidential. They are bargained with each customer, thus with each big forwarding agency, individually, but there will be, in the form of a surcharge, there will be a cost burden passed onto the customers and at that point the risk of modal shift is arising. Would we put the added costs into, let me say, our own pockets, that is wrongly expressed, but pay them out of our own pocket and if we could do that, we would not have a problem with modal shift. We would then have a cost problem, but the volumes would not be lost on us. #01:11:16-0#
- I: *Do all shipping companies that are competing with you act in a way to pass on the cost increases or will there also be a new price war?* #01:11:29-9#
- E4: There is always a price war. That exists for every single customer. You can certain that in particular cases in will come to special conditions here as well, but that is the normal business now for many, many years. But what we are hearing at the moment, from our competitors, is that everybody will be increasing their costs from 1 January. Also the freight rates will be increased. For passengers as well the tickets will become more expensive. There is going to be a surcharge of somehow three Euros per passengers, something like that. #01:12:06-4#
- I: *Is it easier to increase the costs for the passengers than for the cargo? Is there a higher level of acceptance?* #01:12:17-7#
- E4: That will show. I cannot tell you yet. But the passengers will... that is like if my... Yesterday they said in the news that the railway is increasing its prices again in December. At the same time I can in the meantime take the bus from here to Munich if I want to go there. Where that however in the end... How that is now shifting we cannot yet foresee. #01:12:48-7#
- I: *But these three Euros per passenger, that are really simply the cost increases passed on or does one also spare the passengers* #01:12:57-6#

- E4: That I do not know now. Such data and such details you are not using anyways or only anonymous or in no way at all, right? #01:13:19-1#
- I: *No, that is just for me to get an impression how that is working in the end. If we now take one step back: How do you assess the situation of the shipping industry in general at the moment, independent of environmental legislation?* #01:13:37-3#
- E4: The situation of the shipping industry... Well, now not only the ferry shipping industry but... right? #01:13:44-8#
- I: *Yes.* #01:13:45-0#
- E4: Well, (thinking) the motor of the world economy that is not given any attention at all by the general public. No-one of us is buying a t-shirt for ten Euros in a shop is aware that that thing can only cost ten Euros because the freight rates are so ridiculously low, because the vessels are simply transporting the goods very efficiently around the globe with comparatively small impacts on the environment and in general. #01:14:28-6#
- I: *If you look at the economic situation of the shipping companies – how has that changed in the last years?* #01:14:34-6#
- E4: The shipping companies, well... the big slump came in 2008/2009 after the crash, after this real estate bubble in America and this whole story. There we had on our services for example a loss of up to 25 per cent of the cargo Trelleborg-Rostock due to the economic slump. And the colleagues in the worldwide voyage did not have it much better neither. That I only know from following the media as well. Let me say THW and Hansa and foreign media. The deep sea shipping industry has not really recuperated from that yet. Especially when we talk about the container industry, the colleagues are still fighting with extreme overcapacities on the market. #01:15:37-6#
- I: *Has that stabilized in the Baltic Sea already?* #01:15:41-4#
- E4: At a low level. We are not yet back to the figures of 2007 and we find it quite difficult to get back up there as well. #01:15:54-0#
- I: *How does the development for the coming years look? What do you expect?* #01:16:01-8#
- E4: That is precisely this MARPOL topic again, this SECA topic. It is very difficult at the moment to give a forecast. Basically, we cannot say anything yet. By the way, what is quite interesting – and as I am coming from shipbuilding, I am actually a shipbuilding engineer – if you look at the order box for these vessels worldwide, there is almost nothing on the lists any more. What we still... 2006, 2007, 2008, where we definitely still had up to two dozen vessels of this type ordered in the shipyards that have then obviously successively been delivered, I can today count that on one hand. No one is ordering anymore, because all ferry ship operators are in the same predicament here in Europe, that they do not know where they are going. The risk of such a huge investment no one can any longer take, apart from very few exceptions. #01:17:17-2#
- I: *The growth forecast for international trade is very positive. What are the reasons why*

everybody is now hesitating so much? #01:17:33-3#

- E4: Well, especially with us there is really this uncertainty: How do the cost structures look in one, two years? How has the traffic been distributed? Thus at the moment one has no really reliable forecasts on which one could somehow build a business case. On the other hand you have the costs for this tonnage, if you now again... What is the future? Where are we going? – The costs have not been significantly decreasing. Thus, such elaborate vessels such as these ferried, they are today, I would say a vessel like our [name of the vessel or organization 4], let us assume, if we would order her anew today, that we would have to invest somewhere between 100 and 120 million Euros for such a ship. That is more or less double of what we have paid for that vessel at commissioning twenty years ago. Well, that is also a very long time, but the costs are extremely high and the money will have to be earned first of all and that is with the existing fleet. If the market is so much under pressure due to the fuel costs and all the uncertainty. How do you want to somehow recover all this huge amount of money? You have to go to a bank and explain to them: Listen, I want to buy a vessel or want to have a vessel built, that costs such and such amount and I expect this and that profit a year from which I can repay my credit and that will then theoretically take 50 years for me to repay. The bank will then say: Here, you have bets in the belfry. You should better go home. That is the problem. That is why at the moment everything is in such a process of standstill. Everybody is waiting for the 1 January and for the next year. How will that develop? Where will that be going? #01:19:48-7#
- I: *What are the biggest chances, but also the biggest risks for the industry in the next years? #01:19:56-6#*
- E4: (Thinking) I will stay with the ferry industry, as I cannot say anything about the others. (Thinking for a long time) That is a difficult question. Well, the risks we are talking about the whole time. The question is answered, where the risks lie. #01:20:28-4#
- I: *Are there other risks independent of environmental legislation? #01:20:33-9#*
- E4: A big risk that besides is worrying us here for specific services from Germany over to Sweden as well is evidently the fixed link, the fixed link across the Fehmarnbelt that is supposed to be ready in 2021 now. There we have to see, if that... But one day it will be there. And how will cargo be shifted then? Those are risks as well. Therefore... chances? I do not want to sound too pessimistic, but I would artificially have to make up something out of thin air to say: There we see chances. Well, if we would not somehow see a future for our company, our shareholders would certainly say: Come on, people, give up. We can invest our money better somewhere else. Then that would be the end of [organization 4]. But that is not yet the case. We have not yet come to that, but we are hoping that we can – first of all with this SECA issue – we can live with that as [organization 4] on our services and we hope for an improvement of the market. Specifically not only more volumes, but also especially better freight rates. I could now formulate a little bit cautiously: Evidently there is also a chance in such a market consolidation as will maybe take place – a chance for the survivors to find a better market environment. But that is naturally a testimony or a statement, where one... #01:22:39-3#
- I: *Will such a market consolidation take place now? #01:22:42-6#*

- E4: Not at the moment, not yet. If I do not take into account the Sassnitz service, the Herriage service. Maybe these services would have been discontinued earlier or later also without the SECA, because the traffic flows have simply moved away for other reasons in the course of many years. Still, we have not really had the big bang so far. But it is already still too early. That is not to be expected yet. #01:23:13-8#
- I: *Are there other issues that occupy the industry at the moment apart from environmental legislation?* #01:23:21-2#
- E4: Not to such an extent I would say. (Thinking) Years ago we had much to do with vessel safety after the Estonia accident in the 90s and we have been occupied for years with security issues, but that really already collected a lot of mileage by and large. The rules have been changed, have been significantly tightened as well. That is why the vessels are so expensive today, because the building regulations are very much different from back then. Which is also a good thing, because the vessels have thereby become much safer. Then came the 11st of September and we have had to occupy ourselves in the years following very much with security. At the moment that is however also... because, thank God, there is no perceptible threat of terrorism in Europe to that extent that would worry us here. That is currently also rather calm. I cannot say anything so such things as tax legislation or something. Payroll costs are always an issue as well. That also has to do with national legislation and other things. Our main topic at the moment is this environmental issue. #01:25:05-7#
- I: *I have three last questions: Are there any important topics, any important aspects that I have not yet covered? That I should be taking into account as well?* #01:25:18-4#
- E4: No. I cannot think of anything right now. We have actually covered everything... Let me think. (Thinking) As I said, we have touched upon the climate issue as well. That, I think, will occupy is a lot more in the next time, because that... We are through with the sulphur. With the scrubbers we have a follow-up topic at the moment. You are washing the sulphur from the emissions and then that is in the water, in the wash water that we have on board the vessel. There are two types of processes in application. The system that we have now bought is able to do both. The one process, from sea to sea, is called open loop. There the sulphates, that I produce through the washing process there, evidently flow into the sea water again in the end. The process water is cleaned from other substances, thus mainly from these whole particles that I then intercept and so on. Still, I emit water over board that has a high level of sulphates, thus is practically acidic. That will be neutralized in the sea water, but what kind of effect that has on the marine environment will have to be further studied. We certainly do this within the currently existing regulations, but it is an issue, where we do not know as well, what might come about. If there is going to be maybe a full ban on the introduction of water for the Baltic Sea or only for national waters. We can also operate the system in closed loop operations, than nothing is going overboard in the first place. Still, also there waste water is occurring to a small extent, but there also waste waters are occurring, that one has to first of all collect on board the vessel and when for example lying in the harbour, but that one has to get rid of at a certain point in time. Either by giving it back into the sea, even though it is cleaned from all the dirt, that somewhere... for god's sake, it is not like the whole dirt is again emitted into the sea, but these very sulphates are in the water as an acid residue. Otherwise I have to somehow dispose of that on land, where we do not have real disposal systems for that yet. Not to talk of the costs. Well, that is a little aspect in this whole story that we are just coming into contact with now, because

it is also new for the authorities. Now the shipping companies are coming - here in Germany we belong to, I think, to the first ones who are doing that at all – and they now have a such a system that is supposed to be approved. And now they are suddenly aware. That really is a crazy story. #00:89:00-3#

I: *Can you think of any other experts that I should be talking to about this?* #01:29:06-3#

E4: Certainly. In the meantime there are experts with the classification societies that deal with that. We have our vessels with... in earlier times it was called Germanischer Lloyd, now we have to adapt – DLV GL. #01:29:23-8#

I: *Well, funny. I have already talked to that expert.* #01:29:25-6#

E4: You have already talked to that one. Then there are the... There I naturally also think of the people that are building these systems. Especially the scrubber systems. They are however not located in Germany. Our scrubber is coming from the Finnish company Wärtsilä. The technology however is actually coming from Norway. That was originally really a Norwegian company. Those are the experts that we have to do with relating to this sub-topic. There is someone at the Association of German Ship Owners, you have already spoken to them. They also have clever people there. In the ministries, at the Federal Environmental Agency. They do not like us, because we are not sailing, but operating motors. Well, that is a little exaggerated. They clearly like us, but we naturally have differing interests. #01:30:31-1#

I: *Last question: Do you still want to tell me anything?* #01:30:35-4#

E4: (Laughing) No, [interviewer]. That was already very exhausting altogether. The question is, if I shall still provide you with any numbers? In the aftermath. #01:30:55-2#

I: *Well, if you have any numbers that might help me...* #01:30:59-7#

E4: Well, the trade volumes. What did you mean with that? Practically, how much we transport each year? #01:31:05-3#

I: *Exactly. But I can also get that from the internet myself.* #01:31:07-9#

E4: Thus how many units for example. I can give that to you quite fast. #01:31:12-1#

I: *Yes, that is maybe... well, then.* #01:31:13-6#

E4: And passengers. Units, for us that is cargo units, trailers with tractor unit and without. #01:31:24-6#

I: *Numbers that will give me an idea...* #01:31:28-8#

E4: Freight rate differences, as we said... #01:31:31-7#

I: *In how far such modal shifts... or when they become interesting. If you have anything in that direction that would arguably be very valuable.* #01:31:40-5#

E4: Basically we do not have these numbers either, because we do not know where the breakeven point is. We do not know. We have tried, in this study... there are also our numbers included in there, in the ISL results and there we have tried to get that data for once. That is now already a few years back. And in addition those are numbers that are also normally not leaving this house. But I will gladly give you, and this will be possible at short notice, I can give you an impression of what [company 4] is transporting in a year.

#01:32:20-8#

I: *Yes, wonderful. Then let me heartily thank you.*

Interview No 5

Date: Wednesday, 1 October 2014, 10am

Duration: 58 minutes

Method of contact: I met E5 by chance on a conference where he described quite drastic consequences of environmental legislation to the shipping industry during a podium discussion. An email requesting an interview was sent on 19 September 2014 followed by an affirmative answer on the same day. The interview took place on 1 October 2014.

Interview situation: The interview was conducted via telephone with the interviewer in her own office and E5 in a London hotel room. E5 was reached abroad on his mobile phone. The connection was steady, but personal connection was a little difficult to establish. No interruptions of any kind occurred during the interview.

E5 was friendly, but a little reserved. He had to be encouraged to illustrate answers and would mostly answer without much detail. He was very knowledgeable on the subject with 40 years of experience and very much familiar with environmental legislation in all fields. Data and potentially sensitive information was (apart from one instance) freely provided and all questions duly answered, albeit in very few words.

Another expert with a container shipper was named with the option of providing contact information. Interest in the results was voiced at the end of the interview.

- E5: [Introduction] #00:00:00-4#
- I: *Hi this is Thea. #00:00:04-5#*
- E5: Hi there. How are you? #00:00:06-7#
- I: *I am fine. Would you have time now for the interview? #00:00:08-3#*
- E5: Yes. #00:00:14-4#
- I: *Okay, perfect. I think I need about 90 minutes, I hope that's fine for you. #00:00:14-1#*
- E5: As long as I have enough battery on my phone it will be fine. #00:00:22-5#
- I: *Okay. We'll hope that you have that. So thank you very much for making time. I am writing my Ph.D. at the moment and I am studying or trying to study unattended trade effects of current changes in environmental legislation for shipping. I have done a bit of literature review and what I am currently doing is reviewing a lot of experts in the field to get a grasp of what the problems really are and what the key issues are, what the significance is of environmental legislation for the industry and what the consequences on costs and freight rates are. So the first questions that I have are just a little bit of background information. So I would like you to tell me what your position is in [organization 5] and what you are working on at the moment? #00:01:22-2#*
- E5: I am the director responsible for environment and sustainability. #00:01:26-2#
- I: *Okay. And so what are the key issues that you are dealing with at the moment? #00:01:32-3#*
- E5: Everything on the environmental legislation. In particular at the moment the coming sulphur legislation or actually the new limits in the sulphur legislation. It's the coming MRV legislation. It's the implementation of the energy efficiency directive, which is another EU directive. I guess that's my key issues right now. *(Laughing)* #00:02:09-0#
- I: *Okay. Are you working alone or do you have lots of staff to support you with those issues? #00:02:15-1#*
- E5: I am a one man at the department when it comes to the environment. I am also responsible for shore based health and safety and there I have a colleague that helps me. #00:02:28-2#
- I: *Okay. How did you acquire specific knowledge in this area of environmental legislation? #00:02:35-5#*
- E5: Forty years of working in shipping. I don't have a professional background as such. I have my forty years of being involved with shipping and that is really the background I have. *(Laughing)* #00:02:57-7#
- I: *Yeah, well forty years is a long time. Have you been with [organisation 5] all those years? #00:03:02-2#*

- E5: No. I have been with [organization 5] for four years and before that I worked for [a container shipping company]. #00:03:09-9#
- I: *Okay, yes. Okay. So a little bit background on [organisation 5]: How many vessels do you operate at the moment?* #00:03:18-8#
- E5: Around fifty. #00:03:20-0#
- I: *Okay. Do you own all of them?* #00:03:23-3#
- E5: No, we own about two thirds. #00:03:26-6#
- I: *Okay. What business sector is that? Is that all short sea shipping?* #00:03:30-0#
- E5: It is RoRo trade. It is passengers. It is a little bit of container ships and then we have a couple of dedicated or we call sideboard ships. They are dedicated to the paper industry. Our network is very predominantly in North Europe. We do have one route that connects the North Europe with Spain and we have one road down in the Mediterranean. #00:04:08-4#
- I: *Okay. So what kind of goods would you mainly be transporting?* #00:04:12-2#
- E5: Lorries, rolling stock, any kind of consumer goods, steel, paper, cars. You look around the room you are now it's probably been transported on either one of our ships or one of our trucks. #00:04:31-1#
- I: *Okay. What volumes are we talking about round about?* #00:04:36-2#
- E5: We measure in lane metres. Are you familiar with what that is? #00:04:43- 3#
- I: *Yes.* #00:04:43-3#
- E5: Yes, okay. We do about 25 million lane metres a year. #00:04:47-7#
- I: *Okay, yeah that's quite a lot.* #00:04:49-0#
- E5: We do just over 5 million passengers. #00:04:49-2#
- I: *Okay, yes. And my focus at the moment is on goods transport really, we will talk about it a little bit. What flag are those vessels flying?* #00:04:52-3#
- E5: Danish flag, UK flag, French flag, Lithuanian flag. #00:05:03-1#
- I: *So European ones? All of them?* #00:05:11-3#
- E5: Yes. #00:05:14-4#
- I: *Yes, okay. Does the fleet currently undergo any changes due to environmental legislation?* #00:05:21-1#
- E5: Yes. #00:05:22-2#

- I: *Which changes are that? (Laughing) #00:05:35-5#*
- E5: Actually yesterday was the last sailing of a route we have between Denmark and the UK, a combined freight and passenger route, that we have been operating for 139 years. That closed yesterday. #00:05:40-0#
- I: *Oh, that's quite recent. And that's... #00:05:44-4#*
- E5: That was very sad. #00:05:45-5#
- I: *Yes, and that's entirely due to environmental legislation? #00:05:50-0#*
- E5: What is entirely? The environmental legislation was the stroke that broke the camel's back on this one. #00:05:57-7#
- I: *Okay. What would be other reasons that you are struggling? #00:06:03-0#*
- E5: This route we have been operating for almost 140 years. It was a big blow to the route when the tax-free sales within Europe disappeared. And since then we have been operating the route with one ship and it's been okay without being brilliant. And we just couldn't see that with the new costs coming on that it could be viable going forward. Had there been other good elements in there we might have continued, because it is... The one reason that made us take the decision was the coming sulphur regulation and the costs associated with that. #00:06:55-5#
- I: *Are there any other changes in the rest of the fleet? #00:06:59-6#*
- E5: We have publicly stated that a number of our routes could be at risk because of this. We have not named any. In spring we did close a route between Klaipeda in Lithuania and Sassnitz in Germany. Again part of the reason here was the coming cost increases. And we could not see the route be sustainable going forward. #00:07:29-0#
- I: *Have you been opening any routes at the same time? #00:07:33-3#*
- E5: Let's see...well we have been upgrading in the... (Thinking) actually we did open a route but... the current Russia-crisis killed it again very shortly after. #00:07:53-2#
- I: *Oh, okay. #00:07:55-5#*
- E5: So we also have that. One of our [portry?] routes we expanded that to a new port pair. But with the current Russian situation the traffic in and out of there has been affected. #00:08:14-3#
- I: *Okay, yeah. Just a little bit talking a little bit about environmental legislation as a whole. What initiatives are you aware of that are currently being undertaken by legislators? #00:08:35-5#*
- E5: The ones that have been approved or the ones that are being worked on? #00:08:41-1#
- I: *All of them. #00:08:41-9#*

- E5: Okay, where should we start? We have the sulphur regulation, we have the NO_x tier three levels, we have the Ballast Water Convention, we have the MRVs [EU system for monitoring, reporting and verifying (MRV) emissions from large ships using EU ports], we have the propeller sound limitation, what else can I mention. We have well ... EEDI is approved. Hong Kong convention is awaiting ratification. This shipboard energy efficiency management program. What have I forgotten? #00:09:26-7#
- I: *Just talking about those- which of these occupy you the most?* #00:09:34-4#
- E5: At the moment sulphur followed by the Ballast Water Convention. #00:09:40-0#
- I: *Is that also the ones having the largest cost effects on you?* #00:09:41-5#
- E5: Yes. #00:09:45-6#
- I: *Yes?* #00:09:46-6#
- E5: Yes. #00:09:46-7#
- I: *Comparing those two which one is more important or what cost role do they play?* #00:09:55-5#
- E5: Well the sulphur one is not even 90 days away now. So that is highest on the agenda. The Ballast Water Convention I expect the last countries to ratify that sometime this autumn so it will come into force in the autumn of next year. That is going to be another major one for shipping. It's going to cost shipping worldwide about 30 billion US dollars. And unlike the initiatives on CO₂. CO₂ has an effect on your cost as well: If you reduce the fuel you reduce your costs. Sulphur legislation and Ballast Water legislation - there is no immediate cost reduction at all combined with these regulations. #00:10:56-3#
- I: *Okay. If you think about the other initiatives you just named are there some that don't really play a role in terms of cost? That you are not thinking about too much?* #00:11:12-2#
- E5: I don't know. The deep sea [resolution?] with the propeller noise is still vague so I don't have a picture yet on the effect on cost on that one. The EEDI and the NO_x tier three are really applicable for new buildings - so until we decide on a new building it doesn't have an immediate cost effect. MRV - well MRV will have a cost effect. Yeah. Does that make sense? #00:11:56-6#
- I: *Yes. That made sense. (Laughing). Who are the most active legislative actors at the moment?* #00:12:03-2#
- E5: As far as we are concerned it's the combination between the IMO and the EU. #00:12:12-2#
- I: *Okay. Who influences you more?* #00:12:15-4#
- E5: EU. #00:12:18-1#

- I: *Okay, why is that?* #00:12:20-0#
- E5: Because that is our home basis where we trade. What you tend to see is that IMO sets a kind of a global regulation. The EU will then often complete it a little bit so you have to comply with EU and then you are automatically complying with the IMO. #00:12:42-2#
- I: *Okay, yes. So you do not really have to look at IMO regulation because the...* #00:12:50-0#
- E5: Well yeah, because a lot of the idea they start there. So we follow it quite closely. #00:12:57-7#
- I: *Who is enforcing that legislation?* #00:13:02-2#
- E5: What part of it? (Laughing) #00:13:04-4#
- I: *I do not know. (Laughing)* #00:13:07-7#
- E5: Well I mean the sulphur legislation if we take that is supposed to be enforced by the port state controls in the countries. Whether it will happen or not is a different question but that's the way they are supposed to do it... #00:13:28-2#
- I: *How is that working?* #00:13:29-9#
- E5: Well we have to see. Port state control is already in operation today and they check a lot of other things. They do not check a lot of fuel compliance. There is some worry within the industry that there won't be a lot of policing going on from next year. #00:13:55-5#
- I: *Okay, yes. It is even possible to police sulphur legislation in the ports?* #00:14:03-1#
- E5: (Laughing) That is a very, very good question. There is kind of two kinds of policing here. One is detecting if anybody is not compliant. The other thing is to have the details so you can prove it and issue a fine. There are two different things. You can detect non-compliance for instance by having sniffers on the bridge or in a plane or drone or something like that. You can fly over the ship and say okay, this ship is not-compliant. That is not valid evidence to issue a fine for. To issue a fine it's mentioned in the legislation there you have to take... either the oil record book has to be falsified or that you take a sample from the relevant tank and this is sent to a laboratory and proven to be out of [spectre?]. #00:15:02-3#
- I: *Okay, but how can I make sure that that tank was actually used?* #00:15:07-1#
- E5: (Laughing) You are asking the questions that I ask. How do you take a sample from a tank that was used two days ago? #00:15:16-4#
- I: *Yes. Okay, so are you saying it is impossible basically?* #00:15:25-7#
- E5: I am saying it's going to be very, very difficult. Then it is also an issue of who actually has the right to check for what? If you take an EU directive - the way it is implemented

is that it is transposed into national legislation. So the sulphur directive for instance is 28 national legislations in the EU countries. They would all be slightly different. And then it is a question of what jurisdiction do the individual countries have in this respect. It is something that at least in my mind is not clarified yet and I think the lawyers will be earning some money in the beginning of the New Year when everybody needs to find out exactly how this works. #00:16:16-8#

I: *So would you as a company have to know all those 28 national legislations?* #00:16:23-3#

E5: Yeah, of course. #00:16:24-4#

I: *How do you do that?* #00:16:27-7#

E5: They are all quite similar. What can vary is the fine level for instance and the procedures for non-compliance. We are certainly not planning to be non-compliant in any respect. We do not expect - we do not see that we will have an issue with this but I am sure that somebody will. #00:16:52-4#

I: *Still talking about legislation- who is trying to enforce stricter rules even than existing at the moment and who is maybe trying to keep the rules at a lower level? Who are the actors?* #00:17:13-4#

E5: Basically it is the EU commission - and of course there is a number of different organizations lobbying there. And there will be a lot of NGOs that are trying to have stricter limits to what we have today. #00:17:37-7#

I: *Yes. When we talk about those lobbies- who has most power over the legislator at the moment?* #00:17:46-5#

E5: I do not know. I could not say. #00:17:52-2#

I: *Okay. Overall have environmental efforts been increasing in recent years-would you say that?* #00:18:01-1#

E5: Substantially. Substantially. It has really jumped up the agenda in the past five to eight years. #00:18:10-0#

I: *Okay. What issues do you see next on the agenda?* #00:18:14-3#

E5: Regulation on PMs. #00:18:18-8#

I: *Okay. Is that going to affect your business as well?* #00:18:24-4#

E5: It depends on how you work it out but personally I see PMs as a true area where you have to increase the efforts. PMs are really what is causing a lot of the bad air that we have around in Europe at the moment. And there is really nothing regulating that today. So I think that should come. There will be some kind of regulation for that. #00:18:53-7#

- I: *If we think about the legislation that is in force at the moment or coming into force - how well are ship owners aware of all those efforts? All the things they need to do?* #00:19:08-2#
- E5: I think if you take ship owners as a global you may have some concerns. If you take... if you have the SECA area and clearly those of us who operate in the SECA area as well - if it is the European one or the U.S. one - will be aware of all the requirements. But whether your operators that are predominantly based outside of the SECA area - they may not be fully familiar with what the requirements are inside. #00:19:43-3#
- I: *Okay. How many of those are actually entering the SECAs that occurring often or ...?* #00:19:49-9#
- E5: I don't know on the company level. But I have heard the number 17,000 ship visits a year in the north European SECA area. #00:20:00-2#
- I: *Okay. Yes, so that's quite a lot.* #00:20:04-4#
- E5: That's quite a lot, yeah. #00:20:06-6#
- I: *Where do you get information on all the new rules?* #00:20:09-2#
- E5: (Laughing) I could say through my network. We have... #00:20:18-8#
- I: (Laughing) *Who is in the network?* #00:20:19-1#
- E5: Who is in the network? We have our ship-owners organizations in the country where we have ships. We have the ferry umbrella organisation in Brussels which this called Interferry. We have the European ship-owners organisation and then I get some feeds from the EU commission also. So I signed up to some of these newsletters that they send out so I get that. #00:20:48-8#
- I: *So what you say it is rather easy or difficult to acquire information and understand what you are supposed to do?* #00:20:58-8#
- E5: It is relatively easy to acquire information. To digest it and fully understand what is meant is something more complicated. #00:21:07-4#
- I: *Okay. But at the moment you know what you are expected to do, right?* #00:21:12-2#
- E5: I hope so. #00:21:25-4#
- I: *Okay. (Laughing) Does everyone in the industry have the same level of information or are there some ship owners who tend to be not that well informed?* #00:21:25-5#
- E5: I would say probably yes. Most of the people that I deal with are fully up to scratch when it comes to the knowledge. But I wouldn't be surprised that there wouldn't be ship owners, operators out there in the world that are less informed than we are. #00:21:53-3#

- I: *Would you say it is an issue of company size? #00:21:56-6#*
- E5: Company SIZE? #00:21:59-1#
- I: Yes. #00:21:59-9#
- E5: No. #00:22:01-9#
- I: *No? So a small operator could just as well informed? #00:22:07-7#*
- E5: Yeah, yeah. #00:22:08- 8#
- I: *Okay. How will you as a short sea shipping operator or also the other trades you do be complying with the SECA regulation? #00:22:24-3#*
- E5: Basically through two, perhaps three ways. First of all the easy way is: a number of our ships will switch to the low sulphur fuel on the first of January. Then we have engaged in a substantial program to retrofit our fleet with exhaust gas scrubbers. We have eleven ships done so far. We do another six ships next year. So they will be operating on heavy fuel oil and then the scrubber solution. And then I guess some time in the future, but nothing has been decided yet, we will be also looking at LNG propulsion. #00:23:12-2#
- I: *Okay. Is that different for other ship owners who carry bulk or tankers or containers - do they make different judgements there? #00:23:26-6#*
- E5: Yeah. The vast majority will be switching to marine gas oil, i.e. the low sulphur fuel. #00:23:34-4#
- I: *Okay, why is that? #00:23:35-5#*
- E5: Because to do anything else you have to be in special position. I mentioned that there are about 17,000 ships getting in and out of the SECA in Europe every year. On the first of January it will be about 65 ships in the world with a scrubber and there will be approximately the same amount of ships running on LNG. So that is a very, very small minority compared to the global. LNG probably will make sense for new buildings. Scrubbers, for the investment in a scrubber, you have to meet a number of criteria to be able to take that decision and very few companies actually do that. Meet those criteria. But we are one of the companies that do. #00:23:37-6#
- I: *Yeah. You said that most will be switching. Is that a problem of availability or will that be just fine? #00:24:34-4#*
- E5: On gas oil I do not think so. That is at least what I heard from the industry we are talking about a 7 per cent switch of product here on the first of January globally. And that should be doable. However the gas oil refining capacity in Europe is fully utilized so the additional product that is needed for this will have to be imported. But it is available on the world market. #00:25:09-7#
- I: *Okay. Do you expect any companies to or do any companies tend to over-comply with environmental standards? #00:25:19-9#*

- E5: Yes. We do for instance. #00:25:23-3#
- I: *Okay. Why would you do that?* #00:25:25-5#
- E5: Well basically, if you take our scrubber ships and they are the ones I am thinking about. The legislation has a maximum limit. What you do is that when you design your scrubber you define it so in the worst case scenario you will be at the maximum limit. But most of the time you are not in the worst case scenario. So actually the measurements that we have made is that we will only be emitting on the average basis about half the emissions that we are allowed to emit when we use a scrubber in our ships. #00:26:11-2#
- I: *Okay. Are there any companies that you expect to only comply partly?* #00:26:20-0#
- E5: I hope not. #00:26:24-4#
- I: *But if you would think about what kind of companies were most likely to do that - what would characterize them?* #00:26:34-4#
- E5: Characterizing is that they are irregular visitors to the SECA. They probably... it would be tramp business, I would suspect. The thing is: The financial gains of not complying will be significant. There is definitely a risk that not everybody will be fully compliant. #00:27:07-3#
- I: *Also when we talked about lacking controls before that could also be an issue.* #00:27:15-5#
- E5: It is like a speed limit on a high way you know. If there is a speed limit and you advertise in the paper that there will not be any police then the chance that the speed limit will be decreased is bigger, right? #00:27:29-9#
- I: *So if you don't expect to be controlled why would you comply?* #00:27:35-5#
- E5: Because you have to? #00:27:38-3#
- I: *So you say it is more like the environmental consciousness on your side?* #00:27:43-3#
- E5: It is in the DNA of most companies that we are doing business in an environment where there are certain rules and we might not like all the rules but you have to comply with the rules - that is what good companies do. #00:27:59-9#
- I: *Okay, yes. Do you think that it might be more difficult for smaller companies to comply than for larger companies?* #00:28:13-7#
- E5: No. #00:28:14-4#
- I: *No? Does the business sector again make a difference? So would bulk carriers or container carriers or whoever rather tend to comply than the other?* #00:28:28-8#

- E5: No, I do not think that really. Those who only trade inside of the SECA area they will really not have a chance to not comply. Because if they do not comply you would actually be able to see it directly on their financial accounts that the cost has not gone up. So they do not even have to measure anything there. #00:28:57-2#
- I: *Yes. Would you say that generally the flag a vessel is flying or the main seat of operations are an issue?* #00:29:07-8#
- E5: No. #00:29:09-9#
- I: *No? Okay. Good to know. Is the average age of the fleet somehow a good indicator of environmental friendliness?* #00:29:20-0#
- E5: Yes. #00:29:21-1#
- I: *Why is that?* #00:29:25-5#
- E5: Well basically the newer the ship the more modern technology you generally would have on board. That does not mean that an old ship cannot have been upgraded all along. But a new ship would certainly have all the newest stuff on board. An old ship may have some of the new stuff on board may have all the new stuff on board but may also not have not any of the new stuff on board - and technology is developing constantly. So, no - the newer the ship - it's the same with the car, you know, they are more fuel efficient the newer the car you get. #00:30:01-1#
- I: *Yes. So you just said that technology develops constantly so what are current innovations that would help you comply?* #00:30:14-3#
- E5: Are we now talking sulphur specifically or are we talking emissions in general? #00:30:23-3#
- I: *We could be talking emissions in general.* #00:30:25-5#
- E5: Emissions - well there is a lot of design going on hull shapes, on propeller shapes, on water shapes and how they interact with each other. There is a lot of redesigning ships to sail at slower speed and having the ship hull optimized. So, lower speed sailing, because that is what the shipping world is doing today. There is a lot of control features on your pumps and ventilation systems. So there is all sorts of fancy measurements on how the ships trim is as it goes along through the water. How the stability is managed. There is a lot, a lot of smaller things and bigger things that are being now tested every day. #00:31:27-5#
- I: *Would those be having a significant cost effect?* #00:31:31-1#
- E5: Some of them may definitely yes. I mean we have on a number of our ships we have changed the propeller, we changed have the motors and that is a significant cost. But there we can do a business case and see you know how much fuel we will be saving by doing it and as long as we are within the payback time it will be fine, acceptable. It is a thing we can do. #00:31:57-6#

- I: *Yes. Would those innovations or could they be used on all vessels?* #00:32:03-2#
- E5: Yes. #00:32:03-3#
- I: *Or are there restrictions?* #00:32:05-5#
- E5: No. #00:32:05-9#
- I: *No. Where do you acquire information on all those new technologies?* #00:32:12-2#
- E5: (Laughing) Yes, again I mean that is through our network, that is through a lot of suppliers and innovators. They contact us and say they have a new idea. But then it is also, you know, with our technical people, they get to the technical people from other companies or suppliers or something like that. You hear about the new things in trade publications. You hear about new things. #00:32:45-5#
- I: *Yes. So when you installed the scrubbers was that a risk you took or did you know that they would be working?* #00:32:57-6#
- E5: No, actually we were the first ones to install a full size scrubber back in 2009 and that was definitely a test environment for us and for the scrubber manufacturer. And we operated that ship now for four years before we took the decision to go full scale. #00:33:19-2#
- I: *Okay. Because I hear that a lot of ship operators are currently still waiting to take decisions on what to do in three months.* #00:33:28-8#
- E5: That is right. #00:33:29-2#
- I: *Is that linked to this experience issue?* #00:33:34-3#
- E5: It is linked to a couple of things. First of all the technology is ever evolving. If you decide on something today you have the risk it will be optimized tomorrow that somebody invents something new and smarter and better. That is the one thing. The other thing is that scrubbers are really linked to sailing inside the emission control areas. If you have a trade that also sails outside of the emission control area, how big will that be? The legislation is that in 2020 the rest of the world should have a sulphur cap of 0.5 percent. That is according to the IMO MARPOL and it is according to the EU sulphur directive. But the MARPOL has an escape valve that can postpone the date from 2020 to 2025. #00:34:36-6#
- I: *Do you expect that to happen?* #00:34:38-2#
- E5: Well it is subject to a report that has to be published in 2018 on the global availability of the necessary fuel. And if you are a global operator today and you do not know whether there will be a global limit of 0.5 percent in 2020 or just a European limit – it is very difficult to take such a decision, such a significant financial decision, if you do not know in which environment you will be operating. And that is one of the reasons a lot of people are WAITING, in my mind. #00:35:17-7#

- I: *So it is really the global operators that are waiting it is not the ones just operating in the SECAs? They have taken their decision? #00:35:27-2#*
- E5: Yes. #00:35:27-9#
- I: *Okay. Are there any technological innovations that are currently too expensive, but that will be developed into something great in the future that you know of? #00:35:39-9#*
- E5: Oh, I am sure there will be. There will be a lot about fuel cells if you look 10, 15, 20 years down the line. I think fuel cells will be something that will be coming up. #00:35:53-5#
- I: *Okay. We will see what happens there. I got a few questions on the effects that you expect. In what way is the business model of a shipping company affected by current changes? #00:36:12-4#*
- E5: I mean it is a significant cost increase to all operators. And it is necessary to increase prices because of this. If shipping increases prices but the competing modes of transport do not, you must expect some kind of a modal shift. How much exactly where? I am not sure. But clearly, if you have to go out with a 15 per cent cost increase, your costumers will look out for alternatives. Either for alternatives of moving their goods in a different way or the alternatives of finding a different source for the goods that may then be cheaper. And it is this model shift that we are all very excited to see exactly what is going to happen. I think everybody has got this idea of what may happen but there are so many factors in the equation here that you cannot really make a model. #00:37:24-0#
- I: *Yes. So starting with step one - to what extent will costs increase? #00:37:30-0#*
- E5: That very much depends on WHERE. If you look at the ships who are typically crossing the channel the increase will be less. If you are looking at sailing from Finland to France the increase will be more. #00:37:49-9#
- I: *Okay. So what percentages are we talking about? #00:37:53-3#*
- E5: I think we are talking anything from - and that is an educated guess - from 5 to 40 per cent. #00:38:03-3#
- I: *Okay. That is a lot. How will that make a change to freight rates, to what extent? #00:38:18-1#*
- E5: That is the 5 to 40 per cent I was talking about. #00:38:25-2#
- I: *Okay so you can actually move all those cost increases over to your customers? #00:38:32-3#*
- E5: We hope so. We have to. #00:38:37-3#
- I: *Are there any differences in short sea shipping and other trades? #00:38:43-4#*

- E5: Well, I guess there is a difference in the way that the surcharges will be calculated and the price - but the principals will be the same. #00:38:54-5#
- I: *Okay. Do you expect any differences in freight rates for the Baltic and the North Sea? Or is that the same?* #00:39:03-2#
- E5: Again the longer the ocean route the bigger the increase will be. #00.39:09-9#
- I: *Okay. Would that also be the same for small and large companies are they affected in the same ways?* #00:39:21-1#
- E5: Yes. It is down to the ship. #00:39:23-3#
- I: *Yes. Is the amount or share of goods transported by sea in any way influenced?* #00:39:37-7#
- E5: I need that question again please? #00:39:43-3#
- I: *Would you say that the amount of goods transported by sea would be in any way influenced? So...* #00:39:52-2#
- E5: Yes. #00:39:52-9#
- I: *What kind of goods could I move to the street or to the...?* #00:39:58-8#
- E5: Well I do not think it is the type of goods. It depends on the corridor that you are moving goods in. If there is an alternative that involves either road transport or rail transport or if there is an alternative that rather than a long ocean voyage you have a longer road voyage and a shorter ocean voyage. These are kind of moves that you could see. And in addition to that you will see some shift because of sourcing will completely change. So instead of buying your paper in Finland you may buy your paper in Canada. #00:40:38-6#
- I: *If I say that I move goods from the ferry to the lorry for example moving from France to Finland – what would that mean in terms of time and also in terms of costs?* #00:40:55-5#
- E5: Well in terms of costs you would do it because it is cheaper than the new shipping cost. And... #00:41:07-3#
- I: *Yes.* #00:41:07-9#
- E5: In terms of time again it will very much depend on from where to where, you know. If you have to go a detour because you are staying on the road or are you basically driving along where the ship was sailing in the past. It is difficult to give one answer to that. #00:41:26-6#
- I: *Okay. How significant are differences in freight rate between ship and lorry at the moment?* #00:41:34-4#

- E5: Per ton, on a kilometre basis, how would you like that...? #00:41:43-3#
- I: *Yes for example. Just to give me an idea. I do not really understand that aspect at the moment. Which goods would be moved and when and it would depend on the price basically right?* #00:41:58-6#
- E5: Yes, again you have to look at the kind of goods that we move. Which is, we mainly move lorries or things that go on a lorry. So whether it goes on a ship or they stay on a lorry - it is the same move. And therefore which way it goes is very much a combination of price and time. #00:42:22-3#
- I: *So are there at the moment any differences in freight rate usually or so is it just a time issue at the moment or is it actually a price issue?* #00:42:37-7#
- E5: It is a combination of time and price. Some goods could go cheaper via ocean but they are very time sensitive so they go by road all the way. That is a commodity thing. #00:42:55-5#
- I: *Is it even possible to say how much the difference in freight rate is or does it change too much?* #00:43:03-3#
- E5: No. You cannot give a number there. #00:43:06-0#
- I: *So the one could be cheaper at the one time and then the other one at the other?* #00:43:09-2#
- E5: Yes. #00:43:10-0#
- I: *Okay. That makes sense. If we talk about modal shift what would that mean for the environment?* #00:43:18-5#
- E5: It would be negative. (Thinking) But to what level I do not know. You will have more emissions. If you modal shift you will see probably most of it going back on the road. You will see increased congestion probably in the corridors that are already very busy. #00:43:46-7#
- I: *Okay. Could the road even take the extra amount of lorries?* #00:43:52-2#
- E5: Yes. #00:43:54-4#
- I: *Okay.* #00:43:55-5#
- E5: But there will be pockets where there are difficulties, but... #00:44:02--2#
- I: *What kind of economic consequences do you expect due to modal shift?* #00:44:07-7#
- E5: The additional cost to shipping in North Europe of the sulphur directive is around 3 billion Euros a year. That is a significant amount of money. And you do not add that kind of costs without it having an effect. It is difficult to forecast how big the effect will be and it will certainly be different from area to area. #00:44:40-0#

- I: *Okay. If you talk about that huge amount - who will carry the costs? #00:44:46-6#*
- E5: Predominately the end user, the customer. Because it is simply not that amount of money in shipping that shipping can absorb this cost. #00:44:58-8#
- I: *The way I always understand the shipping industry at the moment is that the competitive situation is quite harsh. #00:45:08-2#*
- E5. Yes, yes it is. #00:45:10-0#
- I: *And if you look at normal economic models where the economic situation is harsh that also means that there is lots of price fights and that also means that normally the costs would not be handed over to the consumer. #00:45:28-8#*
- E5: Yes but these increases in costs are so big that if you do not get additional revenue you will go bust. #00:45:35-6#
- I: *Okay. But you would still say that you could hand 100 per cent of the costs over? #00:45:46-6#*
- E5: I think that is what you have to hope for. Whether it will happen I do not know. But that is... #00:45:55-0#
- I: *So there is not going to be price fights in the industry? #00:45:58-8#*
- E5: There may be. There may be. I mean when you have this kind of change in the patterns and somebody is losing out you know people would take measures to try and regain a lost market share. It may happen. But in the long run the industry cannot afford to absorb these extra costs. There is simply not that amount of money in the industry. You can do it and that will then mean that some companies will go bust or routes will close down and that we already seen. #00:46:34-5#
- I: *Do you expect competitors to leave the market? #00:46:39-9#*
- E5: I would expect some kind of consolidation in the market as a consequence of this. #00:46:48-8#
- I: *Okay. I have got a few questions moving a bit away from environmental legislation to get a more general picture. How would you generally assess the current situation of the shipping industry? #00:47:05-2#*
- E5: It has been seven very tough years since 2008 for the industry. So there is not a lot of fat, not a lot of money in the war chests. In the last 12 months things, signs are improving. So we hope we can get back to where we were before the financial crisis started. It is a tough business. #00:47:41-1#
- I: *What developments do you expect for the upcoming years? #00:47:44-4#*
- E5: In terms of? #00:47:47-0#

- I: *In terms of the competitive situation for your industry. #00:47:54-4#*
- E5: I mean growth in our markets, which are the European markets, is limited. So what you will have to see is you have to see this constant drive on cost reduction on a per unit basis. But when there is so much turmoil in the market as we will see from next year there will also be new opportunities coming up some places. And I am sure there will be somebody there to pick up on those. #00:48:28-1#
- I: *Okay. So where do you see the biggest opportunities? #00:48:32-3#*
- E5: Ah that is a trade secret. (Laughing) #00:48:36-3#
- I: *Okay. (Laughing) Let us say for the industry in general. What could happen? #00:48:44-4#*
- E5: I mean when you look at it and basically you say the longer you sail today the more you have to increase your price that would kind of... the conclusion there is, if you have an option of sailing a shorter route there would optionally... that would be more attractive going forward. #00:49:15-4#
- I: *Okay. What are the biggest risks apart from environmental legislation? #00:49:21-1#*
- E5: I mean the problem we have here is the sulphur regulation will be significant and will have negative effects on companies and jobs and whatnot. And in my mind the problem which we have here is that it is a kind of a big bang implementation. Everybody has to comply as of one day. If you look at say the NO_x tier three legislation that is for new buildings. If you look at the Ballast Water Convention you have a five year phase-in-period. But the sulphur regulation is everybody on one day. And that is a very big shock to the system. #00:50:15-7#
- I: *Okay, yes. If you compare other risks for the industry to environmental legislation would you say it plays a big role or are there other factors that influence the industry even more? #00:50:29-9#*
- E5: No. It is THE factor that influences the industry the most at the moment. In this year. #00:50:36-2#
- I: *Okay. What other topics would currently be occupying the industry? #00:50:41-1#*
- E5: The Russia situation and what is developing there. If you look more globally Ebola seems to be a hot topic, but we are not involved with trade to the involved countries there, but I would have presumed that global carriers are looking at that very carefully to decide what to do. #00:51:08-4#
- I: *Yes. Okay. I have got three last questions. Are there any topics that I have not been addressing in the last minutes that I should take into consideration when researching the effects of maritime environmental legislation on trade? #00:51:31-1#*
- E5: Well available finances. #00:51:38-8#

- I: *Okay. How is that? #00:51:41-1#*
- E5: Well as we talking cost increases there is quite some significant financial issues that you need to consider. If you are switching, which most people will, to the low sulphur fuel - their fuel bill at the end of January next year will have gone up by 50 per cent. Will they have the cash to do that? Do they have the credit line to do it? Will the fuel companies be allowed to extent 50 per cent more credit to their customers? Fuel business is a low margin business. So will their banks allow them to extent that much more credits? So will it be a cash flow situation very quickly in the New Year? The other thing is that this new legislation what will that do to ship values? Take for instance retrofit of a scrubber. That is a cost of for us somewhere between 5 and 10 million Euros per ship. Is that an increase in the ship value or is it a decrease in the ship value? #00:52:57-8#
- I: *How could that be a decrease? #00:52:59-9#*
- E5: Well if the ship trades outside of the SECA area you are carrying some extra weight and some extra costs of operating. For which you do not get any money. So the ship will actually be less valuable trading outside. #00:53:17-1#
- I: *Yes I see. Talking about finances - how is the financial situation at the moment? #00:53:28-2#*
- E5: Well it is very tricky for shipping. As you know a lot of banks have decided to go out of the shipping market and for a lot of companies getting financing is quite difficult. You have to either get finances, for the sulphur, you have to get financing either to pay your increased operational cost or to pay for your investment in new technologies. And that is that. #00:53:54-0#
- I: *Could I not usually cover the additional costs with additional income? If I switch to another fuel? #00:54:09-4#*
- E5: Well I mean that is what we hope for. But there is still a time difference between when you have to have the costs and when you get the income. #00:54:19-3#
- I: *Okay yes. Well with scrubbers I totally see that because you need to invest but if I am able to put 100 per cent of the extra costs to the consumer I should have not problem. #00:54:33-8#*
- E5: No, but you will still have a cash flow issue that you will need to look at. How much credit are you getting with your fuel supplier? How much credit are you giving your customers? Normally there is a gap there. #00:54:47-5#
- I: *Okay yes. Okay next question. Are there any other experts that you can think of that I should be talking to? #00:54:55-0#*
- E5: There is quite a few. Depending on – are you looking for the same market kind of business that we are in or are you looking for a different market? #00:55:20-6#

- I: *Well one of the questions that I am asking myself is if there are any significant differences between the markets so... #00:55:30-2#*
- E5: Yes. I mean we are very much in the RoRo business. If you want to talk to a big operator in the container business you could talk to Unifeeder. They have a totally different business model to what we have. We have a lot of own ships. They predominately charter their ships. But they are also heavily involved inside of the SECA area in the container transport. So that could be one option. #00:55:56-2#
- I: *Yes that's quite interesting. #00:56:03-5#*
- E5: To look at that. #00:56:05-1#
- I: *Okay yes. Have you got any contact details for them? #00:56:13-7#*
- E5: I would have yes. I do not have it right here in my little hotel room where I am now but I can send you a couple of names. #00:56:22-4#
- I: *Yes, that would be amazing. Okay, last question. Is there anything else you would like to tell me? #00:56:30-1#*
- E5: Well I would like to see the end result. #00:56:35-9#
- I: *Yes me too. (Laughing) #00:56:36-2#*
- E5: (Laughing) But otherwise no. #00:56:41-9#
- I: *Yes, I'll keep you informed as soon as there are any major developments. #00:52:47-0#*
- E5: It's a topic that a lot of people are interested in right now. We have heard several approaches for something similar from a lot of institutions. #00:56:59-9#
- I: *Yes, I see that, but I also see there is lots of interest from the industry as well. #00:57:06-4#*
- E5: Yes. We would like to know what we are heading for. #00:57:09-4#
- I: *Yes. I am trying to find out. #00:57:13-0#*
- E5: Yes, well the only thing that is certain is that we are heading for change. #00:57:17-3#
- I: *Yes. Okay then I am through with my questions. Do you have anything else you would like to ask me? #00:57:26-4#*
- E5: No. If I do then I will send you a mail but right now I cannot think of anything. #00:57:32-3#
- I: *Okay perfect. Thank you so much [E5] and have a wonderful day in [city 5]. #00:57:36-8#*
- E5: Thank you. #00:57:37-7#

I: *Bye.* #00:57:38-8#

E5: Thank you, bye. #00:57:40-0#

Interview No 6

Date: Thursday, 23 October 2014, 10 am

Duration: 118 minutes

Method of contact: I contacted E6 via email when first starting to research the topic on 1 February 2013 asking for input on research gaps. A telephone conversation regarding research gaps took place on 4 February 2013, where E6 identified cost increases due to environmental legislation as a major research gap. Contact was made again via telephone in August 2014 asking for support in setting up interviews and for an interview with E6 himself. Following a personal conversation in the office building of E6 on 27 August 2014 both were readily granted. The interview took place on 23 October 2014.

Interview situation: The interview took place in a conference room in the office building of E6. The room was spacious and quiet, no interruptions occurred and the interview could be conducted very smoothly. Coffee and water very available and both were served at different points during the interview. After an hour and a half E6 asked for a little break to go to the bathroom. The interview was resumed right after and lasted another half hour.

E6 was very open, friendly and in a good mood. The last half hour however, answers were shorter and a little time pressure to get through the questions timely was felt. Answers in general were detailed, very precise and filled with significant knowledge on environmental legislation and the industry. A wish to stay in contact was voiced at the end of the interview.

- I: *Then let us start. Well, thank you very much that this is possible today. The aim of my study is principally known. I am trying to identify trade effects of current environmental legislation for the shipping industry. I have done a literature review. At the moment I am conducting a number of expert interviews and afterwards a data collection via questionnaires is planned. Well, today I have a few questions that are a little bit... well, I have a many issues that I do not fully understand so far, thus that will give me a little bit of an insight into the economic structure of the shipping industry, what environmental legislation signifies for the industry and which variables could influence trade effects. The results will be fully anonymized. Right. #00:01:00-0#*
- E6: I am anxious to see in how far I can answer your questions in terms of NUMBERS, but we will see. #00:01:05-2#
- I: *Yes, we will see. Well, it will not that much be focused on numbers anyways. In order to afterwards evaluate the information a bit it would be interesting to know in which position you are currently working at [organization 6] and with which topics you are currently mostly occupied? #00:01:23-9#*
- E6: I am – the English version is called director, the German is effectively a “Referent”. Well, we have 1, 2, 3 hierarchical layers: chief managing director, managing director and then you have the directors of the different divisions that are dealing with the various topics. That is my position, that means I am the expert for the area and the area that I cover is officially called environmental protection and climate policy. That means, related to that mainly, one has to add that, the main issues are CO₂ emissions, atmospheric pollutant emissions, emissions in general and the related political issues. Thus the legal – slash – lobby areas and everything that is technically related to that. Thus as it is what has to be arranged technically on the vessels, reconstructed, done, implemented. In this respect it has become quite a large area and relates also the fields like sulphur, that means with the emissions of atmospheric air pollutants for example the question of fuel qualities, well, an area that is then always discussed in relation to that and the question: Wo does the fuel look? Which technical treatment systems? Centrifuges on board? And in relation to the fuel switching, how does that link to that? Well, that is the area that I am in charge of that is then fanned out a little bit in the shape of a pyramid. #00:02:49-2#
- I: *Are you doing that alone or is there...? #00:02:52-8#*
- E6: I am doing that alone. I have a colleague [colleague of E6] who is occupied with different topics that are environmentally focused as well like ballast water, ship recycling and such things. That is a huge area. We have to separate that among ourselves a little bit and then evidently under the management, the managing directors. #00:03:08-3#

- I: *What are currently the most urgent questions, those that currently define the daily routine?* #00:03:13-4#
- E6: For me? #00:03:14-4#
- I: *Yes.* #00:03:15-7#
- E6: Well, we have the change of the fuel quality which means the coming into force of the sulphur limits in the Special Areas in 2015. In Europe these Special Areas are North and Baltic Sea. Well, but there are in the mean while many, not in the mean while, there are many shipping companies that call at ports in the USA as well. USA, Canada, the same applies there, there is a Special Area for sulphur in force as well. And here we have the challenge that they either, if they want to achieve these sulphur limits, that are or will be implemented as a binding limit, but are politically clearly agreed, that they can either solve that with a cleaning system, a scrubber on board or simply with the fuel. Well, and we, the shipping industry is up to now operating on low-sulphur fuel, but in relation to the grade that is heavy fuel oil and what is now required to our knowledge is the switch to marine diesel. And that is another grade that has a different viscosity, different physical properties and that you may not so easily, say, fill into the bunker tank and just keep on operating, but there are different provisions, precautions that need to be done on board. And on board a ship and thus also for our members and thus also for the association that is one of the most urgent questions, because apart from economic issues like: What will that lead to? How will the shipping companies be able under the current circumstances to absorb the additional costs of the fuels and what does that than mean for the shipping companies themselves? Those are the questions that the association is evidently occupied with, not economically for the shipping companies themselves, but related to politics so to speak. For example: Are there any subsidies that one can somehow make use of for these topics? That is currently a huge topic. We have other themes in the area of CO₂, CO₂ emissions, climate policy. An enormously complicated field politically, down to the requirements that we have now introduced via the IMO in the area of shipping efficiency, well, that means on technical ship efficiency, the so-called Energy Efficiency Design Index, that is designated for newbuildings, to comply with certain binding values- gram CO₂ per ton mile. Those are also issues that are currently being discussed or that have been discussed and are now being introduced, where ship owners have to see with the newbuildings that are now coming to technically comply with these things. How will they be verified, how can one comply with that, is that all correct, how will the values be verified, when the shipyard is building a vessel, how can that be controlled whether the rules are adhered to? – Questions like that. Well, but that is an issue that is valid for newbuilding. The political regard is towards - and that is important for us: What can be done for the existing fleet – with regard to saving fuels – slash – with regard to reducing CO₂ emissions. Well and that is another area that is currently intensively – I am just coming back from... last week I had the IMO committee meeting in London, I am just coming from there – that is currently intensively discussed. Well, are there standards, are there specifications, political, regulative demands that one can... that one can work on in order to control the existing fleet in their CO₂ emission, in order to regulate it. #00:06:48-1#

I: *Can one assume that something will be happening in that area in the next years?*
#00:06:51-7#

E6: I would say that that will happen, well, in general I would say that it would be impossible to assume otherwise. Of that I am convinced. The question is how one will go about, well, how one can do these things, in which direction it will develop. Will that go towards a target-based approach and the path will be left open or will random limit values be dictated eventually. The discussion led by environmental organizations for example often leads to asking for direct speed limits in order to save fuel. Evidently in the face of the crisis situation one sees how shipping companies have almost entirely I would say introduced slow steaming in order to save fuel, as that forms the biggest share of the costs and thus also the biggest share of opportunities to save money in any way during daily operations. Naturally, it is the concern of environmental organizations to somehow make that permanent [zementieren] and to say: Great, let us introduce a maximum speed level of 16 knots. That is entirely amiss to the issue and the nature of the shipping industry and also to the context of the international exchange of goods. Vessels are not going fast, because they want to go fast or because the captain wants to go fast, but the shipping industry is fundamentally a residual value. The vessel speed is fundamentally a residual value that results from quite different economic factors, in the main part anyways. There are exceptions, one has to add, for example if a harbour is not able to meet the demand and a great long line of vessels is forming in front of the harbour. Then you do not want to be the last in the cue and then some shipping companies are forced to step on the gas a bit in order to shorten the wait time before goods may be handled. Well, but those are individual cases and that is real life and there you have to... well, something is going to happen. #00:08:47-2#

I: *From your point of view: What would be a good way to regulate CO₂?* #00:08:52-0#

E6: Well, we have, [organization 6] has, I myself have said already since 2009: CO₂ regulation is inevitable and we actively want to contribute to that and we have presented a proposal already at the time. The question is always: How does one best introduce such a thing? Ideally via the IMO, that means for all vessels. Because it is at its basis a global business and everything that is done regionally, be it in the United States, be it a New York legislation, be it in California or be it a European rule, whenever you have something like that it is an extreme burden for the crew on board and also for the shipping company on land, because they have to check time and again: Where can we... where do we enter an area with different rules than we have here in Europe. Well, then you have god thousands of manuals on the ship's bridge. That is a nightmare. That is why we are preferably looking towards an IMO regulation of any kind that will then be globally applicable to everyone.

That is the one thing. The other thing is, if you do that, it somehow has to be a system that is simple, that is comprehensible, that is targeted, but that is as simple and practical as possible, because that first of all increases the implementation frequency, or let me say the implementation willingness and secondly also the political acceptance. Because no country, also the developing countries, that do not want such instruments anyways...

what is currently happening with regards to climate policy - take a look at the UN climate conference and so forth, the Kyoto follow-up-agreement - what in any way proves to be extremely complex and complicated, if that is not being accepted you can forget it. Then we will not get there [to CO₂ legislation for shipping]. Well, and that is why we said at the time, well, the shipping companies are most likely to react if the fuel gets more expensive; we experience that right now. Thus it would be, we have said, somehow sensible to introduce a kind of CO₂ fee on fuel. One somehow pays a certain amount per ton of fuel and you study if that has any effect and you naturally have to ascertain that over a monitoring period of, I don't know, three years, if that is leading to anything. Well, but that has been a complicated process at the time, because everybody has said: Well, collecting money from the shipping industry and so on if that is working... it is rather difficult, also politically difficult to be accepted and has so far not led to a great consensus. There were other proposals from other European countries as well, also from the Federal government that said we want to introduce an emissions trading system. An emissions trading system is very complex and therefore – and it says we want to determine a certain maximum amount and there will be no going above that and then there will only be a little bit of trading and all of these are very complex systems – therefore they are being discussed, but it will be a while, I think, before they will be politically accepted as well and that is the prerequisite if they should be implemented at all. But I think that one has to make sure first of all to keep the international trade running and I do not think that we will go back to a regional economy. The international division of labour and the exchange of goods, I believe that that will continue like this, that is supposed to be growing and I believe that the cost advantages of producing here and there and the international trade that is always a win win situation. Well, and that is why there is a lot of work being done at the moment. Now, last week for example, at the IMO we spoke about how to prepare efficiency systems, by saying now, first of all, let us do the first step and say we will introduce a monitoring system and will collect data, real data from vessels, how much fuel they are burning each year. There were attempts by some to collect other data as well from all vessels, for example distance sailed, nautical miles, and what they were transporting each time, the cargo. There you are getting towards the sensitive area of confidential commercial data thus that has all been rejected. Well, but that is an area where all IMO member states have a great interest to really obtain clear facts. Well, currently it is like this: bunker consumption slash CO₂ emissions of the shipping industry are estimated by way of certain models, that are already quite far developed, but still it is being estimated. Thus you have no real data, meaning that you have no true number base and it is difficult to rest a political regulation on that. Therefore one introduced the monitoring principle. I find that quite right. Also the shipping community is okay with that, the international community as well – they say: We have fuel burnt, we can report that. Everything else that goes into the area of what exactly we are transporting, how many containers, how heavy are they and so forth that is a little bit critical, there we have to see. #00:13:41-2#

I: *Who will be collecting this data?* #00:13:44-4#

- E6: Yes, that a question currently under discussion. Well, first of all one has to see: What kind of data do they want? Who can supply that? – Well, the shipping companies. And where shall they be sent to? Ideally it will be the IMO, we are naturally always looking towards the IMO, one can add that there is currently a similar system being discussed at the Brussels level, but we are looking a little bit towards the IMO. There it only makes sense if the flag state is collecting the data in each case that is coming from the own vessels. #00:14:14-6#
- I: *Are all flag states in a position to do that?* #00:14:18-4#
- E6: Yes, well, that is a difficult topic. Well, that depends a little bit on how one designs the system. But naturally some flag states have a huge fleet that they attend to and that is accordingly more work, if you have Panama, Liberia, Cyprus, I don't know how many vessels, 2,000 or something like that, I don't know how many vessels that are, but they have fewer vessels, they evidently have a little less work. Thus they would have to be able to do that, but it is somehow a question, because that is an enormous data collection and data acquisition task. And there you have to be very precise in how to structure that so that the bureaucratic complexity remains somehow manageable. That is an issue that we also focus on quite closely, because what the flag state is doing has to be verified somehow beforehand. That means an enormous effort with the shipping companies already and then with the vessels and with the day books and log books that they have on board and that is... you have to monitor that very closely, because it is often underestimates. The data is available at the vessels and at the shipping companies if they look into the engine log book and the log book. But that is not it. When you introduce a law you have to say: What they are now reporting to the German flag or the Liberian or any other that has to be true. That means some external person has to check that beforehand and has to say: Yes, that is in line with the books and everything. There is a lot behind that and one has to see how to divide that burden between the flag state and the shipper. #00:16:06-6#
- I: *Okay, that was a short excursion. (Laughing) Because, well that is... very good. I still have a few questions regarding your background.* #00:16:17-1#
- E6: Let's go. #00:16:18-2#
- I: *Since when do you work, do you move in this whole thematic area?* #00:16:24-5#
- E6: With [organization 6] or in this thematic area? #00:16:26-8#
- I: *With [organization 6] and in this thematic area.* #00:16:28-6#
- E6: Well, I'm working in this area already for some time. In [specific month and year] I came to [organization 6] and I have since been occupied with this topic as well, because there was an opportunity at the time at [organization 6] to do something in that area. At that time, precisely in 2008, all of that was much more intensively discussed on a different level. In the thematic area I already... well, I have been working on that already in my previous employment, regarding air traffic, sea traffic, environmental policy, CO₂

- emissions, efficiencies and so forth. Well, I am not entirely new to the area. But I am – I studied economics, thus I am no marine engineer, no biologist or any other kind of environmental scientist. #00:17:07-2#
- I: *Interesting. (Laughing) I find it very interesting to see with what kind of topics one deals with during his career. #00:17:12-2#*
- E6: Yes, but I also own a craft certificate in automobile technology, thus I am half a technician and it gives me a lot of joy, especially to see that in retroaction. I have just been on the phone with one of our members who tells us: We now have to see with respect to the sulphur introduction on 1 January 2015, how we have to reconstruct our tank systems on board in order to comply with this 0.1 gasoil so that it will not mix with the heavy fuel oil that we are using as well, as we are operating worldwide. Currently that is an issue on board the vessels that that does not somehow intermix in the settling tank. That means they have to reconstruct on board. Those things are very interesting. Not good for the shipping companies, but in any way interesting. #00:17:54-7#
- I: *Have you ever been working directly for the shipping industry? #00:17:57-8#*
- E6: No. #00:17:58-8#
- I: *No, okay. The... well, no that is fine.*
- How many shipping companies are currently a member of [organization 6], how many are you more or less representing? #00:18:18-4#*
- E6: Uh... good question. I cannot tell you precisely. I would think that we have had around 250 and I think that now we have around 200 members. But there you would have to... I cannot really tell you exactly. My colleagues in management, they would know that. #00:18:35-3#
- I: *Right. Are there currently changes in the number or the composition of German shipping companies? #00:18:43-6#*
- E6: Yes, yes. Yes, yes, evidently. Those are... #00:18:46-8#
- I: *What kind of development do you see there? #00:18:49-6#*
- E6: Well, we are in the sixth year of the shipping crisis. That has its effects. There are many shipping companies, several shipping companies, that merged, that were combined to one. That is changing the amount of your members. There are shipping companies that left in order to save costs under the pressure of the market. #00:19:06-8#
- I: *Thus they do not have to be members - that is purely... #00:19:08-8#*
- E6: No, no, no, no, [organization 6] is an association with entirely voluntary membership. That is different from the Chambers of Industry and Commerce for example or something like that. That is why we largely have to work efficiently as an association and somehow have to prove the added value to the shipping companies. No, no, that is

like that everywhere with the associations. If the pressure on costs is increasing, the naturally first of all look where they can save money and we can feel that here as well, as far as I am informed. Those questions are a little bit more related to the management of the association itself. I am just on the side occupied with administration, as I am very well occupied with these topics. Well, those are my preliminary statements, there you have to see if that also... (laughing) #00:19:50-9#

I: *Right. (laughing) How important is trade shipping compared to other areas, let us say passenger transport or others? Does that constitute the larger part? #00:20:00-0#*

E6: For us? #00:20:01-1#

I: *Yes. #00:20:01-2#*

E6: Yes, yes. We have trade shipping... We are so to say [organization 6], thus the German shipping companies that are organized with us are basically those that control, provide for and operate the world biggest, well, the biggest share of the world container fleet. Well, we have a large share of the tramp shipping companies that means owners that offer vessels, vessels that they own, on the market that are then being chartered out. There are many vessels chartered out. There are some shipping companies, evidently also the big ones like Hapag, Hamburg Süd, DAL and so on, that evidently also operate themselves. But we have relatively few, well, but there are only few, passenger and cruise ship operators. There are a few small ones with us as well - Wiker Dampfschiffsreederei – that service the small islands. I think for them an association is extremely important, because they are just too small in order to manage the whole lobbying work, which is quite a huge amount. We have AIDA with us. But the cruise ships, passenger vessels are one part; trade shipping is dominating – by far. #00:21:13-7#

I: *How many of the members have their main seat of operations in Germany? All of them? #00:21:20-0#*

E6: I cannot tell you. I cannot tell you. Most of them? I would think most of them. Main seat of operations is always difficult, because I mean, with AIDA, they are located in Rostock, but they belong to the Carnival Group and the brand is located in Rostock, but is sailing the Italian flag. I have no idea where the main seat of operations is. Rostock? Well, I think mainly it is here. Well, Hamburg and Leer and Haren an der Ems, those are the big seats of operation, that is somehow true... #00:21:51-6#

I: *Which are the main flags that the vessels are sailing under? #00:21:58-2#*

E6: We have... well: German flag, whereby the share is rather small with a decreasing tendency in the light of the costs. We have... the German shipping companies are mostly sailing the Liberia flag. A large share is Antigua and Barbuda flag, I believe. And then smaller ones. Currently the share of European flags is increasing. Like Malta, Cyprus, some are even going for the UK flag, but I think that has to do with... I am not really an expert there. But the European share is increasing. Well I believe historically the

Liberian flag is the dominating one, if I am correctly informed. Whereby I always need to say right away, not to give way to any misconceptions, the ship and flag register of Liberia has in fact nothing to do with the country. Rather, it belongs to one of the best and most efficient registers that exist worldwide, with regard to the environment and with regard to the treatment of the seamen as well, so that is... #00:23:05-8#

I: *What – in relation to legal environmental topics – what does [organization 6] offer to the shipping companies? Is that mostly advice, is that mostly political representation or what is exactly... #00:23:18-0#*

E6: Exactly. Well, at the basis, at the basis, when you look at the big picture, those are the core issues. Firstly [organization 6] is an interpace between politics and the companies. That means we are transporting interests in the direction of politics and what is done there in order to practice any interest or consensus building and in order to formulate positions that may then somehow influence the direction of law-making at European and global level and national level that is lobbying. Normally, so to say, when some kind of regulation in the direction of sulphur, NO_x, emissions, CO₂, is somehow politically thought about, because the initiative is always coming from the ministries, German or European or from other states, then one has to look at that very closely and say: Does that fit? Does that work? How does that function in the market? What consequences does that have for the shipping companies? And what we have learned with regards to sulphur for example is the question: A political decision is being taken – 0.1 in 2015 – and do all shipping companies and shipping operators, vessel types, vessels sizes, have the chance to really actually comply with regulations without taking the risk that they will not be able to keep their seat of operations or their economic rentability. And in relation to the sulphur questions that was really a huge issue. The small short sea people, the ferries, that operate 100 per cent on the Baltic Sea, SO_x-ECA, they are facing different problems than a huge container shipping company. Well, those are things that one has to address and that is our task. And evidently also the other way round – what may the association do? And that is mainly really advising what has politically been decided, what is written down in the EU regulations, in the directives and then originating from the directives and going into the executive and implementing orders. That is evidently already... that is highly complex and does not form part of the business of shipping companies. That means, with such things... when you send them the documents, they can hardly make any sense of them. I mean we know that from our daily business. You have to be quite familiar with these things and that means we always try to translate that and to advise the shipping companies what they HAVE to do. That is more or less our task. #00:25:42-5#

I: *How well are shipping companies generally informed? #00:25:48-5#*

E6: That also varies significantly. It varies significantly as it first of all depends on the size of the shipping company. Big ones, I would say, I mean, I am now thinking – away from our German area, a large shipping company like Maersk for example, that is really a giant group, they have departments that are dealing with political regulations. They have man power to do that. If you go to a small shipping company in the Altes Land [region

near Hamburg], they have to see how to keep their vessels moving, to procure cargo. They do not have that. That is our task and we do that. There are different pieces of monthly information; we have our commissions, the usual, the structure of an association in order to convey that. But naturally they also have their flag state that they can ask. Well, if a vessel has the German flag flying behind they can call at the See-BG and say: How does that work exactly with regulation ABC? And they naturally also have, because that is required, the technical inspections by the classification societies, well, the technical experts there may also say: The fuel filter xy with the number ABC does not work any more and needs to be changed until 01.01.2015. Such things. #00:27:06-9#

I: *And does that happen that they are also advising... ?* #00:27:09-7#

E6: That happens as well, yes. Whereby it is different fields that are being covered. The flag state may say: Yes, here under the flag law of my state – Germany, Liberia or whatever – this is allowed and this not. And with the classification societies it would naturally primarily be technical questions, what will be possible with fuel pipe ABC, which diameter, which temperature may that tolerate, things like that. With us it is rather a little bit... we certainly also have a lot of technical know-how in the house with the colleagues here, but it is rather: What is happening now? From when on am I allowed to do what and where? Well, and which law is that and where is that written down? And that is our task. #00:27:57-1#

I: *If more and more shipping companies are now leaving [organization 6] – I they then less well informed?* #00:28:04-2#

E6: Well, in any case I would say. Because that is evidently the task of an association and naturally all the political – that is not only related to the environment, that are also flag state and other regulations, questions of insurance,... that are collected here and they are nowhere available as concentrated and cumulated. That is evidently already... well, me being an employee of an association, that is not surprising, but I would naturally say, I would advise everybody against leaving the association, because you are losing a lot of information, also cross information and fast tracks and so on. Just, I think that everybody knows that, but sometimes the economical pressure leaves no other option. That is just like that. #00:28.53-0#

I: *Is it rather easy or difficult to receive and comprehend information from all these different actors?* #00:29:02-4#

E6: For us or for the shipping companies? #00:29:04-4#

I: *For a shipping company.* #00:29:09-7#

E6: Is it easy or difficult? You would have to ask a shipping company. Well, I believe one has to... I think it is ESSENTIAL to know the people. But that is normally always the case, well, in the classification societies and with the flag state and so on, that is the case. Sometimes, sometimes there are... you may have very specific questions, where

the answer is not immediately available, there you have to look out a bit who might be able to help you. But, yes, regarding... naturally there is some effort behind that, but all in all I believe that a shipping company may... may be able to get the information.
#00:29:47-8#

I: *Okay. You said that it depended also a little bit on the size, well, that the smaller ones had bigger difficulties... #00:29:58-6#*

E6: Well, let us say it like that: The added value of an association is naturally the bigger for the people the smaller their organization is. And with the large groups like Hapag Lloyd or others, they naturally already know better just based on their own know-how.
#00:30:16-1#

I: *Are there differences with respect to the level of information available depending if I take a look at the container industry or rather the bulk industry or tanker – are they differently well informed? #00:30:34-9#*

E6: Well, regarding they way in which they are informed, thus the quality or the quantity, they are not differently well informed. Well, that always depends a little bit on: What is the issue? What is being negotiated? And what relevance does that have? For example... we have one good example: MARPOL Annex V, well that is kind of waste management, well, waste. That is related to, for example in relation to the bulk vessels, if they wash their tanks there are always this cargo residues in there, ores and so on. Such things are being regulated. You may wash that, but what to do with the washing water? Those are questions that we are intensively discussing. They are also relevant for the environment, because the question is: Do you just dump that in the harbour or dump that in front of the coast or do you have to dispose of that? Is that somehow a dangerous substance or is it residues of grain and therefore it is totally irrelevant. These rules are not of any interest for the container industry however. Thus it is rather depending a little bit on the topic in question. #00:31:41-3#

I: *I have tried... #00:31:43-4#*

E6: I will have some coffee; do you want one as well? #00:31:44-4#

I: *Yes, thank you, I will have one as well. #00:32:17-9#*

(Coffee is being served.)

E6: Well, but apart from that the information coverage is naturally equal everywhere. That would not be possible any other way and you achieve that with such regular newsletters and so on, all that is being done, always at short intervals. That is being done... I believe, there is not type of vessel... #00:32:39-3#

I: *I the legislator itself also involved in the process or is he normally not informing? #00:32:43-0#*

E6: Yes, yes, very extensively in the usual... the usual information that is made available. There are certain professional journals – Verkehrsblatt – where all of these new

regulations are being published. In the legal papers, the Official Journal of the European Union, the Federal Law Gazette and so on. That you can, there you have... well, no shipping company is looking into the Federal Law Gazette to see: What's new? Unless they have somehow a legal department, like it is done in the huge groups. And that is then our task. And we have to say: Here, that is now constituted, that has been published, that is written in the Official Journal, from now on that is valid and you have to consider this and that. Those are the things that we are then usually doing. #00:33:23-6#

I: *I have tried, from the literature, to filter all the different areas which at the moment, or in the future, however... #00:33:36-1#*

E6: I have already gotten that. Did I not? I do not have that, but I have the little picture. #00:33:42-8#

I: *You already got that? Well... ...in which new regulations are being passed and maybe will be passed. The question is: Which of these are practically relevant? Thus, where happens... in which... well, the areas are dumping of waste, ballast water, air pollution, toxic anti-fouling systems, noise, oily water and finally sewage waters. #00:34:09-9#*

E6: Dumping of ship waste is... well, we have... that is MARPOL V. With our shipping companies here there is no dumping of waste. All of it is kept on board and is being disposed of. I have now seen vessels where everything is burned on board, if it may be burnt or it will be collected and disposed of. In the meantime the waste is being separated on board. In colourful containers. #00:34:39-0#

I: *That means there is really no-one speaking about that any more. #00:34:40-4#*

E6: Yes. Well, it depends on... that is now the German fl... well, the German shipping companies, I cannot speak for the international fleet. There are certainly somehow... then you see someone like that... but for us it is no longer a topic. Ballast water – HUGE issue, huge issue, the ballast water convention is not yet in force, but shortly will be based on the ratification criteria. There exist a large number of ballast water treatment systems. There are however huge problems with them, because of the requirements regarding the ballast water treatment... it works according to the existing test criteria, if you simulate a certain water temperature and a certain salinity, but as soon as the vessel is sailing somewhere else – with hundreds of other temperatures and salinities in the water – the systems do not function properly any more, they are thus not reliable. They are VERY expensive and we are currently getting... the ballast water discussion in the IMO Committee on the Environment is huge. That means there is really still a lot to be done. #00:35:55-6#

I: *And what will now happen next? #00:35:59-2#*

E6: We will first of all wait. Well, as a matter of fact the test criteria for the ballast water treatment systems will be evaluated once again. There are some shipping companies that have already installed ballast water treatment systems on their vessels. There is supposed to be a rule that they will not be penalized, if their ballast water treatment

systems are somehow showing at the inspection of the water that there are still a few organisms in there that should not be in there. A kind of impunity. Normally that is called grandfathering, but they did not want to hear that at the IMO. There will be some kind of non-penalization clause or something like that. But the problem is, an enormous number of ballast water treatment systems would have to be installed as soon as the convention enters into force. And currently it is not like the operators are saying: Perfect, I will buy the system xyz, but rather everyone is a little bit: Well, if I sail somewhere else it might not work.” An immense investment uncertainty. And there are millions of costs associated with that. Especially regarding the capacity of ballast water treatment systems. You can imagine that container vessels, they can make plans for the vessel to stay straight in the water, they do not need that much ballast water. With bulk vessels that is an entirely different question. If they transport ores to China and are empty they have to take in really very much ballast water. That means that those are large amounts and the treatment systems, as far as I know, I am not an expert in this area, but as far as I know, are not very reliably functioning for this application. Thus it is a huge topic. #00:37:32-4#

I: *Thus at the moment everybody is waiting? #00:37:35-8#*

E6: At the moment some have... but the majority is waiting. Regarding hull coatings as well, because that is linked to this area, ballast water, introduction of species that are clinging to the hull. #00:37:49-9#

I: *Is that at the moment still... or are there any costs associated with that or does one generally know what to do regarding anti-fouling systems? #00:38:04-1#*

E6: That is... the question here is... but I am also not to a hundred per cent expert on that, but the question in this respect is always, if you have fouling on the vessel that is always bad, because you need significantly more fuel as the resistance in the water is bigger. That means that no-one has an interest in that. You thus need respective hull coatings, those are very expensive. The toxic ones we had earlier, TBT and so forth, do not exist any more. But the questions here is, and there the shipping companies are looking very closely, in which condition the hull is. There are divers as well that you can employ that will have a look at that. To clean a hull, at some time inbetween, that is done, but the harbours do not like to see that neither, because if I am lying somewhere in Singapore and I say: I need to have some divers clean my hull and they do that in the harbour basin, then... #00:39:01-3#

I: *Oh, then the whole stuff is in the harbour basin. #00:39:04-7#*

E6: Well, there are also some rules that are now coming up, that is certainly also related to the costs. I am not able to estimate, if that... even in this area of air pollution, air pollution and climate policy, because there it is much more. Here it is all of it very much more. That is a topic that is currently known, that is closely monitored, but not so dramatic at the moment. Noise pollution is something that is not yet there, but something that is on the agenda of the IMO and will certainly become an issue in the next years, when these ones have come to some kind of conclusion. [Pointing at diagram] Spills of

oily water, I am not aware, that it somehow anymore... well, this whole bilge water and everything that you have, all that is, as far as I know, collected in tanks by our shipping companies and disposed of in the harbour, because they have to document that, they have to fill that out, the port states may look that up in their books: You normally would need to have around three cubic metres or so on board, where is that? And if they do not have that, well, then there exist severe penalties. #00:40:18-0#

I: *Well, I think that there were still some 270 or so oil spills detected on the Baltic Sea last year. Someone must still do that.* #00:40:30-6#

E6: Yes, well, it is not like the ISSUE does not exist any more. I can only speak of [organization 6] and its members. But as far as we know that is no-one from our membership. Well, and sewage water, that in an own MARPOL subject, MARPOL Annex IV, that is mainly an issue in the area of cruising, cruise shipping, because they have entirely different amounts of waste water that somehow need to be disposed. Among or members, AIDA for example or others, they have treatment systems on board, that means what is still emitted into the water, pumped outside, that is cleaned water. I cannot tell you about the constituent parts of that... but those are treatment systems. That also has to do with the fact that evidently a cruise shipping company is extremely dependant on how clean they organize their management and the vessel and the operation of the vessel and the holiday time of their guests and that is why they are somehow always in a leading role. We have the problem that many are expecting that such waste waters may also be drained in the harbours, that such port reception facilities are existing, but that is nowhere the case. There are very few that are able to take up such amounts. That means that a cruise ship has to spill that somewhere. Well, that means that they can treat it on board, but then they have to pump that out, the cleaned water. Well, but there is always somehow a suspicious factor involved in that somehow. So that the member states are saying: No, you better dispose of that in the harbour. But that then also has to be possible, it then also has to be viable with the sewage treatment plant that they have on land and not just qualitative, but also regarding the amounts and that today is still not the case. There exist also MARPOL IV special area designations, well that means that one can designate special areas where in principle no water, be it treated or not treated, may be pumped over board. The Baltic Sea is designated as such an area under the condition that there exist port reception facilities. #00:42:46-7#

I: *And do they exist?* #00:42:47-8#

E6: They do not, no. #00:42:48-9#

I: *And now?* #00:42:49-1#

E6: That is why that has not yet entered into force and the Baltic Sea is not a special area under MARPOL IV, because like that it cannot be designated. Logically you cannot prohibit the cruise vessels to get rid of their water and in the harbours they say: But not here and so on. What is one supposed to do now? Well, there has to be a solution. It is not possible to just prohibit something and to say: But we do not offer you an alternative.

- And that is that. If you are not allowed to pump the water over board, then at least in the harbour. But then that has to be possible there. And that is not the case. #00:43:22-2#
- I: *Well, but that means if these rules are not in force, then at least in terms of costs they should not be of any interest to anyone at the moment, right?* #00:43:32-2#
- E6: Well, if you have a decision to designate a certain maritime area as a special area than that decision is indisputable for that area. Then the case is decided, linked to the condition that all adjacent states have to act upon that. And then a cruise ship company – no matter which one – has to say, if we go to Turku in Finland we know there we have, we can drain 300 tons... No problem. #00:44:02-2#
- I: *And then they have to do that?* #00:44:03-7#
- E6: And then they have to do that. And they will then do that. But that is simply not the case. That is that. #00:44:14-3#
- I: *Well, if you look at these seven areas – which of them are well regulated, which of them are under- or maybe over-regulated?* #00:44:29-5#
- E6: Yes, good question. This topic... #00:44:37-7#
- I: *Ballast water...* #00:44:37-5#
- E6: ...is regulated. Implementation and practical consequences still remain unclear. This topic is... [pointing at the graph] well, there is surely still... I shy away from using the word “under-regulated”, because that would mean we urgently need more [legislation] in that area. Something is going to happen here. We are very much engaged in the question how to produce something reasonable in this area. And here [pointing at air pollution] there will certainly be something coming up. I do not want to say that it is under-regulated. There will certainly more be done, but... #00:45:15-2#
- I: *That is only related to CO₂ emissions... right?* #00:45:22-8#
- E6: No, that is related to everything. Well, there will be... CO₂ will still be coming. With regards to the sulphur regulation, we have... the sulphur regulation is technically complete, but now there is one coming into force in '15 with the ECA, in '20 in the European waters with the switch to diesel and '20 maybe also worldwide. Unless the IMO discovers that there is still not enough [diesel available] and is moving the date to '25. But there are currently different stages that are coming into force. And then we will see how the effects are. But that is only sulphur. We are also talking about nitrogen oxides, we are anyways talking about CO₂, we are also with the switch to diesel talking about particle emissions as part of the sulphur regulation. There is also particle regulation associated with that, because if you are switching to diesel it goes into the area of fine particulates, the PM 2.5 to 10 or so. There will be something coming with certainty. That will also... And there alone you have subsequent business and technical processes related to that that are extremely difficult to handle for every shipping company. You just have to spell it. #00:46:28-1#

- I: *Is sulphur the largest, the most expensive step if we look at these four categories of air emissions or will CO₂ become even more difficult and still more expensive?* #00:46:42-1#
- E6: Currently it is like this... Sulphur is a big deal, because, as I said, if you go away from the sulphur to diesel fuel the cost difference between these two qualities alone is enormous. That is a difference of more or less 50 per cent. With respect to CO₂ that is difficult to express in numbers, because first of all as of now we do not know that, because in that area everything is still... and because secondly you cannot say, well, this fuel here costs 300 and that one 600, but a CO₂ or energy efficiency regulation in some way always interferes with the business model. And the question will then still be, incidentally a question that we have for the sulphur as well when the fuel is getting more expensive, will we still sail there or will we not sail there any longer? Do we want to keep these services running or do we alternatively sail to another harbour where they do not have these regulations – issues like that. Well, we have the interference with the management systems and also the flows of the cargo that will somehow change with certainty. That is that. And the question is, if there is a bureaucratic system Europe and all vessels that are currently going to Europe are subjecting themselves to that, okay. But will they do that? Well, the Chinese shipping companies, the COSCO and so forth, whether they will then say: No, we will then just sail until, I don't know, Greece and throw everything off board, turn around and sail back and they then do not want to go to Rotterdam or Hamburg or to Poland in the Baltic Sea any more... such things. #00:48:16-0#
- I: *Are those short term effects, because in 2025 the latest the same rules will apply to everyone again?* #00:48:24-1#
- E6: Yes, that is right, but that is first of all... well, whatever that means in the short term, 10 years or so, one can already... That is like that, but the issue that we have in front of us is basically nothing else but an alteration of the fuel provisioning of the shipping industry. That means that the refineries have to adjust to that and that only goes step by step. The amounts will be adjusted. We have new fuels like liquefied gas - LNG - that will somehow take up a share as a shipping fuel. That means we have a kind of change, kind of like a game changer in the whole fuel history and in the whole fuel structure in general and not only here now, but worldwide. That means that effects... there will be a number of changes. That again has an impact on shipping investments. Ship owners are asking us now: Well, what about the fuel after 2020? We are planning a newbuilding, with which motors shall we furnish that, so that we may burn all fuels... and somehow keep all options open? That means there are many already today that are saying: Yes, we don't exactly know, we hope that LNG will be as far developed as a shipping fuel and also cheap and available worldwide. We will just buy dual fuel motors that are able to burn both heavy fuel oil and LNG. They are expensive. Well, you have to account for that in your investment analysis. Thus that has repercussions already today. How that may effect the entire sector worldwide... #00:49:58-0#

- I: *If the large reconstruction due to the sulphur regulation is now coming, will there be another large reconstruction due to NO_x emission constraints or is that really already... has the big step already been done? #00:50:11-2#*
- E6: Sulphur will have significant influence and the CO₂ regulation that will take a certain form will have an influence. NO_x emission regulation is rather a technical problem. Difficult, by all means, especially when we are talking about retrofits. Well, you then have to install a... and there you also have to differentiate, taking one step back, between special areas like with the sulphur and the normal, thus everything that operates worldwide. New motors have NO_x Tier 2 limits - that's how it is called. That is feasible in terms of motor technology; one may cope with that in the special areas. The Americans have that now. That is also a NO_x-ECA. Starting from 2016 new vessels have to comply with the stricter Tier 3 limits. That is again going about 75.8% further down in terms of NO_x reduction. That cannot be achieved so easily any more. That means you have to fit a catalyst. With the newbuilding that is not a problem as such as you may plan that in advance – then simply the motor and a kat behind. There you know what you may expect. But we fear a little bit, let me say... at the horizon we see a little bit the idea of politics to also reduce the NO_x emissions of the existing fleet. And that is touching upon the area of retrofits, well, upgrading. That is with everything that you have inside such a motor, with the turbochargers, with the whole supply system, with the exhaust gas currents, that is not that trivial to install. That is going to be complicated. That is then also relevant in terms of costs again. But that is something... let us see if it get's that far, because the NO_x emissions of the vessels are, seen in absolute terms, not that... we do not have the numbers here, but they are not that high. Especially when they are slow steaming, when the motors are not in high performance... NO_x is always something – when the motors are in high performance you have high NO_x emissions and when they are slow steaming you have lower NO_x emissions. It simply depends on the engine load. Thus the question is always if that is necessary at all. But we have the political aspiration that everybody has to contribute to NO_x reduction. The impact of that, I would say, is not so much an issue. #00:52:40-3#
- I: *CO₂ reduction is really in the end an issue of business-economics or will there again be may technical changes? #00:52:52-0#*
- E6: No, it is an issue of business-economics. CO₂ is always dependant with the factor three point something on fuel consumption. That means the shipping companies have to see how to make the vessels more efficient, how to reduce fuel consumption or how they may somehow accomplish that. But they cannot install a CO₂ filter. That is not possible. At least not right now. That may still be developed. #00:53:18-1#
- I: *Who knows what will still be developed. #00:53:19-0#*
- E6: Yes, exactly. I mean, CCS systems, well, carbon dioxide capture and storage, now exist as well. Who knows towards what that may develop? Yes, and there are also political systems where one somehow looks for a compensation elsewhere. Realizes saving outside the sector and then imports them into the sector – emission trading systems, such

things. Concepts are on the table. Well, it really doesn't make any sense to ignore that. It is simply there. We will have to see. #00:53:46-1#

I: *How is the shipping industry currently adapting to these new developments?* #00:53:54-2#

E6: Yes, relating to environmental legislation it is always important for us to inform early on. In relation to CO₂ we are, we have to be, as an association, you are well advised to say: We will join a few experts in a working group and see what happens, what the issues are and in what kind of direction that develops and we have done that for CO₂ since I'm here. We are discussing sulphur with all of its facets very intensively at the moment with our expert panels here as well, because that is related to technical alterations on board. That means they all look very attentively what will be necessary and what won't. Well, some more and other will say: Well, I will have to talk to my bank first to see if I may get a loan and otherwise I cannot be bothered by anything like that. That also happens. #00:54:37-3#

I: *Which measures is the shipping industry taking? Well, when we are looking for example at the 1 January 2015, what is done, very specifically?* 00:54:47-1#

E6: Well, we have those that mainly sail in the North and Baltic Sea, short sea, who have to see that they comply with the limits and there are the very few that have installed a scrubber. Also those that will still install a scrubber, well, where that will still be coming in order further use heavy fuel oil. The predominant mass, the majority, will simply operate on gasoil with the sulphur content. But as I said they are currently preparing the technical systems for that, because with regards to the viscosity you have a heavy fuel oil that is tough and light diesel oil. That goes through the fuel pumps and so on. A pump that is designed to push a tough substance through the pipes, if you then tuck in such a light liquid stuff the whole technical pumps will break into pieces. There are really some precautions that need to be taken on board. And that is what they are currently doing. Well, that is a specific technical preparation for that. Everything else related to that... It will become interesting – again looking at it the other way – it will be interesting when such things, the... when diesel oil with 0.1 sulphur content has to be burnt in the main machines worldwide, that is when the amount that is being burnt... then the cost burden will also be higher and then the question is: What will shipping companies do then? Will they carry the costs? Is that even possible? Will they all go bankrupt? Will there be any avoidance reactions? That is evidently something that we do not know just now. #00:56:27-1#

I: *May one expect that those that are currently switching to diesel oil, that they are going into a waiting loop or will they stay with diesel oil?* #00:56:38-1#

E6: That is also a little bit looking into the crystal ball, but diesel oil is first of all a relatively easy way to be compliant with the applicable law. If they stay with that... Well, the other way round: You always have every option later on, when the scrubber technology is somehow further developed or when it becomes possible to engage such a scrubber with higher machine performance then there would be no argument against using such

investments on larger vessels. Currently the technology works to some extent for the motors of small feeder and ferry shipping companies, even if it is very energy intensive, but not for the large container vessels. These systems are not yet designed for that, not yet developed and you also have... you don't need such a scrubber when you are going to China. Eventually you just need it here on the English Channel, North Sea, Baltic Sea, that's it. And thus logically they will not make the effort. #00:57:35-1#

I: *Are there significant technical developments currently? In this scrubber technology?* #00:57:41-1#

E6: Well, I'm not so much an expert for that, but since 2010 the topic is... we are intensively discussing that. We are always hearing of some things that went wrong that will be improved. I have no doubt that they will get better, these systems and there is also, I believe, some hope from all actors that one can go on using heavy fuel oil and still comply with the laws. #00:58:09-0#

I: *I have just heard something about heavy fuel oil with very low sulphur content.* #00:58:16-1#

E6: Exactly. That is the next development that we see, that we hear something about here and there. In fact Exxon has gone public with such a product now, press conference and so forth. That one says: We do not have to switch somehow to diesel now, but we have a fuel quality that still has heavy fuel properties. That means: Colour black, viscosity high, but sulphur content low. #00:58:41-1#

I: *How is the price of that? Is that sold at the price of heavy fuel oil?* #00:58:46-3#

E6: No, I do not think so. But it was a little bit, a few dollars, cheaper than gasoil. I believe 50 dollars a ton or something a little bit below. But not in the area of heavy fuel oil, no. And we also have no-one... we have heard about that, I have obtained the data then, but we have not yet been able to speak with the people of the company Exxon, I believe. #00:59:09-1#

I: *There is also no-one who has tested that?* #00:59:11-1#

E6: There is no-one who has yet tested that. It is being offered and I have heard from shipping companies that wanted to bunker in Rotterdam and that were being told: Yes, yes, you could bunker that, but they were also still very hesitant, because if that is not working and you have a mechanical breakdown, you don't want that under any circumstances. Thus, that is a product. But the message for us is: Fuels and fuel alternatives are being developed further. Suddenly such a thing comes onto the market that so far was not expectable. Thus that will again have certain effects, not now in 2015, but maybe in '16, '17, '18. We will see: Will something come up? Will that prevail? Will it be an alternative in terms of price or will they rather say: We will rather operate on gas oil, we pay around 50 more per ton. Thus we first of all have to see how one may establish that. #00:59:59-0#

- I: If you now look at the whole width of environmental legislation – are there differences between the different shipping companies? Are there companies for whom it is easier to sail environmentally friendly than others or who rather tend to do that? #01:00:21-1#
- E6: Well, a shipping company... well, there you have to differentiate for example between a cruise shipping company and a trade shipping company. The cruise ship owners that are very much in the public eye, that furthermore want to get the people on board, they are per se always more inclined to do a little more than is legally prescribed. But at the end of the day – and that is now applicable to both the trading vessels as well as the cruise ship industry – the companies are acting in a market environment, they have to sell their product and what they have left in terms of finances they may well invest, if they have something left, in whatever special... right, that is possible. But first of all - and that is then sustainable economic activity in my point of view – the aim is to keep the shipping company alive. And everybody is aiming at that. And in that respect I would say it is logically a demand first of all to comply with the law somehow. Now one can say that a large shipping company might now operate on gas oil even if heavy fuel oil is still allowed until the end of the year in order to achieve some kind of image benefit. If a shipping company decides to do that and they are able to finance that, they will do that. But currently the market conditions do not allow for that. That means they would just loose, they would just burn money and they would then be off the market and that really is not very sustainable. #01:01:58-0#
- I: *May one, is it possible, may one really achieve a financially significant image advantage through environmentally friendly operations in the trade shipping industry? Is anyone interested in that? #01:02:10-1#*
- E6: Well, what we hear is... what we hear, I have to say, that is a little bit reflection from our members, but I do not know if that is representative or not, but what we hear only goes into one direction and that says: We can do that, we can build an environmentally friendly vessel, but from the one that will charter the vessel we will only receive the standard market charter, not one cent more. Full stop. That is what we hear from everyone in unison. It is nice, but naturally they will not pay more. That's it. What happens increasingly is that some shipping companies want to install a scrubber in a vessel that they then want to charter out on the market or where they are already in negotiations with a charterer. They say: We have to invest as an owner in order to have that installed, but you have the profit, a split incentive, that means you would have to decide for a long-term charter and you would have to pay a share of the cost. Afterwards you may operate on heavy fuel oil and that will save you money every mile. That is somehow slowly starting a little bit in the direction: The one partakes in the costs of the other. But just like that: We will now operate, we tell our crew just to operate on gasoil and we will charter that out... such a thing does not exist so far. Not that we ever heard of that. #01:03:28-1#
- I: *That means vessels that are chartered out would likely always operate on diesel... well, they would relatively seldom invest in scrubbers, but would as a rule simply operate on diesel oil? #01:03:41-1#*

- E6: Yes. Unless someone says, like Maersk – Maersk for example has for example done that for some vessels that they have said: We charter that ship for the next ten years. Well and then that is worthwhile, then you can say, charter company or owner, please install such a thing, we will pay our share, because we will have the benefits afterwards. But in the normal market where you have charter periods of one month, three months, six months, that is a different issue. Something like that is not happening there. #01:04:09-1#
- I: *If you look at these seven areas again, is it easier in some areas or will the rules rather be adhered to in some areas – we have just had the example of the shipping sewage water, where it is practically impossible to comply with that – than in others?* #01:04:31-1#
- E6: You mean if it is somewhere attempted to circumvent a regulation? #01:04:35-1#
- I: *Precisely, because it is more difficult or because it is less controlled. Are all these areas similarly well controlled?* #01:04:48-2#
- E6: Well, according to my knowledge they are. In German harbours they control the MARPOL I to VI rules as well as, well, they are also controlling other conventions, and – I almost said driving and rest periods, well in this case driving, working and rest times and such things, will also be controlled at harbour state controls. Well, I have already been present at such MARPOL controls. They thoroughly control the books and in Hamburg for example that is the harbour policy, they are very experienced in that. They know when they should have... They are coming from there and there, they have a log book, they control the books and say: You would need to have so and so much sludge on board, show me the books, show me the stuff. Or they would have so and so much waste, there definitely exist empirical values. Well, if they come from Rotterdam they have ship's waste in that and that amount, they know that as well, maybe 10, 20, 30, 40 litres. Where are they? Well, that is regularly being controlled, sometimes the one, sometimes the other focus. But I would not know of anything being entirely ignored deliberately or also due to capacity constraints. #01:06:05-3#
- I: *How is that in relation to air pollution? That happens somehow, well, when I have two tanks air pollution is happening somewhere in an area where controls might be difficult to do.* #01:06:18-1#
- E6: Yes, there you may only, well, with the sulphur that is really an issue what may be controlled... well, the sulphur content in the fuel... #01:06:25-1#
- I: *Okay, how is that... well, in the harbour then?* #01:06:29-1#
- E6: And that is done in the harbour, you can only do that in the harbour. And there we have, you have, when you bunker fuel you will get a bunker delivery note, a legal paper that has printed on it the bunker suppliers and that you received so and so many thousand tons of fuel and that the sulphur content is so and so and so high. That is printed on there. And a sample is taken at each bunker transaction. And you have a little vial from

- the bunker transaction standing there on board. And then you may, if you have any doubts or if the port state control has any doubts, you can analyse these samples in the laboratory. Then you can say: Please determine the sulphur level and then you take that and control the bunker delivery note, BDN, the delivery note, if that is correct. That is how that is being controlled. #01:07:15-1#
- I: *And how may I control that this fuel has actually been used and not the one in the other tank? That is filled with heavy fuel oil? #01:07:22-1#*
- E6: That you may... that is rather simple. If you know that the vessel has come in at Rotterdam two days ago and is going round to Hamburg then you know: 24 hours, you know the vessel size, motorization, that exhausts around 50 tons or 100 tons a day depending on the ship size and it should only have operated on low sulphur fuel. That means you can check, how was the tank... the bunker inventory in Rotterdam and how is it in Hamburg. There has to be a difference. If there is no difference you know that he has not used low sulphur, but heavy fuel oil, thus one can relatively clearly see that from the books. #01:08:05-1#
- I: *What are the penalties for such... #01:08:09-1#*
- E6: That is currently still revised by the harbour police. What we have heard so far was not THAT high. Well, penalties between 100 and 3,000 dollars or something. There is still a certain potential for improvement. That is currently under revision, because we have this jump to the very low sulphur level of 0.1 per cent in 2015. I do not have an answer to that just yet, because the level of sanctions is currently discussed by the EU member states, well, the ECA states, how that should be done. That will certainly increase significantly, because they say with a difference of 50 per cent and if you pay 600 dollar per ton or 900 and I would say a large container vessel consumes 100 tons a day, they you are easily at 30, 40, 50,000 dollars a day. That is... it cannot be that a shipping company is trying to cheat there in order to achieve this cost advantage and another one doesn't. Then you will have an enormous distortion of competition in the market that means it is imperative that that is controlled in the harbours as well. And accordingly, I think, will also be seen as an administrative offence in that sense. Otherwise that will go higgledy-piggledy, that will not work. #01:09:35-1#
- I: *You said the German harbour police is very good in this respect. Does it make a difference at which harbour I make land, that in some... #01:09:44-1#*
- E6: In Germany? Not likely. But when you travel to, I don't know, Gabun that is likely a totally different issue, yes. #01:09:54-1#
- I: *Are there differences in the European sphere? #01:09:56-1#*
- E6: Yes, we hear complaints time and again... Italy, even if Italy is again quite good, but Spain, the Spanish harbours. But I do not want to go too far out on a limb with that. But there are complaints every now and then. But the North Sea, the English, France, Rotterdam, the real harbours so to speak are, they are rather far ahead. One also has to

add that they all have their difficulties to accomplish respective controls. There it is like everywhere else as well. #01:10:33-1#

I: *Recently on some conference I heard a shipping owner from the audience say: Well, none of us really does expect that the sulphur regulations will be controlled. I wondered about that. #01:10:45-1#*

E6: Yes, that is obvious. We always warn people against that. Because such things are evidently also anticipated by the Port State Controls or by the controls conducted in European waters by the water police. We are warning against that urgently. Well, needless to say that not all vessels that are calling at the port of Hamburg may be controlled, they would need tons of inspectors, surveyors. But that is also not necessary. You do not need to – the Hapag Lloyd, Bremen Express or one of the... you do not need to control them. You are wasting your time, because everything is going to be all right with them. Hamburg Süd is just the same. For these things, well, there will certainly be some kind of a risk-based approach to say: Which flag is that? Which vessel is that? Has that attracted attention before and that will be evident from the data of the water police for example. And then you go on board and have a look. Certainly not all vessels will be controlled, again, because that is not possible and one will look specifically which one to control. It is currently under discussion to somehow employ some kind of air measuring devices, sensors that monitor the air somehow, somewhere downstream in the Elbe or somehow to install such a sniffer at the Oresund Bridge and to observe. Such things are somehow under discussion. It all costs money, we have to see. But we urgently warn our people not to let it come down to a test. #01:12:23-1#

I: *If there is such a grid, which are the ones that are always being controlled, meaning what flags are that or what else is characterising them, the ones that always need to be looked at more closely? #01:12:42-1#*

E6: (Thinking.) Well, there is a... - initiated by the Port State Controls are also by the monitoring mechanisms – such a kind of Paris MOU – Memorandum of Understanding. I don't know if that tells you anything, kind of a list with white, grey and black listed ones and there is a little bit the history of controls recorded and also of flags and vessels which have attracted attention, which have been detained before, such things. That is the basis of the risk-based approach. One is checking: Hmm, well, which flags are those? Which ones those currently are I am not able to tell. Well, some, any African flags, I have no idea, I don't know now, which ones those are, but there is definitely a grid existing and the vessels are chosen based on that. I also do not want to say that somehow Antigua-Barbuda, which is a good flag, a very active flag, a small country, a very very active ship register, is somehow bad in this respect, that I do not want to... but the Panama flag, the Japanese flag, everything with a Panama flag, they are heavily controlled, they have to comply with that. Well, there are certainly a few every now and again that attract attention and that is noted down and that will certainly be observed and that will... I believe they will also inform between the European harbours. #01:14:03-1#

- I: *Does the size of the company play a role? Is it rather more difficult for small ones than for big global groups or can they rather hide from such controls, the small companies?*
#01:14:20-1#
- E6: No, I do not believe that that is arranged or carried out based on company size, on the contrary, the very big ones you can basically almost always already exclude, because the image loss for a Maersk or an Evergreen or an APL or a Hamburg Süd or someone like that is simply... on the contrary, they are always forerunners, if I may state that so generally... The small ones that are under a different cost pressure among other things... they will likely rather be tempted at times, that is quite possible. But it is also quite often the case that the owners - that we mainly have among our members - are chartering the vessels out to some other shipping company that is then operating the vessels and thereby deciding which bunker to fill in and operate on as well. And that means that the responsibilities are changing again and when the vessel attracts attention that does always depend not on the owner of the vessel, but rather in this case on the operator who is someone completely different. #01:15:26-1#
- I: *Also here: we have discussed this question already before. Are there any differences between vessel types? Because I have read somewhere that regarding bulk vessels it is often smaller companies in the background and regarding container shipping one has more often large conglomerates, thus in this area, should one look a little closer in that area, because they rather... because it is more difficult for them or because they rather tend to... or are there actually really... #01:15:57-1#*
- E6: No, I do not think, I do not think that that is a criterion, that there is a tendency to look closer at that area. I rather think that one really has to look ship specific, simply vessel specific. Because we have a lot of small shipping companies that are absolutely exemplary with their two, three vessels and keep them in top conditions and that do not have any such black spots somehow in their history with regards to their image and the chartering out on the market. You rather have to see: We just take one vessel out and if everything is fine, everything is fine. Then we take the next one that may be a large, medium-size, small one, there you are well advised as an inspector of the authorities not to build up any tendency into the direction of: Small one are especially dangerous and the big ones we can let run freely, but really to control everything. But if you have controlled a large container vessel from Hapag-Lloyd once then you do not have to control it the next time, because you already know or again, again, again. Simply just suspicious vessels or information coming from other harbours. #01:17:12-1#
- I: *If the flag is no significant criterion, is the main seat of a shipping company... well, can one say that the German shipping companies are based on their culture, rather tend to comply with legislation or environmental legislation and we have a different culture in different countries or are they basically no differences? #01:17:40-1#*
- E6: There are certainly these cultural characteristics and peculiarities. Just we have... regarding this issue it is really the case that we have a global market and they want to, German ship owners want to charter their vessels out worldwide and therefore you

always have it that the vessel is operating at times in Asia, at times in South America and at times in the United States. The environmental legislation in the United States is a little stricter than in China, I assume. They now have special areas, ECAs, in the United States. Apart from Europe you have that nowhere else. You always have to keep your vessel fit for the global market. That means the vessel always has to be somehow in a position to comply with current legislation. That's it. Well, otherwise it will not find a charter party. And if now an operator leaves the ballast water somehow at some time somewhere in Indonesia somehow... that is then a different story. That is then so to speak the operative decision of the one that is in charge on that vessel, or the shipping company. But in general you have to take care that the vessel is fulfilling all items of legislation and I believe that is the same also with other non-European operators. That they will say, well, we are competing on a global market that is very hard, that demands a lot of efforts so to speak. In that way I would first of all not see any differences. We here however... The Germans are always very... we are very very aware of the whole issue of regulation. That is very present to everyone. That also means that we have a very sharp eye on what is being regulated, what has to be regulated, how rigorously, strictly that is being implemented, such things. The awareness here is bigger, that is true among other things, but regarding the compliance with the rules, there I believe everyone is well advised – anyway it is the case with our people – to say, we have absolutely no problem complying with the law. #01:19:34-1#

I: *How is interested in law-abiding apart from the legislator? Are classification societies in any way interested in the level of compliance with environmental legislation?* #01:10:45-1#

E6: No, not really, as they are already involved in the preliminary stage regarding we have to... #01:19:50-1#

I: *The classification of a vessel would not change, if I would always...* #01:19:54-1#

E6: No, on the contrary. The classification societies are present when a ship is being constructed and classified. They examine the compliance, the technical compliance; let me say... if the technical prerequisites for such issues are given. That is, tank systems and so forth, that the tank systems are able to process the according fuels in a way that the vessel can operate safely and in compliance with environmental legislation. There are meanwhile a few options that you can buy from Germanischer Lloyd, DNV, yes, like Green Passport and such things, where they do some extra testing and say, we issue you an extra Green Passport as a classification and then you can use that for advertisement as a shipping company: We are somehow special or somehow, in the harbour, in Hong Kong for example we have that case, in the harbour we use certain special fuels for the auxiliary engine, better than required and so forth. Such things you can do. But those are commercial products that you can buy or decide not to buy. What happens now - and that is also why the eye of politicians is VERY much focused on us - The social perception of the shipping industry in general has become greater, clearer and stricter and large loaders that are very much under pressure anyway, they now naturally take a look at how that influences their image if they transport their cargo from

A to B. I'm just saying textile industry in Bangladesh, yes, houses crashing down and so forth. All those are issues of image that have become extremely important and the same holds true for the shipping industry. We know have a mega discussion about ship recycling, the practices that are currently... not currently, but that are how they are, that have historically grown, but that also call for another approach to ship breaking. That is one thing that is becoming much more popular and as I said, large loaders like Nike sports shoes and [inc.] and so on want to know exactly: When you are going from A to B, how much fuel are you wasting, what kind of CO₂ are you emitting and we want to take that into our calculation. In that way there are already monitoring systems operated on a company level. #01:22:06-1#

I: *How does it work with insurances? Are they interested in compliance with the law?* #01:22:11-1#

E6: Oh, I am not an insurance expert, but that will definitely be playing a MAJOR role, because if anything happens and they find out that current legislation has not been complied with or has been acted against, then I would say, again, I am not an insurance expert, but you would risk your insurance cover. That is when we are talking about cases like you are having some kind of accident with machine failure and they find out that you have been using the wrong kind of fuel in order to save costs, they I would think you would lose your insurance cover. No shipper should risk that, as that is linked to uncontrollable costs you are then confronted with. #01:22:54-1#

I: *Are banks interested in that?* #01:22:56-1#

E6: Increasingly, increasingly. Well, banks for shipping investments have been a huge issue in the last four years after the failure of Lehman Brothers, the banking systems and so forth. Shipping has in the meantime become, quote "a high risk investment" (laughing ironically) and the banks are examining that very closely – what shipping finance do they still do, what kinds of loans do they still have and how is that being serviced. And it is clearly evident to them as well that energy efficient vessels – CO₂ discussion, climate, fuel saving – have a different future than poor vessels that still sail around with too large engines or a high fuel consumption or something like that. And that is why, and that is established by the HSH [German bank doing significant ship financing], the KfW bank [German government-owned development bank], well, they are making sure that the investments they finance in ships... what kinds of vessels are that? Efficient, good ones with a good image? Are they likely to retract a return-on-investment somehow? Such questions are increasingly playing a role. How that translates specifically into credit, well financing rates, interest rates and so on I could not say, but I have been at various events where they said that the environmental, the environmental performance of a vessel is included in the investment appraisal, well the credit finance calculation. #01:24:18-1#

I: *If one now assumes that the shipping companies have significant incentives to comply with legislation, what would be obstacles?* #01:24:33-1#

- E6: Well, obstacles are, let me tell you from practical experience, what we have been observing in the last two years. You are coming from South America and you are entering the ECA, but the required fuel with 1.0 per cent sulphur was not available in South America. Non-availability of sulphur fuel in this case. Then you say, we have not been able to acquire it, we have tried everything, we will now enter the USA, enter the ECA with 3.5 fuel and then we have to bunker once we are there. But that is then... such things are known and then you have – that is at least the requirement, but sometimes it does not work – but there are certain ways to already tell the port state: Please, when we arrive, we will not have that aboard, we did not get it anywhere, please allow us, well, no detentions or anything, punishments, we could not do it. Sewage water, yes, port receptions facilities. We would like to get rid of our sewage water, MARPOL IV, but they do not exist, such things are very... We now have a discussion regarding scrubbers. When someone sails on the Baltic Sea next year, well, a scrubber might break down, I mean, that is a complex technical system, you never know. Somehow it is breaking down and you are still in an area with 0.1 per cent sulphur, but only have 3 per cent fuel aboard, what shall you do then? Such things are currently under discussion, well, technical failures and such things that will then play a role. I don't want to rule out people entering in the beginning of next year saying, oh no, somehow we were not consciously aware of that, no idea, forgot about it. That will happen for sure, you cannot exclude that. And I am not someone who would insinuate wilful intent for any of the shipping companies, but even that you can never really exclude. #01:26:23-1#
- I: *Would you say that the average age of the fleet is a good indicator for the environmental friendliness of a company?* #01:26:31-1#
- E6: Yes. Definitely, definitely. Well, you always have... you will always take a look at, if you have, I mean... the German, that is our, the German, our fleet here, the members, average age of 7, 8 years at the moment, that means the newly ordered are naturally always state of the art – what is possible and what is affordable, naturally. In that way... When you look aboard you know that waste is always an issue, water is an issue, then there are already efficient systems installed aboard that make everything easier, that you don't laboriously have to walk to a waste bin somewhere aboard to dispose of your waste, but the systems are really already designed and integrated in a way that makes everything easier. In that way it [age of the fleet] will always be a good indicator. #01:27:18-1#
- I: *We are talking so much. Do you have an appointment right after this or may I still...* #01:27:24-1#
- E6: How much time do we still need? How many sheets are left? #01:27:27-1#
- I: *Two. (laughing)* #01:27:30-1#
- E6: If you will allow me a little break. #01:27:31-1#
- I: *Yes.* #01:27:31-1#

E6: Then I will quickly disappear... #01:27:35-0#

(Break)

I: *Well, I still have... we still have the interesting issues left.* #01:27:39-6#

E6: Oh, they are still coming. Oh my, oh my. Well, I do not have an appointment, but I will be... #01:27:43-0#

I: *Hungry at some point?* #01:27:44-5#

E6: No, not hungry. #01:27:45-8#

I: *Okay.* #01:27:45-9#

E6: I have just been on holidays... Last week I have been in London at the IMO. One week not in the office, that is a disaster. #01:27:55-5#

I: *I have also been away for two weeks and work is piling up horribly.* #01:28:00-8#

E6: Let's go. #01:28:02-1#

I: *Yes... a few questions regarding the effects. How is the business model of shipping companies affected by – well, there are a few things happening in parallel at the moment.* #01:28:16-1#

E6: (Thinking.) I could not say that. That is very multidimensional, that is so very multidimensional. Well, because it is true: You have to take a look at how the whole issue of air [pollution] is handled, how the costs are covered, how such things like ballast water are integrated into new vessels, how reconstructions are planned, how vessels are now modified, how they want to conduct ship recycling in the future. These things are SO complex that I could not... just from the top of my head I cannot [estimate that] at all... Well, that is certainly a thing where you need to, you have to talk to many people within a shipping company, with technical experts, with business experts, I believe. #01:29:04-5#

I: *Do the shipping companies understand everything that is happening in parallel at the moment?* #01:29:11-1#

E6: What do you mean – understand? #01:29:17-6#

I: *Well, do they understand, what is means, for example? Are they able to add up all the costs? Are they able to calculate realistic forecasts for the future or is it too complex for them to...* #01:29:32-7#

E6: It is like this... shipping companies, let me say it like this, it is their task to keep the vessels in business and to generate cargo evidently, that is their absolute priority. In that way they are looking also at the next 12, let's say 24 months. Beyond that I would say that there are few shipping companies that have the freedom and competence and also man-power, only few shipping companies have that available to consider a little longer

period: Where are we going to? I do believe that the shipping companies, all shipping companies, some more, some less evidently, but all understand or suspect at least what they are facing. Well, those are reflections from the working groups and committees that we have. But there are... well, I experience that myself in my day-to-day operations that you are so involved in them that I believe that a shipping company has little opportunities to say, well, ten years from now we see us there and such things, that are in any way not easy to develop without slipping off into some kind of nonsense. Everybody understands that, but I believe that one always has to see that one... At the moment everybody is really only caring about how to get to the next year, in a way. #01:30:52-7#

I: *What influence does the current environmental legislation have on costs, the costs of the shipping companies?* #01:31:01-8#

E6: There is a press release on that issue by our global umbrella organization, ICS, International Chamber of Shipping. I can send that to you, if you want – they are talking about billions. (Laughing ironically) Well, everything that falls into that area. Well, there exists no, there is no cost calculation behind that, but only so to speak a rough calculation, but I mean if you, if one presumes that for the fuel alone, if one assumes that from 2020 onwards the worldwide fleet will have to operate on fuel that is 50 per cent more expensive, which will likely not be the case, but in that case we are easily talking about 70 billion dollars of additional costs, if fuel consumption is at around 250 million... #01:31:59-6#

I: *Are there differences between the big and the small players on the market? Is it going to become more expensive for the ones than for the others?* #01:32:07-6#

E6: Yes, in such a way that the technical equipment that they need is bigger or smaller. The big players evidently have, the big players are large shipping companies with large vessels. If it is small ones, like specialized shipping companies, Esberger or something similar who are specialized on product tankers, which are small vessels, but highly, highly, highly specialized and that are thus very expensive. Product tankers, chemical tankers, all these things, that is not... You can... to operate these vessels calls for millions of certificates and examinations and all of that is expensive and there exist only a few. Thus big or small is not really the indicator, but rather which type of vessel, which shipping purpose. You could not just somehow open a chemical tanker business. You have to be very persistent to take part in the race as the vessels are expensive, the certification procedures and so forth and so forth... And let's see if [the interviewer] is even knowledgeable about transporting chemicals around in the area and such issues. #01:33:13-5#

I: *For what kinds of vessels will it become more expensive than for others? Which areas of the shipping industry are more affected by environmental legislation than others?* #01:33:23-6#

E6: That naturally always depends on the field that we are looking at, but if we are talking about air pollution, sulphur, it will be the ones that burn a lot [of fuel]. That have high

levels of consumption, that operate large vessels with huge engines, that just have a high level of consumption and there are a few of them, Hamburg Süd and Hapag Lloyd, they now have... From their annual reports you can see how many tons of fuel they consume a year. If you have a small shipper that is operating a very small two-tanker with eight tons a day... well, it depends. Regarding ballast water it is like... if you are a huge... if you are an operator of a huge tanker or huge bulker, where you have these large amounts of ballast water you rather have to take a look at that. Well, it thus all depends a little on which problem area, which environmental area you are looking at. #01:34:13-2#

- I: *Are there shipping companies that get off rather scot-free, because they are neither affected much by ballast water issues nor by sulphur issues? Or others that are affected very strongly? #01:34:30-5#*
- E6: Not that I know. I don't know who that could be. Well, there are certainly small shipping companies owning small vessels that are thus not so much affected by ballast water issues. Feeder shippers will have the fuel problem, thus for them it is going to be... that is the problem with the issue itself. A small feeder operator has a cost concern just as much as a large company, because the relations are the same. You can earn little with such a small one. You have comparatively little fuel costs, but you also earn less than with a large Hamburg Express by Hapag Lloyd, well, because you can simply load less cargo. That means that the relations stay the same and that is why it is like it is. And above all it is naturally also like this: A small company on a large market has even less power than a Maersk on the market, which means that they are concerned by that. There are certainly other effects that play a role as well, like increasing vessel sizes for example. That is the so called cascade effect. That has nothing to do with environmental legislation, but it simply happens like that, the market conditions influencing it, that naturally generate additional capacity. Maersk is now sailing into the Baltic Sea with 18,000 [TEU] vessels, that means that they are no longer sailing through the Kiel Canal, but are taking the North route to Gdansk and then you no longer need, I don't know, maybe five feeder vessels. They are no longer occupied, but still produce costs and so forth. What are you going to do with them? Those are the things that eventually add to the difficult situation. #01:36:20-7#
- I: *Well, but may I say that everyone, the small ones and the big ones, are equally affected if you calculate costs in per cent? #01:36:33-2#*
- E6: May one say that? Probably, probably. I'm not so sure neither. As I said, it depends a bit... the one is a little more [affected] in one way, waste, sewage water is more an issue for cruise vessels rather than fuel. They are not sailing much across the Atlantic [Ocean], but sail from here to there, from Mallorca to Barcelona and they don't struggle with the fuel costs so much. They rather have it a bit with the whole hotel charges and such things, they rather have other problems. It is a little bit true that the weights are shifting depending on vessel type and problem area here. But I would say, to come back to your question, I do not think that there is any type of vessel that could say: Oh, whatever, I do not have to care about that. Because if there would be one, that is the disadvantage or advantage, depending, of an open market, if there would be such a thing, investments

would immediately move to that area. If you have something like gas tankers or the like, we have had one big one once, but if that turns out to be an interesting area of business everyone immediately plunges into that and the market is immediately balanced again.
#01:37:35-9#

I: *In what way do these cost increases have an influence on the freight rates of everyone?*
#01:37:43-0#

E6: (Thinking.) The freight rates develop by... that is a... that has almost no influence. The freight rates are developed on the market by demand and supply – as simple as that. And that is eventually the problem, that the vessels – that means container carriers, whereas, it is not much different with the VLCCs [Very Large Crude Carriers], well, with the oil tankers and the bulkers as well in the end – the vessels become larger and larger out of pressure to become more efficient, to reach economies of scale. The bigger the vessel with the same engine, maybe even with a smaller engine, the lower the cost per container - that is why you need ever bigger vessels. It is natural that the supply of vessel space on the world market is increasing accordingly, while the business demand, the transport demand stays the same. If you think about it, we naturally experience a decline in freight rates - Regardless of environmental legislation. That is developing unattached from that. Environmental legislation is simply influencing your costs that you try to somehow meet with the freight rates and that is currently not at all matching, because fuel costs are high, freight rates are low. That is why many operate on a loss. The question remains: How long will they be able to survive that? #01:39:13-0#

I: *How long will they be able to survive that?* #01:39:15-0#

E6: It depends on how much they have up their sleeve. There are certainly a few shipping companies, Greeks for example, but also German shipping companies that have been SELLING vessels in the super high time 2006, 2007, 2008, where the demand for vessels was high and they have evidently made a lot of money at the time. They are now in a position to build new vessels, more efficient vessels, to enter the market anew, but those are the exceptions. The majority... we have been ordering vessels nonstop and that is impinging us. And consequently the market is changing as well. Mergers, shipping companies disappearing from the market or vessels being sold, bought up and so forth. #01:39:59-0#

I: *Do you expect any change in the amount or the share of goods that is being transported by sea?* #01:40:08-8#

E6: Well, if I knew that, I could predict the global economic development. I don't know that, sadly, I don't know that. But as I said, I am very convinced that the way we went towards international division of labour was the right one. That we should not be going back to national production in Germany of sports shoes and t-shirts in large volumes. That is also to the benefit of welfare worldwide, of that I am convinced. And in consequence I also believe that the container shipping industry is going to grow further. With tankers, bulkers, ore transports and so forth I am not sure in how far the steps towards more energy efficiency on land, so to speak the intention to increase the use of

energy with renewable energies, if that is not leading us backwards. But I believe that in the area of container shipping we still have a development that is positively progressing forwards. That will however again increase the pressure on environmental politicians to tell our people: If sea transport is increasing further we have to do even more when looking at a reduction of emissions. But that is how it is. #01:41:29-7#

I: *Are there options to transport certain goods by other means than on vessels?* #01:41:36-4#

E6: Theoretically yes. You could transport them on a plain, well, if you are not in the short sea area. There we have a large number of other options. You always have the train, truck, those that do short sea shipping - that means container. For bitumen and such things, chemicals, it is more difficult. But in the short sea area: Container, ferries that have trailers aboard, trains and so on, those are all competing. That is difficult. Transcontinental transport – that is another issue evidently. Iron ore I believe you cannot transport further... there is no alternative in that. But there are certainly goods that have been transported on plains until now that are again shipped in refrigerated containers. Such things are winning us cargo again. But apart from that I believe that it is the value of the goods that determines that. Well, yes, the expensive chips and the expensive crystals that are needed for the production of TVs and mobile phones somehow and rare earths and so forth, I do not believe that they are being shipped by way of mass containers, but they rather move by air cargo. On the other hand I do not believe that we will ever... that we will transport heavy fuel oil on board an aircraft. That is not going to yield a profit. #01:42:45-2#

I: *Well, but if you only look at short sea shipping, which are the goods or the routes where a shift could actually happen?* #01:42:55-1#

E6: That also very much depends on how a forwarder is actually calculating. It is very much possible that a container is landed in Rotterdam that is going to be shipped to Poland and they say: Well, now, when we have to pay the expensive fuel, it is too expensive for us to take the feeder that is entering Hamburg on the way and then passing through the Kiel Canal to get to Poland. We will rather throw that on the truck and it will pass right through the middle. We fear this option in the area of short sea shipping and we will see next year in how far a shift of goods [to the road] will actually become noticeable. There are visible effects now already, that shipping companies, I don't know if TT-Line has mentioned that, but they have been changing their schedules and now offer different routes because of this... But that will become apparent eventually. #01:43:43-7#

I: *These shifts – do they rather go towards rail or road?* #01:43:48-9#

E6: Towards the road. I do not believe that much cargo is moving to the rail, because the rail traffic... The railway systems are already transporting everything that they are able to transport and I believe by now everything that they might possibly transport. The rail infrastructure in Europe and in Germany is... in Germany it is rather poor for cargo transport, but still relatively good compared to the rest of Europe. If you want to ship to Poland or to Latvia or somewhere up there it is really... it is almost impossible. And the

trains down to Munich, the old ones, are also agonizing a bit. Well, everything that is going to the South of Germany, they are already shipping everything that is possible, everything that may be shifted to the rail and so on. That is a superb option, but limited by the infrastructure. And in Germany we have this difficult issue with the ICEs [fast trains] and the priority for passenger transport and so forth. #01:44:46-1#

I: *What about the infrastructure on the road in the European countries. May one...?*
#01:44:52-7#

E6: Well, in the European countries I believe that we have gotten so far... I mean, if you look at the congestion, everyone is saying that it is bad, but in general I believe that we have a very good infrastructure [on the roads]. Well, and the economic costs of traffic jams and such things are not yet really finding a way into the calculations. And this is what we, what I have heard from loaders in the past: On the topic of the train: "Oh, difficult, the train is coming at a certain point of time, will be provided at one point, they are coming punctually at 4pm to pick the goods up and that is all very difficult... until then... the container might not be quite ready or the shift has not ended or something like that." All that is playing a role and in that case it is better to get a Kühne und Nagel [German truck operator] and tell them: "Get the goods at 9pm and bring them over. That's it." That means that it is independent of how the infrastructure is. It will just go into that direction. We are quite afraid of that. #01:45:45-2#

I: *If I have a very heavy type of good... ore or something like that, will that also be loaded on a truck, or will there be goods that simply...?* #01:45:56-5#

E6: No that you could not do. That is going to be difficult due to the weight of the good. The effort necessary to transport x tons of the good x is just too expensive. That will not be done. That does not pay off. For that case you have the small mini Bulker that will distribute that. They run on small engines, they run slowly, they don't consume as much fuel. That is another story. The earnings per ton are not so high that that [road transport] would be an option. #01:46:21-1#

I: *Thus it is the ferries rather than everyone else that have to fear a shift to the roads?*
#01:46:29-3#

E6: Yes, well, the ferry is a very good example, because the problem becomes quite evident: If you have a ferry from Rostock [harbour town in Germany] across to Sweden the trucks will drive up there and then cross with the ferry. The cargo is already on the truck. If the ferries now say, if Scandlines now says: We will increase the rates by 30 per cent, because we have to use more expensive fuel and a forwarder is not able to pay that he will say: Well, then the journey is not paying off like this. The truck will leave the ship and they will drive up the road until... as far as they can get, I don't know, up until Latvia, Estonia, up there and they will say: If we want to go to Finland we will take the short sea connection with Tallink or something similar, because that is then becoming cheaper and we don't have the longer sea connection which is more expensive. Those are very simple planning models that the forwarders are using. And they make a lot of sense, these models. #01:47:27-6#

- I: *Three last short questions, in order to get an overall picture. How does the competitive situation of the shipping industry as a whole look at the moment? #01:47:43-0#*
- E6: Compared to what? Within the shipping industry or...? #01:47:46-0#
- I: *Yes, within... exactly. How are the shipping companies doing at the moment, not in relation to environmental legislation, but overall? #01:47:53-6#*
- E6: Well, as I said, I already mentioned that we are in the sixth year of the shipping crisis, meaning that bank financing is difficult. The supply of vessel capacity is big, increased, that means you earn little with your vessel capacity – one single container cannot be transported from A to B – shipping companies earn little at the moment, but have high fuel costs in this case, but certainly other costs as well. Still, fuel makes for the largest part when we look at operations. That is a very difficult situation at the moment, extremely difficult. #01:48:26-4#
- I: *How are things going to develop in the coming years? #01:48:29-9#*
- E6: We are time and again hearing from the economic research institutes: Well, only until 2012... well, 2013 maybe... 2014... now we hear: Not before 2015 (laughing)... We are tailing somehow from year to year hoping that things will pick up. There are time and again larger container vessels entering the market, for example. I don't know how things are going in the VLCC [Very Large Crude Carriers] area, we have few shipping companies operating large crude carriers, oil tankers [in the association]. Currently extremely difficult, none of them are earning any money. #01:49:06-4#
- I: *What are the biggest risks and chances for the industry? #01:49:13-7#*
- E6: In relation to environmental legislation, or... #01:49:19-0#
- I: *In relation to... well, overall. Environmental legislation may be one issue among others. #01:49:23-4#*
- E6: Well, currently the situation is... It is... currently it is difficult, because in the face of a relatively... and extremely difficult income situation today you have to see as a shipping company, whether large or small – well, with the big ones it is always a little different – but with the small ones you have to see that you first of all survive. Second of all you should really go and sit together like we are doing today and say: Hmm, what is going on here? What kind of investment is necessary if we... what would we be in for – as a shipping company one would certainly be able to make a rough guess – if we are investing in certain systems. And do we want to make that investment decision today? - An investment decision characterized by EXTREME uncertainty. And those are extreme risks that I would not be willing to take. That means that most [shipping companies], and you may observe that as well, are waiting. They wait and see what comes. That again has the disadvantage that you have to... you have to suddenly, when sulphur or ballast water regulations are coming you suddenly have to react, then all of that is coming up within a relatively short period of time and then you instantly somehow have to build in a scrubber, because the charter party is asking for that,

because it makes sense. And to retrofit ballast water tanks... and maybe an NO_x catalyst and such things and that is then again... Well, the situation... What could we do in the next two years and how much could we gain? May we gain something if we have a super green vessel? May we get that refinanced by the market? That is... You can write something on that... yes or no? That is extremely uncertain, but the costs are high. Well, it is an EXTREMELY difficult situation. What is coming next politically? Will there be enough fuel available? Or shall we rather do LNG? It is very expensive to build an LNG vessel. Such a fuel that has a temperature of minus 160 degrees, that is somehow... the technical systems aboard, isolation and so forth, tanks, yes, tanks double the size and such things – 30 per cent more [expensive] compared to a normal diesel vessel. Can that be done? Does it pay off? Will we get the money back? That means, well, it may be done by those who have the respective financial means up their sleeve. #01:51:42-4#

I: *Are there any chances?* #01:51:43-2#

E6: Well, I believe that those will have a chance that eventually make it possible to put new vessels into operation to own them or to build them – vessels that are extremely energy efficient or more energy efficient than the ones already in existence. Well, really 10,000 TEU vessels. A 10,000 TEU vessel that is operating on 20 per cent less [fuel]. Those are the vessels that will be snatched from your hands in the market, logistically, by everyone. Well, but such a vessel you first of all need to own. In order to do that the fleet that you currently own, you would eventually need to earn money with it in order to finance such newly builds. That however is currently out of the question in the light of the market situation and the freight rates that are extremely low. Thus it is very difficult, if you do not have a lot of investors up your sleeve that say: We will do that, we are very patient. Then you are in a very lucky position. If you have a financing bank like the Commerz Bank [German ship financing bank] they will say: Never again! Shipping! Help! Get out of here! In that case it is difficult. #01:52:51-9#

I: *What role does environmental legislation play compared to other risks?* #01:52:56-6#

E6: (Thinking) Well, environmental legislation is playing a HUGE role in a way, because it is something that is a political aim, there is a political agenda behind that. That means that there are regulations, that might not be in force at the moment – see CO₂ regulation of some sort – but everyone knows that something is coming. A different legal basis will come about and that is entirely different from a changing market situation, where you might maybe have a down swing and say: We have to stand strong and then things will become better and we can forget about it. That is not the case [with environmental legislation]. The people are in for a lot, the shipping companies are in for a lot. They have to educate the people aboard, have to carry out the technical retrofitting of the vessels, have to deal with the economic implications – how do we manage with all the additional costs? At the end those are additional costs. That is something that influences the economic model. That is forming a kind of pedestal of things that just need to be paid, need to be met, due to laws and so forth, reporting obligations, and technical installations and so on. That will simple be there. There is no going back from that, it will increase constantly piece by piece and thus it is something that is predictable. It is

- nothing that comes and goes, but it is predictable – It is going to be expensive. We don't know, how expensive, but it is something that... that we cannot run and hide from, so to speak. Well, no one wants that anyways. The shipping industry needs to become cleaner, new fuels and so forth and so on. But is somehow needs to be integrated into the company and that is a huge challenge with all its many aspects. #01:54:48-4#
- I: *What other issues are occupying the industry?* #01:54:51-9#
- E6: Apart from the environment? #01:54:54-2#
- I: *Yes.* #01:54:54-6#
- E6: Oh, I can tell you very little about that. Something that is a little bit environmentally related is evidently always the question of competitiveness of the shipping company with its flag state and with its crew and so on. That means that there is for example the question of crew costs that play a significant role, the technical maintenance, all those things play a significant role. Questions of competition in general. Bureaucracy efforts aboard, driving and rest times, let's say, such issues also in relation to the employees. That is, as far as I understand that from my colleagues also a significant issue, but I can tell you little about that. #01:55:51-5#
- I: *Is there anything that we have not talked about that would be important for my understanding of the problems?* #01:56:04-0#
- E6: Not that I would know of. Likely that will... when you listen to this again then maybe the one or the other thing will come up, but we now have talked about everything... the shipping company – economic level, technical level, political level, the link between both. I don't know what that would be, but when you are working through this again likely something will come to your mind... oh, well, effect... I still wanted to ask that... but at the moment nothing comes to mind, no. #01:56:37-6#
- I: *Last question – do you still want to tell me anything?* #01:56:40-8#
- E6: In relation to the environment? Something that we have not talked about? #01:56:48-3#
- I: *Anything.* #01:56:49-1#
- E6: Anything? #01:56:49-7#
- I: *Irgendwas.* #01:56:50-4#
- E6: I don't think so, no. Or do you have any sort of indication what I should tell you? #01:57:00-8#
- I: *No.* #01:57:00-9#
- E6: Give me a hint as to what I should be telling you. #01:57:03-1#
- I: *Nothing. (Laughing) It could have been that an important argument that is occupying your mind has not come across.* #01:57:09-3#

- E6: No, we talked about everything. #01:57:10-3#
- I: *Wonderful.* #01:57:12-5#
- E6: No, we have talked about everything. If something comes up later I will be in touch. I have your card. #01:57:16-6#
- I: *Well, we have been talking for two hours now. (Laughing) One never knows how long it will take, it may... I have done the same number of questions in one hour before. It always depends...* #01:57:33-5#
- E6: The people are talking too much. #01:57:35-2#
- I: *Such a source of knowledge. That is evidently my pleasure.* #01:57:42-1#
- E6: Well, I don't want to be accused of not having delivered properly. #01:57:48-8#
- I: *No, I am thrilled. Well, I'll now switch this off.* #01:57:50-3#

Interview No 7

Date: Monday, 27 October 2014, 3 pm

Duration: approx. 90 minutes

Method of contact: Contact to E7 was established via a contact at the ship owners' association. A readiness of E7 to be interviewed was signalled by said contact already on 24 September 2014. Contact details were provided on 26 September. A short discussion took place with the expert at the ship owners association whether E7 would be a valid interview partner as organization 7 was not trading in the Baltic Sea. Still, as problems of shippers trading on the North Sea should be very similar, the interview was agreed to be of interest for the research. An answer by E7 on the 30 September was a little hesitant. The entire catalogue of questions was requested prior to the interview and before an interview date could be fixed. On 2 October E7 agreed to an interview having reviewed the interview guide. The interview finally took place on 27 October 2014.

Interview situation: The interview took place in a conference room in the office building of E7. The room was large and seating arranged in a circle, thus interviewee and interviewer set at a strange angle to each other. A junior colleague of E7 attended the interview unexpectedly, sitting in the background most of the time and providing valuable additional information on two occasions. His role or interest to be present remained unclear. Water was

available at the table and served at different times during the interview. The interview went smoothly and without interruptions for an hour and four minutes, when the audio recorder unforeseenly died. That led to a small interruption in the interview flow and a little gap in the audio recording of a few minutes. The recording was then done with the interviewer's mobile phone and the interview resumed for another 20 minutes.

E7 was friendly but reserved and very much hesitant in giving out any kind of information or personal assessment. Statements were refused for a number of topics based on reasons of business intelligence, lacking competence to answer or other fears. A significant number of questions were answered by referring either to other market actors (association, suppliers, customers, environmental organizations, law makers or competition) or to newspaper articles. A wish to be updated on the research progress was voiced at the end of the interview.

I: *Let us start then. First of all thank you very much to make this possible today. The background... Well [another expert] might have prepared you what this is about. Well, I'm writing my PhD thesis... #00:00:16-1#*

E7: Well, your exposal has prepared me. #00:00:18-1#

I: *That as well. (Laughing) Well, I just noticed the physical proximity [to the other expert's organization]. #00:00:23-7#*

E7: Yes, we are relatively close by, yes. #00:00:26-1#

I: *Well, this is about trade effects, maybe also unintended trade effects due to environmental legislation that are affecting the shipping industry. What I will try to achieve with this interview – well, the expert interviews are leading up to a quantitative study – is to get an idea of the relevant influencing factors. How shall I picture the practical application? Well, the questions today are related somewhat to that. What influence does environmental legislation have at all for the shipping industry, what influence for the container shipping industry compared to other areas? What are the cost effects? What kind of effects maybe also on the levels of trade may one expect? And what kind of other variables are relevant? We want to talk a little about that exactly. The results will be completely anonymized and I will audiotape the interview for transcription. Exact. Wonderful. A little bit of background information so that I know who I am talking to, what kind of questions I may ask. What is your current position with [organization 7]? #00:01:44-5#*

E7: My position is called Department for Sustainability and is thus directly below one of the managing directors. Related to the question what kind of topics I am occupied with – for the first three years, I am here since 2011, the first three years it has clearly been the

environment. Now it is being broadened by social aspects. That is why it is the Department for Sustainability and not just the Department for the Environment. Right.
#00:02:12-0#

I: *Does that mean the significance of the issue within the company has increased?*
#00:02:18-5#

E7: Yes, you could say that. That is certainly true. Well, my position has been newly established in 2011 and when the environmental controlling has been established the question somehow came up: What is now going to be the next step? How are we going forward? And that is now somehow a step further also as regard contents that one has said: Okay, there is not just the environment, there is also social responsibility and thus we have to look into that as well. What do we communicate? What do we measure? Where are we heading in this area? But also as well to expand the environmental topics still further. Environmental protection. What kind of issues are facing us apart from CO₂, let me say, and so on and so forth. #00:02:56-0#

I: *Okay. And are those questions of internal management or also of external communication?* #00:03:00-4#

E7: Both. Well, there is this motto – Do good things and talk about it [“Tue Gutes und sprich darüber.”] – I mean, it is a phrase that can mean more or can be empty. Well, no, it is... it is the idea of both of us naturally NOT to do this PR thing, but the issues need to be implemented internally. Be it that we are investing in vessel efficiency, be it that we develop environmental technologies not together with Germanischer Lloyd [German classification society] and then we may also say: Yes, these things, we are doing them. But not like: Here, we are donating five Euros a months for something, but what really are the relevant fields and what are our activities in these fields. #00:03:46-4#

I: *Talking about external communication – Who is interested in that?* #00:03:53-8#

E7: Customers – they are definitely interested. I would say they are the vital group. Evidently it is also somehow the legislator – What are the shipping companies doing anyways? Owners are also interested, well, we belong to the [a company holding] and this issue of sustainability, environment, social issues is definitely of relevance for the [owning family]. In that way they are naturally also a player. Employees up to a certain degree, the one more, the one less, like it always is. Media... The sciences, who would have known, as we see right here. Well, you are evidently not the first PhD student or student that comes up to us asking: Well, dear [organization 7], what are you doing in this area? Well, it is all of the above. #00:04:45-9#

I: *When you are saying customers – are customers willing to pay higher prices for more sustainable vessels?* #00:04:55-6#

E7: No, very clearly not. Well, it really isn't like that. It is not like you could somehow open up a new field of business, let me say, like the Aldi brothers [German chain of supermarkets] thinking, well, organic products – now you can discuss about that, well,

- they are not as good as Bioland or Demeter [German seals for organic products], but at least they opened up a new field of business and offer organic products – because customers are buying that. We could not say, well, we are doing this or that environmental initiative, dear customer that will cost an additional 100 dollars per container. The market is far too competitive for that. Well, if you look into the current press you will see that. That does not have any potential somehow. #00:05:36-4#
- I: *On how far are customers aware on which vessel their container is being transported?* #00:05:43-9#
- E7: In principle they know that very well, because they may enter into the according systems and may have a look in the intranet and they are also receiving documents from us. You could not say: We absolutely want our container to be shipped on [specific vessel of organization 7], but you can choose a certain service. Then it may be the [specific vessel], but it may be a sister ship as well or it may be the vessel of a vessel-sharing-agreement partner, if we are sharing a service with [another shipping company]. Then it will be changed weekly and if you put your containers there in a week where a [partner company vessel] is leaving then it will be a [partner company vessel]. #00:06:20-6#
- I: *That means as a customer I could not say: I want my container to be transported on a particularly environmentally friendly ship, because I have no influence on that?* #00:06:30-4#
- E7: No, you actually have no influence on that. Theoretically you could certainly influence that if you knew that the vessels of [organization 7] are positively better than those of the competitors and you knew that the vessels of [organization 7] are leaving the harbour in certain weeks... Well, you would have to see, okay, I have to leave my container... but then... well and then... well, that is certainly an illusion. That is not possible. #00:06:54-5#
- I: *Are there even significant differences between the shipping companies?* #00:06:59-0#
- E7: Regarding the efficiency or...? #00:07:01-1#
- I: *Yes, regarding the environmental friendliness or... efficiency is just one of many variables.* #00:07:07-0#
- E7: Certain differences do obviously exist, at least with CO₂ one could say. Clean Cargo Working Group, have you already heard about that? #00:07:15-2#
- I: *No, not yet. No.* #00:07:16-1#
- E7: Okay. CCWG, Clean Cargo Working Group is an alliance of shipping companies. There are 18 of the top 20 involved, well, container shipping companies and the most important of our customers. Well, and they developed a formula how CO₂ should be calculated most aptly in order for shipping companies to compare themselves with one another as well as for the customers to benchmark the shipping companies. Well, and if you now take a look: How efficient is [organization 7] on the service from Europe to South

America and how efficient are others then you will ascertain that the ones have a CO₂ per TEU-kilometer with a value of 40 and the others of 60. Well, thus there are certain differences. But you cannot per se say: This shipping company is particularly green or this one is less so. Clearly, some are doing a bit more, some a bit less. Some are talking about it, some are not. Well, that you spot by examining: Who is publishing reports? Are there any figures in these reports or are there no figures or is it just colourful pictures and so on and so forth. #00:08:18-5#

I: *Okay, well. That was a short side note. Let's get back to your work. What are the topics that you deal with mostly at the moment?* #00:08:27-9#

E7: CO₂ measurements, I would say, is certainly always of topical interest. Well, it has been of high importance since I am working here. But also everything that is relevant on the legislative side and then we are evidently talking about sulphur. You are evidently aiming at that eventually. It is certainly also relevant. Then we are also monitoring the area of ballast water management, though I have to say that I am not the one that will decide that we will install a ballast water treatment system on board the vessel, but I monitor the whole issue really only from the viewpoint of the department of sustainability and not from the rigid technical side. That is it in the area of environment and social issues – well there [on social issues] we are currently only identifying what the hot topics are for us. There we are still in the process of – let me say – brainstorming. I am not going to go too much into detail there. #00:09:33-1#

Employee of E7: And moreover and maybe adding to that the whole reporting thereon. That always raises the question in how much detail do we want, are we able to report eventually, because it is sadly not like you just have to push a button and have the requested figures. #00:09:50-2#

I: *Are figures of sustainability collected? May that be measured?* #00:09:54-5#

E7: Well, the vessels are providing certain data and from this raw data – that is: number of containers aboard, distance and fuel consumption – I can compute certain things relating to the emissions, the energy input and so forth. #00:10:18-6#

I: *If you compare... if you compare the sulphur issue to other issues that are bothering you – how important is that for companies like [organization 7]?* #00:10:33-7#

E7: Currently that is extremely important for all shipping companies that have some form of contact to North America, the Baltic or the North Sea. It is evidently very relevant for us. It means added costs in the range of... what did it say in the press... in the range of eight figures due to the use of better fuel, marine gas oil. For shipping companies only operating for example in the Baltic Sea or only in the North Sea it is... Well, it does not entirely upset the applecart, but for them, they cannot offer a voyage at the old costs, but everything becomes more expensive by factor x. #00:11:23-3#

Employee of E7: In addition maybe to your first question where you asked who had an interest in this information: The non-governmental organizations. That may not be

forgotten in this context. NABU [German environmental organization] or Greenpeace. It is especially currently an issue in Hamburg – NABU, air pollution and shipping. Well, I just wanted to shortly add that. #00:11:43-7#

I: *What role are they playing? Are they very much interested in what the shipping industry is doing?* #00:11:48-6#

E7: Yes, you could say that. There are different ones. Well, NABU is a German NGO that is also linked with other European ones, but is rather present here in this area. Then there are also others like Carbon War Room that look at the global shipping industry, I'd say. Well, yes, Carbon War Room is a subactor in the big picture on vessel efficiency and the NABU is particularly interested in emissions, that is in particle filters for example. #00:12:26-1#

I: *Is the population as a whole interested in what the shipping industry is doing?* #00:12:33-4#

E7: Increasingly, I would assume. It is certainly more on the agenda due to the fact that the press, the media are covering that now. Well, I believe that a few years ago the population had rather little interest in that. Now the media in connection with the laws that are now coming about or recently entered into force, by increased media coverage on that as well and naturally then... well, through that the issue naturally attains significance and the individual citizen becomes more easily aware that the shipping industry also somehow needs to work on environmental issues. #00:13:15-0#

I: *You personally, where did you acquire your knowledge on environmental legislation?* #00:13:23-6#

E7: My studies, my PhD time, my time working here. Well, eventually I am dealing with this topic since 1997. Well, I have already had lectures on environmental law during my studies. #00:13:35-5#

I: *That means that I may ask everything? (Laughing)* #00:13:36-6#

E7: Yes, I just don't know if I will answer everything, but... may or want to, but yes. #00:13:40-8#

I: *Wonderful. I still have a little bit on background. For once [organization 7]. How big is your company? In which area are mostly operating?* #00:13:59-6#

E7: A visit on our webpage is helpful. I have already done that as well, strangely. (Laughing) Well, it is, we have about 150 vessels, around 40 of them are our own vessels and all of them are container vessels. Out of the 150 vessels around 100 plus two, three, four, five are container vessels. And the others are bulker and tanker. Bulker means bulk products, bulk materials and tanker, well, liquids. #00:14:30-0#

I: *How many of them are potentially entering into SECAs? Are all of them entering at one point?* #00:14:41-2#

- E7: No. But there again a visit on our webpage and also of our product catalogue is helpful. There you see that we have very different areas of service. And some services, if we are now talking about container vessels, that is by far the most most important area then there are services that only operate in South America, or that operate from Asia to South America, they are eventually not concerned. From Asia to South America is definitely an important service, but also from Asia. Well, Asia as well as South America Eastern Shore as well as Asia, South America Western Shore – there everything stays as before. Apart from the fact that evidently due to this regulation certain circumstances relating to the fuel availability and prices... there will be certain developments, but... Well, and then we also have different services that mainly operate from Europe to South America Eastern Shore and Western Shore, they are evidently concerned. We have different services between South America and North America, also from North America to Oceania. We have vessels everywhere in those regions. On some services we have several vessels, on other services we provide one vessel and the others come from other shipping companies. Well, how many of the 100 are concerned I could not say, but it is more than 10. But I could not say how many it is precisely. #00:16:12-8#
- I: *What kind of consequences would the coming into force of the ballast water regulations have next year? #00:16:21-1#*
- E7: It means plain and simply that we have to install according treatment systems into the different vessels by and by and eventually into all of them, depending on when the next dry docking is scheduled or how large the vessel is and so forth. By and by there treatment systems need to be installed. With all new buildings since 2012 or 2013, we already have ballast water treatment systems installed, well, for example the [vessel type of organization 7] has ballast water treatment systems as well as the [vessel type of organization 7] that is operating in South America. Right. #00:17:08-7#
- I: *Is that a cost factor? #00:17:11-5#*
- E7: Estimate. #00:17:13-2#
- I: *Oh, I could not do that. (Laughing) Well, is that of importance? #00:17:18-4#*
- E7: YES! Well, if you ask me: What does a treatment system really actually cost, I could not tell. That will likely be somewhere in the area of seven figures. And who is paying for that? I don't know if the customers are paying for that, I don't know if they are very much interested in ballast water at the moment. I don't think that that is too much on the agenda. In that way yes, it is relevant, definitely. #00:17:40-6#
- I: *What is going to be more expensive – sulphur or ballast water? #00:17:43-8#*
- E7: Sulphur. #00:17:44-4#
- I: *Really? Even if the container vessels only spend such a short time in the SECAs in the end? #00:17:50-8#*

E7: Yes, well, as I said, it was in the media that we would accumulate I think 40 million [US dollars] and Maersk or Hapag, one of the two, 250 million addition costs – dollars – in 2015 alone. And we are not talking about 2020 yet. And if we now say, well, as I said, the figures that I now mention need to be treated with caution, I don't know, but if we now say: Okay, we have 40 of our own vessels and need to install ballast water treatment systems into those and each will cost a million dollars then we are somewhere even. But in the end sulphur is clearly the more expensive one in the long run. There is likely no law in any area of transport, I'm very certain there is not, that has influenced transport so such an extent, to such an amount. That is what I would argue. Would you agree? #00:18:46-9#

Employee of E7: Hm. (In agreement) #00:18:46-9#

I: Does the fleet of [organization 7] experience any changes due to the legislation, due to sulphur or ballast water or other things? #00:18:55-6#

E7: Ballast water, as I said: The systems need to go into the ship at one point, if they are not already in there in the beginning. And sulphur, well, the fuels that help to or with which you can comply with this critical value have a different viscosity, other characteristics than heavy fuel oil. Accordingly it means: Do we have enough tanks for this new fuel? Do we have enough pipes? Do we still need to filter something? Now we don't need to heat the fuel any more. And so on and so forth. Thus we need to evaluate ship-specifically how big the tanks need to be, how the pipes need to be positioned and what we need to change. Well, in that way there are certain measures to be taken. #00:19:45-1#

I: *And the fleet as a whole, if we now look at the number of vessels, will that stay the same or will there be any changes? That one moves further into the one or the other area...* #00:19:56-8#

E7: To my knowledge there will be no changes. #00:20:00-6#

I: *Yes, very well. How well are you informed about current environmental legislation?* #00:20:07-3#

E7: Very well. #00:20:08-4#

I: *Who is informing you?* #00:20:10-8#

E7: I myself. That is naturally not all. Well, naturally one can google a little here and there as a standard, or has certain news feeds respectively. There are certain pages that one can have a look at, evidently also by way of the associations. Yes, different sources, where you can assume that you will receive information there. In part evidently also by way of the media or if there is something like the just mentioned Clean Cargo Working Group, you are also talking about that again naturally. There are very different sources. #00:20:45-6#

I: *Is it easy to receive easily comprehensible information?* #00:20:51-6#

E7: Easy? When is it ever easy? It is easy when I have the TIME to deal with that. If I do not have the time, it is not easy, because we do not necessarily... there is no forum or other place where I get everything reasonably packed together. In that way it may be easy for the one to acquire information and more difficult for the other. If you are on the inside for a little bit longer you evidently have your portfolio of sources at a certain point and it is maybe easier for you. Easily comprehensible? Take a look at the EEDI formula, energy efficiency design index, and tell me if that is easy. I do not think it easy. Ballast water, okay; there is filtration, there is infrared, there is this, there is that. Is that easy. Hm. (Not sounding convinced) Maximul sulphur content 0.1 per cent, okay, I do get that. In this area the sulphur content of fuel may not be higher. I do get that. Nitrogen oxides, four gramm per kilowatt hour, hm. How does nitrogen oxide develop? Combustion process, oh, hmm... (sounding critically ironic) Yes, well, it depends on the issue and what kind of access one has. If I had studied business studies, if I would be a controller and had landed in the area of environmental controlling afterwards and would now be in the department for sustainability I would have a little less of an idea and maybe would not know immediately: How do you even spell NO_x? And what do these symbols stand for? I would say, okay, I do have a certain basic knowledge. #00:22:23-1#

I: *Yes. You said that time is a factor. How many employees does a company need in order to understand and implement the legislation?* #00:22:33-5#

E7: I could not say. I would not know. I could just say something, but that would be of little value. It also depends on how [topics] are then divided within the company. Is there one that strictly deals with all pieces of law? With us it is also linked to different departments. Well, I am interested in that. Then we also have a Compliance Management System. They will evidently be informed by the respective technical department. Naturally not only in the area of environment, but independent of topic. Then we have ISO 1400, oh, we also have to keep ourselves informed about the law. There the respective information is collected and then there is naturally the one – everything that is related to the vessel, we have to comply with the ISM code, there are evidently certain requirements – thus there is naturally somebody who is interested in these things and clearly everyone is sharing information, sending any kind of insights back and forth. #00:23:37-8#

I: *One can assume that a large company like [organization 7] evidently has many experts somewhere and is rather well informed – are all ship owners comparably well informed?* #00:23:49-5#

E7: I have to take a look what I thought about that. #00:23:56-0#

I: *I'm jumping a little back and forth.* #00:23:57-2#

E7: Yes, no problem. We will find that. If you say are owners and operators equally well informed – there are differences, I would say. Operators are better informed. Why? Because we, I believe, are more directly evidently somehow affected by the laws. Well, if we now consider whether a vessel should sail into the ECA then we eventually decide

if we want to apply the vessel in the one or the other service. If the vessel is a chartered vessel, then we have to eventually say, well, we now want to sail into an ECA and into an environmentally protected zone; there we have these and those requirements. Owner, please tell me – well, in the end it is the owner then – one that is situated in Hamburg for example, is your vessel able to comply with that? If one has not agreed on such a thing already at the point of contracting. Well, that would be my opinion, I would say the owner, no, the operator, we are, as I said, at the question of owner and operator... but liner shipping companies are likely rather a little better informed, they tend to be. But I can easily imagine that certain charter shipping companies are just as well informed. That is clearly again the question whether there is someone in the company thinking: Boah, if our charter shipping company is really up to speed in the area of environment, then we will be able to sell our vessels better to the liner shipping companies. Thus we have to monitor closely what kind of rules there really are and see that our vessels comply with all requirements and that our vessel may be applied in all areas for example. If I realize as a charter shipping company I have a vessel coming on the market in two years, or in one or in a half year and I would like to get rid of that or charter it out and that will be given off somehow close to the North and Baltic Sea then it likely makes sense to make sure: Will it also be able to sail into the ECA? Can it handle the MGO, the marine gas oil or can it not? #00:26:23-4#

I: *Then one would have to assume that it would be attractive for most owners to have the most environmentally friendly vessels? #00:26:37-8#*

E7: No, not necessarily. Well, as long as the owner is able to charter out the vessel the way it is it is not necessarily like he needs to care about that. Well, if we leave the topic of sulphur and talk about ship efficiency now then it may be that a more efficient vessel may be chartered out better and to a little higher price. But if he now goes and says that he welds some propulsion improving metal sheets onto his vessel, that is propulsion improvement devices, he does not have any immediate advantage, but rather an investment that he needs to... likely the vessel is being chartered out at the moment to someone anyhow so that he is not even able to do that. Rather, he would have to do that at a time when he does not have the vessel chartered out. Well, and then he has this investment, but maybe he does not have anyone who will pay him back the money for that. Thus in that way there is not necessarily an incentive. It may well be, if the owner knows that he has to do this or that, otherwise the employability of the vessel is limited... and then I am not able to apply the vessel for someone, for an owner, for a customer, for a liner shipping company... well, there are different things imaginable or reasons why an owner will do that or will choose not to do that. #00:28:11-3#

I: *Could you say that at the moment rather the one or the other thing is happening? Is there rather a massive investment at the moment or is everybody rather adopting a wait-and-see approach, because they still charter out their vessels rather well? #00:28:21-0#*

E7: There as well I suggest you look through the press again. The owners are so much under pressure, I mean, there are so many limited partnerships [German:

Kommanditgesellschaft] that went bankrupt. There is no money [available]. Well, I believe it is very much a financial problem, especially for the smaller shipping companies. Well, for the larger ones, that are situated here in Hamburg and that somehow own, I do not know, 50 or more vessels, attractive choices may still be open, but even they are in part so much under pressure that they will not do anything voluntarily. I cannot imagine that. #00:28:57-5#

I: *Okay, if you are talking about small shipping companies – are there significant differences? Are they, do they acquire information in a different way? Well, many one say they maybe do not even know what they are required to do? #00:29:18-4#*

E7: I could not tell you that. In the end the VRD, well, the Association of German Ship Owners, is responsible for all shipping companies somehow and also the other associations. They are also passing on information. I could not tell you however how they are working. I do not know anything about that. #00:29:41-8#

I: *Yes, very well. If you now have to attune yourself to... oh, maybe we should talk about legislation first. I think I will jump backwards a bit again. What is happening at the moment? What are the current political advances that are of interest to [organization 7]? #00:30:00-9#*

E7: Of interest... let us say of relevance. #00:30:06-2#

I: *Or of relevance. #00:30:06-2#*

E7: Well, we have everything happening at the IMO. IMO 67 has just taken place with a mixed bag of topics that were on the agenda, well, sulphur, nitrogen oxides, CO₂, vessel efficiency, reporting of such figures, ballast water,... has been on the agenda. Those were in short the most important issues. Then we evidently have the EU, who is coming up with this CO₂ reporting itself at the moment, well not at the moment, that has been active for a while and is trying to develop a regional model. Whereby it is tried to put the IMO under pressure. Well not under pressure, but it has always been said: Dear IMO, if you do not advance then we will advance that within Europe. Then we will do our own thing [German: “Dann kochen wir unser eigenes Süppchen”]. In addition it is evidently also the different regions that are active themselves and develop something, some kind of laws. Well, in the EU we have had 0.1 per cent sulphur in the harbours for a few years now, for example. Turkey has been defining that single-handedly for its own waters as well, for example, that their own harbours have 0.1 per cent sulphur, that that is the maximum level. California as a significant part of the United States does rather a lot regarding different topics, well sulphur as well as, evidently, shore-side power is an issue. Well, New Zealand and Australia are active on certain topics as well. I think it was fouling of vessel hulls that was allowed or shall not be allowed, I believe, in New Zealand from 2018 on. Hong Kong, the whole Hong Kong area or Shenzhen, well Pearl River Delta, is going to be an ECA as well. Right. #00:32:11-3#

I: *Oh, that is interesting. I have not yet heard about that. #00:32:14-5#*

- E7: Yes, but that is what I would say. #00:32:19-2#
- I: *I have tried first of all to extract something from the literature, the areas, well... in which a vessel may potentially harm the environment and which could then potentially be regulated or maybe are already regulated. Waste, ballast water, air pollution, which contains many things, then we have TBT and so forth, noise, oily water and sewage water. If you look at these: Which of them are regulated, which of them will be, which are exhaustively regulated and where will we maybe see a development in the upcoming years? #00:33:01-7#*
- E7: I would be careful to say “exhaustively regulated”. #00:33:05-3#
- I: *That you may do. (Laughing) #00:33:07-4#*
- E7: Right, well. Waste has been regulated in an annex to MARPOL for some time, I do not know if it was MARPOL annex IV. Air pollution is MARPOL annex VI. Well, I try to stay a little at the global level and talk about what is happening at IMO. Rather comprehensively, but not entirely regulated in the sense that we can still stay, okay, 2015 we have and 2020 we still have – regarding sulphur. #00:33:38-8#
- I: *Will there be more happening in that area? #00:33:41-6#*
- E7: In the area of air pollution you mean? Well, I mean, NO_x comes into force from 2016 on in the ECA, well, at the moment first of all only in North America. There will be a new NO_x limit value to be reached for newbuildings from 2016 onwards. EEDI and SEEMP are regulated, that is energy efficiency design index and ship energy efficiency management plan. NO_x, CO₂ is above that... if something would still happen somehow on CO₂ reporting it would likely also happen in MARPOL annex VI, but I don't really know about that. Particles, well, soot is not yet regulated, just indirectly via sulphur. Well, what does indirectly mean. Really, if you talk about sulphur you talk mostly about black carbon that is carbon-based pollution. Not regulated so far, something may come there. At the moment people can not really agree at all what we are even talking about, however, if we are talking about black carbon or particulate matter. What is that including and so on and so forth? Noise is not such a huge issue yet, but something will certainly happen there. Well, we can talk about what is happening above the water and what is happening below the water. Sewage water is regulated in MARPOL, well sewage water I would see including oily water, I would put that together. Yes, well, I think sewage water is... Is that annex V? I do not know. And oil spills would be annex I of MARPOL, I believe. Fouling is also regulated. TBT you have mentioned is prohibited. There are different alternative substances now that are being used. And ballast water is also regulated. #00:35:37-6#
- I: *If we talk about CO₂ – what do you expect to happen there? What are you expecting and is that going to be expensive? #00:35:51-5#*
- E7: Yes, it will be expensive. (Laughing) Well, it depends on how it is done. It may be expensive, but it also depends on how the vessels will then be rated. If one for

example... let us really assume for once that the case occurs and a law is passed that binds us to communicate first of all only key figures on our operative efficiency. Well, really not just: Our vessels are greatly designed, but how efficiently are they actually operating. Then it would theoretically be possible that this law rewards especially efficient ships and penalizes less efficient ships. That is really rather unrealistic, you would likely have to collect money from each vessel and put that somewhere. Then we could, I would say, as [organization 7], we would maybe even have an advantage... well, no, take that from the protocol. (Laughing) No, it is not to be assumed that we would have an advantage from that. There was a proposal on efficiency, a proposal that was discussed at IMO by the World Shipping Council together with Japan. We rather approved of it, but it was not so much on operative efficiency, but I would say on design efficiency. And the idea was, okay, very efficiently designed vessels do not need to pay anything and the inefficient ones have to pay, if they do not put that money into an improvement of their vessel. Well, that they weld propulsion improvement devices on the back. Well, back to the topic, if a law on CO₂ is coming it will cost money. It is linked to investments or we plain and simply have to pay into a fund. As we are already investing in our vessels anyway, well, in the newbuildings in order to make them especially efficient as well as into so-called retrofits, which means that we try to do something with the existing fleet. We are already doing a lot. We are maybe talking about a fund here, about a tax, whatever. I can only tell what may come by reciting what is being discussed at the moment at EU or IMO. If there is something coming on top of that and in which direction that is developing – no idea. #00:38:18-6#

I: *Could you order these seven areas a little bit according to the cost effects they will have on the shipping companies or liner shipping companies – it may be different for others. Which are expensive, which play no role at all and where do you see the greatest future dangers maybe?* #00:38:38-5#

E7: Dangers for whom? For us or for the environment? #00:38:41-4#

I: *No, first of all for you. (Laughing)* #00:38:45-1#

E7: Well, dangers are already existing. Otherwise one would not have developed these laws at a certain point in time. One realized somewhere: Oh, oil in the water is not good, thus we probably have to prevent that. Well, I can not tell you: number one is this and number two is this, I can just repeat what I just said: Sulphur regulation 2015, 2020, I believe you can already read that in the press or at the VDR [Association of German Ship Owners], that is an incredible cost factor. Well, if we take... let us take another example: A shipping company has fuel costs of a billion dollars and has been operating mostly on HFO, heavy fuel oil, simply because it has been allowed. Right. After 2020 it may not operate on normal HFO anymore. Let us say we change to MGO [marine gas oil]. This MGO then costs an additional 50 per cent. It might be 45 at times or sometimes 55, but let us assume it is simply 50 per cent. Well, from 600 dollars to 900 dollars, even if prices are a little lower than that at the moment. Well, that means that my fuel costs are no longer a billion US dollars, but 1.5 billion US dollars. I believe I do not have to add anything to that. That is clearly apparent. And no other of these issues is only roughly

coming into that range [of costs]. Unless we are thinking about CO₂. There one may again really make some cash. Theoretically it would be possible to say: Okay, for each ton of CO₂ that you are emitting – well, the ETS in Europe has gone haywire currently with something like six dollars, but still – if we say we now take 100 dollars per ton, well, then it will be of extreme relevance. It does not need to be very much unrealistic. #00:40:29-5#

I: *Okay. Very well.* #00:40:32-6#

Employee of E7: The clear difference with fuel compared to the other areas is that one has constant additional costs. Well, the one thing are the investment costs, that is what does it cost us to reorganize a specific area. The other thing is then what kind of subsequent costs do we have, for example fuel costs. #00:40:53-8#

I: *Very well. If we assume that additional costs are in some form linked to this issue. If we assume – ballast water is simply also very present – that maybe there will be something happening as well. How is your business model influenced by these current changes in environmental legislation?* #00:41:28-6#

E7: Ballast water is not influencing us at all. We have to do it. We have to carry the costs. That is it. And no one is bearing the incurred costs. Well, so far I have in any way not heard from anyone anywhere - well, not only within [organization 7], but in general – that a customer or anyone would say: Yes, well, now that you have installed a ballast water treatment system we would like to pay an additional 50 dollars per container. I do not know of such an incident. Nothing is happening there. And apart from that... air pollution or CO₂... I would have to think about that. What was the question again? #00:42:12-4#

I: *Everything that is happening. Concretely it is first of all sulphur legislation, CO₂ is still a bit anybody's guess, and ballast water...* #00:42:28-0#

E7: Sulphur will not really change our business model neither, I believe. One has to... I think regarding that issue has rather has to talk about the shipping companies that only operate in these areas. And I think that DFDS, I think that is their name, has discontinued one or two services. Well, not now, but they will discontinue them, because they do not see them as competitive any more. Well, the question in the end is: What is happening in the Baltic Sea and do you fear modal shift? We are ultimately not DIRECTLY affected by that, because we are not operating there. Ultimately we will, well, I do not need to talk about [organization 7], all the large shipping companies that are somehow active on a global scale will go on operating their services as before. One will come to according agreements with one's partners, but everything will go on the way it is somehow and the customers will now hopefully come up with these additional costs. #00:43:41-0#

I: *Okay, does that mean one can pass the additional costs onto the customer?* #00:43:51-0#

E7: Pass on? #00:43:52-6#

I: *Pass on.* #00:43:54-0#

E7: Hopefully yes. Why? Because the customer has no, NO option in the end to bring his container from Hamburg to New York without the transporting shipping companies sailing through two ECAs. And if we now assume that the shipping company needs to comply with this legislation and if we now assume that MGO is the only real alternative at the moment then that will mean that the customer will not get the transport service at the old price, as every shipping company has to carry into investments for MGO. #00:44:39-5#

I: *What kind of cost increases are we talking about?* #00:44:45-4#

E7: There again a reference to the current press. MSC has published something shortly for example, that... where on which services one is to expect increased costs. I can not remember the details. It depends on whether I am sailing only through the Baltic Sea or sailing only through the North Sea or sailing both through North and Baltic Sea and whether North America is affected as well. Depending on how many ECAs and how long the journey is – it depends on that if we are talking about I'll say 50 dollars or 200 dollars. Well, there... I do not know the exact numbers, but just look that up again. #00:45:26-6#

I: *Well, so that I understand that very roughly. I mean, I have no idea what a container costs on a certain journey. Well the customers in the end... is it one per cent in addition or five or ten?* #00:45:38-1#

E7: No, for the customer it is more than that. What am I going to say to that... #00:45:42-1#

Employee of E7: Five to thirty per cent one can say. It also depends where that vessel is leaving from and whether it is dry or refrigerated containers. But one can say depending on the journey, how often one passes through an ECA and how long one spends in said ECA – the longer one travels through that the more expensive it will get. #00:46:02-0#

E7: It is of relevance and something is obviously changing, otherwise you would not study whether there are any shifts in transport with your thesis. Well, obviously maritime traffic is becoming more expensive in specific areas, because otherwise you would not think that that would be an interesting topic. Shifts in modes of transport, the maritime traffic is becoming more expensive and by that other modes of transport are becoming interesting. #00:46:26-1#

Employee of E7: What has also been in the press, something also in the navigation area not concerning us, for example in the Baltic Sea area, is that independent magazines expect that there will be a shift of transport capacity towards the road in the Baltic Sea. But there they have roads. #00:46:47-3#

I: *Right. If there is in principle no alternative for someone who is shipping a container, does that mean that I can automatically pass on 100 per cent of the costs? #00:46:59-0#*

E7: I have no idea. No one knows that so far. Well... #00:47:07-0#

I: *But may I somehow assume that we have no competition by the road, thus cost increase equals freight rate increase? #00:47:16-0#*

Employee of E7: Well, plainly economically speaking certainly rather not, if one looks at it from a neutral point of view. That is my opinion. That is because ship operator 1 has a different margin or different pricing system than we have, for example and depending on each individual calculation a different leeway. And certainly the one may give in more at times and the other one less. That is what I would say, economically speaking. #00:47:43-0#

E7: Yes, sure. I mean, such a fight for rates has occurred already three years ago where the rates went way down, but eventually all of that remains to be seen. Well, I believe, we may not... we may not allow ourselves to comment on that and I believe, if we would know we would not tell you that. (Laughing) #00:47:57-7#

I: *How much competition do container shipping companies have or how competitive are they against each other? #00:48:05-5#*

E7: I would say that things happen as they normally happen on the market. Well, one tries, depending on the strategy, to keep one's share of the market. Some try to grow above the normal growth of the market, but one is also working together in many areas. There are now these vessel sharing agreements that I have been talking about, because you can not operate all four slings on a service with your own vessels. Rather there is then a conglomerate of six shipping companies or even more. #00:48:36-3#

I: *If I now have a container that I want to ship from Hamburg to New York – how much choice do I have? In terms of different shipping companies? #00:48:47-3#*

Employee of E7: There you need to differentiate between shipping companies on the one side, but also freight forwarders. Well... #00:48:52-4#

I: *They will then go aboard the... #00:48:54-5#*

E7: They then go aboard our vessels, yes. There are certain platforms where you can enter, I think that is also possible via intranet, departure point, destination point and then you get... brtt... information on which vessel is leaving when and so on and so forth. #00:49:10-3#

I: *But is it rather five or rather a hundred different companies that are fighting there? #00:49:16-6#*

E7: Then rather five. #00:49:17-2#

I: *Then rather five, okay. #00:49:18-4#*

E7: No, well, there are very well a hundred shipping companies, but the majority operate locally. Something like Unifeeder, they only operate on the Baltic Sea. I do not know whether they also operate on the North Sea. They are sailing around there. Other shipping companies like Maersk are active everywhere – or MSC. Well, you can certainly find some graphics on that somewhere or google it, as I said. If that is of relevance you will find that somewhere. #00:49:47-9#

I: *We said the cost increases will likely lead to price increases of some sort. What are other influencing variables on freight rates? #00:50:04-1#*

E7: What apart from the environment? #00:50:11-4#

I: *Exactly. #00:50:13-0#*

E7: Well, everything. Terminal costs, then charter costs that we have,... Puh... #00:50:24-5#

I: *Or let us say: What role do costs caused by environmental legislation play compared to all other things that lead to costs? #00:50:33-0#*

E7: Let us again take the example of half a billion US dollars. That is already a huge amount. Smaller or regional legislation does evidently not have such a high value. But if we say the fuel costs, that is evidently again trade dependant, but we will just say that, simplified. I do not know whether it is like that or rather close to that, but let us say the fuel costs of a vessel for transport make for fifty per cent of the total price. And if these fifty per cent become fifty per cent more expensive then that has a tremendously high importance. #00:51:11-3#

I: *Okay. Does it make any difference how big the company is regarding how well is can deal with environmental legislation economically? Is it easier for you? #00:51:28-0#*

Employee of E7: Well, that is maybe an economic calculation. If one assumes that one shipping company has one vessel and another shipping company has fifty vessels. The time needed to analyse a law is a certain factor and the shipping company with more vessels may certainly break down the investment costs on more vessels. Thus per vessel it is maybe cheaper, if you calculate it like that. #00:51:57-7#

E7: The costs invested into the analysis? #00:51:59-6#

Employee of E7: Yes, exactly. #00:52:00-8#

E7: Okay. Yes, well, if it is even possible to determine that somehow how long the experts of the company have been sitting together and done random calculations. Finally, if I use ten tons in the ECA, well, let us say a thousand tons in the ECA then we have to pay for these 1,000 tons MDO, MGO and smaller container shipping companies or feeder companies will pay just the same. I could not say that the larger shipping company is somehow less affected by that. Each ton... if we now really, we are talking about it all

the time, okay... heavy fuel oil is being replaced by marine gas oil. We are not talking about scrubber technology or something, where one could now also step in. How far that is developed and why that is no alternative. Instead we are just talking about the system "We go in and replace the fuel" and then the problem is, I would in any case say, the same for everyone. Well, I also have to say that: In principle it is a good thing to change to another fuel and to do environmental protection. We have in principle no problem, if these external costs are being internalized, as one likes to say. One can first of all support that, but if one goes bankrupt, because nobody will pay for that then that is of help to nobody. #00:53:32-7#

I: *Scrubbers are no technical alternative? #00:53:34-9#*

E7: No. Well, the technology is not developed. Well there are, there were, maybe there still are somewhere – I heard that the company had set up firm under a different logo somehow – dry scrubbers. That meant that I had somehow a granulate, would let my exhaust air pass through that and the sulphur dioxide would be filtered out. And then there are wet scrubbers, open loop, closed loop and hybrid that are able to do both. Open loop means that I take sea water, flush my exhaust air through that and drain the water into the sea again. And then closed loop: I have water tanks and lead my exhaust air through them and that is then cleaned somehow. There are certain areas, or at least discussions that certain areas or nations do not want the washing water that now coming out at the end to be introduced into their waters. That means that there may possibly a prohibition coming up. My open loop scrubber obviously is not of any help to me then. And evidently one may also think: Yes, that really is not too good. Well, then my sulphur dioxide is not in the air, but I do have it in the water. And possibly I have at least a certain local acidification there. And in that sense the technology is little developed, especially if we are talking about really large engines. That is why the solution at the moment is MGO. In a few years, decades, it might be liquid gas, LNG. #00:55:12-9#

I: *Is that an alternative for 2020? #00:55:17-2#*

E7: No, because... Well, yes, it may, will maybe be an alternative for the Baltic Sea, but globally speaking I believe not. Well, A it is linked to a fair amount of additional costs. Well, MGO as we said will also be more expensive, but it [LNG technology] first of all needs to be developed corresponding to such a vessel. United Arab Shipping is doing that or has gone to the press saying: Our vessels will be LNG ready, which means they may be retrofit with rather little technical and temporal effort to run on liquid gas. That also requires for gas stations somewhere in the harbours where those vessels are passing through. And up to now these gas stations do not exist. LNG will come, but it requires time, a lot of time. #00:56:12-2#

I: *Are you then hoping for a development of the scrubbers or will you simply operate on marine gas oil globally? #00:56:22-5#*

E7: I do not know. Do we hope for scrubbers? It would at least be... I think it is always good if you can somehow diversify, if you have several options to solve a problem somehow. Hope for that? Well, I find that hoping always sounds so uneconomical somehow.

(Laughing) Well, if we think purely ECOLOGICALLY, really, I imagine that I am an employee of an NGO, then I would naturally say – and the NABU is also saying that, thus we can just take them [as an example] – scrubber are no solution, because they are an end of pipe technology. Whereas, if I take a better fuel, MGO, I directly change the system. Well, there you may argue again, yes, well, but MGO is also gained from crude oil and the sulphur had to be removed somewhere earlier then. But it has been removed earlier and is not passing through the whole chain and that is per se good first of all. But then again you can say that MGO is still an oil product, a finite resource or based on a finite resource. It is however evident as well that we cannot power such a huge vessel with some kind of solar panels or something. Hoping somehow sound... no, I do not like it in this context. #00:57:46-7#

I: *Okay, well, but the current strategy is first of all waiting if the deadline even is 2020 or if it is maybe 2025 then...* #00:57:54-2#

E7: Yes, but even it is 2025. Well, it will be coming and then we will see what is available. Well, not only then, but also in advance as well. All shipping companies are facing that challenge and all global shipping companies know as well that LNG is no... there are no gas stations in that sense. One may say okay, it works somehow. It has been working with gas tankers for quite a while, but it needs to happen on board the vessels as well. Well, that such vessels are also being build or that they may at least be retrofit to use this technology and I also think the infrastructure... One needs, yes, local, regional rules, that certain safety standards are being met, blablablabla... It creates a mountain of work. [“Zieht einen langen Rattenschwanz hinter sich her.”] #00:58:52-1#

I: *Which companies struggle the most to deal with current environmental legislation?* #00:58:59-8#

E7: I cannot clearly remember, I certainly have written something clever on that as well. Struggle the most... I do not know who struggles the most. #00:59:17-0#

I: *If you are looking for the page it is on page six.* #00:59:19-5#

E7: Amazing. Thank you. Then I can finally see what I have written on that. Struggling the most... yes, I have put down a question mark there. (Laughing) #00:59:30-8#

Employee of E7: The question is: What does struggling mean? Fight for survival? #00:59:34-6#

I: *Fight for survival? For whom is it the most expensive?* #00:59:39-6#

E7: The more vessels I have the more ballast water treatment systems I need to install. And thus speaking about the total sum it will be larger for shipping companies the more vessels they have. If one assumes that it is always the same cost factor, the same value, independent of the type of the container vessel. However, a larger shipping company may evidently hopefully cover the enormous expenses better than a smaller one. Well, from [struggling] little to a lot, I do not know. I find that you cannot talk about it that way. #01:00:16-4#

Employee of E7: You can also see in the press, if you look from the point of view of financial models it is like that that it is often said that smaller ship owners or rather ship owners that have their vessels financed close to a hundred per cent get into trouble, simply because they do not receive further credit lines for the additional costs. Especially with the current banking crisis that one may observe. Thus one could certainly say that if a vessel is financed to a hundred per cent and further follow-up financing is needed then the highly indebted ship owner may run into a bigger problem. #01:01:00-8#

I: *Is it a tendency that smaller shipping companies have rather higher debts? Or are vessels often – I know little about that – are vessels often debt financed to a hundred per cent? #01:01:14-6#*

Employee of E7: I could not say. I do not have an overview so much, but it certainly depends on the ownership structure. #01:01:22-4#

E7: Well, there are, at least there were, these limited partnership funds [KG funds] that were financed to a hundred per cent by private citizens or the like. But I do not know how large the percentage is or anything. There again I refer you to the Association of German Ship Owners [VDR]. They have extensive information on how the German fleet is structured, I believe. Then again you may say to yourself, yes, well, now we know it for Germany, but how do the Greeks do it and what is happening with Seaspan in the United States, who are a huge charter shipping company. Well, I believe we are the wrong addressee there. #01:01:56-0#

I: *You do not only operate container vessels. For the bulk carriers, for the, I do not know, where there tankers as well? #01:02:01-4#*

E7: Tankers. #01:02:01-7#

I: *There were tankers as well. Will it be expensive to retrofit these? Do they have different problems from container vessels? #01:02:12-5#*

E7: Well, first of all I need to say that all of those are chartered vessels... #01:02:18-5#

I: *If it would be your own? #01:02:22-2#*

E7: Let us assume that... well, I know for too little about that. As these vessels are operating at lower speeds they have smaller engines. What does that mean? Do they also have smaller ballast water tanks? I know far too little about that, thus... #01:02:45-0#

I: *Okay, let us talk about something else. I have to ask that question, you are also allowed to say that you do not know – do you expect a shift of transport volumes of some kind? #01:03:02-5#*

E7: If I had no clue about that it would mean that I had not read the study of this ISL. I have not read it, but I did flick through it. Well, as I do believe to some extent in this document and also in everything else I have read that is somehow referring to that, yes, I find that easy to imagine. That is if I do believe in the underlying assumptions written in there.

- But I have no own expertise on that or have not conducted own analyses or something. In that way it is only good faith in thoughts that others have had. #01:03:45-3#
- I: *Right. We have already talked about the fact that your fleet will likely not have to face any changes. That means that we will assume for the moment that that [modal shift] is not and will not become a reality for you? #01:04:02-3#*
- E7: If there is modal shift I only know it about the Baltic Sea, where we are not active with our vessels. Well, if a customer says: Do not bring the container to Hamburg, bring it to St. Petersburg we will engage a feeder company that is going from Hamburg to St. Petersburg. #01:04:26-2#
- I: *Are there shipping companies who tend to overcomply with environmental legislation? #01:04:39-5#*
- E7: I had to smile when I read that question. Well, evidently I do not know that. What I can say is this... and there I want to refer to studies by Maersk on this topic. You can find presentations by Maersk online, I believe by Niels Björn Mortensen. There a glance at the Triad Alliance is worth the while, that has just been founded, because there is a certain fear that shipping companies are taking the risk saying: Yes, we are not being controlled that often and the cost savings are immense, we will try running on heavy fuel oil. But I could not say: Yes, those are the rotten apples. #01:05:32-0#
- I: *Well, but what is characterizing the rotten apples? Who is doing that rather than somebody else? Is it rather...? #01:05:40-4#*
- E7: I do not want to say anything on that. #01:05:43-3#
- I: *Rather small ones, rather big ones? Is it depending on the fleet? Is that somehow? #01:05:50-2#*
- E7: I do not believe so. Well, those are questions... I will beware of naming a shipping company somehow. I would not know it – and even if I knew I would not do it. #01:06:03-3#
- I: *No, certainly, but entirely irrespective of a name? #01:06:10-2#*
- E7: I could not say. Well, I do not know. #01:06:12-4#
- I: *Is it easier in certain areas to get around environmental legislation? Which ones are the most heavily controlled? #01:06:28-1#*
- E7: I could not tell you. Well, we are all somehow being controlled. But there again the reference to what I just said about the Maersk study. They have also looked into that and then it was somehow only one in a thousand vessels that was controlled in any harbour. That is not very often. And then, at these port state controls they are looking through everything at times. At times certainly the garbage book is looked at and the ballast water management record book and the oil record book. Well, and the different things are already looked at there. But well, that is simply done in this low frequency.

- But I do not know which issue that know... where one can better cheat [“betucken”] and which shipping company is doing that. Well, I do not know. #01:07:20-1#
- I: *How is that with the sulphur legislation now – is it even possible to control that?* #01:07:27-7#
- E7: Yes. #01:07:28-9#
- I: *How would one do that?* #01:07:31-4#
- E7: Yes, theoretically the oil record book would be an option, because there should normally be everything in there. Then you have the bunker delivery notes and there it normally states, well, MGO 0.1 per cent sulphur or... and that is then attested again by a third party. Or it simply states heavy fuel oil with 2.8 per cent. There again the reference to the just mentioned... the Triad Alliance has been founded or formed in order to point out to governments or port state controls or everyone in this area: Yes, we now have this law, but the economic influence of this law is so big that there is a certain incentive to circumvent that if it is not adequately controlled. #01:08:31-2#
- Employee of E7: And a further issue is also this sniffer technology that is in parts installed locally and that functions in a way that the authorities have so-called sniffer on there and passing vessels are being controlled. And in that way certain limits may simply be checked. #01:08:55-3#
- I: *Is that already in use?* #01:08:57-3#
- E7: No, it is not in use. I refer to the same thing that I have just mentioned and just to research that. You will certainly find something on that. Triad Alliance and Maersk. #01:09:09-0#
- I: *What are the most important obstacles when complying with environmental legislation?* #01:09:17-8#
- E7: I do not know. Well, because for us there are no obstacles, but, I mean, we are complying with it. #01:09:24-9#
- I: *Do you always have complete information? It is always technically possible to a hundred per cent?* #01:09:33-8#
- E7: Yes, well, basically yes. I mean, with some vessels the effort may be higher and with other lower. I need to mention again that I am simply no shipbuilder or vessel technician, but some ballast water tanks may be better accessible and then such a system may be simpler to install, with others it may be more difficult. With some vessels you need to do more maybe in order to get them sulphur-ready, well now with the other fuel, with others it is less. Well, anti-fouling, there you can... the vessels are going into the dock and then it will be possible to paint that differently, well, we do not have that any more, TBT has been off the market for while. #01:10:18-1#

- I: *Okay. But you do not know of any problems that have occurred somewhere at any point?* #01:10:23-9#
- E7: One does not know problems, one only knows challenges. (Laughing) #01:10:26-7#
- I: *Okay, challenges. Well, fine. The last group of questions that I have is linked not so much to environmental legislation itself, but to classify environmental legislation within the global problems. Well, how does the overall economic situation of the container shipping industry look at the moment?* #01:11:01-1#
- E7: I would refer to the VDR. [Association of German Ship Owners] #01:11:05-7#
- I: *That is just as well. Is environmental legislation playing an important role compared to other developments facing the container shipping industry or are there other risks that are really bigger?* #01:11:21-2#
- E7: Environmental legislation is playing a role. Well, again the example of sulphur – you may not beat around the bush, that is of high relevance. Apart from that for each company standard... there are the standard risks of new competitors, innovation of competitors, changes with customers, other challenges that need to be met and so on and so forth. Well, everything that can be found in traditional economics textbooks I would almost say. #01:12:01-8#
- I: *What is important at the moment? What is occupying the shipping companies?* #01:12:10-2#
- E7: I would say the overcapacities in the market. And the low freight rates. I would say that is occupying the shipping companies. And yes, not only container, but with bulk and tanker shipping companies it also partly looks similar. And there again, I mean, you are also able to read. I do not have original sources, but certainly one hears something here and there, but in the end it is not my core business evidently. In that way, if you work yourself into this topic for a period of one, two, three, four years, yes, just read and research, then I cannot tell you any more than you would know yourself or would be able to find out after a few hours of study. #01:12:54-8#
- I: *Yes, but sometimes, if one moves through the halls internally, one gets more of a feeling or a notch than if one...* #01:13:04-7#
- E7: No, but what I just said it the relevant part and what you hear on the halls would be something company-specific again and should likely stay in the company. But well, overcapacities are an issue that is interesting to all shipping companies. That is again linked to efficiencies, to utilization rates and is by that becoming an economic issue as well. #01:13:30-1#
- I: *What kind of development do you expect for the coming years?* #01:13:34-0#
- E7: I just made a line there. Economic consequences, what consequences for the environment to expect... no... what I expect? No idea. Well, I mean we have already

talked about the upcoming laws in the field of the environment. Do you mean what I expect independent of the environment or just like... #01:14:00-9#

I: *What do you expect irrespective of the environment and where would you put environmental legislation in there. Well, it is rather other developments that occupy the ship owners or is environmental legislation playing an important role in the upcoming years as well? #01:14:14-2#*

E7: Well, environmental legislation will stay relevant in the next ten, fifteen years, guaranteed, that goes without saying. Well, the last EEDI deadline or the next limit, the last one will be from 2025 on - that is interesting to everyone building vessels. Sulphur you have already mentioned. Maybe that will only come in 2020, let us assume that... I mean 2025, but let us assume that it will come in 2020. But that will have an impact for years to come after that, evidently. And without a doubt there will be ever new regulations or laws being developed, because one has gained new insights. Well, to my knowledge there is no standstill in any area anyhow. Apart from that, what I expect for the shipping industry in the upcoming years, I do not want to be so pretentious as to answer anything to that. In that respect I am... I have other tasks. One may be interested in many things, but regarding the field of sustainability... #01:15:20-6#

Interview No 8

Date: Thursday, 20 November 2014, 3:30pm

Duration: approx. 94 minutes

Method of contact: Contact was established at an evening event where E8 came to the researcher for having heard about her PhD project. The interview took place almost half a year after the initial contact. That is due to the contact being established long before the qualitative data collection started.

Interview situation: The interview took place in the office building of E8. The room was rather small; seating was arranged at one end of a long table, thus interviewer and interviewee were sitting quite close together. That helped the conversation and led to a very personal atmosphere. A colleague of E8 opened the door and left the office shortly afterwards, walking past and wishing a good night. Apart from that, no other disturbances occurred. Water was available and served at several occasions during the interview. E8 was playing with her phone during the interview and was softly knocking it on the table at certain points, a sound that might be heard on the audiotape.

E8 was friendly and interested throughout the interview and readily offered explanations. At certain points E8 seemed slightly impatient, but was again very friendly the minute after. E8 answered all questions as well as possible and was well informed on a number of topics. E8 also voiced new arguments that had been discussed in the other interviews so far. At one point E8 asked for a certain statement to remain confidential, even if anonymized, as the information was not supposed to be made public. The interview went on for an hour and a half and the interviewee showed sign of relief when the time was over. E8 offered freely to contact her or her colleagues again for further information or contact details of other experts.

I: *Very well. #00:00:02-2#*

E8: Where do you have the microphone? #00:00:03-7#

I: *That... well, it is recording in any way. #00:00:07-6#*

E8: Good. #00:00:09-3#

I: *I am not an engineer. #00:00:11-0#*

E8: If there is enough sound... #00:00:12-8#

I: *No, no. That is working. That is working very well. #00:00:14-6#*

E8: It looks like it. If the glass is in the way I can put in in the back here. #00:00:18-8#

I: *That is okay, right. I am currently writing my PhD and I am studying trade effects of environmental legislation on the shipping industry, if there are any. I have evaluated the literature and now I am doing a round of expert interviews. In succession there is supposed to be a quantitative study. The aim of the interview today is to get some insight on current environmental legislation, how the processes work, that I do not exactly... how that looks in practice... and also to inquire on some variables that I have thought about, how that could work. And you may be able to tell me where I am going completely wrong and where it maybe looks rather well. Right. In the beginning, to get an overview – in which position are you working at the moment and what issues are of key concern to you? #00:01:26-8#*

E8: I am in the transport committee of [organization 8] and there I am responsible for the issue of shipping. At the moment we are... what was the last thing that we were occupied with? Last week it was the issue of water and shipping administration and before that it was... we still have to deal with... we will deal with scrapping, we will deal with the Hong Kong Convention [for the Safe and Environmentally Sound Recycling of Ships, 2009], such issues are now on the agenda. We will certainly touch upon the issue of emission control areas again in the beginning of next year, because likely the shipping companies will then rise again and scream blue murder [“Zeter und Mordio schreien”]. That is to be expected. #00:02:21-4#

- I: *And which of these are the topics that take up most of your time at the moment?* #00:02:29-2#
- E8: At the moment... well, it all takes up relatively little time. In [organization 8], in politics, things are only done when there are loud complaints from somewhere again. The whole shipping topics are classified under “further issues” in [organization 8]. #00:02:50-0#
- I: *Okay. Why is that so?* #00:02:51-8#
- E8: Plain and simple because little is done in the parliament on that. The real work is taking place at IMO. The delegations of the government are there and the parliament is only presented a ready-made proposal. Do or die. It may only... we have a contractual obligation to adopt the IMO regulations and that is what we do. #00:03:15-3#
- I: *Okay. That means that we do not really...?* #00:03:19-2#
- E8: There is not much being talked about, no. #00:03:20-3#
- I: *...talk about it.* #00:03:20-8#
- E8: That is not really being questioned. That is more or less governmental action that is happening there. The parliament is involved only marginally, every time something goes wrong. Then it is being brought into parliament. #00:03:34-9#
- I: *That means: How should I precisely picture your work in this area?* #00:03:41-0#
- E8: We are sitting there and we are supposed to make the legislation, the German legislation. And that is what we do. #00:03:49-3#
- I: *And if this shipping law is now coming, will you still be commenting on that, or...?* #00:03:54-1#
- E8: Certainly. All four fractions are expressing what they think of that, where they still see room for improvement. Sometimes we succeed in still making changes, but it is all very rudimentary as a rule. Especially if you have such an omnibus law [“Artikelgesetz”], where one adopts the IMO regulations one-to-one, MARPOL regulations or whatever is on the table. MARPOL Annex VI that is adopted one-to-one. Maybe there is even a dynamic reference inserted so that it is always adapted automatically. #00:04:27-4#
- I: *Okay, yes well.* #00:04:29-4#
- E8: And we are then as well exercising our so-called Right-to-take-up-issues [“Selbstbefassung”], where we discuss certain issues, situation of the shipping industry, situation of the vocational training system in the shipping industry. Well, we discuss the vocational training system in the shipping industry next week in [organization 8], because the formation level is eroding due to the shipping crisis, the self-made crisis. The number of apprenticeship places is eroding. And there we will, we have made a petition that will then be discussed but clearly be rejected by the government, because it is an opposition petition. But you just do that anyway. #00:05:07-9#
- I: *Why is the crisis self-made?* #00:05:11-4#

- E8: Self-made because they have build too many vessels. The responsibility is with the shipping companies – the shipper of today is only a ship manager any more, the vessels do not belong to him any more. The exception proves the rule. [“Ausnahmen bestätigen die Regel.”] And here many small ones, allegedly all these members of the middle class, what they also are, have formed shipping companies and have... have polished the golden buttons on their jackets and have then said that they are now ship owners, but they do not own a vessel, because they are all owned by these ship funds, these one-ship-limited-partnerships [“Ein-Schiff-Kommanditgesellschaften”], these tax-saving schemes. #00:05:53-6#
- I: *And who is behind that?* #00:05:54-4#
- E8: All sorts of people. Do ask your parents if they have invested in a ship bond. (Laughing) #00:05:59-4#
- I: *I doubt that. (Laughing)* #00:06:01-3#
- E8: That has been sold down to the very normal population. Like formerly the Bauheim model in... when the East [of Germany] was added. In the sense of investments for old age. Sadly gone askew. #00:06:17-3#
- I: *What does that mean for environmental legislation if I have these interesting ownership structures?* #00:06:25-9#
- E8: That is very different, than you have no real responsibility. The shipping company is doing the ship management that means it is operating the vessel and is collecting a fixed sum from the one-ship-partnership. And it is also getting that. Well and everything that is now... if the ship needs to go into classification, then is gets tough. Because then they need to find money somewhere. The shipping company itself is saying: I provide the crew and care about the operation of the ship and I simply state that I need to go into classification. Dear owner, please make sure that money is available. And if money is not available the vessel is so-to-speak put on the dump and when in doubt it is being sold or scrapped. #00:07:12-2#
- I: *That is unfortunate.* #00:07:14-7#
- E8: Well, we now get into a situation is this year, next year at the latest, where the majority of the German fleet, that is the fleet operated by German shipping companies – they do not fly German flags anymore anyways –, are successively going bankrupt. #00:07:30-6#
- I: *Okay. And you always hear a lot about overcapacities...?* #00:07:38-2#
- E8: That is it. Well, you know, [interviewer], they have plain and simply... they have by way of this structure of a ship fund and thereby the possibility to save taxes, to save personal taxes, because they have founded that as a limited partnership [Kommanditgesellschaft], so that they may, how is that called... I think that falls under the Principle of Transparency [“Transparenzprinzip”] that we are currently employing, in terms of financial law... that therefore means that this limited partnership... the loss or gain of the limited partnership may directly be attributed to my personal income tax.

That is transparent. Thereby it is not the limited partnership being taxed, but the limited partner who is in this KG is profiting from the respective taxation. And is drawing that into his personal income tax. Loss or gain. In the beginning naturally there is always a loss in the concept. Well and evidently thereby we have practically created a tax saving scheme, that due to the tonnage taxing, the ascertainment of profits of tonnage taxing... are you familiar with that? #00:08:53-3#

I: *Yes.* #00:08:54-0#

E8: ...evidently is going excellent as long as the economy is playing along. Because I do not need to tax the real profits, but only this fictitious amount that has been fixed at one point. And then that is going along. Well, then you have, if you have entered with a delay, still this difference value, but well. Apart from that I only have this fixed value, no matter how much I gain with that thing. That has in a whole brought 5.5 billion worth of tax advantages to all the shipping companies over the entire time that the tonnage tax has been in operation according to the ministry. Divided by the owners of the vessels they have gotten something out of it. And that was the motivation. Every time a German may save taxes... you know, one of the books with the largest editions is the Konz – one thousand legal tax tricks... #00:09:51-2#

I: *I would need to...* #00:09:53-6#

E8: As soon as a German may save taxes all thinking about the risks up here is suspended. #00:10:02-1#

[Short interlude talking to employee of E8] #00:10:15-8#

I: *You said that I have a problem in the moment where it comes to classification. Who is bearing liability in the end if a vessel is not complying with certain laws? The owner or the operator?* #00:10:29-8#

E8: If the operator has designed the right contracts the owner is liable. (Laughing) #00:10:35-0#

I: *Thus, it really depends on the contracts?* #00:10:37-1#

E8: Yes, certainly. But he is not so stupid normally. He only does ship operations and then he says: I cannot operate it any more, I have to put that down and then it is over. (Laughing) The owner is liable and the owners are these many many limited partners that have subscribed to this fund – it is then also not tradeable any more, it is a closed fund, it is not being traded any more – that means you need to then find someone who is willing to take over your share with exactly the amount of your share. You will not find anyone evidently, as no one is so stupid if it [the fund] has become non-performing. Well, and in order to use that tax-wise they have been distributing fictitious losses, all losses that could be distributed. That means that they have also taken capital out of this one-ship-partnership in the beginning that is now successively being requested again from the owners, from these poor – well, one cannot say poor – from these tax savers. Well, and they then have to inject additional capital, additional capital, additional capital and if they cannot do that any more the company will go bankrupt. That means that the bank may still, because they have a vessel loan on it, may still secure the vessel, but it

on the hook and see what to do with it. The scrap value is however as a rule not reaching the loan value of the vessel. That's it. #00:12:02-5#

I: *That seems to be the reason why the banks do not have any money any more...* #00:12:05-9#

E8: Certainly. That is why we may hope that the HSH Nordbank [ship financing German bank] will still... it has to hold up for another two years, because then this... how it is called?... this... well, I cannot think of the technical term right now, well, this liability of the federal state is then gone. This guarantee obligation. At the moment, currently, the HSH Nordbank is... the federal states of Schleswig-Holstein and also Hamburg are involved with 15 billion, if the HSH Nordbank is no going under water. (Laughing) In addition... #00:12:35-9#

I: *Will they be able to cope with that?* #00:12:37-0#

E8: In addition to the ten billion that they have already put down. That is why... we have created this crisis ourselves, because we have been the biggest container shipping nation of all times. And we have built these 4000, 8000 TEU vessels on a conveyor belt, like blithering idiots, whether there was a demand or not. And the same like the coal-fired power plants seven or eight years ago have been build based on the motto: Oh, the coal price is increasing, then the price for electricity that we might charge the customers will increase, which is not true any more. Well, because wind energy is stabilizing the whole thing, the price development. And that is how they they calculated in the shipping industry as well. And now we have overcapacities and we do not know how to deal with them. #00:13:35-3#

I: *Will that be neutralized by the economic development of the coming years maybe, this overcapacity?* #00:13:43-9#

E8: What did you say? #00:13:43-9#

I: *Will that be neutralized by economic growth in the coming years?* #00:13:49-4#

E8: No. I rather go by the idea that in the long term fewer goods need to be transported by way of shipping, simply because more and more is being transferred back to Europe and to America, simply because production costs in China are becoming too high. Ultimately it all got started, if you look back at it, with globalisation that is with the creation of... with the shift of basic production to China. That is how it mainly got started... that the services across the Pacific from America and Europe-Asia here got started. And there we again see certain tendencies, that one day this cost advantage is not there so much any more. Then one can rather also handle that with countries closer to Europe. I am thinking towards the direction of Afrika or also towards the East of Europe. And there we would not necessarily need these vessels any more. #00:15:09-9#

[Static noises in the recording]

E8: And on the other hand it is meanwhile happening in the shipping industry that we are using large units, simply because we get by with significantly less personal in relation per cargo unit. And what naturally also has to be taken into account is that the ship

transport is currently practically free of charge, free of cost. Very low costs per transported item. Especially with no so valuable goods. The bottle of wine being transported over here from Australia has a costs volume of 20 Cents at the maximum for sea transport. Well, and that is then... if we would work with the prices that we used to know from land transport then we would never ever do that. Or the ones we knew in former times before containerization, where everything had to be handled by hand.
#00:16:05-9#

I: *Will prices for sea transport increase?* #00:16:11-0#

E8: Yes. It will automatically increase at the moment where we are able to reduce the number of vessels and where we finally put down our cards to see whether we want to go on with this most dirty method of transportation of all times or not. Well, that we then also bring the ecological standards to the level that we have had for a long time on the land. That means emission trading. That is still not foreseeable that something is happening there, but something needs to happen. Well and then this whole issue of exhaust gas treatment that we basically do not know at all in the case of a vessel. The first step. But that is still a laughing stock compared to what we do in the trucks.
#00:17:08-8#

I: *What would have to happen?* #00:17:10-5#

E8: Hm? #00:17:11-6#

I: *What would have to happen with the shipping industry?* #00:17:17-4#

E8: We would have to build up a CO₂ trading system - but one that is actually working, not the one we have at the moment - for the shipping industry. If necessary we really have to – if we do not manage to do that by way of a trading system, which is what I am expecting, that we will not be able to do that – we at least need to agree that CO₂ levies need to be paid on the high seas as well, per ton of CO₂ produced or so and that many levies... and that then needs to be paid into a funds that is placed at some kind of head office preferably at a UNO organization. And that is then distributed to the countries that are in need of it. And that is how one should do it. #00:17:56-4#

I: *Is that realistic?* #00:17:57-8#

E8: At the moment it is unforeseeable. It is unforeseeable, thus we let the maledives sink under water. But there is a little movement coming into the business. There is a little movement coming into it. It is currently not very much foreseeable, but there is a little movement coming into it. #00:18:16-5#

I: *CO₂ is the one thing. What are other things that need to be done?* #00:18:21-0#

E8: We need [to deal with] particle emissions... those are notorious polluters [“Dreckschleudern ohne Ende”] that are travelling the seas. You can see the chunks [of dirt] coming out of their chimney. We are practising garbage incineration on the seas. That is well-known. We are burning the utter hindmost, really the bog from the refineries. We have a massive nitrogen oxide pollution. We have... the sulphur story can be handled, if one wants to, but that is naturally also there still. That is also from the prehistoric times of the diesel engine on the streets, that is a problem from the 80s on

the streets. In street traffic we have long gotten rid of it. Thus, all of that we still have there. We really are still 30 years behind with these things. Nitrogen oxides... well, first of all sulphur oxides, nitrogen oxides, particles, that is soot emissions, CO₂. #00:19:20-6#

[Static noises in the recording] #00:19:27-8#

E8: ...evidently, because noise is transmitted very much differently under water across far longer distances. We have not wasted any thoughts so far on the increases in noise level of these seas [“Verlärmung der Meere”]. We are now starting with the issue of offshore wind energy. But that something is coming from shipping is quite known in the specialist circles of scientists dealing with the issue of mammals in the ocean, but it has not yet reached government committees. Well, we likely have to come up with altogether different concepts for the placement of motors on the vessels. We have to build in noise capsules. Well, that is going to become very costly in the long run. #00:20:14-5#

I: *Are there any aims that have already been reached?* #00:20:19-4#

E8: Starting on the first of January we will have reached a very, very small aim. When we will finally have introduced the SECA areas here and the Americans as well and the Japanese as well than we will at least have started to scratch at the sulphur dioxide emissions. #00:20:35-0#

I: *How much is the population interested in this topic?* #00:20:40-2#

E8: Up to now not at all, apart from those that have been on a cruise, who have been on a cruise ship and who have found the chunks of dirt somewhere at the back behind the chimney or when the wind was coming from the right direction and the clouds of exhaust were flying towards them on the sun deck. #00:20:54-7#

I: *How do political initiatives then work without pressure from the population?* #00:21:02-4#

E8: I believe by way of the environmental organisations, by way of the environmental organisations and there you have here in Germany especially... they are very active... NABU, BUND with their soot-free campaign, soot-free for the climate. They have also come up with this polar bear and such things. They are also the ones that have started to target the cruise ships. At least enough pressure has been built so that AIDA is doing a first attempt now with exhaust gas treatment aboard, that will fail in my opinion, because it is not really possible the way they are planning to do it. #00:21:35-7#

I: *That is also quite interesting. Why is that not possible?* #00:21:38-1#

E8: Hm? #00:21:38-9#

I: *Why is that not possible?* #00:21:40-3#

E8: Well, because this procedure... well, I have not seen it, not seen it in its entirety, they did not want to show me, but they were already half a year delayed. And based on the knowledge that I have as a trained engineer who has dealt with the topic of exhaust gas

treatment for a long time I have my doubts that they can manage to do that in the way that has been presented to me by [employee of AIDA]. #00:22:07-2#

I: *Okay. Where are the problems?* #00:22:10-0#

E8: The problems are, if you... such a diesel engine is a system where everything needs to be intertwined. And you now need to add a real wonderful clean chemical plant into that. And if you do not do that, if you do not coordinate everything with each other, but just add a blackbox somewhere at the end and you proclaim: I now have a soot filter. I also now have a nitrogen oxide filter at the same time – that is not working. Because normally... what you need in order to remove particles from the system will lead to higher nitrogen oxide emissions. (Laughing) We also see that with the Euro 6 trucks. And if you are driving behind such a Euro 6 truck in a tunnel, you can smell that it is a Euro 6 truck. #00:23:01-3#

I: *Oh well, that is interesting.* #00:23:02-1#

E8: Because he is always injecting urea, in order to convert the nitrogen oxide back to nitrogen. For that he needs ammonia and he is doing that by way of this Add Blue System and that is ensuring that one is able to manage this reduction of the nitrogen oxide. It smells of ammonia however, because you always need to overdose a little, because you will not be able control that exactly, because we do not yet have sufficiently precise sensors and fast enough control units which are able to manage it without large nitrogen oxide... without large Add Blue... well, without large ammonia excess. Well, and if you have a soot filter today that is normally designed in a way that the regeneration of the filter is tried with a catalytic coating – the filter material becomes clogged after some time – a regeneration is tried by way of... by the generation of more nitrogen oxides so that they indirectly burn the soot again via a nitrogen oxide reduction. So that they take up the one attached oxide, an oxygen molecule and oxidize the soot at respective temperature conditions. That means you create an incredible surplus of nitrogen dioxide. And that way you are obviously increasing the nitrogen oxide emissions if you are not regenerating at times. Because all of that is not really so much interlinked, not controllable. That is only reasonably manageable if one actually takes the engine control in hand and accepts that a little more fuel is needed. Then it is reasonably controllable. Otherwise it isn't. And our shipping blokes are still miles away from that. #00:25:05-9#

I: *Are, well, is there a problem with the technical solutions on the market or is it simply a problem of deciding how these systems are run?* #00:25:15-7#

E8: No, the technical solution and evidently for once... well, it is a technical solution and we now run the danger that we first of all only have first solutions everywhere and block an overall solution with these first solutions. What is currently under construction for the SECA areas is that they buy wet scrubbers now, that are... you have certainly heard about that already, wet scrubber, dry scrubbers... with a dry scrubber you create plaster, which is fine, because when the coal-fired power plants are successively shut off we need to see again somehow where we get our plaster from. In former times we had mines for that, we mined that in surface mines in the mountains, the plaster. Evidently, we do not want to do that again. Thus, we have to... at the moment we have power plant plaster in use, sheetrock from Knauf... they all use that from the power plant coal desulfurization plant [“Kraftwerkskohleentschwefelungsanlage”]. Well, and if we have

successively shut them off at one point in time we don't have that any more. Then a wet scrubber, if I have the respective volumes, load volumes so that I can store that, would be somewhat suitable, because it is a highly purified plaster. All that is possible. But it is expensive. Thus, the gentlemen go for wet scrubbers. The wet scrubber is only a dilution system, nothing else. And above all, once I have raced the exhaust gases through the wet scrubber I would need to take care of the nitrogen oxides as well. That is difficult however once I have put the exhaust gases in contact with the water and those reaction systems there. Then really after that a catalytic treatment again, because to break open a nitrogen oxide molecule is not very easy to do. [Laughing] #00:27:03-4#

I: Will there be... one day also some kind of reference values for nitrogen oxides coming up? #00:27:04-2#

E8: They are already agreed upon. That has already been prepared, but they actually were supposed to be agreed on in five years time or so, in that order... maybe will be. But they have now postponed that again. Somehow political pressure by our dear ship owners has made sure that that was pushed a little further to the background. But it will come – as sure as eggs is eggs [“So sicher wie das Amen in der Kirche”]. #00:27:32-8#

I: *How does that work with the interest groups at the moment? Who has a louder voice?* #00:27:40-1#

E8: Well, it has been in the last years... the environmental agencies were relatively well placed. Now we have to see, at the moment the ship owners are a little louder, but they are evidently not able to... such an international regulation at the IMO they will not be able to turn back. That is certain as well. There they got up too late. They had to have been up earlier. That is going to be implemented, that is it. And I welcome that. #00:28:10-0#

I: *How has the political interest in the issue of maritime environmental protection developed in recent years?* #00:28:17-6#

E8: Not at all. “Further issues”. [“Ferner liefern”] #00:28:23-0#

I: *We have...* #00:28:25-5#

E8: We are always just a side issue [in organization 8] and when something happens, when a ship is sinking then the fat is in the fire. [“Dann ist der Teufel los”] The politician, no matter if you are in Germany, no matter where you are, is only reacting to disasters and catastrophes. #00:28:43-9#

I: *Yes, well then it is evidently difficult if one wants to talk about normal operations. I have tried to summarize the different types of pollution. Those are all under normal operations. In principle there are seven things how such a vessel may influence the environment. We have been briefly talking about ship waste, ballast water, air pollution...* #00:29:11-0#

E8: Tank cleaner. #00:29:13-0#

I: *... then these protection systems. Tank cleaner?* #00:29:15-0#

- E8: Yes, you may indirectly put it under this heading – ballast tank cleaning. Ballast tanks are also being cleaned, are also being emptied and so forth. That you can here... well, I would phrase that a little more general. #00:29:28-0#
- I: *If you now look at these seven areas – which are currently rather well regulated and where would we still need to do something?* #00:29:40-0#
- E8: We are quite well regulated here in the area of ship waste, at least in traffic navigation we are relatively well regulated. There [pointing] we are also relatively, at least in Europe relatively well regulated, in Germany very well regulated, because we are also controlling that. #00:29:58-8#
- I: *Yes, exactly, that... I have a few questions on that as well...* #00:30:01-6#
- E8: There you should talk to Mrs Proich-Moritz of the BSH. They are very good. She will have nice slides that are also showing how well we are in that. #00:30:11-6#
- I: *I find that very interesting.* #00:30:13-6#
- E8: They are also, maybe they are even on the homepage. Otherwise you need to send my best regards and need to ask whether you may take a look at these slides, because there you can see exactly when in the German North Sea area and Baltic Sea area - In the German area of responsibility they are actually policing, there they also control by air, but it may be guaranteed that just as much oil is leaking around Spain. Nothing is done there. And in the meantime, that is relatively well verifiable. They take samples, they then also take samples and are relatively well able to allocate that to the respective vessel. #00:30:48-3#
- I: *Is that still a big problem?* #00:30:50-4#
- E8: Not so much in German waters any more, because it is being persecuted strictly, but there are no walls between German and non-German waters. Well and that is then possibly slopping over – evidently residues of oily water are still swashing on our beaches. That is still a problem. You can see that in the summer season time and again, if you have those bitumen blocks on the coast. It has improved, it has significantly improved, but basically it is only us there in the Federal Republic of Germany that do it relatively well. I think that Denmark is doing something as well, but Mrs Proich-Moritz may tell you. No matter which direction you go to the West or the East it is getting worse.
#00:31:34-8#
- I: *How is that in the north? The Scandinavian countries?* #00:31:39-3#
- E8: I could not say that right away, but considerably better than in the South. Well, we do that rigorously. #00:31:50-4#
- I: *Are all these areas also being...* #00:31:55-0#
- E8: Something is also regulated on sewage water. (Pointing) There nothing at all, to my knowledge nothing at all. Hull coating systems I do not know if we have regulated that yet. In any case we have regulated parts of it that certain hull coating systems do not

work any more. (Pointing) This is definitely already regulated. There we also already have solutions developed in the meantime. (Pointing) Well, there we also already have regulations in part. For air pollution there are these MARPOL regulations. We have now started with the SECA areas and now according to IMO the CO₂ emissions shall first of all be included, that is documented how high they are. That is then the next step that they are aiming at. The nitrogen oxide act is still under work, but is currently resting a little. And dumping ship waste into the sea I believe we already have rather clean... (Pointing) Here I am not sure. I do not know that. #00:32:46-7#

I: *Ballast water.* #00:32:47-3#

E8: But it is a huge problem. #00:32:51-3#

I: *Which of these regulations for the shipping industry are or signify the greatest costs for the shipping industry? Air?* #00:33:06-4#

E8: Yes and... (Pointing) #00:33:09-9#

I: *Noise, when it is coming?* #00:33:11-0#

E8: If it is coming then it will be really expensive, because it also [influences] basic... it could also mean that we have to do without diesel engines or gas engines and that we have to use a fuel cell. Then it will become really expensive. #00:33:26-2#

I: *Is that technically developed enough that that would be possible? No?* #00:33:31-5#

E8: Not at all. #00:33:34-4#

I: *Then it will be very interesting.* #00:33:35-4#

E8: Well, that is going to be very interesting, because the ship hull is a resonator like no other. #00:33:45-2#

I: *How well are vessel owners or operators, depending on whom we are talking about, informed about environmental legislation?* #00:33:54-1#

E8: Oh, they are well informed. They just wait it out until the last day when they have to implement changes. They have been informed about the SECA regulation for seven, eight years, that they are about to come. #00:34:06-4#

I: *Who is informing them?* #00:34:08-2#

E8: That is done by way of their associations, VDR [Association of German Ship Owners] and the producer association VSM [Association for shipbuilding and maritime engineering]. They are all sitting at the table at the IMO negotiations. They are all sitting at the table. They know about that. #00:34:22-4#

I: *That is of no concern to us. How does the shipping industry prepare for...* #00:34:39-2#

E8: What is of no concern? #00:34:40-5#

I: *All these questions are linked to the first questions. Thus I am skipping the whole paragraph. How is the shipping industry preparing for the new environmental legislation, for the SECAs for example?* #00:34:56-3#

E8: By waiting it out and trying to put the politicians under pressure to stall these regulations again with exemptions. #00:35:07-6#

I: *Is that somehow yielding success?* #00:35:09-6#

E8: No. #00:35:10-6#

I: *Not at all? Okay.* #00:35:11-8#

E8: No, we will now see it at the first of January. #00:35:15-5#

I: *Are there differences between the shipping companies? Are there shipping companies that are better prepared than others?* #00:35:21-7#

E8: That is a tough cost competition momentarily in this area. You know that freight rates in container shipping are now below a thousand euros or dollars, I do not know that now, I think it is dollars that they use for calculations. And they need around 1,500 to suffice. That means they run the business on their last leg. [“Sie fahren das Ding auf dem Zahnfleisch”] That means that they naturally shy away from all costs that are additional costs compared to what they operated on before. Well, there is maybe the one or the other ship owner who acts within the system with more care on the whole, because the vessels also belong to him personally, but he is also not coming round the cost arguments. Well, and if I do something like that, let us take the example of the SECA, I have additional costs of twenty to thirty per cent. If I buy sulphur-free fuel that will cost me around twenty per cent more. I can do it. That is not a problem. #00:36:36-2#

I: *Will they pay... well, can you pass these costs on?* #00:36:38-7#

E8: Yes, certainly. Not everywhere, but in many places. Well, certainly not in the East Asia trade. But there it is also not very relevant, because you only have the short distance in the North Sea and around Japan, for most of the rest of the journey it is not relevant. Where it becomes relevant is the ferry traffic, in the British Channel and in the Baltic Sea. There the costs may be passed on. They argue the contrary, but... [Static noises in the recording] They will certainly ask for slightly higher freight rate for the passage of trucks or trailers and in my opinion they will also receive them, because to drive the same distance with the truck is far too wasteful. That is even more expensive. #00:37:27-0#

I: *Okay. Where are there – you hear this argument time and again that there might be model shifts.* #00:37:34-4#

E8: That is such a stupid ordered study by the ISL. [Institute of Shipping Economics and Logistics, Bremen] #00:37:39-1#

I: *Yes, exactly, I have seen the study as well...* #00:37:42-0#

- E8: They are claiming that cargo will then be moved to the streets, but have not done any calculations what kind of costs that would imply there and whether there is enough truck capacity at all and enough drivers. #00:38:00-0#
- I: *How... I know little about that... how are the freight rate differences between street and... #00:38:09-0#*
- E8: I do not know right now. For the street it depends on... I need to get a truck and I also need to have a driver for that. Well and on the vessel I take... if I take a look at the ferry connection to the Baltic states I do not drive on the ferry with my truck, but only leave the trailer there and let it be pulled onto the vessel and I take my tractor unit and drive on here. That means that it sails across with my trailer alone and it is then taken over at the destination port by another tractor unit. That means I am... these drivers not and the bottleneck is meanwhile with the drivers of the trucks. Why do you think they are starting with gicaliners and such trickery. #00:38:54-3#
- I: *With what? #00:38:55-1#*
- E8: With gicaliners. #00:38:56-6#
- I: *Oh, yes, yes, certainly. How does it look in terms of capacities on the streets. Does one rather have under or over...? #00:39:06-5#*
- E8: Part this part that. In part we have overcapacities because we have much to much roads and too little traffic. And we have the complete opposite. Well you can not say that in general. The German share – if we now look at the Baltic Sea, which is the crucial area according to this ISL study, where some cargo could be lost off this short short sea shipping, could be lost, let me emphasize – there the connection up to the Polish border on the road is reasonably useful, after that is becomes critical. #00:39:44-1#
- I: *Yes, okay. #00:39:47-3#*
- E8: One only forces that on oneself if one can not get rid of the cargo any other way. #00:39:50-8#
- I: *If we now look at the Baltic Sea – for which routes or which goods could one shift cargo at all? #00:40:02-0#*
- E8: For all goods that are rather lightweight, but have some volume. That is electronics and stuff that is carted over from somewhere in Asia. These typical advertised-for-products that come from China. Vice versa from China, from Finland paper over here, paper reels I would deem rather impossible, because the weight plays a relative role there and then you can only load relatively few reels on such a truck. #00:40:37-7#
- I: *On what factors does the decision depend which way of transport I chose at all to transport my good? #00:40:45-3#*
- E8: First of all on the price and then on the reliability. We have recently seen it with the railroad strike... in the instant where my medium of transport... where I need to rebuild my logistic chain as the one who is responsible for the supply of a certain factory

- because my present distributor is not able to deliver within the agreed time frame any more. That does not mean that the goods always actually need to be there within the next day. They do have agreed times when they need to deliver. But when they can not guarantee that any more I need another... then I need to build my transport chain up anew, build my logistic chain up anew and when I do that I do that with the intention of letting it run like that a little time once more. When cargo is gone it is gone. #00:41:41-5#
- I: *Is the railroad also... is that also competition?* #00:41:47-1#
- E8: Pardon? #00:41:47-6#
- I: *Is the railroad also placed in competition to the ship?* #00:41:51-9#
- E8: Well, for the Baltic Sea in the direction of the Baltic states it is not, because they are not able to handle that. And we also still have this lane system change in the area of the border between Poland and the Baltic states. They are still linked to the Russian network and it is thus very complex and it is no competition and for a foreseeable amount of time it will not be. Decades will still need to pass and furthermore the railroad systems there are rather ailing. In the direction of Sweden it is certainly worth a thought. #00:42:31-8#
- I: *Okay. If one now...* #00:42:34-4#
- E8: What is also done. There are a lot of mass transports coming... also coming with the railway from Sweden. #00:42:40-8#
- I: *Yes, okay. If you look into the Southern direction, I do not know, Italy to Europe, to Germany or so... are there any reasonable...* #00:42:53-6#
- E8: There is already a hell of a lot transported via the railway. There is a great great deal done via the railway. The vessel is however also not a serious competitor there because the transport times are simply too long. #00:43:03-5#
- I: *Yes, okay. Well, there is somehow such a theory that one hears about that there could be some kind of shifts, that vessels that now come to Hamburg will somewhere in the Mediterranean...* #00:43:17-8#
- E8: That can happen, can happen. But not because of the SECA areas, but simply because the Hamburg port has no future in the long run, because it is too far away, at the back of beyond [“Am Arsch der Welt”] to speak in explicit terms. It merely has the advantage that a majority of its goods – I can not come up with the number now, was it thirty or was it fifty or seventy per cent? – I don’t know – but a majority is being processed here in the vicinity so that the harbour... there is a rather high value creation around the harbor, also induced by the harbour. But in a foreseeable time it is no longer accessible, at least for the large carriers. Well, and one needs to think about that. Take it for granted that in ten, fifteen years the Hamburg port is no longer called at by East Asia services. #00:44:15-7#
- I: *They are then travelling to where?* #00:44:19-0#

- E8: Rotterdam. First of all: the SECA story is a marginal note. That is not so important. #00:44:27-8#
- I: *It seems... twenty per cent additional costs first of all seems rather a lot...* #00:44:33-0#
- E8: Yes, do forget that with the low freight rates, with the rates that fuels and the rate that these transport costs there make of the total costs of the economic goods... with what there transport costs there make twenty per cent increase are not a problem. If for a bottle of wine instead of twenty cents – add twenty per cent – twenty-four cents... they easily pass that on to the customer. That is not a problem at all. #00:45:01-2#
- I: *How does it look with goods, with goods that only, that are only transported in the SECA area, from Finland...* #00:45:12-9#
- E8: That does not matter. The question is who is making the cheapest offer. Well, and the truck is not getting less expensive neither, because they have a problem with their drivers. That means they need to spend more and more, also more money on the drivers. First of all. We have a congestion problem. That then means that it will become significant somehow. We also cannot do deliberate amounts with foreign drivers now trying to compensate. That is already being done. Now we are also somewhere at the end [“am Anschlag”] there. We are already getting drivers from Turkmenistan and other places in order to manage. Well and at a certain time the limit is reached. The railway is shooting itself in the foot, because it is not willing to accept that they need to be service provider for the forwarder, but they want to compete with the forwarder. That cannot work in the long run. Well and apart from that the railway system would evidently be interesting, at least in certain areas on the main routes, if we were to truly develop that down there. Then one only disembarks one time in... in the Mediterranean one time and is distributing that in the whole of Europe, but there is also a lack of... there is also a lack of preparedness within the EU, Europe, to work on a coordinated approach. We do not even manage... have you read the newspaper today, Hamburger Abendblatt, I don't know if you have taken a look inside... #00:46:44-2#
- I: *I have not seen it yet.* #00:46:45-5#
- E8: Our port industries have yet again stood up, Mr Peters, and... or was it yesterday even, I do not know... have dared to claim that certainly a harbour cooperation is impossible, because Hamburg is the best. That is it. Only Mr Bonz [“Herr Bonz”] is missing. #00:47:11-5#
- I: *Back to this idea of the modal shift. Well, if there is the danger that truck transport becomes less expensive on certain routes suddenly – will there than be political alternatives to work against that?* #00:47:33-0#
- E8: Truck transport is not getting less expensive. #00:47:35-2#
- I: *Certainly, the price is not decreasing, but if for a certain route it suddenly becomes more attractive for the truck, to load the goods on a truck?* #00:47:44-4#
- E8: Trucks are not becoming less expensive, because there is, look onto the White Paper Traffic of the European Commission from the last election period. There it said very

clearly that we need to get the way of an internalization of the external costs, because the road toll, the whole Distance-Cost directive is a joke at the moment. This Vignette directive that the whole thing is based on, our truck toll system, that has been artificially downscaled in comparison to what kind of toll calculation – we also have a railway toll, that is then called trackage fee [“Trassenpreis”] – how the trackage fee is calculated by the rail services. There we need to do full-cost accounting and with the truck toll we have capped everything, capped everything and as cheap as possible. And we also need to adjust that accordingly. Well and that is foreseeable that one day we also need to get into full-cost accounting completely there as well. The logistics association naturally does not like to hear that, but if one does that for the whole of Europe it is not a problem. Then also the difference between the systems that are now still largely financed via taxes as national... where that is in the hand of the nation like in Germany or the Netherland or Belgium and the systems where concessions are handed out like in Italy and in France, where the toll is significantly higher, because they have a concessionaire who need to finance his investments with that. One would have to adjust that and the state need to refinance that just the same. #00:49:12-2#

I: *And that is then also another argument against this argument of modal shift...* #00:49:17-4#

E8: Yes, certainly, that is not working. #00:49:18-9#

I: *...when all modes of transport at the same time ...* #00:49:21-5#

E8: I am always saying: We need equality of arms. Well and that means that I need to give a lot more thoughts on how I deal with this Eurovignette directive, that I eliminate all the cap stories from that. We now are the first ones who start to include air pollution control into the calculations. Other states are not yet doing that. It is permitted, but is also being capped. Then one needs to have a concept for this noise story that also needs to be included in the calculations. Then the accident situations need to be included. Well, I am curious what will come out of that. (Laughing) The truck is not getting less expensive then, I do not need to worry. #00:49:59-8#

I: *No, but that is ... then the system makes sense again.* #00:50:03-6#

E8: Right. #00:50:04-4#

I: *Are there companies that tend to overcomply with environmental legislation?* #00:50:19-7#

E8: No. #00:50:20-8#

I: *Not at all?* #00:50:21-7#

E8: No. #00:50:22-6#

I: *Are there some that undercomply?* #00:50:24-7#

E8: You will not receive information on single companies from me. #00:50:31-5#

I: *No, not single companies...* #00:50:32-5#

- E8: But the tendency to undercomply is immanent. (Laughing) One only does what is currently necessary. And if I do not enforce, which is often forgotten in politics, because that implies cost centers again... In order to enforce I also need people who control what I have put into the law, no matter whether that comes from Europe or the IMO or somewhere else. I also need to enforce. If I do not enforce the subjects to the law will one day notice. #00:51:10-7#
- I: *To what extent is the law enforced currently?* #00:51:15-1#
- E8: What are you aiming at? At what area? You need to differentiate a bit there. #00:51:20-8#
- I: *Then please do differentiate.* #00:51:23-2#
- E8: Well, in the area of shipping in the EU-Europe enforcement is rather good. Well, who is disembarking in EU-Europe... there is a central office, I think they are based in Paris, that coordinate the harbour states controls, or in Lisbon, I don't know right now, but there is a European office that coordinates the harbour state controls and there exist respective lists as well... white list, black list and so forth, who is being controlled more often. I have participated in such a harbour state control in the Hamburg harbour once. That is quite a sincere business. ["Da geht es schon zur Sache"] #00:52:09-7#
- I: *Will there... do they control everything or what may they... are they able to control everything?* #00:52:15-0#
- E8: They do for example... where has the ship waste gone? The books, records are controlled. Where has the sewage water gone? The books on sewage water, the... [Static noise in the recording] All of that is being controlled. The bunker receipts are controlled. Well, also whether he has bunkered HFO or MGO, how much of it, when he has bunkered again,... with that you can evidently project how much he has consumed of what and where he has most likely switched what on and off. Well, there is an awful lot, the whole crew records are being looked into. #00:52:55-5#
- I: *It is possible to forge these records?* #00:52:58-3#
- E8: In principle yes, but not in Germany. In may also be forged in Germany, but with German-flagged ships it is a charade ["Affentheater"] anyway, because it has to be done by German authorities that are staffed only from Monday to Friday and on Friday only until midday. With foreign-flagged vessels is it meanwhile like that today, that the books are largely kept electronically and there are my plausibility checks, control options, well, that it is not altogether easy [to cheat]. Well, if you forge consistently you will one day get bust. (Laughing) #00:53:37-4#
- I: *And in how far may one... if I now burn heavy fuel oil half the way?* #00:53:43-6#
- E8: You get that simply with the bunker receipts. That is not a problem at all. The bunker receipts must be produced and in case of doubt there will be inquiries. And in case of doubt the harbour police will follow up on that – what has he... where has he really bunkered. Well, that can be worked out. #00:54:00-0#

- I: *I have been on a shipping conference this summer. One speaker on the podium was saying: No one of us is expecting to be controlled on that. #00:54:08-9#*
- E8: They have got it coming. [“Die werden sich umgucken.”] I have already probed into that. Well, the ship security that is doing the harbour state controls here is prepared. Starting from the 1st of January it’s getting serious. #00:54:19-4#
- I: *Okay, that is going to be interesting. #00:54:21-4#*
- E8: And I am wondering when the first vessel will be chained up. (Laughing) If they are carrying it so far... There are such cases like this ship here where something was malfunctioning... That can happen now and again. #00:54:40-1#
- I: *Is that working? Can they start on the first of January straight away? Someone said that they would bunker a lot at the end of the year... #00:54:45-7#*
- E8: Well, no, they now have to... Excuse me, that is not an issue at all. Today all have a tank for heavy fuel oil on their vessels, for HFO and then all of them also have tanks for normal gas oil. All of them, because they need to operate on gas oil within the harbour already anyway. There they are not allowed to operate on HFO at all any more. Not any more in Europe, in America, basically everywhere. None of these harbours allows for HFO any more. That exists already and the gentlemen [ironic] can not tell me that they are not able to simply bunker a little bit more of that. And maybe they now need to put out the heating of an HFO tank and then they need to clean it once and then they put... or they don’t even need to clean it, they just need to pour MGO respectively on top of it and Bob’s jour uncle [“Fertig ist die Laube”], because it is lighter anyway and will stay on top of it. All of that is possible. They do not need to talk such nonsense, these gentlemen. Well and I am quite curious about that... because it is possible, as experts have credibly assured me, to see that by way of the respective bunker lists, bunker receipts, which all of it needs to be documented. Also here... fuels, used oil, bilge oil... all of that needs to be attested for. That is meanwhile all included in detail in the IMO... in the respective agreements. Those are the files standing around on the vessel. And partly also kept electronically. #00:56:21-2#
- I: *Are controls everywhere as good as the German...? #00:56:25-8#*
- E8: Let me say that in Europe it is well controlled – and in the United States as well. The Americans are sometimes still much more brutal. But when you look outside of that to Guinea, to Nigeria or to some other place it certainly looks a little different. #00:56:42-6#
- I: *How does it look with the sanctions? #00:56:47-0#*
- E8: ...but those are the harbour state controls. #00:56:47-8#
- I: *Yes. #00:56:48-0#*
- E8: Those are not the flag state controls. That is something a little different. #00:56:52-2#
- I: *How does it look with the sanctions? #00:56:57-7#*

- E8: Well, there we need to see how we will deal with that. They are also regulated respectively. Normally you have to... the skipper needs to make a kind of payment on an account of a few thousand Euros if something... he also has a cash register in the safe aboard so that he is not being chained up for that. If he cannot provide he will be chained up... if there is somewhere a suspicion of a defect that puts the safety of the vessel operation in question he will be chained up. #00:57:40-6#
- I: *There is this OECD study that suggests that it is much cheaper to pay a fine at times than to act in accordance with the law.* #00:57:49-8#
- E8: The fines are not yet very high. There we could again act a little bit. #00:57:55-3#
- I: *Is that done? Is there a tendency that one intentionally... or that one is betting on that?* #00:58:02-3#
- E8: [Interviewer], it is also... I would not say betting on in, well, not as a rule, because you then jeopardize your credibility in some way and many shipping companies need to be certified today, because these large companies like the car producers or the chemical industry have certification systems and the logistic chain is included in them as well. In that way, if you get bust with that you might jeopardize the certification of the supplier to whom you supply and you only do that once, that you are no longer part of the chain. I do not want to exclude that for smaller areas, but the one supplying such big chains or the chemical industry has certain requirements that he needs to fulfil. #00:59:00-8#
- I: *Does that means it also depends a little on the size of the company?* #00:59:05-9#
- E8: Certainly, first of all with the size of the company and for whom I practically... from whom I have received the order. Well, it also depends a lot on the self-monitoring of the logistics sector, within the sector. What does my customer want from me? Has he set himself an objective that he wants to achieve? #00:59:29-9#
- I: *Does that now exist a lot that environmental standards actually...* #00:59:35-0#
- E8: Yes, many are EMAS [Eco-Management and Audit Scheme] certified. Well, if that is enough is another question, but it is coming into operation more and more. And the chemical industry, the car industry is relatively strict. The chemical industry is very brutal on that issue. #00:59:50-3#
- I: *That is very interesting.* #00:59:51-7#
- E8: Well, you can reach a lot more that way than with governmental controls. #00:59:55-6#
- I: *Are there differences between the shipping sectors that container shipping operators rather comply with environmental legislation than tanker or bulk carriers?* #01:00:10-2#
- E8: I do not know, I do not know. I cannot say it in general. To my knowledge it depends a lot on the specific shipping company, thus less on the type of shipping company and the country it is based in. Russian oil tankers are evidently a problem. That is well known. #01:00:29-5#

- I: *Right, but that is then not the flag, but... #01:00:32-8#*
- E8: The owner. #01:00:33-1#
- I: *...the seat. Exactly. #01:00:34-1#*
- E8: The owner. If they fly a Russian flag or have the one of Liberia glued on is largely irrelevant, but the vessel is coming from Russia. #01:00:43-7#
- I: *When... or what prevents shipping companies from complying with environmental legislation? #01:00:51-2#*
- E8: The costs. Plain and simple the costs. That certainly costs something and that needs to... in today's situation where I have incredibly overcapacities on the markets that somehow needs to... I somehow need to receive a return on my investment. I cannot get blood from a stone. ["Ich kann es mir nicht aus den Rippen schneiden."] #01:01:11-0#
- I: *What would you do in that situation? #01:01:15-2#*
- E8: Well, I have already suggested... we have to think about it in politics as well that we actually really also start to scrap vessels. Well, I would very much welcome a European initiative to severely take tonnage out of the market. What is happening at the moment is, if these vessels that are redundant... they are sold to somewhere if you are lucky. But they are not taken from the market. If I have sold them I have gotten rid of them as the German society, but they still exist. I really need to get rid of them. Talking about a house or farmstead one says "warmer Abriss" [literally translated "warm demolition"; colloquial language for demolition of a building by arson in order to receive insurance payments]. That is also possible for a vessel... is called differently there... is also normally not done. Well and I really need to be able to scrap them. Well, scrapping is currently done in Bangladesh and Pakistan and somewhere in China at the beach. That certainly is also not working well. Although they all have a certificate, but in principle it is, well, not state of the art. We thus need to scrap in Europe... and I have already suggested that, that we put a surcharge on the harbour fees and that we pay grants from Europe as well so that we really – a Swedish member of the Green party has addressed that in the European parliament – that we can really scrap vessels here in Europe. That we really get rid of the tonnage, get rid of it. And then we also have work for the shipyards in the East. #01:02:46-3#
- I: *But there are still vessels being build...? #01:02:47-1#*
- E8: Yes. There is basically nothing being build any more in Germany apart from a few battleships and a few special constructions and then that is... but container vessels are not being build here any more. Evidently they are still being built in China, because there are orders and if you have a vessel in your order book it takes three years until it is being delivered to you. What they are building now are the mega carriers, the huge cargo ships. Now they have the 20,000 TEU in the making. #01:03:17-4#
- I: *The macroeconomic forecasts, also the trade forecasts still predict significant increases. #01:03:26-7#*

- E8: Do not trust in any forecast that you have not falsified yourself. That also holds true for that. Well, I do not trust in these forecasts. Evidently we will still have a certain increase somewhere, but the effects that now come into being for example due to the societal changes in China have not yet been included in the calculations. I sometimes have the impression that the economy is more and more going daft on a disdainful fortune telling. [“schnöde Kiekerei”] #01:03:59-9#
- I: *Yes, one should do that once to foresee the macroeconomic development. (Laughing)* #01:04:06-0#
- E8: The result is always true, but only with the March report for the year before, namely when the hard figures are available. (Laughing) Before that it never holds true. Do compare that once. Compare that. It’s never true. #01:04:25-7#
- I: *That is true. May one say that the average age of a fleet is a good indicator as to the environmental friendliness?* #01:04:36-0#
- E8: No. #01:04:36-8#
- I: *Why not?* #01:04:38-4#
- E8: Because in the last decades, at least with certain... well, one can not say it so generally. For certain things yes – regarding waste water and such things. Certainly a lot more has been done in modern ships than before, also ship waste and so forth. Regarding the issue of air pollution it is getting a little more complicated. There it is not that straightforward, because rather little has been done in the development there. #01:05:12-7#
- I: *Where do the environmentally vessels come from? Well which ones – if you take a look – which ones are the environmentally friendly ones sailing – what is defining them?* #01:05:25-8#
- E8: Currently you can find them in Scandinavia. Those are the LNG vessels in ferry service. #01:05:34-4#
- I: *Why are they in Scandinavia?* #01:05:36-4#
- E8: Pardon me? #01:05:37-4#
- I: *Why are they in Scandinavia? Is it also a cultural question?* #01:05:42-1#
- E8: Because Norway has enough money to pay for this indulgence, plain and simple. And they have enough natural gas to also liquidize that and sell that to somewhat reasonable prices. #01:05:52-8#
- I: *Okay, well, then we know what we need to do. [Ironic] Well. Are there any technical developments that are currently... current technical developments that may make it easier for the shipping industry to sail environmentally friendly?* #01:06:12-1#
- E8: Yes, certainly. If we would finally change to a gas, natural gas motor we would be much much further ahead, much much further ahead. #01:06:22-7#

- I: *What is preventing the shipping industry to do that? #01:06:25-7#*
- E8: Let me do a rubbing movement between index finger, middle finger and thumb. Wedge. [“Knete”] #01:06:32-0#
- I: *Is it only the money? #01:06:33-0#*
- E8: First issue: Wedge. Second issue: The missing legal security at the moment still that will however be removed within the next year according to my knowledge, this insecurity. #01:06:48-3#
- I: *That comes from...? #01:06:49-5#*
- E8: Because the IMO regulation had not yet been adapted. For example according to SOLAS you may, you have to... SOLAS normally demands that you... well, really prevents that you are operating a gas-powered vessel safe from when you are transporting gas. Due to the security of the crew. One can certainly also... solve the security another way, therefore some rules include provisions that need to be adapted. #01:07:22-5#
- I: *Okay, well. Yes, that means that as soon as that happens you expect an increase...? #01:07:29-4#*
- E8: Well, we have additional costs... we have additional costs at that point, plain and simple. That has to be made clear. They first of all need to be absorbed. Well, after than one can do some thinking that one then also maybe institutes knock-on financing via public agencies then as well at a certain time. One may think about that. It is also being thought about that in all earnestness actually. Well and I also already see that... well, from what I hear from the ferry shipping companies the willingness to deal with these issues is high. The Baltic Sea shipping companies really earnestly want to switch to LNG for the ferries. And we are already getting the first LNG ferry in the North of Germany now next year between Cuxhafen and Heligoland. It is at the moment being built there in Berne in the shipyard. #01:08:21-0#
- I: *Yes. These additional costs - do they amortize themselves or...? #01:08:26-5#*
- E8: It depends a little on how the price for the gas delevops. The gas, the price of gas, depends a lot on in how far Japan powers its atomic reactors up again, because they currently buy up all available liquidized natural gas on the market and thus bring up the prices evidently. The price for liquidized natural gas is more volatile than the price for HFO. That is a little bit the problem at the moment. #01:08:59-4#
- I: *Yes, that is then certainly also a risk appraisal. #01:09:02-2#*
- E8: Certainly. In the beginning it is a little bit more expensive, but you also no longer have difficulties with retrofitting, if you design that properly with a real gas motor and not with these dual fuel motors. That is not with one of these altered [“umgefriemelt”] diesel motors, but if you built in a real gas motor, which however is currently very seldomly available. Then you can also calmly look at the air pollution – “Not of interest to me.” #01:09:32-5#

- I: *In how far are these motors appropriate for all vessels or all vessel types?* #01:09:39-6#
- E8: Retrofitting you can basically forget. Retrofitting you can forget, because the necessary alterations at the tanking systems and around that are unaffordable. #01:09:46-8#
- I: *That means, how... or may... are there things that I can do with existing vessels?* #01:09:53-4#
- E8: Yes, certainly. You can put a chemical plant behind it, but that is about it. Apart from that: Oven. What I already said before: scrapping, get rid of it! In modern vessels you often already have dual fuel motors that are already preliminarily set up so to speak. There you can do something. But with what these old holes are – forget it. There you also in addition have difficulties simply with retrofitting acceptably for the SECA. It mostly only works with this... if you do not also want to sail on marine gas oil in the end it only works as well with a wet scrubber, with this dilution process that takes place in the water. It's a complete con. #01:10:36-9#
- I: *If we look at the SECA again. How is the business model of the shipping industry influenced by this piece of environmental legislation?* #01:10:46-9#
- E8: Yes, the fuel costs [static noises in the recording] but if by the costs, that are necessary due to the scrubbers... the utilities costs increase somewhere between fifteen and twenty per cent, one has to see it like that. #01:11:02-0#
- I: *Are there any differences between the shipping companies.* #01:11:04-9#
- E8: No. They all have to get someplace somehow. #01:11:07-1#
- I: *Equally expensive for everyone?* #01:11:09-0#
- E8: The bunker prices are... yes, the one maybe has little bit larger tank that he sometimes may wait a little when the price is still dropping further, but in principle they are the same for everyone. #01:11:17-9#
- I: *Do you expect a bearing on the freight rates?* #01:11:26-6#
- E8: Yes, certainly, if... I mean, but we have already said that in the beginning, naturally if my utilities costs are higher than I also have to change something at the freight rates. Then I can think about what may be accepted. That's it. #01:11:39-9#
- I: *What are other influencing factors on the freight rates?* #01:11:43-6#
- E8: That is certainly always the system supply and demand. That means I need to find a customer for the offered freight rate as well. If I do not find one I have give some thought to the question if I want to operate on a smaller profit margin. And if I do not want to do that then my mill might stop grinding altogether and is contributing a profit margin of zero. There one needs to calculate thoroughly which way one wants to go. #01:12:14-1#

- I: *Which factor plays the largest role? That is what has the biggest influence on freight rates? #01:12:23-6#*
- E8: Well, the labour cost make first of all for the largest share. Quite clearly. That is why ships are flagged out in the end. We only practically have a hundred and a few vessels under German flag, trading vessels. That is negligible. That is why ships are flagged out as much as possible to decrease labour costs. Above all also the crew regulations. The rules are better under foreign flags. We are over-regulated in that field. #01:12:54-6#
- I: *Does the flag have any influence on environmental legislation? #01:13:00-5#*
- E8: No. #01:13:00-9#
- I: *Not at all? #01:13:02-1#*
- E8: That has no influence. Everything that is regulated at the IMO, well if you get here with such a flag then you cannot escape from harbour state controls, if you really have such adventure-flags then. You can expect that where ships normally change flag to... Liberia, what else do we have... yes, well where ships normally change flag to, especially Liberia is by the Germans... the flag systems there was founded by them. That is highly efficient and consumer-oriented. Well, that is not a bad flag. (Laughing) The reputation is not necessarily bad. They simply have used all options that a German administrative system yields just very badly. (Laughing) #01:13:58-6#
- I: *In how far does the size of the company have an influence on how expensive it gets for the company, the environmental legislation? #01:14:07-9#*
- E8: Yes, company size certainly has an influence in such a way that the more vessels I have the more... the total sum is certainly getting larger. Per vessel it has practically no influence, per vessel the costs are more or less always the same. Maybe for smaller shipping companies it is even... if I only have one vessel and that is so old that I practically cannot acceptably retrofit that, but actually need to operate on the more expensive fuels I might even maybe have a disadvantage. That can happen if I cannot retrofit a scrubber, because I simply do not have the space or something else. Then I have to operate on the more expensive fuel. Then I evidently have a cost disadvantage. #01:14:49-9#
- I: *What one hears at times is that the small ones maybe have the biggest problems, respectively maybe somehow also... #01:15:00-8#*
- E8: Certainly, if you have the fewest vessels. That is the problem and you cannot replace them very regularly, because there is evidently always an investment behind that and a vessel costs a few million. #01:15:12-4#
- I: *Do you expect a consolidation of the market? #01:15:16-9#*
- E8: Yes, certainly. I have said that first. I do expect that we need to dispose of half of the fleet [“die Hälfte der Flotte in den Ofen schieben”]. We easily need to dispose of 1,500 container vessels out of 3,500. #01:15:29-0#
- I: *Is that then half the companies leaving the market? #01:15:33-1#*

- E8: No. #01:15:33-5#
- I: *Will companies leave the market?* #01:15:35-6#
- E8: Yes. #01:15:36-1#
- I: *Okay. What kind of consequences does that have?* #01:15:40-9#
- E8: Very few. There are a few jobs less in Germany. But not so drastic. #01:15:48-5#
- I: *Not in such a way that then suddenly the prices might be influenced even more...?* #01:15:53-9#
- E8: Yes, certainly, that will happen like that. Evidently then, when the market... the demand evidently stays the same. The number of suppliers is brought to its knees. That means that the number of vessels is decreasing and thus also higher freight rates can be achieved. I again get into a zone where we maybe get from a customer market to a supplier market or where we achieve that it is at least for once to some extent equal. #01:16:22-1#
- I: *Is that a desirable development?* #01:16:24-6#
- E8: Yes, because what we had before has been pushed by Germany due to tax saving reasons. That was an undesirable development despite them always saying... the ship owners always claim that it is a cyclical up and down that we have had every five years. That was true before, but then we have just now in the... when the Bauheim scheme in the East [of Germany] failed at the end of the 90s... when they all have already been running in the red enough in the East they have entered into ship funds. And we have shifted to the tonnage tax... that was after 2000, shortly after 2000... then the boom of ship funds started. There we have barked at the wrong tree. [“Wir haben uns verspekuliert”] We have created a bubble. #01:17:09-7#
- I: *Damn. (Laughing) One always gets the feeling: Another bubble. Which shipping companies struggle the most to adjust to environmental legislation?* #01:17:28-1#
- E8: In principle those who have not earned much money, who do not really have reserves. Well, the very small ones, those that only have one, two vessels, for them it is evidently the hardest. Who maybe also lack the expertise. Who also in the Ship Owners Association not really... who maybe are not even a member. One somehow needs to prepare for that, one needs to receive information. #01:18:03-9#
- I: *For whom is it the easiest?* #01:18:07-7#
- E8: It is not easy for anyone. (Laughing) That is costly for all of them. Those that are relatively well present in the committees still have it the easiest, because they know about developments early on. That means they COULD set aside reserves in time, could set up accruals, at least to absorb the risk, the financial risk with reserves in the accounts of the previous years, if the fiscal authorities play along. #01:18:45-9#
- I: *Is that being done?* #01:18:48-3#

- E8: If one is a real entrepreneur who does not want to imperil one's company one will do such a thing. (Laughing) #01:18:55-7#
- I: *Yes, well, the question is then how well the shipping industry is preparing for this development?* #01:19:01-5#
- E8: Badly, badly. You have seen [German shipping company]. [German shipping company] is basically bankrupt, but you are not allowed to use that. What I have just said. #01:19:12-0#
- I: *No, that is being anonymized anyways. Well, all names will be...* #01:19:15-6#
- E8: No, but do not use the statement neither, because in principle it only survives because the [German state] has entered into that. (Laughing) Without the [German state], without the investments of [politician of German state] back then three or four years ago it would have been the end of it. #01:19:36-4#
- I: *They still have nice offices.* #01:19:40-3#
- E8: Yes, you have certainly already been there. #01:19:42-4#
- I: *Yes, I have already talked to everyone.* #01:19:48-6#
- E8: Yes, the golden buttons are still well polished. I also received a nice invitation to a shipowner's dinner again. #01:19:55-5#
- I: *Oh, interesting, yes.* #01:19:57-3#
- E8: But I am not going – to the Atlantic [Hotel in Hamburg]. #01:20:00-4#
- I: *They certainly have nice food.* #01:20:02-0#
- E8: Yes, but I am not doing that to myself. #01:20:06-6#
- I: *I always find it interesting to talk to all sides.* #01:20:09-7#
- E8: Yes, I do go to... let me say it like this: I do go to professional appointments, I do go there. Certainly I talk to the ship owners. I am certainly doing that. #01:20:17-1#
- I: *Yes, certainly, but it is evidently also a political statement to go to dinner with them.* #01:20:21-8#
- E8: Right. And they draft it with evening gowns, with smoking and I am not doing that to myself. I am saying to myself: Gentlemen, make sure that you for once invest your money somewhere else where you actually need it. I can pay for my dinner myself. But that is Hanseatic. (Laughing) #01:20:47-5#
- I: *I am also coming from the North. I can very well relate to that. In order to take a step back from environmental legislation – How does situation of the shipping industry look in general?* #01:21:01-9#

- E8: Well, they complain a lot like any industry sector, but all in all we have... we need the shipping industry, we cannot do without them. For the German shipping industry it looks catastrophic. #01:21:18-6#
- I: *What kind of developments do you expect for the upcoming years?* #01:21:22-5#
- E8: If no change of direction, no rethinking appears with the German shipping industry, we are now only talking about the German shipping industry, we would not have a German shipping industry any more in foreseeable time.
#01:21:36-5#
- I: *Is such a rethinking foreseeable?* #01:21:38-9#
- E8: Currently I do not see it yet. #01:21:41-3#
- I: *In which direction does one need to think?* #01:21:44-8#
- E8: I need to regulate the crew regulation, come down significantly with my demands. I need to think about the wage and salary pay scales. I need to become competitive at least with flags that have a good reputation. #01:22:18-8#
- I: *What are the biggest chances and risks for the industry?* #01:22:24-2#
- E8: Which industry? #01:22:25-9#
- I: *For the shipping industry, the German one.* #01:22:27-9#
- E8: Which one do you mean now – the vessel operators or the ship builders? #01:22:31-7#
- I: *Are there any differences?* #01:22:33-3#
- E8: Yes, certainly. #01:22:38-5#
- I: *Yes?* #01:22:39-5#
- E8: For shipbuilding I only see chances in specialist fields any more and for that they would need to come down from their high horse first of all that they are only naval architects, that is artists that are creating vessels. They also need to become service providers for retrofits and above all also for scrappings. They have not yet managed that step.
#01:23:05-1#
- I: *How does it look for the operators?* #01:23:07-0#
- E8: Well, the operators... the biggest risks are simply the overcapacities and the non-willingness to take responsibility for the whole systems of shipping as well. That means to let others do the training for once. #01:23:28-2#
- I: *Are there any chances?* #01:23:30-7#

- E8: Chances for the shipping industry? Yes, certainly, if we manage it, if we show national commitment and also show that we actually, with an updated crew on the vessels also with largely European staff we can also be competitive. But for that ver.di [German labour union] also needs to come down from its high horse for once. They still have 5,000 members in this area and they are making a fuss [“ein Bohei”] as if it is the end of the world. If we take the labour agreement by the horns a little... I have already for all intents recommended: Why are you not terminating all these labour agreements? #01:24:19-8#
- I: *If one now... #01:24:22-8#*
- E8: We now have, according to the labour agreement, we are paying a German captain on a German-flagged ship 10,000 Euros, a third officer with a mariner’s certificate [“der sein Patent ausfährt”] today receives 6,000 Euros. 6,000. Take a look at what you receive at [German university]. #01:24:45-5#
- I: *Little. I have already talked to a captain as well, that is... #01:24:50-1#*
- E8: It should not be more than remuneration group TVöD 13. #01:24:55-6#
- I: *And a part-time position. I have a child. (Laughing) #01:24:58-6#*
- E8: I assume that in earlier times it was also normal that that was split up. (Laughing) #01:25:06-1#
- I: *No, exactly. #01:25:07-5#*
- E8: Well, we also expect that they are still taxed normally, that they are also still paying pension insurance, social insurance contributions, okay. That they are not doing in Denmark. We could find solutions for that as well... in Italy neither. But then you need to be prepared to have their cards put on the table and to say okay, we as the government maybe incur the entire social insurance contributions, make them tax-free, but for that the pay goes down to 3,000 Euros and then you are suddenly competitive. That means someone who needs to do third officer here in order to make use of his sodding mariner’s certificate [“scheiß Patent”] as a navigating officer and who would sign up on a vessel for 3,000 Euros will not be able to do it, because a non-German vessel, non-German-flagged vessel will not take him. They will not haul in the trouble. Well, and on a German-flagged ship the ver.di labour agreement is against it. #01:26:05-7#
- I: *Why are they still being hired then? #01:26:08-6#*
- E8: They are not being hired. Currently we are training at the navigation schools like crazy. #01:26:14-7#
- I: *And they are then all unemployed? Crazy, yes. #01:26:21-3#*
- E8: I have suggested to the ship owners to form a dual study program [“dualer Studiengang”] for them – there exists one already in Wismar that is not working. A dual study program also means that you hire the people in the beginning of their studies and let us see if there is something about that in the labour agreement. There will not be anything in the labour agreement. They you can negotiate that yourself. Do think for once! And then

- you have securely tied them to you for five years to the pay scale work. But the golden button lobby has not yet come so far. #01:26:59-0#
- I: *Astounding. If we now take a look at these risks – what role does environmental legislation play for the shipping companies compared to other things that occupy them?* #01:27:14-0#
- E8: It is one issue, one overall issue. They are naturally always trying... environmental legislation is always the political issue, the issue with which they they to put politicians under pressure. But other business sectors do the same things, because it is always said ecology, we can only afford that if we have earned enough money, which is evidently nonsense. Without ecology we may one day not be able to earn any money any more, because there is nothing left. We currently see that in China and we have also seen it in the Ruhr area in the 60s. #01:27:51-9#
- I: *I still have three questions.* #01:27:53-9#
- E8: Oh, that is good. Then we are almost through. #01:27:55-9#
- I: *Are there any issues that we have not yet discussed that would be important for my understanding of the problems?* #01:28:04-7#
- E8: Oh, [interviewer], I cannot tell you that. For that one would need to go into marketing maybe as well. (Laughing) #01:28:09-8#
- I: *Something that comes to mind that is still of importance...* #01:28:15-1#
- E8: You really have to... well, something that is important to me: Take a look at the system how we came to be in this bubble. Well, I would urgently advise you to take a look at that. At my homepage you find, you find a speech there that I have once held in front of the chamber of commerce. Then you also find something that I have once done at the [another organization]. I do not know how well that is documented, you will have to take a look. Then... well, there you find a lot of things. Otherwise you can also still call my office in [German city] and call [name of employee of E8]. He can still send you the one or the other thing again. I tend to... also at the chamber of commerce I have found rather drastic words. Naturally the representatives of the Ship Owners Association were not amused, but in the after-dicussions they realize: You are right, [E8], you are absolutely right. And if you talk to ship owners that are in the association then the German Ship Owners Association is split in two. There are on the one side these golden button ship owners like [name of a former manager of a large German shipping company] who levitate somewhere very far away and then there are the small ones. And now someone takes it over from somehow from down there in Leer [German city] who comes from the small firm sector. I hope that things will get a little better in the Ship Owners Association. If not they need to split up unto two associations. They can not go on like that. #01:29:46-0#
- I: *Are they then... is the small firm sector concerned differently or do they have different problems?* #01:29:50-8#
- E8: That is... certainly... it has to, it needs solutions for the implementation. The big ones have their departments for that. He needs to do it himself, the owner. #01:30:05-0#

- I: *Can they manage that? #01:30:08-5#*
- E8: To a certain extent yes, but they need additional services for that and that would normally be a talk for the association who could organize that. But it is not doing that, because it only ever looks at the big ones. #01:30:23-0#
- I: *Who is helping them then? #01:30:26-1#*
- E8: A little bit the association, but it is all getting there very late. #01:30:29-2#
- I: *Are the classification societies helping? #01:30:31-7#*
- E8: Pardon? #01:30:32-8#
- I: *Are the classification societies helping? #01:30:33-7#*
- E8: Yes, certainly, for cash. They do everything, everything for money. #01:30:38-8#
- I: *Yes, well, that is then again out of question for the small ones. #01:30:41-9#*
- E8: Yes, certainly. I somehow need to get through that thus I need to talk to them. There is absolutely no way around that. Without the classification society you cannot go forward. Thus you need to talk there. #01:30:54-6#
- I: *Are there other experts that you can think of that I should urgently talk to? #01:31:00-4#*
- E8: Do talk to Mr Marquardt, if you have not already been there, of the VSM. Have you already been there? #01:31:07-0#
- I: *No, not yet. #01:31:08-1#*
- E8: Do go to the VSM, send greetings from me and go to Mr Marquardt. That is the one who does the engineering there, who is also sitting in the IMO committees or otherwise to Mr Löpen, who is the leader of the director of the VSM. That is at the shipbuilding naval engineering. Do go to Rolf Nagel of the Flensburger Schiffsbauengesellschaft. He has a project on emissions that is on modern emission optimized shipping. That is worth the while. I have again been there as well. Not Ralf Nagel, not this, well, this speech bubble from the Association of German Ship Owners from Bremen. It does NOT make sense to talk to the maritime coordinator of the government, if you get to him anyway, which I do not believe, but I would save myself that. #01:32:02-4#
- I: *What I have been wondering about: I have taken a look at the Ministry of Transport if I can find a contact, but I have... I had the feeling they are not dealing with this topic at all. #01:32:12-0#*
- E8: No, there is one, but if she is allowed to answer I do not know. But [employee of E8] can tell you, how she is called. I have already forgotten that. Oh, the power has broken down in [German city] again. How is she called... well... you could talk to Achim Wehrmann, leader of the subdivision shipping, if you have not yet talked to him. He is

also responsible for the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency of Germany [“Bundesanstalt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie”]. You should talk to Mrs Proich-Moritz at the BSH and with Mr Wehrmann. But there is one more, who is sitting in the committees, I do not know the name. There you can call [employee of E8] if he still knows the name. When I see her I know how she is called. Well, then I know who that is, but I cannot think of the name. #01:33:33-4#

I: *I also have it with names...* #01:33:34-8#

E8: Apart from that apart from Wehrmann no one is really occupied with... those that are occupied with that are sitting in this subdivision. And maybe it is worthwhile again via the Ministry of the Environment. At least it was in earlier times. Or the Umweltbundesamt. To ask again in Dessau. #01:33:57-8#

I: *How is it with the European level? Is that worth the while?* #01:34:01-5#

E8: Talk to Mr Marquardt. He can tell you something about that, but it is mainly controlled over the national bodies. #01:34:11-6#

I: *That means directly from IMO to the national bodies?* #01:34:14-6#

E8: Exactly. #01:34:15-1#

I: *Because the EU now also has their own...* #01:34:20-5#

E8: Certainly, but there are also Marquardt and co sitting here and they are basically copying the IMO regulation there and put them into practice. And enforce them here as an EU regulation then. They have done that. But the real work has taken place in the IMO bodies and not at the EU. #01:34:38-8#

I: *Is there anything you would still like to tell me?* #01:34:44-7#

E8: Not really. I have told you enough. I believe. #01:34:48-4#

I: *Yes, right, then I am through. Very many thanks. I am now switching this off.* #01:34:55-2#

Interview No 9

Date: Thursday, 4 December 2014, 9 am

Duration: approx. 93 minutes

Method of contact: Contact was established via a common friend who told the researcher about being befriended with an expert who could be of interest for the

research question. After several attempts E9 could be persuaded to talk to the researcher. An interview date was set to 27 November 2014 and then reset to 4 December 2014, where the interview took place at 9 am in the morning (initially planned at 10 am).

Interview situation: The interview took place in the office of the researcher. E9 and the researcher were sitting at a comfortable speaking distance at a little table at the office. Water was available at the table. The conversation was held without any interruption and lasted about an hour and a half. The interviewee had to leave promptly for another meeting afterwards.

The conversation was very friendly and open. E9 showed interest in the questions and thought thoroughly about his answers in order to provide as much valuable information as possible. A number of research assumptions were refuted by the expert, leading to new intelligence on the research questions. Some topics could not be deeply discussed, as the expert had no knowledge on all subjects, but E9 could provide very deep knowledge and experience in other fields.

E9: I have no idea what you want to know. #00:00:04-1#

I: *We will see on what kind of questions...* #00:00:06-7#

E9: Just start. Ask away. #00:00:08-3#

I: *Right, ease up. It is also interesting for me if you have nothing to say. (Laughing)*
#00:00:14-4#

E9: Yes, then start. #00:00:15-7#

I: *Okay. I am trying to explore trade effect of current environmental legislation, if there are any. And that is why I ask myself first of all in what way environmental legislation has an influence at all on the shipping industry at the moment. I am currently doing a round of expert interviews and you are one of my experts today. Exactly. I am asking a few questions of different issues, also how much you have to do with environmental legislation in your day-to-day business. Exactly. Everything is being anonymized and I am recording it, just that you know. What are you currently doing? How does your daily routine look?* #00:01:01-2#

E9: Well, I am chief mate. Yes, my daily routine really consists of... that among other things I am naturally also the garbage manager. That means that I am the one who is trying to implement the company-own environmental policy aboard more or less to the best of my knowledge and belief. Among other things I am very regularly phased into the sentry so-to-say aboard. That means a three-watch-system, thus every day I do an eight-hour-watch at sea and in addition I just do everything else as well. Well, I have all my deckhands below me. That means I am doing maintenance, that means upkeep, cargo

handling, cargo care, in the harbour that is evidently my main job loading and unloading the vessel, well, ballast water is certainly also such a big issue. That is now... also more and more put into the spotlight. What else? Yes, safety officer, ship security officer, that is me as well, that is responsible for security, for drills, for... yes ISPS-relevant [International Ship and Port Facility Security Guide] things. Well, the one who more or less runs the show so-to-say. #00:02:20-8#

I: *How is that working with the ballast water now?* #00:02:24-6#

E9: Ballast water now exists on the new objects of our company; there we have such a ballast water treatment facility. But that is now coming more and more. I do not know, I think 2017 or so I think it comes into force. That our ballast water that we take respectively also discharge into the environment again, yes, that we need to treat that. Well, microorganisms need to be devitalized and there are certain requirements, ballast water act something, I do not have it at the top of my head, where exact target values and parameters are written down that we need to comply with or rather that the system needs to fulfil. And yes, but in principle it is already the case with us that we have a so-called clean ballast company policy. That means out at sea we take... we have about 200 miles distance from land and 2,000 metres water depth, that is this reference value where we take water. That also always depends a little on what we are able to do. Well, sometimes it is simply the case that we are forced to also take water in waters near the coast or to drain water because of different loading conditions, flotation depth restrictions, where you just need to take care that you do not have too much water aboard, because due to that you are diving in deeper logically and then you cannot enter the harbour any more at certain times. Well, that actually is an important topic for me. Well, in the harbour I am also occupied a lot with ballasting. On the large vessels for example, if you are coming into Hamburg we now need to pass under this Köhlbrandbrücke here. [Bridge in Hamburg] 30,000 tons of water just for ballast. Exactly. And these new systems are now also able to devitalize these microbes and so forth if there are any in there and to filter the mud above all and so forth. #00:04:18-2#

I: *Does that have any influences on the way you operate your vessel?* #00:04:26-7#

E8: Yes, in any case that is first of all a beastly technical effort for us. Those are incredibly complex systems that are still not working a hundred per cent fail-safe. Well, we have these things on the new vessels now and that still is such a trial-and-error story. Well, we have tremendous problems with them. Well, that they run fail-safe. It also has to fit... what I need to say... also somehow needs to fit into the work flow. Well, you do not want to busy yourself with correctly adjusting the system all the time. There are very, very many valves and pressures and so on, you need to make sure that all of it fits and the pumps also one day need to operate fail-safe. That means... yes, this system causes a lot of problems at the moment and is also extremely expensive. Well, everything that breaks down always immediately costs an incredible amount of money. #00:05:15-4#

I: *And who is doing all these adjustments? Are you doing that?* #00:05:19-4#

- E9: I am doing that. I am operating the system in general as the one who also in any way together with the officers in charge of the watch is the only one who is allowed to touch the ballast water system at all. That is very clearly regulated. Who is allowed to operate a pump at all and who is not. Those are pumps that have up to 2,000 cubic meters an hour. That means that if you do not watch out or something the tank will flow over very fast. That means a lot of attention always needs to be given to that. Yes, and evidently in cooperation with the engineers that are aboard. Well, that is always divided into sections: deck area, machine area – and that is already falling under the area of the machine in cooperation with me who is operating the thing. Well, if something is not working I evidently have to, if I cannot solve it myself, I evidently have to call any engineer and tell him: Here, take a quick look what we have here. Exactly. #00:06:05-9#
- I: *Who is teaching you that?* #00:06:09-8#
- E9: Oh god. Who is teaching us that? Basically in shipping a lot is simply learning by doing and taking a manual and reading how it is done. #00:06:20-4#
- I: *That means you are getting the system aboard and...* #00:06:22-7#
- E9: Yes, I have already received an instruction from the people who produce that, well, from the producer. He is anyway always here, because something is broken all the time. But most of all it is really trying it out and these systems are new. Nothing existed before and for that reason it is incredibly difficult with the... you cannot rely on experience, but you simply have to try a little how it works best. And well, really a training in the sense that you are now doing a seminar is maybe also not really necessary. You have also acquired basic skills during your studies, let me say. That is not rocket science, that thing. One just needs to kind of understand how it works and how it works fail-safe above all for the one operating it and that is currently the problem a bit. #00:07:10-1#
- I: *Okay, okay. What would happen now if the thing did not work? Does that have any kind of consequences for the ship?* #00:07:17-2#
- E9: No, there is then a large button called emergency bypass and then you do it the conventional way. Then you are just very conventionally pumping the water out or yes, you take it and you render it back to the environment. Well, that button exists luckily. (Laughing) #00:07:35-4#
- I: *That is certainly very good to know in an emergency.* #00:07:38-5#
- E9: Yes, yes, certainly. It is absolutely essential that the ballasting system is working, otherwise we cannot operate. That is very, very important. #00:07:47-5#
- I: *Back to the beginning. Since when are you working in this area?* #00:07:55-3#
- E9: I have started as watch officer during my studies in 2006. That is when I started. Well already... #00:08:07-5#
- I: *A few years of experience meanwhile, yes.* #00:08:09-0#

- E9: Well, I first started... after the university entrance diploma ["Abitur"] I trained to be a ship mechanic first. I have first started very Jack-like. Well, mainly I have worked rather in the machine. Then I have one day thought: That is nothing for eternity, do something else. #00:08:23-9#
- I: *Interesting. Are there any changes in your working environment where you can say that they attributed to environmental legislation?* #00:08:34-7#
- E9: Well, with certainly this ballast water story is more and more coming into focus and that does have an effect I would say. What is for example related to this MARPOL Annex V story, that is garbage record book, that story for me so far does not mean that I can say that much has changed, because it has always been that way. In our company we have "no garbage overboard", that means we do not through anything over the railing or something. Well, I know from many colleagues that in the 70s they have thrown everything over board. They even had a garbage chute in the back. And that does not exist anymore and that is also absolutely being... very strictly... #00:09:16-2#
- I: *Well thus it is not only with you?* #00:09:17-9#
- E9: I think in the meantime it is almost everywhere like that. You never know what they do out at sea, but with us I can just say, well, also with a very clear conscience, with us nothing, well, first of all naturally no oil is pumped over board somehow, if at all only over this oil separator and yes, garbage is being collected and disposed of at land and that is more or less my daily routine really. I have someone naturally who is doing that for me. In the end I am just the one supervising that, the one who is documenting that, who makes sure that it looks proper. For me that is a small subdomain that normally works automatically, because everyone knows to throw his garbage in the garbage bag and normally the 25 people on average that are on board know that too. #00:10:00-9#
- I: *With the oil over board... is that even still possible?* #00:10:03-5#
- E9: Yes, you can do that through... oil over board is not possible anyway, but there exists a so-called oil separator on board. That means that so-called machine bilge water and all the oil emulsive water naturally may not be pumped over board just like that and that is going through a so-called oil separator. That works with deep coal filters and I don't know how many things, also a very complex thing and there is such a 15 ppm monitor attached, just like for bilge water, that is for the cargo holds. There it may happen that a container is leaking or somehow there... all that is a little bit oily and the water is not being pumped over board. Well, that always goes through the oil separator. Always through to the so-called 15 ppm. And 15 ppm, as far as I know there do not yet exist any big restrictions regarding distances from any coast lines. There is the USA, like California, there are very particular, they have very strict rules, emissions and also the discharge of ballast water, well, Canada as well. They are even stricter. That is ultra-strict. And the Chinese meanwhile have become stricter as well. #00:11:16-7#
- I: *Oh, that is interesting as well.* #00:11:17-8#

- E9: Despite them throwing their garbage overboard immediately somehow we already have to comply with rather strict rules. But well, apart from that oil overboard is not possible, but 15 ppm, that is possible, that is allowed. #00:11:35-8#
- I: If you... *I have tried to put together a little what actually may be protected. Right. We have just been talking about ship waste. Ballast water, air pollution, then anti-fouling systems, well hull coatings...* #00:11:54-3#
- E9: Yes, exactly, TBT-free. With us that is anyways already basically in the law all of that. Well, we have completely different coatings in part already complete silicone coatings. #00:12:02-8#
- I: *Are they working?* #00:12:03-8#
- E9: Yes, they are working, yes, clearly. Yes, they are naturally extremely expensive. That is why TBT still existed for so long. That was the only reason. There already exist much better systems, well somehow Teflon-containing or silicone-containing and that is also especially with the minimization of friction today's regarding vessel efficiency an important issue. Fuel consumption is the biggest regulating screw with us. #00:12:29-7#
- I: *Do you ever have anything to do with noise?* #00:12:32-2#
- E9: Noise pollution? No, not really, that is not an issue at all. #00:12:38-4#
- I: *Right. Oily water, we have talked about that and other sewage water. That is probably...* #00:12:45-3#
- E9: Yes, grey water probably. #00:12:48-7#
- I: *Does that not play a role neither with you?* #00:12:50-1#
- E9: No, it does not play a role any more. You cannot say that. #00:12:51-7#
- I: *If you look at these: In which areas would you say that shipping is clean, that the aims are reached and where would one still need to do something?* #00:13:02-1#
- E9: Well, certainly the maximum is reached for the dumping of ship waste, because we have zero garbage overboard. I am disposing of everything on land in a certified so-called reception facility. I mean, I would say, more than that is not possible. It is also done that way here and one could maybe still verify the off-carriage in how far that is then treated on land, but that is then outside of my responsibility. So to say I can... I pass that over the brink, give it to the disposal company and that is what I do. Then it has naturally also left my area of work and then it naturally also does not interest me anymore. That is all well. The transport of foreign organisms and ballast water, yes that is a huge issue for us. The question always remains if that... if it is really achieving something. Well, I am of two minds about that to be honest, because one has not done that for hundreds of years now and I do not believe that you can now turn time back or something with this ballast water act somehow, because all these small animals, these Chinese mitten crabs

that are here in the Hamburg harbour, you have them, they are also coming from Asia. And they are all... you cannot get rid of them anymore, I think. That means a lot of work for us and a lot of technical effort, extremely expensive. Such a machine already has an electricity intake of 200 kilowatts alone. One machine when it is running plus the pumps. That is environmental pollution again if you want, because you need the 200 kilowatts... there needs to be a generator running for that somewhere. That is not negligible when that thing is running for three hours. #00:14:34-7#

I: *How much of your working time do you use for these ballast water stories?* #00:14:41-2#

E9: Ballast water handling is already rather complex, because with us everything is also being documented. Well every single... single cubic metre that I transfer somehow I need to put down in a so-called ballast water handling book. Well, from tank to there, to there. Also internal transfers, that means that I pump from one tank to the other. I also need to document that. That is an incredible amount of documentation and that will like not become less one day. Well, when in doubt there is no kind of debureacratism perceptible in shipping, but rather the opposite is the case. Well, there is much more to document, what also makes sense, evidently especially for these oil-containing issues, oil record book and so on. And that is also being controlled to an unbelievable extent. That means harbour states – they also come aboard with us – and they let it be shown to them. That means that they can retrace everything. You are entirely vitreous today. Our vessels are completely linked. You can even see on land what you are pumping to another place and such things. Well, such wangling does not exist here and here and there at times, what certainly was the case with shipping in earlier times. That does almost not exist at all anymore. #00:15:49-4#

I: *Are they coming aboard often?* #00:15:51-8#

E9: Yes, rather often. USA, Canada very often. China as well, they are rather strict as well. Well, one has to make sure that your documentation and everything that are doing in the normal daily operations that that is proper and that that is coherent, that you can always say: Well, someone may come at any time. They are coming without prior notice and that you always have a clear conscience and you say: Yes, come in, sit down, you can take a look, everything is in order. #00:16:16-1#

I: *How is that within the EU?* #00:16:18-1#

E9: Technically the same. There are different harbour state controls, Tokio Memorandum, Paris Memorandum, on which basis vessels are being controlled and they really inspect everything. They inspect the overtime of the people, they inspect all your record books, garbage record book, they take a look if your – what do I know – your life rafts are serviced, they take a tour on board, they take a look at the engine room. Above all they take a look if this so-called oil separator is running or if he is being bypassed. Well, is there is a stub [“blinde Leitung”] running somehow that pumps directly overboard or something. They look at everything. And they are also trained. In Hamburg the harbour police is doing that. I have already had MARPOL inspections here in Hamburg as well.

They take a look at all of that. One needs to work very precisely there. Well, that is really... yes. #00:17:11-1#

I: *Right, once again back to well regulated, not so well regulated.* #00:17:15-7#

E9: Yes. Pollution by sewage water. Yes well that is maybe also not yet a hundred per cent perfectly regulated, because I think, let us say sewage water, grey water, black water, everything that comes from the shower more or less and excrement or something, in the harbour they are running over the tank, well, they are not being disposed into the water here, but I think that that is not yet strict enough, well, it is nonetheless often done. Well, I would rather say that these foreign organisms in ballast water are not such a huge problem compared to when each vessel from Asia is pumping their excrement over board here. In the river Elbe for example. That is a little bit my personal opinion, but well. I see it like that. #00:18:06-2#

I: *One rather does not want to know that that is happening. No wonder that no one takes a swim there anymore.* #00:18:11-7#

E9: Yes, yes, exactly. Right, but especially this ballast water story is really a red rag for us currently a little bit. But well, if it comes now we are maybe prepared and able to do that. Apart from that... noise pollution... I can say little about that, because noise emissions... in that sense one could say due to the auxiliary systems in the harbour or something... such a gantry crane alone and these container are already so loud, that the OWN noise emission from the vessel is not very relevant. Well, I would rather say not at all really. Well, also a large vessel is not loud when it sails past in the Elbe and I do not experience it that way when I am standing at the shore that it is incredibly loud. #00:18:53-6#

I: *I think it is rather about the noise emissions under water for the animals that...* #00:19:01-0#

E9: Oh well, okay. That I can obviously not assess at all, because I do not have the... have the knowledge background in what way that is damaging for a whale or... #00:19:10-1#

I: *No, the question is anyways if that is an issue at all.* #00:19:13-1#

E9: No, for us not at all, not in the slightest. Well, the issue noise pollution... is likely coming one day as well. Then air pollution? That is a huge topic also in the meantime and with certainly nothing has been done there with air pollution I would say. Nothing has happened yet there. There one may do a substantially more. That is first of all a fuel question, what is happening with the fuel? Well, and we are operating on 700 heavy fuel oil or 800 heavy fuel oil, that is really... that is road tar and that needs to be treated. You have likely already concerned yourself with how that is being treated aboard. Yes, that is first of all an incredible filth that you are operating on, but it is a matter of costs. There the merchant people and the environmental protectionists somehow need to come to an

agreement. We, we are able to also operate on gas oil. It is also now at 5 degrees west we already now need to switch to low sulphur, to low sulphur content. #00:20:16-9#

I: *Is that technically...?* #00:20:19-0#

E9: That is normally not a problem. We have a tank that is filled with low sulphur and that is then switched to and yes, well, sometimes an engineer needs to get up at night time and needs to shift round a few outlets. That is also being policed, but we have now been retrofit already to gas oil for 2015. Well, then we can only operate on gas oil any more, I believe. Then it is no longer with low sulphur heavy fuel oil here at all. Then we are operating only on gas oil any more from 5 west, well European coast. Well, gas oil really actually is what you are also canting in your car more or less. And the machines can handle that without problems. Just, well, if you ask an engineer now he will not be happy that he needs to switch the stuff all the time. That is no pleasure for the machines neither evidently, let me say, to change the operating fluids all the time, well technically a challenge in any case. #00:21:13-0#

I: *Have you had problems or do you expect problems due to machine failure or something else?* #00:21:19-1#

E9: Do to the switch to another fuel? First of all it is a risk to put a tank down and to put another one into operation. Well, something may not fit there, a valve may not operate properly and the fuel pressure might then fall and all of that has already happened to us, but I would not see that as a problem. Well, one may get a grip on that as well I think. And that has already been in place here in California for a long time in the way that that is being switched. Well, that is incredible. There you are leaving the zone and switch again to the other stuff and then back again. Especially for old motors that are evidently due to the fact that gas oil is much lighter it leaks out of all corners, it really runs down at times. #00:22:03-5#

I: *That is crazy. That means, if all of that is leaking out does one then have more oil-containing water?* #00:22:09-5#

E9: Well, it does not sputter oil, but rather... yes, I would say that. Well, with older motors that are partly also not designed for that, that one does that the whole time. There are also the so-called... the clearances in the whole... in the whole fuel system. That really is, such a vessel is being incredibly... it does an incredible amount of operating hours. That means that... how to say this? It is characterized by a high wear. Some tolerances are also maybe not like in a car any more. That means if before there has always been rather thick fuel running through then there are evidently much different dimensions of movement for that and for another fuel and that is then naturally also leaking out a little from time to time. That is certainly a problem. On the other hand it needs to be said, if you would operate a machine entirely with gas oil now from the beginning then... that would first of all naturally be incredibly good, because it burns very, very clean. It renders this whole heavy fuel oil preparation unnecessary. That means you no longer have this whole slush, this whole sludge, because you do not need separators anymore. Well, it has an incredible amount of advantages. You do not need that much steam

anymore and steam also at the same times means more heavy crude oil consumption, because the steam also needs to be generated somehow. That means that that also has incredible advantages. On the other hand the question stands evidently what the refineries will do with the heavy crude oil if no one is buying it anymore, because it accrues anyway during the distillation. That means if you are producing fuel then yes... gas oil is lighter than fuel oil, but what do I do with it? Do I convert that to road tar, to tarmac or... Well, it accrues, it accrues during the distillation that is why, yes, I do not know exactly what the best way would be. For us it would be... well, if you ask an engineer and you tell him from today forward we will only operate on gas oil then he will say: Oh, perfect, that gives me less to do, because that is all clean and yes... #00:24:08-8#

I: *Is it in any way difficult to acquire the one or the other somewhere or may I bunker that everywhere I want? #00:24:17-9#*

E9: Normally that is not a problem. Well, you normally get fuel everywhere. The cost factor is then naturally decisive. It is many times more expensive than heavy fuel oil. . #00:24:32-6#

I: *Do you also need to pose such questions like what costs what or is someone else deciding about that? #00:24:37-9#*

E9: No. That is not evaluated by anyone of us aboard. That is not within our power of decision. There is an extra bunker department within our company who is doing all of that. Who consult what is best, where we bunker, where that is currently. That is also always changing daily where... if you bunker 10,000 tons of fuel then it is always immediately a few million Euros. That is why... there is a lot being negotiated and we are not really informed about that. #00:25:05-5#

I: *Ah well, thus they tell you: Do sail there to bunker? #00:25:08-6#*

E9: Exactly right. Yes, we normally bunker once in Europe and that is enough for one round trip and then we bunker again in Europe. Well, we do not need to fill the tank all the time or go to the gas station in that sense, but rather we once bunker full and then off we go. #00:25:24-2#

I: *When you say that one always needs to switch the tanks at a certain border. If I would now do that half an hour later – would anyone notice? #00:25:34-7#*

E9: Good question. One could surely somehow reconstruct that, but one is really very fixated on doing that well in time. The fuel also needs some time until it runs through. That means you really already need to let me say switch an hour earlier so that the whole pipe system so-to-say, well, from the tank to the settling tank and so on, so that it really actually reaches the machine, because the aim is to really be on the fuel at 5 degrees west. If you only switch there then you are already sailing for an hour somehow and still burning heavy fuel oil, to exaggerate a bit, depending on how fast you are going. #00:26:21-4#

- I: *If one looks at the statistics one sees... there also exists this air supervision. They are regularly finding out that people are also driving around on the Baltic Sea with heavy fuel oil or something. Would it always be possible at a harbour state control to find out which tank I have used? #00:26:43-6#*
- E9: Yes, yes certainly. #00:26:44-4#
- I: *Yes? Thus I cannot modify the books somehow... #00:26:48-6#*
- E9: It is certainly somehow possible. Well, especially the higher the capacity, the bunker capacity aboard, the more tanks one has, a cubic metre sometimes goes... one can certainly easily relocate that somehow... And there certainly still exists shipping companies who do that or who say: No, we are not yet switching there or whatever. That is certainly possible. I would not exclude that, but one is really trying here... well, with us for example there is no kind of order somehow based on the motto: Here, do take care that you are saving a little there or something. We are really focused on doing everything according to regulation and to comply with that, honestly. Well, there is no cheating done or something. Well, I do not know that, but I also do not know any other shipping company. I have always been with the one that is why I cannot talk about others now. But due to the fact that they may always supervise more and more people are becoming more careful and in earlier times, well, they deceived at each possibility. [“wurde an jeder Ecke beschissen”] Well, shipping has also been a little Mafia business in earlier times I would say, but meanwhile, no, I would not say that anyone... #00:28:02-2#
- I: *How much is the shipping industry interested in the issue of environmental protection? #00:28:07-4#*
- E9: Interested? Well, that always depends. The shipping industry is a very wide term. There are first of all the people on land. That is firstly maybe the environmental protection officer. Then there is the merchant and that sometimes stands in opposition to each other. The one wants to operate environmentally friendly, the other one also wants to save money and that naturally sometimes goes against each other. That is crystal clear. Especially now with the fuel one could say, okay, the environmental officer says: We want to reduce emissions; we are operating on gas oil. Then the merchant is saying: Yes, life will go on. Who is supposed to pay for that? That has... fuel consumption for example has a direct effect for us. The more we so-to-say... the higher the operating costs the more we need to charge for the cargo. That means that the containers become more expensive and one is in an incredible competitive situation in the meantime in sea transport, especially in relation to the containers. That is no speciality shipping any more, anyone can do containers. The Chinese are there. There every last dollar really is decisive and that is why... and we aboard are in the end the vicarious agents of the people who make the decisions on land. And we are bound to implement what they give us and we anyway have an incredible amount to do aboard, well, I above all, that is why I implement that and then the issue is over for me. I cannot make big decisions anyway. I cannot, I don't know, say based on my own decision premises somehow, oh, I am now

sailing into the shipyard and then I have a catalytic converter retrofit and then...
(Laughing) #00:29:46-0#

I: *That would also be nice. (Laughing) #00:29:47-0#*

E9: Or something. That is evidently not possible. Well, that is why... well, interest clearly, well, I am actually interested that I do not pollute my oceans and that is why I do not throw anything overboard or something. That is a matter of course. I am also not throwing anything onto the road. Then I am also not throwing anything into the water. And that one has come that far in shipping is in any case already a big achievement, because for decades or I would almost say for centuries they have... well, industrial waste does not exist yet for such a long time, but let us say that has at least existed for a hundred years now... everything has been thrown overboard then, everything. And oil... they have washed the tankers, the tanks at sea in earlier times. That was completely normal and that is certainly still happening, and if one can retrace that so well... I have never worked on a tanker. I only know the stories how they clean their tanks before taking on new cargo. #00:30:37-4#

I: *Is that still like that or has that also been changing? #00:30:40-8#*

E9: Well, I do not know that to be honest. Well, regarding tanker shipping that is certainly a huge issue. It would certainly be interesting to ask someone there who... will likely never admit that he washes the tanks at sea, but that has certainly happened at times. That is a huge rascality. [“Riesensauerei”] That needs to be said about that. #00:30:58-9#

I: *One can imagine that. Of these measures – which one are the most expensive for the shipping companies? #00:31:06-9#*

E9: I think dumping of waste, or rather dumping... it means to dump, well that is thus overall dumping? Well, to dispose of that the right way is not a huge cost factor I think. That is not a big thing. Emission of oily water is also... one has an oil separator, also not a big issue. It certainly gets interesting regarding air pollution. Well, minimizing NO_x values. CO₂ emissions... well, that always goes hand in hand with the consumption, that is why a big vessel likely makes sense, well, economies of scale, small engines, well, with us they are also all already regulated electronically. That means they all burn... well, they use the fuel as well as possible. A diesel motor with a vapour system with the whole shebang has an efficiency factor of fifty per cent. That is already incredible, if one compares that to a car or something, in which one guy is sitting. Well, basically sea transport is a fine thing. One hears that time and again. That is no environmental rascality in that sense. Just the quantity of vessels then evidently still makes it... that one is blowing out a lot and what is coming out up there is evidently the last crap. Das is totally clear. That is getting more expensive for the shipping companies in the future, with this catalyst technology and... well, everything that already exists in power plants or in coal power-burned power stations, what already is in there in filter technology alone that also needs to be serviced, that needs to be cleaned, that also only allows for certain operating conditions I think. That will be a huge challenge for the shipping

industry to operate these things correctly. Well, there is such a fuel, like for example these LNG vessels or LNG motors, real gas motors. That is the future in all likelihood, I think, that one abandons the heavy fuel oil and operates the motors with gas. There already exist combustion engines, well also these big cross clamp diesel motors, I'm saying, that run with gas and LNG and LPG tankers. Those are partly turbine vessels they are already operating on boil off gas. Well, the gas that is vaporizing anyway during the journey due to temperature differences and so on. They use that as fuel gas. Well, the gas that is boiling there, well vaporizing so-to-say, is being collected, I think compressed anew, compacted, and rushed through a turbine again. That is evidently super-efficient. The only problem is, I believe, for big vessels, that one does not really know where to keep this gas in the end, because that uses a lot of space where you really also cut put container and it is also evidently expensive. #00:34:17-9#

I: *Is that a technical problem?* #00:34:21-8#

E9: No, certainly not. Well naturally everything that is powered with gas that is naturally also such a thing... well, it is not, I would say, not altogether hazard-free. Well, in the meantime there already exist a lot of diesel motors and also turbines are in any way rather safe, but well, I think the people also need to first of all become familiar with it and need to be trained for such a thing, because it really is a completely different combustible than elsewhere this black oil that runs out of there. #00:34:55-2#

I: *Could I bring such... such a thing like gas onto an old vessel to or would one only do that for newly-builds?* #00:35:04-1#

E9: I think that is impossible to install on an old ship. That would no charge off. That I don't believe. That would only be for new tonnage that would be equipped with it. That I don't believe. Well, to retrofit an old vessel to LNG is impossible. That would also be a safety risk. Well, one would need to make an incredible effort. One would really need to build in a new main engine and if you move such a main engine... the main engine is now sitting on the ship, is directly sitting under the superstructures in order to already save space and one would need to take the superstructures off first and take the whole machine out below. You cannot dismount it just now. That is why, well, I think not. #00:35:49-4#

I: *What does one do with old vessels?* #00:35:53-1#

E9: Old vessels, they are being broken up. #00:35:55-7#

I: *Now more than before?* #00:35:58-7#

E9: I believe yes, that recently also due to this shipping crisis many, yes, a lot of tonnage was broken up... also partly ones that have not even reached twenty years. Simply to make space for new tonnage. Ships that are more efficient and so on. With us for example the biggest entities are already rebuild to efficiency, to this slow steaming. Well, one is already sailing slower. That also has an enormous impact for us, that one... ten years ago one has only been going at full speed, that is 25 knots and let go... and

that simply does not exist anymore. The timetables are designed on 17, 18 knots and the design concept or the waterline of such a vessel for example, with this interesting nose here is built in any case according to that. That is also a 24 knot vessel. A container vessel is incredibly slim in the underwater sphere. They are all build to speed like in earlier times and that is now – relating to the efficiency – being minimized again, because one is now sailing slowly and the hull concept and the hydrodynamic properties of the underwater vessel they are no longer at all designed for these sailing list speeds so-to-say. That means they are now more and more taking care to build other bulge bows to the front and other propellers that are more efficient for the sailing speed. Well, they are no longer designed for 20, 22, 23 knots, but for 18 knots and that is really the speed that is sailed at in the meantime. #00:37:40-0#

I: *That means if I would now bring new tonnage on the market, would I also make sure that that would be designed for 18 knots? #00:37:47-5#*

E9: Yes. I think still, that... they likely will be, because the charter party and the ship owners are still demanding that. They will likely still be able to well do 20, because the charter market is somehow also working with such parameters... what is the vessel able to do, how fast is it, how much does it consume and so on and so forth. But that will come more and more. Well, for our large vessels for example, they have been designed for a 12 cylinder unit. They have already taken away one cylinder. That means it already has 11 cylinders. Fundamentally less specifically fuel consumption does the vessel have already anyway and that is now being optimized even further. Well, there is still a lot of potential. Well, most of what one may simply save in CO₂ emissions is simply by sailing more slowly as well. First of all it is more economical for the company and if I operate on half the amount it is also clear what is happening to the CO₂ emissions and that is also being done. Well in that sense one already contributes to the relief of the air by simply no longer doing so much, by not sailing so fast any more. #00:38:58-9#

I: *If you say on the charter market... does it interest the charter market whether I have a ship that is environmentally friendly? #00:39:04-9#*

E9: I think at the moment that is not yet relevant. That will certainly come. Well, the development goes into that direction. Well, I believe that one day it will be. But maybe efficiency and environmental protection are working hand in hand there, because on says: Well, a slower vessel is first of all also much less fuel and thus also more environmentally friendly. Well, what use is it if I say: Here, okay, that ship may do 25 knots, but such a 25 knots ship, let us say, needs around 250, 300 tons per 24 hours. 300 tons of fuel. We now need around 100 for the big ones. That is a third of that and that is already a big difference. Well, earlier it was 250 tons. That was normal. #00:39:57-0#

I: *Oh, that is crazy. #00:39:57-7#*

E9: Well, one has already done a lot and that is really bringing improvements. Adapted sailing lists. There one can optimize a lot, by optimizing the sailing lists alone, by working together in alliances and so on and so forth. I believe that there is still a lot to do and things are going better and better I would say. #00:40:22-3#

- I: *How well would you think vessel owners and operators are informed about environmental legislation? #00:40:28-8#*
- E9: I would say rather well, because we are also forced to deal with that. Especially because, as I said, we are also being policed and anyone who is being policed will automatically deal with that. That is a law of nature. If someone is standing behind me looking over my shoulder then I make sure that I comply with environmental legislation. We also have all sorts of literature aboard, MARPOL, the newest... we are always being updated. And we get the new law gazettes each month and the amendments and this whole stuff. Well, this environmental literature that concerns us alone we have that aboard, we also need to have that aboard in order to really make sure that we say in line with all these regulations. Above all in the US this CFR code there. That is such an oeuvre of books. They partly do not understand that themselves what is written in there and that is why it is the more important for us to take a close look in order to know what they actually want from us. What are we allowed to do here and what not and when in doubt we rather do nothing then to argue with the Americans for example, because they can't take a joke at all. #00:41:48-5#
- I: *Do you manage to read all of that? #00:41:50-8#*
- E9: Oh god, certainly I am only reading the things that are relevant for me and it always depends. Well, I think I have read everything at one point, but if you are not somehow daily retrieving that data then you are forgetting some things again and the things that concern us, that are important to us, that is known to every ship officer and also every ship officer should know that. Otherwise he will someday get into trouble. That is one day attracting attention. #00:42:25-0#
- I: *Are there differences between the captains? Do all have the entire regulations aboard and are well informed? #00:42:32-3#*
- E9: Yes, yes, in any case. #00:42:34-8#
- I: *Are there, I do not know how that works, are they differences in quality? Are there better captains and worse captains? #00:42:41-8#*
- E9: In relation to the compliance with environmental laws or...? #00:42:44-6#
- I: *No, in relation to... overall. #00:42:45-7#*
- E9: Yes, it is like that with every boss. You have a good boss and you have a boss that you maybe not like so much. #00:42:51-8#
- I: *No, I only know that from aviation. There it is always the ones... I do not know, there are the pilots that go to Lufthansa and then there are the ones that have to fly for Ryanair, because they have also not done so well in their tests. #00:43:06-0#*
- E9: Well, okay. I can't... yes, there are always some people where you shake your head in disbelief or something. I cannot give a global statement... idiots exist everywhere. I think with Lufthansa there are also a lot of idiots, I think. Hard to say. #00:43:33-2#

I: *That means this information... do you read through that yourself or do you also have other sources? #00:43:41-4#*

E9: Yes, well, we evidently are also referred to the newest regulations by the company. We have such a fleet circular system. That means there really exists a live interaction between the ship and the land organisation. That means we are writing weekly and we are sometimes receiving new information daily. Here, please make sure that... or port state there and there... take care especially to... take another look if everything is in order. Well, there always exists an active communication. That means we are really also through that always informed and are also dependant on that, because I do not have the time to deal with some new regulations all the time or something. That is not possible. Well, I depend on someone from the outside telling me: Take care, there is something new again, please implement that. And we also have a quality management. We also have an ISM system. That is also all marked down how what is to be done, ballast water treatment, garbage record handling and such things. All of that is really also written down in detail, please do that so and so and that is what we do with this and that form in this and that folder with the number 305. That also has a lot of advantages obviously, because everything is standardized. That exists on every vessel no matter where I arrive. Wham, folder out, the presentation is in there. That's how it works. Well, it is not like everyone is doing his thing and interpreting the things like he wants to, but there exist very clear standards how things are to be documented. That also makes sense because otherwise you lose track. #00:45:15-6#

I: *Would you think that a one-ship company would have it in any way more difficult or that the processes are different? #00:45:21-5#*

E9: With certainty. Yes, I believe that, yes. That is always easier in a big company to implement things and I also always have the feeling that they are a little closer to the whole events happening at the IMO and so on. One-ship companies, with certainty, they have it extremely difficult, because they have the same legislation. They need to comply with ISPS, ISM, this whole stuff, I'm just saying, comply like the big shipping companies and that is a crazy effort and to keep up to date with that is almost impossible. Well, in relation to shipping as a whole there exist such an incredible amount of laws and process technologies that somehow need to be applied. Very, very difficult for a one-ship company, I really believe. Well, many are in the VDR or in communities of interest. That means they are also already getting input from the outside, they are also informed, but for them it is evidently also difficult to implement that just like that. Well, they also clearly have... no garbage overboard is not that difficult. You buy four dustbins, I think, for a coaster or a smaller vessel. And an oil separator they also have on the dockyard, but I still believe that that is really... that it is not easy for them. #00:46:48-4#

I: *If you now think about that some have it more difficult and some have it easier – is it mainly the size that plays a role or do other things play a role as well like port of destination, flag, fleet? #00:47:06-7#*

- E9: Well, that is a good question. I think due to a different mentality there are certainly also differences regarding environmental protection in general I would say. And some shipping companies certainly have... take things a little easier and some don't. I think European... well, I'm simply saying that, European shipping companies are very, very clearly focused on complying with that. That I do believe, yes. And how that is with the Chinese... I don't know. They theoretically also need to comply with that and will also do that more or less, but yes... #00:47:57-6#
- I: *Does the flag play any role? So to say those that are flying this flag are normally always doing well and with this and that flag one would be careful?* #00:48:12-1#
- E9: Regarding the complying with environmental regulations, right? Oh god, as I said, I would need to have experienced how that is with other shipping companies, because I cannot say anything about that. I can only ever talk about my company, that everything is in order there, well. Well, also with a clear conscience. Not now... and with other shipping companies... I can imagine that it is certainly not the same with other shipping companies, but I also do not have any prove or... #00:48:44-9#
- I: *No, it is just interesting to know who...* #00:48:48-1#
- E9: With certainty. There are certainly... #00:48:49-1#
- I: *For whom it is the most difficult.* #00:48:50-4#
- E9: Yes. There certainly exist large differences. That I do believe. And some are maybe also not willing to simply spend money on some things. They say, do I now need to order the ship disposal company if I can perfectly throw it over board here? Well, that thinking certainly still exists – with some people. The ocean is big. A lot is fitting in there. And many people are also certainly doing that, I think. #00:49:21-9#
- I: *The additional things that are now expected of you due to environmental legislation, ballast water, air pollution – it is possible to fulfil that?* #00:49:35-9#
- E9: (Thinking) Yes, it is possible. But means even more work to be done and we are already rather short of people aboard I would say. Well, we already really have a lot to do and a lot of... the area of responsibility is incredibly wide. Well, one also needs to do a little error management. That means the more I... I'm now exaggerating a bit... the more lying on your shoulders the more... the more prone you are to make mistakes. One should not forget that. Well, I am now supposed somehow to do three things at a time and so and maybe I will then say, okay, that is currently not so important, I will do that later and later I will forget that or something. Really simply due to the pressure of work. (Coughing) I am sorry. And yes, that is... - I think I need to drink something soon when I am talking so much here. - ...that is certainly an issue. Well, due to fatigue or something. You are coming into the harbour at night and then immediately work goes on and they are all coming up. The vessel disposal company is coming, then the planner is coming and then they are all standing in your office wanting something from you and you are like, okay, well, who is first? First of all the most important things first. The

most important thing for me is the cargo and then I say: You take a seat here or someone else needs to take care of that, because I don't have time for that right now. That is always the same in seafaring, that is very, very... very, very typical. One sometimes has a little peace at sea, on the watch, then you are nicely traveling the various parts of the globe. But then in the harbour it all comes at once. Then it hits you hard. Then all of them want something from you and everyone is tearing at your arms saying: Here to me, I now have the bigger problem and you are confronting that more or less alone. And also regarding these environmental stories, certainly, when that is getting more you simply have to take time for that and I do all of that after my watch. During my watch I cannot work and I do all of that after my watch. That means I normally always work at least thirteen, fourteen hours a day. That is normal – every day. Just simply to manage my odd bits of paperwork. That is making most of it. Well, this administration, documentation, to put everything on record. That everything adds up, that nothing is wrong. All this data that needs to be recorded and so on. That is what I meant in the beginning. That always yield a pool of mistakes somehow where you also sometimes write down something wrong. That has also once in a while happened to me that I simply put down something wrong when maybe I have also been a little tired when I take a look at that the next day I think: What have you been doing there? And especially in such a document to cross something out, especially in the garbage record book or also the oil record book – the chief is doing that, I am not doing that – but do cross something out in those. Then they are immediately looking: Why have you crossed something out there? What is that there? Well, one immediately stands with one's back to the wall and needs to explain one. People are coming up and you are always the one explaining, the one who always needs to say: Yes and I have done it this and that way and he will be asking: Why have you done it this and that way? Yes, because of this and that and that. And then they always immediately want PROOF of everything. That is, I don't know, likely the same elsewhere, but in seafaring it is very typical. You always need to prove everything somehow. When you are now doing a lifesaving exercise or something then best with pictures and with a two-page documentation so that you can prove: We have really actually done it. That is more or less how it is. And it is getting more and more. They people always come aboard with a huge mistrust and look at you first of all according to the motto: You do want to deceive me and then you are always the one so-to-say... you always have a duty to inform [“Bringschuld”]. #00:53:34-0#

I: *Are you being controlled less than others because one thinks: A Germany company, we generally trust them.* #00:53:46-7#

E9: That is often exactly the other way round, simply because for those people it is also less work to inspect a vessel where everything is in order. Well, one maybe needs to look at it from that point of view for once, because according to my experience the authorities responsible for controls rather inspect vessels that look good, where everything is in order, where they have nothing much to complain about, because then they don't need to do much. If they are now entering an old Greek vessel that is 30 years old and where nothing is on the right, the correct place anymore and everything looks horribly and everything is rusty and they are walking through the machinery and everything is oily

and so on. What will they need to do then? Then they need to really become active. They really need to say: Here, take you, you are first off all being chained up and you need to go into the shipyard and then a huge process needs to be set in motion [“...ein unheimliches Rad muss in Bewegung gesetzt werden.”]. That is evidently pure hypothesis but I would say that that is how it is. Well, they always rather like to enter the new vessels and also like to come to us, where they are saying: Here, come on, with you everything is in order anyway. Then we will have lunch and then they are happy.
#00:54:59-3#

- I: *One can almost speculate on that is one is an old Greek vessel...? #00:55:04-2#*
- E9: Maybe. Well, that is all speculation. Well, I cannot prove that, but it is like that with certainty. (Laughing) #00:55:12-6#
- I: *Are there companies that are better? Who try to over-comply with environmental legislation? #00:55:21-8#*
- E9: I think in the meantime that is a little bit the case in passenger shipping. But that is just what I know from the normal media. Well, AIDA now... that is also always an important topic in Hamburg... there is now also such an – I don't know – such an interest group who does... or the NABU is fighting against that, that they are operating the auxiliary engines here and so forth. Which is evidently totally normal in any harbour of the world that the auxiliary engines are running, but well, shore connection is also a huge topic. That already exists in parts with us as well that we take a shore connection and that will come up I think. And if they have enough capacity at land to produce the electricity, why not. Well, I think it is good. That is a good thing. One has to make sure that in the harbour, let me say, for a container vessel you need to hold available three, four megawatts. Well, first of all you need to channel that electricity through a wire. Well, but that is in any way a possibility, I think that is good. And the... in order to come back to the question... well, passenger ferries like AIDA or others who are now starting with this LNG barge or something, they over-comply with certainty, because that is simply not yet mandatory to do it like that and they certainly have that way... well, they are also selling a little bit of a green ship story. Well, the passengers then think it is great and so on. Well, that also has to do a lot a lot with representation to the outside, if they now do... I have heard, I think this environmental officer is this, this Ms Griefahn, a former politician who maybe somehow kick-started that. I do not know, but maybe that also appeals to the business people, if they can sell it all as green and so on. I mean you can't make something out of nothing and something needs to be burned, otherwise nothing comes out of the socket or what? #00:57:23-2#
- I: *How does that look in merchant shipping? May I sell green shipping there? Or is someone trying that? #00:57:32-5#*
- E9: I think at the moment nor really, but it will certainly become an issue. The business man finds it interesting if it yields something, for example he likes fuel consumption and only with this argument something can be achieved in merchant shipping, well, we are now talking about container line shipping, that is what I can talk about, of bulk shipping,

tramp shipping, tanker shipping, I know nothing, but of the normal container shipping... well, one has to see. Maybe one day it will be... one will be able to sell that well somehow with... that is coming up more and more, this sustainability and this whole story. Well, a few years ago they have... I don't know, one or two years ago we have also received in info sheet or rather a real booklet: "Driven by Responsibility" and then they had enlisted all the things that are up and running already in our company, ballast water treatment and so forth, good hull coatings, well outer coating under water and so forth. And that is more and more coming into focus and the company has also sent that to their customers to say: Look what we are also doing here. The container is maybe a little more expensive with us, but in exchange we are transporting our container with super vessels. #00:58:55-7#

I: *Are the customers paying more then?* #00:58:59-1#

E9: Well, a business man can probably tell you something about that. I would say not. At the moment the maritime freight commerce is simply so highly competitive and the people are simply taking the cheapest offer and then cheap prices maybe still in relation to reliability. Maybe they are paying a bit more because a certain company works more reliable or has a better pre-carriage and post-carriage concept per container. But first of all for a final consumer it is interesting to bring his container from A to B as fast as possible and as cheap as possible. That I think is of the most interest for the customer. #00:59:42-9#

I: *What keeps a shipping company from complying with environmental standards?* #00:59:47-6#

E9: Yes, well environmental standards in that sense are being complied with more or less. Now really it is more or less about doing more with regards to air pollution and so on. I think it is first of all the costs that discourage people to do something about that and the missing legislation. That means as long as nothing is decided upon a shipping company will not move. They are waiting as long as the legislator is saying: Starting in 2015 you are building a catalyst into your vessel or something else, otherwise you are not allowed to operate anymore and then the shipping company will move, but before that he will not do anything. Those are all, well, a ship operator, a shipping company owner, a ship owner, those are also special people. They want to earn a lot of money with the ship and put in little. Well, deep sea navigation, merchant shipping, has been subject to an incredible process of rationalization already during the last decades. They are economizing in people. We are really... we are the last of the Mohicans, those that are still European seamen. There are no longer many of us left. And that is why we need to take care even more that we somehow still... that we can justify being aboard, that we maybe are able to do a little more than others, that we know a little more at the sides, how to save fuel, that we operate economically. That certainly depends on the people aboard to know: Hey, here I can put the generator off or this or that. I am operating that or that way and maybe with sufficient background knowledge it is a win for a ship owner to have European seafarers for example. And that is at least partly still being done that one says: Okay, that is yielding something for me. The bloke is thinking for himself.

But then I would insinuate at the same time that the others are not able to do that. That I cannot judge upon. I can only... well, we have still been trained very thoroughly. And that is why we also understand the vessel as a whole. I know exactly what is going on and how the procedures are. I am not really a hundred per cent sure that many people now that who are going to sea. They are really bus drivers or truck drivers. #01:02:18-9#

I: *Do you know how the training is done in other countries? Well, where the differences are?* #01:02:25-1#

E9: Oh god. Well, we have received integrated training in our company. That means we have first been trained in the engine area, have first passed through the engine area and have then gone on as deck officers. That means we have so to say gotten to know both areas and have been trained in them as well. One more and more distances oneself from that approach. Well, I am just insinuating that many navigating officers have no... that they know rather very little about technology. That is why it always has been an asset for me that I have started in the beginning to work in the engine and to gain experiences there, because one gets to know the whole business. One knows exactly what is happening there when you somehow do something with the hand gear above. #01:03:15-5#

I: *Does one need to know that or is there always someone who...?* #01:03:21-9#

E9: I am of the opinion that one necessarily needs to know that. That is my personal opinion. Yes, but well, one does not want to pay anything for the people and... you get what you pay for. If I simply pay them a quarter or even less of what I earn then they are not able to do the same things. It simply is like that. Partly those are really people that are superbly trained and they are glad that they even manage to some extent up there. If he manages to get the vessel through... I don't know... through highly frequented sea areas. He is already gals enough about that. He does not think about anything else. They do not have either... that already starts with the school education and so on. In parts you cannot expect that anymore from the people. They simply do not have that. They manage. They get from A to B. That is what the ship owner is asking of them. Yes, that is it. Well, we really are one of the least... we are the last professional group of European seafarers that has maybe still been reasonably trained. That is more and more vanishing and shipping companies are not putting any value any more an employing European seafarers. I am talking about container line shipping above all. That is becoming constantly less and that is why you also have worse and worse trained people. That is getting more and more severe. #01:04:50-2#

I: *What happens when directions are not being complied with?* #01:04:53-7#

E9: When directions are not being complied with. You get, if you now for example... in a harbour state control they always find out that you have wrongly documented something or that something has gone wrong or you really have an act of crime, well with oil or something you quickly get into the criminal act area. They you are first of all being personally penalized and the company is being penalized. #01:05:21-1#

- I: *That means there are really also personal penalties for... #01:05:24-1#*
- E9: Incredibly rigorous, clearly. Clearly, the officers are also held fully responsible. Well, I am always... so and so it is said in shipping as a general rule one is always sailing close to the wind [“mit einem Bein im Gefängnis stehen”], because one is jointly liable for everything. Everything that I write down somewhere with my signature – one has to sign everything with a signature – you have decided it that way, you have done it that way, you have documented it that way and you are liable. You are liable for everything. #01:05:51-7#
- I: *That means if now somewhere... if your name appears behind a wrong figure that will cost thousands of Euros? #01:06:01-3#*
- E9: There are certainly always... I mean everyone makes mistakes and that evidently always depends on the people. If they can comprehend that you... that you put some wrong figure down by mistake and not in bad faith. Evidently you have to prove that again. You again have the burden of prove. There it starts again. I think then they will say, okay, everyone can make mistakes. #01:06:21-5#
- I: *But if I have written wrong figures down on purpose? #01:06:24-6#*
- E9: Then you have committed an act of crime and then you are held liable and then you really need to... either pay a lot of money or go to prison. In the US you even go right to prison, well with oil things you immediately go to prison as an officer. #01:06:35-8#
- I: *If I would have to pay a certain sum of money would the shipping company pay that for me? #01:06:40-8#*
- E9: Difficult to say. Well, maybe. It has not happened to me personally and I do not know of any case where that happened, but I know how it is. They are then also threatening with it. Well, it really is like that. I have already had that several times that they threatened someone with that. Well, that is not right here and so, that will cost this and that much. #01:07:04-4#
- I: *Is that paid by... or is the charterer or the owner of the vessel liable afterwards? #01:07:14-4#*
- E9: Well, with us it is the case that we are always managing owner. That means the owner is at the same time the one operating the vessel. Apart from that the charterer... (Thinking) ...to be honest I don't really know. If the shipping company is chartering the ship out with crew members and operating the ship then it is certainly evidently also the shipping company that is held liable. It has to be. The operator is always the one who has an influence on that. Well, one can the other... the charterer is then saying: Yes, I have told you to comply with this regulation. You have not done that thus you have to pay. I think it is that way. But I do not know. #01:07:59-2#
- I: *Would make sense. Would you say that the average age of the fleet is a good indication for its environmental friendliness? #01:08:05-0#*

- E9: Yes, with certainty. Clearly. The newer the vessel, the more environmentally friendly it is. Entirely clear. Especially in today's time a lot of value is put on efficiency and also in that respect than on the fuel consumption again and thus, clearly, the newer the vessel the more environmentally friendly it is. With certainty, yes. #01:08:22-2#
- I: *Again regarding the harbour state controls – is always everything being controlled or one time this and one time that?* #01:08:27-4#
- E9: No, not always everything, it depends. It always depends on what kind of inspection it is. Well, in Hamburg for example it is still separated. The harbour police do the MARPOL inspection and the other one does the dangerous goods inspection and so on and so forth. It is also a kind of harbour state control, but they are really specialized only in certain areas. There are examples of Rotterdam where one person examines everything. He can really say: Show me your record book, show me this and now I want to walk through your vessel, want to look at your logbooks or something else. Well, that is not written down somewhere. It is fixed or written down in the Paris Memorandum and also Tokio or something, whatever they are all called, all that may be inspected. That is written down there, but that are pages... They can inspect everything, everything. #01:09:16-1#
- I: *Are certain things controlled more often and other less often or is it entirely arbitrary?* #01:09:23-7#
- E9: Well, I would say things like the oil record book or something are actually being controlled often. Certificates are being controlled. Today one also has such emission certificates for example for the auxiliary engines and for the main engine and that is... they need to be up to date and that is being checked. That is often done. Well, I would say almost always. Certificates are the most important and all the logbooks, record books and so on. First of all all this administration, this whole paper work that is being inspected. #01:10:07-1#
- I: *In it possible to inspect all that? Well, if you now look at the different types of pollution?* #01:10:17-9#
- E9: If you can influence all of that or...? Well, inspect... Well, air pollution for example you cannot inspect in that sense. There exist no measuring modules for NO_x emissions or something like that. The only thing that one can evidently do is that you can see by way of the exhaust-gas plume in how far your engine is working. Well, an exhaust-gas plume does give a lot of information about the functioning of the combustion engine. If it smokes out black there then something is not in order. Then she likely has deficiency of air or the fuel is bad or an injection nozzle is broken or something else. Then you have to say: Wait a minute, something is not right here. Well, relating to that, okay, clearly one can draw conclusions in how far... if something is alright or not. Okay. Noise pollution we can exclude. Pollution by sewage waters can clearly be controlled. Oily water can be controlled. Poisonous hull coatings are being controlled one time - that is in the shipyard. One knows for example what a coating one has on the hull here and if one needs this TBT-free certificate there. As far as I know there is a certificate

and they are also inspecting that, that you have a hull coating that is TBT-free. Yes well. And yes, transport of foreign organisms in ballast water – yes, well, what does control mean? I evidently cannot control that in this sense. I can exclude that by using by ballast water treatment facility if I have that aboard. And disposal of waste can be controlled, clearly. #01:12:08-1#

I: *How is the business model of the shipping industry being influenced by current environmental legislation? #01:12:14-6#*

E9: The business model – how is that meant? Well, business model... #01:12:21-2#

I: *Costs, fleet composition... #01:12:26-2#*

E9: Fleet composition, I think... that is hard to say. Well, one evidently always tries more and more to build bigger ships. Economies of scale is the big keyword. Well, in how far does that influence...? Yes, one tries to make sure more and more that the vessels are already prepared for future environmental legislation. Ballast water treatment for example is such a story. The facilities are now already being installed to make sure maybe that they are finally operational when that comes in force. Well, maybe that is... that is actually influential, because it is a significant cost increase. I don't know, I think such a facility costs somehow several million Euros. Well, that really is a huge thing. Well, that is why it certainly influences clearly also the history and I believe at Maersk for example, I have recently read that there are already these, what is the correct term, I forgot, but any way one can... in how far one can recycle the ship. There exists also an indicator in how far that is sustainably produced and if one now cuts it into pieces and separates everything then the vessel components are already built in in a way that the knacker has an easy job. He can build out the pipes like that and does not need to take the isolation material off the pipes and more. That is named... there exists a certain term, but I don't know any more how it is called. And clearly, that is also being done, that one now maybe constructs vessels that are easy to demolish and so on. #01:14:23-8#

I: *What influence does environmental legislation have on the costs? #01:14:28-2#*

E9: Influence on the costs... Well, first of all it is certainly always difficult for a shipping company to implement certain environmental rules. Ballast water stories are first of all expensive and that is a thing that, yes, that one does in order to comply, but that has no benefit for the company, in terms of costs not at all, I would say. Rather at the contrary. Well, I would not know of any benefits for us. For us that does not yield anything really. #01:15:05-3#

I: *Are there differences between the shipping companies? It is even more expensive for some than for others to...? Well, the main issues are really ballast water and then later also this sulphur thing. #01:15:18-2#*

E9: Yes, well, we have... you have already mentioned these one-ship companies or something like that. They evidently have higher costs by that, because if a big liner shipping company buys this and that many facilities and they evidently already get

different prices than if one person comes along and wants to have a special facility for his little vessel. He rather does not want to have that at all, but he needs to have it. That is why, well... but there also exists, as far as I know, an example of a shipping company at the Lower Elbe [“Niederelbe”]. How are they called? I don’t know exactly. They have in any way achieved a contract with a paper factory in Sweden, because they have started to retrofit catalyts and everything in their vessels already at the time. Well, they have started to enter the environmental track already very early and have said: Take a look we have incredibly green vessels here. They have sailed the Baltic to Sweden as far as I know, sadly I cannot come up with the name of the shipping company now... well, the vessels are called Cellus and Typhos or something and they are around 400 meter vessels and they have already... certainly ten, fifteen years ago they have already started to fit in exhaust gas catalyts there and so on. And that was really the deciding factor that they have received the contract with the paper factory in order to sail the paper rolls back and forth. Well, there it may also be a positive factor. Well, a company wants to be perceived as green from the outside. Well, I certainly also need to work together with shipping companies that operate their vessels green. Benefit for the company, but it is certainly very risky to rush entirely into one sector first of all for a shipping company I would think, but I do not know. #01:17:02-3#

I: *How do the overall costs for the shipping companies develop at the moment?* #01:17:07-5#

E9: Operating costs are a huge problem. Well and that is certainly increasing as well. I mean the fuel costs have currently been decreasing a bit again, but one day it will likely be the case again that it gets more expensive and that is why the costs are going higher and higher as likely everywhere else as well. Operating costs. #01:17:27-0#

I: *Would you say that that has an influence on the freight rates?* #01:17:32-4#

E9: Oh yes, difficult topic. They want to... the freight rates are very, very low and normally the companies want, need really significantly more per transported unit in order to sail to some extent cost-effective. And the problem is that due to this competitive situation that currently exists it is just incredibly strong, the cost pressure is so strong that they cannot go higher with their rates. They would have to all agree and would have to say: Well, for example we want to operate more economically now and still, well, better, or whatever else. They would have to agree and say, well, we increase the rates together. Sea transport has become far too cheap. It does not cost anything anymore. A twenty foot container from Hamburg to Asia, I don’t know, a few hundred Dollars or something, that is nothing anymore. And especially to make sure of sustainable operations one evidently needs to pay the price for that. The end consumer must be aware of the fact that that simply costs more money. That is the same like... here... fair trade coffee or something. That also costs more than normal coffee. And whoever wants to have everything cheap, cheap, will also get cheap. That is always such a thing between supply and demand. If the final customer is willing to so say to pay more for that then it is being done that way and then the business man, or rather the ship operator will also budge. But as long as everything needs to be cheap and mass, mass, mass what is now

dominant in the Asia and in the Asia-Europe service nothing will happen. The regulations will be complied with that need to be complied with. Full stop. Nothing more will be done. No one will do excessively more than that. That would simply be a competitive disadvantage. That is very clear. The more I put on the weighting scale the more expensive that will also get for me and then the business man will ask himself: Why are we even doing this whole bullshit at all if the others are not doing it? Are we the buffoons here? That is what I think. #01:19:38-9#

I: *It is possible to transport certain goods on another way then the water? #01:19:44-1#*

E9: No alternative. That does not exist. Well, there is this rail track to Shanghai, but evidently you cannot drag off as much by that as with the ship. Well shipping is... will always stay the transport mode number one between the continents. Always. There is no better alternative than shipping. One simply has to say that. It is super economical. It is just a very fine thing. You can transport everything. Secure. #01:20:13-5#

I: *Does that look... the other way round. Does that look different here on the Baltic Sea or here in the European sphere? #01:20:21-5#*

E9: I can't say much about that, because I am not operating on the Baltic Sea so much. Baltic Sea, I believe, they are already a bit further ahead. They have to, I think, they have not been allowed to operate on heavy fuel oil for some time, as far as I know. And also the Swedes and so on, they are already very strict. From what I heard, but that is simply only seen out of the corner of my eye. Well, I cannot say much out this Baltic Sea story, because I am simply not there and know not much about the regulations of the single states. Well, regarding the Baltic Sea... I am sorry. #01:20:58-9#

I: *Would you or would you know if one could transport goods on another way? Could you image that? #01:21:07-1#*

E9: No, I do not think so. Well, it is, as I said... there exists no alternative compared to the vessel regarding such flexibility and such transport capacity. Well, a vessel can quickly enter different harbours and leave them again, can take all sorts of things aboard, also bulky goods, break bulk, heavy cargo. You can load everything onto a vessel. It is... a container also has, also is... a container is variable. There are not just standard containers. There are different types of containers. Well, also in the Scandinavian area or in the Baltic area, whatever, there is absolutely no alternative to sea transport. Well, that is perfect. The whole infrastructure is present. Hamburg, Elbe, Kiel Canal. Well, that is excellent and you also do not have this... well, to shift something to the road I think no one today will somehow announce that with a clean conscience and say: Let us drive a few more trucks somehow to Scandinavia. There everything is already much too packed with trucks. The railway, there is infrastructure is simply not available to transport this mass of goods with the train. And what else do we have? That was it already. #01:22:22-2#

I: *Air. (Laughing) #01:22:23-7#*

- E9: Yes, air, yes. Captive balloon or something. (Ironical) Well, there exists no alternative, not in the feeder area neither. By no means. #01:22:31-9#
- I: *How do you see the competitive situation overall in shipping at the moment?* #01:22:37-5#
- E9: Competition between the single...? #01:22:41-8#
- I: *Between the shipping companies.* #01:22:42-2#
- E9: Oh, between the shipping companies. Yes, incredibly strong competition. Well, the shipping companies, the big liner shipping companies, are growing more and more together. They affiliate, they are growing bigger and bigger. Alliances are being built in order to operate profitably at all. Smaller shipping companies have no prospects on the market. There are only big shipping companies that operate, that also charter from smaller shipping companies and that is turning to that more and more. Well, it grown more and more into, let me say, five big shipping companies and the rest will one day, that will not exist anymore. Well, already now that is incredible. Well, Maersk for example, that is such a giant shipping company or MSC. Those are shipping companies that before... well, MSC, they have started 30 years ago or something. That is now among the biggest shipping companies in the world. That is really incredible what kind of tonnage they have. One cannot imagine that. Well, no one is able to fight that. Well, if I would now resolve to found a shipping company, I could never be that successful to catch up with them one day or something, I do not believe that. Container shipping is tight in the hands of a few shipping companies and that is it. #01:23:59-4#
- I: *What are the biggest chances and risks for the next years?* #01:24:04-0#
- E9: The biggest chances... well, the biggest risks I would say... the biggest risks are always a decline in prices, that the container rates go further down, that more shipping companies fall by the wayside in any case, I think, that the shipping crisis, that still continues, will for the moment not be overcome so fast and I believe in that firmly, because the problem, the real problem leading to the shipping crisis is the oversupply. Too much tonnage, many too many vessels and much too cheap and no quality, but only fast transport from A to B anymore. Cheap, cheap, cheap. Every piece of tat comes from Asia today. Well, I think one could take a thousand products in this room that come from China or somewhere. Meanwhile everything is produced there. One certainly also needs transport capacity, but I simply thing the decline in prices... that they simply do not know what to do with the tonnage and yes, those are the risks. What was the other thing, the...? #01:25:21-0#
- I: *Are there chances?* #01:25:21-8#
- E9: Chances. The chances with certainty are that one could maybe manage to lead the shipping company as a whole into the direction that they in any way build clean ships and operate these vessels very economically, what will evidently also benefit the ship owners. Yes, and certainly as well, clearly, for all of us somehow to operate a vessel in

a really clean way. Emissions are, I think, a huge issue for the future and there maybe are chances to do something there. And maybe finally to free oneself from the conventional ship propulsion that really has existed the way it is today for fifty years. Really nothing has happened in the last fifty years regarding the ship propulsion of large vessels. One really needs to state that. Well, we are here in 2014 and we still have conventionally propelled vessels that burn heavy fuel oil. They have indeed all become a bit more efficient, but really regarding the actual ship propulsion nothing has changed. The vessel size is certainly a factor that makes it more efficient, but the propulsion itself is to a hair the same as on the Cap San Diego²³ lying there. It really is exactly the same, simply a bit bigger. Exactly the same propulsion concept, exactly the same engine really, if you want, a bit bigger and so on, but exactly the same. And then you do ask yourself: Hm, somehow they have tread water a bit and certainly also in view of the lack of legislation. Or the legislation has not made the ship operators do something earlier, because they evidently have – that is a good example for that actually – the ship operator has said: Great, no legislation, I am going on doing my thing, because it is working. The advantage is the operational reliability. Today I have vessels that have few breakdowns, that are very reliable in operation, their construction is fully developed, the engines are technically mature. That is evidently also a fine thing for the ship owner again, but maybe that is now the chance, let me say, to close that chapter, to develop new propulsion systems and to really say: Here, I want to chance something and properly and build something else into the vessel. #01:27:53-4#

I: *What role does environmental legislation play compared to other risks for the ship owner?* #01:27:59-5#

E9: Well, good, the risks overall for the ship owner now... well, environmental legislation does not play a significant role. Well, the ship owner has very different concerns and very different risks to overcome in his normal daily routine as a ship operator, rather than environmental legislation being so important that it does not let him sleep at night. Well, competition and markets, all sorts of things, fuel prices that is for him first priority. Environmental legislation becomes interesting to him only when he already needs to pay a fine, not before that. Well, it needs to be complied with. That is also important to him, but it does not keep him from sleeping I would say. #01:29:01-1#

I: *What other issues are occupying the industry?* #01:29:05-3#

E9: Oh god, yes, well, topic number one is the price deterioration. What I already said: Fuel consumption, cooperation with other shipping companies, mergers are a big issue, especially now in liner shipping. THOSE are the main topics. Staff certainly as well. Yes. They certainly also think every day: Will we still exist in ten years? Or in five? Well, currently nothing is as insecure as the existence of an established shipping company. They can be gone very fast or bought out or something. I think that is what is worrying the people in shipping. #01:30:02-9#

²³ General cargo ship built in 1961. Currently a museum ship in the Hamburg harbour.

- I: *Two last questions: Is there any important issue that I have not touched upon that would be important for me understanding the problems? #01:30:14-7#*
- E9: Relating to what? #01:30:16-5#
- I: *Environmental legislation. #01:30:18-1#*
- E9: Environmental legislation. #01:30:19-1#
- I: *Trade effects of environmental legislation. #01:30:21-4#*
- E9: Well. Environmental legislation... something important in addition... it has really already more or less everything been talked about that is pictured in this diagram. Well, as I said, noise pollution... I would not know about that. #01:30:44-5#
- I: *Would you say that there are trade effects of environmental legislation? #01:30:49-3#*
- E9: Yes, certainly and that will also become stronger and stronger in the future, because environmental legislation is coming more and more into focus now and that will certainly lead to trade effects as well. Yes and it already now has trade effects that one also simply operates with bigger vessels and that one tries to operate more and more efficient due to the cost pressure. Efficiency always also means environmental protection in a metaphorical sense. That I would say. Well, today one handles the use of fuel much more subtle and yes, one thinks about it more, about waste of resources, than one has ten years ago. Ten years ago, I must honestly say, no bastard has been interested in that and that is in the meantime absolutely topic number one. A ton of fuel or how much do I use more? The people are talking a lot about it and that is evidently why it also has incredible implications and that is becoming more and more. And if one also included air pollution and these things then that will one day also force the ship owners to develop their vessels further and it has also always been that way that they have developed their vessels further, just not so incredibly, how shall I say that?, so incredibly much that one can say, yes, well, now we have designed the new super vessel here. It has always gotten a bit better a per cent by a per cent maybe, but that is also the same with air transport, it is similar. Well, one puts more people in, has more economical power units, but the airplane is more or less still powered by kerosene-eating turbines and that is the same as in shipping as well. Everything has become more efficient, but the underlying problem maybe, that one maybe wants get a grip on in the future, still exists, namely that one has the old propulsion systems that burn dirty fuel. Resources are, I think, the main problem of the shipping industry and something has to change there. There something really needs to change, I would say. #01:33:20-3#
- I: *Last question: Do you want to tell me anything else that you have on your mind? #01:33:25-2#*
- E9: No, not really. #01:33:26-5#
- I: *Perfect. Then I am through. #01:33:28-0#*
- E9: Yes, see. #01:33:28-5#

I: *Thank you very much. #01:33:29-5#*

Interview No 10

Date: Tuesday, 16 December 2014, 10 am

Duration: 93 minutes

Method of contact: Contact was established via email only five days prior to the interview. Again, another expert served as a middleman to encourage E10 to take part in the study. E10 agreed to be interviewed if the interview would take place at short notice.

Interview situation: The interview took place in the office building of E10. E10 and the researcher were sitting at one corner of a large table at a comfortable speaking distance. The table was however located openly in a rather busy area. Although no actual disturbance occurred in the form of third persons or other, people were constantly walking by and the voice level was quite significant negatively influencing the interview process as a whole. The interview lasted about an hour and a half.

E10 was friendly and seemed very much at ease in the situation. Information was freely provided, answers contained a lot of detail and technical expertise and E10 did not seem to withhold anything on purpose. A number of answers seemed however to be made on a political notion, trying to influence the researcher to overestimate negative effects of maritime environmental legislation on shipping.

E10: You have come via Mr. Plötzke... well, the VDR [German Shipowners Association] was your initial point of contact, right? #00:00:04-5#

I: *Exactly, exactly, well, in order to get in contact with the ship owners. For the expert interviews I have a rather broad sample. Well, there are all sorts of stakeholders included. Well, but in order to get in contact with the ship owners that interest me.* #00:00:29-4#

E10: What is especially of interest to you? Big ones, small ones, medium sized? #00:00:30-7#

I: *The differences.* #00:00:31-5#

E10: The differences? #00:00:33-0#

I: *Exactly. Well, I have a one-ship company among them and then also very big ones and also the different sectors. Maybe they are fighting with different problems than the container shipping companies.* #00:00:49-1#

E10: That in any case, yes! #00:00:50-0#

I: And that is what is interesting to me. In my doctoral thesis I am investigating trade effects of environmental legislation particularly concerning the shipping industry. Regarding the method currently a lot of expert interviews are taking place that are then followed by a data collection via questionnaires as soon as it becomes clear what the right question actually are. That means that today we try to find out what the right questions actually are. I have a few topics... they deal with the question how the shipping industry is actually affected, impaired by environmental legislation, what kind of things are of relevance and what kind of things are not of relevance. If there are costs impacts or if there are impacts of freight rates and a few variables. Everything that we talk about today will be completely anonymized. It cannot be traced back neither to you nor your company what you are telling me. I am recording it in order to have a full transcript and so that I cannot dream something up that you have told me. Simply for background information, so that I know who I am talking to: In what position do you work here? #00:02:14-2#

E10: In am in engineering, well ship owning. I am leading the group of superindendants. That means we are mainly caring about the operating fleet. Due to the size of our company we have an extra department for newbuildings and we have an extra department for project management who deals with transshipment projects and other specialties, but I am responsible for the operating fleet from the side of the ship owners. Not for the commercial side, that means I am not dealing with the profits of the journeys in the area of commercial profits, but I rather only oversee the budgets for the vessels relating to technical management, operation of the vessels, without fuel. Well, fuel is also not my topic. That is being done in Operations with us. Operations means that [organization 10] has a fleet of round about 500 TC [Time charter] In vessels, that means we are chartering vessel with which we transport our cargo. They are being hired by the chartering department and the cargo is contracted by them. Then operations need to process these journeys in the form of profit-effectuation of what was calculated beforehand. And operations do bunkering, harbour arrangements, agent nominations and such things. Well, that is not my area. For me the vessel is important, if our own ships are in question and those are currently around 30, to handle that, to maintain that, to repair that, to keep the classification status, to hold documents available, crews, for that we have a crewing department, to take part in decision-making there and also the purchase of technical equipment as well as victuals. That is our task. Well, classical ship owners or ship manager, like it is called today, because KG-vessels are being management by a ship management. [“KG-Schiffe werden im ship management bereedert”] Today all of that is provision of services. In our company that is still for the own fleet, whereby they also make sure that we are working economically compared to service providers. That is certainly the case. #00:04:41-1#

I: Does it make a large difference whether it is an own vessel or a chartered vessel in respect of how one deals with the vessel? #00:04:50-1#

E10: That makes a very large difference, because with an owned vessel, if the big boss is saying: Do that! Then that is being done, no matter what that means for the vessel. If we see a commercial advantage we also take critical cargo or other cargo that we... that

other normal owners who do the management, who cannot calculate the risk, would not take. #00:05:10-2#

I: How long have you been working in this field? #00:05:14-2#

E10: In this field or in this company? #00:05:17-2#

I: In this company and in this field. #00:05:19-0#

E10: I have been working in this field for 20 years and in this company for around 15 years. #00:05:26-1#

I: Okay, yes. We can look back on long years of experience. #00:05:31-2#

E10: Yes, actually. #00:05:34-2#

I: What are the issues that currently occupy you the most? #00:05:37-1#

E10: What occupies me the most is the change of the ECA zone to gas oil in the vessel operation. That has certainly been underestimated a bit by the legislators what that means in practice. #00:05:52-1#

I: What does that mean in practice? #00:05:54-1#

E10: That the whole vessel as it sails at the moment maybe needs to be changed in the form of tank configuration in order to achieve appropriate – how does one say in English – cruising ranges in the ECA with gas oil. Because not every tank is gas oil capable and the whole pipeline system in the engine room suddenly needs to be taken apart in order to realize economically justifiable switchover times. And all of that needs to, if we do it right, needs to be officially coordinated with the classification society, and needs to be rebuilt plan-approved. Economically as close as possible to the limit of 2015, because no one on today's market can afford to operate half a year on gas oil when he does not need to. #00:06:48-0#

I: How long does such a change take? #00:06:51-2#

E10: That depends on the vessel. That is totally varied and that depends on the trade, how long do I want to operate in the ECA and all of that is... that is really ship by ship. #00:07:01-0#

I: Hoy exactly should I picture that? Will there be new tanks build in or the pipes...? #00:07:07-0#

E10: No, the tanks that are now on heavy fuel oil... in earlier times one has said low sulphur, heavy fuel oil and heavy, well, raw sulphur-containing heavy fuel oil. Then it was easy, one had heavy fuel oil in both cases. Well, that meant the tanks were heated, one had the transfer pipes in the machine room, that means pumping from the storage tank to the settling tank, from the settling tank – purifier, purifier – day tank. All these pipes where the same whether they were operated with low sulphur or high sulphur. Gas oil for example has due to its properties no necessity to use a purifier, a separator, that

means we pump from the tank to a designated gas oil day tank and from there to the machine and that we evidently preferably want to do with a pipe that does not come in touch with heavy fuel oil, because otherwise we will contaminate it for a long time to come, because the percentage is too low, in order to again... well, if I now have 0.1 bunker I have no possibility to compensate something and that makes difficulties. In the past in the heavy fuel oil range one could from low sulphur – high sulphur, there one had tolerances and if one bought highpercentage heavy oily, sulphur, that had maybe 0.7, then one still had 0.3 for compensation and those are now completely omitted. That means we should preferably separate. Already while bunkering, that means tanks that have before been filled with heavy fuel oil, where the bunker connection is linked to the heavy fuel oil pipe, need to be rebuilt. I suddenly need to access this diesel oil pipe plus I need to connect all diesel oil tanks with this tank in order to be able to bunker. And all those are alterations in fuel-forwarding pipes, thus the fuel tanks need to be gas free, hot work. Those are extreme exercises that shipping has to undertake at the moment that are not making life easier. #00:09:09-0#

I: Is that technically always possible? #00:09:10-2#

E10: Technically virtually everything is possible given appropriate time, given appropriate planning, workshops or crew, depending on how you want to do it. Well, it is possible for that matter. The question is what the shipping company wants to sell, how much cruising area it wants to have. And there we are the... we are our own... we have sat together with the commercial people and have said: Okay, what are the requirements for us and in order to fulfil them it gets a bit more complicated, because they evidently take the own vessel for the more flexible service as well, when it gets difficult. And that is why the requirements remain higher than if I only had to charter out a vessel on the market and I just have this and that much and now it is your problem where you bunker. But also on the market... the market is making sure what the vessel is capable of and what I pay for that. Well, it also has a market value. #00:10:10-2#

I: But that means that there are certain vessels that simply are not at all SECA-friendly or that would be too expensive for that or that are not being used for that any more...? #00:10:18-2#

E10: No, no, no. All ship owners will do that, will retrofit. All vessels will be capable [to operate in the SECA]. I do not see that that a vessel may not enter the SECA, because each vessel does have a certain diesel oil capacity by nature. If I only take that and say: I can only operate for three days in the ECA he may still enter the ECA. He just needs to bunker every three days, worst case. Yes, well, I do not see that. A vessel will be able to enter the ECA. #00:10:43-1#

I: But that then is, if I need to bunker every three days that has to be a clear competitive disadvantage. #00:10:48-0#

E10: Absolutely! #00:10:49-1#

I: Do you have any specific knowledge about environmental legislation due to your background? #00:11:01-1#

E10: The bad thing about shipping is that one has to know everything and is not allowed to miss anything, because otherwise one immediately is the culprit at port state, despite actually having difficulties to have all this information really always at the ready in their whole extensiveness. That is the main problem we have. Port state is worse than classification or flag state. Port state is the highest police authority for us, but not a fair one, that is the main problem. #00:11:38-1#

I: Where do you get the information from what you have to do? #00:11:44-2#

E10: Well, making an effort. Internet, the classification societies help us a lot there, because they are our... We see the classification society as a service provider, not only as a technical expert and certainly the VDR [Association of German Ship Owners], own activities in relevant groups and VDR memberships, in other organisations, for example InterCargo, WHO or something else where we partly participate. #00:12:18-0#

I: Would you say that it is rather easy or difficult to acquire all information? #00:12:24-0#

E10: It is time-consuming. It is incredibly timeconsuming and it is incredibly hard to understand. Well, what politicians release as legislative text or what text is already worked on in discussion, to put that into a usable translation is always the most difficult. That means to participate. Only then one understands the causal relations that are meant. #00:12:52-2#

I: Does such translation work happen here in the house or does someone else deliver the information? #00:12:59-1#

E10: No, no, that is just if one takes part in the work groups of the VDR [Association of German Ship Owners] or if one receives the information via the classification society. They are translating that into shipping English and they say this and that is of relevance and the rest is a covering law and not relevant for the law. #00:13:16-2#

I: Does one need to be able to pay for such information? What does the class charge for such information? #00:13:23-0#

E10: The classification society, as I said, the class is... does not play a role any more. The class? What is the history of the class? The class is the intermediary between the ship owner and the insurance. That is the origin of the class. That means the technical compliance with directions for shipping that means the technical controls, like the Technical Control Board [TÜV]. That is the function of the class. That is very important for new-building. That is later in the annual class survey regarding the extensiveness of the documentation almost not altogether tenable any more. In the rest of their function the class is at the most a service provider for me. Everything else relating to environmental legislation that I need to implement are... are more or less mostly flag-state-relevant that means statutory certificates or statutory things that the flag states

handles and not the class. But rather that the class offers on behalf then, because it wants to make use of its service network. So that the flag state has by far a greater importance than the class and the flag states implement, perceive that differently to inform their let me say members quote unquote. #00:14:47-0#

I: That means do there exist better and worse [flags] in this area? #00:14:51-2#

E10: Absolutely, yes. #00:14:53-2#

I: Does that play a role when I am with a worse class... #00:14:57-1#

E10: Not class, flag! #00:14:58-0#

I: Flag, sorry. Then I am necessarily worse informed? #00:15:04-0#

E10: That is certainly an issue that one has to think about. Yes, well, flag choice is a difficult story. A lot of issues play a role there. A lot of different emphases. What I always... I always hear, yes, well, flag of convenience... Liberia for example to me is a first class flag who takes things like informing members or registered client information very seriously and operates exemplary and by that has reached a very high safety standard with a very large fleet. #00:15:42-2#

I: Which flags are not able to achieve that? #00:15:44-1#

E10: All of them are able to do that. They just need to pay for that. That is costing money. You simply have to provide enough people who are running to the IMO, who understand that, who are knowledgeable there, who take part in the votes there, who translate that back again to the shipping level and tell it to the people. That is money. That is about money. #00:16:08-1#

I: And if I am with a worse flag, does that mean that I have a less clean...? #00:16:16-1#

E10: That has absolutely nothing to do with that. No, no! That is the responsibility of the owner. How do I implement the regulations? And that has nothing to do with clean or unclean at all. There are people operating very modern vessel because they, how to say this, not simpler, but just unnoticed through the world and the trailblazers [“Vorprescher”] are and say: We are the clean shipping people. I always see the difficulty there. The one thing printed on the paper, nicely in high gloss: We are green shipping and do everything great and the others who do a good job and do not appear at all. That is how I see it. #00:16:56-1#

I: Are all ship operators equally well informed or are there differences? #00:17:03-2#

E10: There certainly exist differences. And there exists a clear tendency for me that the big companies have an information advantage over the small companies due to the higher number of employees and actually also due to managers who have the time to go to such committees, that is what I think. Because it is very difficult to combine that, to stay up-to-date and to handle the daily work abroad, in part docking and repairs and at the same time to stay informed is very difficult, almost impossible. #00:17:38-0#

I: What current advances are known to you that are happening at the moment in the area of environmental legislation? #00:17:45-1#

E10: How far does environmental legislation go? All MARPOL provisions are environmental provisions. Solar in parts are IMO provisions and there exist national provisions in every country that unfortunately affect shipping also more and more. That means do we now want to talk internationally about IMO? IMO is... for a long time they have been talking about CO₂ emissions. Gas, well, greenhouse gas emission regulation... they have tried to introduce market-based measures, but they have fallen flat on their face. Now they are simply trying a watered-down version using monitoring systems. The EU almost has a monitoring system on the line, as quasi national law, but is then again led up the same garden path [“auf das gleiche Glatteis”] that it has managed to take for air transport, where it has also landed flat on its face. One will see how that will influence shipping when national states or national areas are demanding such a thing and a vessel, a big ship owner that comes here one time and suddenly a thing is asked of him that he is not at all interested in, that brings a bulk of administration, if he is not saying: Okay, then I am just not going there, basta! One will have to see that. Or if they say: Okay, here I am, do try to stop me. And that would be competitive distortion. Well, I am keen to see that, but what is happening apart of that: We have a new MARPOL V. It has not yet been implemented in the whole world, but is already totally enforced, that means a huge problem for bulk shipping. Washing water disposal through the hatches is partly not allowed any more. But there are also no exception rules, thus twilight zone. #00:19:49-1#

I: Thus, what is happening then? #00:19:51-1#

E10: We inform our flag state that we have a problem with the twilight zone and ask him to show us a solution and because he is also not able to do that he will at a certain point say: I will take note of that. And we will then pump it out someplace with the knowledge of the state, because he is also not able to do anything. IMO cannot do anything. No one can do anything, but the rule exists. That means in the harbour states, or in the harbours the facilities are missing to implement these regulations. That has nothing to do with money... well, after all it has to do with money. Because no one in the harbour is willing to invest in infrastructure thus things do not get there. It would be profitable. We could demand a lot of money from the ship owner or cargo owner for the clean up, but there are no facilities, thus they cannot demand that. That is how it is. #00:20:42-1#

I: Which measures occupy you the most at the moment? #00:20:47-0#

E10: Yes, at the moment the ECA switch. And I am intensively dealing with the CO₂ area by way of lobbying activities at the VDR [German ship owners association]. That will also be the next thing that will more strongly concern the entire shipping industry, because it restricts the regulations for newbuildings, because it restricts a little bit the operation of vessels and because it signifies a lot of red tape for ship owners. #00:21:22-1#

I: What will then likely be the next step? What do you expect? #00:21:27-1#

E10: Yes, the European will put their monitoring system into law. That has passed this triple party agreement, then everyone just shortly needs to raise the finger and it is through. And then it is being enforced, I don't know, '17, '18, no idea. And then it will have to be transferred into national law again in the EU. That still has a bureaucratic run. And then we start to build up our bureaucracy. Those are amounts of administration that no one can yet really picture. #00:22:04-0#

I: The reporting alone will be really... #00:22:06-1#

E10: All the environmental laws that at the moment... in the last ten years... I don't know exactly, I do not want commit myself, but all environmental laws only signify red tappe for us. Physically they have not changed shipping operations at all. We have paper, documentations, what we are supposed to do, what we do. That is all. Just paper. The vessel as such nonetheless needs to get from A to B, nonetheless tries most economic. That is what we economically as a basic rule always do. That means fuel is much too expensive to waste. Thus we do that furthermore that we bring the cargo from A to B with concentrated attention, best experience and best practice using the most economic mode and trying simply to bring in our basic materials like fuel, lubricating oil profitably. There are other people who claim that we put that into the sea, but we have a very different opinion on that and have had for a long while. We simply need to document that. That is the whole legislation. Green shipping or something is just creating paper in order to show what we have daily done before already. #00:23:33-1#

I: How has environmental legislation developed in the last years? #00:23:37-0#

E10: Yes, everybody looks at his own area. Ballast water treatment, best example. We are on the one hand talking about CO₂ savings. On the other hand we are now talking about each vessel getting a treatment facility that is an absolutely immense waste of energy [“Energieverschwendung hoch drei”]. That means we will have a larger carbon footprint for the same amount of transport services performed. That means one is only looking at the one issue and is forgetting the adjacent issue. One is not doing a comprehensive survey of the system shipping. That does not exist. In the IMO it is also going like that. There are sub-committees that deal with a thing. They are then coming up with a solution for this one thing and the adjacent issue is not being looked at. That is a recurrent problem. [“Das zieht sich durch wie ein roter Faden”] Naturally I can treat ballast water. But I can also imagine for example that one would release the ballast water with a pump that is a little bit more powerful to the shore and it is treated there. That would have substantial advantages. The facility would be 100 per cent used to capacity. You can locally determine in which way from where you want to treat the water for you local area and the investment would have a higher return, because it is simply being used sensibly. It can be maintained by people who are engaged in that. The investigation whether it has really been treated like the state wants it and very well be analysed and monitored. While now, with the rule that is coming now, each vessel needs such a facility worth 3, 4 million, depending on the size. That has a utilization efficiency of 5 per cent, 6 per cent. And then it is being scrapped. And on top of that these other people are coming and want to know from US if it really holds what the manufacturer promises,

which we are not at all able to check, because we no not have a laboratory aboard. Question: Is that right? In my eyes in the bulk trade it is not. If you look at a big vessel, Panmax upward, Capesize, that has key ports where it takes its cargo. Those are iron ore mines, coal mines; those are the very big ports. Vast quantities of ballast water are released there. A shore based facility would make a lot of sense there and the vessels would be extremely unburdened by that and that would make sense. But this way, that everyone is doing it for himself and everyone may then again be detained... one more reason to detain... I do not know if that is right. #00:26:13-1#

I: Does that only apply for bulk vessels? #00:26:16-7#

E10: Bulker and tanker. Container vessels have been living for years – also before the ballast water discussion – mainly from ballast water management, because through many small tanks respective to the cargo allocation the water is just being apportioned and only small amounts are collected or released, depending on the cargo situation. Never 100 per cent. Meanwhile a bulk vessel... we are loading a whole batch and have to release 100 per cent ballast water. Then we are sailing to the port of discharge, we empty out 100 per cent and take 100 per cent ballast water in again. Exactly the same applies to a tanker. For us that is an entirely different issue than for a container vessel. The first ballast water treatment facilities came up and were advertised with: We can do 250m³/h. For us that is a no-brainer, we cannot make use of that in the slightest. We will be thrown off the pier if we do not take as much as this ship can take as cargo and that means we have to hold available very high ballasting capacities. We have now had the first vessel delivered with a ballast water treatment facility that is now doing 5.500m³/h. For that you need 2`000 ampere continuous current. That has to come from somewhere. In addition to the by far larger ballast pumps of 375 kW. Those are powers – and that is environmental pollution. #00:27:49-2#

I: Does that also extend the time that the vessel needs to stay somewhere due to the ballast water pumps... #00:27:57-6#

E10: That is exactly why the system needs to be so big in order to keep that controlled. Otherwise we lose the possibility to operate the vessel, because many terminals are clearly also calculating: Our terminal costs this and that much. In contrast we need to load this and that many vessels only then we are getting enough money in again. And in Australia for example they are black-listing the vessels. That means if a vessel is not able to take enough cargo in a certain amount of time then it is not allowed to come back. Deal done. #00:28:24-3#

I: Does that mean that no thought is given to different business models at the IMO level? If it is being said that container vessels manage rather well, but... #00:28:34-1#

E10: IMO, there are no shipping people present... well, there are shipping experts, the VDR is there as an advisory body, but the voting is eventually done by the states, the coastal states. And they are evidently also driven by political decisions. That means if it is supposed to be green like ballast water then evidently the biologists and others are very strong. They call the shots and they give in the end the advisory vote for the state, or

they are winning recognition with the politicians and they are saying: Okay, you are voting for this. Rather less the shipping politics or the shipping experts. The results is that due to that in my eyes ballast water has not yet been ratified in the EU, because many have then realized: Oh, these and those problems are still all there that have not yet been thoroughly discussed. Then the biologists want to do testing under all circumstances and cannot develop a sensible sampling procedure for the whole thing. And then certain flag states are find out that if they would sign it with a large fleet then suddenly their fleet would not be worth much any more and are not signing it. The regulation at IMO is 35 states or 35% of the fleet. #00:30:14-0#

I: Yes, they are almost there. #00:30:15-1#

E10: Yes, but they are not yet there, because the ones that could now swing it are clearly saying: I am not signing that. And for us that is now one of the biggest problems to assess that. Will that now soon be signed? Will it not be signed? We are talking about two to three million per vessel in newbuildings and in retrofits even more. Well, and the timeline that has been set, which may not be changed anymore, because the ratification process is under way, is soon running out. No one knows what he is supposed to do. And the Americans have then surged ahead and have said: We need our own rule. They have done their own rule but cannot produce a single approved facility. What will the ship owner do with them? To build in a five year approved facility for 3 million in order for them to tell him after 5 years: Sorry, you cannot use that one here anymore. Be so nice to dismount it again. You cannot sell that anywhere. Those are the problems, well, that is now coherent. And that is extremely difficult for the shipping industry. One day it will come to real conflicts I would say. Even if they would now have one approved system I would not know of a single producer who would be able to build enough systems to equip the world fleet. And how is that supposed to work? #00:31:45-1#

I: Exactly that is what I asked myself anyway regarding the retrofits for the SECAS, when all vessels need to get into the shipyards at the same time... #00:31:54-1#

E10: We are not going into the shipyard. The most difficult in the ECA zone is the tank cleaning. That is the most displeasing and the most difficult. The pipelines, that is alright. With a little bit of fantasy and a little bit of clever thinking that is manageable... #00:32:09-4#

I: That one can do oneself so to say... #00:32:10-2#

E10: ...over time one can do a lot or prepare a lot in the last shipyard visit or something, but tank cleaning is really difficult. And that is why one experiences a very high need for tank cleaning in Asia at the moment. Well, the workshops are raising their prices very much, because all sorts of people now still need to clean one or two tanks. That seems to be true. They do it in Asia for Europe, because no one can pay for that in Europe anymore. (Laughing) #00:32:45-2#

I: Which aims have already been achieved if one looks at environmental legislation? #00:32:54-2#

E10: Which aims have already been achieved... Yes, well, it has already been achieved that it is legally forbidden to pour oil into the water, what one has before already tried to avoid forever based on sanity and reason. Where the pressure on manufacturers has become a little bigger is to optimize the systems a bit. The oil separator technology however has NOT changed significantly despite the new legislation. When I still went to sea, that was 1974 to '84, the oil separators have not been much different than the way they still are today. And the [carbon filters?] that is a thing to make 5 parts per million that has been retrofit or upgradet by the industry, that is new, yes. But apart from that, what has become much more is surveillance, surveillance, surveillance. Eletronic monitors for the water that we emit. But the technology behind... (Laughing) #00:34:05-2#

I: What would have to be done? #00:34:08-1#

E10: I can just say that from the shipping side: Much better publicity. That means we as associations need to take money into our hands and illuminate people that... there are now so many people reporting on all the plastics in the ocean. That is not on us. That is being alleged: Shipping. No! We have garbage management plans. We document our garbages. We have incenerators aboard. We have to give off garbage in the harbour. We have to have ash at the harbour, otherwise we are being detained. Well, we do not have a system anymore in order to throw anything overboard, but one would have to visit the coastal regions in Asia in order to know where the stuff comes from. Well, that would have to be published for once. Right!? Every vessel needs to give off garbage, needs to prove by way of a certificate how much they have given off and where. We are only allowed anymore to release shredded food waste into the ocean to make the fish happy that something is coming. Incredible! Yes, and when we come to harbours saying: We now have our garbage here, we are overflowing and the Americans for example then say: No, not you. #00:35:33-0#

I: Because? #00:35:35-2#

E10: No, not because! Or rather to a price that is insane. Why do they have to tell us a reason? They are like: No. That is exactly like the WHO. In the past we had a deratting certificate, that we had no rats aboard. Today we have a health exemption, a sanitary exemption certificate. That they were not able to issue in America for years because they did not have the local administration for that. But in every harbour, they have demanded that it was valid. Well, such things make it difficult. It is so bad that we do not need to think about interior decoration of the superstructures anymore, because there are only regulations affixed that have to be there, that have to hang there, and the wallpaper is already secured. We only need to put all the regulations that we all have to stable on that, and we do not know anymore if that is a red wall, a green wall. And no one is reading that anymore. This superabundance of information aboard – no one is looking at that anymore. There is a direction on each sink how one is supposed to wash one's hands. Is anyone too stupid to do that? #00:36:54-1#

I: If we now look at the legislative procedure. Which lobby is more powerful? #00:37:03-1#

E10: Which lobby is more powerful? #00:37:05-2#

I: Mhm. (In agreement) #00:37:06-1#

E10: No. I would see that differently. Which national interests are more powerful; that is it. We would long have had market based measures, we guess, if there would not have been 1,2 countries that would have made use of their power – and those are powerful ones, those are China and Brazil – and got up and said: Sorry, we have not signed Kyoto. We will also not sign there. And by that it is dead to the IMO. Because it requires unanimity. And that was a killer. That means that it is about national interests. #00:37:45-2#

I: I did not know that. How is environmental legislation being enforced? #00:37:50-1#

E10: Enforced? In shipping really only the IMO is binding for me, or just now national laws, or national requirements for different national areas. And if the national areas... America is bad. They give us a lot of requirements for paper work. They need to be met if one wants to be economically successful there. It is simply being enforced by law and order. Here, take this, do that! #00:38:23-1#

I: Is that a successful enforcement. Or is it possible to get around it? #00:38:30-2#

E10: No, well I would [see] no way... (Laughing) How shall I describe it... (Laughing) If one wants to do business in Europe according to a certain standard as an economic firm, worldwide and in the transport sector shipping, one needs to stick to the rules. If one wants to operate on the cheap then one does not need to. Then one simply gets there... I have seen a Chinese ship. For me that was the (Laughing) no-no. He did not have a class anymore and he still could pass through any harbour in America with the stamp from port state control. Everything fine. Because, yes because the detention for the ship... the owner would have said: Here, take that crap, see what you do with it. That means that there are two groups. The one is saying: I am so low that if they detain me it it their vessel. We have also had a few in Europe lying in the harbours where we then had to pay the crew and everything. And the others need to comply with everything to 100 per cent. One can also observe the port state [control]. They are going on the good vessels. On the ones where they know: I would have to chain them up here and that is a problem for the harbour there they are not seen. #00:39:53-1#

I: That means such vessels are also operating in Europe? #00:39:57-2#

E10: If it does not matter to them, yes. You can also do nothing against that. What will you do against that? Chain vessels up here, okay and then you have the crap lying in front of your door. That is going to stay like that. ISM has not gotten rid of that, port state will not get rid of that, no one will get rid of that. That is reality. #00:40:20-1#

I: What happens next in the area of environmental legislation? #00:40:30-1#

E10: As I said that was gas that is exhaust gas that is coming up next. We will see how that develops. And as I said, the EU has decided their measures, they will certainly go forward with that and they will... they have put in that if the IMO puts similar regulations into effect internationally they would recall theirs. That is the only reassurance. How long the IMO still takes however, no one knows. #00:40:58-1#

I: *I have tried to depict the different ways of pollution a little that we have in the area of operations... (showing chart) #00:41:12-0#*

E10: That is a crap vessel. That has containers on it... #00:41:11-2#

I: *(Laughing) Sadly I only have this chart. Right, dumping of waste and ballast water we have already talked about. Air pollution, harmful hull coatings, noise, oily water and then all other sewage waters. Does the chart make sense? #00:41:37-0#*

E10: Yes, it does... One sees everything on it that is in the public discussion. We have been doing sewage treatment on our ships already since the 60s by biological sewage water facilities that are equivalent to every sewage treatment plant on land. That means black and grey water is being treated by bacterial growth and is then being let outboard. These facilities still have valid IMO approval. They are still state of the art. Also nothing has really developed much, but what some states ask is a disinfection of the water before pumping it out, what however signifies a total chlorination without control. That is questionable for the environment, because I am pouring chlorine into the environment. I do not know if that is beneficial. With a little bit of – how shall I say – human waste in the sewage water, that is maybe not decomposed to 100 per cent in a biological treatment facility, nature is easily coping with. Otherwise the world would be a huge turd. [“Scheißhaufen”] Right! (Laughing) Well, for a freight ship with 21 people aboard I see not further grounds for action at all. We are talking about cruiseliners. There the situation is a little different. However also there it needs to be recognized what kind of effort cruiseliners are already making in order to reasonably operate environmentally-friendly. Well, that is a measure that does not really raise new questions. Oily water from the machine room... well, as I said, we have used oil separators already in the 60s. We still use oil separators working with gravity or through immulsion breakers, labyrinth layout in the oil separators. Coal filter? Has been added after... We have fulltime supervised oil monitors. Every port stater can take a look at the operation of the oil monitor at any time for years back. That is no longer an issue of discussion. #00:44:08-2#

I: *One always asks oneself... because there are these flyovers and they are again and again finding oil spills in large numbers on the Baltic Sea. #00:44:17-0#*

E10: Come off it, where do they find them? Large numbers... Those are then the ships that they are also not chaining up in the harbour because they are then inheriting the ship. I cannot throw away more money then when I am throwing my oil away. I can either burn it or use it for lubrication. I need to take care of something and that is ship management. I have to animate the people to use little chemicals for cleaning so that my oily water separator does not become unstable. I have to try – like in the past – to wash my soot

sludge off with diesel oil that immediately separates in the waste water separator and to try not to use some sort of immulsion breaking cold cleaner for cleaning who surely will not let the immulsion break in my oil water separator neither and then it is overboard, yes! That is ship management. Little chemicals also mean little costs. Well and that is to be seen in the interest of everybody that he cleans his things aboard with as natural cleaning methods as possible. And if I have an oily bilge I am losing money. Every business man or every half reasonable ship manager will try to minimize that. #00:45:41-0#

I: Makes sense, yes. #00:45:43-0#

E10: Well, those are the issues, that... And MARPOL I is the oldest rule. That has already existed for how many years? I don't know that from the top of my head. '79? Could be, right? Noise pollution, yes... That is why we are building all these wind mills in the North Sea, right? (Ironical) Evidently we are responsible for a certain noise emission. That cannot be avoided; for the combustion engine and for the propeller least of all. Then we have to go back to sailing ships. Let me say that regarding noise pollution we are already on a good way. Our ships are operating at 13 knots max. Every container does not manage to do 13 knots as minimum speed thus I am not feeling like one of the main polluters. The power is at least to the second if not exponent cubed if I am going faster. We are rather the slow ones and that is why we are making the least noise. Anti-fouling, yes! Is anti-fouling a type of pollution? No anti-fouling – the vessel is grown over – has very many barnacles – has a lot of resistance in the water – I have incredible amounts of fuel that I need to burn in order to get forward, that means on the CO₂ balance I am falling very much to the back. The order of the day is to find a compromise. And there are already rules in the anti-fouling area which heavy metals were prohibited. That was another one of these rules that has long been obsolete when it finally came into force. There no longer existed any coatings any more that still contained that at all. Well, there again the law was significantly slower then the business who had already implemented that in the end, because these coatings simply did not exist any more. The legislator did not manage to keep up, because he again could not get any signitures. Well, that was a toothless tiger. #00:47:39-1#

I: The colours that are now being used: Do they still emit a lot to the environment or what kind of coatings are those? #00:47:47-2#

E10: Those are still self-polishing coatings with a little better technology and with a little better composition that the surface parts easier in order to bring new biocides to the fore. No thick – we call that leach layers – lying above that that it cannot come out. They are however already strongly adapted to the ship speed, ships area, where the vessel operates. There exist silicone trials with varied results. Silicone does only emit this silicone oil into the environment anymore, but... Let me say it like this: Each yacht owner has to ask himself how he is doing it. That means for pleasure we are doing the same thing. Because it is not possible any other way. And that is also a discussion that has to be held looking at the big picture. Anti-fouling cannot be discussed when discussing on the CO₂ side. Anti-fouling for us is the absolute economic factor in order

to be able to economically, sensibly do shipping. Otherwise we can forget it with the fuel consumption. There we have no course of action any more. That is how it is. Because that is also this air pollution. Well, and air pollution... there we are again at the same starting point. We have different pollutants in the air: NO₂, SO_x, and then CO₂ as a greenhouse gas. We certainly have more NO_x as liability than a passenger car, because our motors are trimmed to operate economically. If we want to reduce NO_x as a persistent, wide-ranging polluter we have to accept significantly higher fuel... accept higher specific fuel consumptions. That is the same in passenger cars. That will not be different in shipping. If we want to do something there in the direction of improvements we have to accept less efficient motors. That is the way it is. SO_x is under way. As I said, that is fuel independent or simply after-treatment facilities. And the CO₂ discussion is an idle discussion. CO₂ depends entirely on the state of the economy. Now everyone is doing slow steaming, because anyway there is nothing happening on the market. If all hell would be let loose on the market like in 2008 everyone would say: Full steam ahead! Every fuel, it does not matter, gone, will be covered by the market, easy! Thus we are operating at full steam. And then CO₂ is there again like crazy. Otherwise the legislator would have to say: I need a speed limit. But then I would say to the legislator: Then do limit your trucks as well. And the train and all the other modes of transport relating to speed. Then you can come to us and well, with you as well. Apart from that I do not see that. No political options. Well, ballast water, as we said, is an issue that from my point of view is tackled entirely wrong by biologists. Would they have said: Okay, ballast water, we want to go to 5, 15 mic or whatever – filter and then filter 95 per cent of all species out and that is then fine the thing would be through. Then we would have had a ballast water filter aboard for 10 years already and everyone would be happy, and we would have solved 95 per cent of the problem. However, as they want to have 110 per cent the thing is floating. That is a political will thus it is also politically not viable. The technician has been left on the way. (Laughing) And dumping of waste is a joke. We are not allowed to do dumping of waste. #00:52:21-2#

I: *Which of these legislative initiatives are the most expensive for shipping?* #00:52:32-1#

E10: That depends how they are being implemented in the future. As I said: This (pointing on air pollution) is not final, that is not final (pointing on ballast water) and there (pointing on noise pollution) no one has done anything so far in the form of legislation. One does have certain rules for vibration aboard, but that is manageable. (Pause) Well, for container shipping this (pointing on ballast water) not as bad as for us. For them however this (pointing on air pollution) is much worse. Those are the differences for you. Well, the container man will have a huge problem here (pointing on air pollution) and I will have a problem there (pointing on ballast water). #00:53:21-2#

I: Do bulkers and tankers have similar concerns? #00:53:29-0#

E10: Tankers still have different concerns as well. Well, tankers have different concerns. They have the same concerns in the ballast area, but apart from that they have different concern than we do. We have wash water in the hatches, they have tank cleaning by slot system, which however based on older laws, because that has been much more important

at the time, because the pollution was much bigger, based on older laws they already have shore facilities. They are releasing their slot ashore. A refinery HAS to take it and that is how it has been decided. Let me just say, if we have washed a hatch that has had carbon then we have a little bit of carbon dust in the wash water. Hundreds of billions of tons of carbon are lying in the environment. (Laughing) Who is bothered if that little bit of wash water is going it? That is settling down, that is gone. That really is the question. That is the difference. While the oil remains swimming above. Or iron ore hatch for example... at a designated iron ore carrier today bulldozer-clean is already in the charter party. That means once the bulldozer has scraped through it the hatch is good for the next load. One also has to keep things in proportion. Concentrates, fertilizers,... there we certainly wash. Corn! There the shipper is demanding that the thing is really clean. Yes, those are specifications for us from the outside. And then we are washing and then we need to pump the water. #00:55:01-1#

I: If one now compares your concept or business model with container shipping. Do they have it easier or more difficult? Will it be more expensive for them? #00:55:15-0#

E10: No, they have no problems with cleaning the hatches, because the cargo should normally always stay in the box. The difference between them and us is that the container people hide their ballast trip in empty containers. We have to do the ballast trip. The container people on the other hand always operate half empty on average. While we, when we are loaded, scandlink draft, not a single more gram will fit in there. We are operating at significantly lower speeds. That means if we look at the efficiency – what the EU, what the IMO are also saying, this energy efficiency index, if that is now operation or design, is always based on a transported ton of cargo per fuel amount. There we are evidently far ahead of the containers, far, far, far. They can never make even. That is why they unfairly simply only count the TEU that they COULD take on. This one is half empty. That is not a fair discussion. Regarding cargo utilization, what the vessel can carry and what it actually carries, we are certainly better. However, we are not able to sell that enough. That for example is also an issue, yes. #00:56:35-2#

I: Which shipping companies are most affected by environmental... #00:56:41-1#

E10: All the same! That does not matter. Everyone needs to participate. Everyone has these issues. If a container breaks and he needs to clean the cargo hold, he has the same problems. He however has much more to do with fuel and air pollution. Anti-fouling wear is much higher with him due to higher speeds. All those things are different in nuances, but in the end, it is all operating vessels that underlie the same legal acts. I do not see a big difference there. #00:57:14-2#

I: Are there companies that get away relatively scot-free? #00:57:17-1#

E10: Yes! The grey ones. The army. They are caring crap about all that. (Laughing) No, but apart from that... (Laughing) That get away scot-free... We are following different approaches. The one wants to be first class carrier and want to advertise that and follow his business model and other say: Okay, I am in the low segment and I want to work very differently. Anti-fouling for example: We are also investigating whether we should

use high-tech antifoulings in order to maybe improve the efficiency of the vessels, minimize friction losses in order to be better on the market. Such things, yes, are being investigated and undertaken, but not due to legal reasons, but due to marketing tactical reasons. The legislator prescribes a minimum amount that needs to be fulfilled and shipping itself is in many areas much further, because it does take part in the market that is currently extremely hard, that is almost not existing anymore. #00:58:35-1#

I: Can one sell such an idea like green shipping to the customer for higher prices? #00:58:42-2#

E10: To a minor degree. On a small scale, but not on a big scale. Currently we have enough tonnage on the market that the customer can choose whom he takes. That then means that if I do green shipping it can make the difference that I do win the tender, but not necessary that I get a premium because of that. If the market is the other way round, that tonnage is short and cargo so much then every vessel is being taken, then it does not matter. Well, at the moment it is a little bit like the shipper can choose and he will certainly, if he has an ISO certificate, say: Okay, I take the one with a little higher standard as my partner. But that does not mean that we get a premium. #00:59:34-1#

I: Are there companies that overcomply with environmental legislation as a rule and that are always better than they need to be? #00:59:46-1#

E10: That is difficult. Overcomply. How can I overcomply with a sewage treatment? Overcomply with oily water? Well, there are companies who say: We want to stand out as a green sustainable company. That exists. If they are now overcomplying with anything can be set aside for the moment. Because: It depends on how big the company is, how much it sells, how much it transports. Does it transport too much, does it only transport for the sake of transporting or are we acting in a way that we really offer tailored to suit the market's needs? I do not know that. #01:00:36-1#

I: What keeps ship owners from complying with certain environmental laws? #01:00:43-0#

E10: If they are as clear as ballast water (Ironical) that keeps us from implementing that, because they are really not transparent if they are not clearly outlining a clear approach to a solution. Ballast water is the best example. Nothing moves. If the legislator is not able to pass a clear rule that very obviously keeps the ship owner from following it. And then there will be no support. Very, very simple statement. #01:01:14-1#

I: One reads time and by that it is less costly to pay fines than to comply with certain laws. #01:01:24-1#

E10: That is over today. The fines are so very crazy, crazy. To speak very honestly, from my personal... what we experience here in the fleet... I would not want to go to sea with my mate's certificate anymore, because I would always just be risking prison sentences. ["Mit einem Bein im Gefängnis stehen"] Accidents happen, human errors happen, all sorts of things happen at sea. You cannot always immediately end in prison for that.

That is why that leads to all let me say clever seafarers that own a reasonable certificate to quickly search for something ashore and to not placed at the disposal of shipping any more so that we have to try and survive with the weaker candidates that do not see through the big picture, which is not beneficial for the environmental system in shipping. And that is a very clear statement. I stand by that, because there are things that can make one wonder: How is the captain able to help it, how is the chief able to help it? He has reported, he has done this and as a punishment he goes to prison for that, thank you. Not with me! #01:02:26-0#

I: Is it more difficult for some companies than for others to comply with the rules? #01:02:31-2#

E10: No. Why? For the ones who have no money, for them it will get difficult, but that is a market situation that is the same everywhere. In the industry, everywhere. #01:02:45-2#

I: If it is also a financial question: It is possible to say that it is somehow related to company size? Do small ones have to carry a greater lot than big ones? #01:02:55-2#

E10: I am going to say what I said in the beginning: For the small ones it is always more difficult to be up to date with all the information that they need in order to follow. And they cannot do anticipatory tests. That is certainly a little better in a big company. #01:03:15-0#

I: Does it depend in any way on the flag or seat of operations? #01:03:22-1#

E10: Flag is as I said also an issue. Flag really is an issue. And what was the other thing? #01:03:30-0#

I: Seat of Operations, that is main seat of the company. #01:03:32-2#

E10: No... #01:03:33-0#

I: Is it possible to say: Russian companies are rather like this, German ones rather like that? #01:03:37-0#

E10: Russian companies certainly have a different approach, partly. (Laughing) How shall I say that? I cannot say: Hey, corruption simply does play a role in Russia that is how it is. But apart from that the seat of the company does not play a role for the technical ship management area. I cannot imagine that. #01:04:07-0#

I: In order to come back to harbour state controls – do they always check for everything? #01:04:15-1#

E10: Yes! #01:04:16-1#

I: That means I cannot extricate myself from any of the rules? #01:04:24-0#

E10: The harbour state control approach has once started with safety, with the pretension to just check for safety. I do not see that at all. They are really normally checking

everything. Time and again and are partly coming from requirements that by far exceed the law. That is always difficult. With a vessel that is well maintained I can... and there is certainly "There is a sign missing here", because everything is already signed, because everything is already paved with paper and then there is again a hydrant sign missing then that is worth at least 2,000 dollars for the Ukraine. But then the problem is not that that sign is missing, but the problem is that the guy is lacking 2,000 dollars. If that goes on further and it is not just the Ukraine, it is many countries in the world, then the harbour state controls remain a pain in the neck and do not have very much to do with the actual task. There are however also states like Australia that overdo it in every respect. The ones who have invented shipping. That is why they no longer have a single ship under their flag, because no one can afford that any more. But then haul us over the coals with their demands. #01:05:41-1#

I: If something is not as it should, who is then liable? Owner or operator? #01:05:49-3#

E10: The owner is certainly the one. The owner is always responsible for the ship availability, for the service of the ship. He charters out a transport machine in accordance with the laws. That is written down in the charter party. That means the owner is the who has to care for everything. #01:06:06-9#

I: How does that work in the SECA for example, if the wrong type of fuel... #01:06:12-1#

E10: Now we get to the point. The disponent owner has to care for that. That is the charterer, because he cares for the... your vessel goes to there and your vessel needs to get fuel from me for that, then also the appropriate fuel. That is the charterer. And then we get again to the vessel speeds. The owner hands a transport machine to the charterer and the disponent owner, the charter is saying how fast he goes. That means as an owner I have no influence on air pollution, because I do not provide the fuel, do not prescribe the ship speed. Again other groups are doing that, who are not seizable in legislation. That is why it always goes to the ship owner and the ship owner cannot manage any more. That is the biggest problem with air pollution with CO₂ monitors. Due to the monitoring the consumption should go back. That is the political framework. That is feasible. If I am now operating during these years with the bad market I am even sailing a bulker at less than 13 knots. If it picks up and the charterer is saying: You have a 13 knots machine, now I want to see 13 knots then I have to do that, whether my monitoring results gets worse or not. #01:07:30-2#

I: How is that being solved? #01:07:33-2#

E10: No idea. I will just report worse numbers then. In return I have a higher transport output. (Laughing) #01:07:42-2#

I: Is it possible to say that the average age of the fleet is a good indicator for environmental friendliness? #01:07:49-2#

E10: No, no, no! What we have seen in the years 2004 to 2008 for example is that the shipyards have built a standard type. That type of vessel has been chosen based on the best production procedure and not on the best economy of the ship. And the shipyards

were booked out. When a ship owner wanted to build a ship the shipyard has said: This is my vessel. Take it or leave it. Thus, the owner had no opportunity to build environmentally friendly or more economic ships, because they had no supplier. That has changed with the crash in 2008. We for example have only started then to order and that according to our specifications when the shipyards were hungry and have said: Okay, you can use your design and I want to build it. The main thing is that I have something to do. Then it was possible again to build environmentally friendly ships. That means that the supplying industry does not always offer environmental friendly ships and the ship owner than has no possibility to get them. That is why the age of the fleet only is related to that if it fits into this time frame. #01:09:15-2#

I: How are shipping companies influences in their business model by environmental legislation? #01:09:25-1#

E10: Business model... There are so many models in shipping. Wow! I do not know that. (Laughing) Geschäftsmodell... (Laughing) #01:09:40-2#

I: What is now happening here for example? #01:09:45-1#

E10: Nothing happens at all. We no that we – if we now talk from the operations side of view – well, with the chartered vessels we simply need to calculate with higher fuel costs if we are operating in the ECA and we need to incorporate that in our calculations from the beginning. If we can generate the equivalent amount back from the customer I do not know. I do not believe so. But in any case, whether we have profit or loss, it in any case needs to go in there from be beginning. That is it. In my eyes it influences the margin. One simply has to try to incorporate that in time and then one has to see whether one can live with that or whether one has to give up the business because it does not yield any profit anymore. #01:10:36-0#

I: Are there any changes in the fleet structure? #01:10:40-1#

E10: We will see. In our business area, bulk, there is a total oversupply, because investors have jumped in when actually the hype was already over. The vessels are now all entering the market. It will separate between the economic vessels and the ones build or contracted between '4 and '8 that are not economic. They are maybe already in young years going on the beach and are being scrapped. That could happen, that could be a consequence of the market. But that is then rule of the market and not environmental legislation. #01:11:16-2#

I: That means a direct impact of environmental legislation is first of all not noticeable? #01:11:25-2#

E10: That (pointing on ballast water) would be noticeable. Because the ships could not do it that fast if it was now signed. Ballast water can leave a huge crack in world shipping if it has to be implemented from one day to the next. How that is supposed to work I do not know. Exemptions. But as I said first of all political agreement needs to be reached, then we can talk further. #01:11:54-1#

- I: Are there companies that are far more affected by the air pollution issues than you are? #01:12:01-1#*
- E10: By the currently discernable rules not. Because it is simply a reporting. It is simply red tape. It is how I say it: Environmental legislation is red tape. I am just reporting. #01:12:15-1#
- I: And if we look at the sulphur legislation? #01:12:19-0#*
- E10: They have anyways higher fuel costs when they sail faster. That means the higher fuel costs for the superior grade gas oil fuel is somehow calculated with them as well. They have to make sure that they can somehow refinance that with their container rates. They evidently have a higher spending for fuel per day, but that is a known value that is just equivalent to us in proportion. The cost increase per ton fuel is the same, they simply need more. But they can calculate that. #01:12:56-2#
- I: Those that voice the biggest concerns are short sea shipping on the Baltic Sea... #01:13:02-2#*
- E10: Feeder! That is certainly one of the most difficult issues, because they want to burn heavy fuel oil until the last day, because otherwise they are dead. And from the 1st of January onwards they are supposed to only have gas oil. How are they supposed to clean their tanks? I do not know at all how that works with these guys, no idea. They have the biggest problem with switching there. We have six specialized vessels that only operate on the American East coast or other American waters, that are however only 50 per cent of the time in the ECA. There the switch was also more difficult, but cushioned by the size of the company. We have started in time to retrofit in the shipyard and tanks cleanings are now or have partly been undertaken in Asia and are further being undertaken and all well. We will manage somehow. #01:13:58-0#
- I: How will the costs develop in the upcoming years? #01:14:02-1#*
- E10: No idea. (Laughing) #01:14:06-0#
- I: That is also interesting. #01:14:08-2#*
- E10: I will tell you: For ballast water you can calculate per ship between 3 and 5 million, Panamax to Capesize, per ship. #01:14:16-2#
- I: In how far does environmental legislation play a role compared to other risks if we talk about the costs? #01:14:29-1#*
- E10: Well, other developments are always from us... We are saying: We need to act in the market, we need to drive the market, we need to be able to use the market profitably, that means we are often, as I said, a little I do not want to say ahead of environmental legislation, but green shipping is a market segment, where everyone positions himself a little at the moment. The big ones say: I am green. Try to underline that with some kind of questionable certificates maybe. To check how green they actually are requires a lot of expert knowledge and insider knowledge within the company, thus it is difficult to

evaluate. Thus that means that the market is the driving force for the ship owners, less the legislation. The legislation, as I said, is the same for all ships. If it comes, it comes. Then everyone has to pay. That is what one would think. Ballast water is coming; everyone is retrofitting a ballast water treatment system. Then everyone has the same competitive disadvantage. #01:15:42-0#

I: How does it look with the freight rates? May one...? #01:15:46-0#

E10: Freight rates are shit! (Laughing) #01:15:51-1#

I: How are they determined? Where do they come from? #01:15:53-1#

E10: From the market. Market. #01:15:54-1#

I: Does environmental legislation have any influence on the freight rates in the end? #01:15:59-0#

E10: No. If there is a surplus supply of tonnage the freight rates are down. If there is a surplus offer of cargo, the freight rates are up, independent of environmental frame conditions. The environmental frame conditions are valid the entire time. That means that if the market is so bad as at the moment – to maintain a vessel, to invest, to pay back debt services while complying with all obligations is expensive – then it can happen that many ship owners will go bankrupt. And that will also happen. But that has reasons based on the up and down tendencies of the market. Market! Well, the driving force for the survival of the ship owners is the market. If the market is bad very many ship owners are doing very badly. #01:16:47-1#

I: Is it possible to ship certain goods with other modes of transport? #01:16:54-1#

E10: You can certainly load our iron ore onto a truck or also onto a train. Our barge makes 230,000 tons at once. The railway is at 1,000 tons I believe, the heaviest train, and the truck does not make 30 tons. How many trucks would we have to drive in order to transport 230,000 tons of iron ore? That will be the end of it. Well, we are also not loading until the metallurgical plant, cannot do it, but rather we are loading from the mine... from the mine it gets to the lading port by train most of the time, from there it is loaded, then we do the major transport over the sea, unload in Rotterdam for example and in Rotterdam it is either loaded onto inland water vessels or onto the train again and is then going, for example, to Thyssen-Krupp in Duisburg. It is certainly shipped there, for example by inland water vessel, because again with the ship it is simply more economic than with the train. #01:17:50-2#

I: Are there goods for which it is different, that somehow have switching opportunities? #01:17:55-5#

E10: Everything could for example be flown, everything could be trucked, and everything could go by train. #01:18:01-1#

I: Economically sensible, real alternatives? #01:18:07-0#

E10: That depends on the route of transport to a big extent. The railway tries to run from Hamburg with the train to China. I believe that is not economical compared to them. Even if he has to make many detours, ship transport is by far the most economic way of transport. Because few people are involved, because the route of transport does not cost any charges, because the maintenance of the route of transport does not cost any charges, because else the available people build rails, and what else not. They are simply missing then. Plainly a much more open route of transport is used. With a higher degree of efficiency than the train. Efficiency regarding the fuel efficiency. Well, a ship consumes much, much less than the train. #01:19:03-1#

I: You said earlier, one would have to, if one would now introduce speed limits for shipping then one would have to do that for the other modes of transport as well. #01:19:15-0#

E10: That is my opinion, yes. That is my personal thing... #01:19:18-1#

I: If they are not standing in competition to each other then that would not really matter. #01:19:24-1#

E10: No, as I said, the vessel speed, for a container, that is the best example, is governed by the market. If the market demands a lot of haul capacity and there is not enough capacity available, of build ship capacity, then that is impairing the economy. Then the vessels are sailing faster in order to satisfy the economy, also in order to keep our economy running and the profit opportunities. That means it really is an intervening factor into the economy. And then the vessel speed is simply increased. By that I can increase the haul capacity. That has a substantial influence on the world economy. The haul capacity, if that is not there, the world economy in its current setup is doing extremely badly. A [company like] Mercedes, if I tell him: Right, China out! Then 75 per cent of his cars are falling out. They must somehow have gotten here. Or sometimes even gotten here two times, because the things are assembled here, then it is sent back again for further... Everything is so intertwined in the economy, so that without transport nothing goes any more. #01:20:36-1#

I: A few further questions, all a bit further away: How does the general situation of the shipping industry look? #01:20:42-1#

E10: Very – I am rather speaking in general for the entire maritime shipping industry in Germany – it does not look good any more. Very bad, because they also... that is not easy. When the market was up there was too much invested through debt capital, that means capital has not played a role. There was enough money to quickly build a ship and to build another ship and to build yet another ship, without knowing how I might maybe employ it later on, when the market is not so fortunate any more. And that is the situation we are in now. Now that the vessels are there the market is not there anymore. Because it is debt capital it does not bother every ship owner directly, but rather very much the banks and very much the private investors. And that is happening very far off the stage. One does not realize that so much in the public, how many of these limited-partnership-vessels are collapsing. #01:21:40-2#

- I: What kind of development do you expect for the upcoming years? #01:21:44-2#*
- E10: As I said, hopefully the economic vessel will get separated from the not economic vessel. Well, we will see a leap in the efficiency of the vessels. The economic ones will... have a higher chance of survival. #01:22:03-2#
- I: What are the biggest chances and risks? #01:22:06-1#*
- E10: (Laughing) Chances... No idea, what is a big chance? Spoken as a big one: That the small ones die. Than we have fewer competitors. (Laughing) That is a chance. No, risks are that the unrealistic legislation makes our lives harder and harder. That common sense is more and more turned off in our business in the area of crewing. Today it is not being in demand any more that a well educated person is aboard, but it is only demanded that he has all papers aboard. On the Philippines however he gets them partly on every corner. That is where I see a problem. That means that they don't look any more – like in earlier times when I was being trained – on an acceptable education, an acceptable career, acceptable maybe also personality. That does not play a role anymore. Today it plays a role that the certificates are there and then everything is fine. Because port state only looks at the certificates and as I said documentations the check is: You are all right, your documents are there. Something is going wrong there. #01:23:22-0#
- I: And it is actually possible in certain countries such a document then... well, also for certain ship owners, that... #01:23:30-2#*
- E10: Forget that I said anything. Although in China I am also going to the fake market. #01:23:38-0#
- I: And is it not possible for port state control in that moment to identify whether it is a real or... #01:23:45-1#*
- E10: It is not possible on a very big scale, but yes, for that matter. How is one supposed to tell an authentic document from a fake one? #01:23:54-1#
- I: Who can issue such a document? Is that one agency per country or are those... #01:24:00-1#*
- E10: No, normally, by law, we have a certificate for each steel plate, for each shaft we have a certificate, for the machine like we get it from the supplier there is a certificate. Then there are the type approval certifications, then there are the installation certifications, then there is the overall certification, statutes, which are evidently the most important and then there is classification certification. Then there is the crew certification, that he has this health training, that he has his STCW training, that he has his fire and lifeboat drill stuff, all such things. Those are all certifications. Folders, folders, folders full of documents aboard that need to lie there in order to say: We are allowed to. I am saying: Bureaucracy has a stranglehold over us. Because what is missing is time and again a certain document. We are detaining that vessel, you are missing this and that document. Evidently that then goes into the fax machine... bscht... here you have that document. Well, that is the most difficult for me. And has nothing to do with best practise and best

knowledge and further development. We try to train the people, yes, in order to keep the level up. We cannot somehow train them to move forward in order to make improvements. We train them in order to try to keep a certain level. Technical developments for example – also very difficult to train aboard. That means they also still need [to be trained on] electronic machines, common-rail machines. Who is training the people for that? Where do they learn that? #01:25:47-0#

I: Well, where are they learning it? #01:25:49-0#

E10: Where are they learning it? (lacht) #01:25:50-1#

I: Are people afterwards able to, I do not I know, keep the ballast water machine or something running? 01:25:58-1#

E10: They have to. #01:25:59-2#

I: But if they are increasingly bad educated, how shall one picture that? #01:26:06-2#

E10: Yes, that can be imagined as being difficult. No, that is the challenge. If one brings more and more technology aboard, more and more complex technology it will get more and more difficult to also concretely maintain that and to manage that and to supervise that. #01:26:28-1#

I: Which role does environmental legislation play compared to other risks? #01:26:39-2#

E10: All risks end in the environment, how was that again? A ship grounding is an environmental risk, a collision is an environmental risk, that means that the economic risks have always been big in shipping. Shipping has never been without risk. That is why it has been reasonably paid in the past and reasonably skilled people have been employed. That is a question of insurance cover. And environmental legislation... when an accident happens the environmental laws go eventually out of force, because after all an accident has happened. Oil is leaking. We can only try to minimize it. We cannot try any more to say: You now have oil pollution. Evidently, we have oil pollution. Everyone knows that. We try to limit it. Those are the things that we will do. #01:27:44-1#

I: Can I get insurance cover for non-compliance? #01:27:47-2#

E10: I do not believe so. #01:27:50-1#

I: No matter how complicated the legislation is, I have to... #01:27:52-2#

E10: I can get insurance cover for human error. #01:28:00-1#

I: What are other issues that occupy the industry, apart from environmental legislation? #01:28:03-2#

E10: When is the market coming? Where is the market? Yes, that is what we live by. #01:28:08-1#

I: I have three last questions. Are there any issues that I have not yet addressed in the last 90 minutes that I should still consider? #01:28:20-2#

E10: (Thinking) Yes, for me for example the role of the harbour state would be of importance. When does one force the harbour state to interfere with the system? That means when will it be said to him: If you want to unload a bulk vessel, you also have to hold available a wash water facility, otherwise you will not get a license ashore. And maybe you also have to permit that a ship, even if it is a private terminal, if you want to do harbour business then you have to permit, that supply is being delivered to this vessel, that deliveries happen. That is a problem. In Africa there are so many private terminals. They do not even allow us to bring lubricating oil aboard. Without lubricating oil, we cannot leave. When is something coming on that. Because we can only do a proper business, if we can properly supply our vessels. #01:29:28-0#

I: Are there no rules for harbours? #01:29:34-0#

E10: There are certainly a few, but those are all local rules. There is nothing somehow on the IMO level regarding that. We are now trying that with the garbage management. We can that fill out such a paper that there are no facilities here or no uptake of garbage. But that is a toothless tiger. We have that paper aboard and what now? #01:29:59-1#

I: Can you think of other experts I should still talk to? #01:30:05-1#

E10: Every shipping company has its people. The business person here in this company would see many things differently, he would however not be so much the environmental guy. Experts... I mean, you do have [employee of ship owners association], he will know a lot of experts. I can only share. Regarding containers you have certainly already been with [name of another expert]... #01:30:40-2#

I: I cannot say anything about that. #01:30:41-2#

E10: Well, you do not need to. I know that. And then ship owners. Regarding ferries I can also imagine where you have been and cruiseliner, I can also think about whom you have met there. Well, he will make sure that you meet the right people. (Laughing) Well, it is a small community, thus everyone knows the others a little. #01:31:08-2#

I: Is there anything that I have not yet asked that is still on your mind? #01:31:13-1#

E10: No, well, no, no. Well will fight on. We are a shipping company, that has specialized on bulk cargo and with that we certainly have a big global market with many simple providers in the shipping sector. Thus, we are fighting against the Chinese, who partly operate on the local market that we will never be able to reach competitively, because they are simply operating without rules, because they never see another harbour then China. And China will not hurt China. We have for example RightShip vettings that is a very nasty issue. We do not really need that so much in the area of bulkers like tankers. Tankers are hostage of that and these vettings are looking for tankers and that is now supposed to be implemented here. I would say: Why? We are not as much a danger as a tanker, but they do not get information for example from China. There are Chinese

ship owners that are not even listed with them, because: National, no information available. As long as it is this way it is unfair competition. And that is staying like that. That will not change. And there one has to try to find one's own line and has to say: Okay, how far can we go and where is our strategy? That is the most difficult. And these vettings are a very difficult issue for me, because that is also just producing paper, producing paper to a large extent. And produces so and so much security, yes. (Laughing) It is difficult for me to assess that. If I ask a tanker captain: What is here misincident? Then he will say: Here, misindicent, I have to hand that in for two months. If that is that that statistics, that has nothing to do with prevention, safety improvement or awareness. That is my point. #01:33:31-1#

I: Thank you very, very much! #01:33:35-0#

Interview No 11

Date: Wednesday, 14 January 2015, 10 am

Duration: 94 minutes

Method of contact: Contact was established via the ship owner's association in mid-December 2014. E11 was willing to support the research but could only offer a meeting in the New Year. The interview took place on the 14 January 2015.

Interview situation: The interview took place in the office building of E11. The room was quiet, and no disturbances occurred. The interview could just be conducted in a very concentrated matter. Water was served in the very beginning of the interview.

E11 was calm and friendly and very openly and supportively communicated all information that he knew of, without detailing too much business relevant information of the own organization. E11 seemed to be a quick thinker and could answer all questions with a lot of insight, background knowledge and lifelong understanding of the industry. There were not many new aspects coming up, but a welcome substantiation of previously heard arguments could be made by the expert. E11 left the interviewer on a friendly notion wishing good luck and referring to his own daughters that were writing their PhD as well.

I: *First of all, very many thanks that this is happening today. #00:00:05-2#*

E11: Yes. No problem. #00:00:09-0#

I: *Right, well, this is about the following: I am currently writing my doctoral thesis – you have probably already heard that – and I am studying trade effects and effects on shipping due to the current environmental legislation. I... we will be talking about different things that play a role there. I am also trying to identify different variables that may play a role or not. I also want to know whether there exist differences between the ship owners, if some are more affected than others. We will also be talking about that. It is important that everything that is said here will be completely anonymized, thus it is not retraceable and that I naturally also make careful use of the data respectively. Right, to start with: With whom am I actually speaking? In which position do you work and what do you do? #00:01:04-4#*

E11: My name is [E11]. I am responsible for the chartering of the vessels, for the bunker supply, everything to do with technology, operations of the vessels. That is my main task. #00:01:19-5#

I: *What are the issues that currently occupy you the most? #00:01:23-7#*

- E11: Currently the... currently we are really rather interested in the operational problem that we have here in the North of Europe. Kiel Canal, for example, you have already heard that that is a permanent problem. We as [organization 11], we are a so-called feeder operator on the Baltic Sea. That means we have to pass through the Kiel Canal with almost all vessels. That is a real problem. Until recently it evidently was the new SECA, the new SECA regulations, but in the meantime that has calmed down a bit at least from the operational side. #00:02:07-2#
- I: *In how far does this SECA question still play a role? Are all questions answered there?* #00:02:18-5#
- E11: The vessels may in any case be supplied with appropriate bunker oils at the moment. That was really one of the main obstacles, where no one was sure if that would work or not. It has been shown: It works, at least for the ships that we operate. That that is very much significantly more expensive than what we bunkered before is surely publicly known. #00:02:45-0#
- I: *How much did the prices increase now?* #00:02:49-7#
- E11: They really did not increase at all. In general the raw oil prices, as you have surely been following in the press, have fallen by more than 50 per cent in the meantime. That means that we are today paying for the bunker we currently need still less than what we have paid half a year ago. #00:03:10-2#
- I: *Then for heavy fuel oil?* #00:03:11-3#
- E11: Right. #00:03:11-9#
- I: *Oh, that is funny. Yes.* #00:03:13-4#
- E11: But it stays as it is: The difference in price still lies at about 250 US dollars per ton. That means if these SECA regulations had not come into force we would still have lower costs. #00:03:27-9#
- I: *Do you expect the price to stay on this low level somehow in the long run?* #00:03:33-3#
- E11: No. That would be against everything that I had learnt in my decades of shipping and bunkering. I cannot imagine that. #00:03:44-4#
- I: *Do you have any specific knowledge on environmental legislation from your professional career?* #00:03:54-8#
- E11: I had to acquire that knowledge myself, because if you have to supply the ships with bunker fuels you also need to know what you are doing, but apart from that: No, no specific knowledge. #00:04:06-4#
- I: *Simply based on your experience – how easy is it to handle environmental legislation? Is everything easy to understand or does one have to...?* #00:04:15-7#

E11: No. The ideas are always very simple, but the implementation in practice is a real problem. If you talk about environmental legislation, ballast water management... if you take a look at the chaos that is meanwhile, that... I can understand every ship owner who is saying: But what am I actually supposed to do now? #00:04:42-2#

I: *Where does this chaos come from?* #00:04:45-2#

E11: It comes from the fact that there are indeed certain international rules, but the local, the national implementation is always different. Here in Europe we have the additional problem: There exists a European directive that then needs to be implemented nationally. Well, you know yourself that the countries cannot really agree most of the time. At the VDR [German ship owners association] I have once... but we have only talked about that briefly, as I said: Feeder in the Baltic Sea. The Baltic Sea has a direct passage to the North Sea and thus to the North Atlantic. We only move in this area. That means our vessels go to the South up to Rotterdam at most and to the North up to St. Petersburg and at most and [Gefle-Rouma?] in the Baltic Sea. Despite that it is at least at the moment still expected of these ships that they also comply with these ballast treatments, which does not make any sense at all to me, because if I sail with the ship from Rotterdam to Hamburg, why should I not release any ballast water? I am constantly moving in the same sea area. #00:05:54-9#

I: *Sometimes one hears about some kind of certificates of exemption...* #00:05:58-2#

E11: Yes, but that is not yet clear, but it should... if you now for example have to order new-buildings you already have to comply with all the regulations. But how shall you do that if you do not even know what is coming? The same applied to vessels with gas propulsion that is where the main engine can run on LNG. There the whole regulations are not even decided. That means the first ideas that one has discussed here years ago with mobile tank containers – forefront of the bridge [“Vorkante Brücke”], they are no longer being approved. You see, that is sometimes a little bit difficult. #00:06:41-2#

I: *In order to get an overview. How many vessels do you operate at the moment?* #00:06:49-8#

E11: At the moment that question is not easy to answer. Until recently there were twenty vessels in operation for us. Last year we made a very big step with a few of our customers and also with one competitor. That means we are now cooperating with our vessels - slot agreements - that means the whole operations of our vessels have been handed over in the meantime. We are currently operating only two vessels directly at the moment and for all others sailing list management, bunker supply and such things has been taken over by our competitor or in the meantime cooperation partner. #00:07:39-9#

I: *But there are still twenty in under your ownership?* #00:07:42-2#

E11: No. With [organization 11] there are really not any vessels under ownership, because, as I said, feeders in the Baltic Sea, that is a business that underlies very strong

- fluctuations. That is why we do not have any own ships. In the past we have sometimes also chartered ships of shareholders that have at that time been built by this circle of people, but they never belonged to [organization 11]. #00:08:17-7#
- I: *To whom do these ships belong now?* #00:08:20-9#
- E11: They belong to very different shipping companies. At the moment for example we have only two ships on long time charter here. They belong to a shipping company from Friesland, [name of ship owner]. Until recently we have had a vessel here that belongs to the circle of owners. Then we have a vessel that belongs to a Hamburg shipping owner. A second vessel, the ship owner is located in Stade. Well, you see, it is diversified, but it is very many German ship owners. #00:08:53-6#
- I: *How is the situation if I now for example need to build in a ballast water treatment facility? How is paying for that?* #00:09:01-8#
- E11: The ship owner is paying for that. But as we are chartering the ships and the ship owner evidently wants to retrieve the money for the investment, we are paying in the end of the day. That is the reason why we naturally need to grapple with these issues, because in the end of the day it costs our money. #00:09:21-3#
- I: *If certain regulations are now not being met – who is liable for that? Is [organization 11] liable or the ship owner?* #00:09:29-1#
- E11: If it is related to bunkering we are liable, because we are responsible for the bunker supply of the ships according to the charterparty. If it is related to ballast water the ship owner is liable, that is the owner of the ship, but if I charter a vessel and I do not demand the corresponding written affirmation I would argue that I would maybe have a problem with that as a charterer in front of the courts, let me say it like that. #00:10:02-1#
- I: *It is possible to freely negotiate who is liable for what? Yes?* #00:10:05-9#
- E11: Yes, but as a rule it is the case that for everything that is directly related to the ship the shipping company, thus the owner of the ship is liable and everything that is related to bunkering the charterer is [liable]. #00:10:20-1#
- I: *But one can imagine that in the moment where the ship owner is maybe not within reach or something then the charter is always jointly liable...?* #00:10:29-6#
- E11: As charterer we are in any case always addressed first by the authorities, but in the end of the day the liability still lies with the ship owner. #00:10:39-3#
- I: *Does the fleet that you currently operate experience any kind of changes that could be traced back directly to environmental legislation?* #00:10:51-8#
- E11: No, sadly that could not happen, because there were no alternatives to what we have done. That means the ships were simply switched fuel-wise from heavy fuel oil to gas oil and that was that. #00:11:06-3#

- I: *Would investments in scrubbers be thinkable? #00:11:10-1#*
- E11: No, because the promises of the industry regarding scrubbers have turned out to be a little full-bodies in retrospect. Things have been promised that one could apparently not at all hold in practice. Then it is the case, if you look at the vessel types that we are operating here in the Baltic Sea, later you cannot... you will be able to fit a scrubber, but you would have to place it at the forefront of the bridge, in front of the superstructures. Normally containers are places there and you are massively changing the stability of the ship. You have problems with the feeder tanks for granulate and waste. No one could really solve that and the investment would have been so high that everyone involved said: No way. #00:12:06-1#
- I: *If you say: What they promised they could not hold. What kind of promises were those? #00:12:12-1#*
- E11: Well, they have to... that only makes sense of the ships are still supplied with heavy fuel oil of 3.5 per cent sulphur content maximum, in order to get out the maximum of the price difference. For that the scrubber will have to be able to filter that out and that is under all operating conditions of the ship. And if you take a look at how the vessels operate here that is a real challenge. In the beginning it was said: No problem. And later everyone had to back-pedal and say: We cannot guarantee that. #00:12:49-6#
- I: *Okay. There are a few that have decided for it. #00:12:52-6#*
- E11: Yes. But those are mainly Ro-Ro-Ferry companies of the Baltic Sea. These vessels are constructed completely different. They still have space everywhere in order to do something. And also, those are test vessels at the moment. There are very specific criteria that need to be fulfilled in order for really only 0.1 evaporating from the chimney in the end. That is at least my state of knowledge. #00:13:23-2#
- I: *How may that even be verified? #00:13:28-1#*
- E11: That is exactly the problem. At the moment no one knows that exactly. Normally you would have to hold measuring instruments into the exhaust plume. The only thing we can prove is that we have a scrubber aboard and that it is complied with according to the indications of the producer. I think respective sensors will be... they would have been installed then in order to recheck that, because you also need to adjust that all the time in order for it to work. But as that has never been implemented in practice. I cannot tell you anything about that even if I want to. #00:14:03-6#
- I: *But... well, such measurement processes, that someone actually measures something at the exhaust during operations – that does not yet exist in this form, right? #00:14:16-6#*
- E11: That will have to be introduced as well, because, as I said, if the first Ro-Ro vessels in the Baltic Sea are now equipped with it the shipping companies will persist on it being controlled. That means the producer will have to build in according sensors. #00:14:35-7#

- I: *What happens when I have done all these investments and the sensor is then saying: That is not enough? #00:14:43-8#*
- E11: Then the ship owner and the producer will have a massive problem. #00:14:49-0#
- I: *That is incredible, yes. #00:14:52-8#*
- E11: Well, I would assume that the contracts would be written in a way that the liability lies very clearly with the producer of the scrubber, whereby the ship owner also needs to fulfil certain things. That means the needs reasonable personnel aboard. Maybe one has even agreed on a maximum sulphur content of the fuel. That is also possible, because I know that... it is logical: The lower the current sulphur content, the easier it is to filter out. #00:15:21-4#
- I: *If you say certain personnel: Do I need to specifically train the people in order to operate such scrubbers? #00:15:29-4#*
- E11: Yes. Depending on what kind of a system you have that training is more or less intensive. There are different possibilities. There are first of all dry scrubbers, where the whole stuff is filtered through granulate. They are a little easier to handle. And then there are wet scrubbers. There exist two systems, open and closed. That means with the open you are practically pumping the stuff that you filtered out with the water right back into the sea, what I am not allowed to do here and with the closed you have a closed loop and you have to imagine, that really is a rather big chemical laboratory that you have aboard. That means you also need to have people who understand something about that. #00:16:18-2#
- I: *How is that when switching fuel? Is there some kind of technical difficulty or is that simple? #00:16:25-8#*
- E11: Yes. The general problem is: Heavy fuel oil needs to be heated in order to be able to burn it. With gas oil you should rather not do that. That is outgassing and then you will get heavy explosions. That is really the main difference. The next problem is, if you take gas oil you maybe even have to operate a gas oil cooler after just in order to have no problems with too high temperatures. Yes, that is a real challenge. #00:17:06-2#
- I: *But in principle that now has... #00:17:09-6#*
- E11: For us it is comparably simple. Our vessels are solely operating in the SECA. That means they will from the beginning... we have in... when have I delivered that? I believe sometime in mid-December we have supplied the vessel with gas oil for the first time instead of heavy fuel oil and then we have used the last heavy fuel oil shortly before Christmas and we are just switching once. There exist tables for that, how that has to be done in order to have no problems with it and since then the ship is constantly running on gas oil. He had no problems. The problems start if you enter the SECA from outside. The switching is the problem, if you have to do that time and again. #00:17:58-0#
- I: *And what can that then lead to? #00:18:01-7#*

- E11: In the worst case the main engine stops. I have read reports by the US coast guard somewhere along the way. They also have such regulations there and they apparently increasingly have these problems, because if they do not do that properly the main engine stops. This would maybe not be really perfect on the river Elbe. #00:18:25-0#
- I: *No, one can imagine that. We have now been talking about SECAs all the time. If we now look at the big picture: Which environmental regulations are keeping you busy?* #00:18:40-5#
- E11: In principle all the ones that relate to us, whereby I sometimes do not put the sense of certain regulations somehow into question. You now mean regarding the shipping industry? #00:18:56-6#
- I: *Right.* #00:18:57-5#
- E11: Yes, well, there ballast water treatment is now occupying is next. That will be the next big hurdle here in the Baltic Sea. #00:19:04-2#
- I: *Do you have a rough idea on when that starts? What are you expecting?* #00:19:09-0#
- E11: Allegedly is it is starting in 2016. But all that meanwhile seems to be adjourned to a later time. Thus, I cannot even tell you what the status quo is now, because no one can currently answer that question. But if one wants to, as I said, implement these regulations also for coastal traffic then we will get real problems. How that is supposed to be implemented in the end I have absolutely no idea. #00:19:36-4#
- I: *Is that mainly a financial or a technical problem?* #00:19:38-2#
- E11: Both. #00:19:40-7#
- I: *If one compares that with the introduction of the SECA – would you see that even more critical or...?* #00:19:51-3#
- E11: If it is implemented the way some people imagine that, yes, because like that you are practically paralyzing the whole coastal traffic. #00:19:58-8#
- I: *How can one picture that?* #00:19:59-9#
- E11: Yes, it is about the reporting. You have to report everything and if you imagine that: A feeder. Alone... it is about such trifles like the sailing list having to be changed at the last minute. That is really due to the short time between the harbours rather the rule than the exception. You can suddenly not do that anymore, because you have to comply with the reporting times or you cannot comply with certain criteria, because you now have loaded ballast water in a certain area that you are afterwards not allowed to release there anymore. That is... Yes, one has to wait and see and that is really implemented in practice. I hope that the understanding is there with the authorities that one will simply introduce certain exceptions. #00:20:52-2#

- I: *That will become interesting. On which level is legislation mainly done? Which level interests you the most – the international or rather the local or what the EU is doing?* #00:21:03-8#
- E11: The problem is: There is not really any international law. The IMO makes suggestions that however have to be implemented in EU as well as national law afterwards. That means in the end of the day you have to see what comes out of it for each single harbour. #00:21:23-7#
- I: *Do the harbours themselves make any regulations again, that are then only valid there?* #00:21:29-8#
- E11: Yes, partly, yes. Also, each harbour authority has its own ideas what needs to be done how. #00:21:36-2#
- I: *Is there a certain alignment in the Baltic Sea area, that one can say similar rules apply everywhere?* #00:21:41-9#
- E11: There are discussion groups in the Baltic Sea area, among others where our friends from Russia are actively involved who have very different ideas on what should be done and what should not. That is difficult. #00:21:56-7#
- I: *What kind of different ideas are those?* #00:21:58-4#
- E11: It starts with seeing reason whether they are not accepting that as a SECA area or not. #00:22:07-3#
- I: *Okay. I have not heard that before.* #00:22:09-7#
- E11: Still. There was at a time this idea - I have heard that at the time - we are now all changing flag to Russia, then we do not need to do that at all. #00:22:17-2#
- I: *Okay and how is the status quo on that?* #00:22:20-7#
- E11: As far as I know they have never ratified these rules. That means that the EU has declared the Baltic Sea to be a SECA area, however Russia has that: That is of no interest to me. #00:22:30-3#
- I: *That means in the moment that I enter the Russia sea area I could switch back again?* #00:22:35-9#
- E11: If you are sailing with a Russian ship you would theoretically not have to do that. I do not know what the state of things is today, but that was two or three years ago. We have been discussion this topic for quite some time. There it was said: Oh, we are all operating under the Russian flag and then we do not need to comply. #00:22:52-0#
- I: *But apparently no one has decided for that?* #00:22:53-9#

- E11: No. You could not do that. Imagine what kind of trouble you would get into. Apart from that you would not necessarily want to sail under a Russian flag. (Laughing) #00:23:02-9#
- I: *I do not know what kind of consequences that would have.* #00:23:05-8#
- E11: That is alone... you also need relating... that is then your flag state and if you are for example entering a Baltic state with a Russian ship there maybe exist certain small reserves. They also have very different regulations. You have to, for example, if you... Ships are bunkered in St. Petersburg. It is however not allowed for Russian citizens to enter the ships, because with that they would leave the Russian territory. For that they would need corresponding permissions. Thus, you see, it is all a bit different. No, not that flag state. That is, I think, not a good idea. #00:23:50-8#
- I: *Does that have an influence for example also on the controls, hat one is then being controlled more often here if one sails under Russian flag?* #00:23:58-7#
- E11: That can happen. Well, you know that there are these black-listed flags, where port state control rather more has an eye on them. Yes, that does exist. #00:24:07-3#
- I: *Okay. Yes, well. Then it is not such a good idea. Again, back to environmental legislation – which aims have been achieved if one is now looking at it from an environmental perspective? What has happened in the last years?* #00:24:23-8#
- E11: Well, what has been achieved at any rate, if I am now only talking about our shipping routes, for the Baltic Sea, in the past ships have dumped the waste that they had aboard over board. Today that does not happen anymore. Also, oil-containing bilge water was pumped out. Today that also does not happen anymore. A lot, a lot has happened, and I am of the opinion that it was right that one has done that. Regarding the SECA regulations, well, the last step was maybe a little too big, this from 1.0 to 0.1. Also, that does not really make sense to me. As you know, the SECA area ends at Plymouth which means the English Channel is included. If you are now however on the other side of Great Britain, Irish Sea, there it does not apply. The wind comes from the West all the time. That means that stuff comes over here anyways. The Mediterranean is also not included. That does not really make total sense to me. If such regulations are coming, they should apply worldwide and not only in some small areas. #00:25:37-0#
- I: *Where do you still see need for action for the environment?* #00:25:41-3#
- E11: Well. We have covered waste. We have covered disposal of sludge and in the meantime with the fuel – at least here in the North – we are... well, if you look at it internationally, I would claim that something needs to be done with all issues, because on the open seas you are still allowed to do all sorts of things. There you are allowed to wash your cargo holds, there you are allowed to throw waste overboard and EVERYTHING. Something would need to be done there urgently, but on the Baltic Sea we are doing good. #00:26:24-5#
- I: *How strong in the interest of the population to have clean ships?* #00:26:31-4#

- E11: Zero. At least I would claim that. Well, shipping has, at least here in Germany, never had a real big lobby. We are only getting bad press if we – like last year – soil the tablecloths of a restaurant at the Elbe, because something is not working with the main engine and he is suddenly emitting a huge soot cloud or if some kind of oily remainders are washing up at the cost or if a ship breaks apart. Then we are aware of shipping and that is as a scapegoat. That 99.9% of sea traffic is conducted without a problem is not noticed by anyone. #00:27:16-1#
- I: *Yes. That is where mostly the problem is.* #00:27:18-3#
- E11: Yes, and well, if it is working no one is interested in that. That is however not lamentable. That is just a statement. #00:27:26-2#
- I: *Which lobby has the biggest influence on legislation – the one of the shipping industry or the one of environmental protection?* #00:27:34-3#
- E11: Currently definitely environmental protection, because that is favoured more by voters. #00:27:43-1#
- I: *How does the implementation of new or of environmental legislation work from your perspective?* #00:27:53-6#
- E11: Here again that holds only true for our area here, for the Baltic Sea area: Well. #00:28:02-3#
- I: *How does this process work? Well, how early on are you being informed and by whom?* #00:28:10-1#
- E11: The SECA regulations coming into force on 1.1.2015 have first been discussed by German authorities in 2008. Thus, you see... and also the process: Normally such processes are really initiated by the IMO and the IMO is a huge organization. Before one is really coming to terms there years go by. And thus, yes, we have very early information. What does sometimes not work is afterwards the implementation into national law. There are then at times still some surprises. #00:28:54-6#
- I: *Does one still have any influence there?* #00:28:57-2#
- E11: No. #00:28:57-6#
- I: *Will something still be changed there? (E11 shakes his head) No.* #00:28:59-1#
- E11: No. #00:28:59-3#
- I: *Okay.* #00:29:00-2#
- E11: We have tried that here when this 0.1 per cent regulation was discussed, because it was said: Why 0.1? In the beginning they still listen with interest and when we came apart the first times one actually agreed that one would rather try to make it 0.5 per cent so that one can go on using heavy fuel oil. For environmental reasons that has been overturned at the last minute without at any point in time so much as speaking with us

about that again. We were informed afterwards, and we were then allowed to voice our concerns, but that has not changed anything anymore. The decision has been taken somewhere else. #00:29:44-0#

I: *How has the political interest in maritime environmental protection developed in the last years? #00:29:50-3#*

E11: I would say that is a constant fever curve, up and down. As soon as something happens on the world's oceans that is coming into focus again and at other times no one is interested. #00:30:05-9#

I: *Well, in principle it is thus [influenced] by certain accidents or certain things... #00:30:09-7#*

E11: That is the only thing where that really comes to the boil again and again. Apart from that as I said the regulations that we have up here in the Northern European area they are already very good, and the controls are equivalent as well. Thus, I do not see much anymore that would have to be done in addition. #00:30:29-3#

I: *What do you expect as next steps? What is coming next on the agenda? #00:30:34-0#*

E11: At the moment I cannot think of anything else. From the colouring of the hull over the bunker up to the waste disposal we have really covered pretty much everything in the meantime. #00:30:46-8#

I: *Sometimes it is also being spoken about CO₂. #00:30:49-7#*

E11: Yes. Whereby I would claim that that is something that every shipping company is focusing on for a new-building anyway, because the less a vessel consumes the higher the rate that you will receive from a potential charterer, because he is then saving a lot of money and if you take a look at how the bunker consumption of ships has declined further and further in the course of the last ten years, fifteen years then one can see that there is already a lot happening. At least here in Northern Europe. #00:31:28-5#

I: *Is that also a result of slow steaming? #00:31:31-2#*

E11: Yes. #00:31:31-5#

I: *Could one then assume that if the trade flows are again significantly increasing that such a development will again turn around? #00:31:40-2#*

E11: This discussing is already under way, because slow steaming really only makes sense up from a certain bunker price, because you have to, if you do slow steaming, operate in regular lines. Then you have to deploy additional ships in order to still manage the departure frequency and that point is reached. That is definitely reached. Because you have to, what they do on the Far East... on the main race tracks for the container ships... they need two additional ships and in the meantime they are not saving that in bunker anymore. At least not with the current prices. On the other hand, it is true that if you are now again starting to go faster, what are you going to do with all the redundant vessels?

There is not more cargo. At the moment that is a real dilemma, because everyone has been pretty much taken by surprise by the current oil price. #00:32:39-9#

I: *Do you expect that something will change in the next years, that the trade flows will significantly increase again?* #00:32:47-8#

E11: No. #00:32:48-0#

I: *Why?* #00:32:50-0#

E11: Because what we have seen the last... until 2008 has been a bubble, credit-financed for the bigger part. In my opinion, if the economy has learnt only a little from that that will not happen again. #00:33:08-8#

I: *One does sometimes see such trade forecasts, with such curves that climb into infinity...* #00:33:16-2#

E11: Yes, I know. I have also seen the forecasts here for Hamburg with twenty per cent increase every year and if I look at the development of this company here: Yes, there was years, really, where one could get dizzy. That was double-digit – each year. But again, that was all credit-financed and the bubble has burst in 2007, 2008 and the main trade flows are currently still running between Asia and Europe and between North America and Europe respectively and Europe as well as North America are really mature markets. Where shall a double-digit growth rate come from again? In any case the regional traffic within Asia will be increasing further for example. Africa is also certainly a growth market, also with high growth rates, but if you take a look at what kind of volumes those are, even if you have a ten per cent increase each year you will need a lot of time to be where we currently are in the Far-East-Europe or Far-East-North-America traffic. And far that you do not need such big vessels. That makes no sense. #00:34:37-2#

I: *How does it look on the Baltic Sea on the moment? Are there also overcapacities?* #00:34:41-7#

E11: Yes. Russia is currently a country that is a huge worry for us, because due to the economy there the mood is dropping a bit. That is clear. The oil price is extremely low. That means money is lacking there to consume. Where is all that supposed to come from? Apart from that Russia has sadly not managed to take its own economy away from these pure resources in the last ten years and Russia has really been the growth market in the Baltic Sea in the last years. That is currently falling away a bit. Not only we are concerned how that is going to develop this year. #00:35:30-7#

I: *How is the development in the Baltic States or something? Can one hope for something there?* #00:35:36-0#

E11: The real regional markets are extremely small. The main volumes going there, that is very, very much transit goods that go further into the East. Take a look at the population key figures... but apart from that they have picked themselves up very well. They also

have good growth numbers, just like Poland as well, but again, those are extremely small markets. That does not justify sending a 2,000 TEU container ship directly to them. #00:36:11-3#

I: *I have tried to summarize that a bit - Down here you have the German version – in which ways ships might pollute. #00:36:22-1#*

E11: That does not exist anymore. (Pointing on waste) #00:36:23-2#

I: *Yes? #00:36:25-9#*

E11: That is not allowed. #00:36:27-0#

I: *Right. The question is which of these are basically finally regulated, where something can still be done... #00:36:35-3#*

E11: If you look at that worldwide then something needs to be done everywhere. If you only look at the area here, North Europe, the main part is [done] apart from... well, even there (Pointing on noise pollution) we are not so very bad anymore, because the machines have all become more silent. #00:36:59-4#

I: *Does one talk about noise? Well, is that an issue? #00:37:04-5#*

E11: No, not on the ships. Because: What do you want to do? First of all one has already done a lot a lot in that regard in the last thirty years, simply in order to find staff for the ships at all. That is a question of convenience. If that is rumbling and trundling the whole time, who will then still work there? Well, a lot of things have already happened there, at least with the vessels that we are operating here and apart from that: Certain sounds cannot be turned off. If the propeller is rotating then it is rotating. The vibrations of the main engine are evidently transferred via the hull into the water. You cannot do anything about that. You can reduce these vibrations. That is done or has been done, but in general I would not know what you would want to do about that. Such a ship diesel simply is a little bigger. Waste, as I said, we are not allowed to do here anyways. Air pollution... we have just done the next step. Whereas I would really have found it more sensible if one would have said that one would do a particulate filter. That would have been very much better in my eyes than everything else, but okay, that is my... We have had noise. Sewage waters... we are not allowed to dispose of anything here anyways. Ballast water is currently under way, whereas that makes no sense up here, because all the oceans are connected anyways. And there the exchange [of waters] exists already in a natural way. This (pointing on “poisonous hull coatings”) has been prohibited for a long time anyways. When has that been... before 2000. TBT could not be used anymore. Well, that (pointing on “oily water”) has already been done as well. And that is in anyway strictly prohibited and that is also strictly being controlled. That means the ships have to maintain oil record books and woe betide something is being found there. #00:38:54-0#

I: *Of all these regulations – what is the most expensive for a shipping company? #00:39:01-6#*

E11: (Thinking) Yes... that is actually a very good question. I would argue everything that is to do with the main engine. That means air pollution. And right after that you have ballast water and the rest, as I said, there the vessels are anyways designed in a way that the capacity of the respective storage tanks, no matter it is now tanks or something else, are in a way that nothing needs to be done anymore. And what they now want about that... (Pointing at “noise”) #00:39:53-8#

I: *About the noise.* #00:39:54-7#

E11: ...then it is also getting really expensive, because I would not know at all how one would do that. You then somehow need to absorb all vibrations of the main engine with silencers that they cannot get into the water via the hull. Which is not working at all, because on the other side you need to via the... you are in any way connected to the water again. I would not know how one wants to solve that really at the moment, but that would then become really expensive. #00:40:25-4#

I: *If you say dust, that is particles, will something come up on that? Is that an aim of the legislator that one will have a look at particulate matter or something like that again?* #00:40:39-3#

E11: No. No. #00:40:39-3#

I: *No. Okay.* #00:40:41-4#

E11: Well, at least at the moment I have not heard about that and I would argue that for a main engine it would be fairly difficult to do something like that. #00:40:50-5#

I: *Is that or would that make sense in some way?* #00:40:57-3#

E11: No. Then it would make more sense if one would say one switches the engines away from oil to gas. That would be the logical and right step. And the first projects are also already underway. #00:41:18-5#

I: *Right. We have said: In principle you are informed well in advance and rather well on what is happening. Where does this information mainly come from?* #00:41:30-4#

E11: Normally you will get relevant information from the BIMCO [Baltic and International Maritime Council] for example. You also get information from the IMO and [German city] is a village regarding the shipping industry. That means one has known each other for many years and one is really also always talking to the same people and as soon as new things pop up one is talking about that. #00:41:57-7#

I: *Are there some that tend to be less informed than others?* #00:42:03-1#

E11: I can hardly, hardly assess that now. I know that the shipping companies that we work with are normally always very well informed, because if they plan a new-building project they need to inform themselves in advance about all these rules, also the ones that are maybe still coming. Otherwise they are losing a lot of money. [“Viel Geld in

- den Sand setzen”] Then they are building and missing the market and no one wants that.
#00:42:30-6#
- I: *Can it be more difficult as a small shipping company to receive and process information than for the big ones?* #00:42:40-2#
- E11: In principle not, no. You can always address the German Ship Owners Association. Most [companies] are a member anyways and they care about such concerns then.
#00:42:48-5#
- I: *Does one need specific personnel in the company that knows about...* #00:42:53-9#
- E11: That helps but is not absolutely necessary. I can take the standpoint that all of that is not my problem, ship owner you care about that. Unless, as I said, you have own ships.
#00:43:06-7#
- I: *If one would now have own ships?* #00:43:09-1#
- E11: You have to have it. Is also already being ordered. You have to comply with certain criteria as a shipping company in the meantime, comply with certain procedures. They you need to expert knowledge or you buy external expert knowledge. That works as well. #00:43:26-1#
- I: *Is it more difficult for a small shipping company to afford own people or is that really of no significance?* #00:43:31-3#
- E11: For them that is really impossible, because it is too expensive. That means that they will buy this know-how, because that is still cheaper than... if you have only one vessel, then you will normally have a technical inspector who cares about all these things. He is then in persona also the one who takes care of crewing and at the same time of charter, that means a little staff as possible. They could not do that anymore. Then he would have to do such things as well... suddenly undertake audits. Then everything needs to be inspected aboard as well, if that really is so. You will not manage that anymore.
#00:44:05-6#
- I: *But such a thing can be bought?* #00:44:08-2#
- E11: Yes. Ship management. #00:44:09-6#
- I: *Okay, right. I have asked that. Are there differences between owners and operators? Are they equally well informed?* #00:44:22-5#
- E11: Based on my experience: No, because that always depends a bit on what kind of operators you are dealing with. As I said, there are two possibilities. Either they say: That is of no interest to me, ship owner that is your thing. Or I care about that myself and talk to the ship owner how that shall best be done. That depends a bit on how one wants to handle that in the company. My experience is that operators that are only active within a small area are always well informed, solely based on self-interest. If you now

- have operators that operate their vessels worldwide it is a little bit more difficult to always keep a good overview. They are rather not so well informed. #00:45:10-4#
- I: *That means one can also assume that the ones that come from outside into the Baltic Sea often know less about what is expected of them than... #00:45:22-6#*
- E11: That can happen. Again: That depends entirely first of all evidently on the shipping company who operates this vessel and on the one who has chartered the vessel. #00:45:34-4#
- I: *If one says that it depends on these parties – are there tendencies that one says certainly, I do not know, if the owners are European one can assume that they are better prepared than if the owners are African or can one somehow...? #00:45:51-4#*
- E11: No. Well, I do not believe that one can say anything like that across-the-board. That simply depends on the individual companies. Good companies exist everywhere and bad companies or less good companies, let us say it like that, exist everywhere. That is at least my experience. #00:46:05-3#
- I: *Are there some directly in the Baltic Sea area as well where one says: Oh, they are rather not so careful and others where one knows that they manage the ships better? #00:46:16-8#*
- E11: I can only say to that that we have always tried for example where we have realized that it is not working so well to have as little as possible to do with them. #00:46:32-1#
- I: *Right, that is what I talked about. How is the shipping industry preparing for new legislation when we are now talking about the SECAs, about ballast water and whatever may come up next. How do such decision-making processes take place? #00:46:50-1#*
- E11: You take a look at the alternatives, what can I do? And then you work out what would be the cheapest way for the companies involved in the end of the day. #00:47:04-1#
- I: *Are there companies that tend to over-comply with environmental legislation or that operate especially environmentally friendly? #00:47:15-6#*
- E11: Yes, there has been a tendency in the last years to paint oneself greener. The problem is just that in the moment where that costs any money most are not willing anymore to go through with it full consequence. Well, many have written green on their flags, but it may not cost any money. #00:47:40-0#
- I: *Who is interested in that, if one is green? #00:47:43-6#*
- E11: Actually, meanwhile everyone. Because imagine that as a container shipping company you want to... you get an invitation to bid by a large enterprise who wants to bring its goods from the Far East to here or let us stay in the area: Paper, Scandinavia, big market up there. Scandinavians are environmentally conscious. That means that the paper producer will tell the shipping company: Watch out! You have to fulfil these and those criteria in order to win my charge at all. And if the ship owner is able to say: Look here,

- I have and especially environmentally friendly ship, that consumes less, has a scrubber installed, I can offer you that. Then the chance is bigger that the paper producer says: Watch here, we will do that, because he can then say in his web page: See that is what I have all done. #00:48:39-2#
- I: *Can one push through higher freight rates for more environmentally friendly ships?* #00:48:44-3#
- E11: If that pays out for the charterer yes, apart from that no. Everyone is saying that, but I have not yet experienced that until now. Well, paying out now in a way that the current costs of the ship are also respectively lower. Then it is being accepted, otherwise no. #00:49:16-2#
- I: *Thus, it is alone...* #00:49:18-9#
- E11: At the end of the day what counts is: Do I make a surplus or a loss with that? #00:49:27-0#
- I: *Well simply the fact that is the vessel is more environmentally friendly if it is then not consuming less?* #00:49:33-9#
- E11: If it is about pure freight transport, that is cargo transport I would argue simply that it plays hardly a role. There what plays a role at the end of the day is: What does the transport cost me and who is the cheapest? #00:49:46-9#
- I: *Are there companies that rather tend to comply with environmental legislation or rather less?* #00:49:55-0#
- E11: Not to my knowledge. Well, at least not up here, for that the controls are really far too strict. That is also not necessarily about the size of the punishment, but if you have attracted attention here somewhere then you will be endlessly controlled again and again and if an inspector WANTS to find something he will. For that a ship is simply too big. #00:50:20-3#
- I: *Does it costs... well, is that also an issue of time? Does that take time to get into a harbour state control?* #00:50:26-3#
- E11: Yes, if you are retained then it is getting really expensive. Well, that is pure self-interest when you are regularly operating up here you better comply with the regulations. Something happens time and again, certainly, people make mistakes, but that is never on purpose I would argue. #00:50:44-7#
- I: *Is everyone controlled in equal measure apart from that?* #00:50:49-0#
- E11: No, that depends a bit on the flags. As I said, they have criteria according to which certain flags are rather more likely to be controlled than other flags. Rule of thumb. #00:51:02-8#

- I: *I had recently heard something like... that there are also ships that comply with the regulations so little that the inspectors have no desire to take a look at that... #00:51:17-2#*
- E11: I have also heard these rumours, but as I said, they are rumours. I cannot confirm that. That is also why we are not employing such ships. #00:51:27-3#
- I: *No, that... I would not assume that at all. #00:51:29-4#*
- E11: Self-interest. Sail for once with a ship to Norway or to Sweden. They are very different there. Because then you immediately have the trade unions, the unions up your neck. No one wants that. #00:51:41-5#
- I: *Are the environmental standards easier to fulfil by some shipping companies than by others? #00:51:50-2#*
- E11: In principle no, because each one has to comply with the same regulations depending on the sea area. In that respect the actual implementation should also always be the same. Whereas it evidently is more difficult to make investments for a small shipping company with a thin capitalization than for a company like Hapag Lloyd for example. #00:52:17-4#
- I: *Does it make a difference whether I now have a bulker or a tanker or a ferry or whatever? #00:52:26-1#*
- E11: In principle no, because the technology on the ships is always the same. #00:52:31-7#
- I: *You were addressing problems with space for example. Is there... #00:52:35-4#*
- E11: With us? With the scrubbers? #00:52:36-7#
- I: *Well, are there some that have issues with space and other not? #00:52:40-1#*
- E11: Yes. A container vessel is built for placing containers really on each centimetre. Have you seen the pictures of the CSC Hope yesterday? #00:52:51-5#
- I: *Yesterday? No. #00:52:53-1#*
- E11: Or have you ever seen pictures of these vessels – you can also see it here (Pointing at the container ship on the graph) – I would argue that that is drawn much too big. They are slimmer. One really tries to completely fill each free metre with containers, thus where do you want to place a scrubber now? You can only put that somewhere... the main machine is back here, where do you place it? There is no space in the hull, there are containers standing about everywhere, you can only put that up above. The chimney comes out here. That means with a new-building you would normally have to include it directly in the superstructures. You cannot do that retroactively anymore. The space is simply not available. That is simply too narrow. #00:53:36-8#
- I: *Are there ship types that later have more problems with ballast water than others? #00:53:43-0#*

E11: They will all have problems with that. And the problem is the treatment and the technical solution that you chose in order to kill certain organisms. There are in the meantime a few systems that are now approved, but the biggest problem has obviously been that they had only been approved by certain agencies and were not approved by others. To my knowledge... #00:54:15-5#

I: *Now in the American area or...?* #00:54:17-3#

E11: That really was the biggest problem. Due to them really the biggest confusion came about, because they wanted to introduce something that could technically not be implemented at all. They did however not let themselves be persuaded that that was not possible at all. #00:54:31-6#

I: *Where does one get the information in the end which technology is the best or how does one find out?* #00:54:41-1#

E11: There one needs to go [“losmarschieren”] oneself. There you actually have to sit together with the producers. Then, what we have always done, there are often the first models that are being built, one then keeps some kind of contact with the respective shipping companies and talks about all sorts of things. But the first prototype, yes, that is always the risk. But you have that with new-buildings in general, when you are getting the first ship of a series you can expect that you will always get the teething troubles. [“Kinderkrankheiten”] #00:55:18-8#

I: *What hinders shipping companies to comply with environmental standards?* #00:55:23-7#

E11: Money. Well, that is my argument and... yes, whereby at the end of the day it always comes round to the money. If you are not training and instructing your crew correctly then you cannot implement that correctly. Above all things because if you take a look at out of how many nationalities a crew is made meanwhile there exist great cultural differences there. As a Northern European it is clear, that one does simply not throw waste into the environment. In other countries that is seen entirely differently. I even do not want to judge that. Thus, if you want to implement all of that then you also have to have someone who controls that. And you need to pay these people accordingly and instruct them accordingly and motivate them and control them and yes, that is a very cumbersome process, very tedious and in the end of the day it also costs money. #00:56:24-9#

I: *What kind of a development have you seen there in the last years?* #00:56:29-1#

E11: That the controls have become very much better due to the required reports, what you all have to do by now. But there is still room for improvement, because the controls are not yet dense enough. #00:56:46-3#

I: *That is the harbour state controls then?* #00:56:48-4#

E11: Right. #00:56:48-8#

- I: *Also in the Baltic Sea area? #00:56:50-5#*
- E11: Also in the Baltic Sea area. Ten per cent of the vessels are supposed to be controlled; that is what I recently read somewhere. Ten per cent. Thus 90 per cent are missing. Nothing happens there. #00:57:00-9#
- I: *Is that also your experience that you have the feeling you are only being controlled every now and then? #00:57:07-8#*
- E11: Oh well, the thing is that our vessels are evidently controlled more often alone for the fact that they are entering very many more harbours within a shorter time. Those are weekly round trips that start here in [German city], then go through diverse harbours in the Baltic Sea and end again here in [German city]. There the chance to be controlled is very, very big. If you have a bulker that has operated in Brazil and is going to some place in the Far East the chance is respectively lower. Thus, we are also very much stricter and also the ship owners are very much stricter regarding the actual implementation of the whole legislation. #00:57:43-0#
- I: *How do these harbour state controls work? #00:57:46-7#*
- E11: That is being decided by the respective authorities which ships will be controlled where. That is being implemented nationally. #00:57:55-8#
- I: *And will they always control everything? #00:57:59-0#*
- E11: No, they are deciding on a focus themselves. Well, at least according to my knowledge. They cannot with the – I almost said with the number of crew - with the number of personnel that those authorities have they cannot take apart a whole ship. They will check the documentation and will take a look at certain neuralgic points that is for example the sludge tanks, where waste oil and such things go into. They will take a look at whether the pipes are rightly installed. They will look at the oil record books, look at the waste record books. #00:58:35-9#
- I: *Can one also cheat in these record books? #00:58:39-0#*
- E11: Certainly! Paper doesn't blush, but my inspector also is not stupid. That has to make sense what you write in there. #00:58:49-6#
- I: *What happens when discrepancies are found? #00:58:57-1#*
- E11: That depends on how serious the discrepancies are. First of all, a corresponding penalty is imposed that is however still comparably small, at least here in Europe. That is then also always hitting the chief engineer of the ship and the captain, not the shipping company, despite them actually being the one that... that should not be forgotten. In the worst case the ship is contained. #00:59:26-8#
- I: *Can one speculate on that that one says: I do what I want and then the ship will just be contained? #00:59:34-2#*

- E11: Yes, because I will assume that it will not be contained. And if you are short of money in the shipping company... And you should not forget that we have had an unprecedented decline in charter rates for the ships since 2008. No one is earning any money any money or let me say it like this: Almost no one. Then one is saving – everywhere possible. And you – if you do not do the maintenance it will one day come back to haunt you. [“dann fällt Ihnen das irgendwann vor die Füße”] #01:00:04-5#
- I: *If we now look at the Baltic Sea – at what level do you estimate the overall compliance with the environmental rules?* #01:00:17-0#
- E11: Very high. Necessarily, because if you are now dumping oil here somehow that can immediately be seen. You know that the Germans conduct respective control flights. The Scandinavians have their cost guard that controls everything. That is very high. #01:00:37-4#
- I: *The OECS has done a study a few years back where they have said: Financially it can make more sense to pay the fees than to comply with the laws. Would you underwrite that?* #01:00:50-1#
- E11: Yes. #01:00:50-5#
- I: *Is that in practice a sensible behaviour. Would I get through with that?* #01:00:56-2#
- E11: Yes. #01:00:56-9#
- I: *And what would be the consequences of such behaviour?* #01:01:01-1#
- E11: Here in Germany it is like this: If the vessel is caught with a forged oil record book then it is not the shipping company that is held liable, but the chief engineer. The fine for the chief engineer depends on his income. If he comes from the Philippines you can figure out yourself how high the penalty will be, because he has not been caught in the act, but rather it was proved afterwards that he has not done certain things like he should have done them. If the vessel is now caught on the spot as it is dragging along an oil trail that is again something different, but the real penalties, they are minimal. #01:01:36-2#
- I: *Why is everyone still complying then?* #01:01:40-0#
- E11: No, not everyone is complying. #01:01:41-4#
- I: *Or the majority?* #01:01:43-8#
- E11: Up here you are reduced to complying, because here you will immediately be caught, at least for such big things like draining waste oil, cleaning tanks on the seas or something. You cannot do that on the Baltic Sea. That is simply too small here. As soon as you are out of here you can theoretically do what you want. Unless you want to go to the United States, then rather not. Yes, because they have a different case-law. There it is not the chief engineer that is held liable – well, he obviously as well, but there the owner of the ship is held liable and if you take a look at what kind of fees are imposed there... That

- can break your neck financially. They try that with deterrence and that is maybe also not the worst idea. #01:02:27-8#
- I: *Yes, that is surprising that one has obviously decided here against really deterring people.* #01:02:35-2#
- E11: Yes, that is a general issue. That would also not only concern the shipping industry, but also big industrial companies that have at some point twenty years ago buried a few barrels somewhere that they should not have buried. They would then also be held fully liable for that. Can you image that they would want that? (Laughing) #01:02:57-3#
- I: *Can one say that the average age of the fleet is a good indicator for environmental friendliness?* #01:03:04-4#
- E11: Yes. The more modern the ship the lower will the bunker uptake be, the better is the technical equipment. Yes. #01:03:14-0#
- I: *That means could I also assume that a shipping company with a very old fleet would have bigger problems than a shipping company with a young fleet?* #01:03:26-2#
- E11: That depends a bit on what kind of vessels those are, where they have been build. There exist twenty-year-old ships that have been built for example here at Sieters; they are excellent, because one has simply build in modern technology from the start also with a view for certain things. But in general, I would agree with that, yes. #01:03:52-4#
- I: *Are there substantial technical developments that you know about that make it easier for the shipping industry to respond to the new legislation?* #01:04:03-2#
- E11: LNG. LNG-powered main engines. With that you are at the same time solving the CO₂ problem as well as the sooty particle problem, sulphur problem – all that you will not have anymore. #01:04:14-8#
- I: *Are there still other difficulties or would that be a technology that would immediately be applicable without a problem?* #01:04:23-6#
- E11: The technology is there. It is not yet proved and tested. The respective legislation is not yet a hundred per cent completed, but just from a practical point of view I really do not see any problems. #01:04:38-6#
- I: *One is sometimes talking about supply problems that could arise or similar things.* #01:04:45-6#
- E11: At the moment all involved parties here in Northern Europe are feverishly building up their own logistics at the moment in order to get away from Russian gas. There I also do not see any problems. #01:04:57-7#
- I: *Would that also lead to a decrease in operating costs or would that not be thinkable?* #01:05:05-1#

- E11: The operating costs are later likely lower, because the technical effort will likely not be quite as large. With heavy fuel oil or gas oil you still need to do a lot – well, gas oil not anymore, but heavy fuel oil is very cumbersome to treat before you can even burn it. The problem is the security. We are suddenly talking about extremely cold materials. There the safety regulations are, I believe, in parts very, very strict and have to be, so that nothing happens. #01:05:39-7#
- I: *Would LNG be applicable for all vessel types and on all routes?* #01:05:45-4#
- E11: Theoretically speaking yes, practically speaking we have the problem with the tanks. An LNG tank would have to be much, much bigger than an oil tank that is clear, because the volume is very different. How one wants to put that into practice on small ships, without afterwards sailing about without cargo I do not know yet. #01:06:12-6#
- I: *Would that then even be thinkable on your ships?* #01:06:15-2#
- E11: Regarding retrofitting it has been calculated that no, it makes no sense. There are the main engines, all that can be done, the problem are the tanks. That will get so expensive I the end. You are also losing so much space that you would normally need for containers. Economically that is not viable for the existing fleet. New-buildings are in progress. #01:06:36-0#
- I: *Can one do something with the existing fleet in order to make the vessel in some way more efficient?* #01:06:42-7#
- E11: Just let it sail slower. Technically, as I said, we had all that calculated together with the shipping companies that are friends of ours or known to us. No one has done anything, because it was not advantageous. #01:06:58-0#
- I: *Are there innovations that are dreams of the future, that are still too expensive or not yet developed that one can hope for?* #01:07:07-4#
- E11: Yes, as I said, LNG really is the thing is the future for me regarding propulsion technology. How that is going to be one day with fuel cells and such things, there I am not technician enough. That would certainly be great if one could one day work that out. I would also save ballast, because all the batteries that I have down there, I would then not need any ballast treatment anymore. (Laughing) Yes, as I said, those are really the developments. #01:07:36-2#
- I: *How is the business model of the shipping industry influenced by current environmental legislation, by the SECA, by ballast water?* #01:07:44-2#
- E11: Well, first of all you need to reflect very carefully: What kind of a vessel do I need and is it even possible to push the higher rates that I need in order to make a profit at the market? That is what we have here in Northern Europe at the moment. If the Ro-Ro shipping companies are now saying: The traffic is not paying off anymore then it is being stopped. As simple as that. It is always a financial issue. #01:08:19-9#

- I: *How much will the rates have to increase or are they increasing at the moment?* #01:08:25-2#
- E11: To my knowledge apart from Maersk Line in the container sector really no one is making any profit anymore at the moment. But that has gone on already for a couple of years. They would have to double the amounts in the Far East traffic in order to be where they have once been. #01:08:40-7#
- I: *Can one now reallocate an investment, for example by retrofitting a scrubber or also the higher fuel costs, can one reallocate that to the customer?* #01:08:53-1#
- E11: Yes, we are trying. One can certainly do all sorts of things. The question is: Do the others do that as well? If I am the only one who is doing that, I am automatically losing cargo. If the add-on is too high and there are alternative routes like here in Northern Europe for example the rail or the street, then I am losing cargo to the competitors. That is the market. #01:09:14-3#
- I: *How does the current development look?* #01:09:17-2#
- E11: That is currently not yet really foreseeable, because we only just started, and we have passed the new add-ons on to our competitors and our customers and there one now needs to see how that becomes accepted in the market and what rail and road are doing. #01:09:38-9#
- I: *Thus, it is not: Wham! All prices immediately rose on the 1st of January?* #01:09:44-0#
- E11: Sure! #01:09:44-2#
- I: *Sure?* #01:09:44-7#
- E11: Certainly. We had to do that. That is... Again: Even if the current crude oil prices are extremely low, we still had this cost increase and before we have also already benefited from the gas oil, from the HFO getting cheaper. They have all been raised on the 1st of January. #01:10:06-9#
- I: *And are there now reactions on the side of the customer? Are they willing to pay higher prices?* #01:10:13-7#
- E11: At the moment they were not yet willing, but again, one will only see that when the Chinese New Year is over and when everyone has slowly sobered up a bit again, then one will see if shifts will happen, for example to Denmark, to Poland. #01:10:30-9#
- I: *If one now talks about shifts – are those rather shifts to the railway or to the street or to...?* #01:10:39-5#
- E11: Both. The containers will then... at the moment... let us take Hamburg-Gdunia as an example, that is currently being done to a large, large extent with feeder ships, because the amounts... normally it is comparably cheap to do that in large amounts on a ship, but the containers are going further into the back country from Gdunia. That is why there

- are for example direct train connections by the HHLA that are being offered. Well and then one has to see in the end, the customer figures out, who in the end of the day needs to pay for this overall transport, he figures out: What is cheaper for me? Is it cheaper to do that by train, then I am closer to my place where I want to have the container in the end or will I do that by ship and then I will still have to transport the container further forward again. That is a numeric example. #01:11:29-3#
- I: *Are there differences between the freight rates for ships and the freight rates for trains at the moment?* #01:11:37-2#
- E11: At the moment we are still cheaper. That is why we get the cargo. That is very simple. #01:11:41-6#
- I: *Thus, is that a constant trend or does that fluctuate back and forth at times?* #01:11:46-2#
- E11: As a rule, it is... that always depends on where you want to have the containers in the end. That question may really not be answered so globally. If I have customers sitting directly in Gdania, that is in the harbour where the container is being unloaded, it is evidently cheaper to do it with the ship. If I am however located in Warsaw or even further to the South of Poland it can easily be cheaper to do that by truck or by train. You have to take the whole transport chain into account. We are only a very small part of that. We are mainly transporting containers that come here from the Far East or America or somewhere. We take charge of the last bit until the harbour in the country of destination and the containers are going further on from there. #01:12:31-8#
- I: *Do sufficient capacities exist everywhere?* #01:12:36-5#
- E11: No. #01:12:37-1#
- I: *Where are the bottlenecks?* #01:12:39-5#
- E11: Everywhere. #01:12:40-4#
- I: *Thus, also on the water one would at one point...* #01:12:44-8#
- E11: Yes, not really on the water. Even if the Baltic Sea is relatively small. A lot of ships fit on there. The problem is the waterways and the problem are the available berths. And: Yes, there are problems. #01:13:04-6#
- I: *And if I am now looking at rail and road – one can imagine that not all sorts of amounts can still be switched at will or is that...?* #01:13:15-0#
- E11: Still, theoretically seen... well, railway, yes, they are slowly reaching... reaching the limit, but if I take a look at what is currently financed especially by the EU in terms of traffic routes, be it railway, be it street... There is invested massively and extended and the more they extend the more cargo they attract. #01:13:36-3#

- I: *How do the freight rates on the street and on the railway develop? May one...?* #01:13:42-7#
- E11: They are currently getting less expensive, because the energy costs are sinking and that really was the biggest cost factor in the last years. For us as well by the way. #01:13:55-1#
- I: *Could one think that also the freight... well, that with the sinking energy costs also the freight rates on the water might sink?* #01:14:04-0#
- E11: With us that is not possible anymore, no, because yes, our energy costs are sinking, but still due to the introduction of the SECA we have massively lost ground vis-à-vis the truck, also vis-à-vis the train, because our energy costs are, no matter where the current prices lie, around a third higher than before. #01:14:25-1#
- I: *Do you also expect tightened environmental legislation that leads to cost increases on street and railroad?* #01:14:32-6#
- E11: No, because the lobby is stronger. #01:14:36-0#
- I: *Okay, yes.* #01:14:37-5#
- E11: Yes, that is like it is. #01:14:38-4#
- I: *For which routes or well roughly are switches thinkable at all?* #01:14:49-2#
- E11: Everywhere where there are alternatives. You have no alternative... sure, you also have that by now, sorry, I have to correct myself, but in general you have, if you want to bring a container from Hong Kong to San Francisco or to Los Angeles you have no other option, apart from taking the airplane. That is extremely expensive. If you take Northern Europe und here or Europe in general than you always have the alternative transport on land to transport at sea, always. And even if you have a little piece of water in between you have a ferry in most cases who services that. #01:15:30-4#
- I: *Are there any routes in the Baltic Sea area where one could assume that they would first of all not be replaced even if the freight rates would increase significantly, because the ship just makes a lot of sense there? No?* #01:15:41-8#
- E11: No. #01:15:42-4#
- I: *Are there certain goods that are more difficult to shift?* #01:15:48-0#
- E11: Bulk materials, cheap, everything that is cheap. I mean for example if you have grit or something like that, building materials, if you have to take large amounts of that from A to B there is really only the alternative that you either take a ship or you try that by train. Whereas the ship is then still cheaper unless you need the building materials somewhere entirely different in the end. If your destination may not be reached by waterway in the end, if it is located in the middle of the inner land it can definitely make sense to rather do it by train, but trucks with those amounts that just does not pay off.

- You will do that with small charges, but not with big charges. Everything else depends on the price. That means: Where is the transport the cheapest? #01:16:42-0#
- I: *What does a switch in transport mode mean if you look at the transport time and transport costs? #01:16:54-4#*
- E11: Regarding the transport time, if you go from water to the street or to the rail you can even achieve an improvement. You will even achieve that, because a ship cannot go as fast as a truck and also not as fast as the train. Regarding the costs you will only switch if the transport on land is cheaper than the transport at sea, unless you also have the time factor up you neck. #01:17:22-3#
- I: *Does... can one imagine that for most goods costs play a larger role than time? #01:17:30-7#*
- E11: Time can certainly also be a cost factor, if I only receive the money when the goods have reached the customer then a few day or weeks can certainly make a difference. #01:17:43-6#
- I: *How significant are the cost differences at the moment? How much flexibility does the shipping industry still have? #01:17:48-6#*
- E11: We have already lost containers because he was five Euros cheaper than we were. Well, there is no minimum level. #01:17:58-2#
- I: *I have asked that. Do you expect changes in the amount and share of goods that are currently transported aboard ships? #01:18:09-8#*
- E11: In certain relations yes. #01:18:11-4#
- I: *Yes. In what kind of relations? #01:18:14-4#*
- E11: Everything that may easily reached by overland route. That means I would draw the line there. Denmark, South of Sweden, Poland maybe, but that will still take a while, depending on the development of the infrastructure, Baltic states. #01:18:27-3#
- I: *Well, those are exactly your routes. #01:18:30-5#*
- E11: Yes, yes. That is why we have been so much against this 0.1 per cent and not only us, but also the ferry shipping companies in the Baltic Sea have screamed blue murder and have said: You cannot dare to do that. #01:18:40-3#
- I: *Can one move to more attractive routes? Does it make sense to operate further then in order to have less competition? #01:18:48-2#*
- E11: I can only move to where there are flows of cargo. Well and that depends again on... as I said, we are feeder, mainly a feeder carrier, that means we arrange the connecting transport for global shipping companies to Russia, Poland or wherever else. Where do you want to move to? There are no alternatives. #01:19:17-9#

- I: *What kind of... if you now look at changes... where do they take place? Can one now assume that there will be modal shifts in the North and Baltic Sea area? Does that concern the whole European Union? Is that a global phenomenon? #01:19:40-7#*
- E11: You mean regarding the environmental legislation? (Affirmative nod by I) Globally that will not have any consequences, because it will still be cheap without competition to transport the goods by sea. At the moment there exists no cheaper alternative. Locally there will definitely be shifts if all these regulations are being implemented, yes. #01:20:06-4#
- I: *Yes, okay. What influence do I have overall on the costs of the shipping companies by the SECA, by ballast water? If you now take a look at the overall costs? #01:20:22-7#*
- E11: What kind of influence that has? At the moment you are building... if you now want to have a ship that complies with all of these regulations – and you should not forget that they apply only to a very small area of the globe, Baltic Sea - you are thus building a vessel for a very special sea area. Shipping is international however and no bank will finance an extremely expensive ship that you can economically operate only there – unless the charter party guarantees that he will employ the ship for rate xy for the next ten years. #01:21:11-6#
- I: *Will I get such guarantees? #01:21:14-1#*
- E11: No. #01:21:14-7#
- I: *Okay, that means: What will happen now? #01:21:17-7#*
- E11: That is very simple. Normally the ship owner will try to build an alternative. That is a ship that he can use globally as well as in special areas, but that will also be expensive, but he will simply hope that when he is operating it in this special area where he actually also wants to go that he will receive higher rates for it accordingly. Thus, he employs so-called dual fuel engines where he can burn heavy fuel oil as well as gas. #01:21:49-6#
- I: *If you now compare the costs due to environmental legislation with other cost drivers that a shipping company has to deal with – what kind of role does it play? #01:22:02-8#*
- E11: That always depends a bit on what you want to do. The biggest cost driver for... in the operation of the ship that you can actually have an influence on is the bunker consumption and the costs for the fuel. That is everything that has to do with the propulsion of the ship. That is expensive. The rest, I would argue, can all be managed. #01:22:34-4#
- I: *Are there other costs that are sinking or increasing at the moment? #01:22:40-8#*
- E11: All costs are increasing at the moment. That starts with the pay for the crew, if you need spare parts, if you have repairs to do, also the harbour fees are really rather increasing. On the other hand, the income side is furthermore very, very low, which is again related

- to the fact that simply much too little is paid for the transport of the goods. #01:23:08-3#
- I: *If you look at all these cost increases – which ones are the most significant?* #01:23:13-3#
- E11: So essentially you cannot... you cannot see it that way. Well, I would think that the sum of many small contributions equals a sum in the end that you cannot balance with your earnings anymore. Because in the past it has been the way that the charter you would get for your ships increased in relation to the cost of living and that was an indication for what you later had to pay in addition for repair for example. That is not working any longer for a few years now. The rates that you get for your ship remain at an extremely low level. The costs however are still going further up. #01:23:53-9#
- I: *What is the reason for that?* #01:23:55-3#
- E11: Oversupply of tonnage and too little cargo. Take a look at what number of vessels they have built. And: supply and demand. #01:24:06-7#
- I: *That cannot go well in the long run.* #01:24:10-7#
- E11: That is already not going well anymore. #01:24:12-4#
- I: *Which ones are the shipping companies that will not make it?* #01:24:15-6#
- E11: There are very many shipping companies... they exist already, that have not made it. Take a look at all these distress sales of ships that have been undertaken under German management in the last years. #01:24:27-8#
- I: *Why have they not made it and other have?* #01:24:31-8#
- E11: That is a question of how long your bank has patience, because the financing of these ships is done by the bank and these banks have not received any money any more for roundabout seven years. Nothing. When is their patience ending? #01:24:51-5#
- I: *Are German ships rather financed by German banks or is that...? (Affirmative nod by E11) Okay. That means in the end it is European against Asian banks?* #01:25:02-7#
- E11: With the Asians it is a little bit different, because there the big shipping companies... if you take, a good example is China Shipping. Those are state-owned enterprises. They can finance themselves very differently. Greek ship owner, who also have very, very many ships have a different tax model. That means their costs have maybe not been as high in the last twenty years. They have lined their pockets [“Die haben sich dumm und dämlich verdient”] nicely with their ships. Here in Germany we had this so-called KG-model [specific limited partnership model based on German law], that means the ships have practically been financed by very many small investors and they are now going down the drain in series, because they have to, in order to operate the vessels further you nevertheless constantly have to make funds available, in order to operate them. If you do not have the revenues anymore on the other side that you would need you will

- be in the red every month and you know about that yourself from private life. How long will your bank support that before they are shutting off the supply? #01:26:03-2#
- I: *Is that now the end of the German shipping industry? #01:26:06-1#*
- E11: It will certainly become much, much smaller, yes. And it will concentrate more and more. Until now we had a... very, very many shipping companies. I do not believe that many of those will still be there in two, three years. #01:26:20-9#
- I: *What kind of effects will unfold due to the concentration of the market? #01:26:25-3#*
- E11: The advantage of the German shipping companies has really been the flexibility with which they have reacted to everything in the last twenty years. That was always related to the fact that there were very, very many players and you have always found someone who would do certain things. You had big, small, middle-size. This whole spectrum was covered and especially the small ones were evidently rather more willing to cover a niche market and the feeder market on the Baltic Sea for example is a pure niche market, if you look at it globally. An incredible amount of things has been done there. That will stop or has already stopped. Then there will only be standard vessels. #01:27:06-2#
- I: *Is that a development in the interest of the customer? #01:27:16-0#*
- E11: No, I do not think so, because if you stall technological development and only have standard measurements anymore then you are also missing very, very many chances. #01:27:24-5#
- I: *Can one assume that if the market is concentrating that then the freight rates will increase again? #01:27:31-2#*
- E11: That is what one is trying to achieve with that. If you control a fleet as big as possible then you can evidently one day also say: You will only get my ship if you pay the price of xy. That is what is behind it. Apart from that one is also lowering the own costs, because if I now bring ten ships together under one roof then I am evidently also lowering the administrative costs accordingly. #01:27:58-6#
- I: *For which companies is it financially the most difficult to prepare for all of these cost increases? #01:28:06-9#*
- E11: Small companies with a thin capitalization. That is logical. #01:28:15-2#
- I: *We are now taking a step back from environmental legislation specifically. How does the competitive situation of the shipping industry currently look in general? #01:28:27-8#*
- E11: Hard as bone. (Laughing) That is related to... because, we have already talked about that, there have simply been built TOO many ships and the forecasts for the amounts of cargo were maybe a little bit off the aim and now everyone is fighting to keep his ships busy at all. #01:28:50-2#

- I: *What kind of developments can one expect with these too many vessels? Will some now be taken out of service or scrapped? #01:29:00-0#*
- E11: Many will be scrapped, but the problem lies with these very big ones. There the summit is not yet reached. There is still a pile of them coming. That again has a cascade effect on the smaller ships. What does that mean, smaller ships? I mean we are talking about 10,000 TEU ships that are now being replaced by 20,000 TEU ships. That is somehow really a little sick. But due to this cascade effect highly modern ships are being made redundant that then find a new employment. They are again replacing someone and so on and so forth. If that goes on like that then I do not see any chance. #01:29:41-8#
- I: *Does one have this problem with the increasing ship sizes also on the Baltic Sea is that that really...? #01:29:45-9#*
- E11: Here on the Baltic Sea you have the problem that... first of all you have the Kiel Canal. There are sadly only certain ships fitting through that. When they are bigger, they are only going in once and then the lock is shut forever indeed. The alternative is to sail around up North... is expensive, costs time and many harbours are not able to accommodate such large ships. Well, that is somehow the limit. We have not yet entirely reached that, if you leave the Kiel Canal out of this, but that will still take some time. #01:30:16-4#
- I: *But there is now no tendency that all harbours are being reconstructed and...? #01:30:20-1#*
- E11: Sure! Poland, Baltic states. In Poland Gdansk, DCT, Maersk is going with its very big 18,000 TEU ships into the Baltic Sea. They do that and they also want to keep doing that within this M2 that they are doing together with MSC. That has been the first one. And they are expanding further. They want to become the great Hub of the Baltic Sea. That means what is currently done for example in Bremerhaven, Hamburg that is then supposed to go further from there. #01:30:53-0#
- I: *That is going to be interesting. What are the developments for the next years? #01:30:58-7#*
- E11: Tell me how the world economy will develop. My personal opinion is that we will keep on working with what we have in the next years regarding the vessel types. At least here in Northern Europe. Starting in 2016, `17, `18 the first vessels will likely come up that operate on LNG, but they will not be bigger due to the restrictions that we unluckily have here in the harbours and owing to the waterways. And apart from that it is my assessment that the transport will localize more once again. That means we are again taking a step back from globalization, that obviously has not entirely brought about what many have hoped for and if I hear that from Brussels in parts, also what they express in Berlin and elsewhere, one is rather more bethinking Europe again. #01:32:01-7#
- I: *Also, with regard to the sinking energy prices? #01:32:06-2#*

- E11: Yes, because you have to keep your people busy and you can only do that, if you have producing industries. This idea that was behind it, production is taking place in the cheap countries and we are only consuming, because we have the know-how and we will be paid for that. That has sadly not worked out entirely. #01:32:29-7#
- I: *What are the biggest chances and risks for the industry for the next years?* #01:32:36-9#
- E11: The chances are to continue to offer cost-efficient, environmentally friendly transport. The biggest risk: A collapse of the world economy. #01:32:53-6#
- I: *Does environmental legislation play a role compared to other risks?* #01:33:01-5#
- E11: No. #01:33:02-7#
- I: *Which risks are more important or where does environmental legislation rank?* #01:33:07-5#
- E11: Everything that has to do with the economy directly, or rather with the misjudgement of the market development, if you, as has happened, build too many vessels then your fundament is suddenly gone, because you simply will not receive any money for your ships, either no occupation or if you find one you will not receive any money for it. Those are the biggest risks. Environmental legislation – all of that may technically be solved, but for being in America. Then one evidently has legislation that may technically not be solved, but they have it [incomprehensible]. (Laughing) #01:33:39-2#
- I: *Which other issues keep the industry busy at the moment entirely independent of environmental legislation?* #01:33:46-6#
- E11: The flows of cargo and the development of the sizes that is behind it. What do I do? What kind of ships do I built? What kind of ships do I need in ten years? That is my long-term business. #01:33:59-8#
- I: *Okay. I have two last questions. Are there important issues that I have not touched upon that I would have to take into account if I now... well, in order to understand this problem?* #01:34:14-2#
- E11: I think that was very comprehensive. #01:34:16-5#
- I: *Do you want to tell me anything in the end that is still on your mind?* #01:34:22-1#
- E11: No. Right now, not. I think we have talked about more or less everything that has to do with container shipping or shipping in general up here. #01:34:30-4#
- I: *Yes, wonderful. Then let me thank you heartily.* #01:34:34-3#

Interview No 12

Date: Monday, 16 February 2015, 10 am

Duration: 79 minutes

Method of contact: Contact was first established in November 2014 by contacting organization 12 and determining the person responsible for issues regarding the maritime environment. The person named was difficult to get hold of, but his secretary could finally be reached. She confirmed that her superior was no longer responsible for that area and promised to name a competent colleague. After frequent reminders E12 finally contacted the interviewer on January 8th 2015. After many attempts to find a date the interview eventually took place on February 16th 2015.

Interview situation: The interview was conducted via telephone. The interviewer has at home in sick bed but did not want to delay the interview once more, as it had been nearly impossible to fix a date. Due to technical difficulties the interview started a little late.

E12 was friendly, but cautious. He was arguing that the research questions were much too close to the arguments of industry lobbyists and warned the interviewer several times to stay unbiased. E12 was only working in his position for 2 months and had little knowledge on specific legal and technical questions. He had experience in environmental policy making on cars and was frequently referring to that sector. He could give insight on political thinking and reasoning but knew little about the shipping industry as such. Due to this, a number of questions could not be answered satisfactorily. His insights on how issues make it onto the political agenda were quite interesting however. Overall, E12 had little sympathy for the complaints of the shipping industry and asked for much wider environmental regulation. E12 talked a little down to the interviewer and treated her like a child, which made the interview somewhat strenuous.

E12: That's not a problem. #00:00:01-2#

I: *I also don't know what...* #00:00:02-3#

E12: Yes, somehow the technology is not helping much. Last time I was on the road I had a new iPhone or rather had downloaded the new iPhone Software which works differently than the one before in terms of deleting E-Mails and just by that your E-Mail was gone. Then I couldn't reply to it anymore. #00:00:18-6#

I: *But it is working now. I am in sick bed today, but ...* #00:00:22-8#

E12: Yes, it does sound a bit like that. #00:00:23-9#

- I: *I didn't want to reschedule it again. #00:00:26-5#*
- E12: Okay, I hope that it's not too bad for you. #00:00:30-2#
- I: *No, no, as long as the voice is working along everything is fine. #00:00:35-0#*
- E12: Okay. I have your paper with the research hypotheses right here in front of me. I don't know how you wanted to structure the interview, or which points you are mainly going to focus on. #00:00:44-7#
- I: *I have a list of questions. I would just go through them. In the beginning... #00:00:51-7#*
- E12: I can either answer them or not depending on my background. And yes, I think we should just go through them and see how much material you will get out of it. I also made some general observations that will be revealed throughout the conversation. #00:01:02-3#
- I: *Yes, wonderful. One thing right at the beginning. I have sent you this research consent form. #00:01:09-9#*
- E12: Oh right, I think I still have to send that to you. #00:01:12-4#
- I: *Right. I need your signature there, because otherwise I cannot use any of things I am collecting. #00:01:18-2#*
- E12: Yes, certainly. No problem. And I will scan that and send you the scan. #00:01:21-4#
- I: *Exactly. It's also important, I am just saying that right in the beginning, that everything that you are telling me will be anonymised completely meaning it cannot be traced back. I will still record the conversation so that I didn't come up with something you might have told me. #00:01:36-5#*
- E12: No, no. No problem. #00:01:37-4#
- I: *Okay, wonderful. Just to know who I am talking to you- in which position are you currently employed? #00:01:43-4#*
- E12: Okay, I am in the [European institution]. And the main work of this unit, well there are two divisions, one is Water Industry which isn't that important for us, it's about waste water and so on. The other one, which will be of interest for you, is the Marine Team and the team is mainly engaged in the implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. #00:02:18-0#
- I: *Okay, yes, that is exciting. #00:02:18-9#*
- E12: EPEC 2008, I believe '56, but don't pin me down on that. So the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. It's the framework directive that is used to work on the marine environment at European level. My function here is that I am supposed to build up the knowledge base, how to put this in German, well the knowledge, the basis, the factual

basis for the marine strategy. Especially related to the topics of availability of knowledge, making knowledge available and modelling. In this case, I have to say, I've only been working on this subject since last September. Before that I've been in the United States and I was the Environment Counsellor for the EU thus was working as a diplomat in the environmental sector in the rather horizontal level and before that I was occupied with the topic of vehicle emissions both related to pollutant emissions as well as CO₂ and before that with the topic of environmental effects of transport. And therefore, I also have a bit of perspective on your work here. #00:03:32-4#

I: *That is quite exciting. Is there a similar section in DG MOVE or are there similar experts with whom you would work together or is the whole team aggregated?* #00:03:46-2#

E12: Yes, of course we have one across from us in the DG MOVE and we also have a GD MARE. Those are our main contact persons. #00:03:55-6#

I: *Which topics are occupying you the most at the moment?* #00:03:58-7#

E12: That's a good question. Speaking about me, that depends a bit on my job description of course and that's only partly relevant for you. Well my main task is to increase our understanding of the environmental quality in the sea and the impacts of that environmental quality. To improve this understanding and to ultimately contribute to the goal of designing the European environmental policy related to the sea in a more efficient, effective and rational way. Well that is evidence-based policy making. #00:04:37-7#

I: *What are the biggest questions there at the moment?* #00:04:41-8#

E12: Well, there are two answers. The one thing is: what is written in the directive. The directive determines by law which subjects we are supposed to work on and there are eleven environmental descriptors written down which should represent or depict the so called good environmental status and that is basically everything under the sun. So, everything that is relevant somewhere. It reaches from biodiversity to the condition of the ocean bed, to noise and chemical substances. All of that are, that is basically the environmental policy onshore replicated in the sea. So very, very broad. In practice one will not be able to approach all these topics at the same time. How that is done is in the end the responsibility of the member states. We have this directive which is actually a machinery to make sure that that the member states are doing this. So, the member states actually have to define for themselves what is good environmental status? They have to determine indicators that describe that status. Have to define objectives for good environmental status and then have to define Programs of Measures in order to reach that status. That is the deadline for this year. This year the member states have to establish those Programs of Measures and then notify the Commission. The whole directive has a six-year-old policy circle, meaning that after six years everything starts again from the beginning - How far did we come? What needs to be done still? - and so on. In fact, the Commission does play an important role in the implementation of this directive. We have 28 member states, most of them have coastlines and of course not

everybody is simply doing his own, that would be completely irrational, but it is organised according to regional sea, how to say this, sea basins, organised according to regional sea conventions, so the HELCOM Commission for the Baltic sea, OSPAR for the Northeast Atlantic, the Barcelona Convention for the Mediterranean Sea and the Bucharest-Convention for the Black Sea. There are not only EU member states sitting there but also other countries, but those conventions are pulled up to create a convergence between the involved member states within those sea basins. And then all of that is put together on European level. That's a big management exercise in which the Commission is really active to organise for example an exchange of information and to make sure that for example the parameter that are used, the indicators, the definitions, the approaches are being harmonised as far as that makes sense. #00:07:18-3#

I: *Does this collaboration work the way one would imagine it to work?* #00:07:23-4#

E12: Well you can imagine, if 28 member states sit at one table, that's always like herding cats and that's never ideal but big improvements are being made. The directive only exists for a few years now and is now being realised and by realising it it's a big learning process for all participants. One of the really big challenges, as far as I've been told by my colleagues that are mainly working with the environment, is that different authorities which weren't working together in the past are now forced to do so. For example, planning authorities, maritime safety authorities, environmental authorities and so on. Those are all historically developed silos. It is always the case that one policy was developed around one topic and was implemented there, the corresponding institutions were established and that everything consolidates itself and then new interdisciplinary topics are coming up and that is a big challenge for everyone. And one of our tasks is to well break down those barriers and to make sure that the authorities on-site are actually talking to each other. #00:08:32-5#

I: *Which current changes do you know of that are especially related to the shipping industry?* #00:08:38-7#

E12: Well, I can't claim that I have a general overview. One of the topics that have really occupied me is the desulphurization of fuel in the shipping industry. I think that you already encountered this topic. #00:08:51-5#

I: *I did encounter it, yes.* #00:08:52-7#

E12: Well the famous SO_x- ECAs covered by the MARPOL Convention and that is a nice example for what is going on here. And I would like to insert some remarks that occurred to me while I was reading your research proposals. Well that is inspired by the shipping industry and the perspective is the one from the shipping industry. That is reasonable but I think you have to be careful as a researcher, as an academic, that you're not too close to one stakeholder because that is a risk for your credibility. For example, when I am reading here that those first three bullet points from the research hypotheses, that's completely reasonable from the shipping industry's point of view because they are on the receiving end of those measures so to say. A matter is imposed on them now which wasn't there before, which will obviously lead to costs. Those costs are rising and that's

obviously influencing the competitiveness but that does sound a bit defensive. And that is especially illustrated by the example of the desulphurisation. If you take a look at what is happening with sulphur right now. Now on the first of January this year the sulphur, the marine, I don't even know which directive it is now, the European directive that implements the European law that was agreed on in the IMO, it came into force and as a result one isn't allowed to operate on heavy fuel oil in the North East Sea or in the Baltic anymore as it happened before but you need to buy fuel that doesn't contain more than 0,1 percent sulphur. That is a big step because heavy fuel oil is two and a half percent of sulphur on average and suddenly, they have to get down to 0,1 percent. That means you have to buy marine distillates now, marine diesel instead of heavy fuel oil. That is a high rise in costs, no question. But if you take a look at the main competition onshore, meaning the road transport, which is driving with diesel fuel and the level of sulphur has been decreased down to 10 ppm for years with the diesel fuel. That's a hundred times stricter. So, if you observe the rise in costs of an industry, you need to compare that to what's happening somewhere else and the shipping industry is in many respects the very last industry that was approached with all these measures after all the other sectors have already been done. Typically, in the case of the desulphurisation they started with the biggest source, those were the fumes of power plants, so the Large Combustion Plant Directive was introduced, now Industrial Emissions Directive, forced desulphurisation of the flue gas. Then the road traffic was approached, the sulphur fuel, meaning the level of sulphur went down massively, also because of other reasons. Now one of the big remaining sources is the shipping traffic. Therefore, those measures. You have to view that in context. From the individual perspective of a vessel operator it is of course a pure cost factor, no question. I think from their perspective it is very important to consider, how the implementation is and whether there is a level playing field inside the sector. So: is everybody sticking to it? There are great efforts now, for example within the scope of the HELCOM-Commission, to introduce an enforcement that is actually credible because the incentive to bypass it is of course big for individual operators. That's an exciting topic, now they are working with remote sensing there, with chemical sniffers, with planes, so a highly interesting topic and really, really important to introduce this level playing field to avoid free riders. If you have a level playing field then the industry is forced in the end to pass those costs on to the end costumers, how it is also supposed to be for good economic reasons. You need to see the costs in order to know which effects you are causing. And that's only working if the industry is passing it on to the costumers and in for that they need a level playing field. Well that's an interesting topic. But anyway, my small advice is that you need to take a step back and also look around the shipping sector, what else is happening there. #00:12:54-3#

- I: *An argument that is often mentioned by the shipping industry in particular is this idea, there will be modal shift on the streets, we wouldn't want that to happen. #00:13:04-6#*
- E12: Yes, that's right and I also observe that this is reflected in your research questions because if you have the research setting, ship operators fear that environmental legislation could influence the number of goods transported on board vessels and

increase overall emissions. You have to be a bit careful there. That's a talking point that you would typically expect to be used by a shipping lobbyist, but of course, those people aren't stupid. It is common knowledge that the key interest of the shipping operators is by no means to clean up the air. That might be in interest of a private citizen who would like to breathe a clean air just like all the other citizens have it, but the business interest of shipping is obviously to keep the market share and not to clean up the air and that's a bit disingenuous. So that's a talking point that you would typically expect from a lobbyist but then the credibility argument comes into play. So, I think you have to be careful as an academic that you won't be recognized as a lobbyist. Of course...
#00:14:03-1#

I: *Well, I still have the possibility to negate all of those statements.* #00:14:09-4#

E12: Sure. Well I am just saying. The research proposal is what it is and that's your starting point, but I think as an observation that you, you don't necessarily have to negate it but I think you have to be careful that you are being received as balanced, as unbiased. It's a risk that an industry, which of course has an interest in your work, is going to eat you up or absorb you in a sense. So, you must be careful to keep that in balance. It is certainly true that there is a risk related to having the modal shift back on road not only in terms of emissions but also in terms of all those other effects related to road transport that ultimately come with it and that's also one of the reasons why the European Commission is actively supporting the modal shift to the sea as an example. I just saw a report about shipping last week, one moment I need to look for it quickly right now, I thought it was really interesting... I can't find it right now. It was published in the Daily about the modal shift and it said, well it was basically a criticism stated by experts from the industry that all this money was being invested suboptimal, but it was 350 million euro or something like that as a program from the European Commission to consciously support the motorways of the sea, to support the short sea shipping as an alternative to road transport. So, it was quite a conscious policy, among other things based on the consideration that the road transport should be relieved. How... of course the policy is never going to be implemented in an ideal way and there's always room for improvement but at least there's this effort. But it's also clear that an industry that is producing a certain environmental effect as a side effect of its activity, has to approach it pro-actively so to say. In Austria they have this so-called Floriani-Principle. Maybe you know it too. Dear saint Florian, spare my house, set others on fire. ["Lieber Heiliger Florian, verschon' mein Haus, zünd' and're an."] And if you want to solve an environmental problem as a policy maker and have to approach different industrial sectors, then you will generally hear about this Floriani-Principle for obvious reasons because the industry always wants others to do it and not the sector itself because that's related to burden sharing. That's very clear from the industry's perspective. From the perspective of the policy maker you have to try to impose the same marginal costs on everyone and that is a challenge because those costs are generally unknown, even inside those sectors. A very general topic, that those costs in the end... that's an information asymmetry that those costs are only known to the industry itself in the end and they obviously won't disclose that to the regulators. Yes. #00:17:11-4#

- I: *To understand this problem with the shift - in how far are there actually ways to shift the goods from the water back to the road? #00:17:24-0#*
- E12: Well, in the end you are dealing with a goods market and there are shippers and they will look for options and within a diverse decision-making environment and the industry as well as the politics try to influence this decision-making environment, so that someone who, I don't know, has to transport one hundred tons of cement from A to B is induced to do that simply with a ship instead of doing it by road or rail. And in order to guide those streams of goods you need to influence the decision-making environment of every single party. That's difficult and requires detailed knowledge about the respective sector. #00:18:10-4#
- I: *Are there specific goods or specific routes that aren't at all eligible for those shifts? #00:18:17-8#*
- E12: Yes, I already reached the end of my expertise there. I would assume that. I mean everything that you are transporting in bulk can be done easier with big vehicles. So when you are transporting bulk materials, iron ore, those things, that is currently done by ship for obvious reasons. Container transport, coastline container transport, no question. The more it gets into the distribution, the distribution logistics, into very detailed consignments, the less easy it gets to do that by ship. #00:18:54-7#
- I: *If you are saying that you've also dealt with road transport earlier, how big are the cost differences still between road and water at the moment? #00:19:07-4#*
- E12: Yes, that is just difficult to generalize. Because it depends extremely on what things you wish to transport. If you, I don't know, want to carry computers from a distribution centre to the end customer then the costs incurred by the delivery truck do not play a role anymore because the added value of that product is very high compared to the ton that you are transporting. If you are transporting scrapped iron instead of that, the equation is a totally different one. That depends extremely on the sector. What can be achieved by law or with cost signals or incentives or other instruments, that is on the margin. The markets are going as far as it still makes sense on the margin. At that time, we had, it is already ten, twelve years ago that I was actively involved in this thing, many examples of traffic that seemed pointless at first glance. For example, potatoes from Bavaria that would be driven via lorry over the Brenner to Italy in order to be washed there, loaded back on the lorry, over the mountains again, back to Bavaria and be processed there. It obviously pays off for the operators because otherwise they would not do it. But with big problems along the line, the mountain valleys are damaged and so on. So apparently there is a misalignment between the costs the operator sees and the effects which will then happen in reality. That is in many respects a matter of price and how much the freight transport costs. This is also actively discussed in Germany with regard to the truck toll. #00:20:46-0#
- I: *If you are saying, you are basically trying to actually burden all modes of transport equally, everyone has to contribute to environmental protection. If that entails that there are those shifts... back on the lorry, I don't know: The relevant studies indicate that*

transporting via lorry is harming the environment more every transported ton than transporting via ship – can you take countermeasures against this as a law maker? Is that even wanted? #00:21:36-8#

E12: Well, ideally you would... in an ideal world, that we are far off from, you would want to reach an environmental goal that indicates that all relevant sectors are burdened with the same marginal costs. Then you would be able to see, how much does it cost, what is the cost curve of road traffic, what is the cost curve of shipping and so on and you would ensure that, for example for every tonne-kilometre there is the same amount of marginal costs related to the appropriate measures. That is the ideal, that you are trying to reach that, but it does not work in practice because of different reasons. Starting with the fact that the world is complicated and that this kind of knowledge is often not available or is not available in sufficient detail and that is of course a political question too. You can, well there are not just economic costs during the implementation but also political costs during the preparation time of these political instruments. That is a very political discussion, which measures are in how far politically acceptable. That is related to the respective political constellations in the member states, so that means in the Council on European level and also in the Parliament and in the European Commission itself. #00:22:57-1#

I: *Is it more difficult to regulate shipping politically than it is to regulate road traffic? #00:23:03-2#*

E12: That is very difficult to say. I cannot give you a general answer to. You would have to ask someone who is in a high position somewhere in the DG MOVE, Mister Rüter, I would send him a question sometime and he would be beware of answering that question. That is a really sensitive question. It is clear that whenever a stakeholder is addressed, with the intention to burden him, there will also be a big resistance of course. That is of no question. And you can only pass this resistance if a sufficiently strong political will exists. That means generally speaking that there is a public that is also in favour of that. If the public says for example that the level of air particle pollution from diesel cars is too high, we will not take it anymore. You might remember that there was a big campaign some years ago. Greenpeace was driving around in a pink Mercedes with pig's ears and nose, the diesel pig. That really mattered to the public. That applied a sufficient level of pressure so that you were finally in the position to pass the so-called Euro-V-Standards that will enforce diesel particle filters to be used with diesel. That works if the public is sufficiently interested in a thing. If that is not the case, the resistance from the sector prevails, which is also keeping the costs low. #00:24:35-2#

I: *How much did public interest change with regard to shipping? #00:24:43-6#*

E12: I think that public interest was in general, without keeping track of it systematically, dominated by the financial crisis and by other crises in our environment from the Ukraine to the Arab Spring. If I compare that to ten years ago or even before that, public interest in the environment decreased significantly. But I also think, if you are looking at surveys, that people still want the environment to be kept clean, but they want to

delegate that so to speak. Everyone is already busy enough with their own lives and would like the lawmaker to take care of things. So, on the European level there is often the result that the environmental policy is on a very high level in terms of the European action being supported by people, whereas on other issues the EU experienced a lot of negative press lately. The public support does exist, but I think that it is less mobilized at the moment than it used to be in the past simply because other crises dominated, because there is obviously a news cycle for every topic, you will read about it in the news for some time and then it is fading away again. #00:25:59-9#

I: *Does that mean if the public is less interested the lobbies of the shipping industry will grow stronger or can exercise more power?* #00:26:13-6#

E12: That is a good question. I think what you can generally observe or at least what I observed in different sectors of environmental policy is the fact that it moves in waves. On the one hand there is a starting wave when a measure is being introduced. Conscious public policy is practiced and that is in the media and that is discussed politically. Someday a law will be passed and has to be implemented. The implementation is not as publicly presented, that is technical and time-consuming and difficult, and difficult to understand. If you try to read these texts, you know how it is, try to read an IMO paper, you will fall asleep. That is really, really difficult. That is reserved for a small group of specialists. Of course, that is an area where industrial representatives can exercise a lot more pressure because few people actually have the funding to follow these processes. #00:27:12-0#

I: *Are there, well if you talk to the industry then you often hear that they try to exert influence during the implementation and also try to bring down the original idea of creating a law. Does that work?* #00:27:29-2#

E12: That is working. For example, if you are digging for the topic NO_x emissions emitted by diesel cars, there we have, if you are looking at the limits in the legislation, they are since... since the middle of the last century... so 1970s, when they started to set those limits, this limit value decreased steadily. Right now, we reached EURO 6, so it is already the sixth version and the limit value of the NO_x emissions decreased every time. So, you should have the impression that diesel cars are emitting fewer and fewer nitrogen oxides, but if you put a mobile measurement device into a diesel car and drive around with it, you will see that those NO_x emissions are basically still the same as they always used to be. They did not change at all. This is particularly related to this mechanism that you just described. It is incredibly complicated to perform those emission measurements in practice. And that implicates that only a very small group of specialists which is coming from the regulated industry itself is able to make these rules and of course you will have a problem, the fox guarding chickens, that they will obviously take advantage of this, insert flexibilities that will obviously be used by the industry. #00:28:47-6#

- I: *I would like to speak a bit about the actual measures that are happening right now. What kind of current developments are there to better protect the maritime environment? #00:29:00-2#*
- E12: Well on European level there is the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. That is the main instrument. That is a framework instrument. It does not actually lead to direct actions itself, but it is an instrument to push forward a wide range of measures in a wide range of sectors. What kind of measures those are, is being decided by the member states right now because now they have to develop their Programs of Measures. I received, for example, a document last week, a public consultation from Great Britain, where this program is undergoing a public consultation and you will find similar processes in Germany. #00:29:41-4#
- I: *Is the legislation... well, where is the legislation or the main part of the legislation being developed? Does that take place within the member states? Is it rather mainly the IMO that is deciding on the main points? What is left to do for the EU? #00:29:56-8#*
- E12: That is diverse. You should not forget that the oceans are big and therefore a big number of players are involved. The IMO is of crucial importance everywhere where the regulation of shipping as such is at stake and that is an international enterprise, so for example all design criteria for a ship are regulated on IMO level in general. The IMO is a cumbersome tanker just like all the other international organisations because a lot of member states are obviously represented there and therefore the progress is relatively slow and you could obviously proceed much faster with smaller entities because it would be easier to reach consensus than it would be in the case of a really, really big... a really big corporation. But the IMO is obviously THE place on the international front, indispensable. It is also seen that way in Europe. We are represented there the EU member states as members of the IMO, the European Union as observers. There is a really dynamic and relatively complicated area of international law that is dealing with the question of what competences belong to the EU and what competences belong to the individual member states under the Treaty of Lisbon. And a couple of times I have already found myself in the situation that an EU-position in the Council, was negotiated in the Council and then the EU went into an international committee like for example the IMO with that position. That is the case everywhere, where a topic of the IMO is touching the EU competence and therefore it has to be coordinated on European level. You can imagine that this is an organizational and administrative nightmare and it requires a lot of effort and the battle obviously is not over yet. The Treaty of Lisbon has not yet existed for a long time yet. There are still areas of conflict between the EU institutions and the European member states related to the division of competences. That is a really active area for the involved lawyers. #00:32:12-4#
- I: *In your opinion which environmental goals were already achieved on European level? #00:32:20-9#*
- E12: Related to the ocean? #00:32:22-4#
- I: *Related to the ocean. #00:32:24-0#*

- E12: None. I think that the state of the sea is regrettable, is not improving and we are facing a really big challenge. Of course, we have really big challenges in the environmental policy in general because first of all the world's population is growing, there are more and more people and it grows explosively seven billion or so by now. And of course, the technical standard and the wealth of humanity on the whole are also growing. That means that the pressure on the planet on the whole is growing tremendously and as a consequence we can observe for example an unprecedented extinction of species. Well the loss of biodiversity can only be compared to the last big episodes of mass extinction in prehistoric time. #00:33:09-2#
- I: *Would you say that environmental goals were already reached in the shipping sector?* #00:33:15-4#
- E12: Yes, environmental goals, you have to differentiate between the environmental goals related to the state of the environment and the environmental motivated goals related to the performance of a sector and of course there has also been progress in shipping in that sense. And you could start a discussion about that, I do not know, from double-hulled tankers, so single-hulled tankers are not used anymore to the flue gas desulphurisation to the design criteria for fuel efficiency. So there are movements to improve shipping environmentally and that is why I believe that you are able to find positive examples if you are searching for them, but I think that the general impact on the sea is an impact that you cannot keep up, if you want to keep the sea in any kind of state. #00:34:10-7#
- I: *Just in relation to shipping. Where do you see the biggest need for action?* #00:34:16-4#
- E12: (Thinking) Yes, that is a good question. I do not have an adequate overview of that at the moment. There is... well the shipping industry is causing a number of effects related to air and water. A topic is evolving at the moment, which is: What to do with the sulphur if you are not allowed to emit it into the air? We have talked about this earlier, that you will buy fuel with a low level of sulphur instead. However, the shipping industry found out in the meantime that it is cheaper to desulphurize the sulphur, the exhaust gas, on board. Meaning to practice desulphurisation with so-called scrubbers on board and then you will have the sulphur on board and what do to with it? There are so-called closed loop scrubbers that neutralise that on board and then they have to dispose it in the harbour and so-called open loop scrubbers that simply pump the washing water into the sea – basically pump concentrated sulphuric acid into the water. And there is the question, how strongly does it take off? I do not have the overview at the moment to tell you if that is the problem number one. At least it is something that is appearing at the horizon at the moment. Big topics at the moment are desulphurisation, where a lot of work was already done. The next thing is nitrogen oxides, well they... there are not only emission control areas for sulphur dioxide but also for nitrogen oxide under the MARPOL-Convention. A big political issue at the moment, if and how to introduce these nitrogen oxide emission control areas. I think that is a really current, big topic and is not only subject to a lot of tension but above all also to legal disputes. It is exactly

about what I just said earlier, about this distribution of competences between the member states. #00:36:04-2#

- I: *What do you expect, what is going to happen in the next years there?* #00:36:07-3#
- E12: That is really difficult to see. In general, I do believe that we are still observing the birth pangs of the Treaty of Lisbon at the moment and that someday we will finally be able to create an agreement between the member states and the EU about... how to approach that topic. The political will does exist, to reduce nitrogen oxides and to introduce a NO_x emission control area particularly in the Baltic Sea. The HELCOM Commission, well the Baltic Sea Commission, is already at an advanced stage. Russia is the complicating factor at the moment, which is also a member in the HELCOM. And as long as the EU is busy with itself and has not yet clarified its competences properly, the EU cannot effectively approach Russia. Of course, the relationship EU-Russia is impacted by the Ukraine at the moment and it is in any case a front that is paralysed by third tendencies at the moment. But it will come. Nitrogen oxide is one of the big topics in air quality and the quality of... air quality and water quality onshore and that is why this topic will come and I expect that there will already be significant progress in the years ahead. #00:37:18-2#
- I: *Are only able implement those NO_x emission control areas in cooperation with the Russian authorities or would you be able to do that on your own?* #00:37:29-7#
- E12: You cannot do that because it is an IMO instrument and the involved states have to agree with that and Russia is eventually a neighbouring state as well. #00:37:39-3#
- I: *That is interesting too, yes. If you now compare these ideas to the regulation of sulphur - is that again something the ship-owners can heavily complain about? Is it also going to be expensive or is it actually not that important in the end?* #00:38:01-1#
- E12: Well, the instruments are different because you are physically dealing with another phenomenon. Desulphurisation is about the fact that there is a substance in the fuel, namely sulphur that has to go somewhere. Either has to go out before, before burning it or out of the exhaust gas and somewhere. But it is in any case a thing that is already contained in the fuel and needs to be put somewhere. Nitrogen oxide is totally different, because nitrogen oxide is coming from the air. How much or how little nitrogen oxide is produced by a ship depends on the burning process. This means what kind of engine you have and how you are operating it. And in the end, it is related to the building criteria of maritime engines. You can retrofit them, rebuild them but in the end, it is design criteria for ships and has to be approached very differently. These are obviously costs, no question. So, whenever you want to change the way an industry is managing its activity, whenever you want to change this, you have to spend money, because this transition costs money. It is quite possible that it does not cost that much money than before, but you have to reach that stage in the first place. That means you need to finance this transition and the industry is not going to do this by itself, because an industry is already occupied with pursuing their own intrinsic priorities and of course the role of

the environmental policy is also to impose more priorities from the outside. No industry is fond of that, neither onshore or at the sea. #00:39:35-1#

I: *What is to be expected regarding CO₂? #00:39:42-2#*

E12: Yes, of course it is generally the case that CO₂ is one of those really difficult problems, because CO₂ is of a different nature compared to sulphur dioxide and nitrogen oxide. The air pollutants are unintentional adverse effects so to say. Nobody is spending money to pump pollutants in the air. That is the adverse effect of other economic activity and you can, in a general statement, you can cope with that by improving the techniques, the qualities of the fuels, the quality of the machines and so on. If you do that then there will be fewer adverse effects, which nobody wanted in the first place. So there it is about an improvement of the respective technology. Regarding CO₂ it is different in so far as CO₂ is the main product that you want to produce. So as long as you are burning fossil fuel you want to generate CO₂ because that is the mechanism that dissolves the energy out of the fuel, gets it out. So as long as you are driving with fossil fuel you need to produce CO₂ in order to generate energy and therefore it is a different topic in its nature. It works partly also via the efficiency of machines, by increasing the efficiency, but in part you will need to switch to other fuels in the end. And that is why the climate change is such a different problem compared to other environmental topics. It is also different, because it is far more complex. Well nitrogen oxide only come from a handful of sources or sulphur dioxide only comes from a handful of sources and therefore you need three, four political instruments to approach this and then the job is done. CO₂ is being emitted everywhere, no matter what you do, wherever you go to, what you do in your private life or in business, it is producing CO₂ and that is why we have those phenomena across the society which goes deeply into the energy policy and which is present in all the other political sectors in some form. Hence the introduction of an emission trading system to take account of this diversity. That is a very different system. In the end we will only be able to take a grip of the climate change if all sectors are participating, of course that also includes the shipping industry. And what was achieved until now are the so-called design criteria in the IMO which means that at least new ships are build according to higher efficiency standards. #00:42:07-2#

I: *That means, can one expect that the shipping industry will also be a part of the emission trading system sooner or later? #00:42:14-1#*

E12: That is impossible to forecast. That is a really, really deep political question. #00:42:19-2#

I: *What does it depend on? #00:42:22-7#*

E12: (Laughing) Well that is... What does all of this depend on? Whenever you want to reduce the emissions of a sector there are a lot of influencing factors and of course one influencing factor is the interest of politics itself. Maybe you kept track of how our European emission trading system is doing. It is not doing well, because the price of allowances is considerably lower than expected. This has to do with the financial crisis, which caused many marginal profitable industrial sectors to be taken out of production

and after the crisis we started with a sort of adjusted industry where a lot of old plants did not exist anymore and the economic volume in general also decreased. As a consequence, we have far less emissions than what was intended. But the emission legislation had planned a certain volume of emissions that would be introduced to the market as planned, allowances, thus there is an oversupply of allowances and then it happens what happens in a market where the supply is bigger than the demand, then the price collapses. That happened to the trading certificates and one tried to face this by for example strengthening the emissions target, which failed because of the resistance of certain member states. Then they tried to take second-best measures and for example to take out allowances from the market now and to park and introduce them back to the market at a later point. But this as well... that is being done but in a weakened form. So, it is really, really difficult to proceed in this matter. That is one of the most difficult political topics to capture.

If you are specifically thinking about the shipping industry, of course the shipping industry will not remain immune against this discussion. But it is even more difficult to approach the shipping industry than other sectors because of its international characteristic. Just like the air transportation. If you think about the history of climate legislation, internationally it started in 1990 with the framework convention on the climate change, then there was the Kyoto protocol in '97 and then they said, okay, shipping and international air transportation, we are parking it and we are giving it to IMO and ICAO ["International Civil Aviation Organization"] now and they should do something about it. They decided to work on the big fishes first and to deal with both these international bunker fuels in their own committees first. As a consequence, nothing happened. ICAO and IMO established working groups and composed papers, but nothing happened, which you should not find surprising, and in the end the pressure increased and then the IMO created these design criteria which is quite advanced compared to other sectors. It is also difficult in the air transportation and in the end the lack of international progress resulted in the EU integrating the air transportation into its emission trading system on its own. And that again led to what in the internet you would call a shitstorm, heavy resistance from the industry... and in fact from outside Europe... heavy resistance from other countries so that we are now in a situation where we pulled back a bit. So, it was one of the topics that politically were originally perceived, around 2001, '2, '3 as a gap closure, where one would say, okay, now we already have done all the other sectors, we are already doing something there and now we also have to approach the other sectors. And then we approached that, and it turned out to be much more difficult than we thought it would be. And this difficulty lies in the international multi-stakeholder nature of these industries and I do not think that is going to change in the foreseeable future. #00:46:29-1#

I: *Is that due to the fact that they try to escape this legislation or because it is difficult to enforce it in the first place?* #00:46:40-8#

E12: Well, it is just an international situation. We talked about the level playing field in the beginning of our conversation, what is important in the industry. If you have to impose a rule on an industry, then all parties need to be equally subjected to this rule. And if

you have an industry where the ships are registered somewhere on the Bahamas or in Nigeria, then it is difficult to force through something single-handedly in Europe. What we are able to enforce is the access to our market. For example, we can enforce these things like port state control measures, we are quite able to enforce those, because Europe is still the biggest market globally so that these ships will come even if we tighten the rules a bit. That is quite feasible. So, there is political scope, but it is limited. #00:47:30-0#

I: *Are there... or do you notice kind of tendencies that shipowners try to bypass the safety zones, so they are not approaching the North Sea and Baltic Sea anymore, but they call at a port somewhere else? #00:47:44-2#*

E12: I do not have enough information about this. The DG MOVE would need to say something about this. Generally, I would think that if you are looking at the total costs of a cargo ship approaching a port, then the costs of pulling into an emission control area are probably only a fraction of that. They are certainly integrated into the marginal analysis somehow, but if you are then deciding whether you are or are not approaching the port in Rotterdam, I think, a lot of other considerations also play an important role. Because if you have goods that are being transported to Northern Germany or to Poland, whether you are transporting them from Hamburg or from, I do not know, Genoa that is a huge difference onshore. There is a reason why we have all these ports everywhere. So, I would assume that at the border it will certainly, on the margin it will make a difference, but the question is how big it is. That is a quantitative question. I am missing the information for this. #00:48:46-0#

I: *A topic that still remains, which is also an environmental indicator, is noise. Are there movements that you would regulate the shipping industry in relation to noise? #00:49:01-9#*

E12: Noise is a topic, if you are looking into the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, a descriptor, the eleventh of the eleven that is “Introduction of Energy Including Underwater Noise”. So that is a topic. It is in the beginning, because the knowledge is insufficient. There is a wide range of noise sources from the shipping industry, through construction, so through the construction of offshore structures, through... I do not know what else. And then of course a really big topic that nobody speaks about, military. All of these are noise sources and noise are definitely a topic. It is slowly beginning at the biological perspective, that we have a better understanding of the impact of noise and which species are affected. That is definitely a topic. It is also going to grow, and I think it would be in the interest of the shipping industry to address this proactively now, because I am certain there are low hanging fruits, that there are options to reduce the noise of a ship, of a ship propeller, of an engine in a cost effective way. #00:50:08-1#

I: *A question that I asked myself is how much knowledge do ship-owners actually have about what they should do? So how well would you say are ship-owners informed about the environmental legislation? #00:50:28-0#*

E12: That is a good question and I have not been into this topic long enough to decide this. Generally, it is a topic, because the legislation is obviously complicated and diverse. Associations actually exist because of that. Every industry has its association on a European level and one of the tasks of these associations is to establish an overview of the rules that you are actually subject to. Those are the organisations... Then there are maybe also consulting companies which do the same thing. I think that is a constant challenge, also a challenge for the policy makers to make their rules as clear as possible. Now the Juncker-Commission purposely lined up with the claim to approach things clearly. That is also the claim of every new administration, it was also like that with Baroso. That is a good claim too. You should do that. You should make the legislation clearer and I am sure that we can reach improvements in many respects. And that is because all these rules have grown separately from each other. Each has a good reason for its existence, and it is often crunching if they are being applied at the same time, no question. Therefore, there are these re-fit activities in the Commission where you are looking at existing legislation and ask yourself if they are still fit for purpose. So, there is an active effort to make legislation more practical. You will find, that actually sounds a bit like a no-brainer, so a non-political topic, but it is actually a highly political topic in reality and that is because whenever you somehow open up an existing rule it opens doors for those who always wanted to change something about that rule. It is really, really difficult to only update a law formally without changing the content. And thus, the corresponding big political meaning of all these re-fits. #00:52:25-2#

I: *What is it like if new laws are being passed and I am for example looking at the NO_x regulation - do I have to look at all the existing legislation of the shipping industry and calculate a model based on that or do I look at... am I only making an impact assessment for that one measure? #00:52:48-2#*

E12: In general, you are doing this impact assessment for this one measure. Ideally you obviously want to understand where the shipping industry stands. So in any case, if I am now dealing with the concrete example, I want to reduce the NO_x emissions, then I would first ask an consultant to find out how that can be achieved, what are the techniques, what are their costs, how is the industrial structure in Europe, which operators are there, how are they positioned in terms of different techniques, so for example small sized ships, medium sized, big sized, different usage profiles of these ships, what does it mean for these ships? You would try to understand this as accurately as possible. And then you would try to design measures in a way that the sector is influenced as little as possible. Of course, that is being perceived differently in the sectors because they are just observing that a bunch of bureaucrats are sitting there who want to impose something on us that we do not want. Understandably. From the perspective of the policy makers the motivation is of course to reach your goal with as little negative adverse effects as possible. So. Both sides actually have the best intentions so to say, but then the real world gets in the way. First of all, the real information, where the industry stands is obviously... and where the industry stands... is obviously only available to the industry itself. But the industry obviously has no interest at all in showing the legislator exactly what is going on. Therefore, the legislator is in the dark,

needs to hire consultants from somewhere, which also do not have the knowledge or if they do have the knowledge then they have that knowledge, because they are dealing with that industry a lot. Those kinds of consultants obviously cannot afford it to annoy their main costumers. Therefore, this consulting industry will be very careful with their statements. And the result is that these impact assessments are in general more conservative compared to what would actually be possible. That is the one thing. The other thing is that the industry usually has time horizons. So, if someone who is already changing the production process, to put another element into the specification sheet, then it fits well. But if they already did that just two years ago and this investment needs to amortize over the next fifteen years, then it does not fit at all if they come along with a new rule. Well, now it would be good if the legislator knew exactly what the time horizon is. Then you would be able to custom-tailor it for the industry. Well, but the industry will not do one thing for sure, namely, to tell the legislator those things because that is commercially sensitive. You will not communicate that to anybody. So, you have... as legislator you need to somehow guess a little bit where the industry is standing, then you will make a proposal and then you will listen to hear how loud the whining is and that way you will find out if it is possible or if it is not possible. That does sound a bit dysfunctional, but it has do with the interests of the involved actors. #00:55:56-2#

I: *Is [organization 12] in any way actively involved in informing the industry about current and future legislation?* #00:56:06-1#

E12: That is the aspiration. So, the idea of the impact assessment also has to do with consultation. I cannot speak for [organization 12] as a whole now but in the political sectors I was working in, it was always the case that even in a stage where it would still take years until any measure would be introduced, we would start with the preparatory studies, that you would already create stakeholder-groups and already try to first of all inform this industry about what is going to happen and secondly to get as much information as possible from that industry. That did not always happen. A popular counterexample that I know of is the end of life vehicle directive, so a directive on scrap cars and it was prepared, and the industry was surprised when the proposal came from [organization 12]. And there was a lot of bad blood. I do not know how that happened. But in general, those parts where I was involved in, industrial participation as well as NGOs and other stakeholders were always represented from the beginning. #00:57:11-0#

I: *Would you say that most or all of the shipping companies are equally well informed or are there some who find it more difficult to access information?*#00:57:22-0#

E12: Oh, certainly. You always have a really unequal profile. I do not think that you can tell anything to Møller-Mærsk, they are big enough to know everything. But if someone is operating a small shipping company, he will have bigger difficulties spending his time to keep himself up to date. So, I think that is certainly... there is certainly a distribution between those who have a good knowledge and those who do not in every industry. The general statistic is already indicating that. #00:57:48-6#

- I: *Would you say that ship-owners always understand everything that is being demanded from them? #00:57:55-7#*
- E12: I cannot say anything about that. I do not know. #00:57:59-9#
- I: *An interesting thing that the association told me was that actually more and more ship-owners are leaving the association for financial reasons. #00:58:14-7#*
- E12: Yes well, that is of course a decision of each individual ship-owner who is undertaking a cost-benefit analysis. The membership in the association is obviously a cost factor, but the withdrawal from the association is a risk factor. For example, you will have less knowledge about legislation on different levels than before and that knowledge will either be purchased from any kind of consultants which again costs money or you will risk falling in the legislative trap and then paying fines or otherwise. Those are also costs. So, I assume that ship-owners need to consider cost-benefit-observations but that is also going to be an expression of the economic situation in general. #00:58:58-8#
- I: *Would you say that shipping companies generally tend to stick to environmental standards? #00:59:07-1#*
- E12: I have not been in the business long enough for this. I think what you can observe in other sectors that I saw is that nobody is actively appearing as a criminal to actively avoid things and break laws. But many laws have many grey areas and I think that many grey areas are being used extensively. #00:59:31-6#
- I: *(Hesitant) Well, it is difficult. Of course, I have a number of questions related specifically to the industry... Could you also say that company size is a factor? So, it is rather big ones who comply and rather small ones who have difficulties? #00:59:58-4#*
- E12: Yes, I think compliance is not only a question whether you can do this, but also if you want to. There the group policy or company policy comes into play. In general, the basic rule is that bigger organisations have more options for action than small ones. The bigger they are, some day they will be big enough so that they can afford a position that does nothing but monitoring the legislation, to have a vice president for government affairs. Only big companies can afford that, small ones cannot. Of course, there is a difference there. I assume that the challenge in compliance is certainly different depending on the company size and it also has to do with the company policy. #01:00:43-5#
- I: *Are there differences according to the flag state or also headquarter? If we are now talking about the company policy? #01:00:54-8#*
- E12: Yes, I am again not sufficiently informed there. I would expect it, but I cannot say that. #01:01:00-3#
- I: *What prevents ship-owners from meeting the environmental standards? #01:01:04-8#*

- E12: Cost pressure, internal perception. What you will often see in other industrial areas and I would expect that to be also true for shipping companies is that the knowledge is not equally distributed. That many things are just specifically related to perception and you therefore might get a different idea of something. Once you get the idea, because you were forced to or because you were inspired somehow by something, then you will suddenly also have ideas and are then able to do it. I think that the state of knowledge is definitely a topic. #01:01:51-6#
- I: *How do the inspections work?* #01:01:55-4#
- E12: I also do not know that. #01:01:57-2#
- I: *Okay. Meaning you also cannot give an assessment as to how well it is working or how frequent controls are?* #01:02:05-6#
- E12: No, it is difficult for me to assess that. I would generally expect that controls are not sufficient, because public authorities are under cost pressure, especially at the moment in this current public atmosphere it is politically almost unenforceable to say, we will increase the staff in order to monitor the legislation. #01:02:26-8#
- I: *Has ..., have... or could you say that in the course of the financial crisis the personnel capacity maybe rather decreased than increased?* #01:02:36-2#
- E12: It certainly did not increase. I would say as a general tendency. They are pulling no punches [“die Bandagen sind härter geworden”] in the course of the financial crisis. #01:02:47-7#
- I: *If I hear at a meeting of ship-owners that nobody actually expects to be monitored - is that naive or realistic?* #01:02:58-2#
- E12: I would say it is naive. I cannot evaluate how realistic it is, because I do not know the industry that well, but we do live in a densely populated world, highly industrialized world and it is characterized by a high density of rules, no matter if you want that or not. I think to operate in this kind of industry and to think that you are above things is not realistic in my opinion. #01:03:24-3#
- I: *In how far did the current environmental legislation... so if we are not only looking at sulphur but also... there are a couple of measures that happened there, actually have an impact on the business model of the ship-owners?* #01:03:43-5#
- E12: On the business model of the ship-owners... That is an interesting question. Well as far as I understood the environmental policy in other areas, it is generally the case that although environmental policy is causing costs, but it is also just one cost factor among many cost factors and therefore shifts things marginally but is not fundamentally questioning it. I would also expect that in the shipping industry. #01:04:14-8#
- I: *Would you think that there are differences between the shipping companies?* #01:04:20-6#

E12: Certainly, certainly. #01:04:23-7#

I: *On which... or what would you think?* #01:04:26-2#

E12: Well, as already mentioned it also has to do with the company policy in the first place, with the attitude of the companies. There are for example company bosses who would like to be green if they could afford it. Nobody likes to be a bad person. Then there are... well there is political orientation from the management. There is the sector that you are working in and how strong the competition is, how you are positioned inside. There is also a... how do you say, a spread, so a distribution of companies in every market. Some companies are technology leaders, some are followers, some are well administered, some are badly administered, some have a heritage of old ships that they need to drive around with and do not have the capital cover to renew that. Others have for some kind of reason had the opportunity to put new ones up for themselves. All of that interferes or influences the way that the management will make decisions. And as a consequence, you will find a company policy that for example might also change with a change at the top. #01:05:29-3#

I: *Did... do you expect an impact on freight rates that results from a cost influence?* #01:05:37-9#

E12: That is a good question. The theory, well if you read a European impact assessment, you will generally find the assumption that marginal costs are passed on to the customer and then they will calculate how strongly the sector is going to move. You are de facto dealing with a competitive industry, and it is an individual company decision whether they are passing on the marginal costs to the customer or whether they first absorb the costs to keep market shares. That also has to do with the positioning in the market. Therefore, I think it is more complicated than simply passing on the costs. In the end you would expect and hope that in a well-functioning market the costs are ultimately passed on just like that as they also should be, because the final customer is after all the reason for why this activity is being done in the first place and should also pay the relevant costs. #01:06:30-5#

I: *But you would... first assume that, because of the way the shipping industry is positioned at the moment, with the increased competitive situation, that you actually are not passing on all of the costs because you also cannot afford to do so.* #01:06:47-0#

E12: Yes, you will also find that with road traffic. I cannot really say that for the transport of goods, I was not really dealing with that, but very clearly for the automotive industry. So we have a beautiful history of environmental measures that we introduced in the automotive industry, from Euro 1 to Euro 6, with the CO₂ for cars, may other measures and every time there was an impact assessment where the costs were calculated and you would then say, this costs this many hundred or thousand Euro and it will impact the automotive market volume in that or that way. Something like that was de facto never observed. So, with the introduction of a new emission legislation where the impact assessment would state 400 Euros per car, you never observed an average price jump of 400 Euros, but what happened instead was that the industry would introduce innovations

as an option which they would have otherwise introduced for free or maybe a year later. So, inside that diverse operational framework of industry the industry regrouped itself in order to somehow absorb the costs and you actually did not observe any effects on the purchase prices of the products. Apparently, that is how consumer markets work. #01:07:59-7#

I: *If I have different statements from certain ship-owners who are saying, yes, we are passing on hundred per cent of the costs - can I also assume that there are arrangements? #01:08:12-6#*

E12: I do not know that. That is a really tricky topic. Someone in my position needs to be very careful with that too. There are legal requirements in terms of arrangements and each individual ship-owner is in that situation where he needs to decide what he is doing, but you would hope that the individual market players are complying with the laws. Of course, I am also not naïve. Of course, there is this temptation to not be doing this but that is also associated with a legal risk. #01:08:42-5#

I: *Okay. I need to check... We already discussed that. I will take a step back again. How would you evaluate the competitive situation of the shipping industry in general? #01:09:04-6#*

E12: Yes, as I said, I know far too little about that. #01:09:07-6#

I: *Okay. So, you probably also cannot say anything about the developments in the next years? #01:09:16-2#*

E12: No, that depends on the general expectation of how the economy is going to proceed in general and I think that is quite uncertain at the moment. So, when I look at and that is... you would need to talk to people who are dealing with the development of economy in general. I saw that both the development in Greece as well as the development in the Ukraine ironically caused the DAX to reach a new maximum level. Apparently, the economy holds the view that it is not going to be that bad. At least for the investors. I think that it would be also interesting to consider that. #01:09:52-7#

I: *Would you say or what kind of role does the environmental legislation play in comparison to other risks of the industry? #01:10:02-5#*

E12: (Thinking) That is a good question. I assume that environmental legislation does play an important role amongst many other topics. It is an important role, because there are many environmental rules and because they are often associated with possible sanctions in the case of non-compliance or with costs for the compliance. But that is one element amongst many elements. The most important thing is how to survive the competition in day-to-day business in a generally quite competitive market. How is the economy developing? There are a number of topics that a management needs to keep an eye on. Environmental legislation is of one of them. #01:10:48-7#

I: *Last questions. Are there other topics that I did not mention before that would be important for my comprehension of the problem? #01:11:01-7#*

E12: Well, we already had a relative broad discussion, so I would think that we already covered everything. #01:11:11-4#

I: *Okay.* #01:11:12-7#

E12: So basically, I think that there is the temptation for the industry to say: Everything sucks, we are only having difficulties with that, all of these environmental activists they should leave us alone. That is psychologically quite understandable. But I think that from a professional perspective each industry needs to be aware of the fact that we live on a very densely populated, overused continent which is highly civilized, which is dense, which is highly regulated and nothing will be able to reduce this number of rules and therefore it is a risk for the industry to say: I am not getting involved, I am withdrawing into my corner to sulk and if a new law is introduced again then I will be terribly annoyed. I think that is a general guidance that it needs to be a great interest of the industry to participate actively. And... because you are on site when decisions are made. And in terms of participating actively I am not only talking about traditional lobbying to mitigate rules, but also about understanding that these environmental rules and other rules always have a reason to exist. The NO_x emission controls and SO_x, they are not there for fun, but they exist because it is in the interest of the industry to understand that there really is a problem and that it had to be approached and I think that is why it is in the interest of the industry to understand what these problems are and to address it pro-actively and to say, we want to be a part of the solution, not only of the problem. #01:12:42-2#

I: *In how far is the industry getting involved at the moment?* #01:12:45-6#

E12: That is varied. So, from some organisations and some companies you are hearing something and from others you are not and that again depends on this differentiation and on the company strategy and so on. For example, if you are the green market leader in your sector, then you want to say that out loud first of all because it creates good PR and second because it puts pressure on your competition. So, you have an interest in stepping into the public and approaching the legislator and being pro-active. Whereas if you somehow missed an investment circle or do not have an interest and suddenly this green thing comes along, then that is an irritant and then you would rather want to fight that. So that is obviously the distribution of interests in the industry. #01:13:25-7#

I: *But that means that those who are collaborating pro-actively right now are often companies who have a special interest in environmental protection?* #01:13:36-4#

E12: Well I cannot come up out of blue air with that, this the interest of the industry right now, how they are doing this. I think that the general logistic is obviously that if you invested for any reason to make your ships cleaner, then you do not want your competition to have a cost advantage by still driving around dirty, but you want to impose the same standards on them. #01:14:01-1#

I: *Are there other experts that you could think of who I should really talk to?* #01:14:10-3#

- E12: There certainly are a lot of them. Ship-building... #01:14:24-1#
- I: *Is there someone directly from [organization 12] who might also have further knowledge about the industry?* #01:14:31-7#
- E12: There certainly is someone. But then again, I am a bad contact for you because my network is only under development. There is a man in [department of organization 12] who was responsible in the former [department organization 12] for the ship-building industry until recently. His name is [name of colleague]. #01:14:52-8#
- I: *[Name] and then what?* #01:14:54-8#
- E12: He is of interest for you. That is someone who knows the industry very well. #01:14:58-4#
- I: *I did not really get the name.* #01:15:00-7#
- E12: [Spelling the name.] #01:15:02-9#
- I: *[Spelling the name.] Okay.* #01:15:05-1#
- E12: If he has an interest in speaking with you, I cannot say... #01:15:11-1#
- I: *Yes well, I have to see that.* #01:15:12-9#
- E12: That is an expert in shipbuilding, who therefore knows more about shipyards than shipping companies, but as he knows the industry very well I would expect that he also has some good observations about that. Yes, apart from that I think it would be in interest for you to cover the spectrum inside of your industry and to speak with some ambitious companies and some unambitious companies and to find out where they are standing and why they are standing there. So, if you would speak to Møller-Mærsk that would be interesting for you, I think, to find out what is driving this company. They obviously have completely different considerations than if you are in the cruise sector or if you are a local short sea shipping operator. #01:16:00-0#
- I: *Yes, I already talked to different big and small ones. That is really quite interesting. Whereas it is obviously the most difficult to approach those who care the least.* #01:16:14-1#
- E12: Of course, of course. That is also the general problem in terms of compliance checking. But exactly there is the added value. The rest was already discussed by many others and where it is not so easy to get through, if you manage to find a little crack somewhere, you can actually create real added value. #01:16:33-2#
- I: *Okay. Would like to tell me anything else at the end?* #01:16:38-7#
- E12: I already told you that in the beginning. I think your work starts intellectually close to the industry, which is also fine, but I think you need to be careful to be perceived as balanced, because otherwise you will have an effect where the industry thinks it is great and others, well where the green NGOs say, well yes, that is a paper from the industry,

- we do not even need to continue talking about that. And that would be a pity because then you closed a door. And people can bear being told things that they do not really like as long as they have the feeling that it makes sense. #01:17:18-8#
- I: *Yes, that is true. The theses are adopted from the newspaper, but I am really rigorous when it comes to testing. So, I do not know if everyone will like the results. #01:17:36-2#*
- E12: Of course, it is...I am making it easy for me. I have this position in [organization 12] and therefore I can brag about this. It is not that easy for you, because you are only starting your career and I think you need to... it is important to find a tone when talking to these people where they are able to accept things that are not that pleasant and that is happening if you, or it seems to me, if you get the impression that is someone who has worked carefully and real facts, that is actually what I found out here and give people the impression while presenting, I know where you are standing, I know that is a problem for you, that is difficult for you, there is no way around that. And how are you able to do it so that everyone can somehow live with that. So you are conveying pragmatism, conveying intellectual honesty and carefulness. #01:18:32-5#
- I: *Okay. Thank you very, very much. #01:18:35-8#*
- E12: Good luck with your work. #01:18:37-4#
- I: *Thank you. Exactly... #01:18:38-4#*
- E12: I would be interested in the final result. #01:18:40-2#
- I: Yes, me too. *(Laughing.) #01:18:42-6#*
- E12: How much longer do you have? #01:18:43-9#
- I: *I still have two years, but the qualitative investigation are almost over and that means that the first results are hopefully published within the next months. #01:19:00-3#*
- E12: Okay. Well, then I wish you good luck with that. #01:19:02-9#
- I: *Thank you. Thank you for your time. I would be much obliged if I would also get the Research Consent Form. #01:19:09-9#*
- E12: Sure. #01:19:10-5#
- I: *Exactly. Thank you very much and have a nice day. #01:19:12-8#*
- E12: Yes, and happy recovery. #01:19:14-3#
- I: *Thank you. Bye. #01:19:15-4#*
- E12: Good bye. #01:19:16-4#

Annex B7: List of codes and coding frame

Codesystem	Category 1	Subcategory 1	Subcategory 2	Subcategory 3	Codings Total
					2730
	Legislative aim				4
		Operative efficiency			14
		Ship recycling			9
		Sewage water			28
		Oily water			37
		Noise pollution			27
		Anti-fouling			21
		Air pollution			39
			Nitrogen oxides		23
			Particulate matter		10
			CO2		54
			Sulphur		132
		Ballast water			73
		Dumping of waste			40
	Legal framework				0
		Political interest			41
		Political process			66
		Significance of environmental legislation			0
			Of minor importance		39
			Important		34
		Acceptance of legal framework			0
			Issue well regulated		10
			Adjustments necessary		51
			Issue under-regulated		33
			Issue over-regulated		14
	Awareness of legislation				0
		Much paperwork			24
		Difficult apprehension			41
		Easy apprehension			9
		Lacking awareness			34
		High awareness			58
	Compliance				0
		Effectiveness of controls			2

		Unsure about effectiveness	17
		Controls lacking	36
		Controls working	65
	Estimated compliance level		0
		Lacking compliance	35
		Over-compliance	16
		High compliance	25
	Motivation to comply		0
		No commercial advantage	28
		Lacking time	13
		Want to	12
		Have to	45
		Commercial advantage	45
		Unwilling non-compliance	12
		Willing non-compliance	38
		Lacking financials	57
	Felt need to comply		0
		Have to contribute	31
		Already clean industry	26
	Technical options		2
		Economically viable	13
		Economically not viable	38
		Available	44
		Availability problematic	63
		Implementation viable	10
		Implementation difficult	51
		Operation viable	7
		Operation difficult	25
		Developing	50
Effects			0
	Effects on consumer prices		0
		No/negligible effect	1
		Increasing	11
	Effects on trade flows		3
		Supply increasing	5
			Growing companies
			5
			Increasing ship sizes
			17
		Supply decreasing	1

			Redeployments	5
			Vessel scrappings	17
			Consolidation	64
			Routes closing	20
		Effects on freight rates		3
			No effect	6
			No direct link	9
			Effect unsure	18
			Freight rates increasing	43
		Effects on costs of operators		2
			New vessel investments	8
			Burden sharing owner-operator	29
			(Re-)construction cost increases	54
			Operational cost increases	106
	Differences between operators			0
		Customers		6
		Ownership structure		6
		Financial situation		9
		Company culture		30
		Existing		9
		Not existing		30
		Company size		62
		Classification society		7
		Seat of operations		18
		Age of vessels		30
		Vessel specificities		21
		Flag state		28
		Routes of operation		27
		Fleet composition		38
	Viability of modal shift			3
		Possible		53
		Impossible		23
		To other water routes		14
		To rail transport		17
		To road transport		35
		Changed sourcing		5
	Market structure			0
		Supply of capacity		6

		Overcapacities		28
		Unchanged		2
		Demand for capacity		2
		Unchanged		7
		Decreasing		5
		Increasing		11

Table 10-2: List of codes and coding frame

Annex B8: Definitions of categories

Category Definitions

This is how all category definitions will look like:

Label:	
Description:	
Examples:	
Decision rules (if needed):	

The definitions can be found here as follows:

Label:	Environmental legislation Dumping of waste
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where dumping of waste is mentioned
Examples:	„ And dumping of waste as well is always... especially in the media and the cruising industry... a topic, also for politicians.”

Label:	Environmental legislation Ballast water
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where ballast water is mentioned
Examples:	“Currently, because a lot of what we do is driven by regulation, a lot of our work is around the Ballast Water Management Convention and the various implementation issues or challenges, technology selection, technology challenges around that.”

Label:	Environmental legislation Air pollution
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where air pollution is mentioned, especially whenever the theme of discussion are emissions of CO ₂ , NO _x , SO ₂ , particulate matter or other types of air pollution.
Examples:	“Well, we have first of all been talking about air [pollution], that is where currently most things are happening, I think.”

Label:	Environmental legislation Anti-fouling
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where anti-fouling measures are mentioned
Examples:	„Toxic anti-fouling systems is the area, I would suspect, that is the least regulated at the moment...”

Label:	Environmental legislation Noise pollution
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where noise pollution is mentioned
Examples:	„The deep sea resolution with the propeller noise is still vague so I don't have a picture yet on the effect on cost on that one.”

Label:	Environmental legislation Oily water
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where pollution through oil-contaminated water or oil spills are mentioned
Examples:	„Oily water is still spilled in European waters.”

Label:	Environmental legislation Sewage water
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where sewage water pollution is mentioned. This category is also relevant whenever a reference to grey or black water is made.
Examples:	„Management of grey water is always an issue.”

Label:	Environmental legislation Ship recycling
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where ship recycling is mentioned. References to the Hong Kong Convention also fall under this category.
Examples:	„The Hong Kong convention is awaiting ratification.”

Label:	Significance of environmental legislation to the industry Very important topic
Description:	This category refers to a section of an interview that indicates that environmental legislation is of great importance to the industry. References to it being the most important topic at the moment, more important than other topics or in general of great concern fall under this category. It will also apply if only one specific rule is mentioned as being important.
Examples:	„It is THE factor that influences the industry the most at the moment. In this year.”

Label:	Significance of environmental legislation to the industry Other topics more important
Description:	This category refers to a section of an interview that indicates that environmental legislation is of minor importance to the industry. References to it being less relevant than other topics fall under this category.
Examples:	„If you are a LNG gas tanker owner and you are spending all your hard earned [costs?] on building more ships, because you anticipate a massive boom in LNG trade around the world with the U.S. shale gas revolution and all that and then on top of that you have actually made a lot of money, you know,

	over the past four or five years because of the Fukushima accident in Japan, when Japan suddenly decided to close off all the nuclear power stations, to use gas to power the country. So you do all that and life is great and then all of a sudden, I think it was announced a couple of weeks ago that Japan started opening some of the Nuclear reactors again, made them operational. That is a massive risk and it means a massive reduction in cargo. So what does this do for your freight rates? What does that do for the ships that you have already been building? And all that. So this is an example of the kind of risk that ship owners live and die by every day. And actually, those who predict those better are those who make more money. I guess the environmental regulation is a bit of a constant. It is much more predictable; it is a much more predictable risk. It simply translated to a constant increase in operational costs.”
Label:	Acceptance of the legal framework Over-regulation
Description:	This category refers to a section of an interview suggesting that there be too much regulation on vessel-source pollution.
Examples:	

Label:	Acceptance of the legal framework Under-regulation
Description:	This category refers to a section of an interview suggesting that there be too little regulation. The category is applied whenever an interviewee hints at a possible or necessary increase of environmental legislation in a specific field or in general for the shipping industry.
Examples:	„It depends on how you work it out but personally I see PMs as a true area where you have to increase the efforts. PMs are really what is causing a lot of the bad air that we have around in Europe at the moment. And there is really nothing regulating that today. So I think that should come. There will be some kind of regulation for that.”

Label:	Acceptance of the legal framework Necessary adjustments
Description:	This category refers to a section of an interview suggesting that adjustments to the legislative framework are necessary, without the level of legislation being either too lax or too strict. These adjustments refer to suggested changes in policy making, implementation and enforcement. Issues of participation in the process are also applicable here.
Examples:	„I mean the problem we have here is the sulphur regulation will be significant and will have negative effects on companies and jobs and whatnot. And in my mind the problem which we have here is that it is a kind of a big bang implementation. Everybody has to comply as of one day. If you look at say the NOx tier three legislation that is for new buildings. If you look at the Ballast Water Convention you have a five year phase-in-period. But the sulphur regulation is everybody on one day. And that is a very big shock to the system.”

Label:	Awareness of legislation – Acquisition of information Full awareness
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Description:	This category refers to passages in an interview that suggest that ship owners and/or operators are fully aware and informed about the legal requirements that they have to meet.
Examples:	„Most of the people that I deal with are fully up to scratch when it comes to the knowledge.“, “It is relatively easy to acquire information.”

Label:	Awareness of legislation – Acquisition of information Lacking awareness
Description:	This category refers to passages in an interview that suggest that ship owners and/or operators are not fully aware or informed of the legal requirements that they have to meet. This category is relevant whenever an entire lack of awareness or missing awareness on parts of environmental legislation is hinted at. It also applies if certain groups are described as being less informed than other groups.
Examples:	„But I wouldn’t be surprised that there wouldn’t be ship owners, operators out there in the world that are less informed than we are.“

Label:	Awareness of legislation – Apprehension of information Easy
Description:	This category refers to passages in an interview that suggest that information on environmental legislation may easily be apprehended by ship owners and/or operators.
Examples:	

Label:	Awareness of legislation – Apprehension of information Difficult
Description:	This category refers to passages in an interview that suggest it is rather difficult for ship owners and/or operators to apprehend information on environmental legislation.
Examples:	„It is relatively easy to acquire information. To digest it and fully understand what is meant is something more complicated.“

Label:	Costs to ship owners and operators Operational cost increases
Description:	This category refers to a section of an interview where operational cost increases are mentioned or discussed. Operational cost increases mean increases to the fuel costs, maintenance, management and operations, personnel and all other types of costs that increase with the amount of goods transported and are not linked to the construction or reconstruction of a vessel.
Examples:	„And we just couldn’t see that with the new costs coming on that it could be viable going forward. Had there been other good elements in there we might have continued, because it is... The one reason that made us take the decision was the coming sulphur regulation and the costs associated with that.“

Label:	Costs to ship owners and operators (Re-)construction cost increases
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Description:	This category refers to a section of an interview where construction or reconstruction costs of vessels are discussed. That is always the case when retrofitting a vessel with ballast water management systems or a scrubber is discussed, or when the construction of a new-building with LNG propulsion is suggested as well as in all other cases where changes to the vessel at a shipyard is producing costs.
Examples:	„The other two major ones is either exhaust gas screening systems, which is I guess a technology transferred if you like from the land-based industry, from power stations with for over 60 years most qualified, certified power stations they are using exhaust gas screening, scrubbers as they call them, to clean the exhaust gas. This is transferred to ships and there are a lot of providers that offer solutions to this. And the basic principle is: You can still operate on dirty fuel, if you like, which would not be normally allowed to use, but this is being treated, so the resulting exhaust gas is at least as clean as it would have been if you were to burn the most expensive fuel. And although your operation cost remains very stable, to a certain extent, minus the operational costs of the system itself, you have got the capital costs as a ship owner which you have to consider.”

Label:	Burden sharing among owners and operators ?
Description:	This category refers to...
Examples:	...

Label:	Available technology options Available
Description:	This category refers to technology options being available. This includes that technical equipment is operable on board of vessels and little, if no technical problems occur in using technology options. Minor modifications that are necessary, but not very difficult to conduct, will still fit this category.
Examples:	“Yes. For those companies that have chosen to comply by fuel switching as opposed to comply by technology it is very straightforward. There is a certain procedure that needs to be followed. For certain ships there could be some modifications that need to be done on the fuel tanks and on the fuel supply system. But they are not in an enormous scale. And most ship operators are quite familiar with what they need to do. So the switching, technologically, it should not be a problem.”

Label:	Available technology options Availability problematic
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that hint at technology options being not available at all or not available for all competitors.
Examples:	“The supply of LNG is not [available] at the moment. It is easier, I guess, in ports within Europe, so if you look at major ports it would be much more easy to take care of that. But again, if you look at deep sea, I think what is holding the industry down at the moment is making sure that there is going to be availability on certain ways where the ship is stopping.”

Label:	Available technology options Economically viable
Description:	This category refers to technology options being available and implementation being economically feasible for all or some vessel owners and/or operators.
Examples:	„Some of them may definitely yes. I mean we have on a number of our ships we have changed the propeller, we changed have the motors and that is a significant cost. But there we can do a business case and see you know how much fuel we will be saving by doing it and as long as we are within the payback time it will be fine, acceptable. It is a thing we can do.”

Label:	Available technology options Economically not viable
Description:	This category refers to passages that hint at technology options being available, but implementation not being economically feasible for all or some vessel owners and/or operators.
Examples:	“And as you pointed out – if a vessel is too old there are less options.”

Label:	Available technology options Developing
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that deal with future possible technology options that are not currently widely applied, but may be applied by vessel owners and operators in the future in order to comply with environmental legislation.
Examples:	“The other thing that is being, I guess, considered and we are considering ourselves in respect to certain clients is further down the line fuel cells and batteries and hydrogen fuel cells. This is a possibility, but I think we are probably at least five to ten years away from starting to see cases.”

Label:	Freight rates Effect positive
Description:	This category refers to statements that hint at a likely increase in freight rates due to the increase in operational costs experienced by environmental legislation. The category is applicable when passing costs on to the consumer of shipping services is described.
Examples:	“I think if you look at again the ship owner/operator short sea market, if there is no other way to mitigate for that cost it will have to be passed to the customer. So, if the cargo owner is a customer, then the freight rate might increase.”

Label:	Freight rates Effect unsure
Description:	This category refers to a position in an interview that states that the relationship between freight rates and operational costs is unsure.
Examples:	“

Label:	Freight rates No direct link
Description:	This category refers to a passage in an interview that indicates that there is no direct effect or only limited directed effect of increases in operational costs of ship operators or owners on freight rates. This is for example the case when the influence of mechanisms of supply and demand on freight rates is described.
Examples:	“On the other hand, if you are in the deep sea, the freight rate is not so much affected by individual operational costs. It becomes a function of supply and demand of the [product?]. So I do not think that this, I mean, I do not think that we can find a direct link between increase in operational costs and increase in freight rates in the deep sea, because simply if there is enough ships to carry the available cargo globally of all ship types, that is what will define the freight rate in many cases, with or without environmental legislation. The freight rate will simply reflect what more ships and what cargo we have and therefore ship owners will be losing money.”

Label:	Trade flows No or negligible effect
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that describe maritime environmental legislation to be having only a negligible effect or no effect at all on international, European or regional trade flows. This category also applies if interviewees speak of consumer prices not being affected.
Examples:	“Anyhow, with respect to these large relations, I think it is not really relevant.” “Because the deep sea, that is a completely different business model. The consumer is not really affected.”

Label:	Trade flows Positive effect
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that point at environmental legislation having some or significant effects on the flows of international, European or regional trade. This category also applies if interviewees speak of increases in consumer prices.
Examples:	“I don’t know if it is perceptible or measurable, but the legislation that is currently planned by the EU or is in force for European harbours certainly has effects on international trade and those who operate it. In such a way that for those, the bunker costs or whatever else are higher.” “My guess is that short sea, whatever is transported by short sea, a certain proportion of this cost will be passed on the supply chain and ultimately to the consumer.”

Label:	Felt need to comply Shipping is a clean industry
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Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that point at shipping being a very clean transport mode. The felt need to comply with environmental standards is low.
Examples:	„Roughly put, let’s say in principle the shipping industry is one of the most environmentally friendly methods of transport that exist, compared to everything else. Therefore the shipping industry is first of all rather something “good” - in quotation marks.”

Label:	Felt need to comply Shipping has to contribute
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that point at shipping damaging the environment and therefore having to contribute to advances in achieving a cleaner environment.
Examples:	„Nonetheless the shipping industry has to make its contribution to the global climate protection and environmental protection aims.”

Label:	Willingness to comply Having to follow the rules
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that point at the shipping industry complying with the rules, because they “have to”. Comments arguing that there is a need for shippers to comply will fall under this category. Answers hinting at a commercial advantage from compliance will be classified under the category “Willingness to comply – Commercial advantage”.
Examples:	„But, the majority of companies, I would say, in my experience, maybe 80%-90% of companies that either own or operate ships, what they do is very much driven by what they have to do, which is regulation.” “So what I am saying is, there is a vast majority that will comply with whatever is out there, because that is their licence to operate.”

Label:	Willingness to comply Commercial advantage
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that point at the shipping industry or parts of it complying or overcomplying, because they gain a commercial advantage from it.
Examples:	„Of course you have got some industry leaders or industry pioneers that will go beyond compliance in various different ways, but even those who do that, they do that because they recognize the commercial ... or they have found ways to gain commercial advantage from going beyond compliance.”

Label:	Willingness to comply Unwilling non-compliance
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that point at the shipping industry unwillingly not complying to environmental legislation. This may be due to a number of reasons, among them technical difficulties, accessibility or apprehension of information and others.

Examples:	„That is not to say that, that there would not be non-compliance incidences, which will be discovered by port state control, but personally I do not believe that these happen willingly. They happen as a result of an accident, as a result of an oversight. But I don't think that strategically these guys have chosen not to comply.”
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Label:	Willingness to comply Lacking financial resources
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that point at the shipping industry not complying due to a lack of financial resources.
Examples:	„There is a motivation, but the financial resources are not necessarily there.” “No, but you will still have a cash flow issue that you will need to look at. How much credit are you getting with your fuel supplier? How much credit are you giving your customers? Normally there is a gap there.”

Label:	Willingness to comply Willing non-compliance
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview that point at the shipping industry or parts of it willingly circumventing the rules and regulations on environmental legislation. The category also applies if willing non-compliance due to lacking controls is mentioned.
Examples:	„I think it is companies that you, I and no one else have ever heard about and never will. They are invisible shipping companies. They have one ship, one or two ships, which are either very old, maybe chosen willingly to operate not internationally, but maybe in a more restricted area of operation, they would probably choose a non-trustworthy or less trustworthy flag, they would probably choose a class society which is not a member of IACS [International Association of Classification Societies] and that you and I have never heard of.” “It's like a speed limit on a high way you know. If there is a speed limit and you advertise in the paper that there will not be any police then the chance that the speed limit will be deceived is bigger, right?”

Label:	Actual compliance in the market Full compliance
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview hinting at full compliance with environmental legislation by all operators.
Examples:	E: „ <i>What percentage of ship owners would you expect not to comply?</i> E2: (thinking) I don't have any answer to that. (laughing) I think, I would say zero.”

Label:	Actual compliance in the market No full compliance
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Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview hinting at no full compliance with environmental legislation by all operators.
Examples:	„I cannot really clearly say. As NEVER everyone follows the rules.” “I would assume, that environmental laws and regulations here in Germany and by that also in [city A] are complied with to 90-95%, simply because the controls work correspondingly well. “

Label:	Actual compliance in the market Over-compliance
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview hinting at certain operators over-fulfilling environmental legislation targets.
Examples:	„A number of shipping companies try to establish a name with that. Well, the AIDA for example, they always advertise with and for the fact that they run particularly environmentally friendly.”

Label:	Effectiveness of controls Controls are working
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview hinting at controls of environmental compliance working and being effective. Descriptions of how these controls work also fall under this category.
Examples:	“Those who only trade inside of the SECA area they will really not have a chance to not comply. Because if they do not comply you would actually be able to see it directly on their financial accounts that the cost has not gone up. So they do not even have to measure anything there.”

Label:	Effectiveness of controls Controls are lacking
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview hinting at controls of environmental compliance lacking. The category refers both to the fact of lacking controls and reasons behind this lack. Statements referring to limited financial resources of authorities and technical difficulties to control compliance fall under this category.
Examples:	“Well we have to see. Port state control is already in operation today and they check a lot of other things. They do not check a lot of fuel compliance. There is some worry within the industry that there will not be a lot of policing going on from next year.”

Label:	Effectiveness of controls Unsure about effectiveness
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview where interviewees were unsure about the effectiveness of controls.
Examples:	“I think, I don’t know. I cannot tell whether there is absolute efficiency. I assume, and I would say, that it works in any case more efficiently [in city A] than in most other harbours of the world and also in the EU. “

	“Well I mean the sulphur legislation if we take that is supposed to be enforced by the port state controls in the countries. Whether it will happen or not is a different question but that is the way they are supposed to do it...”
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Label:	Differences between ship operators Exist
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview where interviewees argue that differences generally exist between ship operators.
Examples:	„I guess, you know, it is not easy to put the shipping industry in one big box and read everyone the same.” “Again, we are trying now to put commercial shipping into a whole big basket and we treat everyone the same...”

Label:	Differences between ship operators Do not exist
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview where interviewees argue that there are no differences between ship operators.
Examples:	“Ideally all of these upcoming requirements should not have any effect on competitiveness, because they apply for everyone. So what are the golden rules of competitiveness? It is having a level playing field. Everything applies for everyone.”

Label:	Differences between ship operators - Size Size does not matter
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview where interviewees argue that the size of ship operators does not matter
Examples:	<i>I: Would that also be the same for small and large companies are they affected in the same ways?</i> E5: Yes. It is down to the ship.”

Label:	Differences between ship operators - Size Smaller companies have it easier
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview where interviewees argue that smaller companies have it easier to comply with environmental legislation.
Examples:	“Large companies have a reputation to lose.”

Label:	Differences between ship operators - Size Larger companies have it easier
Description:	This category refers to sections of an interview where interviewees argue that larger companies have it easier to comply with legislation than smaller companies. Answers that mentioned better equipment with resources such as personnel, money or information fall under this category.
Examples:	“And as I mentioned the example with the packaging regulation, there are often small companies affected and medium-sized [companies], that don't

	<p>even know about it, as they don't have personnel who could engage themselves with that.”</p> <p>“I think that, I would say it is the big shipping companies that first of all have the resources to implement various initiatives.”</p>
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Label:	Differences between ship operators – Fleet composition Fleet composition does not matter
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that fleet composition does not matter in terms of effects of environmental legislation on the shipping company.
Examples:	I: “ <i>Does the business sector again make a difference? So would bulk carriers or container carriers or whoever rather tend to comply than the other?</i> ” E5: No, I don't think that really.”

Label:	Differences between ship operators – Fleet composition Older fleets have it harder to comply
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that companies operating older fleets will face more difficulties due to environmental legislation than companies operating younger fleets.
Examples:	“You know, certain companies will close down, it is going to be the evolutionary process and whether it was possible, you know, 10-15-20 years ago to operate a ship, which was 30 years old and you did not have to comply with much, because much was not there, it probably will not be possible now and that is a fact.”

Label:	Differences between ship operators – Fleet composition Passenger vessels have it harder to comply
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that companies operating passenger fleets will face more difficulties due to environmental legislation than companies operating fleets for the purpose of transport of goods.
Examples:	“I think that all vessels that first of all carry passengers and not containers or goods, that they handle the topic with more sensitivity. On the one hand precisely because they transport passengers, and when you talk a look at [city A], to the harbour of [city A], then you have the issue of different berths. Cruise ships are located very close to the harbour. The harbour is inside, with the residential buildings. Container vessels are not so much situated there, thus the cruise ships are more relevant and more sensitive.”

Label:	Differences between ship operators – Fleet composition Tramp shipping has it harder to comply
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that companies operating tramp fleets will face more difficulties due to environmental legislation than companies operating liner fleets.

Examples:	<p>“The other thing of course is, if you start thinking about ships that are tramping, and they are going from one port and they do not know where they are going next and all that. It simply means that if they have to wait at an anchorage for the next cargo that cannot be, well, it can be within an ECA, but it means that you have to be burning expensive fuel whilst you wait there. Or you generate [inc.]. This is also a consequence which is just thought of now.”</p> <p>“I: <i>But if you would think about what kind of companies were most likely to do that [comply only partly] - what would characterize them?</i></p> <p>E5: Characterizing is that they are irregular visitors to the SECA. They probably... it would be tramp business, I would suspect.”</p>
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Label:	Differences between ship operators – Fleet composition Cargo shipping has it harder to comply
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that cargo shipping companies will face more difficulties due to environmental legislation than companies operating passenger fleets.
Examples:	„Now, how much of that, how this is going to affect your operational costs depends on how much of your fuel costs is operational costs. In certain, certainly in cargo ship types it is the big majority. It is, I would say, 80-85 of the operational costs of the company, because have very small overheads, they do not have the big offices, so the majority of it is fuel costs. If you take for example a cruise ship with 3,000 people on board, maybe then the fuel cost is still important, maybe 50 per cent, but you have got other costs as well. So, all in all, it could be anything from, you know, I would say, 20, 15 to 20, 25 per cent of the overall operational costs of a company, could be affected by this, by ECA.“

Label:	Differences between ship operators – Fleet composition Short sea shipping has it harder to comply
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that short sea shipping companies will face more difficulties due to environmental legislation than deep sea shipping companies. Short sea shipping in this respect is often referred to as goods transported within the same sea, e.g. Baltic Sea or goods transported on the same continent, e.g. Europe. These goods are not crossing an ocean in transport. For the purpose of this study, goods travelling within an ECA will be defined as short sea; goods leaving the ECA will no longer count as short sea.
Examples:	<p>„And again, I think we have to separate the commercial shipping, so the deep sea shipping, we have to separate that from the short sea. Because the deep sea, that is a completely different business model.”</p> <p>“I guess it depends on where it is coming from. If it is coming from outside, if it is not a regular route within that ECA, then the proportion of compliance cost increases is small. It is hard to say, it is just... My guess is that short sea,</p>

	whatever is transported by short sea, a certain proportion of this cost will be passed on the supply chain and ultimately to the consumer.”
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Label:	Differences between ship operators – Fleet composition Longer routes have it harder to comply
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that shipping companies operating longer routes will face more difficulties complying with environmental legislation than shipping companies operating shorter routes.
Examples:	„I mean when you look at it and basically you say the longer you sail today the more you have to increase your price that would kind of... the conclusion there is, if you have an option of sailing a shorter route there would optionally... that would be more attractive going forward.“

Label:	Differences between ship operators – Flag states Flags play no role
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that the flag a vessel is flying plays no role in respect to the effects of environmental legislation on the company and the level of compliance.
Examples:	„The flag, that is first and foremost an issue of costs, but concerning labour costs, as far as I understand it at least, but not necessarily linked to environmental laws. Plus, if we travel through European waters, I think, there are no big differences.“

Label:	Differences between ship operators – Flag states Flags play a role
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that the flag a vessel is flying plays a role in respect to the effects of environmental legislation on the company and the level of compliance.
Examples:	“I: <i>So if there are differences - what kind of companies are most likely to violate the rules?</i> E2: I think it is companies that you, I and no one else have ever heard about and never will. They are invisible shipping companies. They have one ship, one or two ships, which are either very old, maybe chosen willingly to operate not internationally, but maybe in a more restricted area of operation, they would probably choose a non-trustworthy or less trustworthy flag, they would probably choose a class society which is not a member of IACS [International Association of Classification Societies] and that you and I have never heard of.”

Label:	Differences between ship operators – Seat of operations Seat plays no role
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that the main seat of operations plays no role in respect to the effects of environmental legislation on the company and the level of compliance.

Examples:	
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Label:	Differences between ship operators – Seat of operations Seat plays a role
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that the main seat of operations plays a role in respect to the effects of environmental legislation on the company and the level of compliance.
Examples:	“I think if you take ship owners as a global you may have some concerns. If you take... if you have the SECA area and clearly those of us who operate in the SECA area as well - if it is the European one or the U.S. one - will be aware of all the requirements. But whether your operators that are predominantly based outside of the SECA area - they may not be fully familiar with what the requirements are inside.“

Label:	Differences between ship operators – Classification society Class society plays a role
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that the classification society with which the ship is registered plays a role in respect to the effects of environmental legislation on the company and the level of compliance.
Examples:	„I: <i>So if there are differences - what kind of companies are most likely to violate the rules?</i> E2: I think it is companies that you, I and no one else have ever heard about and never will. They are invisible shipping companies. They have one ship, one or two ships, which are either very old, maybe chosen willingly to operate not internationally, but maybe in a more restricted area of operation, they would probably choose a non-trustworthy or less trustworthy flag, they would probably choose a class society which is not a member of IACS [International Association of Classification Societies] and that you and I have never heard of.”

Label:	Viability of modal shift Modal shift possible
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that a proportion of the goods transported by sea might be moved to other modes of transport.
Examples:	„If shipping increases prices but the competing modes of transport do not, you must expect some kind of a modal shift.” „It depends on the corridor that you are moving goods in. If there is an alternative that involves either road transport or rail transport or if there is an alternative that rather than a long ocean voyage you have a longer road voyage and a shorter ocean voyage. These are kind of moves that you could see.”

Label:	Viability of modal shift – Modal shift possible
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	To road transport
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that a proportion of the goods transported by sea might be moved to road transport specifically.
Examples:	„It is a combination of time and price. Some goods could go cheaper via ocean but they are very time sensitive so they go by road all the way. That is a commodity thing.”

Label:	Viability of modal shift – Modal shift possible To rail transport
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that a proportion of the goods transported by sea might be moved to rail transport specifically.
Examples:	„Because the rail, I think, is withal most efficient here in Germany, but there, in the south of Europe, there is not an awful lot of goods transported by rail.“

Label:	Viability of modal shift – Modal shift possible To other water routes
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that a proportion of the goods transported by sea might be moved to other water routes, be they shorter, operated by other companies and/or involving ports located in another area.
Examples:	„You can go through the Kiel Kanal with small feeder vessels, which is cheaper, but naturally takes a longer time, certainly, well, as a matter of fact you certainly have different alternatives.” “On the other hand, I think, certainly with Emission Control Areas. Certain ports that are outside the emission control areas would certainly be gaining competitive advantage. If a slightly different route can mean you are out of an ECA then certain ports will certainly be happy to be in that position.” „It could be moved to competitors, you know, it could increase the utilization of other competitors within the same route. So it is a bit of a last man standing wins.”

Label:	Viability of modal shift – Modal shift possible Changes in sourcing
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that a proportion of the goods transported by sea may instead be sourced locally or from another location than before.
Examples:	„And in addition to that you will see some shift because of sourcing will completely change. So instead of buying your paper in Finland you may buy your paper in Canada.”

Label:	Viability of modal shift Modal shift not possible
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Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that modal shift may not occur, that is all or certain goods transported by sea might not be moved to all or certain other modes of transport.
Examples:	„The majority is transported by truck, as it is simply not possible with the train, due to technical reasons due to connectivity.”

Label:	Demand for capacity Will increase
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that demand for vessel capacity will increase in the following years.
Examples:	“Well, you know, what the shipping industry does depends on what happens to the world. You know, all the economies they predict a global three per cent annual growth of the global GDP. You know, that is what you have to work with.”

Label:	Demand for capacity Will decrease
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that demand for vessel capacity will decrease in the following years.
Examples:	

Label:	Supply of capacity Will increase
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that supply of vessel capacity will increase in the following years.
Examples:	“Well, we have got an overcapacity in the major fleet and that is expected to continue over the next few years and we are on that part of the cycle right now where overcapacity means effectively very tight margins for companies, if any at all.” “The trouble right now is that the fleet is increasing a bit faster than the GDP. So whether we are going to still have a prolonged overcapacity...”

Label:	Supply of capacity – Will decrease Consolidation
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that supply of vessel capacity will decrease in the following years due to consolidation.
Examples:	“Consolidation, yes. It will happen, inevitably. It is... Yes, I think it will happen. Whether you can directly pinpoint it to environmental regulation or whether you can pinpoint it to a number of factors.” “You know, certain companies will close down, it is going to be the evolutionary process and whether it was possible, you know, 10-15-20 years ago to operate a ship, which was 30 years old and you did not have to comply

	with much, because much was not there, it probably will not be possible now and that is a fact.”
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Label:	Supply of capacity – Will decrease Routes closing
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that supply of vessel capacity will decrease in the following years due to certain routes closing.
Examples:	<p>“We have publicly stated that a number of our routes could be at risk because of this. We have not named any. In spring we did close a route between [two European cities]. Again part of the reason here was the coming cost increases. And we could not see the route be sustainable going forward.”</p> <p>“You can do it and that will then mean that some companies will go bust or routes will close down and that we have already seen.”</p>

Label:	Supply of capacity – Will decrease Older vessels taken out the market
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that supply of vessel capacity will decrease in the following years due to older vessels being taken out of the market.
Examples:	“Sometimes, a certain moment of depreciation creates a shift in the industry and a shift in the stocks of many companies. If it no longer makes sense commercially to operate older vessels you [change?] your strategy altogether.”

Label:	Supply of capacity – Will decrease Vessels redeployed
Description:	This category refers to all parts of an interview where the argument is made that supply of vessel capacity in certain waters will decrease in the following years due to vessels being redeployed to avoid additional costs.
Examples:	<p>“Well, certainly in the discussion that I have been involved it is in a lot of the ship operators and owners strategies – one of the strategies to cope and to comply is to simply redeploy.”</p> <p>“And what a lot of companies do actually, they redeploy vessels as well. So, certain vessels, older vessels, would be taken out of the routes where, you know, ballast water regulations for example are in place. So it is about shuffling the costs a little bit as well.“</p>

Annex B9: Confidentiality agreement

Institute für Angewandte Wissenschaften Hamburg
Hamburg University of Applied Sciences

Confidentiality Agreement

for all data discussed among researchers in the interpretation group for qualitative research of the University of Applied Sciences Hamburg

I hereby expressly declare that I will treat as strictly confidential all material that was presented to me by other researchers in the interpretation group for qualitative research of the University of Applied Sciences Hamburg.

I will only forward, publish or make any other use of data, texts, interview abstracts, emails, contributions or protocols if I received the explicit written consent by the researcher concerned.

Name

Place, Date

Signature

Annex C1: Designing the questionnaire

Classification of costs according to Stopford, p. 221, as used in the questionnaires:

Cost category	Definition
Operating costs	Expenses involved in the day-to-day running of the ship, e.g. crew, stores, and maintenance
Periodic maintenance costs	Incurred when the ship is dry-docked for major repairs
Voyage costs	Variable costs associated with the specific voyage, e.g. fuel, port charges, and canal dues
Capital costs	Depending on financing dividends to equity or interest and capital payments on debt finance
Cargo-handling costs	Expense of loading, stowing and discharging cargo

Table 10-3: Classification of costs (Stopford, 2013, p.221), used with permission of Taylor & Francis, permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc.

**Annex C2: Maritime Environmental Legislation Survey
(English version)**

Research title: Cost effects of environmental legislation for the shipping industry

To whom it may concern:

My name is Thea Freese and I am a PhD candidate at the University of Applied Sciences Hamburg (HAW Hamburg) and the University of the West of Scotland (UWS Paisley) undertaking a 5-year research project to ascertain the effects of maritime environmental legislation on the cost and freight rate structures of the shipping industry. My research focus are regulatory impacts on different shipping trades and compliance behaviour. I am currently employed as a researcher with the University of Applied Sciences in Hamburg and am passionately interested in the economic and ecologic future of the shipping industry. My work is supervised by **Prof. John Struthers** and **Prof. Andrew Hursthouse** at the University of the West of Scotland, and **Prof. Michael Gille** at the University of Applied Sciences Hamburg. I am advised by **Capt. Muhammad Shafique** of the School of Maritime Science and Engineering at Southampton Solent University.

I intend to survey shipping companies active in the specially protected waters of the North and Baltic Sea. I am contacting you now as your company fits those sampling criteria and you were named as the responsible official regarding environmental legislation within your company. I hope that you will agree to take part in this study, which involves completing either the online-survey following this link (<http://maritimelegislation.questionpro.com>) or sending in the paper version of this questionnaire as attached to this letter and posting it in the pre-stamped envelope. The questionnaire will take around 20-30 minutes to complete. There are no foreseeable risks associated with this project.

All data submitted will be agglomerated and anonymized to ensure full confidentiality of your answers. Do not sign your name or company name on the questionnaire, to ensure confidentiality of the survey. If an answer contains information that you do not wish to disclose, please skip the respective question.

The findings of this survey will be valuable in understanding how to best draft environmental legislation to serve the needs and concerns of the shipping industry while achieving good environmental status. Your participation is voluntary, and if you have any questions about the project, please do not hesitate to contact me:

Thea Freese
PhD candidate, HAW Hamburg and UWS Paisley
B.A. Foreign Trade and International Management, LL.M. European Legal Studies

Personal details withheld.

HAW Hamburg
Berliner Tor 5
20099 Hamburg

Email
Phon
Mobi

I consent to participate in this study:

Check the box to indicate your consent.

Consent date: _____

Your contribution is valuable in achieving legislation that will protect the environment while better meeting the needs of the shipping industry.

Maritime environmental legislation survey

- CHARACTERIZATION OF THE SHIPPING COMPANY*

*Shipping company means the organizational entity for which decisions are made by a central management.

1) How many vessels does your company **own**?

- Zero 1-2 3-9 10-19 20-49 More than 50

2) How many vessels does your company **operate**?

- Zero 1-2 3-9 10-19 20-49 More than 50

3) If your company **owns more vessels** than they operate/manage, the surplus vessels are mostly:

- Operated under bareboat charter Operated on the time charter market
 Operated on the spot market Not in operation

4) If your company **operates/manages more vessels** than they own, the surplus vessels are mostly:

- Contracted under bareboat charter Contracted on the time charter market
 Contracted on the spot market

5) What is the **average age** of the vessels under your ownership/ operation?

- Less than 10 years 10-20 years More than 20 years

6) In which field is your company mostly active **in the North and Baltic Sea area**? (You may tick more than one box if several fields apply)

- Container vessels General cargo carriers Bulk carriers (Liquid/Dry)
 RoRo/ RoPax vessels Crude carriers Specialized cargo carriers

7) How may your operations mostly be characterized?
(Indicate how much time your vessels spend in liner or tramp operations.)

8) Where are you operating your vessels?
(Indicate how much time your vessels spend inside Emission Control Areas (ECAs).)

9) Which flag do most of your vessels fly?

- Panama Germany Liberia UK
 Marshall Islands Greece Other, please name: _____

10) Where is your central management located? (Name country.)

11) Are you a member of an industry organization which provides you with information on environmental legislation, like the national ship owner's organization?

- Yes No

Please provide the name/s of the respective organization/s:

- DEVELOPMENT OF COSTS

12) Choose one vessel **typical of the trade of your company** and active at least in part on the **North and/or Baltic Sea**. Answer all following questions (a-g) with this vessel in mind.

a) Provide an estimate of the current total costs for this vessel following the example.
(Distribute 100 percentage points.)

No	Cost category	Definition
5	Cargo-handling costs	Expense of loading, stowing and discharging cargo
4	Capital costs	Depending on financing, dividends to equity or interest and capital payments on debt finance
3	Voyage costs	Variable costs associated with the specific voyage, e.g. fuel, port charges, and canal dues
2	Periodic maintenance costs	Incurred when the ship is dry-docked for major repairs
1	Operating costs	Expenses involved in the day-to-day running of the ship, e.g. crew, stores, and maintenance

Vessel type chosen:

- Container vessel
- General cargo carrier
- Bulk carrier (Liquid/Dry)
- RoRo/ RoPax vessel
- Crude carrier
- Specialized cargo carrier

a) How have your **total costs** for this vessel changed since 1.1.2015?

- Increased Decreased Stayed roughly the same

b) If you said increase or decrease, how significant was the change?

- Less than 5% 5-10% 11-20% More than 20%

c) How have your **voyage costs** (e.g. fuel cost, port charges, and canal dues) for this vessel changed since 1.1.2015?

- Increased Decreased Stayed roughly the same

d) If you said increase or decrease, how significant was the change?

- Less than 5% 5-10% 11-20% More than 20%

e) How do you **expect your voyage costs** to change in the next five years (2018-2022)?

- Increase Decrease Stay roughly the same

f) If you said increase or decrease, how significant do you **expect** the change to be?

- Less than 5% 5-10% 11-20% More than 20%

- ENVIRONMENTAL COMPLIANCE COSTS

13) Rank the following endeavours to protect the environment by the total costs they produced for your company **since 01.01.2015**. (Rank from 1 to 8 with 1 being the most expensive measure and 8 being the least expensive measure.)

- Ballast water legislation
- Air pollution legislation (including NO_x and SO_x)
- Legislation on CO₂ reduction
- Sewage water legislation
- Legislation on oily water treatment
- Noise pollution legislation
- Legislation on toxic antifouling paint
- Legislation on recycling of waste

14) Rank the following endeavours to protect the environment by the total costs you expect them to produce for your company **in the next five years (2018-2022)**. (Rank from 1 to 8 with 1 being the most expensive measure and 8 being the least expensive measure.)

- Ballast water legislation
- Air pollution legislation (including NO_x and SO_x)
- Legislation on CO₂ reduction
- Sewage water legislation
- Legislation on oily water treatment
- Noise pollution legislation
- Legislation on toxic antifouling paint
- Legislation on recycling of waste

15) Which type of forthcoming legislation are you worried about the most and why?

16) Again, think of the same vessel **typical of the trade of your company** and **active at least in part on the North and/or Baltic Sea**. Estimate the **costs** of the following environmental protection aims for this vessel **in 2016**:

Environmental protection measure	Annual operational costs	Annual investment costs
Ballast water treatment		
Nitrogen oxide legislation		
Low sulphur legislation		
Carbon dioxide legislation		
Sewage water treatment		
Oily water treatment		
Non-toxic hull coatings		
Recycling of waste		

To compare the above figures, give your overall annual operational and annual investment costs:

	Annual operational costs	Annual investment costs
Vessel total in 2016		

Vessel type chosen:

- Container vessel
 General cargo carrier
 Bulk carrier (Liquid/Dry)
 RoRo/ RoPax vessel
 Crude carrier
 Specialized cargo carrier

- FREIGHT RATE DEVELOPMENT

17) Again, think of the same vessel **typical of the trade of your company** and **active at least in part on the North and/or Baltic Sea**. How have the freight rates for this vessel developed since **1.1.2015**? Draw the rough development into the graph below following the example:

Vessel type chosen:

- Container vessel General cargo carrier Bulk carrier (Liquid/Dry)
 RoRo/ RoPax vessel Crude carrier Specialized cargo carrier

18) How do you expect the freight rates for this vessel to change in the next five years (2018-2022)?

- Increase Decrease Stay roughly the same

19) If you checked increase or decrease, how significant do you **expect** the change to be?

- Less than 5% 5-10% 11-20% More than 20%

20) Rank the following factors by the influence they have had on your freight rates since 01.01.2015. (Give number between 1 and 6 with 1 having the most influence on your freight rates and 6 having the least influence on freight rates.)

- ___ Changes in demand of transport capacity
___ Changes in costs due to environmental legislation
___ Changes in labour costs
___ Changes in fuel costs (dependent on market developments)
___ Changes in cargo handling costs
___ Changes in other costs, please specify: _____

- SIGNIFICANCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL LEGISLATION

21) How important is environmental protection for decision-making within your company?

Not at all important

Very important

22) Rank these business goals by importance for your company using the numbers 1 (most important) to 4 (least important):

- ___ Run a profitable operation ___ Protect the environment
___ Bring cargo to its destination safely and efficiently ___ Increase customer satisfaction

23) Before environmental legislation comes into force, the new rules are **well known** to the shipping industry:

24) Before environmental legislation comes into force, the needed changes in operations are **well understood** by the shipping industry:

- COMPLIANCE WITH ENVIRONMENTAL LEGISLATION

25) Which compliance method do you currently use to comply with sulphur legislation in the North and Baltic Sea area? (Tick several boxes if applicable.)

- Use of low sulphur fuel
- Installation of scrubbing technology
- Use of LNG
- Other, please specify: _____

26) How high would you estimate the rate of shipping companies employing the following behaviours **in Baltic and North Sea areas** in 2017? (Tick the respective box in each row.)

	Less than 70%	70-80%	81-90%	91-95%	More than 95%
Treating their ballast water					
Filtering their NOx emissions					

	Less than 70%	70-80%	81-90%	91-95%	More than 95%
Operating on low sulphur fuel, LNG or operating a scrubber					
Releasing their oily water to port reception facilities or using an oil separator					
Discharging their sewage water to port reception facilities					
Discharging their garbage to port reception facilities					
Using non-TBT hull coatings					

27) How would you rate the following statements?

	Not true at all	Somewhat untrue	Somewhat true	Absolutely true
Shipping companies need to contribute to a cleaner environment				
My company would not do anything that is against the law				
Being environmentally friendly will increase our reputation				
Our customers are more likely to buy from us if we make a special effort to protect the environment				
Our customers will pay higher freight rates if we make a special effort to protect the environment				

	Not true at all	Somewhat untrue	Somewhat true	Absolutely true
Port state controls are very effective				
Controls are so tight that it is impossible to circumvent environmental legislation				
Shipping companies are uncertain about what is expected of them				
It is technically possible to circumvent environmental rules				
Technical solutions to comply with environmental legislation are easily available				
People make mistakes - Noncompliance may happen due to human error				
Noncompliance may happen due to higher forces, like the weather				
Noncompliance may happen when financial resources are tight				
Membership in an industry organization is crucial to be well informed about legislation				
Shipping companies need specialized legal personnel to understand environmental legislation				
It takes a lot of time to be well informed about environmental legislation				
A strong network with other companies is needed to be well informed about environmental legislation				

Thank you for your valuable contribution!

Annex C3: Survey variables

Variable name	Variable description	Variable source	Variable type	Level of measure
CompletionTime	Time taken to complete survey	QuestionPro	Continuous	Ratio
CountryCode	Country where survey was taken	QuestionPro	Categorical	Nominal
Consent	Consent given	Questionnaire title page	Categorical	Nominal
ConsentDate	Consent date	Questionnaire title page	Categorical	Nominal
VesselsOwned	Number of vessels owned	Questionnaire Q1	Categorical	Ordinal
VesselsOperated	Number of vessels operated	Questionnaire Q2	Categorical	Ordinal
CharterTypeVesselsOwned	Charter type vessels owned	Questionnaire Q3	Categorical	Nominal
CharterTypeVesselsOperated	Charter type vessels operated	Questionnaire Q4	Categorical	Nominal
AverageAge	Average vessel age of fleet	Questionnaire Q5	Categorical	Ordinal
ContainerVessels	Operation of container vessels	Questionnaire Q6	Categorical	Nominal
GeneralCargoCarriers	Operation of general cargo carriers	Questionnaire Q6	Categorical	Nominal
BulkCarriers	Operation of bulk carriers (liquid/dry)	Questionnaire Q6	Categorical	Nominal
RoRoRoPaxVessels	Operation of RoRo/RoPax vessels	Questionnaire Q6	Categorical	Nominal
CrudeCarriers	Operation of crude carriers (liquid/dry)	Questionnaire Q6	Categorical	Nominal
SpecializedCargoCarriers	Operation of specialized cargo carriers	Questionnaire Q6	Categorical	Nominal
TrampOperations	Share of tramp operations (vs. Liner)	Questionnaire Q7	Continuous	Ratio
ECAOperations	Share of ECA operations (vs. Non-ECA)	Questionnaire Q8	Continuous	Ratio
Flag	Flag state	Questionnaire Q9	Categorical	Nominal
CentralManagement	Central management location	Questionnaire Q10	Categorical	Nominal
IndustryAssociationMembership	Industry association membership	Questionnaire Q11	Categorical	Nominal
IndustryAssociationName	Industry association names	Questionnaire Q11	Categorical	Nominal
CargohandlingCosts	Cargo-handling costs	Questionnaire Q12 a	Continuous	Ratio
CapitalCosts	Capital costs	Questionnaire Q12 a	Continuous	Ratio

VoyageCosts	Voyage costs	Questionnaire Q12 a	Continuous	Ratio
PeriodicMaintenanceCosts	Periodic maintenance costs	Questionnaire Q12 a	Continuous	Ratio
OperatingCosts	Operating costs	Questionnaire Q12 a	Continuous	Ratio
TotalCosts	Total costs (should be 100 percent)	Questionnaire Q12 a	Continuous	Ratio
VesseltypeQ12	Vessel type chosen (Q12)	Questionnaire Q12 a	Categorical	Nominal
TotalCostDevelopment	Development of total costs	Questionnaire Q12 b and c	Categorical	Ordinal
VoyageCostDevelopment	Development of voyage costs	Questionnaire Q12 d and e	Categorical	Ordinal
ExpectedVoyageCostDevelopment	Expected development of voyage costs	Questionnaire Q12 f and g	Categorical	Ordinal
BallastwaterRank	Ballast water (2015-2017)	Questionnaire Q13	Categorical	Ordinal
AirpollutionRank	Air pollution (2015-2017)	Questionnaire Q13	Categorical	Ordinal
CO2Rank	CO2 (2015-2017)	Questionnaire Q13	Categorical	Ordinal
Sewage waterRank	Sewage water (2015-2017)	Questionnaire Q13	Categorical	Ordinal
Oily waterRank	Oily water (2015-2017)	Questionnaire Q13	Categorical	Ordinal
NoisepollutionRank	Noise pollution (2015-2017)	Questionnaire Q13	Categorical	Ordinal
AntifoulingRank	Antifouling (2015-2017)	Questionnaire Q13	Categorical	Ordinal
WasteRank	Waste (2015-2017)	Questionnaire Q13	Categorical	Ordinal
ExpectedBallastwaterRank	Ballast water (2018-2022)	Questionnaire Q14	Categorical	Ordinal
ExpectedAirpollutionRank	Air pollution (2018-2022)	Questionnaire Q14	Categorical	Ordinal
ExpectedCO2Rank	CO2 (2018-2022)	Questionnaire Q14	Categorical	Ordinal
ExpectedSewage waterRank	Sewage water (2018-2022)	Questionnaire Q14	Categorical	Ordinal
ExpectedOily waterRank	Oily water (2018-2022)	Questionnaire Q14	Categorical	Ordinal
ExpectedNoisepollutionRank	Noise pollution (2018-2022)	Questionnaire Q14	Categorical	Ordinal
ExpectedAntifoulingRank	Antifouling (2018-2022)	Questionnaire Q14	Categorical	Ordinal
ExpectedWasteRank	Water (2018-2022)	Questionnaire Q14	Categorical	Ordinal
ForthcomingLegislation	Forthcoming Legislation	Questionnaire Q15	Categorical	Nominal
BallastwaterOp	Ballast water operational costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
BallastwaterInvest	Ballast water investment costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
NitrogenoxideOp	Nitrogen oxide operational costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio

NitrogenoxideInvest	Nitrogen oxide investment costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
LowsulphurOp	Low sulphur operational costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
LowsulphurInvest	Low sulphur investment costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
CarbondioxideOp	Carbon dioxide operational costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
CarbondioxideInvest	Carbon dioxide investment costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
SewagewaterOp	Sewage water operational costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
SewagewaterInvest	Sewage water investment costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
OilywaterOp	Oily water operational costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
OilywaterInvest	Oily water investment costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
AntifoulingOp	Antifouling operational costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
AntifoulingInvest	Antifouling investment costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
WasteOp	Waste operational costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
WasteInvest	Waste investment costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
CompliancecostsOp	Total compliance operational costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
CompliancecostsInvest	Total compliance investment costs	Questionnaire Q16	Continuous	Ratio
VesseltypeQ16	Vessel type chosen (Q16)	Questionnaire Q16	Categorical	Nominal
FreightrateApr15	Freight rate index April 15	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateJul15	Freight rate index July 15	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateOct15	Freight rate index October 15	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateJan16	Freight rate index January 16	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateApr16	Freight rate index April 16	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateJul16	Freight rate index July 16	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateOct16	Freight rate index October 16	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateJan17	Freight rate index January 17	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateApr17	Freight rate index April 17	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateJul17	Freight rate index July 17	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
FreightrateOct17	Freight rate index October 17	Questionnaire Q17	Continuous	Ratio
VesseltypeQ17	Vessel type chosen (Q17)	Questionnaire Q17	Categorical	Nominal

FreightrateDevelopment	Freight rate development	Questionnaire Q18 and Q19	Categorical	Ordinal
TransportcapacityRank	Transport capacity rank	Questionnaire Q20	Categorical	Ordinal
EnvironmentallegislationRank	Environmental legislation rank	Questionnaire Q20	Categorical	Ordinal
LabourcostsRank	Labour costs rank	Questionnaire Q20	Categorical	Ordinal
FuelcostsRank	Fuel costs rank	Questionnaire Q20	Categorical	Ordinal
CargohandlingcostsRank	Cargo-handling costs rank	Questionnaire Q20	Categorical	Ordinal
OthercostsRank	Other costs rank	Questionnaire Q20	Categorical	Ordinal
Specifyothercosts	Other costs specified	Questionnaire Q20	Categorical	Nominal
SignificanceLegislation	Significance of environmental legislation	Questionnaire Q21	Categorical	Ordinal
ProfitableoperationRank	Run profitable operation rank	Questionnaire Q22	Categorical	Ordinal
ProtectenvironmentRank	Protect the environment rank	Questionnaire Q22	Categorical	Ordinal
CargotodestinationRank	Cargo to destination rank	Questionnaire Q22	Categorical	Ordinal
CustomerSatisfactionRank	Customer satisfaction rank	Questionnaire Q22	Categorical	Ordinal
KnowledgeLegislation	Knowledge about environmental legislation	Questionnaire Q23	Categorical	Ordinal
ApprehensionLegislation	Apprehension of environmental legislation	Questionnaire Q24	Categorical	Ordinal
ComplianceFuel	Compliance by low sulphur fuel	Questionnaire Q25	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceScrubber	Compliance by scrubbing technology	Questionnaire Q25	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceLNG	Compliance by use of LNG	Questionnaire Q25	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceOther	Compliance by other method	Questionnaire Q25	Categorical	Nominal
SpecifyotherCompliancemethod	Specify other method (Q25)	Questionnaire Q25	Categorical	Nominal
BehaviourBallastwater	Treating ballast water	Questionnaire Q26	Categorical	Ordinal
BehaviourNOxemission	Filtering NOx emissions	Questionnaire Q26	Categorical	Ordinal
BehaviourSulphur	Emitting low sulphur emissions	Questionnaire Q26	Categorical	Ordinal
BehaviourOilywater	Treating oily water	Questionnaire Q26	Categorical	Ordinal
BehaviourSewagewater	Treating sewage water	Questionnaire Q26	Categorical	Ordinal
BehaviourWaste	Treating waste	Questionnaire Q26	Categorical	Ordinal
BehaviourAntifouling	Using non-TBT hull coatings	Questionnaire Q26	Categorical	Ordinal
ComplianceNeedtocontribute	Companies need to contribute	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal

ComplianceAgainstthelaw	Would not do anything against the law	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceIncreasesreputation	Increase our reputation	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceHighersales	Increase our sales	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceHigherfreightrates	Increase our freight rates	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceEffectivecontrols	Harbour state controls are very effective	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceTightcontrols	Controls make noncompliance impossible	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceUncertainaboutexpectations	Uncertainty about legislation	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceCircumventiontechnicallypossible	Technically possible to circumvent	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceTechnicalsolutionsavailable	Technical solutions available	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceHumanerror	Human error	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceHigherforces	Higher forces	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceFinancialresources	Tight financial resources	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceIndustryassociation	Industry association membership	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceLegalpersonnel	Specialized legal personnel	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceTime	Time constraints	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal
ComplianceNetwork	Network	Questionnaire Q27	Categorical	Nominal

Table 10-4: Survey variables with description, source, type and level of measure

Annex C4: Contact details of shipping companies

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
1	"K" Line (Deutschland) GmbH	DE					
2	A2SEA A/S	DK					
3	Aasen Shipping AS	NO					
4	ACL Sweden AB	SE					
5	Ærøfærgerne A/S	DK					
6	Africa Express Line	UK					
7	Agder Ocean Shipping AS	NO					
8	Ahlers Belgium N.V.	BE					
9	Ahlmark Lines AB	SE					
10	Ahrenkiel Steamship GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
11	Aker Floating Production ASA	NO					
12	AKOFS Offshore	NO					
13	Ålandstrafiken	FI					
14	Alba	DK					
15	All Overseas, UAB, Klaipeda	LT					
16	All-Transport AS	NO					
17	Alpha Shipping Company	LV					
18	Alpina Shipping Agencies ApS	DK					
19	Ålvtank, Rederi AB	SE					
20	Amasus Chartering BV	NL					
20	Amasus Chartering BV	NL					
21	AMELAND SHIPPING B.V. Harlingen	NL					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
22	AMISCO AS	EE					
23	Anglo-Eastern (Germany) GmbH Ship Management	DE					
24	ANL Germany Hamburg	DE					
25	Anthony Veder Rederijzaken B.V.	NL					
26	APL Agencies, UAB, Klaipeda	LT					
27	Apollo Shipping GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
28	Aquarius Shipping Hamburg GmbH	DE					
29	AQUILA MARITIME MANAGEMENT GMBH & CO. KG	DE					
30	Ara Bulk BV	NL					
31	Aramis Shipping Agency Ltd	PL					
32	Archipelago Lines Oy	FI					
33	Arctia Shipping Oy	FI					
34	Arctic Umiaq Line A/S	DK					
35	ARDMORE SHIPPING LIMITED	IE					
36	Arklow Shipping Nederland B.V.	NL					
36	Arklow Shipping Nederland B.V.	NL					
37	Arklow Shipping IE	IE					
38	Arkon Shipping GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
39	Arriva Shipping AS	NO					
40	Artic Shipping AS	NO					
41	Asia Express Line GmbH	DE					
42	ASP Seascot Ship Mngt Ltd	UK					
43	Asper Norway AS	NO					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
44	Asterion Tanker Navigation GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
45	ASTRAMAR	LV					
46	Atlantic Container Line Denmark	DK					
46	Atlantic Container Line Deutschland GmbH	DE					
46	Atlantic Container Line FI	FI					
47	Atlantic Lloyd GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
48	Atlantic Marine UK	UK					
49	Atlantic Offshore AS	NO					
50	Atlantic Offshore Rescue Ltd	UK					
51	Atlantica Shipping AS	NO					
52	Atlas Shipping Group	NO					
53	ATR - Landhandel GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
54	Auerbach Schifffahrts GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
55	Autonomas	LT					
56	Ave Line, Riga-Ferry	LV					
57	AW Ship Management Ltd	UK					
58	Awilco AS	NO					
59	Awilco LNG ASA	NO					
60	Awilco Technical Services AS	NO					
61	Baltic Bright, PR f	SE					
62	Baltic Offshore Kalmar AB	SE					
63	Baltic Shipping Agency Ltd Sp.	PL					
64	Baltic Shipping Company	DK					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
65	Baltimar A/S Ltd.	DK					
66	Baltimore Shipping + Trading GmbH	DE					
67	Baltnautic Shipping Ltd.	LT					
68	Bastø Fosen AS	NO					
69	BB Sverige AB	SE					
70	BBC Burger Bereederungs Contor GmbH & Co. KG, Burg/Dithm.	DE					
71	BBI Break-Bulk-International Schiffahrtsgesells. mbH	DE					
72	BD-Shipsnavo GmbH & Co. Reederei KG	DE					
73	BEL Schiffahrts- und Speditionsgesellschaft mbH	DE					
74	Belships ASA	NO					
75	Bereederungsgesellschaft Alstership mbH & Co KG	DE					
76	Berge Bulk	DK					
77	Berge Rederi AS	NO					
78	Bergen Tankers AS	NO					
79	Bergshav Management AS	NO					
80	Bernd Becker Shipmanagement GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
81	Berndtssons Rederi AB	SE					
82	Bernhard Schulte GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
83	BG Freight Line B.V.	NL					
84	B-Gas A/S	DK					
85	Bibby Line Ltd - Liverpool	UK					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
86	Bidsted & Co A/S	DK					
87	BigLift Shipping BV	NL					
87	BigLift Shipping BV	NL					
88	Birkeland Fiskebåtrederi AS, Br.	NO					
89	Bitter, Helmut, Schiffahrtskontor GmbH	DE					
90	Bjørklids Ferjerederi AS	NO					
91	Blue Star Line AS	DK					
92	Blumenthal, Johann M.K., GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
93	Blystad AS, Arne	NO					
94	Boa Offshore AS	NO					
95	Bockstiegel, W., Reederei GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
96	BOCS Bremen Overseas Chartering and Shipping GmbH	DE					
97	Boeckmans	NL					
97	Boeckmans Nederland B.V.	NL					
98	Boele Dredging Contractors BV	NL					
99	Bolten, Aug., Wm. Miller's Nachfolger (GmbH & Co.) KG	DE					
100	Bømlo Brønnbåtservice AS	NO					
101	Bonheur ASA	NO					
102	Boomsma Shipping	NL					
103	Bore Ltd.	FI					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
104	Boreal Transport Norge AS	NO					
105	Borr Drilling Management AS	NO					
106	Boskalis Sweden AB	SE					
107	Boskalis Terramare	FI					
108	Bourbon Offshore Norway AS	NO					
109	Braren, Rörd, Bereederungs-GmbH & Co. KG, Kollmar	DE					
110	Brax Shipholding Rederi AB	SE					
111	Breadbox Shipping Lines BV	NL					
112	BREB GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
113	Bremer Bereederungs GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
114	Bremer Lloyd	DE					
115	Briese Shipping BV	NL					
116	Briggs Marine Contractors	UK					
117	Brouwer Shipping & Chartering GmbH	DE					
118	BRP Rederi AB	SE					
119	Bryggen Shipping International	NO					
120	Buck Shipping GmbH	DE					
121	Bugge Shipping BVBA	BE					
122	Buksér og Berging AS	NO					
123	Bulkship Management	NO					
124	Büttner, Carl, GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
125	BV Kustvaartbedrijf Moerman	NL					
126	BW Fleet Managment AS	NO					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
127	BW LPG	NO					
128	BW Maritime ApS	DK					
128	BW Maritime ApS	DK					
129	BW Offshore Norway AS	NO					
130	Caiano Shipping AS	NO					
131	Caledonian Maritime Assets Ltd	UK					
132	Candler Schifffahrt GmbH	DE					
133	Cargo-Levant Linienagenturen GmbH	DE					
134	Cargow, Rotterdam	NL					
135	Carisbrooke Shipping Holland B.V.	NL					
135	Carisbrooke Shipping Holland B.V.	NL					
136	Carsten Rehder, Schiffsmakler und Reederei GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
137	Cecon Contracting ASA	NO					
138	Champion Tankers AS	NO					
139	Charterfrakt Baltic Carrier AB	SE					
140	Chemikalien Seetransport GmbH	DE					
141	China Shipping Agency (Belgium) BVBA , Antwerpen	BE					
142	CHINESE-POLISH JOINT STOCK SHIPPING COMPANY	PL					
143	CHIPOLBROK - Gdynia	PL					
144	Chrishop A/S	NO					
145	Citadel Shipping AB	SE					
146	CLdN ro-ro SA	NL					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
146	CLdN ro-ro SA, Rotterdam	NL					
147	Clipper Group A/S	DK					
147	Clipper Group A/S	DK					
148	CMA CGM (Deutschland) GmbH	DE					
149	CMB (Bocimar) NV	BE					
150	Cobelfret Ferries NV	BE					
151	COG Offshore AS	NO					
152	Coli-Shipping	DE					
153	Color Line Marine AS	NO					
154	Columbia Shipmanagement (Netherlands) b.v.	NL					
155	Combi Lift GmbH	DE					
156	Concordia Maritime AB	SE					
157	Container Management and Shipping A/S	DK					
158	Containerships Belgium NV , Antwerpen	BE					
159	Containerships Ltd. Oy	FI					
159	Containerships Rotterdam BV	NL					
160	Conti-Lines, Belgium	BE					
161	Cool Carriers AB	SE					
162	Cooperatie Kamar Bulk-Transpor	NL					
163	Corleis, Heinz, Reederei	DE					
164	Corral Line ApS	DK					
165	Cosco Container Lines (Netherlands) B.V.	NL					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
166	COSCO Shipping Lines (Germany) GmbH	DE					
167	COSL Drilling Europe AS	NO					
168	Crownbreeze Shipping BV	NL					
169	Crystal Nordic	DK					
170	Crystal Pool Ltd.	FI					
171	CSK Cuxhavener Schiffahrtskontor GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
172	CSL Europe Ltd	UK					
173	CT Offshore	DK					
174	Dahl Management AS, Thor	NO					
175	Danielsen, Rederiet Otto	DK					
176	Danser Container Line BV	NL					
176	Danser Container Line BV	NL					
177	Danship AS, H.H.	DK					
178	Dansk Rederi A/S	DK					
179	DAO Shipping	UK					
180	Dauelsberg, Herm., GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
181	DeepOcean AS	NO					
181	DeepOcean2 UK Ltd	UK					
182	Delphis NV	BE					
183	Deme NV	BE					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
184	Denholm Coates	UK					
184	Denholm Shipping Co Ltd	UK					
185	Dennis Maritime Oy Ltd.	FI					
186	Destination Gotland AB	SE					
187	Deutsche Afrika-Linien/John T. Essberger Group of Companies	DE					
188	DFDS ApS & Co. KG	DK					
189	DHT Holdings, Inc.	NO					
190	Dick van der Kamp Shipsales B.V.	NL					
191	DMA-Trans B.V, Rhoon	NL					
191	DMA-Trans B.V, Rhoon	NL					
192	Dockwise Shipping BV	NL					
193	DOF (UK)	UK					
193	DOF ASA	NO					
194	Döhle, Peter, Schiffahrts-KG	DE					
195	Dolphin Drilling AS	NO					
196	Donsötank, Rederi AB	SE					
197	Drevin Bereederungs GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
198	DS Schifffahrt GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
199	DS Tankers	DE					
200	DSD Shipping AS	NO					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
201	Dumar Chartering B.V., Bergschenhoek	NL					
202	Dutch Marine BV, Hulst	NL					
203	Dutch Maritime Transport B.V.	NL					
204	E.R. Schifffahrt GmbH & Cie. KG	DE					
205	Eastern Bulk Carriers	NO					
206	EBE NV	BE					
207	Echoship ApS	DK					
208	Eckerö Shipping	FI					
209	Eckerö Sverige AB, Rederi	SE					
209	Eckerö, Rederiaktiebolaget	FI					
210	ECU WORLDWIDE (Germany) GmbH	DE					
211	Eides Rederi AS	NO					
212	Eidesvik Offshore ASA	NO					
213	Eidshaug Rederi AS	NO					
214	Eidsvaag AS	NO					
215	Eimskip Deutschland	DE					
215	Eimskip Norway AS	NO					
216	EKSMARIS Shipping	LT					
217	Ektank AB	SE					
218	Elbdeich Reederei	DE					
219	Eletson Maritime Ltd	UK					
220	E-Liini AS (Estline)	EE					
221	EMS Maritime Offshore GmbH	DE					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
222	Ems-Leda Shipping GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
223	Engström Shipping AB	SE					
224	Erikson, Rederiaktiebolaget Gustaf	FI					
225	Ernst Russ AG	DE					
226	Erria A/S	DK					
227	Ervik & Sævik AS	NO					
228	ESL Shipping Ltd.	FI					
229	Essberger, John T., GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
230	Estero Shipping & Trading Rotterdam B.V.	NL					
231	Estonian shipping company	EE					
232	Esvagt A/S	DK					
232	Esvagt A/S	DK					
233	Eucon Shipping and Transport Ltd	NL					
233	Eucon Shipping and Transport Ltd	NL					
234	Eurabia-Schiffahrt-Agentur GmbH	DE					
235	Euro Nordic Logistics B.V., Ridderkerk	NL					
236	Euroafrica Linie Żeglugowe	PL					
237	Euronav	UK					
238	Euronav Ship Management SAS	BE					
239	Euroship Management GmbH	DE					
240	Evergas	DK					
240	Evergas	DK					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
240	Evergas	DK					
241	Evergreen Shipping Agency (Europe) GmbH	DE					
241	Evergreen Shipping Agency (Netherlands) b.v.	NL					
242	Exmar NV	BE					
243	Fairway Shipping Agencies GmbH + Co. KG	DE					
243	Fairway Shipping Agencies, Rhoon, NL	NL					
244	FALCON maritime	DK					
245	Falkeid Shipping AS	NO					
246	Far East Marine Co	RU					
247	Faroe Ship	FO					
248	Faroe Ship Ltd	FO					
249	Fast Lines NV	BE					
250	Fastnet Chartering	DE					
251	Fednav (Belgium) n.v.	BE					
251	Fednav (Belgium) n.v.	BE					
252	Feederlines B.V.	NL					
253	Fehn Ship Management GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
254	FESCO Russia	RU					
255	Fiducia Rederi AB	SE					
256	Finnlines Plc	FI					
256	Finnlines Ship Management AB	SE					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
257	Fisher & Sons Plc, Fred Olsen	UK					
258	Fiskerikompetanse AS	NO					
259	Fjord Line AS	NO					
260	Fjord Shipping AS	NO					
261	Fjord1 Fylkesbaatane AS	NO					
262	Fjordcharter Norway	NO					
263	fjordline.dk	DK					
264	Floatel International AB	SE					
265	Fluvia Tankrode GmbH	DE					
266	Fluvia Vegoil BV	NL					
267	Folmer & Co, H.	DK					
268	Fonnes Shipping AS	NO					
269	Foresight Shipping Ltd	UK					
270	Forland Shipping AS	NO					
271	Forsa Shipping Agency Ltd	LT					
272	Fortuna Seaside Bulk Carriers A/S	DK					
273	FosenNamsos Sjø AS	NO					
274	Frederiet AB	SE					
275	Freese Shipping GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
276	Frontline Management AS	NO					
277	FSV Group	NO					
278	Furetank Rederi AB	SE					
279	GANS CARGO, Ghent	BE					
280	Gard Shipping AS	NO					
281	GasChem Services GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
282	GasLog	UK					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
283	GBS-Shipmanagement GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
284	GCS German Cargo Services GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
285	Gearbulk Norway AS	NO					
286	Gerdes Bereederungs GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
287	German Tanker Shipping GmbH & Co	DE					
288	Geuther, Karl, GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
289	Gillie & Blair Ltd	UK					
290	GLA German Liner Agencies GmbH	DE					
291	GLE Maritime BV	NL					
292	Global Marine Systems Ltd	UK					
293	Globe Agency Ltd.	DE					
294	Godby Shipping Ab	FI					
295	Golar Management Oslo	NO					
296	Golden Energy Offshore	NO					
297	Golden Ocean Management AS	NO					
298	Golfinas JSC	LT					
299	Gothia Tankers Alliance	SE					
300	Gotland Tankers AB	SE					
301	Gotland, Rederi AB	SE					
302	Graig Shipping Plc	UK					
303	Gram & Co AS, P.D.	NO					
304	Gram Car Carriers AS	NO					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
305	Grieg Star AS	NO					
306	Grieg Star Shipping AS	NO					
307	Grona Shipping GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
308	GRS Rohden Shipping GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
309	GulfMark AS	NO					
309	GulfMark UK Ltd	UK					
310	Hafnia Management A/S	DK					
311	Hafnia Tankers	DK					
312	Hagland Shipping AS	NO					
313	Håkans Oy Ab, Alfons	FI					
314	Halten AS	NO					
315	Hamburg Süd Norden AB	SE					
315	Hamburg Südamerikanische Dampfschiffahrts-Gesellschaft KG	DE					
316	Hammonia Reederei GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
317	Hanjin Shipping Europe GmbH & Co. KG	NL					
318	Hannestad AS, M.	NO					
319	HANSA LEVANT LINE GmbH	DE					
320	Hansa Mare Reederei GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
321	Hansa Tankers AS	NO					
322	Hanse-Schiffahrt e.K.	DE					
323	Hapag-Lloyd AG, Area Germany	DE					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
324	Harpain Shipping GmbH	DE					
325	Harren & Partner Group	DE					
326	Hartel Shipping & Chartering BV	NL					
327	Hartman Seatrade	NL					
328	Hartmann Offshore GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
329	Hartmann Shipping Services Germany GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
330	Haugaland Shipping AS	NO					
331	Hauschild, Albert, GmbH & Co. KG, Ellerbek	DE					
332	Hav Ship Management Norrus AS	NO					
333	Havfisk ASA	NO					
334	Havila Shipping ASA	NO					
335	HBC, Hamburg Bulk Carriers GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
336	Heerema Marine Contractors	NL					
337	Helix Well Ops	UK					
338	Hellespont Ship Management GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
339	Herbosch-Kiere NV	BE					
340	Hermann Lohmann Bereederungen GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
341	herning shipping a.s.	DK					
342	Hess	DK					
343	Høegh LNG	NO					
344	Holwerda Shipmanagement BV	NL					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
345	Holy House Shipping AB	SE					
346	HÖOEGH AUTOLINERS GMBH	DE					
347	Høygruppen AS	NO					
348	Hoyland Offshore AS	NO					
349	HS Schifffahrts GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
350	Hudig & Veder/ Amstelland Shipping BV	NL					
351	Hugo Stinnes Schifffahrt GmbH	DE					
352	Hugo Trumpy B.V.	NL					
353	Humber Work Boats	UK					
354	Hurtigruten ASA	NO					
355	Husmann, Heinz, Schifffahrts GmbH, Haren/Ems	DE					
356	Hyundai Merchant Marine (Netherlands) BV	NL					
357	ICL Europe NV, Antwerpen	BE					
358	ID Management ApS	DK					
359	Ilmaris UAB	LT					
360	Imperial Shipping Rotterdam B.V.	NL					
360	IMPERIAL Shipping Services GmbH	DE					
361	Incotrans GmbH Linienagentur	DE					
362	Ineos DeNoS	DK					
363	INOK N.V.	BE					
363	INOK TM Ltd.	RU					
364	Inter Marine Sp. z o.o.	PL					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
365	Intercoast Zinke GmbH	DE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
366	Interglobal Shipping GmbH	DE					
367	Interorient Marine Services (Germany) GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
368	Interscan Schiffahrtsgesellschaft m.b.H.	DE					
369	Intrada Ships Management Ltd/ Scotline	UK					
370	isa - independant shipping agencies Bremen GmbH, Stuhr	DE					
371	Island Offshore Group	NO					
372	J*S Maritime Partners	DE					
373	J. Bekkers Co. B.V.	NL					
374	J. Lauritzen	DK					
375	J. Lauritzen	DK					
376	J.A. Rederiet	DK					
377	Jacob, Ernst, (GmbH & Co KG)	DE					
378	James Fisher & Sons Plc	UK					
379	James Fisher Tankships Ltd	UK					
380	Jan De Nul NV	BE					
381	Jasmund Shipping	DE					
382	JD-Contractor AS	DK					
383	Jebsen Management AS	NO					
384	Jebsen Skipsrederi AS, Kristian Gerhard	NO					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
385	JMB ApS	DK					
386	John H Whitaker (Tankers) Ltd	UK					
387	John Swire & Sons Ltd	UK					
388	Jönsson Nova Logistics	SE					
389	JR Ship Management BV	NL					
390	JSC Sovfracht	RU					
391	Jumbo Shipping	NL					
392	Jüngerhans Heavy-Lift-Fleet Services GmbH & Co. KG & Jüngerhans Maritime Services GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
393	Jürgen Saathoff	DE					
394	K Line Offshore AS	NO					
395	K&K Schifffahrts-GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
396	Karl Meyer Reederei GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
397	Karmøy Skipsconsult Management AS	NO					
398	Kem-Offshore ApS	DK					
399	KGJ Cement AS	NO					
400	Kiltank Rederi AB	SE					
401	Klaveness, Rederiaksjeselskapet Torvald	NO					
401	Klaveness, Rederiaksjeselskapet Torvald	NO					
402	Kleimar NV	BE					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
403	Klip Marine Shipmanagement LTD.	EE					
404	Klippans Båtmansstation, AB	SE					
405	Klovnings Shipping A.S, Brødrene	NO					
406	Knutsen NYK Offshore Tankers (KNOT)	NO					
407	Knutsen OAS Shipping AS (KOAS)	NO					
408	Komrowski Befrachtungskontor KG (GmbH & Co.)	DE					
409	Kontor 17 Shipmanagement GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
410	Koole Tanktransport BV	NL					
411	Kopervik Ship Management AS	NO					
412	KOTUG International BV	NL					
413	Krey Schifffahrts GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
414	Læsø K/S, Færgeselskabet	DK					
415	Lalemant NV	BE					
416	Lampke, Peter W., GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
417	Langh Ship Ab, Oy	FI					
418	Larvik Shipping	NO					
419	Latsco (London) Ltd	UK					
420	Latvian American Shipping Line	LV					
421	Latvian Shipping Company (LSC)	LV					
422	Laurin Maritime AB	SE					
423	Lauritzen Kosan A/S	DK					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
424	Leonhardt & Blumberg Reederei GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
425	Liberty One Shipmanagement GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
426	Lighthouse Ship Management AS	NO					
427	Lillgaard, Rederi AB	FI					
428	Limarko Shipping Company AB	LT					
429	Lomar Deutschland GmbH	DE					
429	Lomar Shipping	UK					
430	London Ship Managers Ltd	UK					
431	Lorentzens Skibs AS	NO					
432	Lothar Brand Überseeschiffahrtsagentur GmbH	DE					
433	LSC - Lischke Shipping & Chartering GmbH	DE					
434	Lubeca Marine (Germany) GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
435	Lüddecke ReedereiAgentur GmbH	DE					
436	Lundqvist Rederierna	FI					
437	Lysander Shipping	UK					
438	M + S Mehrstens + Schwickerath GmbH	DE					
439	MacAndrews Holland B.V.	NL					
440	MACS Benelux B.V.	NL					
440	Macs Cross Trading GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
441	Madsen Rederi A/S, Peter	DK					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
442	Maersk	DK					
442	Maersk Line	SE					
442	Maersk Line	DK					
443	Maersk Tankers	DK					
444	Malin Group	UK					
445	Manfred Schröder Schiffsmakler GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
446	MANN LINES GmbH Germany	DE					
447	Mannlines bv	NL					
448	MAN-TESS Ltd.	LV					
449	MarConsult Schiffahrt (GmbH & Co.) KG	DE					
450	Marine Supply AS	NO					
451	Marinvest AB	SE					
452	Maritime Management AS	NO					
453	Marship Management GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
454	Master Marine AS	NO					
455	Mega freight A.S.S.K. GmbH	DE					
456	Meling Tankers KS, O.H.	NO					
457	Menzell & Co Schiffsmakler (GmbH & Co) KG	DE					
458	Menzell & Döhle GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
459	MERCMARINE	DE					
460	Mercurius Scheepvaart BV	NL					
461	Meriaura Ltd.	FI					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
462	Merktrans AS, Riga & Liepaja	LV					
463	MF Shipping Group, Farmsum	NL					
464	Misje Rederi AS	NO					
465	MLO & PWL Baltic Logistics GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
466	MMT – Marin Mätteknik AB	SE					
467	Møkster Shipping AS, Simon	NO					
468	MOL (Europe) BV	DE					
469	Monjasa A/S	DK					
470	Mowinckels Rederi AS, J. Ludwig	NO					
471	MSC International Marine Services BV	NL					
472	MST Mineralien Schiffahrt Spedition und Transport GmbH	DE					
473	Mundial RoRo Shipping Service Hamburg GmbH	DE					
474	Myklebusthaug Management AS	NO					
475	Naess Shipping (Holland) B.V.	NL					
476	Napier AS	NO					
477	Navidom Oy	FI					
478	Navig8	NO					
479	NavigareCapital	DK					
479	NavigareCapital	DK					
480	Navision Shipping Company A/S	DK					
481	Nawigator Shipping	PL					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
482	NEPTUMAR Schiffahrtsagentur GmbH	DE					
483	Neptune Offshore AS	NO					
484	Nesskip HF	IS					
485	Netfreight Schiffahrts- & Speditions-GmbH	DE					
486	Nielsen og Bresling A/S, Rederiet	DK					
487	Nile Dutch Africa Line BV	NL					
488	Nile Dutch Africa Line BV	NL					
489	Nirint Shipping B.V.	NL					
490	NMT GROUP OF COMPANIES, Antwerp	BE					
491	Nomadic Shipping AS	NO					
492	Nor Lines	PL					
493	Nor Lines AS	NO					
494	Norbroker Shipping & Trading AS	NO					
495	Norbulk Shipping (UK) Ltd	UK					
496	Nordane Shipping AS	DK					
497	Norddeutsche Reederei H. Schuldt GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
498	Norden	DK					
499	NORDENIA Frachtkontor GmbH	DE					
500	Nordgrens Rederi AB	SE					
501	Nordic American Tankers Limited.	NO					
502	Nordic Bulk Carriers A/S	DK					
502	Nordic Bulk Carriers A/S	DK					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
503	Nordic Hamburg Shipping GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
504	Nordic Maritime Services AS	NO					
505	Nordic Shipholding	DK					
506	Nordic tankers A/S	DK					
506	Nordic tankers A/S	DK					
507	Nordmani AS	NO					
508	Nord-Marine DK ApS	DK					
509	Nordö-Link, Rederi AB	SE					
510	NORFOS Shipping Ltd.	EE					
511	Norgas Carriers AS	NO					
512	Norgas Carriers AS	NO					
513	Norient Product Pool A/S	DK					
514	Norled	NO					
515	Nørresundby Shipping AS	DK					
516	North Atlantic Drilling	NO					
517	North Sea Shipping AS	NO					
518	North Star Shipping Ltd	UK					
529	North Star Shipping Ltd	UK					
530	Northern Offshore Services	UK					
530	Northern Offshore Services	UK					
530	Northern Offshore Services AB	SE					
531	Northern Shipping Co	RU					
532	Northern Tanker Company Oy	FI					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
533	Northshore	NO					
534	Norwegian Car Carriers ASA	NO					
535	Novo Chartering B.V.	NL					
536	NSA Schiffahrt und Transport GmbH	DE					
537	NSB Niederelbe Schiffahrtsgesellschaft mbH & Co. KG	DE					
538	NSC Shipping GmbH & Cie. KG	DE					
539	NSK Shipping AS	NO					
540	Nurminen Maritime	LT					
540	Nurminen Maritime Latvia Ltd.	LV					
541	Nygård Shipping A/S	NO					
542	Nynas AB	SE					
543	Ocean Rig ASA	NO					
544	Ocean Yield	NO					
545	Oceangoing AS	NO					
546	Oceanic Container Line GmbH	DE					
547	Oceanteam Shipping ASA	NO					
548	Oceanwide Shipping & Chartering GmbH	DE					
549	Od fjell Drilling AS	NO					
549	Od fjell Terminals (Rotterdam) B.V.	NL					
550	Offen Group	DE					
551	Offshore Heavy Transportation AS	NO					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
552	Oldendorff Carriers GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
552	Oldendorff Carriers GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
553	OljOla AB	SE					
554	Olsen Energy ASA, Fred.	NO					
555	Olsen Gruppen AS	NO					
556	Olsen Marine Services as, Fred.	NO					
557	Olsen Ocean Ltd., Fred	NO					
558	Olsen Windcarrier AS, Fred.	NO					
559	Olympic Shipping A/S	NO					
560	Onego Shipping & Chartering BV	NL					
561	OOCL	NL					
562	Oost Atlantic Lijn B.V.	NL					
563	Opielok Reederei GmbH	DE					
564	Opstad Shipping AS	NO					
565	OPUS MARINE GmbH	DE					
566	Orient Shipping Rotterdam BV	NL					
567	Orion Bulkers GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
568	Orsted	DK					
569	Oslo Bulk	NO					
570	OSM Ship Management AS	NO					
571	Østensjø Rederi A/S	NO					
572	Passat Schiffahrtsgesellschaft mbH & Co. KG	DE					
573	Peak Shipping AS	NO					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
574	Petredec Ltd, Bermuda	UK					
575	PIL Agency the Netherlands	NL					
576	PIL Agency the Netherlands	NL					
577	PIL Agency the Netherlands	NL					
578	POL	PL					
579	Polar Tugs AS	NO					
580	PolarQuest AB	SE					
581	Polferries	PL					
582	Polfracht Shipbroking	PL					
583	Polish Baltic Shipping Company (PZB SA)	PL					
584	Polish Ocean Lines Group	PL					
585	Pol-Levant Shipping Lines Ltd	PL					
586	Polska Żegluga Morska	PL					
587	Polskie Ratownictwo Okretowe	PL					
586	Polsteam	PL					
588	Polyar Tankers AS	NO					
589	Polycrest A/S	NO					
590	Pomeranian Shipbrokers Ltd	PL					
591	Poseidon Schiffahrt GmbH	DE					
592	Poulsen Shipping A/S, J.	DK					
593	Preem AB	SE					
594	Premuda SpA	PL					
595	Prima Shipping Group	FI					
596	Primorsk Shipping Co	RU					
597	Pro Line Shipping GmbH	DE					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
598	Prosafe ASA	NO					
598	Prosafe Offshore Ltd	UK					
599	PWL Port Services GmbH & Co. KG (Peter W. Lampke)	DE					
600	Quadrant Bereederungs-ges. mbH & Co. KG	DE					
601	Rabien & Stadtlander GmbH	DE					
602	Reach Subsea ASA	NO					
603	Rederiet Høj A/S	DK					
604	Rederij T. Muller bv, Dordrecht	NL					
605	Rederij Wanmar	NL					
606	Reederei Bernd Sibum GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
607	Reederei Dartsch GmbH	DE					
608	Reederei Draxl	DE					
609	Reederei Eilbrecht GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
610	Reederei Erwin Strahlmann GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
611	Reederei Foroohari	DE					
612	Reederei H.-P. Wegener	DE					
613	Reederei Hans Peterson & Söhne GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
614	Reederei Hinsch GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
615	Reederei Jens & Waller GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
616	Reederei Köpping	DE					
617	Reederei Lehmann GmbH & Co. KG	DE					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
618	Reederei Moje GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
619	Reederei Nagel	DE					
620	Reederei NORD GMBH	DE					
621	Reederei Rambow	DE					
622	Reederei Rass GmbH & Co. KG, Bramstedt	DE					
623	Reederei Roth, KG, GmbH & Co.	DE					
624	Reederei Rudolf Schepers GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
625	Reederei Stefan Patjens GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
626	Reederei Thekla Schepers GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
627	Reederei Thomas Schulte GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
628	Reederei Voss GmbH & Co. KG, Burg/Fehmarn	DE					
629	Reedereiverwaltung Heino Winter GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
630	Remøy Management AS	NO					
631	Remøy Shipping AS	NO					
632	Rettig OY AB, Bore	FI					
633	RHL Reederei Hamburg Lloyd GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
634	Rickmers Reederei GmbH & Cie. KG	DE					
635	Rieber Shipping ASA, G.C.	NO					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
636	Riga Shipping Co	LV					
637	Rigel Schifffahrts GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
638	RIMSHIP AS	NO					
639	Rix Shipping	LV					
640	RN Dredging B.V.	DK					
641	Robert Wynn & Sons Ltd	UK					
642	Rødne & Sønner AS, L.	NO					
643	Rolf Günther, Schifffahrts- und Transportservice GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
644	RollDock N.V.	NL					
645	Ronja Marin Ltd., Oy	FI					
646	Rostein A/S	NO					
646	Rostein A/S	NO					
647	Royal Arctic	DK					
648	RRS RoRo Stevedores Germany GmbH	DE					
649	Sætre & Sønner, AS, K.	NO					
650	SAFE SHIPPING Ltd., Gdansk	PL					
651	Safmarine Container Lines	UK					
651	Safmarine Netherlands B.V., Rotterdam	NL					
651	Safmarine Netherlands B.V., Rotterdam	NL					
652	Saga Welco	NO					
653	SAL Heavy Lift GmbH	DE					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
654	Samba AS	NO					
655	Sam-Shipping	NL					
656	Samskip BV, Rotterdam	NL					
656	Samskip GmbH	DE					
657	Sanco Shipping AS	NO					
658	SCA Logistics AB	SE					
658	SCA Logistics B.V., Rotterdam	NL					
658	SCA Logistics B.V., Rotterdam	NL					
659	Scan Baltic Service	NO					
660	Scan-Shipping Bergen AS	NO					
661	Schepers, H., Bereederungs GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
662	Schiffahrtsgesellschaft Oltmann mbH & Co. KG	DE					
663	Schiffahrts-Kontor DETRA GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
664	Schiffahrtskontor tom Wörden GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
665	Schulte & Bruns GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
666	Scotline Ltd	UK					
667	SeaBird Exploration Norway AS	NO					
668	Sea-Cargo Agencies B.V., Rotterdam	NL					
668	Sea-Cargo AS	NO					
669	SeaDrill Management AS	NO					
670	Sealift n.v.	BE					
671	Sealion Shipping	UK					

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No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
672	Seastar Maritime Agency Ltd.	LV					
673	Seatrade Groningen	NL					
674	Seatrade Reefer Chartering N V	NL					
674	SEATRADE REEFER CHARTERING N.V., Antwerp	BE					
675	Seatrans Chemical Tankers AS	NO					
676	Seatrans Offshore	NO					
676	Seatrans Ship Management	NO					
677	Seatruck Ferries Ltd	UK					
678	Seaworks AS	NO					
679	Serco NorthLink Ferries	UK					
680	Serromah Shipping	NL					
681	Sevan Drilling ASA	NO					
682	Seven Seas Carriers AS	NO					
683	Shipexpress (Europe) Agency GmbH	DE					
684	Siem Offshore AS	NO					
685	Sigba AS	NO					
686	Simonsen ApS, Rederiet M.H.	DK					
687	Simonsen Chartering ApS	DK					
688	Sinpol Shipping and Agency b.v., Rotterdam	NL					
689	Sinilga Ltd	RU					
690	SinOceanic Shipping	NO					
691	Sinotrans (Germany) GmbH	DE					
692	Sirius Shipping AB	SE					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
692	Sirius Shipping ApS	DK					
693	Skansi Offshore, P/F	FO					
694	SKS Tankers Ltd.	NO					
695	Sloman Neptun Schiffahrts-Aktiengesellschaft	DE					
696	Sole Shipping AS	NO					
697	Solstad Farstad ASA	NO					
697	Solstad Offshore (UK) Ltd	UK					
698	Solvang ASA	NO					
699	Sølvtrans	NO					
700	SOMTRANS, REDERIJ, N.V., Schilde	BE					
701	Songa Offshore ASA	NO					
702	Spar Shipping AS	NO					
703	Speck, Claus-Markus, KG	DE					
704	Spliethoff	NL					
705	Sporens Rederier AS	NO					
706	STA See Transport Agentur GmbH	DE					
707	Star Reefers	UK					
708	Stena Bulk AB	SE					
709	Stena Marine Management AB	SE					
709	Stena Rederi AB	SE					
709	Stena Sessan Rederi AB	SE					
710	Stenersen AS, Rederiet	NO					
711	STOC Tankers AB	SE					
711	Stockholm Chartering AB	SE					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
712	Stolt-Nielsen (SNITS)	NL					
713	Stove Shipping AS	NO					
714	Straits Tanker Pte. Ltd.	DK					
715	Strand Shipping AS	NO					
716	Strandfaraskip Landsins	FO					
717	Subsea 7 Norway AS	NO					
718	Svendborg Uddybning ApS	DK					
719	Svenska Orient Linien AB	SE					
720	Svitzer	DK					
720	Svitzer Sverige AB	SE					
721	Swedia Rederi AB	SE					
722	Swedish Bulk, Red. AB	SE					
723	Swedish Maritime Administration (Sjöfartsverket)	SE					
724	Swire Seabed AS	NO					
725	T.K.B. Shipping A/S	DK					
726	Tailwind (Europe) AS	NO					
727	Tallink Silja AB	SE					
727	Tallink Silja Oy	FI					
728	Tananger Offshore	NO					
729	Tarbit Shipping AB	SE					
730	Tarptautines logistikos centras	LT					
731	Taylor Maritime	UK					
732	TB Marine Shipmanagement GmbH & Co. KG	DE					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
733	TEAM LINES Deutschland GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
734	TEAM SHIP Maritime GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
735	Team Tankers Management A/S	DK					
736	Teekay Marine Services GmbH	UK					
736	Teekay Shipping Norway AS	NO					
737	Terntank Rederi A/S	SE					
738	Thode, Johs., GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
739	Thor Ltd.	FO					
740	Thor Shipping & Transport BV	NL					
740	Thor Shipping & Transport BV, Antwerpen	BE					
741	Thun AB, Erik	SE					
742	Thun Tankers B.V, Delfzijl	NL					
743	TOM A/S	DK					
744	Torghatten Nord AS	NO					
745	Torghatten Trafikkselskap ASA (TTS ASA)	NO					
746	Torm	DK					
747	Transatlantic, Rederi AB	SE					
748	Transeste Schiffahrt GmbH	DE					
749	Transfennica Deutschland GmbH	DE					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
749	TRANSFENNICA POLSKA Spółka z o.o, Gdynia.	PL					
750	TransMar AS	NO					
751	Transmarine Tankers ApS	DK					
752	Transpetrol Maritime Services Ltd.	BE					
752	Transpetrol TM AS	NO					
753	Triton Schifffahrts GmbH	DE					
754	Triton Shipping AB	SE					
755	Troms Offshore Management AS	NO					
755	Troms Offshore Management AS	NO					
756	Trulsen Schifffahrt GmbH	DE					
757	Trumpy, Hugo, Agencies GmbH, Stuhr	DE					
758	TSA Tanker Shipping AB	SE					
759	Tschudi Shipping Company AS	NO					
760	TT-Line AB	SE					
760	TT-Line GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
761	TURKON Deutschland GmbH	DE					
762	Uglands Rederi, A/S	NO					
763	UK Dredging	UK					
764	Uksnøy & Co. AS	NO					
765	Ultrabulk	DK					
766	Ultragas	DK					
767	Ultragas ApS	DK					
768	Ulván Rederi AS, Egil	NO					
769	UmanShipping	SE					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
770	Unifeeder Germany - branch of Unifeeder A/S -	DE					
770	Unifeeder Netherlands B.V.	NL					
770	Unifeeder Netherlands B.V.	UK					
771	Uni-Tankers	DK					
771	Uni-Tankers	DK					
772	Uniteam Marine Shipping GmbH	DE					
773	United Arab Shipping Agency Company (Deutschland)	DE					
774	United European Car Carriers (Norway) AS	NO					
775	United Heavy Lift	DE					
776	UPT United Product Tankers GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
777	Utkilen AS	NO					
778	V Ships UK Ltd	UK					
778	V.Ships GmbH	DE					
778	V.Ships Norway AS	NO					
779	Vaage Ship Management AS	NO					
780	Väderö Tank AB	SE					
781	Van Uden Maritime BV	NL					
782	Vattenfall	DK					
783	Veder Rederijzaken BV	NL					
784	Vega-Reederei Friedrich Dauber GmbH & Co. KG	DE					
785	Ven-Trafiken AB	SE					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
786	Venus Shipping (Rederiet Venus)	DK					
787	Veritas Management AB	SE					
788	Vertom Scheepvaart	NL					
789	Vertraco Shipping B.V.	NL					
790	Vestland Offshore AS	NO					
791	VG-Shipping Ltd.	FI					
792	Viken Shipping AS	NO					
793	Viking Rederi AB	SE					
793	Viking Supply Ships	DK					
794	Vinga Ship Management	SE					
795	Vinnen, F.A., & Co. (GmbH & Co. KG)	DE					
796	Vogt & Maguire	UK					
797	Volga Baltic logistic company	PL					
798	Volstad Maritime AS	NO					
798	Volstad Shipping AS	NO					
799	Vroon Offshore Services Ltd	UK					
800	VT GROUP Verenigde Tankrederij b.v., Rotterdam	NL					
801	VT Marine Services	UK					
802	W & R Shipping B.V., Zwijndrecht	NL					
803	W.E.C. Agencies B.V., Rotterdam	NL					
804	Wagenborg Shipping BV	NL					
805	Wagle A/S, Rolf	NO					
806	Wagle Chartering AS	NO					
807	Wallem Europe	DE					

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
808	Wallenius Wilhelmsen AS Norge Filial Sverige	SE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
809	Wallenius Wilhelmsen Logistics AS	NO	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
810	Walleniusrederierna AB	SE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
811	Warrings, Hillern, GmbH & Co. KG	DE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
812	Wasaline	FI	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
813	Waxholms Angfartygs AB	SE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
814	Weco Bulk	DK	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
815	Weco RoRo	DK	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
816	Weco Tankers	DK	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
816	WecoShipping	DK	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
817	WecoShipping	DK	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
818	Wehr, Oskar, KG (GmbH & Co.)	DE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
819	Werrings Rederi AS, Morten	NO	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
820	Wessels Reederei GmbH & Co. KG	DE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
821	Westchart AS	NO	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
822	Westco AB	SE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
823	Western Bulk	NO	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
824	Wilson ASA	NO	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
824	Wilson EuroCarriers AS	NO	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
824	Wilson Ship Management AS	NO	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
825	Wind Shipping	NL	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
826	Wisby Tankers AB	SE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
827	Workfox BV	NL	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
828	XO Shipping A/S	DK	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

No	Company name	Country	Email	First name	Last name	Gender	Position
829	Zeppenfeld, Horst, GmbH & Co. KG	DE	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]

Table 10-5: Contact details of shipping companies (Full sample)

Personal details withheld.

Annex C5: Contact history

Group contacted	Number total	Contact mode	Date
Shipping associations met at Int. Shipping Conference in London from Germany, Denmark, Sweden, Netherlands, Belgium	5	Personalized emails	01.09.2017-31.10.2017
German shipping companies listed in the book "Wie erreiche ich wen in deutschen Häfen?"	371	Personalized emails	01.10.2017-01.01.2018
German shipping companies listed in the book "Wie erreiche ich wen in deutschen Häfen?"	371	Telephone calls followed by email or paper copy resend	08.01.2018-15.02.2018
UK shipowners listed with the UK Chamber of Shipping	38	Personalized emails	23.01.2018
Danish shipping companies listed with Danish Shipping	48	Personalized emails	23.01.2018
Swedish shipping companies listed with Svensk Sjöfart	46	Personalized emails	23.01.2018
Dutch shipping companies listed with infomarine24.com	26	Personalized emails	22.01.2018
Ship owners associations from Norway, Lithuania, Belgium, UK, ECSA, Poland, Russia, Estonia, Finland	8	Personalized emails	23.01.2018
Latvian shipping companies listed on euromaritime	11	Personalized emails	24.01.2018
Lithuanian shipping companies listed on euromaritime	12	Personalized emails	24.01.2018
Polish shipping companies listed with Port Gdansk	27	Personalized emails	25.01.2018
Shipping companies from Denmark listed on seadirectory.com	46	Personalized emails	26.01.2018

Shipping companies from the Faroe Islands listed on seadirectory.com	3	Personalized emails	26.01.2018
Shipping companies from Sweden listed on seadirectory.com	30	Personalized emails	26.01.2018
Shipping companies from Norway listed on seadirectory.com	216	Personalized emails	27.01.2018
Shipping companies from Finland listed on seadirectory.com	27	Personalized emails	27.01.2018

Table 10-6: Contact history North and Baltic Sea shipping companies

Annex C6: Overview over survey participants

<p>Companies of all sizes in the sample</p> <p><i>Number of vessels owned</i></p>	<p>Companies with older and newer assets in the sample</p> <p><i>Average age of vessels under ownership/operation</i></p>
<p>Companies from different shipping sectors in the sample</p> <p><i>Field of company activity</i></p>	<p>Companies operating to a different extent in Emission Control Areas in the sample</p> <p><i>Share of operations within ECAs</i></p>
<p>Companies flying a variety of flags in the sample</p> <p><i>Flag state of most company vessels</i></p>	<p>Companies belonging or not belonging to industry associations in the sample</p> <p><i>Industry association membership</i></p>

Annex C7: Characteristics of companies in the sample

No	Country code	Number of vessels owned	Number of vessels operated	Average age of vessels	Type of operations	Share of tramp operations	Share of ECA operations	Flag state	Central management location	Industry association membership
1	SG	50+	50+	10-20 years	Crude carriers	90%	20%	Bahamas	Singapore	Yes
2	DE	20-49	20-49	Less than 10 years	Specialized cargo carriers	80%	90%	Germany	Germany	Yes
3	DE	-	-	-	-	10%	90%	-	-	-
4	DE	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	Crude carriers	80%	90%	Portugal	Germany	Yes
5	DK	3-9	3-9	10-20 years	RoRo/RoPax vessels	0%	100%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
6	SE	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	80%	100%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
7	DK	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	100%	20%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
8	SE	10-19	10-19	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	100%	100%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
9	DE	50+	50+	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	90%	40%	Portugal	Germany	Yes
10	DE	10-19	10-19	10-20 years	RoRo/RoPax vessels	0%	100%	Germany	Germany	Yes
11	DE	10-19	10-19	10-20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	100%	80%	Cyprus	Germany	Yes
12	DE	10-19	10-19	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	100%	90%	Other	Germany	Yes
13	DE	Zero	10-19	10-20 years	General cargo carriers	100%	80%	Netherlands	Netherlands	No
14	DE	Zero	3-9	Less than 10 years	General cargo carriers	10%	90%	-	-	-
15	DE	10-19	3-9	-	General and specialized cargo carriers	100%	70%	Malta	Germany	Yes
16	DE	3-9	10-19	Less than 10 years	Specialized cargo carriers	10%	100%	Germany	Germany	Yes
17	DE	3-9	50+	Less than 10 years	Container vessels	0%	100%	Antigua and Barbuda	China	Yes
18	GB	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	RoRo/RoPax vessels	0%	90%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
19	DE	3-9	3-9	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	0%	10%	Marshall Islands	Germany	Yes
20	DE	50+	50+	Less than 10 years	Container vessels	0%	30%	Liberia	Germany	No
21	PL	10-19	10-19	Less than 10 years	General cargo carriers	30%	10%	Hong Kong	Poland	Yes
22	DE	10-19	10-19	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	80%	10%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
23		10-19	10-19	10-20 years	Container vessels	10%	70%	Germany	Germany	Yes
24	DE	3-9	20-49	10-20 years	Bulk and crude carriers	100%	10%	Marshall Islands	Germany	Yes
25	DK	50+	50+	10-20 years	Container vessels	0%	10%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
26	DE	10-19	10-19	10-20 years	General cargo carriers	20%	10%	Marshall Islands	Germany	Yes
27	DE	3-9	3-9	10-20 years	RoRo/RoPax vessels	0%	100%	Germany	Germany	Yes
28	DE	Zero	50+	10-20 years	Container vessels	90%	30%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
29	DE	Zero	-	10-20 years	Container vessels	0%	100%	Netherlands	Germany	Yes
30	NL	10-19	10-19	10-20 years	Container vessels and specialized cargo carriers	10%	80%	Bahamas	Netherlands	Yes
31	DE	10-19	20-49	10-20 years	General and specialized cargo carriers	30%	60%	Isle of Man	Germany	Yes
32	DE	1-2	3-9	10-20 years	Container vessels	0%	70%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	Yes
33	DE	10-19	10-19	-	-	10%	90%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	No
34	DE	3-9	10-19	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	100%	100%	Germany	Germany	Yes
35	DE	1-2	1-2	10-20 years	Container vessels	0%	10%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
36	DE	50+	50+	-	Crude and specialized cargo carriers	90%	20%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	-
37	DE	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	90%	50%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	Yes
38	US	20-49	50+	More than 20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	50%	30%	Liberia	Netherlands	Yes
39	LT	3-9	3-9	Less than 10 years	General cargo carriers	50%	90%	Other	Netherlands	Yes
40	DE	10-19	10-19	Less than 10 years	Specialized cargo carriers	60%	10%	Liberia	Germany	Yes

41	DK	20-49	20-49	Less than 10 years	General cargo and bulk carriers	10%	70%	Marshall Islands	Denmark	Yes
42	DE	3-9	20-49	10-20 years	Container vessels	10%	10%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
43	DK	20-49	50+	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	90%	60%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
44	DE	3-9	3-9	10-20 years	General cargo carriers	100%	10%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	No
45	DE	-	50+	Less than 10 years	Container vessels	0%	20%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
46	CA	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	10%	50%	Canada	Canada	Yes
47	SE	10-19	10-19	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	100%	80%	Netherlands	Sweden	Yes
48	NL	20-49	50+	More than 20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	40%	20%	Liberia	Netherlands	Yes
49	SE	1-2	1-2	More than 20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	100%	90%	Sweden	Sweden	Yes
50	DE	-	-	-	Specialized cargo carriers	10%	90%	-	-	-
51		20-49	20-49	10-20 years	Bulk and specialized cargo carriers	10%	10%	Liberia	Germany	No
52	FR	20-49	20-49	Less than 10 years	Bulk and specialized cargo carriers	70%	20%	Malta	Denmark	Yes
53		10-19	20-49	Less than 10 years	Bulk and specialized cargo carriers	100%	20%	Liberia	Germany	No
54	DE	3-9	3-9	10-20 years	Bulk, crude, and specialized cargo carriers	100%	50%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
55		10-19	10-19	10-20 years	Container vessels and specialized cargo carriers	0%	50%	Germany	Germany	Yes
56	DE	-	-	-	Specialized cargo carriers	10%	90%	-	-	-
57	DE	3-9	10-19	Less than 10 years	General and specialized cargo carriers	10%	80%	Germany	Germany	Yes
58	DE	Zero	10-19	10-20 years	Bulk and specialized cargo carriers	100%	30%	Panama	Germany	Yes
59	DE	Zero	3-9	Less than 10 years	-	10%	20%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	Yes
60	DE	-	-	-	-	10%	90%	-	-	-
61	DE	10-19	10-19	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	100%	20%	Other	Germany	Yes
62	GB	3-9	10-19	10-20 years	-	10%	90%	Isle of Man	United Kingdom	-
63	AX	1-2	1-2	More than 20 years	RoRo/RoPax vessels	0%	100%	Other	Finland	Yes
64	FI	Zero	3-9	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	0%	100%	Malta	Finland	No
65	DK	20-49	50+	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	100%	30%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
66	NO	Zero	20-49	10-20 years	General cargo carriers	10%	90%	Norway	Norway	No
67	DK	3-9	3-9	More than 20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	100%	100%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
68	DE	1-2	20-49	10-20 years	Bulk, crude, and specialized cargo carriers	100%	30%	Marshall Islands	Germany	No
69	SE	Zero	10-19	More than 20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	10%	10%	Panama	Sweden	Yes
70	DK	20-49	20-49	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	100%	90%	Singapore	Singapore	Yes
71	SE	1-2	3-9	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	20%	90%	Other	Sweden	Yes
72	NO	3-9	10-19	Less than 10 years	Specialized cargo carriers	90%	90%	Norway	Norway	Yes
73	DE	Zero	3-9	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	100%	90%	Cyprus	Germany	Yes
74	DE	-	-	-	-	10%	90%	-	-	-
75	DE	1-2	10-19	Less than 10 years	Crude carriers	100%	90%	Malta	Germany	Yes
76	DE	Zero	3-9	Less than 10 years	Container vessels	80%	90%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	Yes
77	DE	50+	50+	Less than 10 years	Container vessels	10%	10%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
78	DE	10-19	10-19	10-20 years	Container vessels and bulk carriers	80%	50%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
79	DE	1-2	3-9	10-20 years	Container vessels	0%	70%	Cyprus	Germany	Yes
80	DE	3-9	3-9	-	Container vessels and general cargo carriers	10%	50%	Liberia	Germany	No
81	NO	50+	50+	Less than 10 years	Bulk and crude carriers	100%	70%	Marshall Islands	Norway	Yes
82	DK	50+	50+	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	100%	60%	Liberia	Denmark	Yes

83	DK	50+	50+	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	100%	80%	Denmark	Denmark	Yes
84	DK	20-49	50+	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	90%	90%	-	-	Yes
85	GB	1-2	1-2	-	-	10%	90%	-	-	-
86	GB	10-19	10-19	10-20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	80%	40%	United Kingdom	United Kingdom	Yes
87	DE	50+	50+	Less than 10 years	General cargo and bulk carriers	100%	10%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
88	DE	3-9	3-9	10-20 years	Container vessels	0%	90%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	Yes
89	DE	1-2	1-2	10-20 years	Container vessels	10%	100%	Cyprus	Germany	No
90	DE	3-9	3-9	-	General cargo carriers	0%	100%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	Yes
91	DE	3-9	3-9	Less than 10 years	Specialized cargo carriers	20%	100%	Germany	Germany	Yes
92	DE	3-9	50+	Less than 10 years	Container vessels and crude carriers	10%	30%	Hong Kong	China	No
93	DE	-	10-19	Less than 10 years	General cargo and bulk carriers	100%	30%	Other	-	Yes
94	DE	10-19	10-19	10-20 years	General cargo and bulk carriers	100%	70%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	Yes
95	NO	20-49	20-49	Less than 10 years	Crude carriers	10%	90%	Norway	Norway	Yes
96	DE	3-9	20-49	Less than 10 years	Container vessels	0%	60%	Denmark	Denmark	No
97	DE	20-49	-	-	Specialized cargo carriers	70%	90%	Netherlands	Germany	Yes
98	NO	3-9	3-9	10-20 years	General and specialized cargo carriers	10%	90%	Norway	Norway	Yes
99	GB	1-2	1-2	10-20 years	Specialized cargo carriers	100%	90%	United Kingdom	United Kingdom	Yes
100	DK	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
101	NL	1-2	1-2	Less than 10 years	Container vessels, general, and specialized cargo carriers	10%	100%	Other	Netherlands	Yes
102	DE	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	General cargo carriers	90%	50%	Antigua and Barbuda	Germany	Yes
103	DE	3-9	3-9	Less than 10 years	Bulk and specialized cargo carriers	100%	90%	Netherlands	Netherlands	No
104	NO	50+	50+	10-20 years	General cargo, crude and specialized cargo carriers	50%	50%	Bahamas	Singapore	Yes
105	RU	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	General cargo and bulk carriers	90%	50%	Other	Russian Federation	Yes
106	DK	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	100%	90%	Other	Denmark	Yes
107	SE	Zero	1-2	10-20 years	RoRo/RoPax vessels	0%	100%	Other	Sweden	Yes
108	NO	3-9	3-9	Less than 10 years	General cargo and bulk carriers	90%	80%	Cyprus	Norway	Yes
109	DE	Zero	10-19	-	General cargo and bulk carriers	10%	50%	Marshall Islands	Germany	Yes
110	DE	Zero	50+	10-20 years	Container vessels, general cargo, bulk and crude carriers	70%	40%	Marshall Islands	Cyprus	Yes
111	DE	3-9	3-9	More than 20 years	General cargo and bulk carriers	100%	60%	Germany	Germany	Yes
112	DE	10-19	50+	Less than 10 years	Bulk carriers	100%	40%	Liberia	Germany	Yes
113	DE	20-49	20-49	10-20 years	Container vessels	80%	90%	Singapore	Singapore	Yes
114	DE	3-9	20-49	10-20 years	Container vessels	0%	30%	Cyprus	Germany	Yes
115	NO	3-9	10-19	10-20 years	General cargo and bulk carriers	100%	100%	Norway	Norway	Yes
116	DE	Zero	10-19	10-20 years	Bulk carriers	100%	90%	Marshall Islands	-	-
117	DE	3-9	3-9	10-20 years	Crude carriers	100%	50%	United Kingdom	Germany	Yes

Table 10-7: Characteristics of shipping companies in the sample (Full list after data cleaning)

Annex C8: Compliance cost data (Selected cases)

Data on costs of environmental legislation for 13 selected companies

Case 1: Small RoRo/RoPax owner-operator		No 7			
Vessel type	RoRo/RoPax				
Owner type	Owner-operator				
Number of vessels	3 to 9				
Average vessel age	10 to 20 years				
Area of operations	100% within ECA				
Type of operations	100% Liner operations				
Central management	Denmark				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Scrubber, Batteries as additional power supply				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	2%				
Capital costs	50%				
Voyage costs	25%				
Periodic maintenance costs	3%				
Operating costs	20%				
Most expensive measure	Air pollution				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	CO2				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	0	0	0	0%	0%
Nitrogen oxide	0	0	0	0%	0%
Low sulphur	60000	800000	860000	50%	3%
Carbon dioxide	0	0	0	0%	0%
Sewage water	25000	340000	365000	21%	1%
Oily water	180000	275000	455000	26%	2%
Antifouling	0	0	0	0%	0%
Waste	40000	0	40000	2%	0%
Overall costs	17000000	10000000	27000000		
Sum of compliance costs	305000	1415000	1720000		
Compliance as percentage of total costs	2%	14%	6%		

Case 2: Large specialized cargo carrier owner-operator		No 9			
Vessel type	Specialized cargo carrier				
Owner type	Owner-operator				
Number of vessels	20-49				
Average vessel age	10-20 years				
Area of operations	80% Non-ECA operations				
Type of operations	100% Tramp operations				
Central management	Denmark				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	0%				
Capital costs	11%				
Voyage costs	37%				
Periodic maintenance costs	8%				
Operating costs	44%				
Most expensive measure	Air pollution				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	CO2				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	10000	250000	260000	39%	1%
Nitrogen oxide			0	0%	0%
Low sulphur	400000		400000	61%	1%
Carbon dioxide			0	0%	0%
Sewage water			0	0%	0%
Oily water			0	0%	0%
Antifouling			0	0%	0%
Waste			0	0%	0%
Overall costs	39510000	300000	39810000		
Sum of compliance costs	410000	250000	660000		
Compliance as percentage of total cost	1%	83%	2%		

Case 3: Medium-sized bulk carrier owner-operator with young fleet		No 14			
Vessel type	Bulk carrier (Liquid/Dry)				
Owner type	Owner-operator				
Number of vessels	10-19 vessels				
Average vessel age	Less than 10 years				
Area of operations	90% within ECA				
Type of operations	100% Tramp operations				
Central management	Germany				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	0%				
Capital costs	50%				
Voyage costs	0%				
Periodic maintenance costs	25%				
Operating costs	25%				
Most expensive measure	Ballast water				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Ballast water				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	15000			33%	3%
Nitrogen oxide	2500			6%	1%
Low sulphur	2500			6%	1%
Carbon dioxide	2500			6%	1%
Sewage water	2500			6%	1%
Oily water	7500			17%	2%
Antifouling	7500			17%	2%
Waste	5000			11%	1%
Overall costs	500000				
Sum of compliance costs	45000				
Compliance as percentage of total costs	9%				

Case 4: Small container vessel owner-operator		No 37			
Vessel type	Container vessels				
Owner type	Owner-operator				
Number of vessels	1 to 2				
Average vessel age	10-20 years				
Area of operations	90% outside ECA				
Type of operations	90% Liner operations				
Central management	Germany				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure		Does not pay for cargo-handling, capital or voyage costs			
Cargo-handling costs					
Capital costs					
Voyage costs					
Periodic maintenance costs	76%				
Operating costs	24%				
Most expensive measure	Antifouling				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Ballast water				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water				0%	0%
Nitrogen oxide				0%	0%
Low sulphur				0%	0%
Carbon dioxide				0%	0%
Sewage water	1000		1000	2%	0%
Oily water		500	500	1%	0%
Antifouling		45000	45000	93%	4%
Waste	1500	500	2000	4%	0%
Overall costs	1200000		1200000		
Sum of compliance costs	2500	46000	48500		
Compliance as percentage of total costs	0%		4%		

Case 5: Large container-vessel operator in time charter				No 47	
Vessel type	Container vessels				
Owner type	Operator in time charter				
Number of vessels	More than 50				
Average vessel age	Less than 10 years				
Area of operations	20% outside of ECA				
Type of operations	100% Liner operations				
Central management	Germany				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	0%				
Capital costs	60%				
Voyage costs	5%				
Periodic maintenance costs	12%				
Operating costs	23%			Does not pay for fuel	
Most expensive measure	Antifouling				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Ballast water				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	5000	40000	45000	42%	
Nitrogen oxide				0%	
Low sulphur				0%	
Carbon dioxide		8000	8000	7%	
Sewage water				0%	
Oily water	3000		3000	3%	
Antifouling		40000	40000	37%	
Waste		12000	12000	11%	
Overall costs					
Sum of compliance costs	8000	100000	108000		
Compliance as percentage of total costs					

Case 6: Large bulk carrier owner-operator		No 54			
Vessel type	Bulk carriers and specialized cargo carriers				
Owner type	Owner-operator				
Number of vessels	20-49				
Average vessel age	Less than 10 years				
Area of operations	80% outside ECA				
Type of operations	70% Tramp operations				
Central management	Denmark				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel, Ethane				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	10%				
Capital costs	40%				
Voyage costs	10%				
Periodic maintenance costs	20%				
Operating costs	20%				
Most expensive measure	Air pollution				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Air pollution				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	5000			14%	1%
Nitrogen oxide				0%	0%
Low sulphur	10000			29%	3%
Carbon dioxide	5000			14%	1%
Sewage water				0%	0%
Oily water	5000			14%	1%
Antifouling	5000			14%	1%
Waste	5000			14%	1%
Overall costs	400000				
Sum of compliance costs	35000				
Compliance as percentage of total cost	9%				

Case 7: Small bulk operator without own assets		No 66			
Vessel type	Bulk carrier				
Owner type	Operator				
Number of vessels	3-9 vessels operated				
Average vessel age	10-20 years				
Area of operations	100% ECA operations				
Type of operations	100% Liner operations				
Central management	Finland				
Industry association membership	No				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	20%				
Capital costs	10%				
Voyage costs	0%				
Periodic maintenance costs	10%				
Operating costs	60%				
Most expensive measure	CO2				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	CO2				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water					
Nitrogen oxide					
Low sulphur	100000			71%	10%
Carbon dioxide	5000			4%	1%
Sewage water				0%	0%
Oily water	10000			7%	1%
Antifouling	5000			4%	1%
Waste	20000			14%	2%
Overall costs	850000	125000	975000		
Sum of compliance costs	140000				
Compliance as percentage of total cost	16%		14%		

Case 8: Large container vessel owner-operator		No 79			
Vessel type	Container vessels				
Owner type	Owner-operator				
Number of vessels	More than 50				
Average vessel age	Less than 10 years				
Area of operations	90% Non-ECA operations				
Type of operations	90% Liner operations				
Central management	Germany				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	na				
Capital costs	na				
Voyage costs	na				
Periodic maintenance costs	na				
Operating costs	na				
Most expensive measure	Air pollution				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Air pollution				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	15000			2%	1%
Nitrogen oxide				0%	0%
Low sulphur	600000			65%	25%
Carbon dioxide				0%	0%
Sewage water	1000			0%	0%
Oily water	10000			1%	0%
Antifouling	300000			32%	13%
Waste	3000			0%	0%
Overall costs	2300000	80000	2380000		
Sum of compliance costs	929000				
Compliance as percentage of total cost	39%				

Case 9: Large owner-operator of bulk and crude carriers		No 83			
Vessel type	Bulk carrier				
Owner type	Owner-operator of bulk and crude carriers				
Number of vessels	More than 50				
Average vessel age	Less than 10 years				
Area of operations	70% ECA				
Type of operations	100% Tramp				
Central management	Norway				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	10%				
Capital costs	20%				
Voyage costs	40%				
Periodic maintenance costs	10%				
Operating costs	20%				
Most expensive measure	Air pollution				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Air pollution				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	100000			10%	
Nitrogen oxide	50000			5%	
Low sulphur	500000			50%	
Carbon dioxide	100000			10%	
Sewage water	50000			5%	
Oily water	100000			10%	
Antifouling	50000			5%	
Waste	50000			5%	
Overall costs					
Sum of compliance costs	1000000				
Compliance as percentage of total costs					

Case 10: Medium-sized specialized cargo carrier		No 88			
Vessel type	Specialized cargo carrier				
Owner type	Owner-operator (some vessels contracted under time charter)				
Number of vessels	10 to 19				
Average vessel age	10-20 years				
Area of operations	40% ECA operations				
Type of operations	80% Tramp operations				
Central management	United Kingdom				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	10%				
Capital costs	10%				
Voyage costs	10%				
Periodic maintenance costs	25%				
Operating costs	45%				
Most expensive measure	Ballast water				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Ballast water				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	10000	750000	760000	95%	
Nitrogen oxide		10000	10000	1%	
Low sulphur		10000	10000	1%	
Carbon dioxide		5000	5000	1%	
Sewage water		500	500	0%	
Oily water		500	500	0%	
Antifouling		6000	6000	1%	
Waste		4000	4000	1%	
Overall costs					
Sum of compliance costs	10000	786000	796000		
Compliance as percentage of total costs					

Case 11: Large general cargo carrier owner-operator		No 96			
Vessel type	General cargo carrier				
Owner type	Owner-operator				
Number of vessels	20-49				
Average vessel age	10-20 years				
Area of operations	70% within ECA				
Type of operations	100% Tramp operations				
Central management	Germany				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	10%				
Capital costs	20%				
Voyage costs	10%				
Periodic maintenance costs	25%				
Operating costs	35%				
Most expensive measure	Ballast water				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Ballast water				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	1000	2500	3500	27%	
Nitrogen oxide			0	0%	
Low sulphur			0	0%	
Carbon dioxide	1500	2000	3500	27%	
Sewage water	2000		2000	15%	
Oily water	3000		3000	23%	
Antifouling			0	0%	
Waste	1000		1000	8%	
Overall costs					
Sum of compliance costs	8500	4500	13000		
Compliance as percentage of total costs					

Case 12: Small Bulk and Specialized Cargo Carrier		No 105			
Vessel type	Bulk, Specialized cargo				
Owner type	Owner-operator				
Number of vessels	3 to 9				
Average vessel age	Less than 10 years				
Area of operations	90% within ECA				
Type of operations	100% Tramp operations				
Central management	Netherlands				
Industry association membership	No				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	na				
Capital costs	na				
Voyage costs	na				
Periodic maintenance costs	na				
Operating costs	na				
Most expensive measure	Sewage water				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Ballast water				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	5000	50000	55000	44%	4%
Nitrogen oxide	0	0	0	0%	0%
Low sulphur	0	0	0	0%	0%
Carbon dioxide	0	0	0	0%	0%
Sewage water	5000	15000	20000	16%	2%
Oily water	5000	0	5000	4%	0%
Antifouling	5000	10000	15000	12%	1%
Waste	15000	15000	30000	24%	2%
Overall costs	600000	650000	1250000		
Sum of compliance costs	35000	90000	125000		
Compliance as percentage of total costs	6%	14%	10%		

Case 13: Small owner operator of bulk and general cargo vessels		No 110			
Vessel type	Bulk, general cargo carriers				
Owner type	Owner-operator				
Number of vessels	3 to 9				
Average vessel age	Less than 10 years				
Area of operations	80% within ECA				
Type of operations	90% Tramp operations				
Central management	Norway				
Industry association membership	Yes				
Compliance with Sox legislation	Low sulphur fuel				
Cost structure					
Cargo-handling costs	20%				
Capital costs	15%				
Voyage costs	30%				
Periodic maintenance costs	15%				
Operating costs	20%				
Most expensive measure	Air pollution				
Most expensive measure (Expected)	Ballast water				
Environmental compliance costs	Operation	Invest	Sum	Percentage of compliance costs	Percentage of overall costs
Ballast water	6000	40000	46000	96%	
Nitrogen oxide	0	0	0	0%	
Low sulphur	0	0	0	0%	
Carbon dioxide	0	0	0	0%	
Sewage water	500	0	500	1%	
Oily water	500	0	500	1%	
Antifouling	500	0	500	1%	
Waste	300	0	300	1%	
Overall costs					
Sum of compliance costs	7800	40000	47800		
Compliance as percentage of total costs					

Annex D1: Technical compliance solutions under development

Solutions to environmental compliance currently under development

During expert interviews, interviewees discussed solutions to environmental compliance and the cleaner operation of vessels that were currently in development and might become relevant in the next years. Although these have little bearing on current compliance costs, a close monitoring of these options may be relevant for future research.

Improved scrubbers

Experts suggest that scrubbers will develop further in the next years, becoming smaller in size and more efficient. E4 explains: "...these scrubbers are in development. I am convinced that the technology that we built in today will already significantly differ from the scrubbers that you will get on the market in five years' time. They are then more mature. One knows the processes better. One was maybe able to make the equipment smaller and more efficient." (T4, para 151; see also T6, para 123 on the improvement of scrubbers over time) Owing to improvements, the technology might become of interest to a larger number of shipping companies.

Mandatory speed limits

Permanently limiting the maximum speed of commercial trading vessels could serve to permanently decrease CO₂ emissions of the shipping industry. This could be crucial to meet the IMO's CO₂ targets for 2050. E6 argues: "The discussion led by environmental organizations for example often leads to asking for direct speed limits in order to save fuel. Evidently in the face of the crisis situation one sees how shipping companies have almost entirely I would say introduced slow steaming in order to save fuel, as that forms the biggest share of the costs and thus also the biggest share of opportunities to save money in any way during daily operations. Naturally, it is the concern of environmental organizations to somehow make that permanent [zementieren] and to say: Great, let us introduce a maximum speed level of 16 knots. That is entirely amiss to the issue and the nature of the shipping industry and also to the context of the international exchange of goods." (T6, para 18) E9 asserts that limiting shipping speeds also requires adjustments in ship design: "That means they are now more and more taking care to build other bulge bows to the front and other propellers that are more efficient for the sailing speed. Well, they are no longer designed for 20, 22, 23 knots, but for 18 knots and that is really the speed that is sailed at in the meantime." (T9, para 99) While mandatory speed limits could prove effective in limiting CO₂ emissions, their introduction remains a request by environmental organizations and does not of yet find political support.

Shore-side electricity

Another technical solution to limit exposure to vessel-source pollution especially in harbour cities is the use of shore-side electricity. E1 explains: "There is currently a very intensive discussion about shore side electricity; that the vessels are plucked into the socket. Or are supplied by small barges and that these barges are then not fuelled with diesel, but with liquid natural gas, LNG. Such things are under discussion." (T1, para 145) E9 adds to this, stating: "...shore connection is also a huge topic. That already exists in parts with us as well that we

take a shore connection and that will come up I think. And if they have enough capacity at land to produce the electricity, why not. Well, I think it is good. That is a good thing. One has to make sure that in the harbour, let me say, for a container vessel you need to hold available three, four megawatts. Well, first of all you need to channel that electricity through a wire. Well, but that is in any way a possibility, I think that is good.”. (T9, para 137) While there seems to be little concern about the positive welfare effects of shore-side electricity, the question of availability needs to be solved.

Low-sulphur heavy fuel oil

While the traditional distinction of shipping fuel is between low-sulphur marine gas oil and high-sulphur heavy fuel oil, as a reaction to sulphur legislation, refineries have started developing a new product with the properties of heavy fuel oil, but a sulphur content below 0.1%. E4 describes this advancement: “A new, interesting development is currently coming from the oil companies, who now also have to struggle with this issue and who are now increasingly coming into the market with heavy fuel oil that contains not more than 0.1 per cent sulphur, what we have always said in the earlier times that that would not exist. When I started I knew that occasionally there is heavy fuel oil with 0.5% sulphur, but only in small amounts, in limited amounts. And now suddenly the colleagues from the oil industry are coming onto the market saying: Dear shipper, I offer you heavy fuel oil with 0.1%...”. (T4, para 151) Another expert adds: “That is the next development that we see, that we hear something about here and there. In fact Exxon has gone public with such a product now, press conference and so forth. That one says: We do not have to switch somehow to diesel now, but we have a fuel quality that still has heavy fuel properties. That means: Colour black, viscosity high, but sulphur content low.”. (T6, para 125) While pioneer companies might be testing the new product, others remain sceptical: “There is no-one who has yet tested that. It is being offered and I have heard from shipping companies that wanted to bunker in Rotterdam and that were being told: Yes, yes, you could bunker that, but they were also still very hesitant, because if that is not working and you have a mechanical breakdown, you don’t want that under any circumstances.”, E6 illustrates. (T6, para 129) He goes on: “But the message for us is: Fuels and fuel alternatives are being developed further.”. (T6, para 129) The developments here should be closely monitored, as they will have a great influence on compliance costs.

Methanol

Other fuel alternatives are being developed and tested by the industry, among them methanol. An expert reports: “Stena is trying methanol as a fuel. That is not really very much science fiction, I would say. But it is still something that one has to observe first of all. Well, methanol is a substance that is not so very easy to handle. In addition, one has to see as well, where the methanol is coming from. Methanol is an alcohol. There you have to very closely scrutinize the sources, so that you do not somehow enter into a food-for-fuel or the other way around fuel-for-food discussion, not that somewhere arable land is used in order to produce fuel. The next question, well, I am not really familiar with the details, but it is a question that comes to me spontaneously, is the question of water consumption in the production process of such substances. Water is also a limited resource on this planet. Thus – does it make much sense? You also have to look at that.”. (T4, para 160) In addition to the question of sourcing,

availability in ports will be an issue: “It complies with the emissions requirements and it is clean and it is technically feasible, but I guess because it is not such a main stream fuel, the supply and availability would be the big issue. If a company has solved that part of the problem, then it is possible.”, E2 reflects. (T2, para 104) Methanol is currently a marginal product, but may prove a promising fuel alternative in the future.

Hydrogen

Another solution that is in early stages of development is hydrogen as a source of power. E4 explains: “What also could one day become interesting, in the future, so to say, would be hydrogen as an energy source. There we already said 10 years ago: Gosh, that is maybe already coming in 10 to 20 years and hydrogen is interesting – no emissions at all apart from water vapour. In rare cases that already exists in the automobile sector, but already for a long time in test applications, via a combustion engine as well as via a fuel cell. The German navy has submarines that are powered by fuel cell propulsion with hydrogen. By way of the LNG we get towards, I would say, the technology how to deal with very cold materials. Once that is established in the shipping industry one could imagine to also do the next step towards hydrogen that also needs to be cooled down very much in order to store it somehow reasonably. And with these explosions... let me say... with all these security issues one would also already have approaches from the use of LNG. The question that I need to ask in relation to hydrogen is: Where is the matter then produced, so that I do not free much more CO₂ during the production process than I am saving in the end? Still, that might also one day be possible.” (T4, para 160). There is of yet little evidence on the possibilities that hydrogen may offer to the shipping industry.

Fuel cells and batteries

A few experts see a future for fuel cells and batteries to power ships. E5 maintains: “There will be a lot about fuel cells if you look 10, 15, 20 years down the line. I think fuel cells will be something that will be coming up.”. (T5, para 184) E2 is of a similar opinion, but likewise believes that the development will still take some time: “...fuel cells and batteries and hydrogen fuel cells. This is a possibility, but I think we are probably at least five to ten years away from starting to see cases. Having said that we have, at least we have one ship that we have worked on, which contains batteries as one of the propulsion methods or fuel methods, if you like. So, it is a bit like a hybrid car, so you have the conventional diesel engine and you have got the batteries and if all goes well and the batteries could take you a long way, but if it does not go well or if you need extra power the engine can kick in. I think the key there is really the fuel cell technology becoming less expensive per unit of power. So, in a way it is quite a similar issue with the smartphone. Everything has progressed enormously in terms of the technology that is out there and what you can do. But what seems to have stopped, or what seems to be the holding point is the battery power.”. (T2, para 106, see also T11, para 274 on the possibilities of battery technology) E8 states that fuel cells could eventually provide a solution once legislation on noise is passed, but will come with significant cost increases: “...it could also mean that we have to do without diesel engines or gas engines and that we have to use a fuel cell. Then it will become really expensive.” (T8, para 119) The development of both fuel cells

and batteries and their possible application for the shipping industry should be closely monitored.

LNG

Different from other solutions, propulsion with liquid natural gas is already in use by various companies across the industry. E8 exemplifies: “Currently you can find them in Scandinavia. Those are the LNG vessels in ferry service.” (T8, para 247) Still, the technology is in its infancy. E3 reports: “...the offers are still limited and there is also relatively little experience there. And I think that there also maybe ship owners are still waiting to see how the market for LNG is developing as well as the infrastructure in the harbours. One needs to be reasonably able to refuel the tanks. [...] That will be interesting to the feeder traffic, thus everything we have in the area of short sea shipping; for them it will be interesting; certainly not for the container shipping industry between China and Europe. For that the space on board to take up LNG is not sufficient, as LNG has significantly more volume and the tanks would need to be bigger and that would nibble off the loading volume and that is certainly not to the mind of the ship owners.” (T3, para 66) E2 argues that the technology will not play a role for the existing fleet: “...where we will see LNG coming in will be on the newbuilding market and in ships, I guess that operate within a fixed route where the supply of fuel is available.” (T2, para 98) Also, the expert adds, it will only play a role on major routes and within European waters: “The supply of LNG is not [available] at the moment. It is easier, I guess, in ports within Europe, so if you look at major ports it would be much easier to take care of that. But again, if you look at deep sea, I think what is holding the industry down at the moment is making sure that there is going to be availability on certain ways where the ship is stopping.” (T2, para 100) E4 describes barriers to the use of LNG, stating that the fuel is “an interesting story, but technically very demanding and will certainly only be practicable and operational with specially trained staff, who know how to deal with this technology. That is a substance that is -163°C cold. You cannot touch that any more. It also cannot touch on any unprotected structures anywhere, as they will thereby be destroyed. There is also a certain problem with explosions risks and such things with gas. Thus, thereby the shipping operations get more complicated.” (T4, para 143) E7 estimates that a wide introduction may take a few years or even decades. (T7, para 147) He adds that a regional implementation is more likely than a global one, saying that it “will maybe be an alternative for the Baltic Sea, but globally speaking I believe not. Well, A it is linked to a fair amount of additional costs. Well, MGO as we said will also be more expensive, but it [LNG technology] first of all needs to be developed corresponding to such a vessel. United Arab Shipping is doing that or has gone to the press saying: Our vessels will be LNG ready, which means they may be retrofit with rather little technical and temporal effort to run on liquid gas. That also requires for gas stations somewhere in the harbours where those vessels are passing through. And up to now these gas stations do not exist. LNG will come, but it requires time, a lot of time.” (T7, para 149) E11 adds: “My personal opinion is that we will keep on working with what we have in the next years regarding the vessel types. At least here in Northern Europe. Starting in 2016, `17, `18 the first vessels will likely come up that operate on LNG, but they will not be bigger due to the restrictions that we unluckily have here in the harbours and owing to the waterways.” (T11, para 374) E9 is very positive about a greater role of LNG-powered vessels, stating: “That is the future in all likelihood. [...] That is evidently super-efficient.” (T9,

para 91) The development of liquid natural gas has to be monitored closely when studying the environmental impact of the shipping industry in the next decades.

New propulsion systems

Another, very vague, suggestion that one expert is putting forward is the development of a new generation of ship engines. He argues: “...finally to free oneself from the conventional ship propulsion that really has existed the way it is today for fifty years. Really nothing has happened in the last fifty years regarding the ship propulsion of large vessels. One really needs to state that. Well, we are here in 2014 and we still have conventionally propelled vessels that burn heavy fuel oil. They have indeed all become a bit more efficient, but really regarding the actual ship propulsion nothing has changed. The vessel size is certainly a factor that makes it more efficient, but the propulsion itself is to a hair the same as on the Cap San Diego [historical vessel in the harbour of Hamburg] lying there. It really is exactly the same, simply a bit bigger. Exactly the same propulsion concept, exactly the same engine really, if you want, a bit bigger and so on, but exactly the same. [...] The advantage is the operational reliability. Today I have vessels that have few breakdowns, that are very reliable in operation, their construction is fully developed, the engines are technically mature. That is evidently also a fine thing for the ship owner again, but maybe that is now the chance, let me say, to close that chapter, to develop new propulsion systems and to really say: Here, I want to chance something and properly and build something else into the vessel.”. (T9, para 195) While the expert is determined in his criticism of current propulsion systems, he does not propose tangible alternatives. E12 is taking a similar stance, asking for new building criteria for maritime engines to decrease nitrogen oxide emissions, while not offering palpable propositions: “How much or how little nitrogen oxide is produced by a ship depends on the burning process. This means what kind of engine you have and how you are operating it. And in the end it is related to the building criteria of maritime engines. You can retrofit them, rebuild them but in the end it is design criteria for ships and has to be approached very differently.”. (T12, para 77)

Easy-to-recycle vessels

A last notion mentioned by experts how the environmental performance of vessels may be improved in the future are vessels that are built in a way to facilitate recycling at the end of their lifecycle. This concept is described by E9, stating that one must think about “...in how far one can recycle the ship. There exists also an indicator in how far that is sustainably produced and if one now cuts it into pieces and separates everything then the vessel components are already built in in a way that the knacker has an easy job. He can build out the pipes like that and does not need to take the isolation material off the pipes and more. That is named... there exists a certain term, but I don’t know any more how it is called. And clearly, that is also being done, that one now maybe constructs vessels that are easy to demolish and so on.”. (T9, para 171) There are not yet any political endeavours to advance the construction of easy-to-recycle vessels.

Annex D2: Histograms of cost developments

Figure 10-3: Histogram of total cost development 2015-2017

Figure 10-4: Histogram of voyage cost development 2015-2017

Figure 10-5: Histogram of expected voyage cost development 2018-2022

Annex D3: Spearman correlations of cost developments

Method	x	y	rho	p-value	Evaluation
Spearman	Percent Total Cost Development	Company size	-0.1093686	0.371	not significant
Spearman	Percent Total Cost Development	Average age	0.2565007	0.04076	significant
Spearman	Percent Total Cost Development	Tramp operations	-0.02516288	0.8374	not significant
Spearman	Percent Total Cost Development	Industry association membership	0.07425717	0.5443	not significant
Spearman	Percent Total Cost Development	Vessel type Q12	-0.04202874	0.7356	not significant
Spearman	Percent Total Cost Development	ECA operations	-0.130463	0.2853	not significant
Spearman	Percent Total Cost Development	Vessels owned	-0.01982143	0.8735	not significant
Spearman	Percent Total Cost Development	Type of operations	0.01929668	0.8817	not significant
Spearman	Percent Voyage Cost Development	Company size	-0.09939963	0.4235	not significant
Spearman	Percent Voyage Cost Development	Average age	-0.02746126	0.8308	not significant
Spearman	Percent Voyage Cost Development	Tramp operations	0.06231685	0.6164	not significant
Spearman	Percent Voyage Cost Development	Industry association membership	0.1007497	0.4172	not significant
Spearman	Percent Voyage Cost Development	Vessel type Q12	0.00166605	0.9895	not significant
Spearman	Percent Voyage Cost Development	ECA operations	-0.1597206	0.1967	not significant
Spearman	Percent Voyage Cost Development	Vessels owned	-0.1879289	0.1308	not significant
Spearman	Percent Voyage Cost Development	Type of operations	0	1	not significant

Table 10-8: Spearman correlations for total and voyage cost developments with company characteristics

Annex D4: Freight rate model developed from qualitative data

Modelling freight rate effects of maritime environmental legislation on the North and Baltic Sea

Annex D5: Freight rate developments

	Freightrate Jan15	Freightrate Apr15	Freightrate Jul15	Freightrate Oct15	Freightrate Jan16	Freightrate Apr16	Freightrate eJul16	Freightrate Oct16	Freightrate Jan17	Freightrate Apr17	Freightrate Jul17	Freightrate Oct17	Variance	Standard deviation	VesseltypeQ17
A	100	100	100	100	95	95	95	95	97	97	97	97	4.6	2.1	4 RoRo
B	100	100	94	97	105	100	86	96	100	94	90	82	43.7	6.6	6 Specialized
C	100	80	60	80	95	60	50	40	75	85	95	97	394.1	19.9	3 Bulker
D	100	30	96	97	97	97	97	97	97	97	97	97	377.0	19.4	4 RoRo
E	100	83	91	99	90	79	71	80	86	95	101	96	91.3	9.6	1 Container
F	100	19	20	20	22	27	31	34	35	39	43	48	491.2	22.2	3 Bulker
G	100	100	100	100	99	97	93	99	98	102	110	122	56.2	7.5	1 Container
H	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	0.0	0.0	6 Specialized
I	100	100	130	135	30	23	65	65	77	90	90	90	1157.4	34.0	3 Bulker
J	100	100	104	110	109	96	80	73	83	87	78	75	180.9	13.5	3 Bulker
K	100	102	102	102	102	98	98	98	98	103	103	103	4.8	2.2	3 Bulker
L	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	43	270.8	16.5	6 Specialized
M	100	110	100	90	150	140	90	57	50	47	47	45	1351.7	36.8	5 Crude
N	100	94	88	82	78	78	75	76	77	75	78	80	64.9	8.1	1 Container
O	100	100	100	91	84	120	75	49	49	50	44	84	643.6	25.4	1 Container
P	100	62	62	62	62	62	62	62	62	70	78	89	166.6	12.9	3 Bulker
Q	100	101	105	118	133	158	149	138	121	74	29	44	1594.0	39.9	5 Crude
R	100	48	34	42	62	50	38	54	52	57	59	130	758.1	27.5	3 Bulker
S	100	41	23	83	40	17	96	118	79	36	124	144	1829.7	42.8	3 Bulker

Table 10-9: Freight rate developments 2015-2017, n=19

Annex D6: Constructs for PLS analysis

Histograms of constructs for partial least squares analysis on determinants of compliance

Annex D7: Description, definition and classification of company characteristics based on questionnaire data

Company size

For the purpose of statistical analysis, participants were clustered into three groups, namely small, medium-sized and large companies. Small companies are defined as those owning AND operating less than 10 vessels. Large companies are defined as companies EITHER owning OR operating more than 50 vessels. Medium-sized companies are defined by default. (CompanySize = 1 IF VesselsOwned = 1 OR 2 OR 3 AND VesselsOperated = 1 OR 2 OR 3; CompanySize = 3 IF VesselsOwned = 6 OR VesselsOperated = 6; CompanySize = 2 ALL OTHER CASES) Putting the variable CompanyType in relation to CompanySize it becomes apparent that all sizes of companies as well as all shipping sector are represented in the sample. The largest group is made up of medium-sized companies with ten or more vessels either in ownership or operation, but less than 50 vessels in ownership and operation. In terms of company type, bulk carriers make the largest group by far with 42 companies in the sample, followed by 32 companies active in specialized cargo carriers. RoRo and RoPax vessels make for the smallest group with a mere six companies.

	Small company Count	Medium-sized company Count	Large company Count	Sum	%
Container vessels	9	8	8	25	17.4
General cargo carriers	9	14	3	26	18.1
Bulk carriers (Liquid/Dry)	7	25	10	42	29.2
RoRo/RoPax vessels	4	2	0	6	4.2
Crude carriers	2	5	6	13	9.0
Specialized cargo carriers	8	20	4	32	22.2
Sum	39	74	31	144	100
%	27.1	51.4	21.5	100	

Table 10-10: Description of sample: Type of shipping company organized by company size

Ownership structure

117 shipping companies of all sizes took the survey as may be seen in the graph above. With reference to Figure 10-6, a large number of companies in the sample may be defined as owner-operators (marked in red), who operate more or less the same number of vessels they own. Another group are solely active in shipping operations without owning any vessels themselves (marked in blue). A third group owns less vessels than they operate (marked in green). For the purpose of this research the three groups are classified as owner-operators, operators with limited own assets and operators without own assets. Only a single company falls under the category ‘owner with limited operations’. This distribution does not reflect the average distribution of companies present in the shipping industry, as there is a vast number of companies that solely own, but do not operate vessels. It rather reflects the type of companies interested in taking the survey and thus interested in issues of maritime environmental legislation. These seem to be companies active in vessel operations rather than companies active solely in holding assets. A further explanation may be that vessel owners are quite often seclusive and difficult to contact. The researcher had experienced it in several cases that despite legal requirements to publish contact information on websites, owning companies would refrain from doing so.

Figure 10-6: Description of sample: Ownership structure

Type of operations (liner or tramp)

Time spent in emission control areas like the North and Baltic Sea might have a bearing on compliance costs. Thus, area of operations was measured in the percentage of time spend within ECAs, as shown in the histogram below. The histogram demonstrates that the share of tramp operations does not show a normal distribution. Rather, two poles become apparent. There are companies which are almost exclusively involved in tramp operations and companies which are almost exclusively involved in liner operations. Companies regularly switching between these two modes or operating vessels in both modes are not very common in the sample. This observation makes sense, as tramp and liner operations involve a very different type of company and especially a different number and skillset of personnel. The two groups will be termed “tramp operators” with 80-100% tramp operations and “liner operators” with 0-20% tramp operations in further analysis. The remaining companies will not be clustered into a third group.

Figure 10-7: Description of sample: Histogram of the share of tramp operations

Area of operations

When talking about the area of operations it is particularly interesting for the researcher whether a high share of ECA operations will influence compliance costs and compliance behaviour. As can be seen in the histogram in Figure 10-8, there is no shipping company in the database that never enters a SECA, as these were deleted from the sample. Furthermore, there is a more or less equal distribution across the parameter values, with peaks at 90% and 100% ECA operations. This would make sense, as shipping companies active almost exclusively within ECAs would have a high interest in an ECA-related study on compliance costs and would be more prone to taking part.

Figure 10-8: Description of sample: Histogram of the share of ECA operations

Flag state

A distribution of participants by flag state most flown by their fleet may be seen in Table 10-11:
Description of sample: Companies organized by flag state

. It becomes apparent that a wide variety of different flags are used with the top three in the sample being Liberia, Antigua and Barbuda, Denmark, and Germany. These values are certainly influenced by the large share of German and Danish shipping companies in the sample. Every single flag named by a shipping company participating in the survey is on the White List of the Paris MoU on Port State Control (valid 07/2017-06/2018) and ships flying this flag have thus in recent years shown good performance in inspections by port state control in Europe. As no medium or high-risk flags are represented in the sample, it is unlikely that flag state will be an interesting indicator in the analysis. It also shows that those companies likely to show lower levels of environmental compliance did not choose to take part in the study.

Flag state	Frequency	Share (%)
Liberia	18	15.4
Antigua and Barbuda	12	10.3
Denmark	11	9.4
Germany	10	8.5
Other	10	8.5
Marshall Islands	9	7.7
Cyprus	6	5.1
Netherlands	5	4.3
Norway	5	4.3
Malta	4	3.4
Bahamas	3	2.6
United Kingdom	3	2.6
Other	12	10
Not valid	9	8
Total	117	100.0

Table 10-11: Description of sample: Companies organized by flag state

Central management location

A descriptive analysis of management location shows the prevalence of German and Danish companies in the sample. A total of seven participants have given their central management location as being an Asian country. That group is however too small to draw effective conclusions on the influence of cultural differences on compliance.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative percent
Germany	57	48.7	48.7
Denmark	15	12.8	61.5
Netherlands	7	6.0	67.6
Norway	7	6.0	73.5
Sweden	5	4.3	77.8
Singapore	4	3.4	81.2
United Kingdom	3	2.6	83.8
China	2	1.7	85.5
Finland	2	1.7	87.2
Canada	1	0.9	88.0
Cyprus	1	0.9	88.9
Poland	1	0.9	89.7
Russian Federation	1	0.9	90.6
Not valid	11	9.4	100.0
Total	117	100.0	

Table 10-12: Description of sample: Central management location

Industry association membership

86.8 % of companies in the sample have stated to be a member of an industry association providing them with information on environmental legislation, while only 13.2 percent do not have any such membership. As can be seen in Figure 10-9, membership does not seem linked to company size, but a limited number of companies of all sizes decide against industry association membership.

Figure 10-9: Description of sample: Industry association membership in relation to company size

An intercorrelation between company characteristics that has been identified during analysis and needs to be considered in evaluation and discussion of results is that company size and average vessel age are moderately interrelated. The respective results of the Pearson correlation may be seen in Table 10-13, showing a statistically significant result with $p < 0.05$, but a very moderate correlation of -0.202.

Correlations

		Company size	Average age
Company size	Pearson Correlation	1	-.202*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.041
	N	111	103
Average age	Pearson Correlation	-.202*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041	
	N	103	103

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 10-13: Pearson correlations for company size and average age of vessels employed

Annex E1: List of academic contributions

Title	Type of contribution	Conference/Journal	Institution
Abiding by the rules? – A sequential mixed methods study on the determinants of regulatory compliance with maritime environmental legislation	Journal paper	Maritime Business Review (Accepted)	/
Compliance with maritime environmental legislation for the shipping industry	3 MT presentation (Qualified for finals)	UWS Annual Learning, Teaching & Research Conference 2018 (26-28 June 2018)	University of the West of Scotland, Paisley UK
Cost effects of maritime environmental legislation - A mixed methods study	Conference paper and presentation	SIGA2 Conference: The Port and Maritime Sector (2-4 May 2018)	University of Antwerp, Faculty of Applied Economics, Antwerp
Environmental legislation and the danger of modal shift	Conference presentation	Maritime logistics conference (November 2017)	Hamburg and Rotterdam Universities of Applied Sciences
Environmental challenges in maritime logistics	Guest lecture	Master of logistics (November 2017)	University of Applied Sciences Hamburg, D
Handelseffekte maritimer Umweltgesetzgebung - Der Einfluss von Gesetzezeseinhaltung	Poster	HAW Galerie des Wissens, 10 Jahre Vielfalt (18 October 2017)	University of Applied Sciences Hamburg, D
Studying Compliance with Maritime Environmental Legislation in the North and Baltic Sea Area: A Model developed from Exploratory Qualitative Data	Conference presentation	7th International Conference on Logistics and Maritime Systems (LOGMS) (23 - 26 August 2017)	NHH Norwegian School of Economics, Bergen, Norway
Studying Determinants of Compliance with Maritime Environmental Legislation in the North and Baltic Sea Area: A Model developed from Exploratory Qualitative Data	Conference paper and presentation	International Conference on Maritime Policy, Technology, and Education (ICMPTE) (7-8 June 2017)	Southampton Solent University, School of Maritime Science and Engineering, Southampton
Trade effects of maritime environmental legislation - The influence of compliance	Poster	UWS Research Conference 2017 (25-27 April 2017)	University of the West of Scotland, Paisley UK
"This is a big bang implementation" - Freight rate effects of maritime environmental legislation on the North and Baltic Sea	Poster	UWS Research Conference 2015 (29-30 April 2015)	University of the West of Scotland, Paisley UK
Trade effects of environmental legislation for merchant shipping on the Baltic Sea	Poster (Audience award)	HAW Forschungs- und Promotionstag (25 September 2014)	University of Applied Sciences Hamburg, D
Emissions ahoi! - Effects of environmental legislation on trade on the European seas	Poster	UWS 10th Annual Research Conference (30 April-1 May 2014)	University of the West of Scotland, Paisley UK

Table 10-14: Academic contributions in relation to the PhD thesis

Additional conferences attended:

European Association of Law and Economics Conference 2017, London (9/2017)
ICS International Shipping Conference 2017, London (9/2017)
Global Maritime Environmental Congress, Hamburg (9/2014)
ISOS Law of the Sea Workshop, Kiel (03/2014)
Hamburg International Environmental Law Conference, Hamburg (9/2013)

Training received:

05/2017-07/2017 Econometrics: Methods and Applications (Erasmus University Rotterdam), successful completion with grade 90.5%
11/2014 MaxQDA: Mixed methods and visuals (HAW Hamburg)
01/2014 Qualitative research process (HAW Hamburg)
01/2014 Ocean Governance: Legal Regulation of Marine Resources (Kiel University)
05/2012 Getting published (UWS)
03/2012 Statistics (HAW Hamburg)
02/2012 Qualitative research methods (HAW Hamburg)
01/2012 Systematic literature research (HAW Hamburg)
12/2011 Epistemology (HAW Hamburg)
11/2011 Academic writing and publishing (HAW Hamburg)

Related Bachelor and Master thesis research projects supervised:

André Dassau: The relevance of LNG as an alternative for the shipping industry to comply with the global SO₂ limits – An analysis based on a small and a big shipping company. (Bachelor Thesis, 2017)

Friederike Becker-Schulte: Effects of the ‘EU Regulation (EC) No 1257/2013 on the recycling of ships’ on the steel industry of Bangladesh (Bachelor Thesis, 2015)

Jörg Hirth: Die MARPOL-Konvention und deren Grenzwerte zum Schwefeldioxid-Ausstoß - eine Untersuchung zum Stand der aktuellen Einhaltung durch Handelsschiffe auf der Nord- und Ostsee (Master Thesis, 2015)